

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D1.1 AWP Y1 including rolling SRIA WP1

EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP

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Technical References

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Task	T1.1 - Overall executive management and support of the Partnership
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Contributing Participants	all Participants
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¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

Version	Date	Reviewer name/institution	Short description of changes
1	03/06/2022	PARC CT / ANSES	
2	07/10/2022	PARC CT / ANSES	Cf Table of history of changes

TABLE OF HISTORY OF CHANGES

Version (date)	Changes
07/10/2022	<p>AWP Y1</p> <p><u>Editorial changes</u> Formatting has been reviewed and page numbers has been revised and are now continuous throughout the document. Underlining and bolds have been removed from the document when relevant.</p> <p><u>Administrative changes</u> The participating organisations, their short names, affiliation, and numbering have been harmonised with those of the Grant Agreement (GA) data according to the modifications carried out during the GA preparation phase.</p> <p><u>Changes in the Work package descriptions and additional deliverables</u> The WP descriptions have been slightly modified in coherence with the modifications carried out in the 7-year description of actions (DoA) during the GA preparation phase.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The additional deliverables and their due dates have been reviewed to be in coherence with the 7-year DoA and reflect the ESR comments on the 1st year ambitions. - The additional deliverables (ADs) have been shortly described in table 2.3c. - The detailed description of work in the WPs has been updated when relevant with clarifications or editorial changes. - The PARC SRIA in Annex has been updated with the description of each project that will start Y1 of PARC. In each WP description, the number of projects starting Y1 has been added based on the SRIA. The nomenclature for the projects has been revised and harmonised between WPs. <p><u>Changes in the general description of the participants and their contributions</u> The table 2.2. has been split in two tables. The table 2.2.a describes the contribution of each participant in the AWPY1. The table 2.2.b provides a general description of each PARC participant. The number of each participant has been added in the tables 2.2.a and 2.2.b as defined in the GA. A complete description of the contribution of each participant in Year 1 has been added.</p> <p><u>Effort and financial changes</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The PMs and staff efforts for the 1st year have been reviewed to take into account and stay coherent with the modifications carried out during the GA preparation phase. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Due to an employee leaving EAA, the budget initially allocated for the activities for tasks 7.1 and 7.2 of WP7 has been transferred to the subcontracting budget planned for VITO as Work Package Co-Leader (85 000€ in Year 1). ○ By mistake, the Affiliated Entity ENSP did not receive PMs in the proposal under WP4, task 4.1 for the first year of PARC.

	<p>Consequently, 2 PMs were allocated for ENSP in T4.1 for year 1, 1PM from the “reserve” from UBA and SpF respectively.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">○ For the Affiliated Entity DGS, 1 PM was transferred from the task 6.3 to the task 2.1 for the participation of DGS in the task 2.1 in Year 1.○ The initial budget planned for LCS in Task 1.1 and in Tasks 9.1 and 9.4 have been transferred to RSU, together with planned activities.○ The Affiliated Entity UOULU was initially Affiliated Entity of the Beneficiary THL from Finland and became the Affiliated Entity of the other Finnish Beneficiary TTL for legal purposes. The change of affiliation led to the transfer of the initial budget planned for THL in WP1 for the management of its Affiliated Entity UOULU to TTL.○ For the Affiliated Entity UOULU, 0.3 PM was allocated to Task 4.1.3 in Year 1.○ For the Affiliated Entity SDU, the budget for other goods, works, and services has been reduced of 6,000 € (audit costs). This amount has been reallocated to personnel costs and 1 PM has been added to WP5 in the 7-years budget. A share (1/7) of this amount has been added to task 5.1 in the Year 1 budget.○ The budget planned for FPS in Task 3.2 has been transferred to the task 3.2 co-leader NPHC, together with planned activities, due to their withdrawal, including in Year 1 budget.○ For the Associated Partner Unisanté, 0.3 PM was allocated to Task 4.1.3 in Year 1.○ For the Affiliated Entity CEA, 0.43 PM were transferred as 0.5 PM to CNRS in Task 4.3.○ For the Associated Partner UCL, 3 PM were transferred from Associated Partner BUL for Task 6.3 <p>- Table 2.3.e has been modified accordingly with the justification of the “Purchase costs” when exceeding 15% of the other direct costs, for all Beneficiaries and Affiliated Entities. The table has been updated with additional justification of the “Purchase costs” for the following participants: THL, FFA, UOULU, ICPS and RIVM</p>
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Abstract

The Annual Work Plan (AWP) describes the activities to be implemented during the ‘PARC year’, including the updated rolling SRIA (Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda) in Annex with projects that are in the planning/executive phase. The AWP covers the period from May N to April N+1 which are referred to as ‘PARC years’.

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List of abbreviations

<p>3R: Reduction, Refinement and Replacement ADME: Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion AE: Affiliated Entity AO/ AON/ AOP: Adverse Outcome/ AO Network/ Pathway API: Application Programming Interfaces ASR/ AWPs: Annual Summary Report/Work Plans CA: Consortium Agreement CL/ ML: Chemical Leader/ Methodology Leader CLP: Classification, Labelling and Packaging CMS: Content Management System COPCSD: Common Open Platform on Chemical Safety Data CSS: Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability CT: ANSES PARC Coordination Team DEPB: Data and Ethics Protection Board DMP: Data Management Plan DoA: Description of Action EC: European Commission ECHA: European Chemicals Agency ED/ EDCs: Endocrine Disrupters / endocrine disrupting compounds EDA: Effect-Directed Analysis EFSA: European Food Safety Authority ERA: Environmental Risk Assessment EWS: Early Warning System FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable FIP: FAIR Implementation Profiles GA: Grant Agreement GB: Governing Board GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation GIVIMP: Good In Vitro Methods Practices GS: Grant Signatory GSB: Grant Signatory Board HA: Hazard Assessment HBM: Human BioMonitoring HBM GV: Health-based Guidance Values IATA: Integrative Approaches for testing and Assessment IB: International Board IPR: Intellectual Property Rights IVIVE: <i>in vitro</i> - <i>in vivo</i> extrapolation JRC: Joint Research Centre KEs: Key Events MB: Management Board</p>	<p>MIEs: Molecular Initiating Events MS: Member States NAMs: New Approach Methodologies NGRA: Next Generation Risk Assessment NHs: National Hubs NHCPs: National Hub Contact Points NTS: Non-Targeted Screening OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development OO: Operational Objectives PFAS: per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances PFDP: PARC FAIR Data Policy PBK: Physiologically Based Kinetic PBTK: Physiologically Based Toxicokinetic POD: Point of Departure QA/QC: Quality Assurance / Quality Control QAWG: Quality Assurance Working Group QIVIVE: Quantitative <i>in vitro</i> / <i>in vivo</i> Extrapolation QSAR: Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship RA/RM: Risk Assessment / Risk Management R&I: Research and Innovation RRM: Rapid Response Mechanism SDGs: Sustainable Development Goals S2PD: Science-to-Policy Dialogue SAICM: Strategic Approach to International Chemicals Management SF: Stakeholder Forum SO: Specific Objectives SRIA: Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda SS: suspect screening SSbD: Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design T/TL: Task/Task co-leaders TTC: Toxicological Threshold of Concern UCWG: Use Case Working Group(s) UNEP: United Nations Environment Programme US-EPA: US Environmental Protection Agency US-NTP: US National Toxicology Program WHO: World Health Organization WP/ WPL: Work Package / WP co-leaders</p>
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Structure of the Annual Work Programme

1. Coherence with part B of the proposal

1.1 Annual Work Plan (AWP) objectives

The first year of the Partnership is crucial to set solid and durable foundations. Indeed, the beginning of any partnership is fraught with challenges (ex: organisational, managerial, communicational, etc.) as partners implement in practice and improve (when needed) the designed framework. The internal processes and habits taken up early on often remain for the whole duration. It is thus critical for the success of the Partnership that these are suitable for the activities and objectives of PARC and that they can be smoothly adopted and refined in its initial phase.

Beyond the internal processes, it is also important in the first year to properly initiate the scientific work and outreach to maximise the impacts of the Partnership. The first Annual Work Plan (AWP#1) has been designed to reflect and address these needs. As such, the 1st AWP objectives will focus on initiating and enabling the wider objectives of PARC.

The specific objectives of this first year are:

- At the PARC management level (WP1)
 - To put in place the general management tools and processes of PARC with a PARC handbook, the ethical rules and the principles of IPR management
 - To develop the modalities for monitoring performance indicators
- At the communicational level (WP3)
 - To develop PARC's communication plan, put in place the tools (website, media, leaflets) and initiate consultations planned by different WPs
- In terms of network development (WP2, WP3)
 - To develop internal and external networks of partners and initiate their animation
 - To nominate Chemical Leaders (CLs) and Methodology Leaders (MLs) to develop internal networks between WPs
 - To initiate the National Hub (NH) activities in and between countries
- In terms of scientific activities within the framework of the PARC rolling Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) (WP2, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7, WP8, WP9)
 - To continue to develop the principles of prioritisation of activities, evaluation of the relevance of projects proposed for initiation
 - To prepare the second AWP with the MB and GSB following input and guidance on the strategy to be implemented from the Governing Board (GB).
 - To implement knowledge management methods
 - To define the framework for reflection on the sustainability of PARC and identify priority activities (WP2)
 - To plan and implement projects in the various fields of HBM activities based on HBM4EU legacy (WP4)
 - by initiating studies for the general population and studies in children and adolescents, selecting priority chemical substances, analysing the experience gained in occupational health and initiating studies in waste management professionals and in the care sector
 - by working on various methodological approaches and associated quality assurance
 - by working on HBM-based indicators and reference values
 - To initiate projects in environmental monitoring and source tracking, by developing the methodological framework (WP4) for identifying knowledge gaps and priority research for substances and matrices as part of the cross-cutting reflection on the development of Early Warning Systems (EWS).

- by analysing the coverage and functioning of existing networks
- by focusing initial work on the presence of PFAS and endocrine disruptors already prioritised in several compartments
- To initiate and plan projects about innovative sampling and analytical methods for screening/NTS, EDA appropriate for human, environmental and multi-source studies (WP4)
- To plan and implement the first (eco)toxicology studies using complementary approaches based on guidelines and NAMs for mycotoxins and BPA alternatives (WP5)
- To initiate projects on hazard assessment/ human toxicology to fill the knowledge gaps on natural toxins and bisphenol alternatives (WP5).
- To review the state of art for future development of innovative methods for the assessment of 5 endpoints and by defining reference substances (WP5)
- To start the development of AOPs for 5 endpoints based on an inventory of available data and in parallel developing the ADME study scheme for the construction of PBTK models (WP5, WP6)
- To develop the quantitative AOP networks for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity based on available data from previous projects and initiating case studies for IATA and initiating mappings for the 5 priority endpoints identified for further projects between WP6 and WP5
- To develop the strategy for the analysis of aggregated multi-source exposures in the general population (lifetime) and in the context of occupational exposure (WP6)
- To initiate and plan the model development on exposure to mixtures observed in real life (WP6)
- To initiate work on health impact indicators for a first group of chemicals (WP6)
- To initiate the first practice reviews, cross-regulatory approaches (WP6)
- To analyse the state of the art in risk assessment (RA) for mixtures, and how to take into account new approaches and methodologies (WP6)
- To initiate and plan projects to develop tools and databases that enable a systematic identification and prioritisation of hazardous substances in products and materials. (WP6)
- To identify regulatory needs and the state of the art in biodiversity impact assessment (WP6)
- To initiate and plan projects to evaluate which factors are most crucial for environmental risk assessment, including environmental modelling, and to develop methods for comparing and ranking risk assessments between substances. (WP6)
- To develop the general data management plan (DMP) and the modalities per field of activity for obtaining FAIR data for the scientific communities and risk assessors, identifying databases and working on the development of innovative methods for data collection and uncertainty assessment (WP7)
- To initiate work to identify the needs and tools available and to be developed for Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD), EWS and integrative models (WP8)
- In the development of resources and networks (WP9)
 - To describe the network of partners, characterising existing infrastructures, catalogues of existing methods and quality assurance schemes, to identify the needs by domain of activities
 - To identify the main training needs and priorities in the different domains of activities
 - To build on and include resources developed and made available by other related H2020 and Horizon Europe projects

1.2 Expected impacts

The establishment of this first AWP will significantly contribute to the achievement of PARC's policy/societal impact (first impact) by putting into action a first network of around 200 European, cross-sectorial public participants collaborating on the development of RA for chemicals at the national and/or European level. Through the communication on the Partnership, the implementation of a stakeholder forum (SF), and the establishment of PARC's work programme, we will develop a common inter-agency

European and national space on chemical RA. Through SYNnet we will develop our relationship with H2020 and Horizon Europe projects working on alternative methods, human biomonitoring and risk assessment from chemicals and other EU partnerships. By the implementation of an international board (IB) and the development of synergies with international organisations, PARC will create a significant node of the international network. AWP#1 will actively contribute to the realisation of OO1, OO2, OO3, OO5 and contribute to the OO4, OO6 in support of the policy/societal impact of PARC.

The communication on the work programme will present the challenges for innovation in RA. The setting up of NHs will also be an opportunity to develop networks of partners at national levels.

At the scientific level (second impact), the PARC rolling SRIA will initiate work favouring collaborations between different networks of participants working in public health (general population, target populations and workers), environment protection, monitoring of different sources for different classes of substances and people working in RA, hazard assessment (HA) and exposure quantification. The first projects are geared towards achieving our scientific objectives and in particular the construction of a common approach and the sharing of data through the development and application of PARC's FAIR data policy, knowledge and methods. The AWP#1 will contribute to the achievement OO7, OO8 as well as initiate work aligned with OO10, OO12.

From an economic point of view (third impact), the first year will contribute to identifying existing networks, seeking complementarity and identifying training and quality assurance needs in order to support the development of innovative approaches and encourage their inclusion in the RA scheme. The aim is to develop a scientific approach to support innovation in chemistry while reducing risks for health and the environment. Achieving these objectives will require long-term work, but the first year will enable the expectations of the various stakeholders to be better characterised, the approaches and tools available to be discussed and the regulatory requirements for concepts such as Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) and Early Warning Systems (EWS) to be better defined, while continuing to develop integrative approaches. The AWP#1 will contribute to the realisation of OO9, OO11 and OO13.

1.3 Correspondence with part B of the proposal

For this first AWP, the actions initiated in the form of projects, case studies and those activities corresponding to recurrent tasks are presented by WP and tasks using the structure described in Part B. AWP#1 has been designed to be intrinsically linked and complementary to the seven-year activity plan (Description of Action or DoA). It will provide the necessary basis on which to continue building the Partnership in the following years. This is true for the specific challenges, the scope of PARC as well as for the activities that will be initiated during the first year of PARC.

1.4 Construction of the PARC rolling SRIA

PARC activities, except for transversal ones that are already detailed in the GA, will be reflected in the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) which constitutes a rolling overview of the daily activities and/or PARC Projects to be implemented under PARC, providing detailed information on timelines, outputs, etc. The PARC rolling SRIA will be administered by the Coordinator and updated each year to integrate new PARC Projects and follow those that have been implemented. It will serve as a basis for the preparation of the AWP. The SRIA annexed to this 1st AWP is a compilation of all projects proposed by the WPLs/TLs concerned and have been discussed during the GA preparation phase with task 2.1 partners and have been agreed to start during the 1st year of PARC. Other projects that were also submitted and that are still under discussion have not been included in this SRIA yet but may be taken up in the next rolling plan.

1. Annual Work Programme Activities

2.1 Annual Work Programme

2.1.1 Structure of the Annual Work Programme

The structure of the AWP is based on the WP.

2.1.2 Timing of the different programmed activities and their components

The first AWP will cover a duration of 12 months (1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023). All WPs will be active in Y1.

2.1.3 Detailed work description

Table 2.3.a: Annual Work Programme Activities for each set of activities

WP N°	WP1	Lead Beneficiary	ANSES
WP title	Coordination and Management		
Partner N°	1	1.13	1
Partner short name	ANSES	EHESP	1.13
PM/par tner ¹	109	6	1
Start	M1	End	M12

Objectives

The main goal of WP1 for year 1 is to set up the overall structure to ensure the coordination, the strategic scientific and administrative management of PARC, including impact evaluation and the ethical issues management, in cooperation with the different governance bodies of the Partnership. The specific objectives of WP1 for year 1 are:

- Task 1.1: Setting up an effective management and governance framework for the PARC consortium in compliance with the legal, ethical, financial and administrative rules and regulations and ensuring the highest quality standards;
- Task 1.2: Setting up the tools to ensure the Partnership’s progress and guiding the PARC consortium and its activities in maintaining the course set out in the DoA, to achieve milestones and produce the agreed deliverables, within the defined budget and abiding by the highest quality standards;
- Task 1.3: Setting up the monitoring framework for the Partnership;
- Task 1.4: Setting up the Data and Ethics Protection Board (DEPB) and discussing ethics and data protection with the other WP co-leaders in order to set the ethics framework for the Partnership.

¹ PMs have been allocated to the Grant Signatories for the management of their affiliated entities and their role of NHCP. In some cases, the Grant Signatories do not have any PM as they do not manage any AEs and are not NHCP in PARC.

Description of work

WP1 – Coordination and Management – will closely interact with all WPs in order to support them in the management and implementation of the work, but also in order to create synergies and to follow-up and monitor the work progress. All tasks of WP1 are closely interlinked and complementary and will involve the following contributors (depending on the task):

- the Grant Signatory Board members (GSB): *EEA (AT), VITO (BE), SCIENSANO (BE), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), CIPH (HR), MU (CZ), UZIS (CZ), DEPA (DK), HB (EE), EEA (EU), ECHA (EU), EFSA (EU), THL (FI), TTL (FI), ANSES (FR), SpF (FR), UBA (DE), BfR (DE), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), GCSL (EL), NPHC (HU), MOH-IL (IL), ISS (IT), UI (IS), RSU (LV), NPHSL (LT), LSMU (LT), LNS (LU), RIVM (NL), NIPH (NO), NIOM (PL), INSA (PT), FMUL (PT), NIJZ (SL), JSI (SI), ISCIII (ES), CSIC (ES), SEPA (SE), FOPH (CH), SZU-SK (SK), UKHSA (UK)*;
- the WP co-leaders (WPL): *ANSES (FR), EAA (AT), EEA (EU), GCSL (EL), INSA (PT), Spf (FR), UBA (DE), BfR (FR), RIVM (NL), KEMI (SE), VITO (BE), UOB (UK), AUTH (EL), UNINA (IT), MU (CZ), ISCIII (ES)*;
- the National Hub Contact Points (NHCPs): *EEA (AT), DOMG (BE), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), CIPH (HR), MU (CZ), HB (EE), TTL (FI), SpF (FR), UBA (DE), BfR (DE), AUTH (EL), NPHC (HU), MOH-IL (IL), ISS (IT), UI (IS), RSU (LV), NPHSL (LT), LNS (LU), RIVM (NL), NIPH (NO), NIOM (PL), APA (PT), NIJZ (SL), ISCIII (ES), SLV (SE), FOPH (CH), SZU-SK (SK), UKHSA (UK)*;
- the National Hub co-Coordiators (NHCs): *UKHSA (UK) and SZU-SK (SK)*.

Task 1.1: Overall executive management and support of the Partnership

Leader: ANSES (FR)

Partners: All GSB members and WP co-leaders (as stated above)

The main activities of this task will be set up by ANSES with the Coordinator assisted by the Deputy Coordinator and supported by PARC Project managers employed by ANSES. The Coordinator, Deputy Coordinator and PARC Project managers constitute the ANSES Coordination Team (CT). The CT and all participants will play an active role to ensure efficient setting up of the management and reporting of the PARC activities and associated administrative and budgetary issues:

Management of the consortium (ANSES):

- Setting up the Governance of the Partnership and implementing their procedures, including:
 - the Governing Board (GB): ensuring the correct knowledge and implementation of its “Terms of reference and rules of procedure” and providing support for its 1st year activities and meeting
 - the Grant Signatory Board (GSB): ensuring the correct knowledge and implementation of the Consortium Agreement (CA)
- Organising and chairing, of the Partnership consortium and governance (GB and GSB) meetings to take place during the 1st year: launch event, kick-off meeting and at least one GB meeting
- Setting up the tools and structure for the day-to-day management and close follow-up of the Partnership, including administrative, logistic issues and budget (templates, FAQs...)
- Establishing the Partnership handbook describing the main processes, roles and responsibilities, and approach and documents to be used, including information on Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), declarations of interest ...
- Assisting participants on specific administrative and financial issues
- Monitoring and ensuring close follow-up of the Partnership’s implementation of the 1st AWP, ensuring respect of the different deadlines, achievement of milestones and deliverables when relevant, and close follow-up of the PARC budget for the 1st year

- Preparing the templates and guiding documents and coordinating the preparation, collection and compilation of the 1st year deliverables, contractual periodic reports and financial statements and submitting them to the EC
- Distribution of EU pre-financing according to the internal rules set up in the CA
- Preparing, if relevant during the period, contractual documents generated by PARC activities: IPR, Material Transfer Agreement and Data Transfer Agreement; preparing, signing, and managing, when relevant, other PARC related agreements (e.g. confidentiality and collaboration agreements) that will arise during the 1st year, e.g. with the JRC

Communication:

- Defining with WP3 the internal communication process so that all participants have a timely access to up-to-date information (including setting up a regularly updated Partnership contact list and a secure collaborative platform)
- Defining with WP3 the PARC rules for external communication and publication
- Ensuring close interaction and co-construction with WP2 and WP3 with regards to external communication products
- Addressing any questions related to PARC

Task 1.2: Scientific steering and implementation of Annual Work Plans

Leader: ANSES (FR)

Partners: All WP co-leaders, NHCPs, NHCs, DOMG (BE), INSA (PT), NIJZ (SI), EHESP (FR)

The main activities of this task will be set up by the Coordinator and Deputy Coordinator, with the assistance of the CT and the WP co-leaders. Other functions relevant for the implementation such as NHCs, Chemical Leaders (CLs), Methodology Leaders (MLs) etc. will also participate in this task. The MB will specifically play an active role to ensure the efficient setting up of the monitoring of the scientific progress and of the overall strategy of the Partnership, making sure that the PARC activities, resources and AWP are aligned. It will also ensure the relevance of the PARC work plan with regard to external events with WP3 (projects, initiatives, EU policies linked to the PARC objectives).

Administration of the MB and PARC activities:

- Moderating the MB and ensuring the cross-cutting scientific links between WPs through the organisation of monthly meetings during the 1st year (2 will be physical meetings, if possible)
- Providing direction to the participants for the update and management of the PARC rolling (SRIA, in order to achieve the Partnership's intended outcomes and collecting outputs from WPs according to the 1st AWP. Translating the PARC rolling SRIA into the 2nd AWP in collaboration with WP2 (Task 2.1 priority setting), and in consultation with the relevant PARC governance bodies. Proposing updates of the PARC rolling SRIA and implementing response strategies through the AWPs (e.g. by proposing to change the scope of a WP/Task, to include new participant(s) or Affiliated Entities, etc.)
- Implementing efficient collaboration with all participants of the Consortium for the planning and implementation of PARC and assisting the PARC NHCs in defining the National Hub (NH) contributions and activities in PARC
- Coordination, in relation to other relevant WPs, including WP2 and WP3, for the correct involvement and consultation on scientific matters and approvals of the Partnership boards, required for preparation of the 2nd year AWP
- Establishing the quality management system and framework for monitoring of PARC's activities (monitoring of scientific progress, evaluation of PARC's performance and impacts with task 1.3, and monitoring of the implementation of the PARC rolling SRIA)

- Update the framework for the analysis of risks that may impact the Partnership and opportunities for synergies (with WP3) (projects, initiatives, EU policies linked to the PARC objectives, National, EU and international initiatives ...)
- If required, and if relevant for Y2, proposing amendments or solutions / redress actions to resolve any issues, and escalating unresolvable risks or issues to the relevant boards (GSB and GB, when needed)
- Preparing and submitting 2nd AWP and the 1st year Annual Summary Report (ASR)
- Reviewing and ensuring the scientific quality control of the 1st year achievements, outputs and deliverables before submission to the EC

Task 1.3: Impact evaluation and Monitoring of the performance indicators of the Partnership

Co-Leaders: DOMG (BE), INSA (PT)

Partners: All WP co-leaders

An initial monitoring frame and set of indicators has been developed with the interim MB during the Partnership's conception phase when the activities and end-users for PARC's results were being identified by the WP co-leaders. This work should be further refined to ensure the key useful and impact-generating results and relevant target groups are clearly identified in order to maximise PARC's impact and exploitation.

Activities to be performed in the 1st year include to:

- Further develop the set of indicators originally developed in the Partnership's conception phase, containing output, outcome and impact (quantitative and qualitative) indicators linked to operational, specific and general objective(s) to ensure their relevance for evaluating the outcome and political, scientific and social impact of the Partnership (e.g. link with Sustainable Development Goals). This includes suggestions for baselines and clear targets for output indicators
- Process the feedback of the EC's expert group on Partnership monitoring frames to further fine-tune the list of indicators
- Process the feedback of the EU's chemicals strategy for sustainability towards a toxic-free environment indicator framework
- Consult different PARC boards on the first set of indicators
- Prepare the first revised monitoring frame and document on first set of indicators further to the consultations
- Interact with WP2 – task 2.2 on sustainability – for the development of surveys for sustainability indicators
- Interact with WP3 on the preparation of easily interpretable indicator leaflets

Task 1.4: Ethics framework

Co-Leaders: NIJZ (SI), EHESP (FR)

Partners: All WP co-leaders

This task is responsible for maintaining an ethical perspective throughout all the Partnership's activities and will set up collaborative and constructive processes to ensure ethical considerations are properly taken into account.

During the 1st year, Task 1.4 will examine the expertise in ethics and data protection available within the consortium, and will set up a Data and Ethics Protection Board (DEPB). In addition, during the first year, this task will set up collaborative and constructive processes to ensure the monitoring of the Partnership's actions with regards to ethical considerations. Discussions on the three aspects covered: ethical dimension of the research, integrity of the research, data protection and processing/use (in collaboration with WP7) will be implemented.

It will build on the experience from HBM4EU and suggest adaptations as necessary to fulfil PARC's ethical needs. The first year will also be used to investigate the creation of the network of accredited Data

Protection Officers (DPO) from the participating organisations.
 A first DEPB meeting will be organised during year 1.

Deliverables:

- D1.1 M1 AWP Y1 including rolling SRIA
- D1.2 M1 PARC governance process timeline
- D1.3 M8 AWP Y2 including rolling SRIA
- D1.4 M8 ASR Y1
- D1.5 M12 Ethics & Data Protection Policy
- D1.6 M12 Optimised list of indicators

Additional Deliverables:

N/A

WP N°	WP2	Lead Beneficiary	EAA/EEA
WP title	A common science-policy agenda		
Partner N°	1	1.1	2
Partner short name	ANSES	INSERM	SpF
PM/partner	44.40	4.50	2
Start	M1		M12

Objectives

The main goal of WP2 is to establish a dialogue and priority-setting process bringing together regulatory entities and Risk Assessment (RA) agencies in Europe (European and national entities and agencies) to develop a strategic R&I agenda for chemicals RA in collaboration with the scientific community. The specific objectives of WP2 for year 1 are:

- Task 2.1: Developing and implementing a well-structured and transparent prioritisation strategy through a fluid dialogue between WP2 and other Work Packages (WPs) and making a proposal for a systematic, criteria-based prioritisation for projects and substances.
- Task 2.2: Making conceptual developments and implementation of network and communication structure of the *ad hoc* network of international and external partners for NGRARoute, scoping study to conceptually develop the information/knowledge management framework for PARCopedia as well as its implementation, and nomination of the Chemical Leaders (CLs) and Methodology Leaders (MLs).
- Task 2.3: Developing a process for continuous dialogue with the National Hub Contact Points (NHCPs) on needs and a concept for capacity building, start developing an exit strategy and further developing

and refining the monitoring framework with T1.3.

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 2.1: Prioritisation

Co-leaders: ANSES (FR), ECHA (EU), EFSA (EU)

Key Partners: EAA (AT), EEA (EU), UBA (DE), BfR (DE), ISS (IT), GCSL (EL), DGS (PT)

Task 2.1 Co-leaders and partners (EAA, EEA, UBA, BfR, ISS, GCSL, DGS) will further develop and refine the proposal for an overall PARC prioritisation process and prioritisation criteria, drawing on the legacy of HBM4EU and further achievements within the preparation phase of PARC, including a process for project review and approval. Prioritisation criteria will capture the importance of the policy/regulatory needs for new knowledge and will be tailored to the thematic work packages. A pool of internal reviewers among all task partners will be established and project review process will be initiated. This prioritisation process will be approved by the MB and convey ultimately to the GB. WP2.1 will thereby ensure that projects under PARC provide added value to the respective regulatory and policy needs, be they national or EU level.

To allow for National and European policy-makers to submit requests for specific information to the PARC Consortium thus ensuring that the PARC responds to new and urgent needs for information in the EU policy community and at national level, outside of the formal timeframes for substance nomination, task 2.1 will set up the principles and process for a Rapid Response Mechanism (RRM), based on HBM4EU's experience.

Task 2.2: Knowledge Management

Co-leaders: BfR (DE), INSA (PT)

Key Partners: AUTH (EL), UOB (UK)

A scoping study for the knowledge platform *PARCopedia* (BfR, AUTH) (with particular focus on defining the functional scope of the Content Management System (CMS) and establishing the knowledge structure as well as the processes and rules for knowledge generation and sharing/dissemination), will be carried out during the first year with respect to:

- developing a knowledge model for the platform, taking into account the expected data/information output from the knowledge-generating WPs, the communication needs of WPs 1-3, and the knowledge needs of all involved parties,
- determining the best way for technically implementing the platform and for linking it to the PARC data landscape, other relevant sources outside of PARC and to the Partnership's website, and
- developing a concept for maintenance of the knowledge platform, both technically and with respect to its content, including a clear definition of roles and responsibilities.

Based on the results, a pilot version of the platform will be set up.

CL and ML will have an important role in channeling the work related to priority substances and methodologies. In year 1 of PARC, the appointment procedure and Terms of Reference (ToR) for CL/ML will be set up and a first group of CLs/MLs will be appointed (INSA).

Under the strategic roadmap framework "PARCroute" (BfR), work on the first strategic roadmap, i.e. "NGRARoute" (BfR) (i.e. a roadmap for actively promoting the paradigm shift towards implementing Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) in major chemical regulation programmes) will begin by setting up the ad hoc network and communication structure and a targeted work plan in collaboration with the related activities in WPs 4-6.

Task 2.3: Sustainability

Co-leaders: INSERM (FR), NPHC (HU)

Key partner: DOMG (BE)

The first steps will be to identify the list of PARC activities that need to be sustainable (e.g. human biomonitoring, toxicology, risk assessment, safe and sustainable by design, prioritisation process, capacity for data storage, access, analysis and use) by Inserm, UBA, BfR, ANSES, SpF and EEA. The current state of these activities and the available networks and infrastructures will be listed. Together with WP9, a peer-to-peer learning process is promoted to foster the sustainable development of the NHs from the beginning of the Partnership. This will be coordinated by the NHCs based on the inputs of the NHCs. To identify the existing knowledge gaps and requests, as well as suggestions and expertise, a survey on needs of the NHs will be launched. The outcomes of the survey will be transposed into the first training and capacity building program in WP9. The mapping of needs of NHs will be a living process and will continue the entire duration of the Partnership.

As part of the development of the exit strategy, an overarching and holistic long-term approach to establishing R&I in chemical risk assessment in the European Union is being worked on from the beginning of the Partnership.

Together with WP1, WP3 and WP6, task 2.3 will follow that sustainability-relevant indicators used in the impact evaluation under task 1.3 are in coherence with indicators developed by the Commission under the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability and zero pollution objectives.

Deliverables:

- D2.1 M9 Prioritisation criteria report
- D2.2 M12 PARCopedia Scoping study
- D2.3 M12 PARCroute roadmap1

Additional Deliverables:

N/A

WP N°	WP3								Lead Beneficiary								INSA/GCSL									
WP title	Synergies, collaborations and awareness																									
Partner N°	1	2	3	3.1	3.8	4	4.2		6	7	8	10	11	12	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	20.4	20.6	21	22	24
Partner short name	ANSES	SpF	EAA	AGES	UMIT	VITO	DOMG		CIPH	MOH-CY/SGL MU	DEPA	HB	BEA	TTL	UBA	BfR	NPHC	UI	MOH	ISS	IUSS	UNINA	RSU	NPHSL	LNS	
PM/partner	1	0.50	5.50	3	2	1	2		1	1	2.50	1	1	13	1	3	1.50	15.10	1	1	1	1.60	1	1	1.75	
Partner N°	25	26	26.2	27	28	29	29.1	29.3	29.5	30	31	31.2	31.2	32	34	35.7	35.9	36	36.1	36.3	36.4	36.2	37	38	50	59
Partner short name	RIVM	NIPH	STAMI	NIOM	FMUL	INSA	APA	ENSP	UAVR	SZU-SK	JSI	NIB	NIC	NIJZ	ISCIH	KEMI	SLV	AUTH	EFET	NKUA	UOC	GCSL	BPI	FOPH	UKHSA	UOB
PM/partner	2	1	3	1	4.50	34.50	3.50	1.50	2.50	1	1.50	3.50	1.50	5.50	1	1	1	10	5.50	13	3.50	19	2.50	2	1	1
Start	M1								End								M12									

Objectives

The main goal of WP3 is to boost the impact of PARC outcomes through the diffusion of the knowledge produced within the Partnership while fostering synergies and collaborations with other projects/programmes at national, EU and international levels. The specific objectives of WP3 for year 1 are:

- Task 3.1: Setting up and running the International Board (IB) and Stakeholder Forum (SF), ensuring the representativeness of stakeholders from different sectors in the SF and that a high level IB is formed and, if relevant, assigning the PARC Ambassador;
- Task 3.2: Developing and implementing the communication strategy for PARC;
- Task 3.3: Exploring and establishing collaborations and synergies with other relevant scientific/regulatory/policy initiatives at national, EU and international level.

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 3.1: Building effective interactions

Co-Leaders: EAA (AT): Stakeholder Forum; AUTH (EL): International Board, PARC ambassador

Partners: ANSES (FR), AGES (AT), EEA (EU), UBA (DE), IUSS (IT), LNS (LU), STAMI (NO), FMUL (PT), INSA (PT), APA (PT), NIB (SI), NKUA (EL), UOC (EL), GCSL (EL)

Activity 3.1.1. Establishment and running of Stakeholder Forum (SF)

In the first year of PARC selection criteria for the membership of the SF will be refined and a list of corresponding candidates and mandates will be defined. Following that criteria, mandate and candidates will be approved by the Management Board (MB) and Governing Board (GB). At its first meeting, the establishment of the SF will take place. A description of the members of the SF will be provided, including the rules of procedures and the outcome of the first meeting.

Furthermore, in light of the actions and commitments in the EU's chemicals strategy for sustainability towards a toxic-free environment and the evolution of SSbD-related actions, the first year of PARC will see discussions on how to build interactions with industry, in particular on the subjects of NAMs and of SSbD, in close collaboration with the relevant WPs. The implementation of a committee or platform, ensuring discussion and open dialogue with key players from industry and PARC but also from other key stakeholders will be discussed and investigated, as will the interactions between industry and PARC in specific case studies or through participation in specific committees.

Activity 3.1.2. Establishment and running of the International Board (IB) and, if relevant, establishment of and liaison with a PARC Ambassador

In the first year of PARC selection criteria for the membership of the IB will be refined and a list of corresponding candidates and mandates will be defined. At its first meeting, the establishment of the IB will take place. A description of the members of the IB will be provided, including the rules of procedures and the outcome of the first meeting. Further discussions on a possible PARC ambassador will be implemented and, if relevant, a list of possible candidates will be established. If an ambassador is to be established, a communication consensus for the ambassador will be created, including general agreement on role, responsibility, internal and external communication. Following that, criteria, mandate and candidates will be approved by the MB and GB.

Concerted and dynamic strategies to manage the expectations from both sides and maximise the inputs from the above fora will be discussed.

Task 3.2: Communication, dissemination, and awareness

Co-Leaders: EEA (EU), NPHC (HU)

Partners: ANSES (FR), SpF (FR), EAA (AT), AGES (AT), UMIT (AT), VITO (BE), DOMG (BE), CIPH (CR), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), MU (CZ), HB (EE), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), BfR (DE), UI (IS), MOH-IL (IL), ISS

(IT), UNINA (IT), RSU (LV), NPHSL (LT), LNS (LU), RIVM (NL), NIPH (NO), STAMI (NO), NIOM (PL), FMUL (PT), INSA (PT), APA (PT), ENSP (PT), UAVR (PT), SZU (SK), JSI (SI), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), NIJZ (SI), ISCHII (ES), KEMI (SE), SLV (SE), FOPH (CH), UKHSA (UK), UOB (UK), AUTH (EL), EFET (EL), NKUA (EL), UOC (EL), BPI (EL), GCSL (EL)

EEA, NPHC and NIB will develop the graphical identity for PARC at the beginning of the Partnership, which is important for communicating cohesion externally and for providing a sense of unity internally. It will include the adoption and registration of a logo, hashtags, lay-out of documents, templates for communication and dissemination products and a PARC flyer.

The PARC website and social media channels (e.g. LinkedIn, Twitter and Facebook accounts) will be created and continuously updated by the selected partners (EEA, STAMI, EFET, BPI, NKUA,). The first documents produced in the PARC will be uploaded on the website and made available in the PARCopedia (knowledge management platform, T2.2). Communication with the scientific community and with all stakeholders, including the general public, regulators and policy makers will be done through the different communication channels.

The first Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP) listing all the communication products and planned dissemination activities focused to each target group will be elaborated for the first year with input from the WP co-leaders and the CT (all partners). This plan will be updated at the end of the first year. A roadmap for the production of communication materials and tools will be developed. Based on the CDP, the first communication materials will be developed (all partners). Two PARC Newsletters will be produced in the first year. Relevant communication and dissemination documents will start being translated into partners' native languages.

A common format for scientific communications resulting from PARC activities will be created at the beginning of the Partnership. An open access and transparent publication strategy will be developed. Furthermore, the guidelines for co-authorship will be defined.

Activities for awareness raising will be planned and start to be developed. A citizens' survey will be planned in the first year of PARC and data collection to be carried out in the second year will be prepared to gather new information, specifically tailored for project needs and more in-depth information about citizens' perceptions and concerns about PARC-related subjects. Information campaigns via various communication tools to improve communication with the general population will be discussed. Collaboration with Task 2.3 will be implemented from the start to involve NHs in these activities.

The strategy for monitoring of indicators through bibliometric analysis, network analysis and other data and tools will be developed.

Stakeholder risk communication persons will be identified and their understanding of basic concepts and perceptions of their role in risk communication will be evaluated through adequate means (NIJZ, EFET).

Task 3.3: Networking and Synergies

Co-Leaders: INSA (PT), NKUA (EL)

Partners: ANSES (FR), MU (CZ), UBA (DE), FMUL (PT), APA (PT), ENSP (PT), UAVR (PT), JSI (SI), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), NIJZ (SI), EFET (EL), UOC (EL), BPI (EL), GCSL (EL)

The synergies and collaboration with partnerships, programmes, infrastructures and other activities will be established at both national, EU and international levels. The following activities that will involve all partners are foreseen within the first year:

- Setting up external communication rules for PARC which will be agreed upon by the MB (GCSL, INSA, NKUA).

- Identification and inventory of European and international partnerships, projects, infrastructures and activities relevant for PARC (all partners), including H2020 and Horizon Europe projects, such as Soil and Water and Cancer Missions, and partnerships, such as the European Partnership for Alternatives to Animal Testing (EPAA).

- Development of an interaction strategy between WP3, PARC's WPs and external initiatives in order to address internal needs and gaps and establish synergies (i.e. list of internal/external communication rules for synergies) (BPI, ENSP, GCSL, INSA, NKUA, UBA).
 - An initial synergies network, SYNnet, will be created and a roadmap for promotion of synergies will be developed and published on the PARC website. This network will be dynamic and continually updated and enriched as PARC progresses (all partners).
 - Launch of SYNnet (all partners).
 Additionally, a specific focus will be put on synergies and collaboration with new countries, notably additional EU Member-States and other relevant countries, not yet participating in PARC (ANSES). A first list of countries will be set up and initial contacts made to encourage them to engage and collaborate in PARC's activities.

Deliverables:

- D3.1 M3 PARC website
- D3.2 M6 Communication and Dissemination Strategy
- D3.3 M9 Report on the establishment of the interactions with SF, IB and ambassador
- D3.4 M10 Database and roadmap for SYNnet

Additional Deliverables:

N/A

WP N°	WP4		Lead Beneficiary	UBA/SpF																																	
WP title	Monitoring and exposure																																				
Partner N°	1	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.9	1.10	1.11	1.12	1.13	2	3	3.4	3.5	3.6	3.9	4	4.1	4.3	4.4	4.5	4.6	4.7	5	5.2	6	6.1	7	7.1	8	8.1	8.2	8.4	10.1
Partner short name	ANSES	INSERM	INRAE	CEA	INERIS	CNRS	INRS	ONIRIS	OFB	BRGM	LNE	CSTB	EHESP	SpF	EAA	MUI	MUW	UG-AT	UNIVE	VITO	KU Leuven	UH	PIH	OIVAM	ISSeP	UAntwerpen	SCIENSANO	EV-ILVO	CIPH	IMROH	MOH-CY/SGL	SHSO	MU	SZU-CZ	VSCHT	JU	AU
PM/partner	27.20	1.50	26.25	9.0.7	16	3.87	9	7.60	2.30	9.50	1	6	13.50	61.90	9.50	16.50	1	1	14.20	37	6.40	1	7	5.50	14.20	18.89	10.50	2	1	2.50	1.50	0.50	54	8	3.50	1	25.40
Partner N°	10.3	10.4	10.5	13	13.1	14.3	14	14.1	15	15.1	15.2	16.6	15.3	16.1	17	18	19	20	20.2	20.3	20.5	20.6	20.7	21	21.1	22	23	24	24.3	25.1	25.2	25.3	25.5	25.6			
Partner short name	REGIONH-RH	UCPH	SDU	THL	SYKE	UOULU	TTL	FFA	UBA	BfG	UFZ	KUM	IPA	Fraunhofer-IBMT/IME	NPHC	UI	MOH	ISS	CNR-IRSA	IRFM	UMIL	UNINA	UNIPD	RSU	UL	NHPSL	LSMU	LNS	UniLU	KWR	TNO	RUMC	UU-IRAS	VUA			
PM/partner	9	9	3.50	3.25	8.10	1.80	9.80	1.50	82.85	14	30	3.32	18.50	14.20	7	3.50	13	9.88	13	6	0.75	0.50	0.50	12.25	3.86	0.25	6.40	37.50	7	1	1	7.25	35.50	15.50			
Partner N°	25.7	26	26.2	26.3	26.5	26.7	27	27.2	27.3	28	29	29.3	30	31	31.1	31.2	31.4	32	32.2	32.3	33	33.4	33.3	34	34.1	34.2	34.5	34.6	34.7	34.8	35.3						

Partner short name	WR	NIPH	STAMI	NILU	NMBU	UNN	NIOM	UG-PL	WULS-SGGW	FMUL	INSA	ENSP	SZU-SK	JSI	GeoZS	NIB	ULFFA	NIJZ	NLZOH	ARSO	CSIC	ULPGC	UGR	ISCH	EASP	FISABIO	IISPV	INNST	UCLM	UPV-EHU	ULUND	
PM/partner	1.16	19.54	5.40	6	1.10	0.25	8.90	1	5.50	1	19.40	2	4.75	34.25	1	1	5.25	14.71	0.20	10.23	28.27	0.25	19.44	36.75	12.50	3.49	1	2.49	3	8	12.50	
Partner N°	35.4	35.6	35.8	35.10	35.11	36	36.1	36.3	36.4	37	38	40	41	45	47	50	53	54	55	56	57	58										
Partner short name	ORU	SU	IVL	SLU	UMU	AUTH	EFET	NKUA	UOC	BPI	FOPH	UNISANTE	EAWAG	USI	SECO	UKHSA	UKCEH	EA	HSE	TOM	UBAH	UINABDN										
PM/partner	12.30	1	13	23.50	1	3.50	4.50	14	3	28.50	5	6.80	18	0.40	0.25	9.40	2.40	1	2	1	1	1										
Start	M1										End										M12											

Objectives

The main goal of WP4 is to monitor chemicals guided by regulatory and policy challenges both in humans and in the environment, observing different sources, chemical fates and exposure pathways. The specific objectives of WP4 for year 1 are:

- Task 4.1: Finalising study design and developing supporting materials for the general population survey, targeted surveys and occupational surveys, identifying exposure and effect biomarkers, proposing innovative (sampling) techniques for Human Bio-Monitoring (HBM) surveys and elaborating a roadmap to explore the links between prioritised exposures and health outcomes
- Task 4.2: Establishing a prioritisation process that supports EU and environmental legislations and performing environmental and multisource monitoring in relation to issues of regulatory and policy concern in a case study
- Task 4.3: Fostering the permeability and harmonisation between the environment-food-HBM communities and prioritised strategic development of innovative approaches from sampling to suspect/non-targeted/Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA) driven exposure data generation and related data processing

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 4.1: Human Biomonitoring

Co-Leaders: VITO (BE), ISCH (ES)

Partners: ANSES (FR), AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), CEA (FR), CSIC (ES), EAA (AT), EHESP (FR), FFA (FI), TTL (FI), FISABIO (ES), FOPH (CH), HSE (UK), KI (SE), IMROH (HR), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), INSERM (FR), INNST (ES), IOM (UK), IPA (DE), KUM (DE), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), IVL (SE), JSI (SI), KU Leuven (BE), LNS (LU), LSMU (LT), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), MOH (IL), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), MUW (AT), NIJZ (SI), NIOM (PL), NIPH (NO), NLZOH (SI), NPHSL (LT), ONIRIS (FR), UKHSA (UK), PIH (BE), REGIONH-RH (DK), RSU (LV), RUMC (NL), SCIENSANO (BE), SLU (SE), SpF (FR), STAMI (NO), SZU-CZ (CZ), SZU-SK (SK), THL (FI), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UGent (BE), UGR (ES), UH (BE), ULFFA (SI), ULPGC (ES), ULUND (SE), UMU (SE), UMIL (IT), UNINA (IT), UNIPD (IT), UNISANTE (CH), UNIVIE (AT), UNN (NO), UOULU (FI), UOC (EL), UPV/EHU (ES), USI (CH), UU-IRAS (NL), WULS-SGGW (PL), CIPH (HR), SHSO (CY), SDU (DK), Fraunhofer-IBMT (DE), UFZ (DE), NPHC (HU), UI (IS), VSCHT (CZ), EASP (ES), SECO (CH),

The design, planning, and implementation of a general population HBM survey will be prepared, building

further on experiences from HBM4EU (INSA, ISCIII, LNS, REGIONH-RH, SpF, UBA, VITO). Eligibility criteria will be defined to allow alignment at EU level of participating national and, in exceptional cases, regional studies. Partners for surveys among three age groups will be selected and included in T4.1 in the course of the first year to participate in a workshop to kick-off the preparatory work and initiate recruitment of participants and administrative tasks such as ethical approval. Candidate studies for participation in the general population HBM survey include (*preliminary, non-exhaustive list*): survey on Children (6-11y): RegionH, SZU-CZ, SZU-SK, NIPH, MU, NIOM, WULS-SGGW, NPHC, INSA, JSI, NIJZ, ISCIII, EAA, UU-IRAS, SpF, UBA, LNS, MOH-IL; survey on Teenagers (12-19y): ULUND, REGIONH-RH, SDU, UKHSA, NIPH, RSU, NIOM, WULS-SGGW, JSI, NIJZ, EASP, UPV/EHU, VITO, PIH, ISSeP, UBA, SpF, UU-IRAS, FOPH, UNISANTE; Adults (20-39y): ULUND, LSMU, UKHSA, NIPH, UI, SZU-CZ, NIPH, MU, NPHC, INSA, UPV/EHU, EASP, ISS, UU-IRAS, VITO, PIH, ISSeP, SpF, UBA, FOPH, UNISANTE, MOH-IL. A selection of chemicals per age group will be made based on prioritisation processes in PARC, considering a common set of chemicals under WP4, 5, 6, and the HBM4EU 3rd priority list. A preliminary shortlist of chemical groups includes PFAS, metals, flame retardants, pesticides and biocides, bisphenols, and phthalates and substitutes. Associated research and policy questions relate to follow up of time trends, exposure of vulnerable groups, linkage to exposure sources and routes, mixture exposure, identification of emerging chemicals, and endocrine and neurodevelopmental effects. Feasibility and a strategy for pooling of human samples will be addressed (in cooperation with T8.2) to monitor exposure levels and their development over time in (sub)populations to complement analysis of individual samples for selected chemical groups (INSA, ISCIII, LNS, REGIONH-RH, SpF, UBA, VITO). The selection, design and planning of targeted studies will be prepared (ISCIII, LNS, SpF, UBA, VITO). Preliminary priorities for targeted studies include dietary exposure to eg. PFAS and mycotoxins in young children, prenatal and newborn exposure to eg. endocrine disruptors and POPs, health effects and risk factors related to (accumulated) exposure in the middle-aged population (40-69y) and elderly (70-85y), hotspots such as industrial and cultivated/agricultural sites, time trends in repeatedly sampled cohorts/regions and/or biobanked samples, and linking chemical exposure with effect biomarkers and health outcomes in longitudinal studies. Occupational studies performed under HBM4EU will be evaluated for lessons learned and study design and protocols for new studies will be developed. During the first year, two occupational surveys focusing on the waste management sector (phthalates, metals, flame retardants, bisphenols) (AU, INSA, ISS, KU Leuven, LNS, MOH-CY/SGL, SHSO, NIOM, STAMI, UMIL, UNIPD, UNISANTE, WULS-SGGW) and the health care sector (HMPs, disinfectants, fragrances) (HSE, INRS, INSST, IOM, MU, RSU, RUMC, TTL, UGR) will be designed and planned. For selected chemicals, we develop an approach to investigate if it is possible to analyse the data from HBM4EU general population studies to identify occupationally exposed groups and to evaluate how general (adult) population studies can identify possible higher exposure of occupationally exposed groups (INRS, INSA, ISS, LSMU, SpF, TTL, UNINA). The implementation of sentinel surveillance systems as a tool to collect reliable and statistically representative data on environmental and occupational exposure and health on a European level will be initiated (AU, INSA, KU Leuven, LNS, MU, NIOM, RSU, RUMC, SpF, UGR, ULUND, UNINA, UNISANTE). The feasibility to (i) assess relationships between exposure biomarkers, effect biomarkers (AU, AUTH, EAA, INRS, INSA, INSERM, ISCIII, JSI, LNS, MU, SECO, SpF, TTL, UGR, UU-IRAS, VITO) and health outcome data, eg. using data or biobanked samples from health examination surveys (EAA, EHESP, Fraunhofer-IBMT, INSST, KU Leuven, LNS, UKHSA, RSU, SpF, SZU-CZ, UBA), (ii) identify the contribution of specific environmental compartments, products and food to internal exposure levels (in collaboration with T4.2), and (iii) apply innovative sampling and screening methods (Fraunhofer, INRAE, REGIONH-RH, SpF, UBA, UFZ, UU-IRAS, VITO, ISCIII) (in collaboration with T4.3) in the general population, targeted, and occupational surveys will be explored, and implementation (as ‘add ons’ to the HBM surveys) will be prepared. In terms of laboratory analysis and quality assurance, the work will focus on the definition of general criteria for the selection of the best, state-of-the-art exposure biomarkers and analytical methods (AU, AUTH, BPI, CEA, EHESP, FFA,

FISABIO, INSA, IPA, KUM, ISCIII, ISS, JSI, KU Leuven, LNS, LSMU, NIOM, NIPH, NPHSL, UKHSA, RSU, RUMC, SZU-CZ, SZU-SK, SpF, STAMI, THL, UAntwerpen, OU, UGR, ULFFA, ULPGC, ULUND, UMIL, UNN, UOC, USI, IMROH, VSCHT). A Quality Assurance Working Group (QAWG) will be created (JSI, IPA, ISCIII, MU) that will work with T9.1 and T9.3 to define the needs for QA and comparability of the HBM data generated under T4.1. Minimum QA/QC criteria to be covered in the innovative techniques will also be defined (INRAE, IPA, ISCIII, MU, ONIRIS, UNIVIE, UOC). A working group on reference analytical methods will be set up (IPA, ISCIII, ISS, IVL, MUI, NIPH, SCIENSANO, ULUND, UNIVIE, UOC) and define general guidelines for development of new analytical methods for exposure and effect biomarkers. The design of the chemical analysis action plan will be initiated (BPI, IPA, LNS, MU, SCIENSANO, SpF, THL, UGR). Supporting materials for general and occupational HBM surveys, such as (dynamic) informed consents, lifestyle and dietary exposure questionnaires, and SOPs for sample collection, preservation, and storage will be developed based on materials elaborated in HBM4EU (CIPH, CSIC, EAA, EASP, FOPH, Fraunhofer-IBMT, IMROH, INSA, IPA, ISCIII, ISS, ISSeP, JSI, LNS, LSMU, MOH-IL, MUW, NIJZ, NIOM, PIH, RSU, SpF, STAMI, THL, UBA, UGR, UMU, UPV). Health-Based Guidance Values (HBM GVs) will be derived for a first set of prioritised substances and reviewed by experts involved via the national hubs (ANSES, LSMU, MOH-IL, NIPH, RUMC, TTL, UBA). A DMP and procedures to make HBM data FAIR will be elaborated, in collaboration with T7.1, for existing and newly generated HBM data (TTL, MU, PIH, SpF, UBA, UU-IRAS, VITO). A helpdesk will be created (PIH, MU, UU-IRAS, VITO) to support the HBM study partners in all aspects of data management. A statistical working group will be established (AU, INSA, JSI, MU, NIPH, SpF, UBA, UH, UU-IRAS, VITO). Statistical analysis plans will be initiated, and analyses will be performed for further exploration of data generated within HBM4EU with respect to exposure sources and routes and determinants of exposure (including occupational exposures), mixtures, and exposure-effect associations (ANSES, AU, AUTH, BPI, EASP, TTL, INRAE, INRS, INSA, INSERM, IPA, ISCIII, ISSeP, JSI, LNS, LSMU, MU, NIJZ, NIPH, SCIENSANO, SpF, STAMI, SZU-SK, UBA, UGR, UNIVIE, UU-IRAS, VITO). As part of a preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe, a synthesis will be made of the experiences from the HBM4EU aligned studies and recommendations from the HBM4EU task on sustainability. A survey will be developed to inquire opportunities and barriers for a future HBM system for Europe among study owners, the GB and other stakeholders. First contacts will be made with international key players in HBM research such as CDC (NHANES), Health Canada (CHMS), Japan or South Korea, to initiate a dialogue to analyse major components and cornerstones of the respective HBM programmes to improve international comparison of HBM data (FOPH, INSA, ISCIII, LNS, LSMU, MOH-CY/SGL, SHSO, NIPH, SpF, SZU-CZ, UBA, VITO).

The description of the WPs organised by activities, sub-activities and projects is available in the SRIA (Annex); For this task, 9 projects have started year 1.

Task 4.2: Environmental and multisource monitoring

Co-leaders: INERIS (FR), AU (DK)

Partners: ANSES (FR), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), CNRS (FR), CNR-IRSA (IT), CSIC (ES), CSTB (FR), EA (UK), EAWAG (CH), EFET (EL), Fraunhofer-IME (DE), FISABIO (ES), INRAE (FR), INSERM (FR), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), IVL (SE), JSI (SI), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), NKUA (EL), OFB (FR), ONIRIS (FR), OVAM (BE), SCIENSANO (BE), SLU (SE), SYKE (FI), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UCLM (PT), UFZ (DE), UL (LV), ULFFA (SI), UniLU (LU), VITO (BE), VSCHT (CZ), ISCIII (ES), VUA (NL), NILU (NO), UKCEH (UK), BPI (EL), NMBU (NO), SpF (FR)

Establishing a process for environmental and multisource monitoring is a key component in PARC. It has the purpose of supporting the EU chemical RA in relation to environmental ecosystems and human exposure, with a close link to human biomonitoring. To do so T4.2 will address knowledge gaps and research priorities identified within T2.1. Moreover, in order to ensure focused and cost-effective monitoring projects in the identified fields of interest, in the first year, T4.2 will develop a framework for

automated assessment of large lists of compounds (UBA, INERIS, AU, SLU, ANSES, ARSO, BPI, UKCEH, CNRS, CNR-IRSA, CSIC, CSTB, EAWAG, Fraunhofer-IME, INRAE, ISS, ISSeP, IVL, JSI, LNS, MU, NILU, NKUA, ONIRIS, OVAM, Sciensano, SpF, SYKE, UAntwerpen, UFZ, ULFFA, VUA), focusing on poorly- and/or non-adequately monitored (groups of) chemicals and unintentional mixtures of emerging concern. The aim is to set up an objective, transparent and reproducible mechanism to select chemicals/matrices/endpoints for which proposals for monitoring projects will be developed. As a first step, partners in T4.2 will establish a detailed inventory of existing prioritisation schemes. The framework will rely on combined use of scientifically-established prioritisation schemes (e.g. OECD, NORMAN, the Nordic Council of Ministers, etc.) to ensure coverage of all compartments and matrices. The first year will focus on the development of the framework whereas its application is expected to start from Y2. T8.2 will collaborate in the design of the prioritisation scheme for the early identification of emerging chemicals risks. Environmental and multisource monitoring is a complex task in PARC, which needs highly optimised processes to be fully beneficial. These processes will be established in the first year and validated in a pilot project focusing on per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs). PFAS and EDCs are two compound groups of regulatory/ policy interest, due to concerns about their persistence, mobility and toxicity (PFAS) and toxicity (EDCs), potentially in combination with other undesired properties and effects. The monitoring activities will involve a range of complementary tools and approaches, including integrated bioanalytical and chemical target, suspect- and non-target screening strategies, in collaboration with Task 4.3. The proposed project topics will also benefit from collaborations with on-going research projects (e.g. Green Deal 8.1 and 8.2 consortia). Following a problem-formulation approach connected to regulatory/policy needs, the pilot project will review, in collaboration with WP9, existing knowledge and infrastructures in the field (INERIS, AU, NKUA, CNR-IRSA, INRAE, MU, ANSES, ARSO, BfG, BPI, BRGM, UKCEH, CNRS, CSTB, EA, EAWAG, EFET, Fraunhofer-IME, FISABIO, ISSeP, ISCIII, IVL, JSI, LNS, NILU, OVAM, SCIENSANO, SLU, SYKE, SpF, UAntwerpen, UBA, UCLM, UFZ, ULFFA) in order to avoid duplication and ensure efficient progress. Such review work will be conducted in synergy with activities planned in T9.2, including reviews as to the potential re-use of existing samples from other programmes, projects and networks. T4.2 will define a list of monitoring data and associated metadata required. Input from WP7 will be sought for inventory of databases (e.g. IPCHEM, NORMAN data base system (NDS), archived data from (digital) specimen banks, etc.) and exploitation of the data (e.g. interoperability of databases, accessibility of data, possibilities for further statistical treatment of the data, individual vs. aggregated data, associated QA/QC data and how to compile these data for the purpose of the project). Likewise, key samples will be identified to address the specific questions of the project. Procedures will be established for contacts to data and sample holders and for formalised agreements on data and sample sharing or other re-use of existing material and information, including QA/QC criteria for shipping and storage, conditions to re-use the samples, availability of relevant metadata etc. Partners in T4.2 will also review the state-of-the-art in the chemical analyses of PFAS and selected endocrine disrupters and exchange information with T4.3 with regard to these compounds being considered in novel approaches. Monitoring study(ies) will be designed focusing on the identified target areas, PFAS (UBA, CNR-IRSA, SLU, UFZ, SYKE, AU, INRAE, ANSES, BfG, BPI, BRGM, CNRS, CSTB, CSIC, EAWAG, EFET, Fraunhofer-IME, FISABIO, INERIS, ISSeP, IVL, JSI, LNS, MU, NILU, NKUA, NMBU, ONIRIS, OVAM, SCIENSANO, UAntwerpen, UL, VSCHT, VUA) and EDCs (IVL, BfG, INERIS, EAWAG, UFZ, SYKE, INRAE, ANSES, AU, BPI, BRGM, CNRS, CSTB, CSIC, EFET, FISABIO, ISSeP, JSI, LNS, MU, NKUA, OFB, ONIRIS, SCIENSANO, UAntwerpen, UBA, UCLM, UL, ULFFA, VSCHT, VUA), and in response to identified regulatory/policy needs. As regards PFAS, as a first step, samples from across Europe will be used from the Water Framework Directive monitoring networks, including suspended particulate matter and sediments to generate a baseline for the freshwater environment. The PFAS work will address compounds with varying chain length and functional groups, precursors and transformation products, with particular attention to “emerging PFAS”, e.g. short-chain PFAS and fluoroalkylether compounds. The study will combine the

analysis of sum parameters, target, non-target and suspect screening approaches. Interfaces will be established to PFAS data from other compartments and matrices, e.g. food, drinking water, wastewater, indoor environment or products. For EDCs the project will contribute to the first EU baseline for already prioritised EDCs (<http://edclist.org>) in multiple environmental compartments. In addition, the aim will be to identify new key EDCs present in the environment, by integrated approaches based on target analysis, non-target and suspect screening coupled with effect-based assessment (batteries of multi-receptor *in vitro* and *in vivo* bioassays), including effect-directed analysis (EDA) studies to identify major toxicants in prioritised samples. A workshop will be arranged with T4.1, T4.3, T6.2, WP7, WP9 and the QA/QC Group to discuss the project design. A data flow plan will be established in collaboration with WP7 in line with the whole PARC DMP. The QA/QC concept will be established and discussed with the QA/QC Group to be formed in WP9. General procedures, including criteria for laboratory selection, will be established for contacts to laboratories in synergy with WP9. The first year will be dedicated to detailed planning of the field study. Running of the monitoring campaign, applying the agreed protocols, will primarily take place on the second year. However, some analytical work (e.g. initial measurements, stability studies, retrospective analysis of existing samples, etc.) will be carried out (SLU, BfG, NKUA, UFZ, MU, SCIENSANO, ANSES, UBA, ONIRIS, INERIS, EAWAG, AU, BRGM, UKCEH, CNRS, CNR-IRSA, CSIC, CSTB, EFET, Fraunhofer-IME, FISABIO, INRAE, INSERM, ISS, ISSeP, JSI, LNS, NILU, NMBU, SYKE, UAntwerpen, UCLM, UL, ULFFA, VSCHT, VUA) to support the preparation of the monitoring campaigns. Likewise, the main part of statistical analysis will take place on the results of the monitoring campaigns. However, statistical analysis of existing data will be started on the first year (UFZ, NKUA, SLU, MU, UBA, ANSES, ARSO, AU, BfG, BPI, BRGM, UKCEH, CNRS, CNR-IRSA, CSTB, EFET, Fraunhofer-IME, INERIS, ISSeP, JSI, LNS, NILU, NMBU, OVAM, SCIENSANO, SYKE, UAntwerpen, UniLU, VITO, VUA). The first year will also include work on the conceptual approach and the information to be included in the feedback mechanism (AU, CSIC, IVL, NKUA, UBA, BPI, BRGM, UKCEH, EFET, ISSeP, NILU, NMBU, OVAM, UAntwerpen, SpF).

The description of the WPs organised by activities, sub-activities and is available in the SRIA (Annex); For this task, 1 project has started year 1.

Task 4.3: Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys

Co-Leaders: INRAE (FR), VUA (NL)

Partners: ANSES (FR), AU (DK), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), CEA (FR), CNRS (FR), EAWAG (CH), EHESP (FR), , INERIS (FR), INRS (FR), , IRFM (IT), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), ONIRIS (FR), ORU (SE), SLU (SE), SpF (FR), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UBAH (UK), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), UGR (ES), UniLU (LU), UNIVIE (AT), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE), WR (NL), AUTH (EL), BPI (GR), CNR-IRSA (IT), EV-ILVO (NL), FMUL (PT), GeoZS (SI), CSIC (ES), , IISPV (ES), ISCHII (ES), ISS (IT), IVL (SE), JU (CZ), KUM (DE), LNE (FR), NIB (SI), NIJZ (SI), NILU (NO), NIOM (PL), , OFB (FR), , STAMI (NO), SU (SE), SYKE (FI), THL (FI), TNO (NL), , UG-AT (AT), UG-PL (PL), UKCEH (UK), UL (LV), ULFFA (SI), UNIADBN (UK), VSCHT (CZ), WULS-SGGW (PL)

T4.3 will evaluate the main approaches and objectives associated to innovative methods undertaken in T4.3 (inventories, selection/prioritisation, shared knowledge and visions among environmental-food-HBM communities) toward applicability in large scale monitoring programmes and specific surveys (INRAE, VUA, ANSES, BRGM, EAWAG, EHESP, INRS, JSI, LNS, MU, MUI, UAntwerpen, UBA, UFZ, VITO, WR, EV-ILVO, NILU, OFB, UL-FFA). In close interaction with T8.2, T4.3 will develop the necessary provisions to ensure the usefulness of the expected data and knowledge sorted out from those innovative methods for contribution to early warning system (INRAE, ANSES, AU, BfG, BRGM, EAWAG, EHESP, INRS, JSI, KWR, LNS, MU, MUI, ORU, SLU, UAntwerpen, UBA, UCPH, UFZ, WR, EV-ILVO, CSIC, LNE, NILU, WULS). In close interaction with T9.3, T4.1 and T4.2, T4.3 will finally elaborate a consensual inventory of method performances and QA/QC criteria to be prioritised specifically for innovative suspect/NTS/EDA screening approaches and define the further needs in terms of interlaboratory

comparison exercises to be conducted. (INRAE, ANSES, AU, BfG, BRGM, EAWAG, EHESP, INRS, JSI, KWR, LNS, MU, MUI, ORU, SLU, UAntwerpen, UBA, UCPH, UFZ, WR EV-ILVO, CSIC, LNE, NILU, WULS). T4.3 will also start the elaboration of an open access workflow for data processing and annotation of High-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) based chemical profiles from suspect/NTS approaches (e.g. inspired from W4M/Galaxy), with an integrative ambition of harmonised application in the environmental-food-HBM studies (INRAE, VUA, ANSES, EAWAG, EHESP, INRS, JSI, KWR, MU, MUI, ONIRIS, UBA, UCPH, UFZ, UniLU, UU-IRAS, WR). T4.3 will then focus on 2 workplans for first pilot studies. 1) the design and feasibility of a HBM monitoring study, in collaboration with task 4.1, to assess the use of personal samplers (wearables like silicone wristbands) coupled to suspect screening/NTS/EDA-based to optimise surveys for characterisation of exposure that are not commonly covered by existing monitoring programmes. The first steps of this methodological development will be done in adults and extended to perinatal or pre-pubertal samples if reasonable. (INRAE, VUA, AU, CEA, EHESP, JSI, LNS, MU, MUI, UAntwerpen, UFZ, UGR, UniLU, UNIVIE, UU-IRAS, WR, BPI, CSIC, IISPV, IISCI, ISS, KUM, SU, UNIABD, VSCHT). 2) the design of a pilot environmental monitoring study, focusing on sewage treatment plants with the aim of mining the wealth of chemical information in both influents and effluents, in collaboration with task 4.2. Using influents, we will assess community wide exposure using Wastewater-based epidemiology (WBE), both for targeted analysis and suspect screening/NTS/EDA (INRAE, VUA, BfG, BRGM, EAWAG, INERIS, IRFM, JSI, KWR, MU, MUI, , SLU, UAntwerpen, UBAH, UCPH, UFZ, UniLU, VITO, ISS, JU, OFB, UL, UL-FFA, WULS). On the effluent side, emissions into the aquatic environment will be characterised using time integrated sampling techniques in combination with suspect screening/NTS/EDA. All activities described above will concern various substances and substance groups simultaneously and address both non-persistent and persistent organic pollutants of emerging concern.

The description of the WPs organised by activities, sub-activities and projects is available in the SRIA (Annex); For this task, 6 projects have started year 1.

Deliverables:

N/A

Additional Deliverables

- AD4.1 M12 Periodic report on available supporting materials for HBM studies
- AD4.2 M12 Periodic report on analytical methods and measurements for exposure and effect biomarkers
- AD4.3 M12 Derivation of HBM-GVs (one dossier per substance; 3-4 substances)
- AD4.4 M12 Procedures for agreement on transparent use of existing data, access to samples and involvement of external laboratories
- AD4.5 M12 Technical specifications of the study (project design, hypothesis and research question as well as analytical procedures including QA/QC and data flows)
- AD4.6 M12 Concept paper regarding common definitions and short to medium term support to policy objectives of innovative (self-) sampling, suspect screening and NTS/EDA approaches

WP N°	WP5														Lead Beneficiary										ANSES/BfR													
WP title	Hazard Assessment																																					
Partner N°	1	1.1	1.2	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.8	3.4	3.7	3.9	4.1	4.7	5	5.1	5.3	8	10.1	10.2	10.5	14	15.1	15.2	16	16.1	16.3	16.4	16.7	16.8	17	18	20	20.3	20.5	24.1	25	25.4	25.5	25.6

Partner short name	ANSES	INERM	INRAE	INERIS	CNRS	INRS	IRSN	MUI	UIBK	UNIVE	KU Leuven	UAntwerpen	SCIENSANO	UGent	VUB	MU	AU	DTU FOOD	SDU	TTL	BfG	UFZ	BfR	Fraunhofer-ITEM	IUF	IfADo	TUB	UKON	NPHC	UI	ISS	IRFM	UMIL	LIH	RIVM	UL-LACDR	UU-IRAS	VUA
PM/partner	49.35	204	36.05	17.30	29.50	9.60	2	19	21.20	40	2.60	42	24	15.75	25	13	15	29	31.34	0.50	10	53.25	71.50	6.80	18	8	21.10	7.50	32.20	8	26	12	7.36	2	11	45	6	4.50
Partner number	25.7	25.8	26	26.1	26.2	26.3	26.4	26.5	26.6	27.1	27.2	29	29.5	31.2	31.3	31.4	31.5	33	33.2	33.4	34	34.5	35.2	35.10	35.2	36	36.4	37	41	42	47	50	52	53	58	59		
Partner short name	WR	WU-TOX	NIPH	IMR	STAMI	NILU	NIVA	NMBU	NVI	IEP-NRI	UG-PL	INSA	UAVR	NIB	NIC	ULFFA	MFUM	CSIC	UNAV	UPO	ISCHII	IISPV	KI	SLU	UU	AUTH	UOC	BPI	EAWAG	ETHZ	SECO	UKHSA	Cefas-defra	UKCEH	UINABDN	UOB		
PM/partner	6.56	6.57	24	8	9	2	10	2.70	9	8.80	12.89	26	11.22	41	8	12	1	21.60	33	14	25.50	45	1	27	34.60	22	17	41.30	27	24	0.10	7	1.09	0.80	0.25	9.60		
Start	M1										End										M12																	

Objectives

The main goal of WP5 is to focus on Hazard Assessment (HA) for human and environmental health on three different directions: fill data gaps, develop and/or improve methodologies for HA to progress towards Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA). The specific objectives of WP5 for year 1 are:

- Task 5.1: Closing regulatory/policy data gaps on hazards identified by key stakeholders through the organisation of a workshop to gather regulatory/policy needs from EU and national agencies on BPA alternatives and test item availability for prioritised groups of compounds (M1-4); and planning OECD test guideline studies to be conducted in years 2 and 3 (e.g. Extended One-Generation Reproductive Toxicity Studies (EOGRTS)) and conducting first *in vitro* studies on prioritised substances (M5-12).
- Task 5.2: Developing innovative methodologies that will directly aid chemical hazard identification, Risk Assessment (RA) and regulation/policy. WP5 will focus on five different endpoints (immunotoxicity, non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, (developmental) neurotoxicity, endocrine disruption (thyroid) and metabolic disruption).
- Task 5.3: i) Establishing different core or extended groups relevant for the activity of this task: omics, Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs), bioinformatics, effect markers, PBTK, *in vivo/in vitro* mode of action; ii) establishing an inventory and mapping available knowledge, reference *in vivo*/human datasets, activities and models in systems biology, PBTK and AOP frameworks and prioritising additional studies and iii) initiating studies to characterise coregulated gene networks, for already published AOPs (to make them quantitative) and linking chemicals to available AOPs, linking omics data to human physiopathology, generating high quality ADME data and ultimately building new AOPs.

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 5.1: Toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern

Co-Leaders 5.1.a: NIPH (NO), INSA (PT); Co-leaders 5.1.b: BPI (EL)

Partners 5.1.a: ANSES (FR), INRAE (FR), CNRS (FR), INRS (FR), MUI (AT), UNIVIE (AT), SCIENSANO

(BE), AU (DK), SDU (DK), TTL (FL), UFZ (DE), BfR (DE), Fraunhofer-ITEM (DE), IfADo (DE), TUB (DE), UI (IS), ISS (IT), UMIL (IT), WU-TOX (NL), NIPH (NO), IMR (NO), STAMI (NO), NILU (NO), NMBU (NO), NVI (NO), INSA (PT), UAVR (PT), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), ULFFA (SI), MFUM (SI), CSIC (ES), UNAV (ES), ISCIII (ES), IISPV (ES), UOB (UK), UNIABDN (UK), AUTH (EL), UOC (EL), BPI (EL)

Partners 5.1b: ANSES (FR), INERIS (FR), UGent (BE), SDU (DK), BfR (DE), IEP-NRI (PL), UAVR (PT), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), IISPV (ES), SLU (SE), UU (SE), Cefas-Defra (UK), UKCEH (UK), UOB (UK), UOC (EL), BPI (EL).

After a prioritisation exercise and further consultation with partners involved in hazard and risk assessment in national and European agencies the following groups of substances were selected for the first round of testing: natural toxins, in particular the mycotoxins enniatins and those derived from *Alternaria* as well as bisphenol A (BPA) alternatives. Based on expert's judgement on data gaps with the selected compounds for human and environmental health, and advice on the studies needed to fill the knowledge or regulatory/policy gaps, two subprojects (mycotoxins and alternatives to BPA) were selected to start in the first project year. The prioritised endpoints comprise genotoxicity/mutagenicity and non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, endocrine disruption and immunotoxicity, among other relevant substance-specific endpoints. The first six months of PARC will be used to develop these proposals further, including sourcing of test items, especially for the natural toxins, to ensure availability of well-characterised test items for the regulatory/policy studies. Sourcing, including synthesis of test items, and formulation in appropriate vehicles should be performed from one central depository (TUB). Regarding the BPA alternative activity, a workshop, in collaboration with WP2, will be organised at the very beginning of the Partnership to gather regulatory or policy needs from EU and national agencies and key stakeholders. Outcome of this workshop will help us to establish the most critical regulatory needs to be filled (PARC will focus on regulatory and policy needs that are not in the remit of the industry) and will allow to refine the project.

There will be an opportunity in task 5.1 to conduct *in vivo* studies according to GLP and OECD guidelines, for example toxicokinetic (OECD TG 417) including metabolism and metabolites identification for further testings, 90-day repeated dose (OECD TG 408) or Extended One Generation Reprotoxicity studies (EOGRTS, OECD TG 443). During PARC, results from other WP identifying additional needs for testing or emerging regulatory and policy issues may lead to additional *in vivo* studies. The design of these studies, including selection of test chemicals, will need more time and the first 6-12 months of PARC will be used to finalise the proposals.

These activities will be closely aligned with activities in tasks 5.2 (to combine *in vivo* studies and NAMs) and 5.3 (for –omics analyses, TK sampling etc.), WP6, WP4, WP7, WP8, WP9 and with other EU programmes and clusters (EURION, EHEN, RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX, PrecisionTOX).

The description of the WPs organised by activities, sub-activities and projects is available in the SRIA (Annex); For this task, 4 projects have started year 1.

Task 5.2: Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling

Co-leaders 5.2.a: DTU FOOD (DK), VUB (BE); Co-leaders 5.2.b: MU (CZ)

Participants 5.2.a: ANSES (FR), INSERM (FR), INRAE (FR), MUI (AT), UIBK (AT), Uantwerpen (BE), VUB (DE), DTU FOOD (DK), SDU (DK), UFZ (DE), BfR (DE), IUF (DE), UKON (DE), TiHo (DE), NPHC (HU), IRFM (IT), LIH (LU), RIVM (NL), UL-LACDR (NL), UU-IRAS (NL), VUA (NL), WR (NL), NIPH (NO), NILU (NO), UG-PL (PL), INSA (PT), UAVR (PT), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), ULFFA (SI), CSIC (ES), UNAV (ES), ISCIII (ES), UU (SE), UKHSA (UK)

Participants 5.2.b: ANSES (FR), INRAE (FR), INERIS (FR), CNRS (FR), Uantwerpen (BE), MU (CZ), SDU (DK), BfG (DE), UFZ (DE), BfR (DE), UU-IRAS (NL), NIVA (NO), NMBU (NO), UG-PL (PL), UAVR (PT), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), UPO (ES), IISPV (ES), SLU (SE), UU (SE), UKCEH (UK), BPI (EL), EAWAG (CH)

This task has a clear focus on developing innovative methodologies that will directly aid chemical hazard identification, RA and regulation/policy. This will help to facilitate the development of NAMs for RA and the transition of endpoint based on animal testing to a more mechanism-based testing as foreseen by the Tox21 and the EU Chemicals strategy.

Starting on the first year of the Partnership, based on the prioritisation activities underwent prior to the start of the Partnership, it will focus on five different endpoints (immunotoxicity, non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, (developmental) neurotoxicity, endocrine disruption (thyroid) and metabolic disruption).

The objectives for year 1 are:

1. To agree and organise test items for prioritised groups of compounds (T5.1 and WP5 leaders).
2. To plan more sophisticated studies to be conducted in years 2 and 3 (T5.1 and WP5 leaders and activity leads)
3. To conduct first assays on prioritised endpoints (T5.2 leaders and partners)

These activities will be closely aligned with activities in tasks 5.1 (to combine *in vivo* studies and NAMs) and 5.3 (for –omics analyses, TK sampling etc.), WP6, WP4, WP7, WP8, WP9 and with other EU programmes and clusters (EURION, EHEN, RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX, PrecisionTOX).

The description of the WPs organised by activities, sub-activities and projects is available in the SRIA (Annex); For this task, 5 projects have started year 1.

Task 5.3: Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs

Co-leaders: UL-LACDR (NL), SCIENSANO (BE), INSERM (FR), Fraunhofer-ITEM (DE)

Participants 5.3.: ANSES (FR), INSERM (FR) MUI (AT), UIBK (AT), SCIENSANO (BE) UGent (BE), BfR (DE), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), LIH (LU), UL-LACDR (NL), WR (NL), ISCIII (ES), IISPV (ES), BPI (EL), UNIVIE (AT), KU Leuven (BE), Uanterwerpen (BE), AU (DK), SDU (DK), NPHC (HU), UMIL (IT), UG-PL (PL), UKCEH (UK), BfR (DE), NIPH (NO), INERIS (FR), Fraunhofer-ITEM (DE), WU-TOX (NL), ETHZ (CH)

In year 1, in task 5.3 we will establish an inventory of available omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes, with initial focus on immunotoxicity, (Developmental) neurotoxicity, non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, metabolic disruption. With regards to AOP development, an AOP core group (participants to be identified within WP5 and WP6 partners) will make an inventory of the available AOPs, prioritise and establish the framework for further development in this task. An extended AOP group consisting of all task partners will start studies on integrating available omics data and other data sets in the building of new AOPs in neurotoxicology and metabolic disruption. Regarding translation to human pathophysiology, in year 1, we will start mapping the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology, thereby focusing on the prioritised endpoints (e.g. immunotoxicity, (Developmental) neurotoxicity, non-genotoxic carcinogenicity and metabolic disruption). Furthermore, an overview of existing human biobanks that can later be used to fill gaps in human pathophysiology information will be compiled (T5.3 leaders with specific partners). A core group consisting of experts in the field of bioinformatics (T5.3 leaders) will draft a strategy for development of bioinformatics tools that are needed to link omics data and other mechanistic information to human relevant disease mechanisms. In addition, the core group on *in vivo/in vitro* mode of action will work on a framework to facilitate the correlation of *in vivo* and *in vitro* mode of action information with human data. Finally, during the first year, the PBTK core group (T5.3 and T6.2 leaders) will make an inventory of available PBTK models, identify knowledge gaps with regard to route specific ADME processes and establish the framework for the integration of *in vitro* ADME data into PBTK models. The group will consist of partners that have already developed PBTK models for oral and inhalation exposure as well as partners coordinating the WP6 case studies. For PBTK development, model compounds will be identified, having high quality *in vivo* ADME reference data. WP5 priority compounds will be assessed with the resultant IVIVE-PBTK models.

The description of the WPs organised by activities, sub-activities and projects is available in the SRIA (Annex); For this task, 3 projects have started year 1.

Deliverables:

N/A

Additional Deliverables

- AD5.1 M9 Report on the workshop organised with national and EU agencies and stakeholders on the of-concern bisphenol A alternatives
- AD5.2 M12 Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted
- AD5.3 M12 List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints
- AD5.4 M12 Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes
- AD5.5 M12 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC
- AD5.6 M12 Mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints
- AD5.7 M12 Draft strategy for the development of bioinformatics tools that are needed to link omics data and other mechanistic information to human relevant disease mechanisms
- AD5.8 M12 Inventory of available in PBTK models, identification of knowledge gaps regarding route specific ADME processes and setting up of the framework for the integration of in vitro ADME data into PBTK models

WP N°	WP6													Lead Beneficiary	RIVM/KEMI																					
WP title	Innovation in regulatory risk assessment																																			
Partner N°	1	1.1	1.2	1.4	1.6	1.7	1.8	1.9	1.12	1.13	3	3.1	3.4	4	4.6	4.7	5	5.1	5.3	7	8	10.1	10.2	10.3	10.5	11.2	13.1	14	14.2	15	15.2	15.4	15.5			
Partner short name	ANSES	INSERM	INRAE	INERIS	INRS	ONIRIS	IRSN	OFB	CSTB	EHESP	EAA	AGES	MUJ	VITO	ISSeP	UAntwerpen	SCIENSANO	UGent	VUB	MOH-CY/SGL	MU	AU	DTU FOOD	REGIONH-GE	SDU	UT	SYKE	TTL	Tukes	UBA	UFZ	UKOLD	UOS			
PM/partner	62.75	17	2	16	3	11	6	2	12	0.50	2	15	2.50	28	11	18	51	11	18	1.35	46	22.90	22	7	4	18	4.50	11	3	30	22	15	2			
Partner N°	16.1	16.4	18	20	20.1	20.3	20.4	20.7	21	23	24	24.2	25	25.1	25.2	25.3	25.4	25.5	25.6	25.7	25.8	26	26.2	26.3	26.4	27	27.1	27.2	28	29	29.2	29.3	29.4	29.5	31	31.1
Partner short name	Fraunhofer-IBMT/IME	IfAdo	UI	ISS	ICPS	IRFM	IUSS	UNIPD	RSU	LSMU	LNS	LIST	RIVM	KWR	TNO	RUMC	UL-LACDR	UU-IRAS	VUA	WR	WU-TOX	NIPH	STAMI	NILU	NIVA	NIOM	IEP-NRI	UG-PL	FMUL	INSA	DGS	ENSP	UC	UAVR	ISI	GEoZS
PM/partner	5	4	1	26	3.85	7	5.50	18.50	2	2	9.50	7	46.45	3.65	7.29	1	41.20	38.40	1	4.73	18.47	28	25.50	2	7	6	5	14.47	5	13	1	9	11.70	3.15	20.50	10.70

Partner N°	Partner short name	PM/ partner	Start
32	NIJZ	15.60	M1
32.1	OI	6	
32.2	NLZOH	0.30	
33	CSIC	60	
33.3	UGR	14	
34	ISCHII	16	
34.3	FINBA	9	
34.5	IISPV	33	
34.7	UCLM	8	
35.1	UGOT	10	
35.2	KI	9.50	
35.3	ULUND	5	
35.5	RISE	12	
35.6	SU	48	
35.7	KEMI	15	
35.8	IVL	6	
35.10	SLU	20	
36	AUTH	50	
37	BPI	40	
38	FOPH	1	
39	AGROSCOPE	1	
40	UNISANTE	1.50	
41	EAWAG	15.50	
44	FOEN	6	
45	USI	2	
46	UNIBAS	24	
47	SECO	0.30	
49	EFSA	3	
50	UKHSA	6	
51	BUL	6	M12
53	UKCEH	2.60	
59	UOB	10	
60	UCL	3	

Objectives

The main goal of WP6 is to drive innovation in regulatory RA by strengthening its scientific basis, with implementation of Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) as ultimate goal. The specific objectives of WP6 for year 1 are:

- Task 6.1: Developing quantitative networks of Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity, to assess their human relevance and to identify associated NAMs. Based on this work, development of regulatory relevant Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATAs) for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity will be initiated, in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders. Dedicated case studies to evaluate the IATAs will be designed
- Task 6.2: Developing innovative methods, tools and concepts and performing integrative risk and health impact assessments based on internal and external exposure of humans exposed to single chemicals and mixtures from multiple sources and routes for different living environments (including workplace)
- Task 6.3: Initiating case studies reviewing selected methodologies and approaches for regulatory RA
- Task 6.4: Laying the groundwork for the development of efficient and protective regulatory RA and underpinning development of regulations through stakeholder workshops, review of knowledge, landscaping exercises, action plan developments and case studies which will inform the decisions on how (and which) approaches should be developed

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 6.1: Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment of Chemicals

Co-Leaders: SCIENSANO (BE), UL-LACDR (NL)

Partners: AUTH (EL); BPI (EL); DTU FOOD (DK); UAVR (PT); ENSP (PT); Fraunhofer (DE); IISPV (ES); IfADo (DE); INERIS (FR); INRAE (FR); INSERM (FR); IRFM (IT); IRSN (FR); ISS (IT); KI (SE);

KWR (NL); LIST (LU); MOH-CY/SGL (CY); MU (CZ); MUI (AT); NILU (NO); NIPH (NO); UOB (UK); UKHSA (UK); UKCEH (UK); UG-PL (PL); RIVM (NL); SDU (DK); STAMI (NO); UAntwerpen (BE); UGent (BE); UU-IRAS (NL); VUB (BE); WR (NL); WU-TOX (NL)

A6.1.1: Development of IATAs for regulatory purposes

This activity will start with the development of IATAs for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption (with a primary focus on thyroid) and liver toxicity: health effects that are considered low-hanging fruit for IATA development based on existing data. For all three health effects, the availability and maturity (i.e. the level of completeness) of existing AOPs and associated NAMs will be mapped (in collaboration with T5.3 and T6.3). Inventories of AOPs and NAMs will be created in close collaboration with parallel initiatives at the European/international level, including the EURION cluster, EU-ToxRisk, RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX, PrecisionTox, and the HESI Genetic Toxicology Technical Committee (GTTC). Where appropriate, AOPs will be combined into AOP networks (AON). In case sufficient information is available, initial steps will be undertaken to quantitate AON. The type of modelling used for quantitation will depend on the AOP. Ideally, dynamic modelling will be performed. However, this type of modelling is very data demanding, which may not always be available; hence, more simple models may need to be used. Any gaps in data, being of either qualitative or quantitative nature, will be discussed with the relevant partners involved in T6.1 and WP5; where needed, additional testing may be performed in WP5 to close these gaps. It should be noted that semi-quantitative or qualitative AON can be useful for IATA development as well.

The IATAs will be based on human relevant AOPs/AONs. Therefore, the AOPs/AONs developed for the three health effects will be subject to human relevance assessment. For this, a draft workflow developed by RIVM will be applied. The draft workflow for human relevance assessment involves qualitative and quantitative considerations and relies on toxicological, epidemiological and clinical data. The workflow itself will be further optimised, in close collaboration with international and regulatory organisations, including OECD, WHO and JRC, and other relevant related initiatives. Since this activity directly relates to scientific criteria for NAMs (A6.4.2), the progress made and possible issues encountered will be discussed in regular WP6 meetings.

The human-relevant AONs will be used to design IATAs for the selected health effects. This will be done in close collaboration with OECD and according to OECD guidance. IATA development for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity will start in year one and continue in year two and beyond; they will be developed through various cycles of optimisation. The progress made and approaches used will be discussed with stakeholders (A6.1.3).

Additionally, a mapping exercise of existing AOPs and associated NAMs (similar to the one conducted for liver toxicity, endocrine disruption and genotoxicity) will be carried out for health effects that are considered of high regulatory relevance but, due to their complexity and the limited amount of data available, are expected to require (much) more time for IATA development (e.g. developmental neuro/immunotoxicity, non-genotoxic carcinogenicity). Approaches such as the development of a conceptual framework will be considered. The mapping exercise will be done in close collaboration with WP5.3 and related initiatives, such as the OECD Expert Groups for developmental neurotoxicity and non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, ATHLETE, ONTOX, EU-ToxRisk and RISK-HUNT3R. Based on the collected information and discussions with WP2, WP3, WP5, and WP7, a strategy for IATA development for these more complex endpoints to be addressed in the next years of PARC will be drafted (INRAE, INSERM, IRSN, MUI, UAntwerpen, SCIENSANO, UGent, VUB, MU, DTU FOOD, SDU, IfADo, ISS, IRFM, LIST, RIVM, KWR, UL-LACDR, UU-IRAS, WR, NIPH, STAMI, NILU, UG-PL, UAVR, IISPV, KI, UKHSA, UKCEH, UOB, AUTH, BPI, MOH-CY/SGL).

A6.1.2: Evaluation of IATAs through case studies

IATAs will be developed through various cycles of optimisation; (interim) evaluations will be conducted through case studies. For both the development and the evaluation of IATAs we will closely collaborate with OECD. To allow for interim evaluation of the IATAs developed in A6.1.1, a first set of case studies will be designed and initiated in year 1. These initial case studies will be based on AON in relation to

genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity, in conjunction with A6.1.1. Case study teams will have a case study leader and together will establish the case study regulatory hypothesis and define case study compounds relevant for these initial case studies. The case study teams will involve both *in silico* and *in vitro* NAM experts that represent the critical NAMs that can be mapped to the AOP/AON. These NAMs should include (pre-)validated NAMs. Each team will involve partners with expertise on QSAR modelling, PBK modelling, essential *in vitro* test methods and detected assays, omics analysis, and uncertainty analysis. For ultimate integration of the data into QIVIVE, we will integrate the tools established in T5.3. The case study modeling and experimental activities will be described and submitted for review via the project management system under T2.1 (M8). Upon approval, case study compounds will be distributed to the various PARC partners and testing will be initiated for at least three case studies in the first year by the various case study team partners. At the end of year 1 the topics for other case studies will be defined and submitted to the project management system (T2.1); case study teams will be established for the additional IATA case studies that involve priority endpoints. In T6.3, lessons learned by different stakeholders from previous case studies will be mapped. These will be implemented in the IATA case studies as soon as this information becomes available (INERIS, INSERM, IRSN, UAntwerpen, SCIENSANO, UGent, MU, DTU, SDU, Fraunhofer, ISS, RIVM, UL-LACDR, WU-TOX, NIPH, STAMI, NILU, UG-PL, UAVR, IISPV, KI, UKCEH, UOB, AUTH, BPI, MOH-CY/SGL).

A6.1.3: Stakeholder engagement

This activity will start with a set of online meetings (organised in collaboration with WP3 and per health effect; M2) between representatives of relevant related research projects/programmes and A6.1.1 partners, with the aim to discuss in detail the status of AOP and IATA development and the plans for the upcoming year. Where needed, additional meetings will be organised. The progress made on AOP/AON and IATA development for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity will be discussed in the annual two-day WP6 workshop with a wider group of stakeholders, with the explicit aim to collect feedback on the work done and input on the next steps. Participants of this meeting will include WP6 partners, relevant WP/task leaders of PARC, representatives of national/European regulatory agencies, OECD, JRC, HESI GTTC, EURION, EU-ToxRisk, RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX, PrecisionTOX, industrial partners and NGOs (RIVM, SCIENSANO, UL-LACDR, STAMI, ISS, UG-PL, UAVR, UKCEH, BPI).

The description of the WPs organised by activities, sub-activities and projects is available in the SRIA (Annex); For this task, 4 projects have started year 1.

Task 6.2: Integrative exposure and risk assessment

Co-Leaders: ANSES (FR), VITO (BE)

Partners: AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), CSTB (FR), DTU FOOD (DK), EFSA (IT), EHESP (FR), ENSP (PT), FINBA (ES), TTL (FI), FMUL (PT), FOPH (CH), Fraunhofer (DE), GEoSZ (SI), ICPS (IT), CSIC (ES), IISPV (ES), KI (SE), INERIS (FR), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), IRFM (IT), ISCIII (ES), ISSeP (BE), IUSS (IT), IVL (SE), KWR (NL), LNS (LU), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIOM (PL), NIPH (NO), NLZOH (SI), OI (SI), ONIRIS (FR), RIVM (NL), RUMC (NL), SCIENSANO (BE), SECO (CH), SLU (SE), STAMI (NO), TNO (NL), UAVR (PT), UBA (DE), UGR (ES), UG-PL (PL), UNIPD (IT), UNISANTE (CH), USI (CH), UU-IRAS (NL), WR (NL)

A6.2.1 Aggregated exposure assessment from multiple sources and routes for general population and workers

A strategy to assess aggregate exposure through different living environments (occupational, general environment, domestic environment) and different routes of entry (inhalation, dermal, ingestion) will be developed in the first year. An inventory of data sources, models and tools for exposure assessment of occupational and general populations will be made. Model structures, input and output, variability and uncertainty will be analysed, and a gap analysis will be performed. The results

will feed into a functional design to connect models to be established during the second year of PARC. A methodological approach to combine heterogeneous datasets will be developed, and criteria to prioritise substance-source-(sub)population combinations for source-to-dose and aggregate exposure assessment in case studies will be defined. Development of realistic source-to-dose models for the general population will be initiated to assess direct exposure to chemicals released from consumer products and materials, and consumer exposure via transfer from the environment. Year 1 will focus on generation of mechanistic understanding, conceptual development and inventory of existing data to parametrise the conceptual model (ANSES, AU, CSTB, EFSA, ENSP, FMUL, FOPH, Fraunhofer, GEoSZ, CSIC, IISPV, INRS, INSA, ISCI, ISSeP, IVL, KWR, LNS, MU, NIJZ, NIOM, NIPH, NLZOH, RIVM, RUMC, STAMI, TNO, TTL, UAVR, UNISANTE, UU-IRAS, VITO, WR).

A6.2.2 Modelling exposure through life

For assessment of internal exposure through life for prioritised subpopulations, exposure routes, and chemical interactions, needs for the application of PBK modelling will be identified. Existing PBK models for the sensitive human sub-groups (e.g. foetus, young children, pregnant women, elderly) and toxicokinetic processes that could be modified in this specific sub-groups will be reviewed. A strategy to account for qualitative and quantitative data generated by omics will be defined. Cohort data that could be used for the development of PBK models for sensitive sub-groups will be identified (ANSES, AUTH, EFSA, CSIC, IISPV, INERIS, INRAE, IRFM, IUSS, IVL, KWR, NIPH, NLZOH, ONIRIS, RIVM, SLU, TNO, UAVR, UGR, VITO, WR).

A6.2.3 Mixture exposure and risk assessment

To initiate and organise the work to be performed for real-life mixture RA for prioritised mixtures of concern (i.e. pesticides, mycotoxins, and industrial chemicals such as PFASs and heavy metals), experts in kinetic modelling, grouping approaches, human biomonitoring and exposure assessment will be consulted. A statistical framework to assess co-occurrence of mixtures of concern (based on grouping and hazard characterisation) from HBM data will be established and applied to existing data collection from ten European countries being either national HBM or HBM4EU studies. Kinetic models needed to convert external to internal exposure or vice-versa will be optimised or newly developed for these mixtures. The epidemiological toxicological and kinetic experts will jointly write a report describing the co-occurrence patterns, recommend how grouping of the chemicals and mixtures of concern should be refined in and how the kinetic models will be optimised in year 2 (ANSES, AU, , BPI, DTU FOOD, EFSA, EHESP, FINBA, ICPS, CSIC, IISPV, IRFM, KI, LNS, MOH-CY/SGL, MU, NIJZ, NIPH, RIVM, SECO, STAMI, TTL, UBA, UG-PL, UGR, UNIPD, UU-IRAS, VITO, WR).

A6.2.4 Human health impact assessment and risk indicators

For a first selection of chemicals, health impact assessments, exposure data, and (dynamic, age-dependent) exposure-effect relationships will be assessed, as well as possibilities for exposure modelling for data-poor chemicals and for derivation of population-specific and population-wide exposures, spatio-temporal variations, and interindividual variations. Usability of health outcome data in European and national health data registries will be explored. From an inventory of methodologies, indicators, and frameworks for HIA and associated uncertainties, methodological improvements to be addressed in PARC will be prioritised. Year 1 will focus on reduction of uncertainty on exposure-effect associations, integrating in vitro, in vivo, and human data, mode of action, and effect biomarkers. Criteria for selection of case studies will be defined and design of case studies and risk and health impact indicators will be initiated (ANSES, AUTH, BPI, DTU FOOD, ENSP, FMUL, IISPV, KI, INSA, ISSeP, IVL, MU, NIJZ, NIPH, NLZOH, OI, RIVM, SCIENSANO, STAMI, UAVR, UBA, USI, UU-IRAS, VITO, WR).

The description of the WPs organised by activities, sub-activities and projects is available in the SRIA

(Annex); For this task, 8 projects have started year 1.

Task 6.3: Review of risk assessment methodology

Co-Leaders: SU (SE), BPI (EL)

Partners: UCL (UK), DGS (PT), EAA (AT), EAWAG (CH), TTL (FI), FOEN (CH), INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR), IRFM (IT), ISS (IT), UNIPD (IT), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), KI (SE), LSMU (LT), MUI (AT), REGIONH-GE (DK), RSU (LV), SCIENSANO (BE), STAMI (NO), SYKE (FI), UBA (DE), ULUND (SE), VUB (BE)

During year 1, case studies will be initiated related to two focus areas. The studies will be ongoing for two to five years depending on the topic and the contributions from partners. The reviews will include in silico (or computational) approaches. Under the focus area Substance and effect specific reviews, case studies will be performed to review substance-specific assessments to understand the differences and similarities, and subsequent implications, across legislations. The case studies will evaluate opportunities for improving particular aspects of the risk assessment of chemicals. This will include aspects such as data availability and/or data sharing mechanisms, methodologies for hazard and exposure assessment, and assessment of the effectiveness of potential mitigation measures considering impact on environment, safety of the consumer and at workplace with attention to vulnerable groups. Effect-specific assessments will also be reviewed, including assessment of skin sensitizers, use of non-animal methods in identification of priority substances such as endocrine disruptive as well as genotoxic and carcinogenic substances, and identification of substances causing developmental neurotoxicity. (EAWAG, FOEN, UBA, KI, TTL, LSMU, STAMI, RSU, REGIONH-GE, SU, VUB, ISS, UNIPD, UCL, SCIENSANO, IRFMN). Under the focus area Use of tools, criteria and methods, case studies will be performed to review the use of tools, criteria, and methods, to promote more transparent and harmonised evaluations of scientific information and data on chemicals. The application of hazard-based benchmarks, such as toxicological reference values and environmental quality standards will be reviewed across legislations, as well as limit values, assessments and mitigation measures related to occupational exposure. Reviews will also be performed on data availability related to exposure via the environment as well as comparisons to available monitoring data. The case studies will also cover issues such as availability and use of academic studies, hazard classes, criteria and test requirements, sources of uncertainty as well as methodological challenges in implementing uncertainty analysis in RA. (SYKE, ISSeP, SU, STAMI, UBA, JSI, UCL, TTL, KI, RSU, INERIS, MUI, ULUND, BPI, KI, UBA, INSERM, INERIS, EAA, IRFM, VUB).

A joint WP6 workshop with WP leaders, task leaders, partners and relevant stakeholders will be organised, in collaboration with WP2, to discuss activities, focusing on ongoing work and proposals for developments and new case studies to ensure the regulatory relevance. (KEMI, all WP6 partners).

The description of the WPs organised by activities, sub-activities and projects is available in the SRIA (Annex); For this task, 17 projects have started year 1.

Task 6.4: Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies

Co-leaders: AGES (AT), UNIBAS (CH)

Partners: ANSES (FR), INERIS (FR), OFB (FR), EAA (AT), AGES (AT), MU (CZ), AU (DK), REGIONH-GR (DK), UT (EE), EFSA (EU), SYKE (FI), Tukes (FI), UBA (DE), UFZ (DE), UKOLD (DE), USO (DE), Fraunhofer (DE), UI (IS), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), LSMU (LT), VUA (NL), NIPH (NO), STAMI (NO), NIVA (NO), NIOM (PL), IEP-NRI (PL), UG-PL (PL), INSA (PT), ENSP (PT), UC (PT), UAVR (PT), ISCIII (ES), UCLM (SI), UGOT (SE), ULUND (SE), RISE (SE), KEMI (SE), SLU (SE), AGROSCOPE (CH), EAWAG (CH), FOEN (CH), UNIBAS (CH), BUL (UK), UKCEH (UK), UOB (UK), BPI (EL)

A6.4.1. Develop regulatory relevant approaches and methods for chemical mixtures

A6.4.1 will complement the recent literature reviews on the current approaches related to mixtures with information on the current regulatory practices in order to identify the main gaps and needs and possible

ways forwards across regulations. We will initiate a survey for collecting data through interviews on current assessment practices and data availabilities. We will review the recent literature for NAM use in exposure data gap filling and initiate a set of case studies regarding mixture assessment provisions using NAMs across regulations. (AGES, REGIONH-GR, UBA, UFZ, UI, ISS, LSMU, STAMI, NIVA, NIOM, ENSP, UGOT, KEMI, EAWAG, BUL, UKCEH, BPI).

A6.4.2. Facilitate the regulatory acceptance and practical use of new methods

A6.4.2 will conduct a landscaping exercise to determine the current status of integration as well as risk assessors' needs from the use of NAMs (including computer-based approaches) across regulatory frameworks. A gaps & needs analysis will identify common scientific barriers for the use of NAMs. We will initiate the design of regulatory scenario-based case studies with the aim of developing evidence-based methods/approaches for NGRA that work in practice, based on established systematic approaches to ensure high quality, objectivity, transparency and reproducibility. (INERIS, EAA, UT, UBA, ISS, IRFM, NIPH, NIVA, UG-PL, INSA, ENSP, KEMI, UNIBAS, UOB, UKCEH, BPI).

A6.4.3. Developing information transfer structures and enforcement methodology for chemicals in articles to support the transition to a circular economy

A6.4.3 will promote a more effective and harmonized enforcement of legislation, support informed substitution of hazardous chemicals in products and materials and inform how sustainability assessments (e.g. LCA) can be achieved with respect to chemicals. It will start by review databases (e.g. chemical, product, patent and manufacturer databases) as well as analytical methods to initiate the development of a prioritisation framework for identification of hazardous chemicals in articles. (MU, Tukes, UBA, VUA, RISE, KEMI, UKCEH).

A6.4.4. Risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity

In A6.4.4 science-policy scoping workshops will clarify regulatory needs, develop a detailed activity plan as well as help to prioritise and coordinate research projects. We will identify and collect datasets in order i) to evaluate which factors are most crucial for RA for fate and effects and ii) to develop methods for comparing and ranking RA between substances. We will identify priority areas at local and regional level with a high interlink between agriculture management and biodiversity which will be used to develop case studies to quantify effects of PPP and other stressors (ANSES, OFB, AU, EFSA, SYKE, UBA, UFZ, UKOLD, UOS, Fraunhofer-IME, NIVA, IEP-NRI, UC, ISCIII, UCLM, ULUND, KEMI, SLU, AGROSCOPE, EAWAG, FOEN, UKCEH, UOB).

The description of the WPs organised by activities, sub-activities and projects is available in the SRIA (Annex); For this task, 11 projects have started year 1.

Deliverables:

N/A

Additional Deliverables

AD6.1 M10 Strategy document on IATAs for more complex endpoints

AD6.2 M12 Report on case studies for interim evaluation of IATAs

AD6.3 M12 Roadmap on aggregated exposure strategy through different living environments, sources and routes

AD6.4 M12 Inventory of PBK models for assessing the internal exposure through life

AD6.5 M12 Report describing co-occurrence probabilities of chemicals forming real-life mixtures of the selected HBM studies across Europe and overview of the kinetic and grouping aspects of prioritised mixtures

AD6.6 M12 Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC
 AD6.7 M12 Technical reports outlining the regulatory needs for ERA development areas
 AD6.8 M12 Technical report: mapping exercise assessing the status of integration and use of NAMs across sectorial frameworks

WP N°	WP7										Lead Beneficiary					VITO/UOB														
WP title	FAIR Data																													
Partner N°	1	1.1	1.6	1.10	3.9	4	4.6	5.2	6.1	8	9	15	15.2	20	24.3	25.1	25.2	25.4	25.4	25.5	25.7	26.4	27.2	31	34.5	35.2	35.12	36	49	59
Partner short name	ANSES	INSERM	INRS	BRGM	UNIVIE	VITO	ISSEP	EV-ILVO	IMROH	MU	UZIS	UBA	UFZ	ISS	UniLU	KWR	TNO	UL-LACDR	UL-LACDR	UU-IRAS	WR	NIVA	UG-PL	JSI	IISPV	KI	UU	AUTH	EFSA	UOB
PM/partner	27	3	1.50	8	3	30.25	12	2.10	2	59.40	0.90	4	8	3	6	1.18	4.43	10.10	10.10	12.50	0.54	5.50	4.10	17	30	6	8	8	1	16.40
Start	M1										End					M12														

Objectives

The main goal of WP7 is to support innovation and transparency in chemical Risk Assessment (RA) through improved exchange and re-use of data between different RA actors and disciplines, and through innovative data analytical approaches. The specific objectives of WP7 for year 1 are:

- Task 7.1: Developing the first version of the PARC FAIR Data Policy (PFDP) and Data Management Plan (DMP), with PARC scientists, stakeholders and the FAIR community, and starting with the implementation of FAIR awareness and skills within PARC *NB. FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable*)
- Task 7.2: Drafting overall landscape and FAIRness assessment of major databases, repositories, platforms relevant for PARC, and starting the development of solutions in first use cases
- Task 7.3: Performing scoping studies to investigate and select innovative approaches to optimise use and insights from FAIR data, and to assess uncertainty; identifying use cases for implementation and evaluation of selected approaches

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 7.1: FAIR Data policy and implementation

Co-leaders: TNO (NL), UOB (UK)

Partners: ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), VITO (BE), MU(CZ), UZIS (CZ), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), KWR (NL), UL-LACDR (NL), UU-IRAS (NL), NIVA (N), UG-PL (PL), JSI (SI), KI (SE), AUTH (EL)

The development of the PFDP will start (**TNO, all**). The policy will concern PARC and external (research) data and new methods. Existing data policies from the FAIR, regulatory and research communities will be retrieved. The PFDP will be drafted with WP2 and R&I WPs, facilitated by expert moderated workshops involving PARC and FAIR communities. Input on the PFDP from perspectives: RA agencies (**ANSES, UBA and MU**); human studies (epidemiology, biomonitoring) (**UU-IRAS, UBA, VITO, UZIS**); hazard and risk data modelling (**UG-PL, AUTH, ISS, TNO**); agrifood, geochemical, nanotoxicology (**BRGM,**

KI), ecological studies (**NIVA**) will be provided. A first overall version of the DMP will be drafted and delivered at M6. **All partners** will provide input to the DMP, which provides operationalisation of the PFDP, and integration of detailed R&I WPs specific DMPs for the data collected within these will be started.

The Train-The-Trainer (T3) model will be applied (**UOB + subcontractor**) to impart a curriculum based on Three-Point FAIRification framework (3PFF). PARC members, in particular appointed data stewards, will be trained as Fair Implementation Profiles (FIP)/Metadata for Machines workshop (M4M) facilitators, who can deliver these workshops on their own to PARC and coordinate the FAIRification during the project. The T3 curriculum and materials will be created, and T3 sessions and the first few FIP/M4M workshops will be delivered (**UOB + subcontractor**), with Trainees as observers “learning by doing”. PARC Trainees will phase-in as workshop facilitators, with **UOB** and the specialised subcontractor as advisors. A communication hub will be created (website, newsletter) (with WP2, WP3, WP9) fostering WP7 visibility for PARC researchers (**KWR and UL-LACDR**).

FAIR data use cases have been identified for Y1. For each of these, coordinating Use Case Working Groups (UCWG) will be established, with domain experts, stakeholders and (FAIR) data experts. The use cases will further be described below (T7.2, T7.3), and will be formalised into “PARC Project Templates”. Additional use cases for implementation in the first three years will be identified. The following procedure is foreseen: (1) new use cases will be drafted together with R&I WPs and T9.2 (that identifies gaps) (Task 7.2 and 7.3); (2) formalisation into “PARC Project Template” (Task 7.2 and 7.3); (3) verification of budget and technical feasibility; (4) submission to WP2 Task 2.1 for approval and check for compliance with stakeholder needs.

Task 7.2: Data libraries

Co-Leaders: MU (CZ), VITO (BE)

Partners: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), BRGM (FR), EFSA (EU), EV-ILVO (BE), IISPV (ES), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), KI (SE), MU (CZ), NIVA (NO), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), UBA (DE), UL-LACDR (NL), UNILU (LU), UNIVIE (AT), UOB (UK), UU (SE), UU-IRAS (NL), UZIS (CZ), KWR (NL)

A7.2.1 Inventory major transnational and national databases, repositories or platforms for chemicals RA

Starting from existing work, including work done in preparation of the Common Open Platform for Chemicals Safety Data (COPCSD), major existing and planned databases, repositories, platforms, that could provide relevant data to PARC and/or integrate PARC generated data in a FAIR and sustainable way, will be identified (MU). Each of them will be assessed against the FAIR requirements (using the FAIR implementation profile (FIP) approach) and the PFDP (UOB). Complementarity with the COPCSD will be assessed, and activities aligned with the COPCSD roadmap (including e.g., the work on increasing accessibility & utility of academic data). An operational distinction will be made between ‘standard’ data and ‘innovative data’. (MU/UOB, ANSES, EFSA, EV-ILVO, IISPV, ISS, ISSeP, JSI, KI, NIVA, UFZ, UNILU, UU-IRAS, UZIS, VITO)

A7.2.2 Implement a PARC FAIR data hub

Based on 7.2.1 and 7.2.4 (reference FIPs (rFIPs)), the requirements for a PARC FAIR data hub will be identified, i.e. its complementarity with other major initiatives, and identification of its main services and components, and translated in a draft architecture (to be delivered in year 2). This architecture will be cross-checked with WP2 and WP8 for integration with PARCopedia and with modelling toolboxes. The first year’s use cases will further help in identifying core data hub services, and assessing which are lacking

and need to be developed and implemented. (MU/VITO, AUTH, BRGM, EV-ILVO, JSI, NIVA, UFZ, UZIS, UL-LACDR, UNILU)

A7.2.3 Concrete solutions will further be elaborated and implemented based on specific use cases

Following data use cases will be initiated: human biomonitoring datasets with T4.1 (VITO), monitoring PFAS and endocrine disruptors with T4.2 (MU), databases of chemicals in articles with T6.4.3 (MU), and personal data for mixture exposure and RA with T6.2 (VITO). Domain experts (from R&I WPs) and WP7 data experts will describe additional use cases for the priority data needs of the WPs. Bottlenecks for data reuse and synergies with existing data platforms will be identified, and use case implementation plans will be drafted (VITO). (MU/VITO, ANSES, AUTH, BRGM, UOB, EV-ILVO, IISPV, ISS, ISSeP, JSI, KI, KWR, NIVA, UBA, UL-LACDR, UNILU, UU, UZIS)

Based on the major data initiatives (7.2.1), and on generic as well as community-specific FAIR enabling resources (data and metadata standards, semantic artefacts, Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), ...), rFIPs will be elaborated. Elaboration of FIPs for use in the identified use cases will be started, and needs for harmonisation will be defined. To facilitate future integration, convergence between COPCSD and its standards, and external data repositories and platforms will be assessed.

The description of the WPs organised by activities, sub-activities and projects is available in the SRIA (Annex); For this task, 2 projects have started year 1.

Task 7.3: Innovative analyses

Co-Leaders: UU-IRAS (NL), IISPV (ES)

Partners: ANSES (FR), AUTH, EV-ILVO (BE), IMROH (CR), INRS (FR), INSERM (FR), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), KI (SE), KWR (NL), MU (CZ), NIVA (NO), UL-LACDR (NL), UNIVIE (AT), UOB (UK), UU (SE), UZIS (CZ), VITO (BE), WR (NL)

A7.3.1 Identify and evaluate innovative methods for combined analyses of FAIR (heterogeneous) data

Inventories will be made of a) computational methods to maximise the reliability and usefulness of meta- and pooled analysis of heterogeneous exposure, toxicological or epidemiological data; b) statistically based methods (e.g. Bayesian) to combine data from epidemiological, biomarker, animal and in-vitro studies, e.g. for mixtures exposure and risk; and c) methods for privacy-preserving analysis of personal, sensitive data. Promising methods will be selected. For their implementation and evaluation use cases will be identified and started, based on inputs from WP4, 5, 6 and 8. (UU-IRAS, ANSES, AUTH, IISPV, IMROH, INRS, ISSeP, KI, MU, NIVA, UL-LACDR, UNIVIE, VITO, WR)

A7.3.2 Methods for uncertainty characterisation, propagation and quantification as a basis for harmonisation in RA

An inventory of methods for uncertainty characterisation, propagation and quantification will be made, and methods selected as a basis for harmonisation in RA. For their implementation and evaluation use cases will be identified for exposure, hazard, risk and health impact assessment, and IATAs, and started, in collaboration with WP4, 5, 6. (IISPV, ANSES, AUTH, ISSeP, JSI, KWR, NIVA, UL-LACDR, UU, UZIS, VITO, WR)

A7.3.3 Novel computational methods for integrating and extracting knowledge from non-structured data

(a) (UOB) an inventory will be made of ontology based approaches and frameworks for knowledge integration. Specifically in close relation to the use case on “databases of chemicals in articles with

T6.4.3”. These use cases will be further refined and prioritised to particular endpoints or chemical classes/imported products with interactions from WP5 and WP6.

(b) **(UU-IRAS)** Machine reading systems such as EURETOS, used for quick plausibility check of newly obtained evidence against the multitude and diversity of existing knowledge, will be evaluated on a use case (i.e. associations of environmental pollutants and biological responses, using omics data).

(AUTH, EV-ILVO, IISPV, INSERM, JSI, KI, MU, NIVA, UL-LACDR, UOB, VITO, WR)

A7.3.4 Identify additional needs in PARC for innovative analyses and promising evolutions in the data science landscape, and translate them in use cases for evaluation

A scoping exercise will be done to identify needs in PARC for innovative analyses on one hand, and promising innovative techniques on the other hand. This will include an inventory, state-of-the-art of promising ideas, and verification of their added value for regulatory RA. For promising ideas a project will be drafted in collaboration with the involved R&I WPs. (IISPV, ANSES, AUTH, ISSeP, WR)

A scoping exercise will be done to identify needs in PARC for innovative analyses on one hand, and promising innovative techniques on the other hand. This will include an inventory, state-of-the-art of promising ideas, and verification of their added value for regulatory RA. For promising ideas a project will be drafted in collaboration with the involved R&I WPs.

The description of the WPs organised by activities, sub-activities and projects is available in the SRIA (Annex); For this task, 1 project have started year 1.

Deliverables

D7.1 M6 Data Management Plan (DMP)

Additional Deliverables:

N/A

WP N°	WP8										Lead Beneficiary					AUTH/UNINA																															
WP title	Concepts and toolboxes																																														
Partner N°	1	1.1	1.2	1.4	3.3	4.6	8	10.1	10.2	12	13.1	14	15	20	20.3	20.4	20.6	24.3	25	25.4	25.5	25.6	25.7	25.8	26.3	26.4	26.5	27.2	28	29.2	31.3	34.5	34.6	35.4	35.8	35.9	35.10	35.11	35.12	36	36.1	36.3	36.4	43	51	52	54
Partner short name	ANSES	INSERM	INRAE	INERIS	BNN	ISSeP	MU	AU	DTU FOOD	EEA	SYKE	TTL	UBA	ISS	IRFM	IUSS	UNINA	UniLU	RIVM	UL-LACDR	UU-IRAS	VUA	WR	WU-TOX	NILU	NIVA	NMBU	UG-PL	FMUL	DGS	NIC	IISPV	INSST	ORU	IVL	SLV	SLU	UMU	UU	AUTH	EFET	NKUA	UOC	EMPA	BUL	Cefas-Defra	EA
PM/partner	2.54	9.50	0.90	1.50	1.50	2.50	20	2.30	1.50	2	2	3.75	8	1.70	14	15.80	3.25	2.70	19.15	1.35	11.45	0.50	16.18	0.86	4.50	0.80	0.50	4	1.45	2	2.75	7.95	1	9.20	6.75	0.25	16.05	10.25	7	63.50	3.40	7.25	12.70	12.50	1.75	0.75	0.85
Start	M1										End					M12																															

Objectives

The overall goal of WP8 is to support the development and consolidation of concepts and tools for Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) chemicals and materials and their operationalisation. The specific objectives of WP8 for year 1 are:

- Task 8.1: Increasing the knowledge on methods related to SSbD and providing an inventory of the methods and tools to put SSbD into practice, paving the way towards the operationalisation of the SSbD framework and criteria developed by the EC across the various users (industry, regulatory bodies and in academia)
- Task 8.2: Developing concepts and protocols for early warning monitoring tools, creating the prioritisation framework
- Task 8.3: Deriving the user requirements and the overarching conceptual model for the PARC integrative risk modelling network

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 8.1: Safe and sustainable by design (SSbD)

Co-Leaders: RIVM (NL), EMPA (CH), AUTH (EL)

Partners: INERIS (FR), BNN (AT), MU (CZ), DTU (DK), SYKE (FI), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), IUSS (IT), UNINA (IT), NILU (NO), NMBU (NO), UG-PL (PL), FMUL (PT), NIC (SI), INSST (ES), IVL (SE), BUL (UK), Cefas-Defra (UK)

During the first year of PARC activities, this task will describe state of the art of methods related to one or several aspects of SSbD (e.g. inventory of methods and tools and their requirements), will increase the knowledge level of these methods for people inside WP8, in PARC and outside of PARC. Collaborations will be sought with strategic partners inside and outside of PARC to enable the operationalisation of SSbD (e.g. collaborate and define shared activities with the Horizon Europe (HE) HE-RESILIENCE-2021-08-CSA EU network and other forthcoming calls under Horizon Europe). Areas of collaboration will include communication, how to engage and motivate future potential users of SSbD, identification and development of compliance/enforcement tools, and the identification of knowledge gaps and barriers to operationalise SSbD. The aim of these activities is to reach a common understanding of SSbD and to enable the practical applicability of SSbD in various sectors.

The following activities and products will be developed under the four areas of work:

A8.1.1. Translate EC SSbD criteria & methodology towards operationalisation

(RIVM, BNN, MU, DTU, SYKE, TTL, UBA, ISS, IUSS, UNINA, NILU, NIC, INSST, IVL, AUTH)

In collaboration with Task 2.1, a structured dialogue will be started with the EC to align to the EC timelines and activities in supporting and operationalising the SSbD concept and criteria that will be developed by the EC, while acting as a sounding board for EC ideas and reflecting on them, collecting first impressions on gaps, incentives and barriers for practical application of the criteria and methodology. In collaboration with WP3, strategically relevant networks outside PARC (e.g. the HE-RESILIENCE-2021-08-CSA EU network and other forthcoming calls under Horizon Europe) including their contact persons, scopes and activities will be identified to harness synergies.

A dedicated communication plan (as part of the PARC communication plan in Task 3.1) will be developed to ensure that ideas and needs of potential users will be heard, and that feedback on practical applicability will be communicated effectively. Moreover, a SSbD-PARC group with contact persons from each task of PARC will be formed to inform and to explore relevant issues about SSbD within PARC.

A8.1.2. Toolbox development

(AUTH, INSERM, BNN, SYKE, TTL, UBA, ISS, IUSS, UNINA, RIVM, NILU, NIC, INSST, IVL, Cefas-Defra)

Outline of the SSbD toolbox: an inventory and review of tools developed in the frame of existing initiatives on SbD (nano), Green Chemistry, Sustainable Products Initiative (Ecodesign Directive), Product Environmental Footprint (EU PEF), etc., and the definition of user requirements and functional specifications of the PARC SSbD toolbox will be the primary work of this task during year 1. The role and inclusion of FAIR data and their application for predictive toxicology, a prerequisite for SSbD, will be explored.

Content of the toolbox: the work will consist in translating criteria and methodology to information needs along the entire value chain. In this context, an inventory of tools in existing toolboxes and assessment of their applicability will be made to assist in the operationalisation of the SSbD concept in chemical management and innovation.

A8.1.3. Towards operationalisation: Use case & indicators

(UNINA, INERIS, BNN, MU, DTU, SYKE, TTL, UBA, ISS, IRFM, IUSS, RIVM, NILU, NMBU, UG-PL, FMUL, NIC, INSST, BUL, AUTH)

Identification of the most optimal set of parameters for selecting potential use cases to test the methodology developed by the EC and complement the use cases chosen by the EC.

Testing the applicability of the EC SSbD criteria and methodology will require a plan on how to engage relevant stakeholders in the value chain, in collaboration with e.g. the HE-RESILIENCE-2021-08-CSA EU network. This plan will be developed in collaboration with WP3, focusing on the barriers as well as incentives for implementation of different stakeholders that are involved in the use cases.

An initial inventory of relevant indicators to follow the progresses of sector applicability of the toolbox will be made. This inventory will be aligned to initiatives by the EC, including the indicator programme foreseen by EEA and in collaboration with task 3.2.

A8.1.4 Knowledge sharing & Education as key factors for efficient SSbD operationalisation

(RIVM, BNN, SYKE, TTL, UBA, IUSS, UNINA, NMBU, FMUL, NIC, INSST, AUTH)

Development of a structural process to share knowledge and information about operationalisation of SSbD with developers of innovative HA and RA tools within PARC and with potential users. Initial steps will be taken to work towards a module in the frame of PARCopedia (WP2). This module will amongst others include state of the art information about the toolbox and lessons learned from use cases. This will be done by informing the scientific community and relevant stakeholders about state-of-the-art, needs and developments of SSbD.

The description of the WPs organised by activities, sub-activities and projects is available in the SRIA (Annex); For this task, 1 project have started year 1.

Task 8.2: Scientific and technical basis for an Early warning system (EWS) on chemical risks

Co-Leaders: SLU (SE), INSERM (FR)

Partners: INRAE (FR), AU (DK), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), UniLU (LU), UU-IRAS (NL), VUA (NL), WR (NL), NILU (NO), NMBU (NO), UG-PL (PL), DGS (PT), NIC (SI), IISPV (ES), INSST (ES), ORU (SE), IVL (SE), SLV (SE), UMU (SE), EA (UK), AUTH (EL), EFET (EL), NKUA (EL), UOC (EL)

A8.2.1 EWS monitoring tools

(SLU, INRAE, AU, UBA, ISS, IRFM, UniLU, UU-IRAS, WR, NILU, NMBU, UG-PL, DGS, INSST, ORU, UMU, EA, AUTH, NKUA, UOC)

Standardised protocols for early warning monitoring tools will be designed (link with Tasks 4.2, 4.3, 8.1,

WP 9). Concepts and requirements of suspect/non-targeted/EDA-based tools will be defined for environmental (link with Task 4.2, 4.3) and human matrices (link with Tasks 4.1, 4.3). Concepts and protocols for metabolomics-based biomarkers will be defined (link with Task 4.1, WP5). Concepts and tools using machine learning and systems modelling and analysis will be defined (link with Tasks 4.2, 8.3, WP6)

A8.2.2: Identification framework

(SLU, AU, UBA, IRFM, UniLU, UU-IRAS, VUA, NMBU, UG-PL, INSST, ORU, UMU, EA, AUTH, EFET, NKUA)

Selection of databases with chemical structure and identifier information to develop a computational method for systematic identification and prioritisation of new substances (link with Tasks 8.1, 8.3, WP6). Environmental and human samples will be selected (link with Tasks 4.1, 4.2, 4.3) including archived samples for trend analysis. Conceptualisation of virtual EDA based on multivariate analysis-correlation as a future prioritisation tool (link with Tasks 4.2, 4.3, WP5).

A8.2.3: Validation of EWS in case-studies

(SLU, INSERM, AU, UBA, UU-IRAS, VUA, NILU, IISPV, INSST, ORU, SLV, EA, EFET, NKUA, UOC)

Identification of possible case studies that can be used for establishment of early warning monitoring tools and prioritisation framework for humans (link with Tasks 4.1, 4.3), environment (link with Tasks 4.2, 4.3), and products (link with Task 8.1, 6.2). Planning and selection of case studies for source tracing to identify potential sources of prioritised substances including drinking water, food, indoor air, products (link with Tasks 8.1, 4.2, 4.3).

A8.2.4: Computational framework to support EWS

(AUTH, AU, UBA, UniLU, UU-IRAS, UG-PL, ORU, IVL, UMU, EA, NKUA)

Establishing a network with agencies and regulators as well as related stakeholders outside PARC to identify relevant EWS initiatives to exchange information on the policy and scientific level. Stimulate an active interaction between researchers to harmonise data reporting of new substances, related also to the open chemical data platform to be put in place by the EC, in collaboration with WP7, based on the FAIR principle to make them accessible for researchers, regulators, policy and other stakeholders (e.g. NORMAN). Evaluation and collection of in silico systems and chemical and toxicological screening data for the development of a systematic scoring system to rank and prioritise substances using multicriteria decision analysis (link with WPs 4, 5, 6 and Task 8.3).

The description of the WPs organised by activities, sub-activities and projects is available in the SRIA (Annex); For this task, 1 project have started year 1.

Task 8.3 Integrative models

Co-Leaders: WR (NL), AUTH (EL)

Partners: ANSES (FR), INERIS (FR), ISSeP (BE), MU (CZ), DTU (DK), SYKE (FI), TTL (FI), IRFM (IT), IUSS (IT), UL-LACDR (NL), UU-IRAS (NL), WU-TOX (NL), NIVA (NO), NMBU (NO), NIC (SI), IISPV (ES), INSST (ES), UU (SE), UOC (EL)

In year 1, task 8.3 will focus on activities 1 and 2.

A8.3.1: Modelling network, model governance and user requirements

(AUTH, WR, ANSES, MU, DTU, SYKE, IUSS, UL-LACDR, UOC)

Stakeholders will be contacted through an online survey and in selected interviews to propose an overview of needs, regulatory user requirements and boundary conditions for relevant RA questions, in close collaboration with WPs 3, 4, 5 and 6, to decide on use cases that will be addressed in this task. Based on an inventory of existing or planned models across PARC, major stakeholders, such as European authorities

and RA agencies of EU MS will be consulted on major questions of risk modeling, such as which technical combination of models and tools will be developed in the PARC model network. In year 1, an inventory of existing front-end access platforms will be made, in relation to the user requirements defined in Activity 1. In the first year, an initial set of use cases will be defined (additional milestone AM 8.3.YR1-2).

A8.3.2: Designing and implementing the PARC model network

(WR, AUTH, ANSES, INSERM, INERIS, ISSeP, MU, DTU, SYKE, IRFM, IUSS, UL-LACDR, UU-IRAS, NIVA, IISPV, INSST, UU, UOC)

We will create a first draft of an overarching conceptual model to map models and platforms to user requirements and RA questions. We will implement the conceptual PARC model as an open-source dynamical system under version control, to allow continuous development and adaptation to regulatory needs to create web service connections between models and platforms in the area of the use cases. In the first year, a first version of the overarching model will be developed (AD 8.3. YR1-1). In addition, a report on the in-depth analysis of uncertainty aspects will be written. Starting from the use cases defined in Activity 8.3.1, participants in this activity will prepare to connect selected models and data platforms in the PARC model network by web services. In the first year, this will involve the following computational tools: MCRA, INTEGRA, USEtox, VEGAHUB, ConsExpo, PACEM, as well as kinetic and non-dietary models and tools for uncertainty assessment

A8.3.3: Application of the integrative model network in use cases

(AUTH, ANSES, DTU, SYKE, TTL, IRFM, UL-LACDR, WR, WU-TOX, IISPV, INSST)

In year 1, participants will start to organise data and available models for selected use cases of chemicals of concern and emerging chemical risks, under the guidance of the PARC model network governance board and in concert with the use cases prioritised in PARC. The use cases may also offer interesting insights regarding uncertainty under specific circumstances.

The description of the WPs organised by activities, sub-activities and projects is available in the SRIA (Annex); For this task, 1 project have started year 1.

Deliverables:

- D8.1 M12 Report on the conceptual design of the SSbD toolbox
- D8.2 M12 Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS
- D8.3 M12 Report on the conceptual design of the integrative tools

Additional Deliverables:

- AD8.1 M12 Concept and plan of effect-based monitoring of chemicals in the environment
- AD8.2 M12 First draft conceptual model describing models in the modular network and their connections

WP N°	WP9											Lead Beneficiary				ISCIII/MU								
WP title	Building infrastructural and human capacities																							
Partner N°	1	1.1	1.2	1.4	1.7	1.10	1.11	2	3.8	3.9	4.6	5	6.1	8	8.2	10.1	10.3	10.4	15	15.3	17	20.3	21	22
Partner short name	ANSES	INSERM	INRAE	INERIS	ONIRIS	BRGM	LNE	SpF	UMIT	UNIVIE	ISSeP	SCIENSANO	IMROH	MU	VSCHT	AU	REGIONH-RH	UCPH	UBA	IPA	NPHC	IRFM	RSU	NPHSL

PM/partner	7.28	3	2.14	2.10	1	3.80	5.10	3	2	7	4	5.88	1	55	3.50	4.64	2	1	2.50	5.35	3	1.50	0.22	15	
Partner N°	24	25.5	25.7	26	26.2	26.5	26.7	28	29	29.3	29.5	30	30.1	31	31.4	32	32.2	33	34	34.2	34.4	35.2	36	36.2	37
Partner short name	LNS	UU-IRAS	WR	NIPH	STAMI	NMBU	UNN	FMUL	INSA	ENSP	UAVR	SZU-SK	UK	JSI	ULFFA	NIJZ	NLZOH	CSIC	ISCIH	FISABIO	FNS	KI	AUTH	GCSL	BPI
PM/partner	8.50	5	6	1.90	5.38	10.30	0.74	4.50	34.43	4	2.40	4.50	1	3.16	1	6	0.10	13.49	33.53	2	5.40	2	3	2.95	6.20
Start	M1										End					M12									

Objectives

The overall goal of WP9 is to promote the further development of existing and new infrastructural and human capacities related to laboratory networks including reference laboratories and exposure monitoring networks. The specific objectives of WP9 for year 1 are:

- Task 9.1: i) Establishing the network of WP9 partners, contact points from other Work Packages (WPs), and expert groups, ii) identifying priority infrastructural needs through consultations with WPs 2-8, ii) finding consensus on the overall architecture of information catalogues, iii) landscaping and developing pilot information catalogues and networks for laboratories
- Task 9.2: i) Establishing the network of WP9 partners, contact points from other WPs, and expert groups, ii) identifying priority infrastructural needs through consultations with WPs 2-8, ii) finding consensus on the overall architecture of information catalogues, iii) landscaping and developing pilot information catalogues and networks for exposure monitoring networks
- Task 9.3: Harmonising Quality Assurance (QA)/Quality Control (QC) protocols/guidance for sampling, analysis and toxicity testing
- Task 9.4: Identifying existing training needs through interaction with WPs and a survey

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 9.1: Laboratory networking

Leader: ISCIH (ES)

Initial consultations with other WPs on the laboratory networking needs and priority areas and two to three online meetings dedicated to Human Bio-Monitoring (HBM) and environment networks/infrastructures will be organised (ISCIH/MU jointly with contact points from other WP).

Initial mapping of existing laboratory networks and reference laboratories will be initiated, and first inventories will be made available (NPHSL in collaboration with SZU-SK, ANSES, AU, BPI, BRGM, CSIC, FISABIO, FMUL, INERIS, INSA, IPA, LNE, MU, NIPH, SCIENSANO, STAMI, FNS, VSCHT, GCSL, RSU, UK). A preliminary shortlist of the networks which will need development promotion or support over next years will be prepared (FISABIO in collaboration with ANSES, INERIS, AU, BPI, BRGM, FMUL, INERIS, INSA, IPA, MU, NPHSL, LNS, NIPH, SCIENSANO, ISSeP, FNS, VSCHT, GCSL, NMBU) in cooperation with WP4. First strategies and tools to achieve the coordination and linkage of laboratory networks in PARC in the environmental (CSIC) and HBM (IPA) fields will be prepared in collaboration with ANSES, INERIS, BPI, BRGM, FMUL, INERIS, INSA, ONIRIS, MU, LNS, STAMI, ISSeP, FNS, VSCHT, GCSL, NMBU and the definition of the concept and architecture of the laboratory

network dashboard to be implemented over the next years will be established (ISCIH in collaboration with MU, BPI, GCSL, ANSES, LNS, NMBU, FMUL) in collaboration with WP2 and 3.

The description of the WPs organised by activities, sub-activities and projects is available in the SRIA (Annex); For this task, 1 project have started year 1.

Task 9.2: Building exposure monitoring capacities

Leader: MU (CZ)

The overall architecture for the catalogues to be developed in WP9 will be defined (MU in cooperation with WP 2, 3, 7, contact point from other WP s and from ANSES, AU, AUTH, GCSL, INSERM, NPHHC, RIVM, SpF, and UU-IRAS) and a dedicated on-line workshop (including the discussion on FAIRification principles and needs for catalogue development, in cooperation with WP7) will be organised. In addition, the catalogues on air monitoring (in cooperation with 4.2) and Human Biomonitoring/population studies/networks (in collaboration with 4.1) and on networks related to articles/indoors (in cooperation with 6.4.3) including the available sample and data collections in support of their further use in WPs 4-8, will be developed, and the initial inventories will be available by M12 (AU (domains: air, articles, indoor), CSIC (domain: air), ISCIH (domain: HBM), ISSeP (domains: air, articles, indoor), FMUL (domain: HBM), NPHSL (domain: air), with contributions from BPI, GCSL, IMROH, INSA, JSI, LNE, LNS, ONIRIS, STAMI, SCIENSANO, SZU-SK, ENSP, UU-IRAS, VSCHT). Inventories will refer to other initiatives at the european level including H2020 and Horizon Europe projects (such as EHEN, urban health cluster and indoor air cluster).

The description of the WPs organised by activities, sub-activities and projects is available in the SRIA (Annex); For this task, 1 project have started year 1.

Task 9.3: Joint activities – harmonisation

Leader: WR (NL)

The existing protocols and guidance documents on sampling (INRAE, LNS) and generic QA/QC in chemical analysis (LNE, UNIVIE), toxicity testing and toxicokinetic studies (WR) will be mapped and inventoried. The core group will be established with experts from WP4 (in particular 4.1.2, 4.2.4/5, 4.3.5), WP5, and WP6 and will meet during the 1st year. The priority setting resulting from their first meeting will define the scope of the following two ad-hoc group meetings. These activities will be performed in collaboration with ANSES, AU, BRGM, BPI, GCSL, CSIC, IPA, ISCIH, INERIS, INSA, JSI, MU, NIPH, NLZOH, NMBU, REGIONH-RH, SCIENSANO, STAMI, UBA, FNS, UCPH, UU-IRAS, UNN, VSCHT. Task 9.3 will also proactively investigate possible links with the European partnership on metrology.

The description of the WPs organised by activities, sub-activities and projects is available in the SRIA (Annex); For this task, 1 project have started year 1.

Task 9.4: Training

Leader: INSA (PT)

Identification (*via* interactions with other WPs through contact points and a survey) and reporting on the internal and external training needs (*NPHSL*) and available training opportunities and networks (*UAVR*) will be performed. An initial meeting will be held to specify the questions for the survey to be organised by WP2 in order to collect training needs, capacities, and opportunities available in the different member states/participating organisations. A follow-up meeting will take place to produce the compilation of training needs, capacities, and opportunities and to define the training timeline plan for PARC (*INSA*). In addition, the work to give support to local training organisers in PARC will start on year 1 (*NIJZ*). These activities will be carried out in collaboration with ANSES, BPI, BRGM, FNS, GCSL, CSIC, INRAE, IPA, IRFM, ISCIH, JSI, KI, RSU, LNE, LNS, MU, NMBU, ONIRIS, SCIENSANO, STAMI, ULFFA, UMIT, ENSP, VSCHT.

Deliverables:	
D9.1 M12	Initial laboratory catalogue and design of the network platform (dashboard) Y1
D9.2 M12	Catalogues on environmental and biomonitoring networks Y1
D9.3 M12	Report on Training events Y1
Additional Deliverables:	
N/A	

Table 2.3.b: AWP Set of Activities

Activity No	Activity Title	Lead Participant No	Short name of lead participant	Person - Months	Start Month	End month
1	Coordination and management	1	ANSES	215.19	1	12
2	A common science-policy agenda	3/12	EAA/EEA	219.41	1	12
3	Synergies, collaborations and awareness	29/36.2	INSA/GCSL	191.45	1	12
4	Monitoring and exposure	15/2	UBA/SpF	1250.11	1	12
5	Hazard Assessment	16/1	BfR/ANSES	1526,98	1	12
6	Innovation in regulatory risk assessment	25/35.7	RIVM/KEMI	1372.35	1	12
7	FAIR Data	4/59	VITO/UOB	294.91	1	12
8	Concepts and toolboxes	36/20.6	AUTH/UNIN A	322.08	1	12
9	Building infrastructural and human capacities	34/8	ISCIII/MU	308.49	1	12
TOTAL				5700.89		

Table 2.3.c: Additional Deliverables List

Deliverable N°	Deliverable name	Activity N°	Lead participant Short name	Type ²	Dissemination level ³	Delivery date	Description
AD4.1	Periodic report on available supporting materials for HBM studies	WP4 (4.1.1)	VITO	R	PU	M12	This report will provide an overview of supporting materials for general and occupational HBM surveys, such as (dynamic) informed consents, lifestyle and dietary exposure questionnaires, and SOPs for sample collection, preservation, and storage, developed in the first year of PARC building further on materials elaborated in HBM4EU.
AD4.2	Periodic report on analytical methods and measurements for exposure and effect biomarkers	WP4 (4.1.2)	ISCI	R	PU	M12	This report will provide an overview of analytical methods selected for measurement of exposure and effect biomarkers in the general and occupational HBM surveys, based on QA/QC criteria that will be defined in the first year of PARC. Measurement results will not yet be available to be included in this first periodic report.
AD4.3	Derivation of HBM-GVs (one dossier per substance; 3-4 substances)	WP4 (4.1.3)	UBA	R	PU	M12	This deliverable will provide the derivation of the first HBM-GV in PARC. It will comprise relevant toxicological and epidemiological information for the first chosen substance in a summarized form with respective references. The point of departure, the further derivation of the HBM-GV(s) and its/their proper

² Indicate the type of each Deliverable using one of the following codes: R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports); DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs; DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.; OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

³ Indicate the dissemination level of each Deliverable using one of the following codes: PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web; CO = Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement (Consortium only); CI = Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.

							application as well as the level of confidence of the derived value(s) will be presented and justified in detail.
AD4.4	Procedures for agreement on transparent use of existing data, access to samples and involvement of external laboratories	WP4 (4.2.1)	INERIS, AU	R	PU	M12	The deliverables will cover the general terms of systematic sample exchange (e.g. who to approach how and when, time lines, data ownership), protocols for practical sample handling (sub-sampling, transport etc.), provision of metadata.
AD4.5	Technical specifications of the study (project design, hypothesis and research question as well as analytical procedures including QA/QC and data flows)	WP4 (4.2.2)	INERIS, AU	DEM	PU	M12	The technical specifications will cover the monitoring project design, hypothesis and research questions as well as analytical procedures including QA/QC and data flows.
AD4.6	Concept paper regarding common definitions and short to medium term support to policy objectives of innovative (self-) sampling, suspect screening and NTS/EDA approaches	WP4 (4.3.3)	INRAE, VUA	R	PU	M12	Global collective definition and prioritisation of main concepts, approaches and objectives associated to innovative methods undertaken in task 4.3 (inventories, selection/prioritisation, shared knowledge and visions among environmental-food-HBM communities).
AD5.1	Report on the workshop organised with national and EU agencies and stakeholders on the bisphenol A alternatives of-concern	WP5	BPI, MU	R	PU	M9	Workshop report containing a list of prioritised substances and tests applied in yr1&2 of PARC
AD5.2	Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted	WP5	ANSES, BfR	R	PU	M12	Report with testing proposal for one or two prioritized substances and a binary mixture in an EOGRT study to be conducted in year two of PARC

AD5.3	List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints	WP5	DTU, VUB	R	PU	M12	List of assays from 5.2 on the endpoints non-genotoxic carc, metabolic disruption, endocrine disruption (thyroid), (D)NT and immunotoxicity
AD5.4	Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes	WP5	UL-LADR, SCIENSANO	R	PU	M12	Inventory of omics data available at partners or via CTD for the above mentioned endpoints.
AD5.5	Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC	WP5	Inserm	R	PU	M12	List with an inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, associated NAMs for genotoxicity, endocrine toxicity and liver toxicity, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC; jointly with WP6, lead WP5
AD5.6	Mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints	WP5	Inserm	R	PU	M12	List with a mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints
AD5.7	Draft strategy for the development of bioinformatics tools that are needed to link omics data and other mechanistic information to human relevant disease mechanisms	WP5	UL-LADR, SCIENSANO	R	PU	M12	Report with a draft strategy for the development of bioinformatics tools that are needed to link omics data and other mechanistic information to human relevant disease mechanisms
AD5.8	Inventory of available in PBTK models, identification of knowledge gaps regarding route	WP5	ITEM	R	PU	M12	List with an inventory of available in PBTK models, identification of knowledge gaps regarding route specific ADME processes and setting

	specific ADME processes and setting up of the framework for the integration of <i>in vitro</i> ADME data into PBTK models						up of the framework for the integration of <i>in vitro</i> ADME data into PBTK models, jointly with WP6, lead WP6
AD6.1	Strategy document on IATAs for more complex endpoints	WP6 (6.1.1)	SCIENSANO	R	PU	M10	Strategy document describing how IATAs for more complex endpoints will be developed in the context of PARC
AD6.2	Report on the objectives and design of three case studies starting in year 1 for interim evaluation of IATAs	WP6 (6.1.2)	UL-LACDR	R	PU	M12	Report describing the objectives and design of case studies aimed at the interim evaluation of IATAs for genotoxicity, endocrine toxicity and liver toxicity
AD6.3	Roadmap on aggregated exposure strategy through different living environments, sources and routes	WP6 (6.2.1)	UNISANTE and ANSES	R	PU	M12	Roadmap on aggregated exposure strategy through different living environments, sources and routes
AD6.4	Inventory of PBK models for assessing the internal exposure through life	WP6 (6.2.2)	INERIS and AUTH	R	PU	M12	Report providing an inventory of PBK models currently available to assessing internal exposure during the lifecourse taking into account age-dependent variation in organ physiology, metabolism and clearance from in utero to end of life
AD6.5	Report describing co-occurrence probabilities of chemicals forming real-life mixtures of the selected HBM studies across Europe and overview of the kinetic and grouping aspects of prioritised	WP6 (6.2.3)	RIVM and ANSES	R	PU	M12	Report describing co-occurrence probabilities of chemicals forming real-life mixtures of the selected HBM studies across Europe and overview of the kinetic and grouping aspects of prioritised mixtures

	mixtures						
AD6.6	Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC	WP6 (6.2.4)	VITO and UU-IRAS	R	PU	M12	Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC
AD6.7	Technical report outlining the regulatory needs for ERA development areas	WP 6 (6.4.4)	UBA, KemI, FOEN	R	PU	M12	Technical reports outlining the regulatory needs for ERA development areas
AD6.8	Technical report: mapping exercise assessing the status of integration and use of NAMs across sectorial frameworks	WP6 (6.4.2)	UNIBAS	R	PU	M12	Report describing the outcome of mapping exercise (surveys) assessing the status of integration and use of NAMs across sectorial frameworks
AD8.1	Concept and plan of effect-based monitoring of chemicals in the environment	WP8	SLU	R	PU	M12	This report will describe the basic concept and methodological plan for large-scale development of effect-based monitoring of environmental chemicals. This will act as a fundamental element of the early warning system to be developed by task 8.2.
AD8.2	First draft conceptual model describing models in the modular network and their connections	WP8	WU-TOX	R	PU	M12	This deliverable will report on the first draft conceptual model of the integrative modeling network envisaged in task 8.3. The models available to the network will be described and their input/output characteristics and the respective interconnections will be laid out. This deliverable will provide the basis of the technical blueprint for downstream development of the integrative modeling network constellation of PARC.

2.2.a Participation in Annual Work Programme activities

The tables below provide a detailed description of the Beneficiaries involved in the AWP, of their AEs and the tasks performed by each entity. As PARC will not implement external calls, no partner envisages the provision of financial support to third parties. Associated partners are also described in separated tables, as these partners are not specifically linked to a participant.

<p>1- AGENCE NATIONALE DE LA SECURITE SANITAIRE DE L'ALIMENTATION DE L'ENVIRONNEMENT ET DU TRAVAIL, FRANCE (ANSES) – PIC : 983552356</p> <p>During the first year, but also the whole Partnership duration, ANSES will be in charge of the PARC coordination and will lead WP1. In WP2, ANSES will also contribute in the priority-setting task and sustainability task. In WP4, ANSES teams working in the field of analytical development will be involved in Task 4.2 for some analytical work to support the preparation of the monitoring campaigns in close relation with the preparation of food diet studies and the statistical analysis of existing data. In Task 4.3, they will contribute in the description and prioritisation of main approaches and objectives associated to innovative methods and on the development of an open access workflow for data processing and annotation of HRMS. Based on their experience in reference activities, they will contribute in the elaboration of a consensual inventory of method performance and QA/QC criteria. ANSES will lead WP5 with BfR and in T5.2a, ANSES will contribute in the organisation and planning through the selection of test items and contribution to the design of studies using High Content Analysis. ANSES scientists will contribute in the core groups about PBTk based on their experience in <i>in vitro</i> tests and <i>In vitro-In vivo</i> extrapolation. In WP6, ANSES will lead with VITO the Task 6.2 on integrative exposure and risk assessment and will contribute in the different activities planned. ANSES will collaborate in WP7 (FAIR data) for the implementation a FAIR data policy and for the elaboration of the DMP. ANSES will work on the mapping of data libraries (T7.2) and will contribute in the implementation of innovative analyses (T7.3). In WP8, ANSES will be associated to the Task 8.3 about the development of integrative models. In WP9, ANSES will contribute in the development of catalogues as sources of information.</p>	
Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	Y
- CNRS, an affiliated entity of ANSES, will subcontract for a budget of 12 k€. The subcontracting concerns RNA sequencing (9 samples with 600 €/sample ie 60 million read 75bp Illumina) and methylseq (10 samples 660€/sample).	
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
<p>1.1 INSERM – PIC 999997833 will be implicated in the PARC project either as Task co-leaders or partners:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UMRS-1124 will contribute to WP5.2a in two activities: in NGTXC and immunotoxicology (as activity leader). For NGTXC activity, the work will be made in tight relation with UMR1085. It will analyse the modifications of cell properties leading to migration or invasion processes by real-time analyses using lab set-up. It aims at identify and characterise biomarkers likely linked with genomic or epigenetic disruption after exposure. For immunotoxicity, UMRS-1124 will participate in the subproject 2: immunosuppression and response to vaccination by using several <i>in vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> model (influenza response modification, cytokine response...). Part of this activity will also be made by UMR 996 taking advantage of its expertise in skin sensitivity for immunotoxic response. Also a study in humans assessing the response to COVID-19 vaccination is currently foreseen. • UMRS-1124 will lead and contribute to T5.3.2 (in collaboration with UMR 1085 and U1133) and T6.1.1, T6.1.2, T7.3.3, T8.2.2 and T8.3 for bio-informatics and systems toxicology activities. In these tasks their expertise in systems biology, network science and text- and data-mining will be used to develop AOPs, AONs, IATAs and early warning systems. For example, in T5.3.2, during year 1, they will continue to develop an in house tool (AOP-helpFinder, initiated within HBM4EU) that allows to automatically explore the literature, with the aim to construct and complete AOPs. This 	

work will be carried out in close collaboration with U1133 (Paris) which will also contribute to T5.3, T6.1 and T8.2. UMR 1124 will also act as partner in T6.3 for evaluation of methods for ED assessments.

- JRU 1211 will contribute to T5.2a in the Development and assembly of a functional/behavioral (developmental) neurotoxicity test battery in zebrafish early development stage.
- U1194 will contribute to T5.2a to characterise by biochemical, cellular and in silico methods the interactions between bisphenols and their analogues with the nuclear receptors using well-characterised and recognised homemade in vitro tests.
- UMR1085 will contribute to T2.3 for sustainability activity and WP9 as contact. In WP5, it will contribute to the task 5.2. related to new innovative methodologies for their potential to assess epigenicity and transgenerational effects. The first year will also be dedicated to meeting, experimental design and BRB-seq experiments in collaboration with DTU (DK). It will also contribute to quantitative system toxicology (task 5.3.), first in the development of AOP based on system biology (T. 5.3.2, see above UMR-S 1124), then, in the characterisation of the impact and predictivity of in vitro ADME parameters for PBPK modeling by studying pollutants effects towards activities of main regulatory transporters (ABC and SLC) for PBPK modeling (T5.3.4) ; and finally, in the integration of multi-omics data and other relevant datasets by implementing bio-informatics tools, to improve knowledge on human disease mechanisms (T.5.3.3.).

1.2 INRAE – PIC 999993274: Under WP4 INRAE will lead task 4.3 on innovative methods, and contribute to task 4.1 and task 4.2 with regard to environmental, food and human monitoring. In WP5, INRAE will contribute to close major data gaps of concern as regards human and environmental health, for PARC selected priority substances, with a focus on metabolic events and toxicokinetics. In parallel, INRAE will lead the development of powerful innovative methods and tools for the determination of non-genotoxic carcinogen chemical potential. Under WP6, INRAE will contribute to task 6.2 with regard to full life exposure modeling. INRAE will also contribute to WP9 with regard to QA/QC and reference laboratory network aspects.

1.3 CEA – PIC 999993274: The involvement of the CEA, and more particularly of the LEMM, in the first year of the PARC project is in the continuity of the work carried out in the context of the HBM4EU project: in particular for the development and application of strategies of suspect screening and non-targeted profiling of human matrices for the identification of exposure markers (in particular of emerging concern) more specifically related to perinatal exposure (e.g. placenta, milk, etc.).

These developments include sample preparation, LC-HRMS metabolic profile acquisition of human samples, processing of the data, and annotation/identification of significant signals through spectral databases matching.

This falls within the scope of activities 4.3.1, 4.3.3 and 4.3.4 proposed for the work plan of WP4 task 4.3, and more specifically within the project on "Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based / EDA screening methods for exploring human perinatal exposure to chemicals of emerging concern".

1.4 INERIS – PIC 999958063: In WP4 INERIS will lead with Aarhus University Task 4.2. Here, based on their long-standing experience in the organisation of large exploratory monitoring campaigns on contaminants of emerging concern and coordination of the NORMAN network (www.norman-netowrk.net), INERIS will participate as a key contributor in the review and analysis of existing monitoring data and in the design of the monitoring studies planned for the first year in T4.2 (focus on endocrine disruptors), including the preparatory process for long-term selection of chemicals/matrices/endpoints deserving priority attention for the development of further monitoring projects in PARC. Thanks to their analytical skills and instrumental capabilities in chemical analysis and

effect-based methods, INERIS will also contribute to the development of innovative approaches (Task 4.3) for implementation of bioassays and EDA approaches to monitor chemical contaminants in environmental matrices with a specific focus on endocrine disruptors.

In WP5, INERIS will assess the estrogenic activity of BPA alternatives in transgenic *cyp19a1b*-GFP eleutheroembryos (Task 5.1), will assess BPA alternatives on zebrafish behavioural assays (Task 5.2) and will develop PBPK/TD models for bisphenols in fish by analysing new and in-house data (Task 5.2). In Task 5.3, INERIS will participate in the core group on PBPK modeling and will start new in vitro experiments for predicting absorption of chemicals by inhalation.

In WP6.2, INERIS will lead the activity Exposure through life, will review the existing PBPK models for the sensitive populations, and will participate in the planned projects on the development of PBPK models and on risk assessment of chemical mixtures. INERIS will contribute on IATA development related to ED and DNT (6.1), and to CS17 (6.4.1) on the use of nonstandard studies for ED assessment. INERIS will lead CS04 (6.4.1) for review and improvement of consistency of approaches used for secondary poisoning assessment. In Task 6.4, INERIS will also contribute to the implementation and delivery of the landscaping exercise aimed at interviewing regulators in France and across Europe about their use and needs in terms of computer-assisted decision making.

In WP8, INERIS will start the implementation of PBPK models in the modelling platforms. In WP8, INERIS will participate to the elaboration of the framework for defining and assessing the concept of safe-by-design chemicals, especially from the environmental economics viewpoint.

In WP9 INERIS will provide expertise as national reference laboratory in the QA/QC Group (QA/QC concept) to support the design of the planned monitoring projects in T4.2 and the definition of criteria for laboratory selection.

1.5 CNRS – PIC 999997930: Two of the CNRS research laboratories are involved in PARC:

- The CNRS research team UMR7221, Physiologie moléculaire et adaptation is a Joint Research Unit between CNRS and MNHN.
- The CNRS research team “Neuroplasticity of Reproductive Behaviors” is part of the Joint Research Unit UMR8246, Neurosciences Paris-Seine, between CNRS, Sorbonne Université and Inserm.

During year 1:

- UMR7221 will be working on the task 5.2. They will use an OECD-validated assay (XETA TG248) to test thyroid potential of prioritised chemicals that affect neuro-endocrine development. They will test the identified compounds and compare DNA methylation of tadpoles after exposure to these EDCs.
- UMR 8246 Neuroscience Paris Seine will work on the proposed project in Task5.1a on “Neurodevelopmental effects of exposure to BPA alternatives” using a relevant human neuronal in vitro model.

1.6 INRS – PIC 998626835:

In Task 4.1, INRS teams will contribute in the development and optimisation of the design (study plan, SOPs, questionnaire, ethics aspect, data analysis...) of dedicated aligned studies at workplaces. In addition, INRS will participate to the feasibility study to evaluate occupational exposure in general survey. INRS will be involved in the definition of the general criteria to be applied in the evaluation for selecting exposure biomarkers and analytical methods for the PARC prioritised substances and in the further evaluation of the effect marker data collected within HBM4EU occupational studies. INRS will work in planning and in carrying out the statistical analysis for data generated earlier within HBM4EU occupational studies and Task 4.1 of PARC. In Task 4.3, INRS will contribute in elaborating work plan for pilot studies on innovative sampling methods, in establishing a common strategic workplan related to non-targeted screening approach and in elaborating an inventory of method performance and QA/QC criteria. In Task 5.1, INRS scientists will study endocrine disruptive potential of selected compounds. In Task 6.2, INRS will contribute to activities planned on the inventory of available data to perform aggregate exposure studies in workers and on modelling occupational exposure by defining a minimal corpus of information and specific case studies for workers. INRS will work in Task 7.3 on implementing

innovative approaches for the analysis of heterogeneous data.

1.7 ONIRIS – PIC 986014022: Oniris (Ecole Nationale Vétérinaire, Agroalimentaire et de l'Alimentation Nantes Atlantique) will be involved during year 1 of the project in WP4 (T4.1.2, T4.2.3, T4.2.4, T4.3.3 and T4.3.4), WP6 (T6.2.2) and WP9 (T9.1.1, T9.2.1, T9.4). In WP4, Oniris' know-how together with its high level mass spectrometric based analytical platform dedicated to the robust characterisation of the contamination of food and human matrices with emerging chemical contaminants of interest (PFAS, EDCs) will be fully mobilised. It will also involve developing innovative analytical approaches (suspect screening, non-target screening) for a broader characterisation of the chemical exposome. In WP6, Oniris will host a PhD student which research will focus on the estimation of lifetime dietary exposure to mixtures. In WP9, Oniris will be involved in the construction of the training offer with a view to disseminating the knowledge produced; it will also contribute to the structuring of a network of laboratories by sharing its thirty-year experience in the field of food safety.

1.8 IRSN – PIC: 999480726: During year 1, IRSN will contribute to WP5 (activity 5.3.2) for the building of new AOPs on neurological effects and neurodevelopment. IRSN will also contribute to Task 6.1. on methodological aspects of AOP development for genotoxicity (activity 6.1.1) and on the relevance of IATAs for human risk assessments (activity 6.1.2).

1.9 OFB – PIC 894000307: OFB will be involved in several tasks and activities of PARC WP 4 and 6, through mobilising a team of 5 experts in environmental chemistry and ecotoxicology. More specifically for this first year, OFB will focus its efforts in assisting WP4.2 at designing the targeted PARC case study on endocrine disruptors monitoring, in line with its involvement in the national strategy on the knowledge development for these compounds. OFB also intends to develop synergies through WP4.3 on the topic of performing suspect screening on sentinel species (terrestrial and aquatic biota samples to which OFB owns access), with specific interest for endocrine disruptor pesticides. Finally OFB intends to devote half of its first year PARC time to contribute to one project of the WP 6.4.4 activity, whose aim is to promote landscape based ERA, integrating landscape structures and more realistic exposures routes into the current risk assessment methods to protect biodiversity. OFB will contribute to establish linkage between WP4.2/4.3 and WP6.4.4 to meet the goal of an effective feed-back mechanism between environmental monitoring and pesticides risk assessment towards biodiversity.

1.10 BRGM – PIC 999993662:

During the first year, BRGM will be involved in WP 4.2, 4.3, 7.1, 7.2, 9.1, 9.3, 9.4

In WP4, BRGM teams will be involved in Task 4.2 to support the preparation of the monitoring campaigns for the two selected case studies i.e. PFAS and Endocrine Disruptors Compounds. The team will bring its analytical expertise on water matrix and more particularly on groundwater but also on monitoring and knowledge of substances properties. In Task 4.3, BRGM will contribute to suspect and non-targeted screening approaches consideration for environmental monitoring and will contribute in the elaboration of a consensual inventory of method performance and QA/QC criteria for HRMS.

In WP7, BRGM team involved in task 7.1 will contribute to the FAIR data policy for PARC and participate to the identification of cases. BRGM will work on PARC FAIR data platform, harmonization and standards and on targeted solutions for FAIR data (T7.2.).

In WP9, BRGM will contribute in the development of catalogue of laboratory networks in environmental monitoring (T9.1), in the inventory of existing methods and guidance on sampling (notably for water) and QA/QC criteria for chemical methods in environmental monitoring (T9.3) and the identification of needs for training (T9.4).

1.11 LNE – PIC 998801144LNE will take part in WP4 & 9 activities aiming at the harmonisation of methods and measurements and the development of measurement infrastructure to sustain risk

assessments with high level data quality.

1.12 CSTB – PIC 999580151: (Centre scientifique et technique du bâtiment) will contribute to two tasks: Task 4.2 and Task 6.2.1.

Within Task 4.2, CSTB will contribute to the development of the prioritisation scheme and will share the ranking tools developed for prioritising substances of interest in the indoor (non-occupational) environments within the French IAQ Observatory, a long-term monitoring programme in place since 2001 (Task 4.2.1). The possibility to use the data and available samples from the IAQ Observatory will be shared with the partners (Task 4.2.2). CSTB will contribute to the design of the case-study for sampling and analysis QA/QC, data flow, data cleaning and data exploitation (Tasks 4.2.3 to 4.2.5). Regarding Task 6.2.1, CSTB will contribute to the selection of substances of interest for the development of the case studies addressing aggregate exposure of the general population, with a focus on substances present in indoor environments (Task 6.2.1.1). The models developed by CSTB to assess general population exposure to indoor substances will be shared and integrated in the review of existing models performed in Task 6.2.1.2. Interoperability with the other models will be analysed. CSTB will contribute to the identification of data gaps in the existing models and the way to fill in these gaps. On this basis, CSTB will contribute to the development of source-to-dose models for the general population (Task 6.2.1.3), particularly regarding indoor exposure routes, i.e. inhalation of indoor air, ingestion of settled dust, dermal exposure to gaseous substances in indoor air. Lastly, within Task 6.2.1.5, CSTB will participate to exposure modeling for the general population including the uncertainties characterisation.

1.13 EHESP – PIC 998161429: In the WP1 of PARC, EHESP will co-lead the task related to ethics frameworks (T.1.4.) and will contribute to the construction and the organisation of the process that will ensure the monitoring of the PARC actions with regard to ethical considerations during their conception. EHESP team will also use its expertise in analytical chemistry to contribute to WP4 related to human biomonitoring (tasks 4.1. and 4.3). In task 4.1., EHESP will work on improving and harmonising conventional analytical methods used in biomonitoring (e.g. implementation of QA-QC activities). EHESP will also provide expertise in data analysis for linking exposures to environmental chemicals, effect biomarkers and health outcomes. In task 4.3, EHESP will contribute to implement innovative non-targeted methods in human biomonitoring to characterise human exposure to chemical mixtures more comprehensively.

Finally, EHESP will contribute to the WP6, task 6.2. regarding chemical mixture risk assessment. During the first year, EHESP will participate to the discussions allowing to prepare the next project on chemical mixture (later years).

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	Y
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The salary of the researchers employed by MNHN and Sorbonne Université involved in PARC will be budgeted as in-kind contribution provided by third parties to CNRS (AE of ANSES) - The salary of the researchers employed by Université de Paris, Université de Paris Saclay, Université de Bordeaux, Université de Montpellier, Université de Rennes 1 will be budgeted as in-kind contribution provided by third parties to INSERM (AE of ANSES) 	

2- AGENCE NATIONALE DE SANTE PUBLIQUE, FRANCE (SpF) – PIC: 917843489

National experience in coordinating biomonitoring programme as well as experience in RA will be transferred to PARC. SpF will be contributing as work package (WP) co-leader and activity lead within WP4 - monitoring and exposure, leading alongside UBA activities addressing the gaps that remain in our knowledge of chemicals to which humans and the environment are exposed. Building further on the HBM4EU legacy, SpF will:

- Participate under HBM activities (Task 4.1.1), in the preparation of the design, planning, and implementation of HBM surveys.

- Undertake the development of standardised materials to support and facilitate HBM surveys targeting the general population, vulnerable and occupationally exposed populations. This includes developing harmonised questionnaires targeted to specific groups and exposure scenarios and guidelines for harmonised collection of health outcomes information.

Within T4.1.3, Sp France will initiate activities to elaborate the roadmap to evaluate the links between selected chemical exposures and health concerns and explore the possibilities to integrate a systematic collection of health measurements, disease, and nutritional data in HBM surveys (T4.1.3c). The preliminary work will include identifying issues related to the linkage of HBM, health examination, occupational and dietary surveys.

SpF promotes the implementation of biomonitoring data in RA, which allows for the identification of the determinants of exposure for both environment and food regulation. As such, in the first year of PARC, within T4.1.2, SpF will participate in the coordination of exposure and effect biomarkers analysis in HBM studies and the implementation of innovative tools and methods in selected studies to improve sampling strategies and identify emerging chemicals of concern (T4.1.2 and T4.3).

As the leader of the French biomonitoring programme, SpF structures the French network of expertise in the field of biomonitoring. In PARC, SpF appointed as National Hub Contact Point, will coordinate within WP2 (T2.3) in the first year and throughout the Partnership, the liaison between the French ministries, research entities, stakeholders, and EU hub and agencies.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

3- UMWELTBUNDESAMT GESELLSCHAFT MIT BESCHRANKTER HAFTUNG, AUSTRIA (EAA) – PIC: 999452014

EAA is WP2 co- lead and therefore responsible of the performance of WP2 tasks, coordination of the work, participation in the MB meetings as well as GS meetings, participation in the task meetings and performing the respective work. EAA is further responsible for task 3.1.a the organisation of the stakeholder forum. During the first year the PARC stakeholder forum will be established and way of working (partners and stakeholders) will be developed. Within WP4.1 EAA will participate in the preparation of a survey in children. With its long standing regulatory expertise EAA will also participate in WP6.3 and 6.4. An EAA expert has further outstanding experience in fair data and will therefore contribute to WP7.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	Y
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y

3.1 AGES – PIC 998254743: Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES) will (co)-lead the task 6.4 “Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies” by members of the Department Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment. AGES will further contribute to WP3 by members of the Department Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment at AGES with the implementation of

questionnaires and evaluation supporting the establishment of the Stakeholder Forum.

3.2 AIT - PIC 999584128: Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT) will contribute with its expertise especially in biological barriers such as the blood-brain barrier and the blood-saliva barrier and their interactions with its microenvironments to WP5.1a and WP5.2.a.”

3.3 BNN – PIC 966278305: The BioNanoNet Forschungsgesellschaft mbH (BNN) will contribute with their core-expertise in the safety-by-design concept and sustainability aspects to WP8.1 – concepts and toolboxes.

3.4 MUI – PIC 999855437: Medical University of Innsbruck (MUI). The Core Facility Metabolomics will provide their long- standing expertise and state-of-the-art technologies for the qualitative and quantitative analysis of small bioorganic molecules and non target analyses and will contribute to 4.1.2 and various aspects within 4.3. The Biochemical Immunotoxicology Group will contribute with their substantial expertise in the fields of immune- and respiratory toxicology to 5.1a , 5.2a and 5.3.a. MUI will also contribute to WP 6.1 with a systematic, deep uncertainty analysis of current genotoxicity TGs and IATAs as a benchmark for a NAM based IATA and to WP 6.3.

3.5 MUW – PIC 999989976: Medizinische Universitaet Wien (MUW) will contribute to WP4.1.1a in the development of (food frequency) questionnaires as well as in the update of SOPs for sample collection, preservation and storage (biobanking) and collection of health outcome data.

3.6 UG-AT – PIC 999873188: University of Graz (UG-AT). The TESLA group of the University of Graz will contribute with their expertise in novel analytical methodologies based on high end mass spectrometry and development of affordable methods and even field methods for specific toxic elemental compounds which occur as ultra-trace concentrations to WP4.3.

3.7 UIBK – PIC 999869114: Universitaet Innsbruck (UIBK) will be involved in WP5, Tasks 5.2 and 5.3 and develop new assays to detect disruption of ED responsive pathways.

3.8 UMIT – PIC 999898408: Private University for Health Sciences, Medical Informations und Technology (UMIT). The Department of Public Health, Health Services Research and Health Technology Assessment of UMIT will contribute with its expertise in developing and applying interdisciplinary methods to guide the comprehensive, systematic and practice-oriented assessment of measures and procedures in public health and medicine and specifically their expertise in dissemination and training activities to WP3.2 and WP9.4.

3.9 UNIVIE – PIC 999866883: University of Vienna (UNIVIE) offers expertise and resources in analytical (WP 4.1, 4.3; HBM and NTS approaches) and toxicological (WP5.1, 5.3; focus on emerging mycotoxins) as well as data (WP7.2, 7.3) and inter-lab comparison (WP9.3) components.

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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4- VLAAMSE INSTELLING VOOR TECHNOLOGISCH ONDERZOEK N.V., BELGIUM (VITO) – PIC: 999645238

In PARC, VITO will be WP7 co-leader and contribute to FAIR data policy, Data Management Plan (DMP), landscape of relevant data platforms, draft architecture for FAIR data hub, use case on human biomonitoring data (lead), exploratory work on privacy-preserving data analysis, and innovative methods for mixtures analysis. As T4.1 co-leader, VITO will coordinate the design, planning, and implementation of the general population HBM survey and first targeted surveys (including effect

biomarkers), establish the data management helpdesk and statistical working group, initiate statistical analysis plans, and contribute to preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe.

Based on its track record in exposure modelling and risk and health impact assessment, VITO will act as T6.2 co-leader and contribute to development of strategies to assess aggregate exposure through different living environments and different routes of entry, internal exposure during life, and risks of mixture exposure. VITO will also explore data availability, uncertainties, and opportunities for methodological improvements for health impact assessment and design case studies. In addition, VITO will contribute to the inventory and application of innovative sampling methods, Effect Directed Analysis, and suspect and non-target screening methodologies with its state-of-the art analytical laboratories and expertise in T4.3, and to the PFAS case study in T4.2. In T1.3, VITO will support the development of the PARC monitoring framework and indicators.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	Y
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1) Expert in setting up data FAIRification processes according to established methods (e.g. the Three Point FAIRification Framework) – budget: 85 000 € in Y1. Although several partners have been involved in FAIRification processes, there is need for a dedicated expert with broad experience in FAIR data Training (including Train-the-Trainer), workshops and implementation to kick-start the FAIRification process and methods in WP7.

2) Software developer – budget: 700 000 € over 7 years. Development, implementation and testing of APIs and (federated) services to support data FAIRification solutions, and system management, hosting and operation. Whereas functional analysis, system architecture, innovative analysis and applications will be taken up by VITO experts, technical implementation work will partially be outsourced due to the nature of the work (non-innovative) and lack of sufficient own appropriately skilled personnel.

Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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4.1 KU Leuven – PIC 999991334: This department participates in T4.1 to design an occupational HBM survey focusing on the waste management sector and a sentinel surveillance system to collect reliable and statistically representative data on environmental and occupational exposure and health on a European level, and to define general criteria for the selection of the best, state-of-the-art exposure biomarkers and analytical methods. Furthermore, the Centre will participate in linking HBM studies to health examination and dietary surveys. The Epidemiology Research Center at KU Leuven University focuses on the etiology of chronic diseases in the general population and has an internationally recognised expertise in epigenetic epidemiology. This Center will participate in Task 5.3 on quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs.

4.2 DOMG – PIC 999575107: DOMG will be the NHCP for Belgium in PARC and co-lead T1.3 on impact evaluation and monitoring of the performance indicators of the Partnership; DOMG also performed these tasks in HBM4EU. DOMG is also a key partner in T2.3 for development of impact indicators related to sustainability.

4.3 UH – PIC 999874934: In year 1, UH will join the statistical working group for analysis of HBM data in T4.1.

4.4 PIH – PIC 920268780: In T4.1, PIH will prepare the participation of the Flemish human biomonitoring campaign in the general population HBM survey, take part in preparation of supporting materials for HBM surveys to be implemented in PARC, contribute to the elaboration of the DMP and procedures to make HBM data FAIR, and join the helpdesk to support the HBM study partners in all aspects of data management.

4.5 OVAM – PIC 954439649 OVAM will contribute to the development of the environmental and multisource monitoring framework and pilot projects focusing on per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs) in T4.2.

4.6 ISSeP – PIC 914156228: In T4.1, ISSeP will coordinate and prepare the Walloon human biomonitoring campaigns in the general population HBM survey, take part in preparation of supporting materials for HBM surveys to be implemented in PARC, and initiate statistical analysis plans for evaluation of exposure sources and routes and determinants of exposure. ISSeP will contribute in T4.2 by establishing a European environmental and multisource monitoring framework, with a focus on per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs) during year 1.

In T6.2, ISSeP will contribute to develop strategies to assess aggregate exposure through different living environments and different routes of entry as well as internal exposure during life. ISSeP will also evaluate the availability of exposure and health outcome data for health impact assessment. In T6.3, ISSeP will contribute to review the use of tools, criteria and methods to promote more transparent and harmonised evaluations of scientific information and data on chemicals.

In T7.2, ISSeP will identify existing and planned databases, data repositories and platforms relevant for PARC and bottlenecks for data reuse and synergies with existing data platforms. ISSeP will identify methods for innovative and privacy-preserving data analysis and uncertainty characterisation, propagation and quantification in T7.3.

In T8.3, ISSeP will contribute to the first draft of an overarching conceptual model to map models and platforms to user requirements and risk assessment questions.

In T9.1, ISSeP will contribute to the development of catalogues on air monitoring and biomonitoring/population studies/networks and on networks related to articles/indoors.

4.7 UAntwerpen PIC 999902870: UAntwerpen will contribute to definition of general criteria for the selection of the best, state-of-the-art exposure biomarkers and analytical methods in T4.1. In T4.3, the Toxicological Centre will contribute to mapping of approaches and objectives associated to innovative methods and tools for monitoring, QA/QC criteria for suspect screening/NTS/EDA, and workplans to apply these methodologies to the use of personal samplers and to wastewater-based epidemiology. The research of Zebrafishlab focuses on investigating the mechanisms underlying toxicity, the development of Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) in predictive ecotoxicology and toxicology, and the development of alternative, non-animal test methods for ecological and human risk assessment including in vitro methods and zebrafish embryo methods. Zebrafishlab will participate in T5.2 on the development of innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling in the areas of metabolic disruption, developmental neurotoxicity and thyroid hormone disruption, in T5.3 on the development of new AOPs, and in T6.1 on the development of Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment of Chemicals and associated case studies. The research group Systemic Physiological & Ecotoxicological Research of UAntwerpen studies the effects of environmental stressors on the performance of aquatic and terrestrial organisms with an emphasis on mechanisms and ecological relevance and owns state of the art (bio)analytical facilities. This group will participate in T4.2 in the survey to identify relevant studies on PFAS present in the environment and in biota and selecting relevant PFAS and ECDs, and to design and operate monitoring campaigns in both the aquatic and the terrestrial environment (in collaboration with T4.3) and generate data (building on existing infrastructures) to respond to specific regulatory needs.

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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5- SCIENSANO, BELGIUM – PIC: 906160809

The main tasks of SCIENSANO in the first year include:

(i) WP4: With respect to Human Biomonitoring (T4.1), SCIENSANO will contribute to the laboratory

analysis and quality assurance (T4.1.2) and the data management and analysis (T4.1.4) based on its experience with measurement of markers in non-invasive samples and the availability of state-of-the-art HPLC-ICP-MS systems. SCIENSANO will also be involved in the different activities with respect to environmental and multisource monitoring (T4.2), with a particular focus on perfluorinated compounds, based on its expertise and its access to a state-of-the-art chromatography platform.

(ii) WP5: Within the project on natural toxins of Task 5.1a, SCIENSANO will perform in vitro genotoxicity test on both enniatins and Alternaria toxins. Moreover, SCIENSANO is co-leading task 5.3 and will also contribute specifically to the prioritised NAM-based mechanistic hazard characterisation, amongst others, by generating transcriptomics data.

(iii) WP6: SCIENSANO is co-leading Task 6.1 and will actively contribute to the development of the IATA for genotoxicity including the development of AOP networks, the IATA design and its evaluation through case studies based on its longstanding expertise in the field and the availability of a state-of-the-art genotoxicity testing facility. Stakeholder engagement will also be covered. In addition, SCIENSANO will contribute to the human health impact assessment and development of risk indicators (T6.2.4) under Task 6.2, with a particular focus on the burden of disease assessment based on its expertise in this domain. Finally, SCIENSANO will be partnering in CS13 ‘Identification of differences and loopholes in the regulation of plasticisers depending on intended use’ of Task 6.3 based on its expertise in the field of food packaging.

(iv) Based on its expertise and its access to state-of-the-art toxicity and analytical labs, SCIENSANO will also contribute to several tasks under WP9.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y

5.1 UGENT – PIC 999986096: will contribute within year 1 of PARC to WP4, WP5 and WP6. For WP4, the involvement of UGent will depend on the selected biomarkers. In case mycotoxins are selected, UGent will contribute based on their longstanding experience in the field. This includes technology development and mycotoxin measurements in complex environmental and human sample matrices (Task 4.1 and 4.3).

Within WP5, UGent will contribute to the hazard assessment of phycotoxins for aquatic ecosystems given its expertise in environmental toxicology (Task 5.1) and to the systems toxicology project (Task 5.3), where it will contribute with the development of bioinformatic and data integration approaches for AOP mapping given its experience in toxicogenomics.

Within WP6, UGent will contribute to the project on specific target organ toxicity (Task 6.1) where it is involved in the development and quantitation of AOP networks given its experience in toxicogenomics.

5.2 EV-ILVO PIC 998175591: In WP2 of PARC, EV-ILVO will share knowledge and experience on chemical compounds in animal- and plant-based food/feed matrices within a farm-to-field approach and environmental matrices.

For WP4, expertise on environmental monitoring (focus on marine environment) and organisation of sampling campaigns at the Belgian Part of the North Sea, as well as on chemical analysis of the marine environment and food matrices will be shared (Task 4.3). In addition, participation in the development and validation of analytical methods using LC-MS/MS, LC-HRMS and GC-MS for different compounds in matrices of animal/plant/environmental samples as well as sharing experience in developing non-targeted LC-HRMS methods for food and targeted and untargeted data processing are envisaged.

As for WP7, EV-ILVO will be involved for the analysis/integration/sharing aspects of FAIR data (Task 7.2) and will actively contribute to the development of use-cases and to the part on innovative data

analytical approaches (e.g. machine learning on data source in agriculture, food and related topics) (Task 7.3).

5.3 VUB – PIC 999902094: VUB is co-leading Task 5.2a with DTU and will also perform collaborative research with DTU to gain new mechanistic knowledge on how thyroid hormone disruptors affect the liver by employing developmental stem cell-based NAMs with human relevance. With respect to WP6, VUB will be involved in the development of AOP networks for genotoxicity, the design of IATAs based on the AOP networks and NAMs (including evaluation), and the execution of case studies (Task 6.1.1). Furthermore, in Task 6.3, VUB will lead case study 10 on the Evaluation of risk assessment approaches used for cosmetic ingredients with endocrine-disrupting (ED) concern and is partnering also case study 18 on New hazard classes and test requirements for endocrine disruption.

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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6- HRVATSKI ZAVOD ZA JAVNO ZDRAVSTVO, CROATIA (CIPH) – PIC: 998128255

Within the PARC, CIPH will participate in the following activities in the first Project’s year:

WP3, Task 3.2. Communication, dissemination and synergies Identify and address areas of needs/improvements in PARC

CIPH will contribute through cooperation with other partners in development of communication materials, for example newsletter. Relevant communication and dissemination documents will be translated into Croatian language.

CIPH will participate and contribute in development of an open access and publication strategy, activities for awareness raising and a citizens’ survey.

WP4, Tasks 4.1.

According to previous participation in HBM4EU project and acquired experience, CIPH will contribute in updating and development of supporting materials for general and occupational HBM surveys, review and update of materials developed under HBM4EU, eExplore and propose solutions for inclusion of novel aspects in HBM studies implementation and iIdentify and address areas of needs/improvements in PARC.

Available infrastructure: Instruments for metals and trace/ultratrace elements analysis (AAS and ICP-MSs), chromatographic analysis (GC-MS, HPLC)

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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6.1 IMROH – PIC 998300333 IMROH will participate in the following activities in the first Project’s year:

WP4, Tasks 4.1, and 4.2: IMROH has long term experience in studies that include human biomonitoring (mainly regarding toxic metals) in various populations (occupational exposure and vulnerable groups like mother-child pairs) and in biomarker matrices (blood, urine, hair, placental tissue, semen, etc.). It is/has been participating in numerous national and international projects (e.g. HBM4EU, CancerRiskBiomarkers, NewGeneris, GEMS/AIR, CONCERT, CYTOTHREAT, RiskGone, PHOENIX) focused on hazard assessment and human health and environmental risk assessment of chemicals, medicines, and consumer products, as well as on the Safe-and-Sustainable-

by-Design (SSbD) approach to foster innovation. IMROH has strong collaboration with occupational health specialists and occupational medicine clinics involved in medical examinations of workers.

WP7, Task 7.3: Previous activities of IMROH related to this task included development and implementation of methodology for integrating diverse datasets with overlapping variables and processing interval-censored data, as well as implementation of various statistical and machine learning techniques. While IMROH cannot be a key contributor for these tasks as only one statistician that could be involved in this WP is currently employed at the Institute, IMROH proposes to be involved in these tasks in cooperation with key contributors. A greater role by IMROH may be provided in the future, when IMROH's biostatistical capacities are expanded, as is planned by employing at least one doctoral researcher.

WP9, Task 9.2: IMROH is participating in Croatian national network for Air Quality Monitoring and Management System and are experienced in sampling and organisation of measuring campaign, data analysis, modelling and health risk assessment development as well as in participation and organisation of laboratory intercomparison tests regarding air monitoring; we are also national reference laboratory for measurements of particulate matter and member of AQUILA. IMROH has long term experience in studies that include HBM as well (mainly regarding metals Pb, Hg, Cd, As exposure) in various populations (occupational exposure and vulnerable groups like mother-child pairs) and in biomarker matrices (blood, urine, hair, placental tissue, semen, etc.). We also can provide expertise in nanomedicine and nanosafety; risk assessment of chemical mixtures including nanomaterials and pharmaceuticals; integrative approaches to risk assessment (AOP, IATA). Therefore, apart from IMROH's interest to gain from networking with colleagues participating in WP9, it can provide necessary information regarding mapping and strengthening of exposure monitoring, at least at national level.

WP4, Task 4.1: With respect to Task 4.1, IMROH will participate in the definition of general criteria for the selection of the best, state-of-the-art exposure biomarkers and analytical methods, as well as in the development of the supporting materials for general and occupational HBM surveys (e.g. informed consents, lifestyle and dietary exposure questionnaires, SOPs for sample collection, preservation, and storage).

WP7, Task 7.3: Previous activities of IMROH related to this task included development and implementation of methodology for integrating diverse datasets with overlapping variables and processing interval-censored data, as well as implementation of various statistical and machine learning techniques. IMROH will be involved in Task 7.3.1, i.e. in the preparation of inventories of computational methods to maximise the reliability and usefulness of meta- and pooled analysis of heterogeneous exposure, toxicological or epidemiological data; statistically based methods to combine data from epidemiological, biomarker, animal and in-vitro studies; and methods for the privacy-preserving analysis of sensitive, personal data. While IMROH cannot be a key contributor for these tasks as only one statistician that could be involved in this WP is currently employed at the Institute, IMROH proposes to be involved in these tasks in cooperation with key contributors. A greater role by IMROH may be provided in the future, when IMROH's biostatistical capacities are expanded, as is planned by employing at least one doctoral researcher.

WP9, Task 9.2: Apart from IMROH's interest to gain from networking with colleagues participating in WP9, it can provide necessary information regarding mapping and strengthening of exposure monitoring, at least at national level. IMROH will contribute to inventorying and analysing existing capacities and network activities with expertise and information from its previous environmental and biomonitoring studies, including those related to environmental monitoring networks (primarily related to air monitoring), and national biomonitoring and population cohort studies. With respect to Task 9.2, IMROH will be involved in the preparation of the catalogues on air monitoring and Human

Biomonitoring/population studies/networks, and on networks related to articles/indoors, including the available sample and data collections.

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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7- Ministry of Health of the Republic of Cyprus, CYPRUS (MOH-CY/SGL) – PIC: 994267946

In the first year of PARC MOH-CY/SGL will participate in:

WP1: All activities involving the National Hub (Task 1.2) and the Grand Signatory (Task 1.1)

WP4: Task 4.1.1 (Design, Alignment and fieldwork of HBM studies: the waste management occupational survey, the targeted survey for pregnant women utilising the HBM4EU-mom samples and a general survey study on children) and Task 4.1.5 (HBM sustainability)

WP6: Task 6.2.1 (aggregate exposure from multiple sources and routes for general population and workers) and Task 6.2.3 (mixture exposure and risk assessment) under the coordination of the relevant task leaders

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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7.1 SHSO – PIC 891074787: The State Health Services Organization, Republic of Cyprus (SHSO) will participate in Task 4.1.1 together with the GS and specifically in a general survey study for children.

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	Y
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The national authority for Labor Inspection intends to assist us in the implementation in Cyprus of the occupational survey on waste management under Task 4.1.1. Specifically, the Department of Labour Inspection-DLI-(Department of the Ministry of Labour, Welfare and Social Insurance) will provide assistance regarding the recruitment of waste management companies and their workers, the dissemination and uptake of results into policy. Our laboratory has long-standing collaboration with the DLI for the market control for the chemical safety of consumer/industrial products in the frame of REACH and CLP.

8- Masarykova univerzita, CZECH REPUBLIC (MU) – PIC: 999880657

Masaryk University (MU) will co-lead WP9 (Building infrastructural and human capacities) in PARC and Task 7.2 (Data libraries). In the 1st year of PARC, MU will be involved in the development and consolidation of the air monitoring network, network related to articles (T9.2), and human biomonitoring network (T9.1), and in activities related to the mapping and development of technical solutions for building such catalogues (T9.2 in cooperation with WP7). MU will further be involved and contribute directly as well as from the position of WP9-(co)leader in the mapping exercises and landscaping of WP4.2 related to case studies on the multisource monitoring of perfluoroalkyl substances and endocrine disruptors. MU will be further involved in 4.1 (e.g. occupational surveys related to the health care sector), 4.3 (e.g. defining of concepts related to innovative methods, designing and sampling in the study targeting prenatal exposures), selected activities of WP5 (mainly 5.2b) and WP6 (task 6.1) and will also contribute to WP2, WP3, and WP8.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
<p>8.1 SZU-CZ PIC 999478689: Due to the long-term experience with regular national human biomonitoring in non-professionally exposed population, SZU-CZ will participate in development and update of supporting materials for HBM general population surveys within T4.1.1, such as questionnaires, non-responder questionnaire, interviewer manuals, SOP's for sample collection, preservation etc. Given the experience with national health examination surveys (already 2nd round in 2019/2020 by the EHES methodology concurrently with the health interview survey EHIS), SZU-CZ will be involved in development of SOPs for collection of health outcome data via questionnaires and health examinations, which is connected with activities 4.1.3. SZU-CZ will be involved in activity 4.1.5, contributing to sustainable monitoring and the establishment of the surveillance system in Europe</p> <p>8.2 VSCHT – PIC 999867853: VSCHT (CZ) will be involved in tasks 4.1 and 4.2 related to human/environmental exposure and monitoring and in tasks 9.1-9.4 and will contribute to the building of human biomonitoring and environmental networks, harmonisation in QA/QC, and training</p> <p>8.3 OU – PIC 998738870: OU (CZ) will be involved in activity 4.1.2 to focus on laboratory analysis and quality assurance The OU anticipates the participation of two faculties in the PARC project - Medicine and Science. Currently, the Faculty of Medicine has in its database approximately 4,000 probands/volunteers aged 35-65 from two areas of the Czech Republic, half from the industrial/environmentally polluted area and half from the non-industrial/unpolluted area of the Czech Republic. The data obtained from these probands are used to solve the HAIE project (“Healthy Aging in Industrial Environment, CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/16_019/0000798), while about 10% (about 400 probands) had venous blood taken for a number of examinations. A portion of each sample could possibly also be used for blood/serum testing for the PARC project. If these samples are not suitable for PARC purposes, then it is possible to contact probands with a request for further sampling of biological material, but this requires a follow-up research project, which we have not yet obtained. The Laboratory of Molecular Epidemiology of the Faculty of Medicine provides sampling of biological material and special molecular-genetic/epigenetic examinations (e.g. analyses of microRNA or methylated selected sections of DNA after environmental exposures), the Laboratory of Chemical Analyzes of the Faculty of Science could then investigate a number of metals and organic substances (pesticides, bisphenol etc.) in the collected samples of human biological material.</p> <p>8.4 JU – PIC 999876292: JU (CZ) will participate in task 4.3 (4.3.1, 4.3.2, and 4.3.4) and contribute to the development of innovative sampling methods, exposure assessment, monitoring, and non-targeted screening approaches.</p> <p>MU and its AEs will jointly cooperate to support the implementation of the ambitious goals related to chemical management, pollution-free environment and to capitalise on the achievements of previous efforts and projects (such as HBM4EU). In support of developing closer ties and synergies and capitalising on the achievements and collaboration established by the National Panel for Human Biomonitoring, the institutions have entered a Collaboration Agreement to confirm the establishment of the Czech national hub on risk assessment of chemicals.</p>	
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

9- USTAV ZDRAVOTNICKYCH INFORMACI A STATISTIKY CESKE REPUBLIKY, CZECH REPUBLIC (UZIS) – PIC: 920415929
 UZIS is official health data institution in the Czech Republic and will therefore contribute to the policy

from the viewpoint of official health information institution, with experience in deployment of health data accessible datasets. UZIS will contribute to the WP7 – FAIR Data through comments and providing national liaison regarding national health datasets. Main tasks during Year 1:

-Activity 7.1.1:

Commenting on the proposal of the template for the data management plan.

-Activity 7.2.1-3:

Contribution to mapping the FAIR data landscape, identification of use cases etc.

-Activity 7.3.2:

Contribution to the scoping study of uncertainty analysis.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?

N

Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*

N

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?

N

10- The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, DENMARK (DEPA) – PIC: 938989101

During the first year of PARC, the main tasks of DEPA will be the coordination of the national HUB, participation in Grant Signatory Board and participation in Governing Board.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?

N

Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*

Y

10.1 AU – PIC 999997736: Aarhus University (AU): The participant has a framework contract with AU on research-based scientific advice provided by AU to the participant. AU will participate in WPs 4, 5, 6, 8 and 9. Department of Public Health of Aarhus University is involved in the following WP/tasks 4.1, 5.1., 5.3, 6.2 and 6.2. PH-AU will contribute with expertise within epidemiological studies of the general population and occupational cohort studies. Focus will be on identifying the level and impact of exposures on public health, including epidemiological/occupational studies on chemical exposures (e.g. pesticides, persistent organic pollutants, metals) and relation to chronic disease, development and reproduction. Another key activity is development of methods for exposure assessment (e.g. mixtures, job matrixes, etc.). For instance, PH-AU will contribute with developed extraction/fractionation and molecular-cellular methods for assessment of effects from the real life mixtures exposure in human samples as well as in integrated models. Their cohort studies are international collaborations including populations from e.g. Greenland, Norway, China and Denmark. Furthermore, they are part of the The Danish Ramazzini Center (DRC), which is a collaborative effort between Danish Regions, Aarhus University and later Aalborg University with the objective to enhance occupational health research by uniting forces at the three hospital-based occupational medicine clinics hosted by the Regions and AU-PH.

Department of Environmental Science/Danish Centre for Environment and Energy, Aarhus University (DCE-AU) is involved in the following WPs/tasks: 4.2, 4.3, 6.4, 8.2, 9.1, 9.2 and 9.3. DCE-AU is interim task co-lead for 4.2 and WP4 contact person in WP9. DCE-AU will contribute with expertise in environmental science, including (eco)toxicology. Based on long-term experience in environmental monitoring, DCE-AU will co-lead the establishment and operation of Environment and Multi-source

Monitoring (T4.2) in PARC, including links to the other WPs/tasks in PARC. The first project will be on perfluorinated alkylated substances (PFAS) and endocrine disrupting compounds, also including a mechanism for future project design. As the task will avoid any duplication, it includes an element on “Review of existing knowledge and infrastructure”, which will proceed in close collaboration with the inventory and network creating activities in WP9, parts of which are based on HBM4EU where DCE-AU was task lead for the analytical phase. DCE-AU has strong competences in the field of analytical chemistry, which will contribute to T4.3 and T8.2, for example with regard to non-target/suspect screening and passive sampling. Furthermore, DCE-AU’s expertise in the field of (eco)toxicity will be part of T6.4 on environmental risk assessment.

10.2 DTU FOOD – PIC 999990655: In the 1st year of PARC DTU will be involved in WP5 – Hazard assessment (Task 5.2a) and WP6 – Innovation in regulatory risk assessment (Tasks 6.1.1, 6.1.2, 6.2.3, and 6.2.4).

10.3 REGIONH – PIC 999654744:

Dept. of Growth and Reproduction, Rigshospitalet (in the workprogramme also referred to as RegionH-RH) will during the first year participate in WP4 (task 4.1.1) with the planning of design, alignment, and fieldwork of general HBM surveys including inventory of innovative sampling methods. RegionH-RH will also be initiating a new Danish HBM survey in children and adolescents. In addition, RegionH-RH will in WP9 (task 9.3.2) participate as member of a QA/QC working group for harmonisation of performance criteria for chemical analyses within the HBM domain and be involved in the drafting and updating of guidance documents with harmonised criteria for quantitative and qualitative chemical analysis.

Dept. of Skin and Allergy, Gentofte Hospital; National Allergy Research Centre (NARC) (in the Workprogramme also referred to as RegionH-GE) will during the first year participate in WP6.3, which concerns case studies of risk assessment methodologies. In the first-year planning of the design, methodologies used and co-ordination across WPs will be performed together with a post. doc. Preparation of recruitment of a PhD will be done for 2. Year and participation in co-ordination meetings.

10.4 UCPH – PIC 999991043: UCPHs main tasks during the first year will be related to project 4.3_01 on suspect screening, non-target analysis and toxicity evaluation of wastewater. We plan to participate in (1) Mining chemical information from wastewater treatment plants for I. human community and II. environmental exposure assessment; (2) Proof-of-concept of HRMS based screening methods for exploring chemicals of emerging concern, and (3) Complementary developments regarding the application of HRMS based screening methods on environmental samples (e.g. dust, soil, sludge, and wastewater).

10.5 SDU – PIC 999904616 : SDU is AE to DEPA and will participate in the following WP tasks the 1st year: WP5.1a., 5.1b, 5.2a, 5.2b, 5.3.2, 6.1.1, 6.1.2. SDU will also use the expertise gained from the work being a member of OECD VMG-Eco, ECHA EDEG, EFSA ED WG and as coordinator of ERGO, one of the projects in the EURION cluster to support the work in task 5.3.2, 6.1.1 and 6.1.2.

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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11- TERVISEAMET, ESTONIA (HB) – PIC: 933659727

The main task of the Health Board is to be NHCP and coordinator for 2 affiliated entities for Estonia. In the first year of PARC Health Board is contributing to WP 1 tasks 1 and 2 and in WP 3 into task 2. Health Board as of GSB member helps to establish PARC partnership within Estonia ensuring all the data and documents are provided. HB is ensuring preparations for successful signing of consortium

agreement and coordinating information to affiliated entities within the country.
 HB is collaborating with SoM, taking steps for setting up a structure for national hub within a country. In collaboration with SoM there will be carried out a survey and market research for mapping out the needs and possibilities for the hub to be an actual sustainable value for the field and people. We are working on ways to promote and introduce PARC opportunities for possible new affiliated entities within the country.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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11.1 SOM – PIC 998429731: The Ministry of Social Affairs will be involved in WP2 as policy makers.

11.2 UT – PIC 999895013: The University of Tartu is involved (as of 2022-08-29) in Task 6.4.2. We will also focus on the status of integration and use of data sciences (i.e. artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML) technologies, decision support systems (DSS)) in the regulatory context, as well as on barriers, opportunities and drivers for success towards the development, validation, and implementation of computer-based approaches for knowledge-driven/evidence-based risk assessment frameworks. The ultimate goal is to support the introduction of next generation risk assessment (NGRA) methods and tools across regulatory domains. Within T6.4.2 UT initiated and leads sub-project "Landscape and readiness of advanced ML and AI approaches for next generation chemical risk assessment".

It is three year project and has started. UT also participates in two other project in T6.4.2. Within PARC, coming years, UT sees strong contribution also in WP7 and WP8 in FAIR predictive model and data organization and also collaboration with WP4 and WP5 in predictive models development

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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12- EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENT AGENCY, EU (EEA) – PIC: 997912624

The EEA will be involved in the following tasks:

- WP2 (A common science-policy agenda), work package co-leadership with the Austrian Environment Agency
- Partners in task 2.1 Priority setting, 2.2 knowledge management and uptake into policy, task 2.3 sustainability
- Partners in task 3.2 Communication and dissemination (WP3 Synergies, collaborations and awareness)
- Partners in task 8.1 Safe and sustainable by design (WP8 Concepts and toolboxes)

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	Y
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WP3: Website development, formatting and layout of communication products.
 Budget: 1466500€

Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
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Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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13- TERVEYDEN JA HYVINVOINNIN LAITOS, FINLAND (THL) – PIC: 996697893

Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare will during the first year of PARC analyse PFAS from 1 year old Finnish Children to see if the sum of 4 PFAS (PFHxS, PFOS, PFOA, PFNA) exceeds the critical level of 17,5 ng/ml derived in the EFSA 2020 PFAS risk assessment. We use 300 recently collected serum samples from approximately 1 year old children that are participants of type 1 diabetes study DIPP (https://dipp.fi/?page_id=2684&lang=en). During the first year of PARC we will also collect mother's milk samples from a new round of contaminant monitoring that has been ongoing in THL since the first WHO recommendation to monitor POP in mother's milk in 1987. Samples will be collected from Helsinki (Southern Finland), Kuopio (Central Finland) and Rovaniemi (Northern Finland). Analysis of samples will not take place during the Year 1. Work of THL during Year 1 relates to Tasks 1.1 - 1.2 / 4.1.1 – 4.1.2.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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13.1 SYKE – PIC 999478010: During the first year, SYKE will contribute with their expertise in environmental monitoring, risk assessment, circular economy and modelling. T4.2.1 & T4.2.3: participation in the planning of activities to be conducted during the following years.
 T4.2.2: compiling and delivering required data as agreed within the task.
 T6.3 (CS1): Defining a methodology and criteria for selecting relevant substances and risk-based thresholds to be evaluated in the study. Compiling necessary background information on the selected substances/benchmarks. Identifying key stakeholders to be engaged with during the study including potential synergies with other PARC case studies.
 T8.1 & T8.3: participation in the planning and specifying of activities to be conducted during the following years, identification of relevant Finnish stakeholders.

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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14- TYOTERVEYSLAITOS, FINLAND (TTL) – PIC: 999880948

TTL will perform following main tasks during the first year of PARC:

- WP4: Setting up occupational surveys on waste management and health care sector within WP4.1. This includes for example development of SOPs, applying ethical permission and recruitment of companies for the surveys.
- Leading feasibility study to assess occupational exposure from the general population HBM surveys (WP4.1).
- WP6: Participation into the activity related to aggregating exposure from general life and occupational exposure (performing inventory of exposure models for occupational exposure, analysis of these models, data gap analysis and preparation of roadmap). TTL is responsible from one milestone.
- Within WP6.3 TTL participates in two case studies: Evaluation of the efficiency of EU OSH legislation and REACH authorisation/restriction processes to control occupational chemical exposure (TTL, KI) and Regulation of occupational exposures to reproductive and developmental toxicants (KI, TTL). These both start at Y1.
- Within WP8.1 TTL participates all activities in Task 8.1 from the viewpoint of occupational exposure and health and is involved in the planning of case studies (Task 8.3).

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
<p>14.2 TUKES – PIC 972221301: Tukes participates in Y1 in task 6.4.3, under which the project 6.4.3.1 (A comprehensive review of databases and testing methods for chemicals in articles) will start in the first year. Tukes will contribute together with other participants to key deliverables: Report on existing database structures with recommended structures and Report on current screening and enforcement structures.</p> <p>14.1 FFA – PIC 902952534: FFA will be involved in WP4.1, participating in targeted surveys in children and performs preparatory work related to these.</p> <p>14.3 UOULU – PIC 999844670: The participation of UOULU in PARC consists of Arctic population monitoring and risk evaluation and assessment. During the Year 1 UOULU participates to Tasks 4.1.1 / 4.1.3. These are separate activities from those performed by TTL.</p>	
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

<p>15- UMWELTBUNDESAMT, GERMANY (UBA) – PIC: 998575910</p> <p>UBA will co-lead WP4 Monitoring and Exposure, using its extensive experience from HBM4EU. UBA has nearly 40 years of experience in conducting HBM studies and therefore highly qualified for diverse activities in T4.1 like the design, planning, and implementation of a general population HBM survey, preparation of targeted studies, relationships between exposure biomarkers, effect biomarkers, health outcome data, selection of chemicals per age group, innovative sampling and screening methods, supporting materials, health-based GVs, data management plan, statistical working group and the sustainable monitoring and surveillance system. In T4.2 UBA will work on closing knowledge gaps and research priorities identified in the field of environmental and multisource monitoring, the develop a framework for automated assessment of large lists of compounds, design monitoring study(ies) incl. some preparatory analytical work, statistical analysis of existing data and the feedback mechanism. It will use its extensive experience in environmental monitoring, especially from the ESB (Environmental Specimen Bank) and work connected to WRRL and MSRL.</p> <p>In T6.3 UBA will work on substance and effect specific reviews, review the use of tools, criteria and methods. In T6.4 UBA will develop regulatory and legally accepted RA and RM methods for chemical mixtures, contribute to a literature review for NAM use in exposure data gap filling and use it for the initiation of case studies. UBA will support not only with its long-lasting experience in translating scientific research into regulatory guidance but also draw from the experience and excellence of its network and partners where needed.</p>	
Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
<p>15.1 BfG – PIC 996893445: The BfG will work accordingly to their expertise in the design of monitoring studies (4.2), screening approaches (4.3) and innovative assays for toxicity testing. UBA and BfG are working together in this field on a regular basis in several research projects and committees.</p> <p>15.3 IPA – PIC 998343692: According to their expertise in the first year IPA will mainly contribute to the Tasks 4.1.2 and 9.1.3 as well as 9.3.2. working on the following activities: laboratory analysis and</p>	

quality assurance, Quality Assurance Working Group, QA/QC criteria, reference analytical methods, supporting materials for general and occupational HBM surveys and statistical analysis plans., development of pilot catalogues of existing laboratory networks and mapping of their capacities in function of PARC needs and the next generation risk assessment.

15.6 KUM – PIC 995625946: the KUM seeks to compare risk assessment methods for hazardous chemicals, advance in the identification of indicators to explain the relative risk from already permitted substances, develop new methods, exchange methodological and technical know-how and if possible, conduct joint studies.

For example, in the tasks 4.1.1, 4.1.2, 4.1.3 they will work on the definition of general criteria for the selection of the best, state-of-the-art exposure biomarkers and analytical methods and in task 4.3.1 they will contribute to the workplans for pilot studies.

15.2 UFZ – PIC 999994632 : In the first year UFZ will be engaged in the design of monitoring studies (4.2), development of new methods in collection of HBM samples in combination with screening tools (4.3), application of toxicity test addressing data gaps (5.1), development of new toxicity tests (5.2), further development of risk assessment (6.4) and the identification of core data hub services (7.2.2). UBA and UFZ have been working together in several research projects and will further intensify the ongoing collaboration.

15.4 UKOLD – PIC 999856407: The UKOLD seeks to compare risk assessment methods for hazardous chemicals, advance in the identification of indicators to explain the relative risk from already permitted substances, develop new methods that allow for a consistent risk assessment and participate in joint studies on how to enhance the realism of risk assessment. Their main contribution in the first year is in the compilation and analysis of data from risk assessment and method development for comparing and ranking risk assessments between substances (6.4.4). Given the background in the risk assessment of chemicals and analysis of complex data, UKOLD will lead a work package in Task 6.4.4 on the development of a holistic risk assessment based on the identification of indicators of relative risks of substances. In the first year, its main contribution will be in the compilation and analysis of ecotoxicological and risk assessment data to provide ground for the development of the holistic assessment and it will contribute to other tasks in 6.4.4. that evaluate the relative contribution of different stressors to landscape-level chemical risk assessment.

15.5 UOS – PIC 999855049: The UOS main contribution in the first year is in the review of fate assessment methods and their comparison with indicator systems (6.4.4). Given the background in the development of risk assessment methods of chemicals, UOS will be participating in activities in Task 6.4.4, with focus on supporting the reduction of complexity of models for fate and effects, and the development of indicators of relative risks of substances. In the first year, its main contribution will be in reviewing fate assessment methods in order to prepare comparison with respective indicator systems and possible new, simplified fate assessment approaches. It will contribute to the other tasks in 6.4.4. Concerning the simplification of model-based assessment methods.

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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16- BUNDESINSTITUT FUER RISIKOBEWERTUNG, GERMANY (BfR) – PIC: 998771171
 With its longstanding expertise, BfR will co-lead WP 5 - "Hazard Assessment" and Task 2.2 - "Knowledge Management and Uptake into Policy" and will contribute to Task 2.1 "Priority setting" in WP 2 - "A common Science Policy Agenda" within the Partnership in the first year.
 The main tasks of BfR in WP5 within year 1 will be to coordinate the identification of regulatory data gaps on hazards in cooperation with the PARC partners, to improve the current hazard characterisation paradigm and to start to improve the mechanistic understanding of toxicity by Data analysis.

For Task 2.2 the main tasks of BfR in year 1 are the conceptual development of the projects PARCopedia and PARCroute in collaboration with the partners of the task, which will include a scoping study and the development of a PARCopedia pilot, as well as different meetings.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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The German AEs will cooperate with BfR in a number of projects and activities esp. in WP5, but also in WP2. They will be performing tasks as described in the respective proposals, the AWP and Section B of the proposal.

In year 1 BfR will cooperate with the following AEs:

16.1 Fraunhofer – PIC 999984059 (WP5)

Fraunhofer IME is involved in WP 4.2 (Environmental and multisource monitoring) and WP 6.4 (Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies).

In the field of environmental monitoring, Fraunhofer IME has significant experience in prioritization processes as well as in designing and conducting monitoring studies. In Year 1, Fraunhofer IME will be working in WP 4.2.1 to support the prioritization of chemicals and activities, namely in the field of PFAS. As soon as samples are available, Fraunhofer IME will additionally work on the chemical analysis of PFAS in environmental samples in the frame of WP 4.2.4 to yield a first picture of the PFAS burden in the European environment.

Fraunhofer IME is also involved in activity 6.4.4 (Risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity). In the field of environmental exposure modelling Fraunhofer IME has contributed in the development of exposure models over the past years (e.g., GERDA Steps, Steps 1&2, FOCUS SWASH). The aim is it to reduce the complexity of currently used models/methodologies without compromising the level of protection required. In a first step a list of the complex exposure models predicting PPP concentrations in surface will be composed. After that, the processes that are included are described and processes which can be simplified will be identified.

Fraunhofer IBMT is involved in WP4 Task 4.1.1a Design, alignment and fieldwork of HBM studies and in year 1 supports the review and update of materials developed under HBM4EU as well as the identification of needs and opportunities for the improvement of methods for a standardized realization of the fieldwork planned in PARC. In Task 4.1.1.b Fraunhofer IBMT supports the implementation of the general survey planned for Germany in year 1. For sampling of human specimens, IBMT provides a mobile biological safety level 2 laboratory. In addition, Fraunhofer IBMT is involved in WP4 Task 4.1.3 Link exposure and health related information. Fraunhofer IBMT has extensive expertise in the standardization of HBM related processes of the pre-analytical and analytical phase. This includes the development of standardized questionnaires for the record of exposure relevant data, standardized methods for the collection and preparation of human samples considering the specific needs of chemical analysis, for cryopreservation, biobanking and for the transport of human and environmental samples under cryogenic conditions (DIN EN ISO/IEC 17025 accredited). Fraunhofer IBMT is involved in WP 5.1a (Toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern). All studies performed in this task will be performed according to the OECD guidelines. In year 1 IBMT will perform the in vitro assay HPRT on genotoxicity/mutagenicity (OECD TG 476). These studies are linked to the results of the Ames test and MNT test of the natural toxins. As soon as data of these assays is available, it will be decided if data from HPRT assay is needed and when the studies will be performed.

In WP 5.1b IBMT will study the genotoxicity of BPA alternatives in vitro via the micronucleus test (OECD TG 487). As soon as the set of test substances are defined, the studies will begin.

Fraunhofer IBMT has long-term expertise in advanced in vitro models and in vitro toxicity.

Fraunhofer IBMT is also involved in activity 6.1. (IATA of chemicals/part Genotoxicity). Here IBMT is involved in testing and evaluating the IATA/DAs developed under 6.1.1 through application in case

studies. IBMT will contribute with 2D and 3D in vitro liver models (Mitotox Assay). The contribution of iPSC-based models is under consideration.

16.3 IUF – PIC 998707054 (WP5)

16.4 IfaDo – PIC 998770686 (WP5)

Recently, IfaDo has established techniques, which allow in vitro to in vivo extrapolation to predict hepatotoxicity in relation to oral doses and blood concentrations (Albrecht et al., 2019; Ghallab et al., 2022). In the first year, we will develop this technique further to be able to apply it for compounds that act via metabolic disruption. The technique will include genome-wide RNA profiling and assays that detect lipid droplet formation. At least 10 hepatotoxic and 10 non-hepatotoxic compounds will be tested concentration-dependently in cultured primary hepatocytes and in vitro-to-in vivo extrapolation will be performed. The study will be performed in collaboration with Dr. Philip Marx-Stölting, who coordinates WP5.

16.7 TUB – PIC 999986678 (WP5)

Task 5.1a: Closing data gaps of concern for human health

Subtask 5.1a.1: Natural toxins and closing of identified hazard data gaps regarding enniatins and Alternaria toxins

The TUB lab (Süssmuth) is the partnering lab for the synthesis of selected toxins from fungi. With regard to the expertise of this lab, it is involved in the selection and planning of the synthesis of the enniatins (Activity 2: Enniatins) and the alternariols (Activity 1: Alternaria toxins). The decisions will be made jointly with the partnering labs, which require the material.

16.8 UKON – PIC 999866204 (WP5)

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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17- NEMZETI NEPEGESZSEGUGYI KOZPONT, HUNGARY (NPHC) – PIC: 998706957

The Nemzeti Nepegeszsegugyi Kozpont (National Public Health Center; NPHC) is involved in the work of several WPs. NPHC is one of the co-leaders of the task on sustainability (T.2.3) and will contribute :

- (i) to the design and implementation of a survey among the national hubs to identify the existing knowledge gaps, requests, suggestions to promote the sustainable development of NHs and
- (ii) to the identification of PARC activities that need to be sustainable in WP2. Furthermore, NPHC is one of the co-leaders of the task on the communication, dissemination, and awareness (T.3.2) in WP3. NPHC will contribute to the development of the graphical identity for PARC, the website, the Communication and Dissemination Plan and the first communication products. Regarding WP4, NPHC will prepare new human biomonitoring studies to generate new human biomonitoring data for children and adults. NPHC will start the work on the development of innovative methodologies that will directly aid chemical hazard identification, risk assessment and regulation as well as on AOP development based on integration of in vivo and in vitro datasets in WP5. NPHC will serve as a WP2 contact point in WP9 and will contribute to the translation of the national needs into training programs. NPHC will coordinate the national hub in Hungary.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	Y
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Preparation of communication products will be subcontracted in T3.2. Budget: 100000€	
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

18- HASKOLI ISLANDS, ICELAND (UI) – PIC: 999884246

During the first year of PARC, we will plan the first phase of biomonitoring under WP4.1, prepare questionnaires and apply for ethical permits. We have a knowledge gap on the exposure of Icelanders to PFASs which we need to bridge, but we will also recruit participants from different diet groups, such as Vegetarians and Vegans, to compare with results obtained under HBM4EU. For WP6.1, 6.2 and 6.4.1 we will contribute with recent data of several different priority chemicals in the Icelandic population and considerable experience in epidemiological research under chemical mixture risk assessment with data from 200 participants from our National Nutrition Survey 2020.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

19- MINISTRY OF HEALTH, ISRAEL (MOH) – PIC: 999596156

The Department of Environmental Health at the Ministry of Health in Israel has conducted 3 previous human biomonitoring surveys, in 2011, 2015-2016, and 2020-2021. With the help of the National Human Biomonitoring Lab and the Centers for Disease Control, both within the Ministry of Health, the Department has published findings on exposure of children and adults to environmental chemicals and has used this data to support policies, with focus on pesticide use. MOH will plan recruitment and field work for human biomonitoring study in children and adults, as part of general population HBM survey under the Task 4.1.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

20- ISTITUTO SUPERIORE DI SANITA, ITALY (ISS) – PIC: 999978821

The ISTITUTO SUPERIORE DI SANITA (ISS) will be involved mainly in scientific tasks but also, as GS, in administrative/managerial ones (Task 1.1) and, as NHCP, in networking ones (WP3). In particular, as concerns the former, ISS will be mainly involved in :
 (a) Biomonitoring and exposure activities (WP4);

- (b) Hazard assessment, and in particular by closing data gaps on human health hazards using regulatory accepted methods (Task 5.1a), and quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs (Task 5.3);
- (c) Innovation in risk assessment, and in particular in establishment of Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATAs) (Task 6.1), Review of risk assessment methodology (Task 6.3), and Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies (Task 6.4).
 Although with a lower staff effort, ISS will be also involved in
- (d) The development and implementation of a prioritisation strategy for PARC (Task 2.1),
- (e) FAIR data (WP7), and
- (f) The development and consolidation of new concepts and approaches such as SSbD chemicals (Task 8.1) and of an EWS (Task 8.2).

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?

N

Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*

Y

20.1 ICPS – PIC: 922722395: Given its specific experience on pesticide hazard and exposure assessment and its expertise in handling and processing computerised data even spatial data, it will be a key contributor in Mixture exposure and risk assessment (Task 6.2.3) and in particular will perform case studies addressing the risk of combined exposure to the real-life mixtures based on co-exposure patterns including aggregate exposure.

20.2 CNR-IRSA – PIC 999979500: Given its expertise and since it is currently monitoring PFAS in different matrices (water, soil, sediment, animal and vegetables) in particular in industrial hot spots, CNR-IRSA will be involved in Task 4.2 related to the risk assessment of emerging pollutants, especially PFAS. In particular, for its specific experience on PFAS monitoring and assessment, in the first year it will be a key contributor in review of existing knowledge and infrastructure (Task 4.2.2) and design of targeted monitoring activities (Task 4.2.3).

20.3 – IRFM – PIC 999661146: Given its expertise and facilities, IRFM will contribute within:

- (1) Task 4.3 to the analytical (LC-MS) screening approach using WBE,
- (2) Task 5.2 to the in silico models for non-genotoxic carcinogens,
- (3) Task 5.3 to the use of in silico models to explore mechanisms of action,
- (4) Task 6.1 to the in silico models related to AOP,
- (5) Task 6.2 to the use of in silico models to aggregate substances for mixtures,
- (6) Task 6.3 to the review of in silico models integrating hazard and exposure,
- (7) Task 6.4 to facilitate the use of in silico models for risk assessment,
- (8) Task 8.1 to the in silico approaches useful for safe and sustainable substances, related to the development and optimisation of the ToxEraser software,
- (9) Task 8.2 to the optimisation of early warning in silico tools identifying the presence of substances of concern and
- (10) Task 8.3 to the optimisation of in silico tools for risk.

20.4 IUSS – PIC: 997963355: Given its experience, IUSS will contribute to Tasks 8.1 (Safe and sustainable by design (SSbD)), 8.3 (Integrative models), and 6.2 (Integrative exposure and risk assessment).

20.5 UMIL – PIC 999995796: Given its experience, UMIL will provide its contribution in several WPs, including WP4 (Task 4.1 – Human Biomonitoring), WP5 (Tasks 5.1a – Toxicity testing, 5.3.1

and 5.3.3 - Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs), WP6 (Task 6.3 – Review of Risk Assessment Methodology).

20.6 UNINA – PIC: 999976590: UNINA will be involved as co-leader of WP8 and in relation to this role, it is involved in the Management Board as well as in WP1. Regarding scientific activities, given its expertise, in WP8, UNINA will be involved in the development and consolidation of new concepts and approaches such as SSbD chemicals (Task 8.1), whereas in WP4 it will be involved in Task 4.1 aimed at consolidating, maintaining and further developing the human biomonitoring platform created in HBM4EU.

20.7 UNIPD – PIC 999995602: Given its expertise, UNIPD will be involved in Task 4.1 for the planning and harmonisation of biomonitoring surveys in occupational settings with particular regard to waste treatment and in Task 6.2 to initiate and organise the work to be performed for real-life mixture risk assessment for prioritised mixtures of concern.

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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21- Riga Stradins University, LATVIA (RSU) PIC: 999843118

During the year one, RSU will be involved in:

- Task 1.1. - Overall executive management and support of the Partnership: establishing of local management structure, oversight of NHCP and link to Latvian Biomonitoring council, co-funding issues
- Task 1.2 - Scientific steering and implementation of Annual Work Plans – running the NHCP
- Task 3.2 – Communication, dissemination, and awareness, this task will be done for the whole Latvian participation
- Task 4.1 - Human Biomonitoring
- Sub-Task 4.1.1 - Design, alignment and fieldwork of HBM studies
- Sub-Task 4.1.2 - Laboratory analysis and quality assurance
- Task 6.3 - Review of risk assessment methodology
- Task 9.1.1. Identify existing laboratory networks, draw up and maintain up-to-date and active a database of laboratory networks: initial assessment
- Task 9.4.1 - Training needs identification: initial assessment

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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RSU has one affiliated entity participating in PARC.

21.1 UL- PIC 999871830: The researchers’ team of UL has extensive experience in the development and implementation of sampling and analysis methodologies of a wide range of environmental samples (water, air, soil, indoor air, trees and plants), food, pharmaceutical, industrial materials and consumer products. Considering this, the UL team will be involved in Task 4.2 related to per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs), which are two compound groups of regulatory interest. In the first year, our contribution to activity 4.2.3 in the project design section would be expressed as the compilation of information about existing samples and data obtained in Latvia, which could be useful and valid for the current study.

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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22- NACIONALINE VISUOMENES SVEIKATOS PRIEZIUROS LABORATORIJA, LITHUANIA (NPHSL) – PIC: 933651094	
National Public Health Surveillance Laboratory will participate in PARC as a Grant Signatory. NPHSL will participate in PARC as a key contributor in WP9 tasks 9.1.1; 9.2.1; 9.4.1. NPHSL will focus on identification of existing infrastructures, available knowledge, and various resources. NPHSL will participate in creating a database of laboratory networks. NPHSL shall also be a part of the training needs identification process. NPHSL will also enrol in WP9 tasks 9.1.2; 9.4.4 as a partner where the focus will be on the promotion of development of new laboratory networks as well as on support to the training organisation processes. NPHSL’s participation in WP4 will be concentrated around laboratory analysis and quality assurance.	
Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

23- LIETUVOS SVEIKATOS MOKSLU UNIVERSITETAS, LITHUANIA (LSMU) – PIC : 972782446	
The main tasks LSMU will be attributed during the first year are 4.1, 6.3 and 6.4. As the tasks LSMU will contribute are related to different aspects of biological monitoring (studies, recommendations, etc.) and risk assessment, LSMU can make the analyses of metals / metalloids in different biological and environmental media. The researchers have extensive skills and expertise in the assessment of environmental impact on health, health risk estimation, assessment of exposure-health outcome associations, epidemiology (environmental, occupational, cancer), biostatistics and bioinformatics.	
Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

24- LABORATOIRE NATIONAL DE SANTE, LUXEMBOURG (LNS) – PIC : 911247586	
During the first year of PARC, LNS will contribute to: WP1: Task 1.1 and 1.2 (as Grant Signatory and as NHCP) WP2: Task 2.1 (as NHCP) WP3: Task 3.1 (international board) and Task 3.2 (as partner and as NHCP) WP4: Task 4.1 (sub-tasks 4.1.1 to 4.1.5), Task 4.2 (sub-tasks 4.2.1 to 4.2.5) and Task 4.3 (sub-tasks 4.3.1 and 4.3.3 to 4.3.5) WP5: sub-tasks 5.1.a and 5.2.a	

WP6: Task 6.1, 6.1.2 and 6.1.3, majority of sub-tasks in Task 6.2.1, and Task 6.2.3 (sub-tasks 6.2.3.2 to 6.2.3.4)

WP7: Tasks 7.2.1 to 7.2.3

WP8: Tasks 8.2.1, 8.2.2 and 8.2.4

WP9: Tasks 9.1 to 9.4

Given its expertise and since it is in charge of the laboratory analyses and the epidemiological monitoring in environmental health as well as the national hub role and the representation of the Ministry of Health in the governing board for Luxembourg, LNS will be involved in WPs 3, 4, 6 and 9. In particular, in the first year LNS will be a key partner in Tasks 4.1.1, 4.1.2, 4.1.3, 4.1.5, 4.2, 4.3 and 9.3, and will contribute in the Tasks 1.1 (as National Hub and Grant Signatory), 3.1, 3.2, 4.1.4, 6.2.1 and 6.2.3.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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LNS adheres the 3 Luxembourg research institutes as Affiliated Entities for PARC:

24.1 LIH – PIC 998331858: LIH will contribute to:

- Working meeting – animal protocol writing- ethical authorisation submission and experiment planification according to WP5 consortium exchanges.
- Epigenetic work plan of using to generate an epigenetic clock that tracks changes in neurodevelopmental and behavioural markers in a manner similar to those that track biological ageing (Levine clock; DunedinPoAm clock) based on ASPAC cohort. We anticipate that this clock will be used in the future to investigate the neurodevelopmental impact of early life exposure to pollutants.

24.2 LIST – PIC 934320200: LIST will contribute to:

- Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for Specific Target Organ Toxicity: Design and evaluation of IATAs based on AOP networks and NAMs, including their Evaluation
- Workflow for Human Relevance Assessment of AOPs and Associated New Approach Methodologies: Problem formulation and defining approach; Evaluation of case studies; design of workflow
- Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for Endocrine Disruption: Mapping of existing AOPs and associated NAMs; Selection of regulatory framework(s) and population groups; Identification of relevant AOPs and AOP networks; Quantitation of AOP networks; Design and evaluation of IATA
- Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for Genotoxicity: Mapping of existing AOPs and associated NAMs; Selection of regulatory framework(s) and population groups; Identification of relevant AOPs and AOP networks

24.3 UniLU – PIC 999878620; UniLU will be involved in:

UNILU will apply their extensive expertise in developing open science community resources to support non-target computational mass spectrometry and data science (e.g. NORMAN Suspect List Exchange, MassBank, MetFrag, PubChemLite for Exposomics) in PARC. UNILU will contribute to Task 7.2 (FAIR Data) and support the suspect and non-target screening approaches for monitoring and exposure (Tasks 4.2.5, 4.3.3- 4.3.5) and the early warning system development (Task 8.2.1-2, 8.2.4).

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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25- RIJKSINSTITUUT VOOR VOLKSGEZONDHEID EN MILIEU, NETHERLANDS (RIVM) – PIC : 999991431

In year 1, RIVM will specifically contribute to the following tasks. Firstly, RIVM will act as co-lead for WP6 ‘Innovation in regulatory risk assessment’, and substantially contribute with its expertise to tasks 6.1 (IATA) and task 6.2 (Integrative exposure and RA). In WP8 ‘Concepts and toolboxes’, RIVM will provide a significant contribution by co-leading task 8.1 (SSbD). In WP5 ‘Hazard assessment’, RIVM will contribute with its expertise to activities in task 5.2 that are related to immunotoxicity, developmental neurotoxicity and non-genotoxic carcinogenicity. In year 1, RIVM will specifically contribute to the following tasks. Firstly, RIVM will act as co-lead for WP6 ‘Innovation in regulatory risk assessment’, and substantially contribute with its expertise to tasks 6.1 (IATA) and task 6.2 (Integrative exposure and RA). RIVM is project leader of the project on human relevance (task 6.1) and on real-life mixtures (task 6.2) and contributes to several projects in task 6.1 on IATAs and in task 6.2 on integrative risk assessment. In the capacity of WP leads, RIVM supports task 6.1 and 6.2 leaders with writing annual progress reports and workplans, identifying new projects. In WP8 ‘Concepts and toolboxes’, RIVM will provide a significant contribution by co-leading task 8.1 (SSbD). Focus will be on setting up a structured infrastructure aiming at (separate) dialogues with the Commission, Internal PARC partners and External stakeholders. This is essential as several knowledge points need to be connected. Additionally we will focus on making an overview of the state of the art in SSbD and as such assessing needs, potential gaps and barriers. Primary goal is to kick start the project by building on the existing knowledge and aiming at a flourishing infrastructure for cooperation. In WP5 ‘Hazard assessment’, RIVM will contribute with its expertise and with experimental work (in vitro studies) to activities in task 5.2a that are related to immunotoxicity, developmental neurotoxicity and non-genotoxic carcinogenicity.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y

AEs will participate in different tasks in PARC in the first year as follows.

25.1 KWR – PIC: 998279769: will contribute with their expertise to WP4 (task 4.3), WP6 (tasks 6.1 and 6.2), and WP7 (tasks 7.1 and 7.3). KWR Water Research Institute (KWR) is involved in task 4.3, contributing to the development of analysis methods to detect and measure exposure biomarkers in wastewater-based epidemiology for monitoring human exposure to environmental pollutants. In task 6.1, KWR contributes to the development of integrated approaches for testing and assessing potentially adverse effects of substances, by using existing and New Approach methods (in vitro assays/bioassays and in silico methods) for genotoxicity assessment as used in water quality assessment. In task 6.2, KWR will apply their model that was developed to evaluate exposure to lead also to determine exposure to other substances in drinking water and contribute to refine available models/tools for the risk assessment of PFAS. In task 7.1 KWR contributes to the efforts needed to safeguard good data quality and availability, and in task 7.3 to the knowledge relating to the statistical methods including uncertainty that may be applied. All these activities are initiated in year 1 and applied in case studies at a later stage.

25.2 TNO – PIC: 999988909: will co-lead and contribute to task 7.1. Furthermore, TNO will contribute to tasks 4.3 and 6.2. TNO is involved in WP 4, 6 and 7. Given the expertise of TNO in exposure assessment and advanced exposome sampling technologies, TNO is involved in WP4 in task 4.3.1 which focusses on innovative sampling approaches for individuals in community exposure assessment. After the split of the task into projects, TNO is now involved in Project 4.3_H02 which aims to provide proof of concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based EDA screening methods for exploring occupational exposure to chemicals of emerging concern. In the first year TNO actively contributes to the discussions and further development of the workplans in this project. Taking into account TNO’s expertise in aggregate exposure modelling and PBPK, TNO is also involved in tasks 6.2.1 which focusses on the project on aggregated exposure from multiple sources and routes for the general

population and workers. In task 6.2.2 (modelling exposure through life) TNO contributes with extensive knowledge of PBPK modelling, specifically focused on two case studies (PFAS and pesticides) as follow-up of the HBM4EU project and we further develop the PBPK model on isocyanates. Further, TNO is coordinating WP7, Task 7.1, in which TNO is instrumental in the development of the PARC FAIR data policy, associated PARC data management plan and creating FAIR awareness. These activities are overarching of PARC and pivotal to ensuring the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of data generated within PARC for current and future use in (the innovation of) chemical risk assessment.

25.3 RUMC – PIC: 892057785: will contribute with their expertise to tasks 4.1 and 6.2.

24.4 UL-LACDR – PIC: 999974553: will act as co-lead of tasks 5.3 and 6.1. UL-LACDR will also contribute with their expertise to task 5.2, WP7 (tasks 7.1-7.3) and task 8.3.

25.5 UU-IRAS – PIC 999985805: will contribute to WP4, in particular to tasks 4.1 and 4.3, task 5.2, WP6 (tasks 6.1 and 6.2), WP7 (tasks 7.1-7.3), WP8 (tasks 8.2 and 8.3), and WP9 (tasks 9.2 and 9.3). In WP7, they act as lead of task 7.3. Given its expertise Utrecht University is involved as key contributor in the following tasks in PARC Task 4.1 (primarily contributing to innovative methods and statistical analyses), Task 5.2a focused on the Effects of BPA alternatives and natural toxins on the neuro-immuno-endocrine system, Task 5.2b focused on Developing and improving NAMs for Immunotoxicity, Contribution to T6.1 will involve IATAs on metabolic disruption, following the completion of the EURION projects at the end 2023, 6.2 (primarily contributing to Mixture exposure and risk assessment and to Human health impact assessment and risk indicators).

25.6 VUA – PIC: 954530344: will contribute to tasks 4.2 and 4.3, and act as co-lead of task 4.3. Additionally, VUA will contribute to tasks 5.2, 6.4 and 8.2.

The expertise of VUA in the field of environmental and human toxicology and – chemistry is embedded in several tasks of PARC. In WP4, task 4.3, where Marja Lamoree acts as task co-lead, VUA will contribute to the method innovations for suspect and nontarget screening and effect-directed analysis with a focus on both environmental and human exposure assessment. Within WP4, VUA has a minor role in task 4.2 in order to ensure alignment of the work embedded in tasks 4.2 and 4.3.

In WP5, VUA will contribute to the development of innovative hazard assessment tools, focusing on thyroid hormone system disruption. For the assessment of the presence of chemicals in articles/consumer products embedded in task 6.4.3 (WP6), VUA will contribute state-of-the-art analytical methods to identify potentially toxic chemicals. In close relationship with the work envisaged in task 4.3, VUA has a role in WP8, task 8.2 to contribute to the development of early warning monitoring tools.

In the first year, the VUA activities are mainly in task 4.3, the advancement of effect-directed analysis in combination with suspect and nontarget screening for the identification of chemicals, and task 5.2 focusing on innovations in the assessment of thyroid system disruption. In both tasks, VUA is embedded in the core team of projects that have started in year 1 of PARC.

25.7 WR – PIC: 999547365: will act as co-lead for tasks 8.3 and 9.3. Furthermore, WR will contribute to tasks 4.3, 5.2, 5.3, 6.1, 6.2, 7.3, 8.2, 8.3 and 9.3. Two groups from WR, each with its specific expertise, are involved in PARC, namely WR-WFSR and WR-Biometris. The contribution of the Biometris group concerns the alignment of data infrastructures and modelling platforms (Task 7.3), the further development of the MCRA data and modelling platform, better modelling of the exposure and hazards of chemical substances in food and the integration of models (Task 8.3 lead). WFSR will contribute to the development of innovative methods for monitoring external (food) and internal exposure (human biomonitoring), with an emphasis on non-target/suspect screening (Task 4.3), and the establishment of non-animal approaches for (early) identification and characterization of chemical

hazards in the food chain (Tasks 5.2, 5.3, 6.1, 6.2, 8.2). In addition, WFSR will contribute to the harmonization of quality assurance/quality control (QA/QC) of laboratory analyses (Task 9.3 lead).

25.8 WU-TOX – PIC: 999981634: will mainly contribute to task 6.1. Additionally, WU-TOX will contribute to tasks 5.1 and 5.3, and task 8.3.

Given our background in toxicokinetics and (in vitro) toxicodynamics WU-TOX will be involved mainly in WP 5 and WP 6. Our activities in Task 5.1a will initially be to follow the discussion and join the experimental work in year 2 of the project. For Task 5.2a (non-genotoxic carcinogens toxicogenomics) we postponed our involvement for later in the project. WU-TOX is actively engaged within Task 5.3 on PBK modelling which will be tightly coupled to our main input in WP 6, specifically on Task 6.1 on specific case studies where we will perform in vitro toxicity studies. It is essential to select the PARC prioritized chemical (i.e. mycotoxins) and use these both in Task 5.3 and Task 6.1 as PBK models and data from in vitro studies need to be connected to advance the risk assessment paradigm. Lastly WU-TOX is following the discussion on model integration in WP8, where we foresee a contribution in future years of PARC.

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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26- FOLKEHELSEINSTITUTTET, NORWAY (NIPH) – PIC: 999478883

During the first year of PARC, NIPH will contribute to:

Task 5.1 – NIPH is task leader and will close hazard data gaps on human health. Managing the activities, interactions with agencies and reporting to the WP leaders/MB is included in the task leader role. Initially two mycotoxins will be studied in 5.1 and NIPH will contribute e with experimental work. NIPH will also contribute to tasks 5.2 and 5.3 with further refinement of the plans, interactions with agencies, experimental work and data

NIPH will contribute to activities in all sub-tasks in 4.1. We foresee preparatory work to involve our Norwegian Environmental Biobank (NEB) in the general population survey, and contribution to activities related to Laboratory analysis and quality assurance. Especially contributions in HBM-guidance values and Data analysis are planned. NIPH will also contribute to several activities under 6.1, 6.2, 9.1 and 9.3 with further refinement of the plans, contribution of data and collection of data. Task 6.4.2 – NIPH, represented by VKM, will also participate in the project “Next generation risk assessment applied in practice”

The experimental infrastructure at NIPH (including VKM) as described in the partner description (bioanalytical labs, in vitro labs), register- and biobank studies (MoBa, NEB, HUMIS, EuroMix) and experience with systematic literature reviews and risk assessment will be used in the planned work.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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AEs will participate in different tasks in PARC in the first year:

26.1 IMR – PIC: 999548432 will contribute to task 5.1 with their expertise in computational in silico prediction and untargeted mass spectrometric detection of chemicals in feed and food, in silico (Q)SAR-based toxicity predictions and hazard ranking of enniatin metabolites detected in feed and food based on a combination of both predicted toxicities and occurrence data. HI will also contribute with expertise in toxicoproteomics, toxicogenomics and multi-omics analyses.

26.2 STAMI – PIC: 953521738 will participate in the tasks 2.2 and 3.1 using their extensive stakeholder network within occupational health.

In T4.1 STAMI will engage in biomonitoring studies with expertise from toxicology, chemistry, and medicine, and in T4.3, our activities will include suspect screening approaches (chemistry).

In T5.1, STAMI will participate in toxicity testing of mycotoxins (toxicology).

In T6.1, STAMI will participate in the development and evaluation of IATAs, and in stakeholder engagement (toxicology, chemistry, and medicine). STAMI will aid in the evaluation of aggregate exposure from multiple sources, and mixture exposure and risk assessment in T6.2 (toxicology, chemistry, and medicine). STAMI participates in several regulatory toxicology case studies in T6.3 (toxicology, medicine, and chemistry). STAMI will contribute to T6.4.

In T9.1, STAMI will work on identifying and maintaining existing lab networks, and aid in the establishment of new lab networks within toxicology and chemistry. STAMI will focus on mapping of exposure monitoring capacities in T9.2 (toxicology and chemistry). The institutes activities in T9.3 will include QA/QC in chemical analysis and toxicity studies. In T9.4, STAMI will aid in identifying training needs and existing training courses within occupational health (toxicology and chemistry).

26.3 NILU – PIC 999654162 will contribute to tasks 4.2 and 4.3 with their expertise and analytical capacity (targeted, non-targeted and suspect screening approaches). In task 2.2 NILU will contribute with its knowledge on risk assessment and risk governance developed in H2020 RiskGone project.

In task 2.3, NILU will contribute with its knowledge of safe by design and sustainability on nanomaterials that will be further developed and applicable also to other emerging contaminants.

NILU will be involved in task 8.1 on safe and sustainable by design by offering perspectives and modelling capacity on the developing the methodology and the toolbox (activity 8.1.3) and support activities under 8.1.1 and 8.1.2. In task 8.2 NILU will contribute to the design of standardised protocols for early warning monitoring tools and to defining the concepts and requirements of suspect/non-targeted/EDA-based tools.

26.4 NIVA – PIC: 997826585 will contribute to tasks T5.2b with their expertise in in silico predictions, effects modelling and experimental approaches for NAM development and hazard characterisation. NIVA will also contribute in preliminary discussions and landscaping work in T6.4 with experience and knowhow related to the assessment of, implementation and regulatory practices of chemical mixture assessment. The NIVA computational platform, including advanced modelling approaches, exposure, effect and risk assessment tools, will be used to advance work in T7.2.1 to T7.2.4 on environmental risk assessment, data re-use, data/ontology standardisation and harmonisation to support FAIRification processes. The computational models and platforms available at NIVA will be aligned with other tools to supporting developing, evaluating, operationalising and implementation of integrative models and networks in T8.3.

26.5 NMBU – PIC: 999902967 will contribute to tasks 2.1, 2.2, 3.1 by actively using their professional networks within food safety, environmental chemistry, toxicology and health. NMBU is involved in several national and international environmental monitoring activities. These results will be made available for the initiation of tasks 4.1., 4.2. and 4.3. NMBU will support the development of meta-databases on monitoring in Europe and the development of innovative tools for biomonitoring. The extensive expertise of NMBU in risk and hazard assessment in food, human exposure and environment will be applied for single compound and mixture assessment (task 5.1., 5.2., 5.3). Innovative new strategies will be recommended, assessed and integrated into comprehensive toolboxes aiming to provide effective support for international risk assessors (task 8.1). NMBU will actively include already established international networks into the PARC activities (task 9.1.1.). This will include the Norwegian Toxicological community, collaboration with NORMAN, and other collaborations. Furthermore, our professional networks overseas (US, Canada, China, India, etc) will be implemented. (task 9.1.2, 9.1.3). In addition, NMBU will actively participate in a PARC associated database and a designated PARC interactive web-based to navigate the database (9.1.4).

26.6 NVI – PIC 999511378: will contribute to task 5.1 with their expertise in chemical analysis as well

as with in vitro toxicology, toxicokinetics and risk assessment of mycotoxins in feed and food. NVI will in the first year establish a new 3D in vitro model for human gastrointestinal tract in their lab and perform preliminary studies of enniatins and alternaria toxins on inflammation, and intestinal barrier function. Furthermore, we can analyse TK samples from other partners for metabolites of enniatins.

26.7 UNN – PIC: 991888051 will contribute to WP 4.1.2 with laboratory analysis and its expertise in applications for high throughput methods together with the use of low sample volumes for analysis where limited sample material is available. UNN will contribute to WP 9.3 with expertise on development, validation and verification of targeted analytical methods for different compounds and compound groups as well as matrices with main focus on human samples.

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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27- INSTYTUT MEDYCZYNY PRACY IMIENIA PROF. DRA MED. JERZEGO NOFERA W LODZI, POLAND (NIOM) – PIC: 999835940

The main task which NIOM will be attributed is:

Activity 1.1.1: Partnership Management and coordination

Work Plan M1-M12: Coordination and the strategic and administrative management of project in Poland in cooperation with the affiliated entities. Cooperation with leader of project.

Activity 4.1.1: Monitoring and Exposure-Human Biomonitoring

Work Plan M1-M12: Continue on-going activities on some case studies performed in HBM4EU. Based on a previous survey under HBM4EU, provide justifications to the pre-nominations (policy questions) and to gather data against the prioritisation criteria. Analysis of data from HBM4EU aligned studies to identify occupationally exposed groups.

Activity 6.2.1: Aggregate exposure from multiple sources and routes for general population and workers

Work Plan M1-M12: Evaluation of aggregate exposure from multiple sources and routes for the general population and for workers. Inventory of existing models and tools for general population and occupational exposure assessment and data gaps. Strategy for aggregate exposure from general life and occupational exposures. Modelling aggregate exposure of general population.

Activity 6.4.1. Develop regulatory relevant approaches and methods for chemical mixtures Work Plan

M1-M12: Identify the regulators needs and map the tools already at hand; identify the gaps associated with use of data sciences in the regulatory context; the institutional, organisational, technological barriers, and opportunities for use of machine learning in chemical risk assessment.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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27.1 IEP-NRI – PIC: 998750316: The main WP/task which IEP-NRI will be attributed is: WP 5 (task 5.1b) and WP 6 (task 6.4.4). The IEP-NRI has been a partner of NIOM in the implementation of national, statutory programmes on environmental impacts on population exposure for many years. AE's status is justified e.g. by the cooperation agreement. With more than 20 years of experience involved in PPP pre-registration evaluation and biomonitoring method development, IEP-NRI will make significant contributions to:

-WP 5.1b on testing of BPA alternatives and related mixtures (lab.GLP). In the first year, it will prepare the state of the art on methodologies.

-WP 6.4 related to environmental risk assessment and e-fate for toxic substances in the environment (in the study).

-WP6.4.4 concerning the links between ecological and chemical status and the effects of hazardous

substances on aquatic organisms. Preparation of existing knowledge will be key in the first year. Institute of Environmental Protection - National Research Institute (IEP-NRI), AE of NIOM plan to subcontract Review of national data regarding occurrence of agrochemicals. Currently available resources (especially human) are not sufficient to fully address this activity under 6.4. IEP-NRI has numerous external (i.e. unemployed) experts with whom successful cooperation was previously established under other European and domestic projects. Procedure of choosing external expert will follow project, EU, polish and IEP-NRI internal regulation of subcontracting

27.2 UG-PL – PIC: 999876001: The main WP/task which UG will be attributed is: WP4 (task 4.2.1; 4.2.2; 4.2.3;4.2.4;4.3.1;4.3.3); WP5 (task 5.1b;5.2a,5.2b;5.3.2), WP6 (task 6.1.1;6.1.2;6.1.3;6.2.3;6.3; 6.4.2), WP7 (task 7.1.1; 7.1.2), WP8 (task 8.1.3;8.2.1;8.2.2;8.2.4). The UG has been a partner of NIOM in the implementation of national, statutory programmes in the development new generation risk assessment. AE's status is justified e.g. by the cooperation agreement. UG-PL will give an expertise in two areas: (i) experimental exposure and hazard assessment (ii) data analysis and chemoinformatic with particular emphasis on the development of efficient computational methods for risk assessment. In the first year, UG-PL will mainly contribute to data collection, critical review of literature as well as design of the computational activities in different tasks (Task 5.2.a, 5.2b, 5.3, 6.1, 6.2.3, 6.2.4, 7.1, 7.2, 8.1, and 8.2) as well as to Task 4.3. in terms of complementary developments regarding the application of HRMS based in the analysis of environmental samples.

27.3 WULS-SGGW – PIC 999865137. The main WP/task which WULS will be attributed is: WP 4 (task 4.1.1; 4.1.2; 4.3.1). The WULS has been a partner of NIOM in the implementation of national, statutory programmes on change in metabolomics pathways in environmental and occupational exposure condition. AE's status is justified e.g. by the cooperation agreement. Taking into account its expertise and as it is currently monitoring the metabolic effects of exposure to chemicals in various biological materials (serum, urine), in particular at industrial hotspots, WULS will be involved in Tasks 4.3 and 4.1 related to the analysis of changes in metabolism using suspect and non-targeted screening approaches (sample preparation and data acquisition, data processing and multivariate analysis). In particular, due to special experience in research in the field of non-targeted metabolomics and lipidomics in various population groups, in the first year WULS will be a contributor in Task 4.1 - T4.1.1d Occupational surveys (waste management study, health care study). Additionally, we declared participation in the following studies: Task 4.1 General survey in children, general survey in teenagers, targeted studies: study on adults (40-69y): environmental exposures and risk factors for common diseases in the adult population >39y, hotspot HBM - connected with ambient monitoring (children/adults As hotspot).

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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28- FACULDADE DE MEDICINA DA UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA, PORTUGAL (FMUL) – PIC: 999888320

During the first year of PARC, FMUL will be involved in task 1.1, 2.3, 3.1a, 3.1b, 3.2, 3.3, 6.2.1, 6.2.4, 8.1.3, 8.1.4, 9.1.1, 9.1.2, 9.1.3, 9.1.4, 9.2.1 and 9.2.2. During this period, FMUL’s work in each task will be as follows:

Task 1.1. As Grant Signatory, FMUL will be responsible for all management issues (legal, financial and administrative) for itself and its Affiliated Entities;

Task 2.3. Collaboration in the initial characterization of the needs and expertise of the national hubs (NHs).

Tasks 3.1a and 3.1b. Collaboration in the process of establishment of the Stakeholder Forum and International Board.

Task 3.2. Collaboration in the mapping of the needs of NHs and exit strategy.

Task 3.3. Collaboration in the establishment of external communication rules for PARC, development

of an inventory of partnerships, projects/networks relevant for PARC, and development of the initial synergies network (SYNet).
 Task 6.2.1. Collaboration in the development of an inventory of existing models and tools for general population and of a data inventory and gap analysis
 Task 6.2.4. Collaboration in the establishment of an inventory of HIA data (and methodologies) for PARC priority chemicals, namely endocrine disruptors, and of an inventory and comparison of current definitions, methodologies, and frameworks of HIA for chemical exposure.
 Task 8.1.3. Collaboration of an inventory of relevant indicators to follow the progresses of sector applicability of the toolbox, in the identification of the most optimal set of parameters for selecting potential use cases to test the methodology developed by the EC and in the test of the applicability of the EC SSbD criteria and methodology
 Task 8.1.4. Collaboration in the development of a structural process to share knowledge and information about operationalisation of SSbD, including the initial characterization of the state of the art about the toolbox.
 Task 9.1.1. Collaboration in the identification of existing laboratory networks.
 Task 9.1.2. Collaboration in the definition of strategies to promote new laboratory networks.
 Task 9.1.3. Collaboration in the coordination and linkage of existing and new laboratory networks.
 Task 9.1.4. Collaboration in the development of an interactive dashboard to show the capacities of the laboratory networks.
 Tasks 9.2.1 and 9.2.2. Collaboration in the collection of inventories in biomonitoring networks and population cohorts.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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FMUL has two affiliated entities participating in PARC.

28.1 PL – PIC: 996273421: The participation of PL will be considered under WP4 and 9 for the future years of PARC.

28.2 UM – PIC: 999995505:
 The University of Minho (UM) has been involved in international projects for Environmental Tobacco Smoke Exposure Monitoring.
 In this context, UM would like to participate in the monitoring of children's environmental tobacco smoke, exposure.
 Study, environmental smoke exposure and smoking behavior in outdoor environments, such as terraces, playgrounds, etc. (4.2 Environmental Monitoring)
 In this first year, we can review the literature on studies in this area

UM and FMUL have been involved in joint research projects in the last decade in the areas of environmental health, human biomonitoring and smoking.

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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29- INSTITUTO NACIONAL DE SAUDE DR. RICARDO JORGE, PORTUGAL (INSA) – PIC: 998308190
 INSA will participate in WPs 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 9. During the 1st year INSA will be involved in Tasks 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 2.3, 3.1, 3.2, 4.1, 5.2, 6.2, 6.4, 9.1, 9.2 and 9.3, assuming a (co) leader role in WP3 and Tasks 1.3, 2.2, 3.3, 5.1 and 9.4.

INSA research groups hold expertise in the development of population-based studies, including HBM studies, in vitro and in vivo toxicological investigation and chemicals RA. INSA has fully equipped laboratories and a complete pipeline for analysis of human biological and environmental samples (e.g. Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometer, Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer, and HPLC) and for cell and molecular toxicology studies. It has bioimaging and state of the art genomics- and proteomics facilities (next-generation sequencing platform with bioinformatics support and 2DIGE-Mass Spectrometry) and certified animal facilities. It is also well-equipped to handle information of personal and sensitive nature and has installed a secure data collection software (REDCap), allowing the swift launch of web-based surveys. Through the participation in large EU Programs and networks INSA established collaborations with EU institutions, public health institutes, academy, and reference laboratories. It has a pivotal role in training activities and knowledge dissemination to citizens, professionals, regulators and policy makers and has facilities and support from informatics and communication offices on events organisation. In the first year of PARC, due to its experience in indicators assessment within the HBM4EU Initiative, INSA will work together with DOMG, BE partners, and the MB to set up the monitoring framework for PARC. In the scope of its role of task 2.2 co-leader, INSA will contribute to the development and implementation of PARC's knowledge management platform PARCopedia and work on the appointment procedure and Terms of Reference (ToR) for chemical leaders (CLs) and methodology leaders (MLs) and in the appointment of a first group of CLs/MLs. INSA and GCSL will lead WP3 on synergies, collaboration and awareness and will also participate in its different tasks, being co-leader of task 3.3 on networking and synergies. Building from previous experience in the HBM4EU aligned studies and within WP4 INSA will collaborate in the design, planning, and implementation of general population HBM surveys. Furthermore, INSA will participate in the design and planning of an occupational study focused on the waste management sector, following the previous involvement in a preliminary study conducted under the HBM4EU. INSA will also collaborate in the feasibility study aiming to evaluate occupational exposures using data from general population surveys (HBM4EU Aligned Studies and other studies) and in the implementation of sentinel surveillance systems as a tool to collect representative data on environmental and occupational exposure and health. Furthermore, given INSA's analytical capacity and the work developed under HBM4EU, INSA will collaborate in the definition of exposure biomarkers and in the analysis of effect biomarkers. INSA will also be involved in the development of the roadmap to explore links between exposure and health concerns and in the preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe. Under WP4, Task 4.1, INSA will also collaborate in the further analysis of the data generated within HBM4EU. INSA will participate also in WP5 given the expertise in toxicological studies and, particularly, in tasks 5.1 on toxicity testing to address data gaps and task 5.2 on the development of novel methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling. In task 5.1 INSA will assume a co-leading role and also participate in the planning and toxicity testing of natural toxins and bisphenol alternatives. INSA will participate in WP6 on risk assessment, particularly in the aggregate exposure assessment for the general population and workers, health impact assessment and in facilitating the regulatory acceptance of new methods. Finally, under WP9 activities, INSA will lead the identification of initial training needs in close collaboration with the remaining PARC WPs, via a dedicated survey.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y

29.1 APA – PIC: 917950286:

The Portuguese Environment Agency (APA) PARC will be involved in WP 3 - Synergies, collaborations and awareness T3.1 (Building Effective Interactions - Stakeholders forum), T3.2 (Communication, dissemination and awareness) and T3.3 (Networking and Synergies) and is the

National Hub Contact point (NHCP).

During the first year and subsequent years the Portuguese Environment Agency (APA) will be engaged in using of its competences on the promotion of education, training and awareness of the environment and sustainable development to give inputs to Task 3.2, the implementation of strategies and actions that enable the collection, dissemination and exchange of information that facilitate access to information and public participation in decision-making processes on the environment and sustainable development will be a support to Tasks 3.1 and 3.3.

The APA, supports numerous initiatives of educational nature and mobilization of society for environmental issues and sustainability in collaboration with stakeholders from different sectors of the society this will be a good support to task 3.1 and 3.3.

As NHCP at PARC, APA will continue the joint work at Human Biomonitoring National Hub which is member since the first moments (HBM4EU). There is a protocol among the Health, Education, Environment entities that supports the work of the PT National Hub.

29.2 DGS – PIC: 986364095: DGS will participate in PARC in WP2, task 2.1, WP6, task 6.3 and WP8, task 8.2. There is already an established relationship between DGS and INSA since INSA already works closely with DGS in the surveillance, health monitoring and epidemiological research and we are under the same Ministry as stated in DL124_2011 - lei orgânica Min Saúde Ligação INSA_DGS as stated in page 2 (art. 5º) and pg 4. (art. 12ª).

29.3 ENSP – PIC: 960782479: ENSP will be involved in the following WPs: WP3, WP4, WP6 and WP9. There is a legal link between INSA and ENSP in what concerns research and training activities as well as a collaboration in research programs and projects of mutual interest. Given its expertise on the uptake of the innovative science into regulatory risk assessment practice, ENSP will be involved in Task 2.2 related to the knowledge management and uptake into policy. In particular, due to its specific experience on regulatory risk assessment, in the first year it will be an important contributor in developing roadmaps in line with the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) and ensure the adequate uptake of research into different regulatory processes including REACH and Chemicals' Strategy for Sustainability.

29.4 UC – PIC: 997826391: University of Coimbra (UC) is a public higher education institution founded in 1290, whose mission comprises three pillars: Education, Research and Knowledge Transfer. INSA and UC signed a protocol for the development of research in scientific fields of common interest. As an AE of INSA, UC will participate in PARC through its Research Centre for Functional Ecology - Science for People & the Planet (CFE) in WP6, respectively Task 6.4.4 due to the team's expertise in Risk Assessment. There is a cooperation agreement between INSA and UC under the scope of scientific and academic activities in common areas.

29.5 UAVR – PIC 999865331: UAVR is involved in WP3, WP5, WP6, WP9. Regarding WP5, we are involved in several projects within the environmental part: in Task 5.1.b, the toxicity of natural toxins and their mixtures and combination with other cooccurring substances to micro algae, and the effects BPA alternatives and associated mixtures to several aquatic species (in vivo and in vitro). Regarding Human and Health, we are participating in T5.1a, within the molecular alteration underlying bisphenol-associated male infertility and within T5.2a, the development of NAMs based on semen biomonitoring. In WP6, we were already included in the environmental part of the mixture risk assessment, considering our expertise and our long term work in mixture prediction hazard assessment. Within this, we are participating in discussion for the environmental part within T6.4 (scoping document and risk assessment approach towards biodiversity protection), but also in using an integrative approach to include the environment in T6.1 and 6.2. IN WP9, our involvement will be mostly on the training activities (T9.4), and we also contributed with information for T9.1 on the Laboratory networking.

Regarding WP3, our activities have not been very active but we are starting looking at synergies with other projects and stakeholders at national level (e.g. ETERNAL project starting date september 2022) within T3.3. In addition and regarding T3.2 we are considering the potentials for communication, dissemination, and awareness at the national level.

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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30- SLOVENSKA ZDRAVOTNICKA UNIVERZITA V BRATISLAVE, SLOVAKIA (SZU-SK) – PIC: 999859802

Within PARC, SZU-SK is in the position of NHCP. In the 1st year, SZU-SK will work on NH extension, approaching stakeholders and institutions in the area of chemical risk assessment, in a cooperation with AE. Within WP4, SZU-SK will contribute to the Task 4.1 based on its long-time experience in human biomonitoring, regarding both, field epidemiological studies and analytical methods. SZU-SK will be involved in laboratory analysis and quality assurance of analyses of the PARC prioritised substances, will contribute to selection of exposure biomarkers, to the harmonization of analytical methods across laboratories and to the selection of a reference method, and will provide expertise in data management and statistical analyses focused on linking exposures to environmental chemicals to exposure and effect biomarkers and associated health effects. Within WP9, SZU-SK will be involved in laboratory networking through contribution to identification of existing networks and mapping of exposure monitoring capacities. SZU-SK will identify existing laboratory networks at the national level (Slovak Republic) and members of international laboratory networks as well as European Reference Laboratories at the level of its professional field of work (heavy metals, persistent organic pollutants).

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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30.1 UK – PIC 999841566: Within the 1st year of PARC, UK will be mainly active in laboratory networking in WP9, task 9.1 Building the HBM laboratory network catalogue, involved in mapping of existing laboratory networks and their capacities. According to its expertise, UK will also join the activities in task 4.1 (subtask 4.1.1 and 4.1.2) focused on issues concerning human biomonitoring and laboratory analyses.

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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31- INSTITUT JOZEF STEFAN, SLOVAKIA (SZU-SK) – PIC: 999971837

During the first year of PARC, JSI will contribute to:

- WP1: Coordination and management of AEs associated with JSI.
- WP2: Establishment of effective mutual communication and activities between societal regulatory partners, 1 hubs/contact at the national.
- WP3: Contribution to activities 3.2 (dissemination strategy) and 3.3 (synergies and collaborations).
- WP4: HBM design (T4.1) and its implementation on children and teenagers. Contribution will be through established National HBM campaign, analytical laboratory and ICT infrastructures, and existing databases. Identification and quantification of organic contaminants including endocrine disruptors and new PFAS compounds. Development and optimisation of innovative sampling methods (DBS, hair) for exploring biomarkers of exposure in human samples using HRMS and MS/MS based analysis (T4.2). Complementarily, adapt our HRMS based workflows for NT/SS in HBM and for environmental samples.). We will also provide data from wastewater treatment plants for human community and environmental exposure assessment. In collaboration with health experts our scientific

contribution in T4.1, T4.2 and T4.3 we will provide the scientific literature review focusing on quality of exposure data for linkage with health data, methodological approaches used in the studies and data gap analysis. JSI has been engaged in NT/SS workflows in HBM, environmental, food analysis. We have been developing innovative sampling methods (including passive samplers, WBE, preparation of solid human/animal tissues, DBS) to support HBM and environmental analysis. Laboratories for sample preparation in organic analysis and infrastructure available as part of the Centre for mass spectrometry (CMS) at JSI, in particular LC- and GC- coupled tandem and HR mass spectrometers, including LC-Orbitrap MS (to be installed by the end of 2021).

-WP6: T6.2.1: In collaboration with health experts we will provided systematic review or SWOT analysis in the field of regulatory risk assessment for selected chemicals. We will focusing on EU legislation, god practices and national approaches (in collaboration with T6.3). The work within the tasks T6.3 (CS2, CS3) will comprise of the “evaluation of efficiency of current practices” by increasing the understanding of how to measure the effectiveness of risk assessment aimed at reducing risk. Specifically, this will address the differences in data requirement and resource needs between methods for evaluating the effectiveness of risk assessment for risk reduction. The results will be used to guide future design of regulation and risk assessment of chemicals towards adequate and feasible evaluation methods.

-WP7: We will identify relevant data sources and data mining (DM) tasks, for which we will draft initial DM pipelines (7.3.3). In this context, we will identify interoperability issues and needs for FAIR principles (7.1.2) and identify relevant reference ontologies and needs for their further development/harmonisation (7.1.3). Inventory of methods for combining different sources of uncertainties in exposure assessment will be made within 7.3.2.

In the context of 7.2 task, JSI will perform initial landscaping exercise of existing and planned (initiatives for) databases, repositories, platforms, portals on a national level. The most considerable contribution will be through establishment of internal ICT infrastructure as part of an overall architecture.

-WP9: Contributing to network activities, particularly on human biomonitoring, environmental (air, indoor, water and soil) and food & feed, for both, target and non-target analysis, contributing to the establishment of the research infrastructure related to the exposure and monitoring capacities, including metrological component and harmonisation of approaches related to methodological part of HBM. Design of the training and capacity building activity.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
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Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	Y
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31.1 GEOZS – PIC: 999466370: In the first year, GeoZS will be involved in WP6 (Task 6.2., Activity 6.2.1). Within activities 6.2.1.1 and 6.2.1.2 GeoZS will gather data from available inventory (concentrations in media from existing studies) and knowledge on various environmental media (soil, dust (household, attic, street)), airborne particles in urban and mining areas to study the main exposure sources. In the activity 6.2.1.3 GeoZS will help in selecting relevant case studies.

31.2 NIB – PIC: 999650476: In the first year, NIB will be involved in WP3 (Task3.1, 3.2 and 3.3) and WP5 (Task5.1a, 5.1b, 5.2a and 5.2b). Within Task3.1 NIB will participate in the activities related to the Stakeholder Forum, within Task3.2 it will be involved in the Communication plan and the activities related to the Citizens surveys, while in Task3.3 it will participate in the activities related to the Research for R&I and possible collaborations, contacts and setting up of database that will be prepared within WP3.

Within the Task 5.1a NIB will be involved in the research on mutagenicity of *Alternaria* toxins using standardised methodology – Ames assay according to the OECD 471. Furthermore, in Task5.1b NIB will participate in the studies of the adverse effects of bisphenol mixtures in *Danio rerio* (zebrafish) embryos by performing Fish Embryo Acute Toxicity Test (OECD TG 236). With its specific expertise in advanced in vitro 3D cell models, NIB will perform genotoxicity studies within Task 5.2a and Task5.2b using human and zebrafish 3D cell models, respectively.

31.3 NIC – PIC: 998756718: The first task (set up the chemicals) will be done in the cooperation within the consortium of PARC. For the selected compounds we will calculate (optimise) their chemical structures, structural descriptors and compile physico-chemical data, like log P values, solubility, transport coefficients, etc. For selected chemicals, we will calculate the toxic properties using available models (VEGA HUB, OECD Toolbox, DEREK, T.E.S.T., available QSAR models) and perform the read across grouping. The original set of chemicals will be extended with chemicals belonging to the same chemical categories. The extended set results from read across analysis. Duration of task 2 is: 3-9 months. We will search the literature and official dossiers for further toxicity data and the 'big data' related to the toxicities (proteomic data, genomic data, high-through put in vitro data). Duration of tasks 3 and 4 is: 6-12 months.

31.4 ULFFA – PIC: 999923240: ULFFA will participate in the project in WP4, WP5 and WP9, as it has extensive experience in bioanalytical method development for sensitive detection and quantification of xenobiotics in various human and animal samples, including blood plasma, blood serum, red blood cells, leukocytes, urine, skin, muscle and brain tissue. They have all the necessary instrumentation, including the sample preparation facilities and ultrahigh performance liquid chromatographs coupled to mass spectrometers for reliable and highly sensitive quantitation. They also have valuable experiences in xenobiotic metabolism research. Under WP4.2, the preparation of an analytical LC-MS / MS method for monitoring as many bisphenols as possible simultaneously in different water types, e.g. surface, wastewater.

Since 2010 their research activity is directed towards studying the presence in the environment and the activity of endocrine disruptors, among which we found a range of active substances, cosmetic ingredients, plastic ingredients, their metabolites or other pharmaceutical materials, both in the environment and in the human body. As the need for in-silico methods for predicting endocrine activity from a regulatory standpoint is increasing, they have developed a useful tool for predicting the interaction between compounds and endocrine receptors - Endocrine Disruptome. They also have expertise in performing various tests on human and cell lines, determining the influence of endocrine disruptors on adhesion processes, carcinogenicity, and processes in the immune system. In first year the immunotoxicity of bisphenols were studying regarding their activities on glucocorticoid system (WP5.2) and dendritic cells (WP5.1).

As an educational institution, it has a lot of experience in the implementation of education, organising symposia, summer schools, so its contribution to the implementation of the project will be visible in this area. UL FFA will contribute to the PARC project in the field of immunotoxicity and endocrine activity of bisphenol A analogues and its alternatives in WP5. In the Task 5.1a we will investigate how newly emerging bisphenols and some bisphenol A analogues modulate glucocorticoid receptor function and how is this connected with immune system. For the WP5.2a we will develop new methods for the assessment of immunosuppression. Under task 4.2.1 UL FFA will deliver an endocrine disruptor prioritization list by risk-based approach incorporating toxicological hazard data combined with the collected frequency and abundance of detection. We will set up QA / QC criteria and procedures (task 4.2.3) and implement them in analytical method validation for endocrine disruptors determination in waste, surface, and drinking water samples. The developed method will be applied in a multisource sampling campaign (task 4.2.4) and the results toxicologically assessed (task 4.2.5.).

31.5 – MFUM – PIC: 999903646: In the first year within Task 5.1 MFUM will use our established cell lines for endometrial and breast cancer and will evaluate the effects of bisphenol mixture exposure

to endometrial cancer cell lines. We will determine with this methodology the impact on motility and cell proliferation in hormone dependant samples of endometrial cancer. The lines will then be determined on specific expression profiles of miRNA to understand the impact this exposure has on carcinogenesis better.

32- NACIONALNI INSTITUT ZA JAVNO ZDRAVJE, SLOVENIA (NIJZ) – PIC : 948891346

NIJZ will be involved in WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP6, WP7, WP9.

WP 1: Partnership Management and coordination

NIJZ will be involved in overall executive management and support of the partnership. As a National Hub's coordinator, it will steer the scientific and regulatory aspects and participate in implementation of Annual Work Plans. As a co-leader of T1.4 it will play a crucial role in the area of legal, intellectual property rights and in particular ethics framework.

WP2: Common science policy agenda

NIJZ will participate in priority setting and sustainability activities.

WP3: Synergies, collaboration and awareness

NIJZ will be involved in communication, dissemination, synergies and collaborations. NIJZ considers the developing of risk communication as a field in itself very important. Guidelines for risk communication should be further developed and implemented at national levels. PARC partners have the opportunity to develop collaboration and synergies also at the level of communicators in national frameworks and at the same time to intensify cross-border communication.

WP4 Monitoring and exposure

Besides activities in T1.4 and WP3 NIJZ's involvement in WP4 and WP6 (see below) is among central activities of NIJZ in PARC. In the area of human biomonitoring (HBM), NIJZ will be involved in design, alignment and fieldwork of HBM studies for general population, link exposure and health related information, data management and analysis. In environmental and multisource monitoring, it will participate in reviewing the existing knowledge and infrastructure and in the design of targeted monitoring activities. Within the task of innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys NIJZ will advocate for inclusion of decidual teeth as a suitable non-invasively obtained matrix for exposure assessment. The skeletal compartment is an important chemical repository, making calcified tissues important for measuring exposure. Teeth have been used to estimate long-term cumulative exposure to various chemicals including opening possibilities of insights into a retrospective temporal exposome.

WP6 Innovation in regulatory risk assessment

NIJZ will participate in the following activities: aggregate exposure from multiple sources and routes for the general population, mixture exposure and risk assessment, risk indicators and human health impact assessment.

WP7 Fair Data

In year one no time for activities in WP 7 have been allocated to NIJZ. However, in view of NIJZ's role in national health data collation, management, analyses, interoperability and exchange, NIJZ is keen to participate in data policy and governance in the forthcoming years.

WP9 Building infrastructural and human capacities

NIJZ will participate in training needs identification; identification of existing training courses, programmes and opportunities, and useful learning resources for the web-based portal on topics identified; establishment of an internal and external training plans and support to local organizers.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y

NIJZ has four affiliated entities participating in PARC.

32.1 OI – PIC: 986222475: Given its expertise in cancer epidemiology (data registries, burden estimation, environmental risk factors impact), OI will be involved in the Task 6.2.4 related to the health impact assessment. In particular, in the first year we will be included in the:

Working group that will explore the health data inventory: we will focus on the availability, quality and accessibility of European population-based cancer registries and the European Cancer Information System (ECIS), their suitability to derive background health data of different EU countries for application of exposure-response functions (in comparison with the use of GBD estimates).

Indicator inventory working group: we will focus on the cancer burden indicators, socio-economic deprivation indicators – both in time and geography.

32.2 NLZOH – PIC: 949131227: The NLZOH activities within WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6 and WP9 of PARC fit the NLZOH's regular public programmes. NIJZ and NLZOH are legally linked through bilateral agreement. At NLZOH we are monitoring the PCB-contaminated site since we discovered, that the soil, groundwater and surface water are contaminated at the industrial site as well in the broad karst area in southeast Slovenia. We are particularly interested in the transformation of the initial PCB mixtures over 40 years in the natural environment. The findings would support the long-term behaviour of mixtures of congeners, their transformation and contribute to the models of congener mixtures in the environmental risk assessment.

32.3 ARSO – PIC: 920448812 ARSO will participate in PARC WP4. NIJZ and ARSO are legally linked through Contract Refreshing the environment and health indicators. Slovenian Environment Agency performs expert, analytical, regulatory and administrative tasks related to the environment (soil, air, water) at the national level. The Agency among others establishes, maintains and implements environmental monitoring and obtains environmental data. Therefore, Agency will be involved in Task 4.2 as a contributor in prioritization of chemicals and activities (4.2.1), review of existing knowledge and infrastructure (4.2.2), project design (4.2.3), data analysis and transfer (4.2.5) and feedback mechanisms (4.2.6).

32.4 UKCMB – PIC: 999582188: The contribution of the UKCMB Division for Gynaecology and Perinatology will be in line with the priorities in WP4 concerning the exposure to endocrine disruptors and their effects on female reproductive health. The UKCMB can contribute to the filling of gaps in knowledge on this topic by prospective recruitment of patients with hormone dependent cancers and evaluation of the levels of phthalate exposure as well as with in-vitro models (cell-lines) pertaining to phthalate exposure in breast cancer and endometrial cancer. NIJZ and UKCMB are legally linked through a bilateral agreement in the frame of IT solution Telaradiology.

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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33- AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS (CSIC), SPAIN – PIC: 999991722

During the first year of PARC, CSIC will participate in:

- The design and starting of fieldwork for human biomonitoring studies addressed to children and parents combined with measurements of environmental aggregated exposure from air, dust, soil, dermal, diet, drinking water and domestic use of consumer products to cover human inhalation, dermal absorption and ingestion. Compounds selected for study will encompass metals, perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), emerging chemicals, flame retardants and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) (WP4 and WP6). Design of methods for the analysis of these compounds in a large number of samples, including real-time personal exposure monitors (WP4 and WP6).
- The definition of harmonised criteria for the development of new laboratory networks, development

of protocols for interlaboratory comparisons, and identification of training needs, opportunities and learning resources (WP9).

- The assessment of the effects of exposure during pregnancy to pollutant mixtures due to the consumption of food residues and environmental exposure to PFAS, metals, pesticides (pyrethroids, organophosphates, carbamates), glyphosate, phthalates, bisphenols, DDTs, vinclozoline, other organochlorine compounds and metabolites. The effects will be investigated in mothers and newborns (WP4 and WP6).

- Building a comprehensive database of exposure factors for Europe including a prioritisation of substances, identification of relevance of exposure routes and sources. Grouping chemicals associated with developmental neurotoxicity, endocrine dysfunction and DNA mutation (WP5 and WP6).

These tasks are very adequate to the instrumentation available in CSIC and in the AEs and the expertise of their research and technical staff.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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33.1 ULPGC – PIC: 999929739: It will contribute to PARC and help the GS in WP4 by selection of exposure biomarkers and the necessary analytical methods, as well as in the start of biomonitoring studies.

33.2 UNAV – PIC: 999641746: It will contribute to PARC and help the GS in WP5.1 by in-vitro screening SOSumu test and mini-Ames test of *Alternaria* perylene quinone as start for future hazard characterisation. In WP5.2a it will setup McrBC-modified comet assays for the detection of global methylation, CometChip technology with enzymes for detection of DNA lesions in one assay, and production of HepG2 spheroids.

33.3 UGR – PIC: 999882015: It will contribute to PARC and help the GS in WP4 by planning general population and occupational surveys, including vulnerable groups (children, pregnant women). In WP4.1.1 it will have a leading role in development of analytical methods and quality assurance, in WP4.1.3 it will identify effect biomarkers of prioritised chemicals and in WP4.3 it will perform non-target analysis and develop bioassays for effect-based biomonitoring.

33.4 UPO – PIC: 999846513: It will contribute to PARC and help the GS in WP5.2b by studying neurodevelopmental toxicological hazards with the nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans* as experimental model and endpoint evaluation with microscopy and fluorimetry analysis. The available instrumentation of the group includes well equipped cell and molecular biology laboratories, e.g. high content microscopy analysis Cytation 5 multimode reader.

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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34- INSTITUTO DE SALUD CARLOS III, SPAIN (ISCIII) – PIC : 999507886

ISCIII will participate in the activities of management, coordination, prioritisation and communication/dissemination related with their role of Spanish Grant Signatory, NHCP in Spain, member of Grant Signatory Board and Management Board. In addition, the planning, implementation and reporting of activities that will be carried out in WP9 of PARC in their role of WP9 co-leaders.

In WP4, ISCIII is co-leader of Task 4.1 Human Biomonitoring defining the priorities and activities, and coordinating the work. Apart from this coordination role, ISCIII will participate in the study design and

develop of supporting materials for HBM surveys. ISCIII lead the activity 4.1.2, laboratory analysis and quality assurance, in which the work will be focused on the definition of general criteria for the selection of exposure biomarkers and analytical methods. The creation of a QA/QC and reference analytical methods working groups working together with T9.1 and T9.3 to define the needs for QA and comparability of the HBM data and the general guidelines for development of new analytical methods for exposure and effect biomarkers. In addition, ISCIII will participate in the reviewing of existing knowledge and infrastructures in the environmental field (T4.2), and activities related to QA/QC concept for innovative methods, in synergy with WP9 (T4.3).

In WP5, ISCIII will participate in projects to generate new data on effect of BPA and alternatives on endocrine disruption (thyroid hormone synthesis), carcinogenicity using omics-based methodologies in vitro, and neurotoxicity during early development using zebra fish embryos (5.1a and 5.2a). Regarding Task 5.3, ISCIII will contribute to the inventory of available omics data, biochemical data, PBTK models for all PARC selected adverse outcomes. The activities will focus on the integration of the results for developing innovative mechanistic based conceptual approaches for regulatory chemical risk assessments (T5.3.1), and on the exploration of the EFSA TKTD Platform for improving the risk assessment of pesticides through the integration of prospective and retrospective risk assessments using forward and reverse TK dosimetry (T5.3.4).

Regarding WP6, ISCIII will lead the project “Quantify effects of PPP relative to other stressors through landscape risk assessment informing on environmental impacts” in the frame of Activity 6.4.4., identifying priority areas at local and regional level with a high interlink between agriculture management and biodiversity. In 6.2, ISCIII will contribute with a case study on pesticides, connecting human biomonitoring data with potential sources of aggregated and combined exposure using the methodology derived for addressing mixture toxicity effects.

In the role of WP9 co-leader, ISCIII will promote consultations with other WPs on the infrastructural needs and priority areas, organise the meetings needed and participate in the definition of the overall architecture for the catalogues to be developed in WP9. In addition, ISCIII will contribute to the development of HBM catalogues and inventories of existing protocols and guidance documents on sampling and generic QA/QC in chemical analysis, and will start with the development of pilot catalogues of existing laboratory networks and mapping of their capacities as Task 9.1 leader. Regarding Task 9.4 focus on training activities, ISCIII will contribute to the identification of needs, as well as capacities, and opportunities available in the different partners. The buffer for training activities is allocated under ISCIII budget, thus financial and administrative activities will be carried out to redistribute it among the partners as PARC moves forward.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (Article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)? *	Y
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ISCIII and the following five affiliated entities described below (IISPV, EASP, FISABIO, UPV/EHU and UCLM), are legally linked, by the fact that all of them are associated to the Biomedical Research Networking Centres Public Consortium (CIBER-ISCIII-PIC 997154957), created by ISCIII around eight thematic scientific priorities and in which participate 90 different institutions among the whole Spanish territory. The affiliated entities foreseen are present in the CIBER ISCIII as consortium members, in addition to ISCIII are:

34.1 EASP – PIC: 999859996:

The main activities to be performed over the first year of PARC include the questionnaire development and other material to support HBM studies (T4.1.1) and the data analysis of information already available in databases (T 4.1.4b). EASP team have extensive experience in the development of questionnaires for different age groups, vulnerable groups and specific exposure scenarios, since they are leaders of HBM4EU task 7.3.” Questionnaires development”. Regarding data analysis, EASP

research group consists mainly of PhD in epidemiology and biostatistics.

34.2 FISABIO –PIC: 951714046 :

During the first year, FISABIO will be involved in activities from WP4: Laboratory analysis and quality assurance (T4.1.2), review of existing knowledge and infrastructure (4.2.2), design of targeted monitoring activities and activity (4.2.3) and monitoring activities, including laboratory analysis and QA/QC (4.2.4).

In addition, activities from WP9: Identify existing laboratory networks, draw up a database of laboratory networks (9.1.1), and leading activity 9.1.2: Promote the development of new laboratory networks and support their consolidation. FISABIO will perform successfully these activities through their expertise in liquid and gas chromatographic techniques coupled to mass spectrometry in its various modalities, and the access to state-of-the-art analytical equipment, allow the group to be highly competitive in the development of new analytical methods for emerging or priority pollutants, or the implementation of existing methods during the investigations linked to the evaluation of internal (biomonitoring) or external (environmental monitoring) exposure to pollutants and to the study of the exposome.

34.3 FINBA – PIC: 909900838:

FINBA, as legal representative of ISPA, will take part in WP4 and WP6. FINBA's main effort will focus on Activity 6.2.3: Mixture exposure and risk assessment. Real-life exposure data will be implemented in a cohort located in Asturias (Spain), an area exposed to metal inputs.

34.4 FNS – PIC: 986357790 :

As WP9 members, the foreseen tasks to be performed by FNS over the first year will be the following ones: the identification of identify existing laboratory networks, draw up a database of laboratory networks (T9.1), and an inventory of QA/QC procedures in toxicity studies, bioassays/effect-directed assays (EDA), and toxicokinetic studies (T9.3). Identification of existing training courses, programs and opportunities (T9.4)

Due to FNS long experience in research, teaching and supervising activities as well as in the participation in a large number of research projects, particularly focused on toxicity, bioassays/effect-directed assays, and toxicokinetics, they have solid expertise for performing the above-mentioned tasks accurately and in a timely manner.

34.5 IISPV – PIC: 985772104:

For year 1 in kind personal will participate in Task 4.3.2, Task 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3, Task 6.1, 6.2, Task 7.2, 7.3, Task 8.2 and 8.3.

IISPV counts with highly qualified technical and research personnel with a broad experience in the study of the: i) Toxicology, ii) Environmental Health and Risk Assessment, and iii) Food Toxicology. The group owns adequate equipment and infrastructures for the best development of the task in which contribute in PARC.

34.6 INSST – PIC: 890173948:

The INSST will be involved in the following WPs:

WP4 Task 4.1

The INSST develops reference methods for the exposure assessment of chemicals for their comparison with occupational exposure limit values. Given its expertise in this field we will participate in Task 4.1 in particular in the occupational survey, developing the strategy and the survey for the sampling collection in year one and collecting exposure samples in one or two large hospitals in the northern region of Spain in year two.

WP8

THE INSST currently participates in two projects related to the Safety and sustainability of nanomaterials:

- 1) OECD project within the Working party of manufacture nanomaterials “Moving towards a Safe (r) Innovation Approach for more sustainable nanomaterials and nanoenable products” and
- 2) H2020 project “SABYNA: The Guidance Platform for the Development of Safer Nanomaterials and Nano-Enabled Products”.

Given its expertise in this field, we participate in several activities in WP8 to translate the work done in the field of nanomaterials to a more general chemical approach for safety and sustainability. In the first year we will contribute to the review of frameworks and tools for the assessment of safe and sustainable by design.

34.7 UCLM – PIC: 999840208:

During the first year of PARC, UCLM will contribute to tasks 4.2 and 6.4.4.

Within task 4.2, UCLM team will contribute to generate the knowledgebase on environmental monitoring of pollutants, given its wide expertise in this context within the frame of wildlife monitoring and its participation in relevant actions (e.g. COST Action CA16224 European Raptor Biomonitoring Facility).

Regarding task 6.4.4, the first-year activities in which UCLM is being involved include the compilation of available tools and methods and the conceptualisation of the problem formulation in order to reach the final objective of quantifying effects of PPP and other stressors through landscape risk assessment informing on environmental impacts.

34.8 UPV/EHU – PIC: 999865234:

During the first year, UPV/EHU will be involved in activities from Task 4.1.1 including the questionnaire development and other material to support HBM studies design. Later on, UPV/EHU will contribute with HBM surveys, once the needs and priorities will be defined.

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	Y
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The following AEs of ISCIII will use in-kind contribution provided by third parties

- 1) ISPV: The Pere Virgili Health Research Institute (IISPV): The URV provides in-kind contributions free of charge to the IISPV according to article 9.2 of the Annotated Grant Agreement. In particular, the URV biomedical research groups, develop their research activity through the IISPV with no charges from URV to IISPV for these resources. This research work is done at IISPV facilities. The URV and IISPV have signed an agreement to this end, implying collaboration that is not limited to the action. Groups of TecnaTox is part of URV and IISPV. Personals from this group will participate in WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7 and WP8 with a total of 457 PMs (€3M) (€ 3,023,694.208).
- 2) EASP: one person from IBS-GRANADA (3PMs, (13440 €).
- 3) FINBA: Participation of a Professor in the University of Oviedo. 3.5 PMs, (19.837,00 €), Participation of a specialist in Pediatrics and specific areas, working as Pediatric Endocrinology clinician at the Central University Hospital of Asturias of the Servicio de Salud del Principado de Asturias (SESPA). 3.5 PMs, (23.985,00 €), and Participation of clinicians (gynaecologists) from Centro Médico de Asturias. 6.0 PMs, 3729 €/month (22.371,00 €)
- 4) FNS: In accordance with the collaboration agreement between the University of A Coruña (UDC) and the Professor Novoa Santos Foundation (FPNS) which establishes the framework for relations within the scope of the Institute for Health Research of A Coruña (INIBIC), the UDC research staff participates in the project as personnel of the INIBIC, whose managing body is FPNS (114.420,14€)

35- NATURVARDsverket, SWEDEN (SEPA) – PIC: 998884079

SEPA will participate in the Partnership as a Grant Signatory. SEPA’s main activities under 2022 are linked to the Grant Signatory role.

SEPA is responsible for the national environmental monitoring programme in Sweden. Screening of emerging pollutants and health-related human biomonitoring are parts of this programme. Therefore, SEPA's expertise and interests are mainly connected to monitoring and exposure (WP4) and Early Warning System (WP8.2). SEPA has great knowledge and experience in monitoring and screening of pollutants. SEPA is responsible for the national human biomonitoring program, with several ongoing studies that are candidates for inclusion in Task 4.1. SEPA is also responsible for the national monitoring of pollutants in the environment, which is included in Task 4.2. Given the experience in identifying and screening for new emerging pollutants and risks, SEPA is also involved in Task 4.3 and Task 8.2.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y

35.1 UGOT – PIC: 999981925: UGOT will be a major partner in task 6.4.1.

35.2 KI – PIC: 999978530: In the first year of PARC KI is foreseen to especially support activities in T5.3.2 to inventory the current state of knowledge and prioritise endpoints/pathways for further development. In T6.1.1. and 6.1.2, 1-year activities KI will be involved in mapping of existing AOPs and associated NAMs, selection of regulatory framework(s) and population groups, and development of AOP networks.

With our extensive experience in epidemiology, biomonitoring and health risk assessment, KI will contribute to task 6.2.4 on Human health impact assessment and risk indicators. In the first year, KI will specifically contribute to the review of available European external and internal measured exposure data, health data and Health Impact Assessments (HIA) of the chemicals and mixtures prioritised in PARC, as well as an overview of current approaches to HIA. KI will also support the assessment of feasibility to derive population-specific and population-wide exposures, spatio-temporal variations and interindividual variations and the development of an integrative approach to take different lines of evidence (in vitro, in vivo, and human data, mode of action, biomarkers of effect) into account to establish human relevant exposure-effect relationships. KI will also contribute to the planning and design of case studies.

KI will contribute to four case studies planned in Task 6.3. Researchers at KI have specific expertise in weight of evidence assessment methodology and have developed the SciRAP tools for assessment of in vitro and in vivo data for hazard and risk assessment. Coupled with our expertise in ED assessment, KI will be involved in the Case Study 17 on the use of non-guideline in vitro studies for ED assessments. CS17 will build on existing approaches for evaluating the adequacy of data for ED assessment, including the SciRAP tools. In the first year KI will contribute to review of existing data evaluation methods as well as review of validated and non-validated in vitro methods for ED assessment. Connecting to our expertise in occupational toxicology and exposure limit derivation, KI will contribute to CS3 and CS8. CS3 investigates how outcomes from regulatory risk assessment under REACH and CAD/CMD transfers into workplace chemical risk assessment, in the first year KI will contribute to a survey of existing regulatory documents and questionnaire design. CS3 consists of a review of exposure limits specifically for reproductive toxicants in the workplace, KI will contribute as the case-study leader, in the first year also leading the overview of available exposure limits and coordinating the partners' work on in-depth reviews of specific substances. Finally, KI will contribute to CS16 with our expertise in applied risk assessment, CS16 will focus on expert group members experience with expressions of uncertainty and to identify obstacles for implementing quantitative expressions of uncertainty. In the first year, KIs contribution will focus on questionnaire design, and respondent recruitment.

Building on our extensive experience from FAIRification of risk assessment data for nano- and

advanced materials including involvement in the establishment of a FAIR Implementation Network within the field (the AdvancedNanoIN), KI will support Tasks 7.1.1 and 7.1.2 in setting the basis for refinement and implementation of guiding principles and a FAIR data policy within the chemical risk assessment community. KI will also support the selection and management of use cases in order to operationalise FAIR data implementation within PARC in Task 7.1.3. Furthermore, in Tasks 7.2.1 and 7.2.3, KI will support the mapping of the chemical risk assessment data landscape by contributing with experience and understanding of the nano- and advanced materials data landscape (having led the publication describing one of the largest nanosafety databases currently available), as well as to the development and implementation of practical solutions building on the same experience. Finally, in Tasks 7.3.1 and 7.3.3, KI will contribute to integration and analysis of (heterogenous) FAIR data through experience with application (as well as development) of AOPs in order to facilitate transparent knowledge mining and integration, involving also interoperability aspects between heterogenous data and experience with ontology implementation.

KI will contribute to PARC in Task 9.4 by sharing its vast experience in developing and organising courses in the area of health risk assessment of chemicals. KI has experience in giving courses to different audiences, including professionals and master and PhD students. KI has extensive networks in the EU and beyond, both with stakeholders needing training as well as with experts experienced in teaching. In Task 9.4 KI will contribute to identify the internal and external training needs, to identify existing courses and learning resources, as well as to develop a training plan for PARC.

35.3 ULUND – PIC: 999901318 :

During the first year of PARC, ULUND will be involved in the following WPs and tasks;

WP4-Task4.1:

Occupational surveys: Development of protocols and questionnaires for sample collection, application for ethics, identification of companies, relevant compounds to monitor and establishment of contacts with the companies, method development of analyses of biomarkers of exposure and toxicity. This is linked to the deliverables of the first year of PARC:

- Identify the most relevant compounds (and relevant biomarkers) in the waste streams selected and use of available knowledge produced and experience obtained in the scope of HBM4EU to support an exposure study.
- Develop a study protocol, information materials and informed consent forms and documentation for ethics approval in each of the collaborating member states.
- Re-use and revise existing SOP, already available from the e-waste study developed in HBM4EU study (Scheepers et al., 2021) and develop new SOPs if needed.

General population survey: Design and alignment of protocols and questionnaires for future fieldwork and sample collection, method development for laboratory analysis and quality assurance

WP6:

Work with authorities to identify and clarify regulatory needs of transforming ERA to protect biodiversity and ecosystem services. Within task 6.3, ULUND will lead a case study on Practical challenges in using quantitative expressions of uncertainty in assessment

35.4 ORU – PIC: 999650088:

ORU will participate in WP 4.3, activities 4.3.2, 4.3.3 and 4.3.4 and in WP 8.2, activities 8.2.1, 8.2.2, 8.2.3 and 8.2.4. Participation is justified by active and extensive research on international level being conducted at ORU in the research areas covered in the tasks listed above.

35.5 RISE – PIC: 999613422:

The Swedish Centre for Chemical Substitution will contribute to the development of a methodology to assess different chemical aspects of goods and articles. The methodology should be able to address questions such as: is this nonstick-coated pan better or worse, from a chemical safety perspective,

compared to that nonstick-coated pan. During year 1, mapping of the chemical content in goods and articles will be carried out, and information on available tools (commercial and non-commercial) for tracking chemical composition through supply chains will be gathered.

The Swedish Centre for Chemical Substitution will also contribute by collaboration with support centers in EU member states, in order to communicate results from PARC and enable support for companies throughout Europe.

The Swedish Centre for Chemical Substitution is situated at RISE Research Institutes of Sweden. RISE is a research partner to Swedish industry, which will be beneficial for the project in connection with industrial contacts and collaboration, as well as access to relevant chemical data.

35.6 SU – PIC: 999885022 :

SU is the Task leader of WP6.3. Project leader and contributor to five case studies within WP6.3. Project leaders of case studies Identify and review methods for evaluating the effectiveness of risk assessment for reducing risk, Methods to identify coordination needs towards a ‘one substance one assessment’ approach, Identification of loopholes for substances with biocidal properties, and Evaluation of conclusions drawn in guideline-compliant developmental neurotoxicity studies. Contributing to the case study Skin sensitisation and risk assessment methodologies

35.7 KEMI – PIC: 937974093:

KEMI is the work package co-leader of WP6 Innovation in regulatory risk assessment (together with RIVM, NL), with a focus on coordinating and participating in the work of tasks 6.3 Review of risk assessment methodology and 6.4 Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment approaches. As work package co-leaders KEMI participates in the PARC management board. Given this expertise, KEMI is co-leading WP6 on innovation in regulatory risk assessment. Based on the specific experience in the area of enforcement as well as evaluation of plant protection products, KEMI will be a key contributor in developing information transfer structures and enforcement methodology for chemicals in articles (Task 6.4.3) and establishing holistic risk assessment approaches to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity (Task 6.4.4).

35.8 IVL – PIC 999476361:

IVL will take part in WP4, WP6 and WP8 during year 1. As a key contributor in WP 4 IVL will take part in the prioritisation activities and the review of existing monitoring programs in order to efficiently integrate as much as possible into the planning of future programs. IVLs long experience in environmental monitoring programs will be key to this.

In WP6 IVL will contribute with the review of existing exposure factors, current PBPK models and factors for aggregated risk assessment. WP6 activities will ensure that key knowledge from previous developments, such as ProScale, UseTox, and the closely aligned Mistra SafeChem project is integrated in PARC.

In WP8 IVL will contribute to the operationalisation of the EC-SSbD criteria and methodology within the framework of PARC and with application SSbD methods and toolboxes in the entire value chain. This is related to activities in the ongoing Mistra SafeCem project together with the Swedish chemical industry. IVL will also work with the Early Warning System (EWS), building on previous work in the EU project Solutions to identify possible regulatory obstacles for its implementation. For the activities during year1 IVLs stature as an independent non-profit research organisation will be beneficial.

35.9 SLV – PIC: 997318402:

Swedish national hub: The SLV organises and administrates the meetings of the Swedish national hub collecting support, suggestions as well as disseminating information regarding PARC WP:s and deliverables. The SLV also organises and administrates the meetings of the competent government authorities within the remit of PARC thus supporting the work of the GB.

Within WP8.2: The SLV contributes to the early warning system work package by providing human biomonitoring samples for non-target screening, contributing in scientific discussions regarding the

results and by contributing to the writing of scientific paper(s).

35.10 SLU – PIC: 999887350 :

Task 4.1.: Selection of archived human time trend samples for exposure assessment and policy measures. Task 4.2.: Development of design of monitoring studies and QA/QC concepts for case study on PFASs in environmental samples. Task 4.3.: Development of design of monitoring studies on Wastewater-based epidemiology (WBE) coupled to suspect screening/NTS/EDA-based exposure characterisation. Task 5.1.: Selection and organisation of test items for prioritised groups of compounds. Task 5.2.: Conduction of first assays on prioritised substances.

Task 6.2.: Generic PBPK models will be developed for pregnant women and their fetuses as well as children with the focus on PFAS exposure. Task 6.4.: Test different models for PPP exposure and environmental effects and compare with monitoring data from different member states, with the aim to find the most relevant steering factors. Task 8.2.: Review and conceptualisation of early warning monitoring tools and exploration of current knowledge and tools.

35.11 UMU – PIC: 999881821:

UMU will participate in Task 4.1.1a: Development of supporting materials for harmonised EU HBM conduct. Maria Wennberg, UMU, is working with development of a core questionnaire for human biomonitoring in Sweden, with SEPA as employer. UMU will participate with IPM the first year of PARC, in the work of developing relevant questionnaires for HBM studies within PARC.

Task 8.2.1, 8.2.2 and 8.2.4: The Patrik Andersson group, UMU, will be responsible for tasks in WP8 included in task 8.2.1, 8.2.2 and 8.2.4 in framing the early warning system. During the first year the work will be focused on developing the computational framework for text mining and data curation. Work will be completed in close collaboration with several partners of the tasks.

35.12 UU – PIC: 999985029 :

Given its expertise ecotoxicology and the use of zebrafish embryo in the context of metabolic disruption, UU will be involved in Task 5.1. In the first year, it will be starting the testing of BPA alternatives and mixtures thereof to investigate potential ED related effects. With its expertise in human toxicology and endocrine disruption as well as epigenetics and cell painting, it will contribute to the DNT/ANT subtask in Task 5.2.1. In year 1, it will identify suitable models and methods for assessing epigenetic endpoints in the context of developmental neurotoxicity, as well as initiate protocols for image-based analysis of 3D BrainSpheres and begin data collection for phenotoxicity assessment. It will further contribute to Task 5.2.2 with its expertise in marine prokaryotes and their use as a high-throughput NAM for testing environmental disturbances. In the first year, here activities will include the construction of a dedicated experimental platform and its first use in evaluating the effect of environmentally relevant chemicals. Additionally, given its expertise in data analysis and artificial intelligence, UU will contribute to Tasks 7.3.2 and 8.3. Here, the first year will constitute the initiation of research on conformal prediction models for toxicity (Task 7.3.2) and begin evaluating the STACKn framework for model serving (Task 8.3).

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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36- ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS, GREECE (AUTH) – PIC: 999895692

AUTH will be involved in WP1 (Tasks 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.4, responsible for AUTH and its AEs management), WP2 (Task 2.2, responsible for the development of PARCopedia), WP3 (Task 3.1b, responsible for the International board), WP4 (Task 4.1, involved in HBM studies and Task 4.3, responsible for the untargeted methods), WP5 (Task 5.1, involved in the bisphenols study), WP6 (Task 6.2, responsible for the lifelong exposure activity), WP7 (Tasks 7.1, 7.2, 7.3, involved the functional links between WP7 and WP8), WP8, where AUTH is co-leader (as well as co-leading Tasks 8.1 and 8.3 and

involved in Task 8.2 responsible for the EWS computational platform) and WP9 (Task 9.1, responsible to act as contact point with WP9).

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	Y
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36.1 EFET – PIC: 959188478: Given it’s expertise, EFET will participate to following WPs and Tasks (Y1):
 WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness, Task 3.2: Communication, dissemination, and awareness, Task 3.3: Establishment of synergies and collaborations at national or EU-level,
 WP4: Monitoring and exposure, Task 4.2. Environmental and multisource monitoring,
 WP8: Concepts and toolboxes, Task 8.2: Early warning system: to work together on mutually beneficial projects focused on use of food residues data for assessment of aggregate exposure and validation of the INTEGRA computational platform.
 EFET has expertise in Risk Communication so it will be involved in WP3.2: by supporting the development and implementation of a communication and dissemination strategy, website and social media and Risk communication strategy.
 In specific, for risk communication (Year 1), EFET will identify stakeholder risk communication persons and work towards the development and validation of a survey in order to evaluate their understanding of basic concepts and perceptions of their role in risk communication.
 EFET remit as EFSA Focal Point is the development of partnerships especially in risk assessment community, for this reason it will be involved in the WP3.3 by supporting synergies with other research projects in national level.

Given EFET’s expertise on official control (monitoring) of chemical hazards, such as EDCs, in different matrices (foods and food contact materials), we will be involved in Task 4.2, related in risk assessment of emerging chemical substances potential EDCs.
 In particular, EFET as partner of the extended project team will contribute in the first year in review of existing knowledge (Task 4.2.2) and support of monitoring activities (sampling) (Task 4.2.4).
 Given EFET’s experience on working with chemical occurrence databases, EFET will be involved in WP8.2, supporting activities for the development of a EWS.

36.2 GCSL – PIC: 912807637:
 The WP/Tasks that GCSL will be involved in during the 1st year of the project are:
 1.2 Scientific steering and Implementation of AWP,
 1.3 Impact evaluation and monitoring of the performance indicators of the partnership,
 1.4 Ethics framework,
 2.1 General scope: Developing and implementing a well-structured and transparent prioritisation strategy through a fluid dialogue between WP2 and other Work Packages (WPs) and making a proposal for a systematic, criteria-based prioritisation for projects, substances and methods. Task 2.1 will also set up the principles and process for a Rapid Response Mechanism (RRM), based on HBM4EU’s experience. GCSL contributes to the overall development of a PARC prioritisation process for projects, substances and methods, and also to the setup of the principles and process for a RRM. More particularly, GCSL contributes to the development of the prioritisation process and criteria for project review and approval. First deliverables (PARC_ProjectReview_Process) & (PARC_ProjectReview_Criteria) due to end of M5 (September 2022). Also, for the project review process a pool of contact points and internal reviewers among all task partners will be established. Up to now two members of the GCSL-Task 2.1 team have been appointed, one as contact point for ST_5.1a & ST_5.1a and one as internal reviewer for ST_5.1a. After the end of Project Submission Window (end

of September 2022) Task 2.1 compliance check and review nomination will be completed in 2-3 weeks period, Reviewers' feedback and Task 2.1 recommendations will be completed in 3-4 weeks period, and the Decision Memo for all the reviewed projects will be sent to the MB before the end of November 2022. Finally, the preparation of 2nd SRIA will have to be completed before the end of the first year. Moreover, for the project review process some templates have already been prepared (PARC_project_template_InitiationPhase) & (PARC_project_template_PlanningPhase), and some others are under preparation (PARC_decision_memo_review of the projects). GCSL also contributes to the development of prioritisation process & criteria for substances and methods.

2.2 PARCopedia: First Deliverable due to end of March 2023: "PARCopedia scoping study"

The GCSL will contribute at the sub-activities of "Conceptual development" and "Content generation/editorial work" of the first Deliverable "PARCopedia scoping study". PARCroute: First Deliverable due to end of March 2023: "NGRARoute interim report". The GCSL will contribute at the sub-activities of "Conceptual development" and "Content generation/editorial work" of the first Deliverable "NGRARoute interim report".

3.1a Establishment of the Stakeholder forum: GCSL participates in meetings organised by the task leader in order to finalise the criteria for the selection of the members of the SF and the process by which interested parties will be invited and members will be selected. Since an open call for members is foreseen, GCSL will be involved in the dissemination of the information through the network of the EURL for Food Contact Materials, the WG of DG SANTE on Food Contact Materials and the Council of Europe intergovernmental Committee on Food Contact Materials (CD-P-MCA). The SF will be very limited in number but interested members that are not selected directly for the SF may form topic specific groups. In this case a topic specific group on food contact materials could be supported by GCSL. GCSL will also contribute as needed in the meetings of the SF.

3.1b Establishment of the International Board and selection of the PARC Ambassador: GCSL will be involved in the finalisation of the criteria for the selection of the members of the IB and the selection process as guided by the task leader. GCSL has relative international contacts through the FAO and WHO expert groups in the area of food additives and contaminants and through the Ph.Eur. and the USP. GCSL will also contribute as needed in the meetings of the IB.

3.2 Communication, dissemination and awareness: Contribution on the creation, translation and dissemination of communication materials. Upload the relevant material on the IAPR website.

3.3 Networking and synergies: Identification and establishment of a database of partnerships, projects, networks and activities including platforms relevant to PARC within the frame of an efficient and dynamic collaboration strategy. Setting up a synergies network (SYNnet), with a defined roadmap, including both PARC partners and stakeholders with a view to promote collaboration and awareness, and include information on SYNnet on PARC's website;

9.1.1 Identify existing laboratory networks, draw up and maintain up-to-date and active a database of the laboratory networks: Collection of the expertise within the GCSL laboratory network. Submission of the data to the Task Leader.

9.1.2 Promote the development of new laboratory networks and support their consolidation: Any there activity according to the task leaders' instructions.

9.1.3 Facilitate the coordination and linkage of existing and new laboratory networks: Organisation/participation in the necessary meetings.

9.1.4 Develop an interactive tool to show the capacities of the laboratory networks: Collect and supply the dashboard development group with necessary relevant information.

9.2 Building exposure monitoring capacities: Collect and supply with data the catalogue of environmental monitoring networks

9.3 Harmonisation of QA/QC of laboratory tests: Supply information on the QA/QC principles and laboratory daily practice of the GCSL laboratory network, provide information on existing PTs.

9.4 Training: Identification of training needs. Information on training courses / programs organised by GCSL

36.3 NKUA – PIC: 999643007: NKUA will contribute to WP3 (T3.1a, 3.2, T3.3), WP4 (T4.2) and

WP8 (T8.2). LAC will support the establishment of SF and IB (T3.1a), will engage NORMAN members in the PARC activities, will seek the synergies and collaborations in national and international projects (T3.2), will be the task force leader (T3.3.; dissemination of PARC to scientists and citizens), will participate in the case-studies of PFAS and EDCs (T4.2) and will assist the establishment of an early-warning system (T8.2). AUTH is linked with NKUA in research related to collection, analysis and interpretation of analysis results of wastewater for viral load and to predict the trends and the associated health risks related to COVID-19 pandemic.

36.4 UOC - PIC: 999588978: UoC will be involved in WP3, Task 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, WP4, in Task 4.1, in WP5, Task 5.1 and in WP8, Task 8.2 and 8.3.

Task 3.1.

The main activities that our institution plans to develop under this task are listed below:

1. Disseminate to local/regional authorities in the EU. We will use targeted written material such as reports, articles in specialised press, newsletters, and press releases to reach individuals in local/regional authorities. We will also ensure that all our scientific publications are accompanied by policy briefs and press releases to maximize the potential that we reach this audience.
2. Disseminate to research community and experts from diverse fields. We will reach this community through scientific publications in international peer-reviewed journals with high impact factor and communications in international conferences. Furthermore, we will also disseminate the publications through social media.
3. Disseminate to entrepreneurs and industry. We will use articles on business magazines, participation in industry conferences/events, as well as social media to communicate our message to his target group.
4. Disseminate to the general public and other stakeholders. We will use the project website, targeted video, TV, and radio as well as written material such as articles in specialised press, newsletters, press releases, leaflets, and brochures to reach the general public as well as service providers from sectors such as education (schools, community colleges, innovation/cultural centres).
5. The Dissemination and Innovation Manager will formulate the strategy in cooperation with all the partners. The plan will take into account the communication and dissemination actions foreseen for the project and ensure these are used to promote the project's assets and maximise exploitation.

Task 3.2.

Leaflets and brochures describing chemical hazards, specially designed printed material for primary and secondary education

Industry oriented secure guides (eg chemical, steel, food etc)

Web site design with all relevant and latest information for chemical hazards and risk assessment methodologies

Web site design with self-guides and knowledge evaluation modules

Webinars, a specific youtube channel and twitter (social media)

WP4

4.1.2 Laboratory analysis and quality assurance

The Laboratory of Toxicology has implemented, accredited and operates under the quality assurance program ISO 17025, in order to justify all laboratory procedures, i.e. sampling, preparation, analysis and interpretation of results needed for this task.

4.1.3 Link exposure and health related information

We plan to use micronuclei frequency, hair analysis and telomeres' length as real life exposure biomarkers for close and effective biomonitoring implemented in general population and special/high risk/vulnerable groups.

4.1.4 Occupational studies

Our research team will perform studies in occupationally exposed population to different pollutants. We

will also prepare all the procedures for handling sensitive biological samples, eliminate and control external parameters for obtaining accurate results.

4.1.5 Data analysis

Laboratory of Toxicology has the appropriate personnel and expertise to establish a concrete statistical analysis and planning of Human Biomonitoring data. Furthermore, statistic combination of biomonitoring data of various origin will be used to obtain valuable, unique results and trends.

WP5

Task 5.1

We plan to use different approaches for the evaluation of the chemicals tested in this task. Among else we will use assays for the investigation of the neurodevelopmental toxicity (e.g. Primary hNPC proliferation assay, Primary hNPC migration assay, Primary hNPC neuronal differentiation assay, Neuronal morphology etc.), immunotoxicity studies as well as traditional sub-chronic and chronic rodent toxicity studies

WP8

The Laboratory of toxicology plans to evaluate the data given from other WPs Furthermore, experimental analysis of certain compounds in different matrices (biological and/or environmental) will be performed with analytical techniques such as Liquid chromatography - mass spectrometry (LC-MS), Gas chromatography - mass spectrometry (GC-MS) High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) ELISA spectrophotometers. These results will be used for the evaluation and the improvement of the models under development.

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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37- BENAKI PHYTOPATHOLOGICAL INSTITUTE, GREECE (BPI) – PIC: 998193633

WP4: BPI participates in human biomonitoring (task 4.1.1, 4.1.2, 4.1.3 and 4.1.4), environmental monitoring (task 4.2.1, 4.2.2, 4.2.4, 4.2.5, 4.2.6) and in the development of innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys (task 4.3.1).

WP5: BPI is Task co-leader in Task 5.1b and participates in the project concerning the investigation of the potential mixture toxicity of BPA alternatives. BPI participates also in Task 5.1a by carrying out in vitro experiments for the investigation of possible endocrine effects of natural toxins (“Enniatins and Alternaria Project”) and in Task 5.3.

WP6: BPI is Task co- leader of task 6.3 and case study leader of case studies 17 and 18. Furthermore, BPI participates in case study 16 and in tasks 6.1, 6.2 (6.2.3 and 6.2.4) and 6.4 (6.4.1 and 6.4.2).

BPI participates also in WP3 (Tasks 3.2 and 3.3) and WP9 (Tasks 9.1.1, 9.2.1, 9.3.2, 9.4.1, 9.4.2 and 9.4.3).

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
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Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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38- Département Fédéral de l'Intérieur, SWITZERLAND (FOPH) – PIC : 957586329

FOPH is coordinating the Swiss institutions taking part in PARC and is the National Hub Contact Point. As such, it will organise the necessary national meetings and take part in the grant signatory board. For WP4 (Task 4.1) it will plan a Swiss HBM cohort with adults and adolescents together with Unisanté. FOPH is coordinating the Swiss Health Study, which is currently in its pilot phase with two study centers and 800 participants. In the next years, we plan to involve more centers and age groups. Furthermore, FOPH will contribute to the development of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe and contribute its experience as a risk assessment and risk management body in Switzerland. For WP6 FOPH will contribute its knowledge about aggregate exposure assessment and modelling, when designing a strategy for aggregating worker and general population exposures. Natalie von Götz is one of the co-developers of the probabilistic model PACEM that can be used for consumer exposure to cosmetics and household products and has wide experience with coupling models.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

39- AGROSCOPE, SWITZERLAND - PIC: 998365711

WBF-Agroscope will contribute to Activity 6.6.4 Risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity. Main tasks during Year 1 :

- Activity 6.4.4.1 :
 Project “Clarifying regulatory needs – transforming EU strategies into regulatory useable research projects”. Preparation of and inputs to the planned workshops that bring together regulators, research partners and policy makers. Participation in literature scanning and pilot studies that are identified at the onset of the project. Participation in the reporting of results from Year 1.
- Activity 6.4.4.2:
 Project “Reducing complexity and ensure predictive capacity of models for predicted environmental concentrations of plant protection products in surface water”. Participation in Desktop study, contribution of data (MEC datasets) as appropriate, contribution to Deliverable 1 on comparison of different existing methods for predicting PPP concentrations in surface waters within agricultural catchments validated against monitoring data.
- Activity 6.4.4.3:
 Project “Reducing complexity and identifying the most relevant predictors for effects in ERA of PPPs”. Contribution to report on the most relevant factors describing the transfer function that enables a link between laboratory lower-tier tests and effects at the ecosystem level (Deliverable 1).
 Project “Benchmarking environmental risk assessment to support transition towards a holistic paradigm” WBF-Agroscope will be involved in conceptualising an ERA methodology that yields comparable results between different ERAs on individual PPP. Contribution of data for internal benchmarking (Deliverable 1).
 Project “Quantify effects of PPP and other stressors through landscape risk assessment informing on environmental impacts”. -> hier ist Agroscope nicht vorgesehen, das war allerdings ursprünglich der Grund weshalb der Bereich Agrarökologie und Umwelt involviert wurde ...

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

40- Policlinique Médicale Universitaire de Lausanne, SWITZERLAND (UNISANTE) – PIC : 903030134

During the first year of PARC, UNISANTE will contribute to task 4.1.1 “Design, alignment and fieldwork of HBM studies”. Unisanté together with TTL, will plan and implement the general population survey of teenagers and adults in 2-4 centers in Switzerland that is to start in 2023. Unisanté will also work with FOPH on a separate occupational exposure survey to understand use of chemicals.

Task 6.2.1: During the first year, for task 6.2.1 “strategy for aggregate exposure”, Unisanté will contribute to the identification and analysis of existing models as well as participate in the work towards the aggregation of the models, by:

- Developing an inventory of models commonly used in general population and occupational risk assessment. The structural analysis will identify the connection points of the models. It will build on the work of previous initiatives such as ISES Europe and the REACH Exposure Expert Group (REEG).
- Identifying common exposure determinants for dermal and inhalation models and a minimum set of these determinants that will be needed to describe aggregated exposure scenarios.

Suitability of Unisanté’s profile and infrastructure

Task 4.1.1: Prof. Murielle Bochud, Dre Semira Gonseth, and their team will contribute their long-standing expertise (>15 years) in data collection and data management for population-based surveys and cohorts. This expertise encompasses writing study protocols for ethic board review; planning participants selection and recruitment; developing study questionnaires and study interviews; planning clinical exams and biological samples collection; planning biological samples processing, storage and analysis; and planning data management and analysis. Unisanté has the needed infrastructure, including IT infrastructure and expertise, and the corresponding human resources. A well-experienced team in project management who has already conducted several large-scale population-based studies and cohorts will be devoted to the task. Unisanté has the capacity to recruit participants from the general population, in particular by creating recruitment materials, and designing procedures. Unisanté has the infrastructure and skills to perform clinical study exams (in-house or through partnerships). Unisanté demonstrates advanced skills in the customisation of REDCap, a software for designing online surveys, interview-guiding questionnaires, and managing participants. Unisanté also demonstrates skills for setting up and using SLIMS, a software for managing biological samples. Unisanté owns a biobank for mid- and long-term storage of collections of biological samples. Unisanté—in partnership with the Lausanne University Hospital—can manage and share data in a modern highly secured database.

Dr. Nancy Hopf and her Exposure Sciences Unit (USE) will use these biobanked urine samples from adults in a separate study to understand the exposure of endocrine disrupting chemicals, specifically metabolites of phthalates and bisphenols. The distribution of these biomonitoring results will be an indication of exposure in the Swiss population due to environmental exposure, but will also serve as the baseline for recommending occupational biological exposure limits for workers in the plastic, fragrance, and chemical industries. USE collaborators have longstanding expertise in developing biomonitoring methods based on applied human toxicology studies and occupational hygiene. These exposure studies include writing study protocols for ethical review boards; recruiting workers in the industry sector for biomonitoring or healthy participants for the toxicology studies; conducting biomonitoring studies collecting biological samples from workers or setting up human controlled experiments; processing, storing, and analysing the biological samples; and communicate the findings to the participants and the

scientific communities.

Task 6.2.1: Prof. David Vernez and his Unisanté team have successfully worked towards harmonising modelling tools and development of advanced exposure algorithms (e.g. with machine-learning techniques) in the context of the REACH regulatory models used for occupational inhalation exposure. The variety of models used in REACH leads to significant uncertainty in the results and may lead to inappropriate decisions. In order to overcome the difficulties in implementing the models, the applicants have previously developed the TREXMO computer tool with the support of SECO. TREXMO allows the exposure to chemicals to be calculated quickly according to six models recognised by the European Chemicals Agency (ECETOC TRA v3, EASE, Advanced REACH Tool 1.5, Stoffenmanager and MEASE). This tool allows on the one hand to reduce the inter-user variability in the use of the models and on the other hand to provide the user with a comparison of the results according to different models. More recently, the applicants developed an algorithm (i.e. TREXMO+) that integrates machine learning allowing it to learn about the performance of different regulatory models. TREXMO+ thus allow to predict when an exposure model is expected to underperform and modifies the exposure outputs accordingly. The applicants therefore have the expertise and IT tools to carry out this task.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

41- EDGENOESSISCHE ANSTALT FUER WASSERVERSORGUNG ABWASSERREINIGUNG UND GEWAESSERSCHUTZ, SWITZERLAND (EAWAG) – PIC: 998124569

WP4 Contribution to the project design of targeted monitoring activities (4.2.3) and prioritisation of chemicals and activities based on existing knowledge (4.2.1, 4.2.2) (Vermeirssen, Hollender)

WP4 Task 4.3.3 Suspect screening of metabolites of industrial compounds and pharmaceuticals in the aquatic environment by compilation of appropriate suspect lists including usage of pathway-prediction systems and application to various sample types within the project “Wastewater based epidemiology for community wide human exposure assessment”.(Hollender)

WP5 (all 5.2.b): For the project on machine learning (Schirmer), available data will be surveyed using available data bases and data cleaned for further processing. Focus will be on acute toxicity data across taxa on the one hand and on mode-of-action specific assay information on the other.

For the project on the microfluidic device with immobilised synthetic phototrophic biofilms (Tlili), we will identify the optimal conditions for a reproducible biofilm formation. This will be achieved by testing different inoculation conditions (e.g. Total density of the inoculum, relative abundance of the phototrophic species within the mixture, duration of colonisation) as well as various flow velocities in the microfluidic device.

The project on zebrafish behavioral effects of neurotoxicants (Groh/vom Berg) will focus on the consolidation of the pipeline for concomitant assessment of behavioral alterations and the underlying structural and molecular changes occurring in the nervous system of larval zebrafish upon exposure to neurotoxic substances.

WP6 (6.3, 6.4.1, 6.4.4): Under the review of risk assessment methodology (6.3) within a case study led by FOEN and Eawag environmental risk assessment of pesticides under different prospective and retrospective regulations will be analysed for differences and similarities to further the one substance

one assessment goal (Junghans, Casado, Kroll, Marti). We will build on our expertise in the field that was build up during 10 years of hazard and risk assessment for pesticides in Switzerland and in the EU. In 6.4.1. we will be involved in the first year as an expert and member of the core group (Junghans) in the landscaping exercise to develop regulatory relevant approaches and methods for chemical mixtures. We can build on two decades of experiences working in the field of mixture risk assessment. In 6.4.4. we will contribute in several projects to improving environmental risk assessment for plant protection products (Kroll, Marti). We will build on our expertise in the field that was build up during 10 years of hazard and risk assessment for pesticides in Switzerland and in the EU.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

42- EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH, SWITZERLAND (ETHZ) – PIC: 999979015

The main tasks of ETHZ during the first year are the following:
 Metabolic transformations of xenobiotic chemicals are well-established critical factors in chemical risk assessment. Recently, the microbiome has emerged as a key contributor to chemical metabolism of potentially equal importance to the liver. However, our ability to predict microbial metabolism and perturbations is limited and still on expensive, slow and ethically questionable in vivo studies. Furthermore, key information regarding metabolic functionality and its impact on toxicant disposition is lacking, in particular for natural toxins. Thus, our works aims to use mass spectrometric metabolomics assays based on chemical tracer probes to quantitatively profile interactions of natural toxins with the gut microbiota and to perform phenotypic profiling in complex human gut microbiota. Gained data will be used to quantify kinetic aspects of the transformation products and link PBPK characteristics with genome-based prediction as a basis for predictive models of differences in transformation efficiencies. Within the first year, we will identify toxins and metabolites of interest, establish corresponding fermentation assays and analytical methods and start building respective PBPK models incorporating microbial conversions.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

43- EIDGENOSSISCHE MATERIALPRUFUNGS- UND FORSCHUNGSANSTALT, SWITZERLAND (EMPA) – PIC: 999907138

EMPA will contribute to Task 8.1 “Safe and sustainable by design (SSbD)”. Empa is co-leading Task 8.1. and will therefore be involved in all activities in this task at the coordination level. Main

<p>contributions to the technical content in the first year will be in activity 8.1.2. “Toolbox development” and activity 8.1.3. “Towards operationalisation: Use case & indicators”.</p> <p>- The “Environmental Risk Assessment and Management” Group at Empa has a very long history of research in Safe-by-Design of novel materials, mostly in the context of FP7 and H2020 projects (e.g. LICARA, SUN, SUNSHINE, Gov4Nano, caLIBRAte, GoNanoBioMat but also many others) and has developed methods and tools to enable safety and sustainability assessments at different levels of detail, e.g. the LICARA NanoScan, the DPMFA modelling method or the GoNanoBioMat Safe-by-Design procedure. The group has also a long experience in sustainable innovation research and thus has the required expertise to work on the tasks mentioned above. As the work is desk- and computer based, only office space is needed for the fulfilment of the work.</p>	
Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

44- FEDERAL DEPARTMENT FOR ENVIRONMENT, TRANSPORT, ENERGY AND COMMUNICATIONS, SWITZERLAND (FOEN) – PIC: 999439210

CH-Swiss Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN), Air Pollution Control and Chemicals Division, Annette Aldrich. As an ecotoxicological risk assessor with twenty years’ experience in the evaluation and authorisation of plant production products in Switzerland, her contributions in PARC will be divided in two tasks: 6.3 and 6.4.

Under Task 6.4, Activity 6.4.4 “Risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity” her main task as part of the regulatory core team in the first year will be to define the drivers of change, i.e. identifying the core inadequacies in the current ERA approach and how to best address them. Her long-term experience and broad network encompasses close collaboration with risk managers, EFSA (PPR panel, working groups, PERA project) and the agronomical field. Therefore, she is well positioned to help ensure that research partners focus on the relevant aspects, which need to be addressed within PARC in order to achieve an applicable next-generation ERA approach.

In Task 6.3 case study “Differences and similarities of prospective and retrospective risk assessment for pesticides” her contribution as a member of the project management team in the first year is to refine the problem formulation and to identify concrete examples for the case study for which an extensive database is available. Furthermore, national disputes about the results of sophisticated monitoring studies in relation to prospective risk assessments have sharpened her perception to focus this case study.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

45- UNIVERSITA DELLA SVIZZERA ITALIANA, SWITZERLAND (USI) – PIC: 999585874

Task 4.1.2 Laboratory analysis and quality assurance. 1) Definition of the criteria to be applied for the selection of the best exposure biomarkers and analytical methods. 2) Data collection of the best exposure biomarkers and analytical methods for the PARC-prioritised substances (=continuation of our task in WP9 of HBM4EU). 3) Set up of reference analytical methods.

Task 4.1.3 Link exposure and health related information. Analysis of HBM4EU occupational study samples for effect markers and evaluation of the effect marker data collected within HBM4EU occupational studies: eg. protein adduct analyses in worker samples collected in the HBM4EU diisocyanate study (our laboratory developed specific isocyanate markers that are not available in other laboratories) and linking these to health effects.

Task 6.2.4: Human health impact assessment and risk indicators Goal: prediction of the toxic internal levels of chemicals and comparison to biomonitoring values. We propose to apply the existing exposure modeling by the NIEHS. Kleinstreuer et al (NTP, <https://ice.ntp.niehs.nih.gov/>) showed that using AOPs in vitro, the levels in biological samples (urine, blood) yielding adverse effects in humans could be predicted. We would use these predicted levels and compare them to all major existing biomonitoring studies and potential determined health effects in order to establish the validity and the usability of the model for PARC.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

46- UNIVERSITAT BASEL, SWITZERLAND (UNIBAS) – PIC: 999907914

UNIBAS engagement in PARC is focused in particular on Task 6.4 ‘Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies’ for which UNIBAS has been appointed interim co-lead together with AGES (AT). We have budgeted a total of 24 PMs for activities in Y1. Our practical work relates mainly to activity 6.4.2 ‘Facilitate the regulatory acceptance and use of new methods’ which is comprised of two activities in Y1 of PARC:

1) Development of scientific criteria for regulatory use of NAMs (Y1): we will carry out a landscaping exercise to determine the use and status of integration and implementation of NAMs in selected regulatory frameworks. Structured interviews will be conducted to identify risk assessors’ needs and expected benefits from the use of NAMs. A gaps & needs analysis will identify common scientific barriers, incl. data quality (i.e. reliability), relevance, and uncertainty of NAMs.

2) Use of computer-based approaches for regulatory risk assessment (Y1): we will review previous and current R&D activities associated with the use of computer-based approaches (e.g. Machine learning, QSARs) for human health risk assessment (RA). In collaboration with EFSA, JRC and OECD we will select specific examples for in-depth review, e.g. automation of the systematic review process, or extending the AOP framework with knowledge information. We also aim to gain a better understanding of risk assessors’ needs, opportunities and expected benefits for/from the use of computer-based approaches in chemical RA.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement	N
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(MGA))?	
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

47- State Secretariat for Economic Affairs, SWITZERLAND (SECO) – PIC: 889610475

Dr. Robert Pasanen-Kase, from Swiss State Secretariat for Economic Affairs will contribute mainly with knowledge transfer in his role of co-leading an OECD effect-biomarker AOP project with more than 25 institutions. The main transfer & discussion work will be dedicated to mixture assessment, effect-biomarkers, Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOP) and mixture threshold derivation. This work will contribute and will allow synergies to the three following PARC tasks in 2022:

- Task 4.1.3 to tasks related to effect-biomarker use & interpretation (proposed in kind contribution 0.25 PM/year),
- Task 5.3: for adding effect-biomarker knowledge to PARC survey, 16 effect-biomarkers covering 7 Mode of Actions are characterised in running OECD occupational biomonitoring activity, this knowledge can be transferred and discussed (proposed in kind contribution 0.1 PM/year)
- Task 6.2. Activity 3: Integrative exposure and risk assessment / mixture assessment (proposed in kind contribution 0.30 PM/year).

For this work mainly knowledge transfer and IT equipment is necessary.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

48- EUROPEAN CHEMICALS AGENCY, EU (ECHA) – PIC: 894182376

The European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) will be task co-leader of Task 2.1, coordinating the prioritisation process. Review of project proposals and recommendations to Governing Board based on their relevance to regulatory needs and requirements.

Task 2.1 – The European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) is task co-leader of Task 2.1, coordinating the prioritisation process. During the first year ECHA will help to develop and define a proposal for an overall PARC Prioritisation process and prioritisation criteria. The criteria are intended to assess the policy/regulatory relevance of project proposals so the knowledge generated within PARC can contribute to EU regulatory science and policymaking. ECHA will contribute to the pool of internal reviewers created for the project review process and will act as a reviewer of several PARC projects. ECHA’s knowledge on regulatory science will also serve to guide PARC projects towards regulatory uptake through continuous interaction with different working packages and projects leaders and its participation in workshops and bilateral discussions when required. ECHA can also support the selection of case studies for further data generation (e.g. on substances of concern) and the development and validation of methods.

To allow for National and European policy-makers to submit requests for specific information to the

PARC Consortium thus ensuring PARC responds to new and urgent needs for information in the EU policy context and at national level, outside of the formal timeframes for substance nomination, ECHA will also help to set up the principles and process for a Rapid Response Mechanism (RRM), building on the HBM4EU's experience. der of Task 2.1, coordinating the prioritisation process. During the first year ECHA will help to develop and define a proposal for an overall PARC Prioritisation process and prioritisation criteria. The criteria are intended to assess the policy/regulatory relevance of project proposals so the knowledge generated within PARC can contribute to EU regulatory science and policymaking. ECHA will contribute to the pool of internal reviewers created for the project review process and will act as a reviewer of several PARC projects. ECHA's knowledge on regulatory science will also serve to guide PARC projects towards regulatory uptake through continuous interaction with different working packages and projects leaders and its participation in workshops and bilateral discussions when required. ECHA can also support the selection of case studies for further data generation (e.g. on substances of concern) and the development and validation of methods.

To allow for National and European policy-makers to submit requests for specific information to the PARC Consortium thus ensuring PARC responds to new and urgent needs for information in the EU policy context and at national level, outside of the formal timeframes for substance nomination, ECHA will also help to set up the principles and process for a Rapid Response Mechanism (RRM), building on the HBM4EU's experience.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (Article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

49- EUROPEAN FOOD SAFETY AUTHORITY, EU (EFSA) – PIC: 893964320	
During the first year of PARC, EFSA will be involved in:	
-Task 2.1: Setting up the process for mapping of needs and prioritisation. Organising the review of the projects proposals, updating of the rolling work plan, supporting the development and drafting of the 3-year common strategy.	
-Task 6.2: Contribution to Y1 projects on integrative risk assessments of chemicals and mixtures of thereof via food, drinking water, air, soil, consumer products, water and at the workplace.	
-Task 7.2: Contribution to drafting the architecture for PARC FAIR data platform and to starting the implementation of first use cases.	
Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

50- Department of Health, UK (UKHSA) – PIC: 986454887

The Department of Health (UK Health Security Agency - UKHSA) will be the National Hub Contact Point for the UK and will coordinate all input from UK partners into PARC and vice versa. The scientific input will focus mainly on WPs 4, 5 and 6: UKHSA are Work package leaders in both HBM4EU and GOLIATH project and as such have extensive experience in core aspects of these WPs.

In the first year for WP4 - the assessment of human and environmental exposure - UKHSA will (1) develop laboratory methods for exposure and effect markers for the prioritised chemicals (T4.1.2) (2) Derive health based HBM guidance values (T4.1.3) and (3) strengthen the link between exposure and health using early effect markers (T4.1.3), information on effect biomarkers will be combined with mechanisms of action to identify classic/clinical and novel biomarkers of adverse health.

For WP5 - UKHSA will begin the development and assessment of in vitro approaches for the testing and assessment of non-genotoxic carcinogens and metabolic disrupting chemicals (T5.2). With respect to T6.1 in the first year UKHSA will be involved in the human relevance assessment, the IATA development for EDs, liver STOT, and genotoxicity, and will specifically feed in recent and current activities at the OECD, in relation to endocrine and metabolic disruption, liver, and nongenotoxic carcinogenicity, and also development and testing with case studies. UKHSA in house analytical capability LC-HRMS, GC-MS, GC-MS/MS and ICPMS with laser ablation & ion chromatography) and expertise in human biomonitoring and environmental assessment as well as in vitro and in vivo model systems, including disease models, for the toxicological assessment and molecular end point analysis – real-time PCR, automated cell imaging and high-throughput sequencing instruments.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

51- BRUNEL UNIVERSITY LONDON, UK (BUL) – PIC: 999749610

Brunel University London (BUL) will contribute to the task 6.4. As part of Task 6.4, BUL will lead the activity of developing regulatory relevant approaches and methods for chemical mixtures, regarding human health and the environment.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

52- THE SECRETARY OF STATE FOR ENVIRONMENT, FOOD AND RURAL AFFAIRS,

UK (Cefas-Defra) – PIC: 999904713

The Department for the environment food and rural affairs (Defra) will to support task 2.2 efforts to install a network of internal and external partners. Preparation for and participation in WP/task meetings and plan for future deliverables. Defra promotes efforts on building a science & policy interface, including through engagement with the OECD and national and international experts to support evidence-based policy making. This will in turn strengthen relationship within the UK, including with Hazardous Substances Committee (HSAC), as well as with international partners through engagement in OECD work areas relevant to chemicals risk assessment and the science policy interface.

Centre for Environment Fisheries and Aquaculture Science (Cefas) - will input to method development (Development of a Fish embryo method for neurotoxicity) and planning for future years deliverables (task 5.1b).

Defra in task 8.1.2. will begin engagement with UK stakeholders on ‘Safe and Sustainable by design’ to familiarise them with the concept and gain understanding of user needs to help inform toolbox development. Preparation for and participation in WP/task meetings and follow up work. Planning for future deliverables. Defra lead on sustainable chemistry policy for the UK which includes but is not limited to Safe and Sustainable by Design.

Additionally, all UK partners will participate in discussions within WP leaders to understand if and how UK can contribute in a more integrated way to future years’ work.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

53- UK CENTRE FOR ECOLOGY & HYDROLOGY, UK (UKCEH) – PIC: 897953251

UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology (UKCEH), will in Y1 focus participation in the science progress and planning meetings, doing so to be part of developing the PARC Y2-7 work plans and integrate UKCEH science contribution and co-funded delivery therein (tasks 4.2.1-6, 4.3.1-5).

In WP5, UKCEH – will focus its participation in the science progress and planning meetings only, doing so to be part of developing the PARC Y2-7 work plans (tasks 5.1b, 5.2b, 5.3.2, 5.2.4)

In WP6, UKCEH – will focus its participation in the science progress and planning meetings only, doing so to be part of developing the PARC Y2-7 work plans (tasks 6.1.4 and 6.4.4.)

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

54- ENVIRONMENT AGENCY, UK (EA) – PIC: 998712001

In WP4, the Environment Agency (EA) will link their work and expertise on PFAS into the PFAS and endocrine disruptor project (task 4.2.2).

EA, will also be involved in WP8. Specifically, and Task 8.2- where the EA will integrate their work into the Early Warning System workstream with contributions 8.2.1 (Implement development on non-target screening monitoring tools), 8.2.2 (Concept and valuation of metabolomics to supplement ecological and chemical investigation), 8.2.3 (PFAS case study on water and PFAS pathways-development of GIS tools for PFAS source- pathway- receptor) and 8.2.4 (Ranking of substances using existing tools)

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (Article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)? *	N
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Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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55- HEALTH AND SAFETY EXECUTIVE, UK (HSE) – PIC: 999461811

Tasks 4.1.1 and 4.1.4 - both the Health and Safety Executive (HSE) as the UK Government regulator for occupational health and safety in Great Britain and the competent authority for chemicals regulation and The Institute of Occupational Medicine (IOM) - will be involved in planning tasks for the ‘Occupational survey health care sector’ and the ‘Feasibility study to evaluate occupational exposure in general surveys. This will include contributing to meeting discussions and to the drafting of project plans. Study design, and other preparatory work (e.g., standard operating procedures, ethics and recruitment materials) for implementation in subsequent years. HSE and IOM will be involved in conducting field surveys in the UK and analysing samples according to PARC harmonised methods/with external quality assurance in years 2 onwards. HSE has a leading human biomonitoring laboratory.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (Article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)? *	N
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Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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56- INSTITUTE OF OCCUPATIONAL MEDICINE, UK (IOM) – PIC: 999464818

Tasks 4.1.1 and 4.1.4 - both the Health and Safety Executive (HSE) as the UK Government regulator for occupational health and safety in Great Britain and the competent authority for chemicals regulation and The Institute of Occupational Medicine (IOM) - will be involved in planning tasks for the ‘Occupational survey health care sector’ and the ‘Feasibility study to evaluate occupational exposure in general surveys. This will include contributing to meeting discussions and to the drafting of project

plans. Study design, and other preparatory work (e.g., standard operating procedures, ethics and recruitment materials) for implementation in subsequent years. HSE and IOM will be involved in conducting field surveys in the UK and analysing samples according to PARC harmonised methods/with external quality assurance in years 2 onwards. HSE has a leading human biomonitoring laboratory.	
Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (Article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)? *	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

57- UNIVERSITY OF BATH, UK (UBAH) – PIC: 999842924

University of Bath (UBAH) – will input to task 4.3. Specifically, suspect screening approaches for chemicals in wastewater – evaluation of existing approaches and retrospective analysis of existing data. UBAH will a design a UK case study linking wastewater and human biomonitoring with an aim of comprehensive spatio-temporal community-wide profiling of chemical exposure via high resolution mass spectrometry and targeted screening. This work contributes to Project 4.3_02: Mining chemical information from wastewater treatment plants for I. human community and II. environmental exposure assessment.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (Article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)? *	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

58- UNIVERSITY OF ABERDEEN, UK (UNIABDN) – PIC: 999929448

In WP4, University of Aberdeen (UNIABDN) - will highlight the collection of human foetuses and their placentas and extend collection term placentas, working towards other maternal and neonatal samples to support the development and validation of novel samples methods and matrices for assessment of chemical burden in the vulnerable group (task 4.3.1).

In WP5 UNIABDN in task 5.1a will contribute to the review of data gaps, especially in exposure to human foetus. Will work on how to close data gaps and contribution of UNIABDN and FREIA foetal human exposure data to contribute to improved human ECC effect understanding and pregnancy PBK modelling.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (Article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
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Agreement (MGA))?	
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)? *	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

59- THE UNIVERSITY OF BIRMINGHAM, UK (UOB) – PIC: 999907526

The University of Birmingham (UOB) will in task 2.2 develop the NAM Toolbox for predicting chemical toxicity – PrecisionTox is creating a comprehensive data management, data integration and data dissemination “toolbox” for rapid interrogation of chemical-coupled omics datasets and of molecular mechanisms predictive of human toxicity, including NAM-based chemical hazard classification and prediction tools for uptake into regulation and policy. Here UOB will provide guidance for the integration of the PrecisionTox NAM toolbox with the PARCopedia knowledge platform. UOB will also contribute to PARCroute road maps the identified socio-technical barriers to the take up of NAMs and opportunities for assimilation of NAMs within existing and evolved regulatory structures and other governance structures including law.

In WP5, UOB will contribute to Regulatory relevant case-studies – Contribute the demonstrated uses of chemical-coupled omics datasets and of molecular mechanisms predictive of human and environmental toxicity (precision toxicology biomarkers) for classifying and regulating hazardous chemicals by three case studies (task 5.1).

UOB will contribute to tasks 6.1.1-6.1.2, Molecular mechanisms of toxicity for IATAs – Contribute adverse outcome pathways (AOPs), IATAS derived from PrecisionTox, and the determined best courses of action to exercise regulatory powers via case studies with regulators and other stakeholders, in relation to substances of toxicological concern based on weight of evidence provided by NAMs (chemical-coupled omics datasets and of molecular mechanisms predictive of toxicity); to Task 6.4.4, Precision Environmental Health – Contribute methodology for precision toxicology for the overall protection of biodiversity, using explainable Machine Learning (ML) and environmental DNA monitoring; and to task 6.4.2, Soft-law regulatory acceptance of Omics data – Contribute to the creation of guidance and instructions for the use and reporting of omics datasets enabling precision toxicology by industry for regulatory compliance.

UoB is WP7 Co-lead as they have extensive experience in FAIR principles.

UoB as Co-lead of task 7.1 will develop the PARC FAIR data policy (PFDP) and data governance strategy. Leveraging ongoing efforts in H2020 NanoCommons and SCENARIOS projects. UoB will contribute to development of the policy, and the use cases for nanotoxicology and mixture toxicology as well as PFAS and exposure assessment. UoB will provide domain expertise and data management expertise to support the use cases and tools for data mining, data curation and on-the-fly ontological annotation of data to ensure harmonisation and fit to existing database data schema (Task 7.2 Data libraries) and will contribute to development of an inventory of ontology-based approaches and frameworks for knowledge integration and provide tools for linking datasets and knowledge and text mining (task 7.3).

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)?*	N

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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60- UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON, UK (UCL) – PIC: 999975620

The University College London (UCL) will contribute to the task 6.3. Within task 6.3, UCL will lead Case Study 13 (CS13) on the regulation of plasticisers depending on intended use. This case study will build on and complements efforts related to harmonisation of testing requirements and hazard assessments envisaged by the ‘One Substance One Assessment’ approach as described in the European Chemical Strategy for Sustainability and is connected to task 8.1. UCL will also contribute to Case Study 1 - Identification and review of methods for evaluating the effectiveness of risk assessment for reducing risk that is aligned with the WP6.3 aim of “evaluation of efficiency of current practices” by increasing the understanding of how to measure the effectiveness of risk assessment aimed at reducing risk.

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be sub-contracted) (Article 6.2 B and 9.3 of Model Grant Agreement (MGA))?	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by affiliated entities (article 8 of MGA)? *	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N

2.2.b General description of the Participants

1- AGENCE NATIONALE DE LA SECURITE SANITAIRE DE L’ALIMENTATION DE L’ENVIRONNEMENT ET DU TRAVAIL, FRANCE (ANSES) – PIC : 983552356

The French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES) is a public administrative institution which undertakes independent and pluralistic scientific expert assessments. Its primary task is to ensure human health and safety with regard to the environment, the workplace and food. ANSES's role is to conduct risk assessment, to provide the relevant authorities with all the information on these risks and the expert assessment and scientific and technical support necessary for the drafting of laws and regulations and the implementation of risk management measures. The Agency is strongly committed to contributing to scientific expertise at the European Union and international levels, through its involvement with EU Agencies and committees as well as with international scientific panels set up by organisations such as the WHO, FAO or OECD. The Agency also relies on a network of 9 reference and research laboratories that are internationally recognised in various fields or disciplines. ANSES is also a major player in European and international research through participating in many European or international research projects.

ANSES has 13 affiliated entities involved in PARC. All of them are linked to ANSES through the R31 Network agreement (Article R1313-1 “du code la santé publique”), which federates the available scientific skills around issues of health risk assessment.

1.1 INSERM – PIC 999997833: public scientific and technological institute which operates under the joint authority of the French Ministries of Health and Research. The institute is dedicated to biomedical research and human health, and is involved in the entire range of activities from the laboratory to the patient’s bedside.

1.2 INRAE – PIC 999993274: French National Research Institute on Agriculture, Food and Environment. Several INRAE research teams are involved in the PARC proposal, making available their competences in food/human toxicology as well as environmental/eco-toxicology (terrestrial and aquatic habitats).

1.3 CEA – PIC 999993274: French Alternative Energies and Atomic Energy Commission (Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives). It is a public body established in October 1945 by General de Gaulle. A leader in research, development and innovation, the CEA mission statement has two main objectives: To become the leading technological research organisation in Europe and to ensure that the nuclear deterrent remains effective in the future. Health and information technologies are a major focus of the CEA, as a prominent player in European technological research. Mathematics, life sciences and computing are part of the interdisciplinary scientific expertise at the Saclay research center (5,000 researchers and collaborators). CEA has a strong experience in EU projects and industrial collaborations.

1.4 INERIS – PIC 999958063: French National Institute for Industrial Environment and Risks, is a large public research institute (500 people) under the supervision of the Ministry of Ecology and Sustainable Development. INERIS's mission is to assess and prevent accidental and chronic risks induced by economic activities to the environment, health and safety of people and goods.

1.5 CNRS – PIC 999997930: Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS) is a government-funded research organisation under the administrative authority of French Ministry in charge of research. CNRS is the main fundamental research organisation in Europe and is largely involved in national, European, and international projects covering all fields of knowledge. CNRS Research Units are very often Joint Research Units, an organisational scheme where different scientific research entities cooperate, leading to the researchers part of the units having different employers.

1.6 INRS – PIC 998626835: INRS is a non-profit organisation set up under the aegis of National Health Insurance Fund for Salaried Workers (CNAMTS) in 1947. It is managed by a joint board of directors representing employers and employees and has a staff of about 580, including researchers, engineers, physicians, trainers, and information specialists in varied disciplines. INRS aims to contribute to the prevention of occupational accidents and diseases and the improvement of working conditions.

1.7 ONIRIS – PIC 986014022: The Nantes-Atlantic National College of Veterinary Medicine, Food Science and Engineering (French: École nationale vétérinaire, agroalimentaire et de l'alimentation, Nantes-Atlantique) also known as Oniris or Oniris Nantes, is a French educational institution. It operates under the supervision of the ministry of Agriculture. It opened on 1 January 2010 in Nantes, in the Pays de la Loire region. Oniris was the result of the fusion of the National Veterinary School of Nantes, established in 1979, and of the National School of Agri-Food Engineering of Nantes, established in 1974. It is one of four French national colleges training veterinary surgeons. It also trains agri-food engineers

1.8 IRSN – PIC: 999480726: French public establishment of industrial and commercial nature placed under the joint authority of the Ministries of Environment, Health, Industry, Research and Defence. IRSN's fields of expertise cover all situations with risks of exposure to ionising radiation of industrial, medical or even natural origin. The research activities, most often carried out within the framework of international programs, enable IRSN to maintain and develop its expertise and to establish its international stature as a world-class specialist of ionising radiations risk management. IRSN is in particular in charge to conduct R&D and expertise in the field of Radiation Protection for Human and in the environment.

1.9 OFB – PIC 894000307: The French Biodiversity Agency (OFB) holds mission to protect and restore

biodiversity in Metropolitan France and its Overseas Territories. It is a public institution under the authority of the ministries responsible for Ecology and Agriculture & Food. It aims at sharing knowledge, research and expertise about species, habitats and their uses, policing environmental and wildlife health, supporting the implementation of public policies, assisting and supporting protected natural area managers, as well as supporting stakeholders and mobilising civil society.

1.10 BRGM – PIC 999993662: Bureau de recherches géologiques et minières (BRGM) is France's leading public institution for Earth Science applications for the management of surface and sub-surface resources with a view to sustainable development (French Geological Survey). Created in 1959, it operates as a public industrial and commercial institution (~ 1000 members of staff including over 700 engineers and researchers), reporting to the Ministries in charge of Research, Ecology and the Economy. Under partnerships with numerous public and private stakeholders (national, European, international), it focuses on scientific research, providing scientifically-validated information to support public policy development. Its activity meets several objectives such as developing new techniques and methodologies, producing and distributing data for surface, subsurface and resource management (in particular groundwater), providing the tools required to manage the surface, subsurface and resources, prevent risks and pollution, and manage policies. BRGM is involved in several networks (national or European) such as the NORMAN, Water Europe or Eurogeosurveys. BRGM is member of EC DG ENV CIS Working Groups (Common Implementation Strategy for the Water Framework Directive). BRGM is also a founder member of the national AQUAREF network (public laboratories). BRGM is certified to the international standard ISO 9001 for all its activities and facilities, and ISO 14001 for all its activities and the Orléans site.

1.11 LNE – PIC 998801144: (Laboratoire national de métrologie et d'essais) is committed to excellence in measurement and testing as well as to progress in quality and safety, for the benefit of industries and consumers alike. LNE's public service mission has been specified in a fulfilment agreement drawn up every four years with the French government. This enables LNE to operate as the national reference laboratory in metrology for French industry - to pursue its scientific and technological development in order to anticipate new measurement and testing in the spheres of safety, health, quality and environmental protection - to provide state authorities and key economic players with the technical assistance they require to draft new regulations and standards at national, Eu and ww level, develop new test methods and carry out market surveillance.

1.12 CSTB – PIC 999580151: The Centre Scientifique et Technique du Bâtiment (Scientific and Technical Center for Building) CSTB, is the French national organisation providing research and innovation, consultancy, testing, training and certification services in the construction industry. The mission of the CSTB is to ensure the quality and safety of buildings, and support innovation from the idea to the market. It brings together multidisciplinary skills to develop and share essential scientific and technical knowledge, and to provide stakeholders with answers to the challenges of their professional practice. The CSTB focuses on four key activities: research and consulting, assessment, certification and dissemination of knowledge. Its field of expertise covers construction products, buildings, and their integration into neighborhoods and cities.

1.13 EHESP – PIC 998161429 (École des hautes études en santé publique) is a public establishment with a dual role of education and research in public health and social welfare. Its research activities fall for a part within social and health policies, health promotion and disease prevention, health safety, in particular in the environmental and occupational health field.

2- AGENCE NATIONALE DE SANTE PUBLIQUE, FRANCE (SpF) – PIC: 917843489

Santé publique France (SpF) has developed more than 25 years of skills in setting up extensive population surveys such as ENNS and Esteban studies, performing quantitative risk assessment (RA)

at a population level, undertaking field investigation, coordinating and implementing national Human Biomonitoring (HBM) programme.

3- UMWELTBUNDESAMT GESELLSCHAFT MIT BESCHRANKTER HAFTUNG, AUSTRIA (EAA) – PIC: 999452014

The Environment Agency Austria is the Austrian institution responsible for the Risk Assessment and Risk Management for REACH and Biocides and has sound experience in this field. Further, experts of EAA are members of the Scientific Committees of ECHA (RAC, SEAC) as well as ECHA- expert groups (PBT, ED, BPC Working Group for Biocides Human Health, Nanomaterials, bisphenols and PFAS working groups) and of the member states committee (MSC) and the risk management and evaluation platform RiME. EAA as Austria's most important environmental expert organisation provides expertise on the state of the environment, on measures to avoid or reduce environmental pollution, and has in-depth knowledge on relevant EU legislation. EAA has a unique role in Austria's regulatory and scientific framework and has more than 30 years of experience in assessing the state of the environment. The EAA-Laboratories are specialists for environmental pollutants and (human) biomonitoring. EAA is HBM4EU national contact point, Chemical Group Lead for PFAS and has been responsible for the Stakeholder Forum and (co)-leading the work on citizen focus groups and accompanying citizen surveys and supporting Stakeholder Workshops. EAA is coordinator of the Austrian platform for human biomonitoring and involved in risk assessment processes under REACH and UNEP. The laboratory is well equipped with: LC-MS/MS, LC-HRMS, GC/MS, GC-MS/MS, AP-GC-MS/MS, and GC-HRMS, LC-HRMS/MS. ICP-MS and ICP-OES, equipment for element species analysis by means of HPLC-ICP-MS coupling, Micro plastics analysis by FT-IR micro-spectroscopy and imaging with micro-ATR device, CIC for PFAS analyses, TOP assay.

EAA has 9 affiliated entities, which are described below. All affiliated entities are linked with its grant signatory EAA via the Austrian Platform for Human Biomonitoring. This platform has been established by EAA in 2007, since 2016 it is an official advisory board of the Federal Ministry for Climate Action, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology (former Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Environment and Water Management (BMLFUW) and it is responsible for a national report on human biomonitoring to be delivered every second year. The mission statement of the platform depicts the link of the participating institutions, which has been established long time before PARC and will prolong in the future. The platform aims to promote human biomonitoring in Austria as an instrument for promoting health and environmental protection, improving the risk assessment of chemicals, supporting national and European prevention goals and developing national competence for human biomonitoring. All institutions have also collaborated with EAA within various short and long-term research projects.

3.1 AGES – PIC 998254743: AGES has longstanding experience in regulatory needs specifically in the field of controlling and assessing the risks of contaminants, residues, pesticides, additives, pharmaceuticals, and microorganisms for human, animal and plant health. AGES will further contribute to WP3 by members of the Department Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment at AGES with the implementation of questionnaires and evaluation supporting the establishment of the Stakeholder Forum.

3.2 AIT - PIC 999584128: Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH (AIT). The goal of the competence unit Molecular Diagnostics of the Center for Health & Bioresources of AIT is to provide novel biomarkers, molecular assays, bioinformatics procedures, biosensors as well as fully integrated point-of-care devices for the whole range of medical and health applications, with a focus on non-invasive or minimally invasive diagnostics.

3.3 BNN – PIC 966278305: The BioNanoNet Forschungsgesellschaft mbH (BNN) aims to strengthen innovative research by promoting cooperation and creating synergies among people working in the fields of Health & Safety, Data & Sustainability & Enabling Technologies.

3.4 MUI – PIC 999855437: Medical University of Innsbruck (MUI). The Core Facility Metabolomics will provide their long- standing expertise and state-of-the-art technologies for the qualitative and quantitative analysis of small bioorganic molecules and non target analyses.

3.5 MUW – PIC 999989976: Medical University of Vienna (MUW). The Department of Epidemiology and the Center for Pathobiochemistry and Genetics of the Medical University of Vienna have outstanding expertise in environmental epidemiology, exposure modelling, risk assessment, as well as excellent facilities for in-vitro toxicity testing, and genetics. Their focus is on pregnancy health outcomes including pre-eclampsia, foetal growth restriction, and gestational diabetes.

3.6 UG-AT – PIC 999873188: University of Graz (UG), founded in 1585, constitutes one of the largest Austrian research institutions. Numerous outstanding scientists, among them six Nobel price laureates taught and carried out their research at UG, and four more Nobel price laureates studied at UG. Today, about 32,000 students and about 4,000-5,000 employees are active at UG; hence, it contributes significantly to the economic and social life of Graz. The University is highly recognized for its narrow cooperation with national and international partners, it's high responsibility for environmental and social aspects, and for its close contacts to industry. UG offers tailor-made training services to our researchers, as well as different internship packages (Graduate Research Scholarship; Pre-doctorate Research Scholarship, etc.).

UG participates in the Coimbra Group and the Utrecht Network and, since 2019, in the Arqus European University Alliance. As a legal entity under public law, UG is organised in six faculties (Natural Sciences, Environmental and Regional Sciences and Education, Arts and Humanities, Business, Economics and Social Sciences, and Catholic Theology) with a total of 76 institutes, plus the administrative and service institutions. The Rectorate (currently headed by Martin Polaschek), the University Council and the Senate are the governing bodies of UG. UG's annual budget amounts to about 230 M€. For more details, please refer to: <http://www.uni-graz.at/en/university/information/about-the-university/>

3.7 UIBK – PIC 999869114: University of Innsbruck (UIBK) Research at the Institute of Biochemistry is focused on the (patho) physiology of mammalian nutrient signaling and metabolism, from cells to the entire body. Specific focus areas are systems approaches to study the linkage between signaling and metabolism in cancers, congenital disorders and metabolic disease, and the metabolic stress response to xenobiotics. The institute has extensive expertise in studying metabolic signaling and disruption through the mTOR network with biochemical, proteomics, metabolomics and systems modelling approaches.

3.8 UMIT – PIC 999898408: UMIT - Private University for Health Sciences, Medical Informations und Technology. The Department of Public Health, Health Services Research and Health Technology Assessment of UMIT will contribute with its expertise in developing and applying interdisciplinary methods to guide the comprehensive, systematic and practice-oriented assessment of measures and procedures in public health and medicine.

3.9 UNIVIE – PIC 999866883: University of Vienna (UNIVIE) .The Department of Food Chemistry and Toxicology at the Faculty of Chemistry, UNIVIE applies a multi-disciplinary approach to better understand the impact of food- and environment-related molecules on human health and disease from a global perspective. They combine in vitro toxicology, mass spectrometry, and systems-based approaches to investigate exposure, toxicity, and metabolism.

4- VLAAMSE INSTELLING VOOR TECHNOLOGISCH ONDERZOEK N.V., BELGIUM (VITO) – PIC: 999645238

VITO is an independent and customer-oriented research organisation that provides innovative

technological solutions and scientifically based advice and support, based on interdisciplinary research and large-scale demonstrators. VITO has over 20 years of experience in human biomonitoring in (inter)national projects. VITO is co-coordinator of HBM4EU and leads the science-policy pillar and data management and analysis WP. VITO gained profound knowledge on sharing of personal sensitive data and has extensive experience in managing large data infrastructures (data centre, computing clusters) and providing related services.

VITO, DOMG, ISSeP, KULeuven, OVAM, PIH, UAntwerpen, and UH collaborate in the scientific advisory board of the policy working group on chemical risk assessment of the Belgian NEHAP (National Environment and Health Action Plan). As such, these organisations exchange knowledge, insights, information, and best practices, identify expertise, synergies and capacities, and support the Belgian position and communication for projects and activities related to chemical risk assessment, e.g. within the context of Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe, and coordinated by the NEHAP national cell. In addition, VITO, KULeuven, PIH, UAntwerpen, and UH jointly perform policy-supporting research within The Flemish Center of Expertise on Environment and Health, which is a scientific knowledge pool for environmental health in Flanders since 2001, steered by DOMG and OVAM. Since 2002 a human biomonitoring network has been established by the Center as part of a programme on environmental health surveillance (Flemish Environment and Health Studies, FLEHS). Since 2019, ISSeP has been coordinating the Walloon HBM. A scientific cooperation agreement has been established between VITO and ISSEP in relation to the implementation of the Flemish and Walloon biomonitoring campaigns and their evaluation.

4.1 KU Leuven – PIC 999991334: The Centre for Environment and Health, part of the Faculty of Medicine KU Leuven, studies the impact of the environment on health and the reverse, how health can affect individuals' interaction with the environment. The Centre has extensive experience in the field of occupational medicine, disability management and RTW.

4.2 DOMG – PIC 999575107: The Department of Environment and Spatial Development (departement Omgeving, DOMG) is the environmental administration of the Government of Flanders. It takes charge of preparing, following up and evaluating the Flemish environmental and spatial policy.

4.3 UH – PIC 999874934: The Centre for Environmental Sciences at Hasselt University (UH) aims to be an international academic leader in holistic, multi-, and transdisciplinary analyses pertaining to the environment, a source of robust science-driven advice to public and private decision-makers from the local to the international level, and an active promoter of academic and educational expertise in developed and developing countries. The scientific research conducted within UH's Data Science Institute is internationally renowned, both for its theoretical as well as for its applied component.

4.4 PIH – PIC 920268780: The Provincial Institute of Hygiene (PIH) is part of the provincial government. PIH is specialised in recruitment, field work, data management and communication of human biomonitoring studies, analysis of different types of micro- and macro-pollutants in water, soil and waste, development of research and surveillance programs in the field of health and environment, and supporting local and regional governments.

4.5 OVAM – PIC 954439649 The Public Waste Agency of Flanders (OVAM) is the principal public authority in the Belgian region of Flanders for sustainable management of waste, materials and soil and circular economy. OVAM manages a database including data on soil and groundwater analyses, risk activities, etc. and develops policies on waste, materials and soil, thus influencing the implementation of environmental legislation.

4.6 ISSeP – PIC 914156228: The Scientific Institute for Public Service (Institut Scientifique de Service Public, ISSeP) is a type 1 Public Administration Unit carrying R&D activities related to environmental monitoring, environmental/human health risk assessment and nuisance prevention. ISSeP provides

technical and scientific support to the Walloon Administration and Government, other stakeholders from the private and public sector, and citizens. The Institute is recognised as the Walloon reference laboratory.

4.7 UAntwerpen PIC 999902870: The Toxicological Centre of the University of Antwerp (UAntwerpen) has a longstanding experience, analytical skills and instrumental capabilities related to the human biomonitoring and assessment of environmental and human toxicology.

5- SCIENSANO, BELGIUM – PIC: 906160809

SCIENSANO is a Belgian public health institute which activities are closely linked to those described in the PARC Partnership as one of its major objectives is to identify and assess potential health risks associated with human exposure to chemicals supporting health policies in collaboration with national and international governmental agencies, participating in (bio-)monitoring programs and developing standards and expertise

SCIENSANO, UGent, EV-ILVO, and VUB collaborate in the scientific advisory board of the policy working group on chemical risk assessment of the Belgian NEHAP (National Environment and Health Action Plan). As such, these organisations exchange knowledge, insights, information, and best practices and identify expertise, synergies and capacities and support the Belgian position and communication for projects and activities related to chemical risk assessment e.g. within the context of Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe, and coordinated by the NEHAP cell.. Furthermore, SCIENSANO collaborates with VUB, EV-ILVO and UGent in multiple research projects.

5.1 UGENT – PIC 999986096: Universiteit Gent (UGent) is a top100-ranking university with a longstanding experience and state-of-the art labs in the fields of Mycotoxins (with top-1 ExpertScape) and Toxicogenomics.

5.2 EV-ILVO PIC 998175591: Own Capital of the Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture and Fisheries (EV-ILVO) is an independent scientific research institute of Flanders Government aiming at economically, ecologically and socially sustainable agriculture and fisheries in a from-farm to-fork approach.

5.3 VUB – PIC 999902094: The IVTD group of the Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) has been a pioneering force in the field of in vitro experimental toxicology for more than 30 years. The team has built a comprehensive knowledge portfolio regarding the development and optimisation of human-relevant primary and stem cell-derived in vitro liver systems for the toxicity testing of chemicals as well as for in vitro liver disease modelling purposes. IVTD is also active at the international foreground of the adverse outcome pathway (AOP) concept and has experience in the field of genotoxicity. Within WP5,

6- HRVATSKI ZAVOD ZA JAVNO ZDRAVSTVO, CROATIA (CIPH) – PIC: 998128255

CIPH is a central public health institute in the Republic of Croatia. It was founded in 1893 with the aim of promoting health and welfare of the population. CIPH deals with public health, health promotion and education, disease prevention, microbiology, environmental health, school medicine, mental health care and addiction prevention. CIPH's main tasks are to plan, promote and implement measures for the enhancement of population health and reduction of health problems. It prepares and implements prevention programmes and other health care measures aimed at promoting healthy lifestyle. CIPH carries out epidemiological surveillance and proposes, organises and undertakes preventive and counter-epidemic measures. It also plays a crucial role in planning, supervision and evaluation of immunisation. In addition, CIPH performs duties concerned with the analysis and evaluation of water safety and the impact of environmental factors on human health. The Institute functions as a statistical

authority which maintains national public health registries, supervises data storage and coordinates the work of other health registers. CIPH may foster and significantly enhance communication and information exchange between the Commission and stakeholders on the implementation of the Strategy from the perspective of the youngest EC member state that is Mediterranean and Central European country, located between the Adriatic Sea and the Danubian plain.

The link of the participant to the affiliated entity: The link between GS and AE is based on the Agreement on the Conduct of Scientific Research Cooperation (2021) and Business Cooperation Agreement (2015) between these two entities (documents in Croatian are attached as well as translated document by official CIPH translator from 2021). IMROH closely collaborates with CIPH not just in complementary activities related to the general, clinical and occupational health research and professional services, but also in providing expert advice to law and policy makers related to human health, environmental protection and safety at work.

6.1 IMROH – PIC 998300333: The Croatian affiliated entity is the Institute for Medical Research and Occupational Health (IMROH), a multidisciplinary, public research institute that integrates services and products within the analytical, monitoring, toxicological, human safety and consulting sectors, and performs basic and applied research to advance knowledge and innovation related to human health, monitoring general and occupational environment (including air, soil, water, and food pollution). The IMROH laboratories are certified by ISO standards and offers transnational access to its facilities. The IMROH participates in numerous national and international projects focused on hazard and risk assessment of chemicals, medicines, and consumer products, on human health and environment. Its ongoing project, co-financed by European Regional Development Fund, is dedicated to improve research infrastructure and equipment.

7- Ministry of Health of the Republic of Cyprus, CYPRUS (MOH-CY/SGL) – PIC: 994267946
MOH-CY/SGL is the State General Laboratory of Cyprus (SGL) of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Cyprus. It is a Department of the Ministry of Health (MOH) and the official National Control Center for human biomonitoring, foodstuffs, water, environment, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, various consumer goods, controlled drugs and other police exhibits for chemical and biological hazards. The SGL develops a wealth of data on sources of chemical exposures and on food consumption, which are used for policy decision purposes by the Government.
In the frame of chemicals management, it collaborates at national level with Ministries and other Stakeholders and at European and international level with EFSA, ECHA, EEA and the WHO. It is designated as the National Reference Laboratory (NRL) for several matrices and parameters, collaborates closely with European Reference Laboratories (EURL) and participates in EU Networks and Technical Committees and Working Groups.
It established a Risk Assessment Unit in 2008 mainly focused on dietary exposure assessment and has been involved since 2004 in the development of human biomonitoring in Europe as a tool for assessment, management and communication of chemical risks.
The organisation has strong analytical expertise, is equipped with state-of-the-art infrastructure (e.g. GC-MS-MS, GC-MS, NMR, HPLC, ICP, ICP-MS, IR-MS, FTIR-NIR, LC-MS-MS, etc.) and facilities for biological sample processing and storage. It is accredited according to ISO 17025:2017 and has a new Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS) with the ability to extract data for data analysis and transmission if necessary.

7.1 SHSO – PIC 891074787: SHSO is the largest healthcare provider in Cyprus, with 9 hospitals and 38 health centers in all cities and districts, with the Directorate of Mental Health and the Ambulance Service, offering comprehensive health services that cover the full range of needs of the population throughout Cyprus. (Primary and Secondary Health Services). SHSO is linked to the MOH by national legislation.

8- Masarykova univerzita, CZECH REPUBLIC (MU) – PIC: 999880657

MU (RECETOX Centre) has an expertise in the assessment of environmental and human exposures, effects and risks (relevant for PARC WPs 4, 5 and 6) which was demonstrated in the HBM4EU project (management board member, leader of WP13 on AOPs, participating also in WP8 (alignment studies), WP9 (HBM samples analyses), WP10 (data analysis), WP12 (PBPK modelling), WP14 (effects), WP15 (toxic mixtures) and WP16 (NTS approaches for emerging chemicals). Apart from HBM4EU, MU (RECETOX) has participated in the ERA PLANET ERA NET (iGOSP project on global monitoring) as well as numerous other H2020 projects (HERA, EURION cluster, EHEN cluster etc.) in the environment and health nexus. MU (RECETOX) research infrastructure listed in the National RI Roadmap provides capacities of (i) the accredited trace analytical laboratories as well as NTS, toxicology and other specialised laboratories, (ii) resources related to the longitudinal cohort studies (www.elspac.cz, www.celspac.cz), (iii) data warehouses, and capacities for an effective data analysis, interpretation and presentation. These capacities (relevant for WPs 7, 8 and 9) have been used in numerous EU projects. The National Centre for Toxic Compounds hosted at MU (RECETOX) acts at the science-policy interface (relevant for WP 2 and 3) and strives for sound chemicals management and maximisation of protection of human health and environment.

MU has four affiliated entities: University of South Bohemia in České Budějovice - JU (CZ), University of Ostrava - UO (CZ), National Institute of Public Health - SZU-CZ (CZ), and University of Chemistry and Technology in Prague - VSCHT (CZ). AEs have vast experience and capacity in various domains of risk assessment and will be involved in work packages 4 (Monitoring and Exposure) and 9 (Building infrastructural and human capacities).

8.1 SZU-CZ PIC 999478689: Health care establishment for basic preventive disciplines - hygiene, epidemiology, microbiology, and occupational medicine. Its main tasks are health promotion and protection, disease prevention and follow-up of environmental impact on the health status of the population. The main activities of SZU-CZ comprise science and research, reference and methodological advice, providing expert opinions on the product health safety, systematic monitoring of the environmental impacts on population health in the Czech Republic, preparation of legislation in health protection, including harmonization of Czech legislation with the norms of the European Union etc. SZU-CZ produces data for international databases, conventions, reports for EU institutions.

8.2 VSCHT – PIC 999867853: University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague is the largest academic institution of its kind in Central Europe with a history of almost 200 years. Currently, UCT is an educational and research leader in technical (bio)chemistry, food and chemical technologies with a wide range of national and international collaborations. The four Faculties of the UCT are accredited to provide three-year Bachelor programmes, two-year Master programmes and PhD programmes. The Laboratory of Food Quality and Safety, which is a part of The Department of Food Analysis and Nutrition, has available cutting edge instrumentation and is accredited according to the International standard ISO/IEC 17025:2018 by the Czech Institute for Accreditation, a member of ILAC network. In addition to running accredited tests, activities also include (i) development/application of novel analytical methods for control of emerging threats (target screening); (ii) development/application of non-target screening strategies, including metabolomics fingerprinting/profiling followed by chemometric data processing aimed at food / feed / food supplements authentication; (iii) investigation of chemical reactions in food and other natural matrices; (iv) analysis of natural biologically active components; environmental pollutants; residues, processing contaminants and natural toxicants. Special attention is paid to studies on food component interactions / breakdown which may result in changes of nutritional value and/or sensory properties. In the recent years, interdisciplinary ‘omics’-based research aimed at the assessment of in vivo / in vitro effects induced by biologically active compounds, both beneficial and toxic, has been initiated. The research team of UCT has participated in many international projects including 5th, 6th and 7th EC framework program and HORIZON 2020, COST, and many others research nationally funded activities concerned with food and feed quality, authenticity & safety related issues; investigations dealing with the impact of environmental conditions on the human food

chain have been also included.

8.3 OU – PIC 998738870: The University of Ostrava (UO) is a public research university educating nearly 9,000 students in six faculties. Our Faculty of Science, Faculty of Arts, Faculty of Fine Arts and Music, Faculty of Medicine, Faculty of Social Studies, and Faculty of Education offer a wide variety of disciplines and unconventional combinations of majors. As a dynamic and intellectually challenging modern institution the University of Ostrava provides an international environment in which to study. Our campus is spread primarily throughout the old city centre providing a stimulating environment to contemplate the living arts and sciences. Teaching at UO is research-driven, and its programmes are often taught by active researchers. Two departments of two faculties OU should participate in the project PARC.

The Centre for epidemiological research (CER) of the Faculty of medicine deals with impacts of selected environmental and life-style risk factors on population health and aging. It involves identification of both risk and protective factors of health including biological predictors that may help in early diagnosis of diseases. Main research outcomes are markers of health status including genetic, epigenetic and physiological markers, cardiometabolic, oncological, respiratory, infectious, neurodegenerative and mental diseases, and changes in socioeconomic structure of population as well as perception of health risks in relation to increasing age of population. Epidemiological research bring together specialists of infectious and non-communicable epidemiology, natural and social sciences and psychology.

The Department of Chemistry (DCH) of the Faculty of Science is considerably focused on synthesis, characterization and application testing of porous materials, mostly for environmental (water decontamination) or analytical applications (specific sorbents for preconcentration of analytes). Due to this orientation the advanced use and development of analytical methods are naturally included in such research. DCH is experienced specially in inorganic analysis (e.g. metals in various kinds of matrices), partly in organic analysis (e.g. determination of pharmaceuticals in mixture).

8.4 JU – PIC 999876292: The University of South Bohemia in České Budějovice consists of 7 faculties, including Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters (FFPW USB). The FFPW USB is hosting institution of South Bohemian Research Center of Aquaculture and Biodiversity of Hydrocenoses (CENAKVA). The main scientific objective of the CENAKVA research infrastructure is to understand the ongoing processes in freshwater ecosystems and their societal importance in terms of conservation of biodiversity, protection of the aquatic environment, and protection of water resources for life and human activity. Within CENAKVA, 4 key research programs are established. The attentions of Research Program 2 targets excellent comprehensive research of the fate of ‘new’ extraneous compounds in aquatic and soil environments and a critical assessment of their impacts on exposed organisms and communities. Unique findings from significant spheres of identification, occurrence, fate, and comprehensive effects of extraneous compounds and their transformation products under real ecosystems conditions are eagerly investigated. Newly discovered findings have a key significance for economically meaningful strategic planning in the field of wastewater treatment, drinking water treatment, and landscape management. At the same time, modern methods for the use of passive samplers in the sphere of national monitoring programs focused on contamination of the aquatic environment and effective analytical methods for monitoring a wide spectrum of micropollutants in different components of the environment and passive samplers are available for practice.

9- USTAV ZDRAVOTNICKÝCH INFORMACÍ A STATISTIKY ČESKÉ REPUBLIKY, CZECH REPUBLIC (UZIS) – PIC: 920415929

UZIS: The Institute of Health Information and Statistics of the Czech Republic (Ústav zdravotnických informací a statistiky, UZIS; <https://www.uzis.cz/index-en.php>) is a government organisation established by the Ministry of Health of the Czech Republic that is responsible for collecting information concerning health statistics in the entire territory of the Czech Republic. UZIS develops and administers health registries and provides population-based data analysis (health services,

epidemiology), public health monitoring and reporting, and policy advice.

10- The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, DENMARK (DEPA) – PIC: 938989101

DEPA is a governmental agency, who provides technical advice to the Ministry and coordinates the research with the Danish research Institutions within the fields of e.g. toxicology, environmental toxicology, and hazard assessment. Therefore DEPA already has an established network with the affiliated entities including a financial framework. DEPA does not conduct research itself and does not have e.g. a laboratory with technical equipment, but finances research within the field.

10.1 AU – PIC 999997736: DEPA has a framework contract with AU on research-based scientific advice provided by AU to the participant. AU will participate in PARC with expertise in human health and environment, represented by researchers from the Department of Public Health and the Department of Environmental Science/Danish Centre for Environment and Energy.

10.2 DTU FOOD – PIC 999990655: The university has (in 2020 figures) around 13,000 students and consists of 18 departments, 6 research centres and 4 companies with a total of 5900 staff employed. Two departments National Food Institute (DTU Food) and Department of Technology, Management and Economics (DTU Management) are involved in the PARC project. DTU Food is responsible for a large part of the research-based public sector consultancy within nutrition, food quality, food safety and environment and health where the Institute provides consulting services to the Danish Environmental Protection Agency.

10.3 REGIONH – PIC 999654744: Region Hovedstaden (RegionH): Region Hovedstaden is a non-academic, non-profit public body with approx. 40,000 full time employees, of which 4,700 are employed in R&D. The main type of R&D activity lies within life sciences. RegionH's annual turnover amounts to approx. 6 bn EURO. Region H comprises seven hospitals and its main obligation is to provide and manage health care service for the citizens living in the Greater Copenhagen area. Region Hovedstaden has collaboration contracts with the Danish EPA for management of respectively a knowledge center on endocrine disrupting chemicals run by Dept. of Growth and Reproduction at Rigshospitalet and a knowledge centre on allergy run Dept. of Skin and Allergy located at Gentofte Hospital. In PARC RegionH will participate as affiliated entity to the DK-EPA with contribution from these two departments.

10.4 UCPH – PIC 999991043: UCPH are actively working on target, suspect, and non-target screening analysis of various environmental matrices. For this purpose we use standard LC-HRMS equipment but also methods such as GCxGC-HRMS and SFC-HRMS is used to provide complementary information. We work with matrix-correction methods and quantification estimation in GC and LC – MS methods; and develop and implement workflows for feature detection, curve resolution and compound identification. This knowhow will be shared with other partners in Task 4.3 and WP9 and is highly relevant.

10.5 SDU – PIC 999904616 : SDU has a long pre-existing link to the DEPA with multiple projects related to improved hazard and risk assessment of chemicals and SDU has already submitted to PARC two contracts between DK-Danish Environmental Protection Agency (DEPA) and University of Southern Denmark (SDU) on projects covering development and validation of ecotoxicological test methods for the assessment of endocrine disrupters with the purpose of developing OECD test guidelines. J.nr 621-00066 covers 2013-2016 and J.nr 621-00212 covers 2017-2020. For 2021 a project (2020-50256) was recently signed. These contracts are the latest in a series of collaborations between DEPA and SDU on Test Guideline development to improve hazard and risk assessment of endocrine disrupting chemicals starting in 2001. SDU is also part of a network on endocrine disrupters chaired by DEPA since 2001. SDU is expert in the development and improvement of the guidelines used for hazard and risk assessment of chemicals and host high-end laboratory facilities for experimental work with

aquatic invertebrates and vertebrates as well as state of the art equipment for chemical analysis such as LC-MSMS and GC-MSMS.

11- TERVISEAMET, ESTONIA (HB) – PIC: 933659727

The Estonian Health Board is a governmental institution, which acts on behalf of public health and a healthy living environment. HB has previously coordinated projects dealing with environmental health effects of the oil shale sector, which also brought us to our biomonitoring pre-study, which has also provided us with the know-how to initiate a national biomonitoring study.

The pre-existing link with the The Ministry of Social Affairs is cooperation agreement and for the University of Tartu this is a Memorandum of Understanding.

11.1 SOM – PIC 998429731: The ministry was established in 2010 with an aim to target policies in the area of children rights, children health etc

11.2 UT – PIC 999895013: The University of Tartu is the only classical university in Estonia to do research in arts and humanities, social sciences, medical sciences and science and technology. The University of Tartu is the leading research university in Estonia and the only Estonian-language university – comprehensive university – in the world. Its competitive advantages are internationality, the quality of teaching and research, and diversity. The university, re-opened as the Estonian-language University of Tartu in 1919, at the beginning of the Republic of Estonia, laid the foundations for Estonian-language higher education and created a community of national intellectuals, who have a significant role in the development of the Estonian state, society and culture.

12- EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENT AGENCY, EUROPE (EEA)

The European Environment Agency (EEA) is an agency of the European Union, whose task is to provide sound, independent information on the environment. The EEA aims to support sustainable development by helping to achieve significant and measurable improvement in Europe's environment, through the provision of timely, targeted, relevant and reliable information to policymaking agents and the public.

The EEA's mandate is:

-To help the Community and member and cooperating countries make informed decisions about improving the environment, integrating environmental considerations into economic policies and moving towards sustainability

-To coordinate the European environment information and observation network (Eionet)

13- TERVEYDEN JA HYVINVOINNIN LAITOS, FINLAND (THL) – PIC: 996697893

Mission of the Chemical Risks team of THL given by the Finnish Ministry of Social and Health is to monitor the exposure and health risk of chemicals to population including vulnerable sub-populations. Chemical risk team in THL has the equipment, facilities and experience to work with harmful environmental pollutants. Laboratory has several equipment for sample preparation (extraction, centrifugation, evaporation and cleanup), two liquid chromatography triple quadrupole mass spectrometers (LC-MS/MS) for PFAS analysis and two gas chromatograph triple quadrupole mass spectrometers (GC-MS/MS) for POP analysis. The laboratory is accredited (T077) by the Finnish Accreditation Services (FINAS) according to the SFS-EN ISO/IEC 17025:2017 standard.

One AE is linked to THL: Finnish Environment Institute (SYKE).

THL and SYKE: Both THL and SYKE are members of National Programme on Hazardous Chemicals, “Risk Group”, set up by Finnish Safety and Chemicals Agency (Tukes). Risk Group was set up to promote co-operation and knowledge sharing between state research institutes and authorities in charge of chemical-related issues for the period 1.4.2020 – 31.12.2022.

13.1 SYKE – PIC 999478010: Finnish Environment Institute (SYKE) is a governmental multidisciplinary research and expert institute providing environmental information, expertise and expert services for public and private decision makers. SYKE has 570 experts and researchers and four office and research facilities in Helsinki, Oulu, Jyväskylä and Joensuu.

SYKE has long-term experience in assessing risks of chemicalisation especially in aquatic environment, including source identification, transport and modelling as well as bioaccumulation, fate and effects. Co-operative partners have been health and food authorities and universities, both domestic and other EU countries. SYKE possess expertise in the field of risk assessment of contaminated soils, both in ecological and human perspectives. This includes determination of threshold values and preparation of legislative acts together with health authorities and national institutes. SYKE has expertise regarding risk assessment in chemical transportation and actual accidents. Special expertise is related to the transport mechanisms and modelling of contaminant behavior as well as ecotoxicity assessment. In recent years SYKE has focused in contaminant identification and management in material circulation and waste reuse as part of sustainable and clean circular economy.

14- TYOTERVEYSLAITOS, FINLAND (TTL) – PIC: 999880948

TTL is a multidisciplinary national research, development and specialist organisation, which work covers all relevant aspects of work life, including surveillance of working conditions, assessment of chemical exposure at work and e.g. occupational medicine. In the field of chemical safety, TTL provides exposure assessment and measurement services on chemical impurities to the workplaces. TTL has long experience on biomonitoring, including both biomonitoring services and research projects related to the biomonitoring of occupational exposure. Several of our methods are accredited by the Finnish Accreditation Service (FINAS). In addition, TTL has special expertise on risk assessment of chemicals and regulatory toxicology (e.g. under REACH) and setting of limit values (OELs and biological limit values) for occupational exposure and its experts are members of scientific committees related to these activities.

AEs linked to TTL include Finnish Food Agency (FFA), Finnish Safety and Chemicals Agency (TUKES) and University of Oulu (UOULU). Linkage between TTL and TUKES and FFA is based on the National Programme on Hazardous Chemicals, “Risk Group”, set up by Finnish Safety and Chemicals Agency (Tukes). TTL also signed a Partnership Agreement in 2014 with UOULU.

14.2 TUKES – PIC 972221301: The Finnish Safety and Chemicals Agency (Tukes) is a competent authority for implementing various EU chemical legislations and the national enforcement authority within chemical products surveillance (e.g. REACH, CLP, Detergents, Biocides, Plant protection products, Cosmetic products, Toys, RoHS, POPs). Tukes enforces compliance of various chemicals and products with regard to particular obligations imposed by legislations. Tukes maintains the national register for chemical products (KemiDigi). Tukes participates in the work of EU agencies such as ECHA (e.g. MSC, RAC, SEAC and Forum) and EFSA and has a lot of EU and Nordic cooperation in the area of chemical safety.

14.1 FFA – PIC 902952534: Authority promotes, monitors and studies the safety and quality of food; the health and wellbeing of animals; plant health; fertiliser products, animal feeds and plant protection products that are used in agricultural and forestry production; and propagating materials i.e. seeds and planting materials. Authority is also responsible for the use of the funds provided by the European Union’s agricultural guarantee and rural development funds in Finland

14.3 UOULU – PIC 999844670: The University of Oulu (UOULU) is a non-profit, higher education providing organization funded largely by the Finnish government. UOULU was founded in 1958 and is among the largest universities in Finland with 15 000 students and 3000 staff members. UOULU has

high-quality research environments for international research groups and is ranked the second-best university in Finland (Academic Ranking of World Universities). The UOULU has experience in participating in European and international projects (including NIH-funded projects) and is well-equipped to manage large-scale projects with multiple international partners. UOULU has been involved in the EU R&D Framework programs since FP4 in more than 260 projects and networks, of which over 20 have been coordinated by UOULU. The Faculty of Medicine, with 1300 students and 400 staff members, has an important role in creating modern, high-quality medical and health care services in northern Finland. Faculty of Medicine has a strong research focus on population health through the Northern Finland Birth Cohorts 1966 and 1986, which include massive data collections as well as coastal cohorts in Oulu (such as the Nugen cohort).

There is also strong multidisciplinary research, especially in Arctic research, which combines health and wellbeing to environmental sciences. The research group of the Arctic health (AH, former Centre for Arctic Medicine) focuses on studying the health and well-being of people in the circumpolar and coastal areas. The main research is at the field of the climate change and human health, including food and water security; environmental health; discrimination and marginalization; and Indigenous health and well-being. The main projects include three EU-funded projects as well as several international projects (listed below). The AH is very well networked with several universities and research institutes in the Arctic and Europe, and it actively participates in the work of the Arctic Council (like Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme, AMAP and Sustainable Development Working Group, SDWG), University of the Arctic, International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) and other networks of One Health. It is co-leading the thematic network of the Health and well-being in the Arctic (University of the Arctic) with more than 20 partners from the different Arctic countries.

15- UMWELTBUNDESAMT, GERMANY (UBA) – PIC: 998575910

UBA is Germany's central environmental authority which is also in charge of the impact of environmental factors on health and the enforcement of environmental and chemical laws. Apart from its Central Administration Division, UBA has five divisions with a total of 14 departments. The German Environment Agency employs more than 1,600 people. In addition to fundamental research, the enforcement of environmental and chemical laws – for example the Human Medicinal Products Regulation, the Veterinary Medicinal Products Regulation, the Biocidal Products Regulation, the REACH Regulation, the Plant Protection Product Regulation and the Water Framework Directive, - and providing information to the general public about environmental protection issues are key areas. UBA is partner of and Germany's contact point for many international institutions (e.g. WHO, EEA, and OECD).

15.1 BfG – PIC 996893445: The BfG is working in the field of qualitative and quantitative hydrology as well as ecology. One mayor focus is the method development for survey and evaluation of data describing the presence, transport and effect of chemicals in surface waters, sediments and dredged materials. The BFG has a long-term experience in design of monitoring and sampling campaigns, development and application of analytical methods for targeted and screening approaches, in the identification of unknown compounds and in effect-based methods.

15.3 IPA – PIC 998343692: IPA's research work aims at the reduction of health risks of insured persons due to various hazardous substances. The goal is to develop preventive measures as well as to improve diagnosis and therapy of occupational diseases and to support the German Social Accident Insurance. Based on long term research collaborations in the field of human biomonitoring IPA and UBA plan to advance and intensify their cooperation. The goal of this collaboration is to use all resources in the most efficient way and combine our expertise to create further synergies. This aims at increasing the quality standard for human biomonitoring even further to strengthen the impact of our research results.

In further detail the partners want to further develop human biomonitoring via the identification of relevant substances, development of new methods, exchange of methodological and technical knowledge and if possible conduction of joint studies.

15.6 KUM – PIC 995625946 the KUM works in the field of diseases that are influenced by occupational, social and environmental factors. Besides physical, psychological and other causes, they investigate the effect of hazardous substances like toxic metals, pesticides and antineoplastic drugs in occupational settings and on the general population. They have long term experience in the conduction of epidemiological and experimental studies.

Based on their research collaborations in the field of human biomonitoring KUM and UBA plan to advance and intensify their cooperation. The goal of this collaboration is to use all resources in the most efficient way and combine our expertise to create further synergies. In further detail this aims at increasing the quality standard for human biomonitoring even further to strengthen the impact of our research results.

15.2 UFZ – PIC 999994632: The UFZ is working on the behaviour and the elucidation of adverse biological effects of chemicals in the environment. This knowledge is used to develop strategies to predict chemicals fate and effects for the risk assessment and provides tools to monitor environmental quality. The UFZ has a long-term experience in the development and application of analytical methods for targeted and screening approaches in the environment and human samples, structure-activity relationships (QSAR), development and application of cell-based bioassays as part of a new risk assessment framework, assessment of mixture effects and effects of chemicals on whole ecosystems.

15.4 UKOLD – PIC 999856407: The UKOLD amongst other topics works and researches in the fields of environmental and sustainability. Their strength and expertise lie especially in the area of researching the effect of anthropogenic stressors like chemical substances in our environment and the connected risk management.

Based on their research collaborations in the field environmental research UKOLD and UBA plan to advance and intensify their cooperation. The goal of this collaboration is to use all resources in the most efficient way and combine our expertise to create further synergies. In further detail this aims at increasing the quality standard for risk assessment of chemicals even further to strengthen the impact of our research results.

15.5 UOS – PIC 999855049: The UOS is known for their research and teaching in the field of social and human studies, cognitive and molecular biology as well as computer science and mathematics. This includes a research centre (IUSF) with long term experience in methods of modelling which aims at understanding environmental systems, predict their exposure to chemicals and evaluate the effects of this exposure.

Based on their research collaborations in the field of human biomonitoring KUM and UBA plan to advance and intensify their cooperation. The goal of this collaboration is to use all resources in the most efficient way and combine our expertise to create further synergies. In further detail this aims at increasing the quality standard for human biomonitoring even further to strengthen the impact of our research results.

16- BUNDESINSTITUT FUER RISIKOBEWERTUNG, GERMANY (BfR) – PIC: 998771171

The BfR was established in November 2002 to strengthen consumer health protection as a successor to previous national institutions, which have worked in the field for more than 100 years. It is the scientific institution of the Federal Republic of Germany that prepares opinions and expertises on questions of food and feed safety, as well as the safety of substances and products with respect to human health. The main tasks of the BfR comprise the evaluation of existing risks and the identification of new ones, the preparation of recommendations for risk limitation and the communication of this process. The BfR also conducts research closely linked to its statutory tasks. Both regulatory work and research feed into the scientific advice given to political decision-makers.

BfR engages in scientific cooperation with international institutions and organisations and with the institutions of other countries involved in consumer health protection and food safety. In the German law it is written that the BfR is entitled to cooperate with other scientific institutions in order to fulfil its obligations under the law.

16.1 Fraunhofer – PIC 999984059: The Fraunhofer Society is Europe's largest non-profit research organization for applied research. As one of 74 institutes and independent research units, the Fraunhofer Institute for Biomedical Engineering IBMT is offering solutions for individual tasks in the areas of e.g. biomedical engineering, cellular biotechnology, (nano)toxicology as well as human biomonitoring and biobanking. The institute promotes the technology transfer to medicine and various areas of industry. With a focus on airway research, our R&D portfolio includes three thematic areas: drug development, chemical safety, and translational biomedical engineering. The Fraunhofer Institute for Toxicology and Experimental Medicine ITEM is one of 74 institutions of the Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft, Europe's leading organization for applied research. Protecting man from health hazards in our industrialized world and contributing to the development of novel therapeutic approaches are the aims Fraunhofer ITEM is pursuing with its contract research. With its expertise ITEM supports government, national and international organisations and industry in assessing the risk of existing and new products. ITEM has currently about 300 employees. Airway research is a main field of expertise applied for three thematic areas: drug development, chemical safety, and translational biomedical engineering

16.2 KIT – PIC 990797674: The Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) is a higher education and research organisation with about 10.000 employees, 25.000 students, and a total annual budget of about 750 million Euro. It bundles the missions of a university of the state of Baden-Wuerttemberg and of a large-scale research institution of the Helmholtz Association. Innovation efforts at KIT build a bridge between important scientific findings and their application for the benefit of society, economic prosperity, and the preservation of our natural basis of life. KIT is one of the German universities of excellence. Higher education, research, and innovation are the three pillars of KIT's activities. In establishing innovative research structures, KIT is pursuing joint strategies and visions. KIT's research profile is characterized by a strong focus on energy technology, nanotechnology and materials research, elementary particle and astroparticle physics as well as climate and environmental research. It has significant competencies in the fields of information and communication technologies, mobility systems, optics and photonics, and the inter-relations of humans and technology.

16.3 IUF – PIC 998707054: The Leibniz Research Institute for Environmental Medicine (IUF) is located in Düsseldorf, Germany. It focuses on the prevention of environmentally-induced diseases by taking an interdisciplinary and translational approach. Specifically, fundamental scientific expertise in the areas of molecular toxicology, molecular immunology, molecular aging research, cell biology and epidemiology are combined in an integrated manner to study environmentally-induced health disturbances with the highest socioeconomical impact. The IUF investigates how environmental factors interfere with molecular processes within an organism and are thereby able to detriment health. In a second step this information is being used for the improvement of risk assessment and the development of novel preventive measures such as drugs, medical devices, nutritional and cosmetic products. In this context, the development and scientific validation of alternative assays predicting the environmental induced disturbance of the developing nervous system is one major focus of the ongoing research program. In order to accomplish its research mission the IUF serves as a partner to national and international Universities and other research organizations, industry partners and government institutions. A cooperation agreement with the Heinrich Heine University Düsseldorf gives the IUF the status of an affiliated institute.

16.4 IfaDo – PIC 998770686: The Leibniz Research Centre for Working Environment and Human Factors (IfaDo; funded in 1912) investigates basics of the physiological processes of the liver, brain and immune system in the context of the working environment. IfaDo consists of four departments:

Toxicology, Immunology, Neurosciences and Ergonomics. The Toxicology Department has a strong focus on the molecular mechanisms of chemicals and has established toxicity tests that meanwhile are used worldwide.

16.5 MLU – PIC 999871539: The Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg is the largest university in Saxony-Anhalt. It is part of the Central German University Alliance Halle-Jena-Leipzig. The university's core scientific research is in Biosciences; the Institute for Agricultural and Nutritional Sciences plays a leading role in the university. The institute has two major research areas: "Molecular plant research" as well as "Molecular research in animals and humans" with close collaboration between the groups. The institute cooperates closely with the Institute for Environmental Toxicology which belongs to the Medical Faculty. Furthermore, collaborations with other faculties and universities, external research institutes and industries exist.

16.6 UKL – PIC 999885895: The University of Koblenz and Landau (UKL) is one of the youngest German universities and has almost 17,000 students. It hosts the iES Landau, the Institute of Environmental Sciences, which is one of the largest national Institutes devoted to research in the Environmental Sciences. The iES Landau has a special focus on Ecotoxicology and is one of the two German locations offering a M.Sc. course in Ecotoxicology. The iES Landau has about 200 staff members and 500 students and is involved in > 60 national and international research projects, among these 5 coordinated EU projects. The fate and effects of chemicals in ecosystems is one of the core research topics in the iES Landau. Besides a coordinated large research project on chemical stressors and their action in a meta-ecosystem context (SystemLink), many other coordinated and individual projects on chemicals are and have been led by researchers from the iES. Notably, several members of the iES have been involved in initiatives to improve the risk assessment of chemicals in aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems, including in the implementation of the National Action Plan on pesticides in Germany as well as serving as experts for the European Food Safety Authority. Researchers from the iES Landau will contribute to PARC their expertise in (1) monitoring pesticides in the environment, (2) identifying and modelling effects of pesticides in ecosystems and (3) assessing the risks of chemicals in ecosystems and evaluating related methods.

16.7 TUB – PIC 999986678 : The Technische Universität Berlin (TUB) established in 1946 as a successor of a Royal Technical Academy of Berlin is a member of the Berlin. It has ca. 35.000 students and ~3.100 people accounted to academic staff. The university is a member of TU9, an incorporated society of the largest and most notable German institutes of technology and part of the Berlin University Alliance, has been conferred the title of "University of Excellence" under and receiving funding from the German Universities Excellence Initiative. One of the focal points of research and education is human health.

16.8 UKON – PIC 999866204: The University of Konstanz is located in Konstanz, Germany, and since 2006 it continuously held the status of an excellence university within the German excellence initiative. Within the department of biology, there has always been a focus area of biomedical research, including pharmacology and toxicology. With four chairs of toxicology, Konstanz has the largest cluster of toxicological research at German universities.

16.9 TiHo – PIC 999464430: The University of Veterinary Medicine Hannover, Foundation (TiHo), established in 1778, is a nationally and internationally renowned university with excellent veterinary sciences and an interdisciplinary orientation. The TiHo occupies a top position in research, teaching and service for humans and animals and trains the next generation for all areas of veterinary medicine. The wide-ranging basic and application-oriented research at the TiHo produces results of the highest international standard in veterinary medicine and animal biology. In addition to infectious medicine, clinical research and systemic neuroscience, a major focus is the promotion of animal health and food safety/quality. Research at TiHo aims at improving the understanding of the development, prevention

and treatment of diseases as well as animal welfare. Further, research at TiHo is conducted for the health of food-producing animals, food quality, consumer safety, and on the importance of animal genetic diversity. The expansion of regional, national and international cooperations with universities and non-university research institutions, including the BfR, further support the achievement of the research goals.

17- NEMZETI NEPEGESZSEGUGYI KOZPONT, HUNGARY (NPHC) – PIC: 998706957

The National Public Health Center (Nemzeti Népegészségügyi Központ, NNK) is the main public health body in Hungary. It is a central governmental office in Hungary with nationwide competence, and is responsible for developing and controlling national public health programs in the field of public health, environmental and settlement health, radiohygiene and chemical safety, health development and occupational health. Three units intend to participate in the partnership: the Air Hygiene and Human Biomonitoring Laboratory, the Unit of Radiation Medicine and the Department of Communication. NPHC has trained communication experts, epidemiologist, scientists and management team to carry out the work. A modern instrumental analytical laboratory equipped with separation and detection techniques (e.g. LC-MS/MS, GC-MS/MS) to investigate substances in environmental and human samples is also available. NPHC has real-time PCR machines, flow cytometers, fluorescent microscopes and other tools to perform toxicological tests.

18- HASKOLI ISLANDS, ICELAND (UI) – PIC: 999884246

University of Iceland (UI) is the leading scientific and educational institution in Iceland with 13.000 students, including around 3500 postgraduates. The responsibilities of the UI also extend far beyond research and teaching obligations as expertise of its academic staff play a key role in both research and in providing expert opinions when it comes to chemical risk assessment, human and environmental monitoring of chemicals.

19- MINISTRY OF HEALTH, ISRAEL (MOH) – PIC: 999596156

Public Health Services of the Ministry of Health is Israel's central authority on environmental health under the jurisdiction of the Israel Ministry of Health. Key areas include enforcement in the field of environmental health and food contaminants, as well as chemical risk assessment and policy development in a broad range of environmental health fields including pesticides and biocides, air pollution, and consumer products. Public Health Services collaborates in research and policy development activities with a broad range of stakeholders including government Ministries (for example the Ministry of Environmental Protection, Ministry of Agriculture), academic institutions and research bodies within the Ministry of Health (Israel Center for Disease Control, Department of Environmental Epidemiology, Cancer Registry).

20- ISTITUTO SUPERIORE DI SANITA, ITALY (ISS) – PIC: 999978821

ISS is one of the main Italian research institutes and a scientific body of the Italian National Health Service, particularly active in both research and regulatory activities in the field of risks connected with exposure to chemicals for both human health and the environment. ISS constantly provides advice to the Ministry of Health and to other Ministries in the definition of laws and regulations and is involved in regulatory activities regarding chemical safety by contributing to Committees and working groups in International institutions (EU Commission, EFSA, ECHA, OECD, WHO). ISS has accredited reference labs and dedicated equipment and trained personnel to perform the above-mentioned activities.

Given the positive results of past and ongoing cooperation (set up through Research Collaboration Agreements) between ISS and other research institutes and universities regarding chemical risk assessment for human and environmental health and human biomonitoring, ISS has planned to involve in the Partnership the below seven affiliated entities that have complementary expertise in this field.

20.1 ICPS – PIC: 922722395: The International Centre for Pesticides and Health Risk Prevention (ICPS) is a unit of the Azienda SocioSanitaria Territoriale (ASST) Fatebenefratelli-Sacco in the University of Milan characterised as a multi-purpose centre of public health, mainly focused on chemical risk exposure.

20.2 CNR-IRSA – PIC 999979500 : The Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche – Istituto di Ricerca sulle Acque (Water Research Institute, CNR-IRSA) is a research institute on water protection (reference Institute for the Italian Ministry of Environment) with long-lasting experience in environmental risk assessment and water policy for the control of chemical pollution.

20.3 – IRFM – PIC 999661146: The Istituto Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri (IRFM) has extensive experience in the development of in silico tools, such as VEGA QSAR models (www.vegahub.eu), that are used by EFSA and linked to the OECD QSAR Toolbox, as well as of SPHERA, integrating in silico models for hazard assessment and exposure within the same system. IRFM has several mass spectrometry instruments that are both GC-MS (high resolution) and LC-MS. IRFM also has automatic extractor for water samples concentration.

20.4 IUSS – PIC: 997963355: The Scuola Universitaria Superiore (University School for Advanced Study, IUSS Pavia) is a Public Institution devoted to research and higher education with a longstanding experience in developing new approaches, technologies, systems, and solutions in the health and environment area by promoting, sustaining and overseeing research and training in the fields of toxicology and chemical risk assessment including human and environmental risks assessment associated with extreme situations, as well as understanding and managing events that are associated with complex chemical exposures and emerging risk factors.

20.5 UMIL – PIC 999995796: will be involved in PARC through its Department of Pharmacological and Biomolecular Sciences (DiSFeB), which will provide its long-lasting expertise in the field of Risk Assessment, Immunotoxicology, Neurotoxicology and AOP development, and its Department of Clinical Sciences and Community Health (DISCCO), which established experience in human biomonitoring of occupational and general population and in the development and validation of suitable analytical methods.

20.6 UNINA – PIC: 999976590: UNINA has relevant expertise in occupational and environmental medicine, particularly as regards biomonitoring, chemical risk assessment and management.

20.7 UNIPD – PIC 999995602: The University of Padova (UNIPD) is one of the leading Universities in Italy with a long tradition and consolidated reputation for scientific excellence and in particular will be involved in PARC through its Department of Cardiac, Thoracic, Vascular Sciences and Public Health and specifically the Occupational Medicine Unit. The most important areas of research of the Unit are based on the study of occupational exposure assessment to chemicals, toxicology of xenobiotics, occupational and environmental carcinogenesis, genome-environment interaction in the development of chronic degenerative diseases, biological aging, effects of urban pollution and occupational respiratory diseases.

21- Riga Stradins University, LATVIA (RSU) PIC: 999843118

RSU - Institute of Occupational Safety and Environmental Health is the designated body for occupational risk analysis, incl. chemical risks. It performs research, policy briefing and elaboration of recommendations, and acts under the auspices of Ministry of Health. MoES and RSU are both parts of Latvian Human Biomonitoring council <https://www.v.m.gov.lv/lv/cilveku-biomonitoringa-padome>. There RSU represents as policy support via the IOSEH <https://www.rsu.lv/en/occupational-safety-environmental-health-institute> main policy support in the field of HBM. MoES represents itself and also all its subordinated institutions. RSU works under auspices of ministry of Health, including the IOSEH. Since Ministry of Health does not have further resource of HBM research, it involves RSU via

transparent Human Biomonitoring council procedures

RSU has one affiliated entity participating in PARC.

21.1 UL- PIC 999871830: University of Latvia is the leading Higher Education institution in Latvia, the national University. Faculty of Chemistry conducts a range of studies in environmental risks and pollution. It has also wide expertise in laboratory science, calibration of methods, new method elaboration. The University of Latvia is established by the Ministry of education and Science (MoES) of Latvia. Legal document – provisions by Cabinet of Ministers for MoES. <https://likumi.lv/ta/id/79100-izglitiba-un-zinatnes-ministrijas-nolikums> . The LU is under MoES auspices since 1919. The MoES delegates tasks to various its agencies and other establishments via their establishment documents.

22- NACIONALINE VISUOMENES SVEIKATOS PRIEZIUROS LABORATORIJA, LITHUANIA (NPHSL) – PIC: 933651094

NPHSL is an LST EN ISO/IEC 17025 accredited laboratory, providing microbiological, parasitological, serological, chemical, physical and clinical diagnostic laboratory tests, assessment of working environment, professional risk assessment and disinfection, participating in prophylaxis of chronic non-infectious diseases, accidents and traumas, prophylaxis and control of infectious diseases, public health safety control, public health monitoring and expertise, prevention of extreme situations, personal and public health care service. NPHSL seeks to assure better status of public health quality and determine different impacts on human health.

23- LIETUVOS SVEIKATOS MOKSLU UNIVERSITETAS, LITHUANIA (LSMU) – PIC : 972782446

The Lithuanian University of Health Sciences (LSMU, Lietuvos sveikatos mokslų universitetas) is the largest institution of higher education in biomedical sciences in Lithuania, integrating studies, research, and clinical practice. LSMU was founded in 2010, however the University's roots go back to 1918-1922 when the Faculty of Medicine at Vytautas Magnus University was established. Since then institution went through various organisational and structural changes. Meanwhile, LSMU consist of Medical Academy and Veterinary Academy.

LSMU laboratory is equipped with inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS) NexION 300D (Perkin Elmer, USA), with high performance liquid chromatographer (HPLC) Flexar (Perkin Elmer, USA), mineralizator Multiwave 3000 (Anton Paar), and relevant reference materials in various human media. Its infrastructure complies with requirements for trace and ultra-trace element analysis in biological media

24- LABORATOIRE NATIONAL DE SANTE, LUXEMBOURG (LNS) – PIC : 911247586

LNS is the national health institute in Luxembourg having servicing, education and research within its missions. Within the LNS, the Department Health Protection is in charge of environmental and occupational health and medicine, including the food surveillance; the stakeholders being mainly the different Ministries in Luxembourg. The new premises in Dudelange foresee in state-of-the art technical infrastructure as well as a highly skilled team to ensure excellence in our daily work.

LNS adheres the 3 Luxembourg research institutes as Affiliated Entities for PARC:

24.1 LIH – PIC 998331858: The Luxembourg Institute of Health (LIH) is a public organisation conducting clinically oriented research at the forefront of biomedical sciences. Officially founded in 2015, LIH has its roots in an earlier institution, the Centre de Recherche Publique de la Santé (CRP-Santé), established in 1988 to serve as a research platform for clinicians working at the Central Hospital of Luxembourg (CHL) and as a provider of public health information to the Ministry of Health. Moving

away from its roots in the CHL, it progressively and successfully developed a fundamental research base. In 2015, the institutional evolution resulted in the establishment of three research departments, including the Department of Oncology (DONC), Department of Infection and Immunity (DII), and Department of Population Health (DoPH). The 37 research groups and 10 technology platforms distributed among those departments currently employ more than 150 researchers having complementary expertise in cell and molecular biology, bioinformatics, statistics, computing, clinical research and epidemiology. Altogether, the newly formed LIH employs 375 staff members, and spreads across a wide scope of activities, from fundamental research to health services. All of LIH's scientific activities have high level of excellence and the departments have achieved international recognition on their own. LIH hosts a large number of trainees, Master students and PhD candidates, affiliated to the University of Luxembourg or foreign partner universities, as well as postdoctoral scientists specialising themselves in a given research domain.

24.2 LIST – PIC 934320200: LIST has used AOPs over the last years to develop complex 3D in vitro models (NAMs) relevant for not well understand endpoints in humans thereby making best use of existing knowledge, potentially also contributing to the refinement of AOPs. Two of these assays are currently under validation by EURL ECVAM NETVAL as part of the thyroid hormone panel. The PI of LIST is representing Luxembourg in EURL ECVAM PARERE. LIST employees serve as national representatives for Luxembourg in international bodies such as EFSA, ECHA and OECD (PI is HoD for WNT).

24.3 UniLU – PIC 999878620: Founded in 2003, the University of Luxembourg is the only public university of the Grand Duchy of Luxembourg.

Multilingual, international and research-oriented, it is also a modern institution with a personal atmosphere.

25- RIJKSINSTITUUT VOOR VOLKSGEZONDHEID EN MILIEU, NETHERLANDS (RIVM) – PIC : 999991431

The National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) is a governmental research and knowledge institute providing policy support to the Dutch government. RIVM performs tasks to safeguard and promote public health and environmental quality in the Netherlands. In its role as trusted advisor, RIVM provides the government with impartial advice on infectious diseases, vaccination programmes, population screening, life style, nutrition, pharmaceuticals, environment, sustainability, safety and security. RIVM's commissioning bodies consist of Dutch ministries and various public services such as the inspectorates. The scientific quality of RIVM work is monitored by the Scientific Advisory Board, which includes a number of well-respected scientists. The independent position of RIVM is set down in statutes. RIVM's Centre for Health Protection (GZB) has its own zebrafish lab as well as facilities or access to RIVM core facilities for cell culturing. GZB has state-of-the-art molecular laboratories for omics analysis (or access to shared facilities) and facilities for bioinformatics processing of omics data. Other relevant infrastructure includes MCRA 9, which is a web-based system for human health hazard identification, hazard characterisation, exposure assessment and risk assessment related to chemical substances. MCRA stands for Monte Carlo Risk Assessment. The MCRA system brings together statistical models, shared data and data uploaded by the user. MCRA 9 has over 40 modules to address all areas of risk assessment, and includes a data repository with data collected in the Horizon2020 project 'EuroMix'. RIVM will act as Grant Signatory and National Hub Contact Point for the Netherlands.

In the Netherlands, there are eight Affiliated Entities (AE) that report to RIVM as Grant Signatory. These organisations all closely collaborate with RIVM, and together they will form the core of the Dutch National Hub.

25.1 KWR – PIC: 998279769: KWR Water Research Institute generates knowledge to enable the water

sector to operate water-wisely in our urbanised society. At KWR, we have a sense of professional and social responsibility for the quality of water. Our scientific findings and the resulting practical innovations contribute, worldwide, to a sustainable water provision in the urban water cycle. ‘Bridging science to practice’ is KWR’s motto. Our researchers work at the interface of science, business and society. Their strength lies in their translation of scientific knowledge into applicable, practical solutions for end-users in the Dutch and international water sector. We have built a solid reputation as top-level innovation accelerators and international network builders, and increasingly play a coordinating role in national and international collaborations. KWR is WHO Collaborating Centre on Water Quality and Health.

25.2 TNO – PIC: 999988909: TNO (Nederlandse Organisatie voor toegepast-natuurwetenschappelijk Onderzoek TNO) is one of the major non-profit contract independent research organizations in Europe. With a staff of ~3500 and annual turnover of 580 M€, TNO is executing research in order to achieve impact on the following themes: Artificial Intelligence & ICT, Healthy Living, Circular Economy & Environment, Industrial Innovation, Urbanisation, Energy transition, Traffic & Transport and Defence, Safety and Security. The Research Group Risk Analysis for Products In Development (RAPID) consists of 60 high level (PhD, MSc) experts including toxicologists, epidemiologists, immunologists, chemists, occupational hygienists, exposure assessment experts, statisticians, bioinformaticians, data scientists and computational modelers. We are working on the interdisciplinary assessment and mitigation of health risks due to exposure to potentially hazardous chemicals/materials via the (occupational-) environment. RAPID adopts, develops and integrates science-based models and methods to predict these potential risks. RAPID is primarily concerned with the application of in silico and desk-based research, performed on public data and data generated in collaborative or B2B projects. Aside, RAPID is highly experienced within EU and international funded research projects (8 coordinating, currently EPHOR Exposome Project for Health and Occupational Research, ~30 participating, over the past 10 years). Specific disciplines of relevance to PARC are exposure assessment and sensor-based exposome technologies, statistics, systems biology modelling, bioinformatics and systems toxicology, and risk assessment. The research group Microbiology and Systems Biology has expertise in personalized health, FAIR, privacy issues, secure learning and ontologies. In addition, TNO has scientific and supportive ICT staff, providing infrastructure support and novel approaches including machine learning, explainable artificial intelligence and federated learning.

25.3 RUMC – PIC: 892057785: The Radboud university medical center (RUMC) is embedded in the Radboud University which is one of the top general universities in the Netherlands (>21,000 students) that offers 13 Bachelor’s and 35 Master’s programmes in English, in addition to the courses taught in Dutch. It comprises 17 research institutes, spanning a range of research fields. RU staff have received numerous prizes and grants due to the quality of their research, such as the Nobel Prize (2010) and Spinoza Prizes.

RUMC is a university hospital with academic training for medicine, dentistry and biomedical sciences. RUMC scientists play a leading role in personalized healthcare research, which we have subdivided over three research institutes: Radboud Institute for Health Sciences (RIHS), the Radboud Institute for Molecular Life Sciences (RIMLS) and the Donders Centre for Medical Neuroscience.

The mission of the RIHS is to innovate and personalize healthcare and public health by developing, testing and applying tests, treatments, and policies as well as innovative modes of healthcare delivery; developing new methodology to facilitate health sciences research and training young researchers in the methodology, including human health risk assessment.

24.4 UL-LACDR – PIC: 999974553: Founded in 1575, Universiteit Leiden (UL) is the oldest university in the Netherlands and one of the leading research universities in Europe. Consistently ranked in the top-100 according to the Academic Ranking of World Universities, the university is located at two campuses and has over 30,000 students and over 1,600 academic staff (from a total of 130 different nationalities).

UL has strong international research collaborations and is part of the Coimbra Group, the Europaeum and a founding member of the League of European Research Universities. UL research commitment is further witnessed by its more than 40 national and international research institutes.

About 29% of the University's budget is from external research funding organisations: mainly from the Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO) and European funding programs (most notably Horizon 2020).

Leiden University researchers have been awarded 16 Nobel Prizes and 23 Spinoza Prizes (i.e., 23 out of 93 times), the latter being the most prestigious Dutch academic award UL has a prominent position amongst European research universities in participation in the EU research and training programmes. To date in H2020, UL has been awarded 193 research projects worth €128M, including 55 ERC grants and 67 collaborative projects (10 coordinators), as well as 66 awarded MSCA collaborative actions, namely 45 MSCA fellowships, 21 ITNs (2 coordinators), 1 CO-FUND and 4 RISE actions.

The Leiden Academic Centre for Drug Research (LACDR; ~200 staff members) is one of the leading academic centres in the world in advancing innovative drug research, developing knowledge and expertise crucial for drug discovery, evaluation, and (clinical) application. With LACDR involvement in 19 running EC projects of which 5 LACDR coordinated, the institute has ample expertise in engaging in large international multi-stakeholder R&D consortia.

25.5 UU-IRAS – PIC 999985805: Founded in 1636, Utrecht University (UU) is one of Europe's leading research universities, recognized

internationally for its high-quality, innovative approach to both research and teaching. It is a LERU Charter Member. Since the start of the ARWU ranking (Shanghai University Ranking), UU has consistently ranked first in the Netherlands and in the top 25 in Europe. Utrecht University is the largest university in the Netherlands; it has over 6700 staff, 600 professors and 30000 students, including 12 Noble Prize laureates and 19 Spinoza Prize winners.

IRAS has 130 staff members, including ~50 PhD fellows, and performs world class scientific research and education in three domains: environmental epidemiology and one health, toxicology, and pharmacology. The mission of the Division of Toxicology of IRAS is to improve the scientific basis of chemical risk and safety assessment through innovative research, teaching and training in mechanistic and predictive toxicology. The division has longstanding expertise in neuro-, immuno- and endocrine toxicology and risk assessment through in vivo and in-silico experimentation. The mission of the Environmental Epidemiology Division of IRAS is to conduct research on environmental contributors (non-genetic factors with a focus on environmental, occupational and lifestyle exposures) to adverse health effects. IRAS has a strong reputation for producing world class research in environmental exposure science, molecular and environmental epidemiology, and public health. This work is very well cited with several papers in the top 1% of most frequently cited papers in relevant ISI fields and by 5 IRAS researchers listed in the top 20 top researchers in environmental health. The Environmental Epidemiology Division of IRAS has been at the forefront of Exposome research. IRAS has been involved in the large EXPOsOMICS project, which was among the first EU-grants on the Exposome, is task lead in the HBM4EU project Work packages 15 (mixtures) and 16 (emerging chemicals), and currently coordinates the EU H2020 exposome project EXPANSE and is involved in two others EPHOR, and LONGITOOLS. IRAS is part of the HERA – project and responsible for WP4 which is setting the scientific priorities for the environmental health programme of Europe.

25.6 VUA – PIC: 954530344: The Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam has 25,000 students and 600 Ph.D. students, and 4,800 employees. VU is ranked number 94 in The Leiden ranking, and is a modern organization at the cutting edge of academic higher education. VU will be represented in PARC by the Department of Environment & Health (E&H), which is a merge of the former department of Chemistry and Biology of the Institute for Environmental Studies (IVM) and the Health and Life Science section of VU. The mission of VU-E&H is to achieve a better understanding of the impact of environmental contaminants on human health and the environment by multidisciplinary academic research and education. For this, VU-E&H strives to break new ground in methods and approaches in environmental

chemistry, environmental health, toxicological research, and epidemiology. VU-E&H is unique in combining analytical chemical, biological approaches (e.g. in vitro assays, genomics, metabolomics), and epidemiology, and has a high commitment to contribute to the environmental and human risk assessment of potentially hazardous substances. VU-E&H has set-up a mother-child cohort (LINC) to study early life exposure to chemicals and health effects in children, including development and behavior.

25.7 WR – PIC: 999547365: The organisation –Stichting Wageningen Research (WR) consists of a number of specialized institutes for applied research in the domain of healthy food and living environment. WR offers a combination of practical, innovative and interdisciplinary scientific research across many disciplines related to the green world and the sustainable use of the living environment. WR is integrated with Wageningen University in Wageningen University & Research (WUR). The research groups involved in this proposal are Wageningen Food Safety Research (WFSR) and the business unit Biometris (WR-BIO) within Wageningen Plant Research.

25.8 WU-TOX – PIC: 999981634: Wageningen University (WU) is a technical university and member of the Dutch federation of technical universities. The mission of WU is to explore the potential of nature to improve the quality of life. Wageningen University has been elected for the 15th time in a row as the best university by Dutch students. In its research WU is focussing on climate, circular & biobased economy, food production, nutrition & health and biodiversity. Scientists are very active in numerous European research and training projects. WU student numbers have doubled over the last six years and expected to increase to around 15,000 students by 2023.

The chair group of Toxicology is embedded in the department of Agrotechnology and food sciences (ATV). The research is performed by 626 FTE of scientists that include 57 professors and 59 employees on a tenure track. The chair group has a long track record in toxicological research and training.

The group (division of Toxicology) consists of a unit on toxicology, headed by prof. Rietjens, and a group on advanced in vitro models for i.e. the gastrointestinal tract (including intestinal microbiome), liver and heart headed by dr. Bouwmeester. He combines co-cultures of cell lines, stem cell-based models and organ on chip approaches in this studies. The division of Toxicology has ~40 staff members, including 30 PhD candidates. The research at WU-TOX is based on mechanistic driven research in toxicology. The research infrastructure at WU is state-of-the-art, we use next generation sequencing, high content confocal microscopy and mass spectrometry (LC-MS; GC-MS). For this we also make use of our universities shared research facilities and there is close cooperation with other national and international leading research groups. Research at WU-TOX, although fundamental in nature, has strong connections and links with industry and regulatory agencies.

26- FOLKEHELSEINSTITUTTET, NORWAY (NIPH) – PIC: 999478883

The Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH) was established in 2001 and acts as a national competence institution placed directly under the Ministry of Health and Care Services. The NIPH is responsible for knowledge production and systematic reviews for the health sector and provides knowledge about the health status in the population, influencing factors and how it can be improved. The institute is a national competence institution in the following areas: infectious disease control, physical and mental health, environmental factors, toxicology, substance abuse, tobacco, nutrition, physical activity and other factors that affects health status and inequality, health-promoting and preventive measures in the population, and global health. The primary deliverable of the institute is knowledge-based advices to the Norwegian government.

There are seven AEs in Norway that report to NIPH as grant signatory. Signed collaboration agreements are in place between the AEs and NIPH as part of the Toxicology Network in Norway. The overall objective of this network is to establish a knowledge network to support the hazard and risk assessment of chemicals.

26.1 IMR – PIC: 999548432: IMR (www.imr.no) is a governmental research institute affiliated to the Norwegian Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries, which also provides around half of the institute's funding; the remainder of the IMR's research funding comes from external national and international research grants. IMR's research-based advice to fisheries- and food-authorities facilitates the sustainable management of resources in marine ecosystems, along the entire food chain from the ocean to the table. With around 1000 employees, IMR is one of the largest research institutes of its kind in Europe and is an international leader in several research areas. IMR has a robust and varied research infrastructure spread over several locations in Norway, ranging from multiple research vessels, a data management centre, as well as state-of-the-art laboratories. IMR has extensive collaborations with several academic and regulatory institutions in countries within Europe and worldwide. IMR is the National Reference Laboratory for several methods analysing nutrients, contaminants and microorganisms in fish and seafood, with around 70 methods accredited in accordance with the standard NS-EN ISO/IEC 17025. IMR's research results are open to the public and communicated actively via different platforms to reach diverse audiences.

26.2 STAMI – PIC: 953521738: The National Institute of Occupational Health (STAMI) is carrying out research on occupational safety and health in Norway. STAMI is a governmental body organised under the Ministry of Labour and Social affairs. STAMI supplies the Ministry with new knowledge of research findings from our own and other international research. STAMI has also as a part of our state assignment a strategic, advisory role for the Norwegian Labour Inspection Authority and the Petroleum Safety Authority of Norway. Thus, knowledge from and through STAMI makes up a scientific foundation for national policy and legislation development and management in the work environment field, which potentially includes also knowledge from the present PARC proposal.

STAMI carries out research on health risks of chemicals in the work place. We also have expertise in regulatory toxicology and we give advice and submit recommendations in chemical risk factors in the work environment, to the Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs, Norwegian Directorate of Labour Inspectorate, government and parliament. We are very active in dissemination of occupational safety professionals, labour unions and employers and their organizations. One of the focus areas is in toxicology, chemical safety and risk assessment of chemicals.

26.3 NILU – PIC 999654162: NILU - is an independent, non-profit research institution. It was established in 1969 and is one of the leading European institutes in environmental and climate research. The environmental chemistry research at NILU has been graded very excellently in terms of scientific quality and productivity in an evaluation of basic chemistry research in Norway by the Research Council and also top score in the evaluation of geoscience (Flexpart-group). The institute has an excellent track record for participation and management of externally funded project internationally as well as nationally, including 41 projects under FP7 (about 12 mill EUR) and about 12 projects under H2020, including one ERC grant. NILU's laboratories are among the most advanced in Europe and perform many EN/ISO/IEC 17025 accredited inorganic and organic analyses.

Toxicological research at NILU is undertaken by the Health Effects Laboratory (HEL), which is certified for Good Laboratory Practice (GLP) in in vitro toxicology, genotoxicology and nanotoxicology. HEL is among the leading laboratories in Europe in in vitro toxicology and nanogenotoxicology.

26.4 NIVA – PIC: 997826585: NIVA performs research on environmental issues related to fresh and seawater environments. Resources at NIVA, including the experimental and computational tools in NIVAs Computational Toxicology Program, NCTP (www.niva.no/nctp, see e) for details), competence and knowledge on effect assessment, modern laboratory facilities, GLP accredited laboratories, and a wide range of in silico, in vitro and small-scale in vivo endpoint analysis involving both classical ecotoxicological test methods and new approach methodologies (NAMs). NIVA also has a well-equipped chemical laboratory and take part in national and international monitoring programs as is appointed an expert advisor to the Norwegian Environment Agency in matters related to exposure,

effect and risk assessments. The use of NAMs and next generation risk assessment involving Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) and Aggregate exposure Pathways are key to many of research tasks performed (see www.niva.no/radb for details about activities and projects)

26.5 NMBU – PIC: 999902967: NMBU is an agricultural Norwegian University located in Ås, Norway, established in 1859 and the 2nd oldest institution of higher education in Norway. NMBU currently has 1700 employees (including 350 PhD and postdoctoral research fellows) and 5200 students and research is focused on environmental sciences, veterinary medicine, food science, biotechnology, aquaculture and business development. Research at NMBU include both basic and applied research providing a foundation for education, research training and research geared towards the private sector. NMBU contains seven Faculties and hosts three Research Excellence Centers funded by the Norwegian Research Council and the Nordic Council of Ministers. NMBU has broad experience in conducting R&D projects funded by national and international public agencies and industry.

26.6 NVI – PIC 999511378: The Norwegian Veterinary Institute - NVI is a national biomedical research institute in the fields of animal health, fish health and food safety, whose primary functions include surveillance and diagnostic regarding different species and diseases as well as research and advisory support to the governing authorities.

The wildlife group, consisting of 4 veterinarians/researchers and 1 technician, is responsible for working with all wildlife species (both land and marine species) throughout all of Norway, its territorial waters and arctic/Antarctic dependencies. This work is often carried out in cooperation with other departments at NVI and other institutions such as the Institute of Marine Research, the Norwegian Directorate for Nature Management or the Norwegian Institute for Nature Research.

NVI carries both passive and active surveillance programs based for example on routine necropsies of wild species sent to NVI, or on active collection of samples during hunting periods or specific field actions. The Health Surveillance Program for Wild Cervids is the largest active surveillance program in wildlife at NVI and is also the basis for different research projects carried by the group. Other programs have focused on diseases such as Chronic Wasting Disease, Tuberculosis, Rabies or Echinococcus and species such as wild boars. NVI is also responsible for managing the Wild Cervids serum bank, currently with more than 5000 samples.

NVI and the wildlife group are involved in several national and international research projects concerning wildlife health, transmission of diseases between wild and domestic animals and diseases of zoonotic potential.

26.7 UNN – PIC: 991888051: The University Hospital of North Norway (UNN) is serving the entire region of North Norway including the counties Nordland, Troms and Finnmark as well as Spitzbergen with a population of approximately 500 000 people. UNN is organised into divisions and centres and working with continuous improvement of its health services and patient security. The divisions perform patient care, research, education and training of patients, whereas the centres perform important support functions for the divisions. The Department of Laboratory Medicine is a part of the Division of Diagnostic Services and it serves the University Hospital and the entire North Norwegian region with its services.

The Environmental Pollutant Laboratory is a part of the Department of Laboratory Medicine, which is accredited according ISO 15189. The Environmental Pollutant Laboratory is a collaboration between the Arctic University of Norway (UiT), the Northern Norway Regional Health Authority and UNN. UNN is responsible for the establishment of the laboratory and management of the employees, equipment, methodology and conduction of research projects and UiT provides the lab areas. The Northern Norway Regional Health Authority supports the Environmental Pollutant Laboratory through direct strategically funding. The Environmental Pollutant Laboratory was established for conducting human exposure studies, to investigate exposure to chemicals and possible health effects and to solve knowledge gaps related to this topics.

27- INSTYTUT MEDYCYNY PRACY IMIENIA PROF. DRA MED. JERZEGO NOFERA W LODZI, POLAND (NIOM) – PIC: 999835940

Nofer Institute of Occupational Medicine (NIOM) is the leading research institute in the field of occupational and environmental health in Poland with a broad competence within various fields. NIOM is a research institute providing activities in the broadly defined environmental health of both working people and the general population. The individual scientific institutions of NIOM offer research related to risk assessment, from in vitro tests through the assessment of exposure using biological monitoring tools to risk estimation, management and evaluation. Significant infrastructure relevant to the foreseen work includes ICP-MS systems, LC- MS/MC; GC/MS/MS mass spectrometers ; Synapt G2Si Q-TOF mass spectrometer (Waters MS Technologies, Manchester, UK) equipped Waters Acquity™ Ultra Performance LC system (Waters Corp., Milford, USA) connected to with an electrospray (ESI) source (Waters, Manchester, UK) ; Pegasus GC-HRT (Leco); high resolution TOFMS.

27.1 IEP-NRI – PIC: 998750316: Institute of Environmental Protection - National Research Institute (IEP-NRI) is a research and development unit supervised by the Minister of Climate. One of the most important activity of IEP-NRI is comprehensive environmental research, integrating investigations conducted in most research fields. The Institute operates in the following research fields: protection of the atmosphere against pollution, climate protection, protection and restoration of the biologically active earth surface, management of waste and sewage in the environment, management of chemical substances in the environment, environmental chemistry and risk assessment.

27.2 UG-PL – PIC: 999876001: The University of Gdansk (UG) offers education in nearly all fields of academic knowledge. It is currently one of the most modern academic centres in Poland. The University of Gdańsk implements a host of diverse scientific research, representing the Humanities, Economic Sciences as well as the Social, Exact and Natural Sciences. The most notable successes have been achieved in the fields of biomedical and biomolecular research. The following innovative research and undertaking regarding, among other things, blue biotechnology, biodiversity, marine ecosystems, sustainable development of cities or biomedicine, have also been conducted at the University of Gdańsk as part of European centres and networks of excellence.

27.3 WULS-SGGW – PIC 999865137: Warsaw University of Life Sciences (WULS-SGGW), with its nearly 200-year tradition is one of the oldest and the largest universities in Poland. The mission of WULS is to serve the economic and intellectual development of Polish society with special emphasis on rural areas, the food industry and the environment in a broad sense. The university is committed to maintaining the highest level of research, education and implementation of research results. The Laboratory of Human Metabolic Research (LHMR) focuses on the use of ultra-performance chromatography systems for metabolomics research, combining with ICP-MS techniques for the determination of metals, as well as molecular biology techniques (genotyping and gene expression) in assessing human exposure to various environmental factors as well as studying changes in metabolomic profiles in chronic diseases.

28- FACULDADE DE MEDICINA DA UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA, PORTUGAL (FMUL) – PIC: 999888320

FMUL is a Portuguese institution with recognised quality and merit in research and education, having a long history in human biomonitoring projects (COPHES, DEMOCOPHES and HBM4EU). At the national level, FMUL is responsible for the epidemiological and public impact evaluation for human health of waste incineration in Lisbon and has been involved in health impact assessment in collaboration the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Portuguese Directorate-General of Health. FMUL has also a solid background in both quantitative and qualitative methods, including construction and validation of questionnaires (traditional and modern psychology), large-scale national and international inquiries (using CATI-systems) and conduction of focus groups, in-depth interviews and consensus methods (e.g. Delphi); results have been used to inform policies by the General-Directorate

of Health and to support health promotion programmes by local City Halls. FMUL have adequate workspaces, equipped with the necessary resources to assure the execution of the foreseen activities, namely, individual/open space rooms (which follow national and international guidelines for COVID-19 safety rules), with computers with internet access, bibliographical databases and analytic software. Also, it has two equipped laboratories.

28.1 PL – PIC: 996273421: Polytechnic of Leiria (PL) is a public higher education institution that develops its activity in the field of education and research, training citizens to contribute with their relevant skills to regional and national sustainable development, adding cultural, economic and social valued knowledge and innovation to society. The activities of Polytechnic of Leiria are developed in the sphere of education, training and research, providing several services to the community and extending its cooperation to the technical and cultural fields, investing in well-equipped and modern facilities, to assure quality support services. Polytechnic of Leiria has a strong identity brand based on the growing research and development (RD&I) unique ecosystem oriented to innovation, to entrepreneurship and to the regional social and economic collaborative business sector.

28.2 UM – PIC: 999995505: Universidade do Minho (UM) is a Research University focusing on the regional, national and international socioeconomic environment, and invested in growing the Knowledge, RD&I chain namely through intellectual property management, standing as one of the PT HEIs with more registered patents. Research global figures: 31 Research Units: 85% ranked Excellent (7) and Very Good (20), including >90% of the total number of researchers; ~600 active research projects, corresponding to ~€150 million total budget; ~3.000 refereed papers in scientific journals, with yearly increasing citations (>75.000 in 2019); ~1.200 researchers (400 researchers with contract and 800 fellowships), with a Postgraduate students/total student ratio ~40% and >200 PhDs awarded yearly. In the H2020, UMinho has 96 approved projects (21 as coordinator) and ranks 2nd among PT research organisations regarding EU contributions.

29- INSTITUTO NACIONAL DE SAUDE DR. RICARDO JORGE, PORTUGAL (INSA) – PIC: 998308190

Instituto Nacional de Saúde Dr. Ricardo Jorge (INSA) is a public organisation of the Portuguese Ministry of Health (MH), with scientific, technical, administrative, and financial autonomy. INSA develops its activity as a State Laboratory of the health sector, National Reference Laboratory and National Health Observatory. Its mission is to enhance public health mainly through research and diagnosis activities in several health sciences domains, to provide the MH with adequate data for knowledge-based decision-making essential to formulate national health policies and programs, to monitor guidelines defined by the MH and to answer the questions raised by the scientific community and the society.

29.1 APA – PIC: 917950286: – The Portuguese Environment Agency (APA) is a public institute under the Ministry of Environment and Climate Action and it is the entity responsible for implementing environmental policies in Portugal, for monitoring, planning and evaluation, licensing and inspection, and is therefore the main environmental regulator in Portugal. APA is the National Authority for Water and Waste and the National Assessment Authority for Environmental Impact and Environmental Assessment Strategic Plans and Programs, the National Competent Authority responsible for REACH, CLP and biocides to assess the risks from chemicals with regard to effects on the environment to identify risk management measures. APA is the Designated National Authority to the Basel, Minamata, Rotterdam and Stockholm Conventions as well as to the SAICM. APA is Programme Owner in HBM4EU and has been closely working with INSA and at the National Hub level in which both are deeply involved. APA and INSA have common duties in what concerns health and environmental

policies and have a long-lasting collaboration under these areas.

29.2 DGS – PIC: 986364095: The Directorate-General of Health (DGS) is the institution of the Portuguese Health Ministry responsible for the definition of regulations and norms in the Public Health domain. DGS is the National Competent Authority for the implementation of chemical regulations such as REACH (Reg. (EP and EC) N° 1907/2006), CLP (Reg. (EC) N° 1272/2008) and Biocides (Reg. N° (EU) 548/2012). In these terms, DGS has long experience in assessing and performing regulatory risk assessment of chemical substances and mixtures based on human health effects, exposure and risk characterisation. In particular, DGS is responsible for the evaluation of biocidal active substances and products issuing the respective authorisations of placing on the market for the different uses, including the assessment of the risk management measures (RMM). Within HBM4EU, DGS is Programme Owner and LTP of INSA for the WP5, task 5.3 – Use of HBM data in chemicals risk assessment. DGS and INSA work closely in the surveillance, health monitoring and epidemiological research and are under the same Ministry as is stated in the Health Ministry organic law.

29.3 ENSP – PIC: 960782479: The National School of Public Health (ENSP), one of the NOVA faculties, is a pioneer institution in public health teaching and research and has expertise in epidemiology, health economy, promotion of health, policies and management, occupational and environmental health, exposure and risk assessment and a relevant experience in translating scientific knowledge for communicating with different stakeholders (eg. Policy actors and regulators, citizens, health professionals...). ENSP and INSA have been collaborating in several past and ongoing research projects and have an active collaboration protocol concerning training activities as well the participation in research projects and programmes.

29.4 UC – PIC: 997826391: University of Coimbra (UC) is a public higher education institution founded in 1290, whose mission comprises three pillars: Education, Research and Knowledge Transfer. INSA and UC signed a protocol for the development of research in scientific fields of common interest. As an AE of INSA, UC will participate in PARC through its Research Centre for Functional Ecology - Science for People & the Planet (CFE) in WP6, respectively Task 6.4.4 due to the team's expertise in Risk Assessment. There is a cooperation agreement between INSA and UC under the scope of scientific and academic activities in common areas.

29.5 UAVR – PIC 999865331: . In PARC, UAVR will be involved in WPs 3, 4, 5, 6 and 9, based on the One Health approach. There is a formal link through a cooperation protocol between the two entities established since April 2019 that expresses the will of these entities to cooperate in the academic and research area (Clause 2) and facilitate common collaboration in research networks.

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA)?	N
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30- SLOVENSKA ZDRAVOTNICKA UNIVERZITA V BRATISLAVE, SLOVAKIA (SZU-SK) – PIC: 999859802

Profile: SZU-SK is the state university belonging to the Ministry of Health of the Slovak Republic. It involves multidisciplinary research groups with expertise in environmental health, biomonitoring, environmental epidemiology and development of new biomarkers of exposure and effect. The facilities offer well-equipped laboratories for analyses of toxic organic pollutants and trace elements in environmental and biological matrices together with infrastructure for long-term storage of samples. Department of Environmental Medicine is focused on research of health effects of environmental exposure to toxic compounds. It has conducted several cohort studies in children, aimed at the assessment of exposure to wide range of environmental pollutants and associated health risks in children. Department of Toxic Organic Pollutants was established as the National Reference Centre for

Dioxin and Related Compounds (NRC-DIOX) by the Ministry of Health of Slovakia. It is accredited by Slovak National Accreditation Service as a test laboratory for the analysis of selected POPs in the environment, feed, food and biological specimens (ISO/IEC 17025:2017, certif. No. S-111). The NRC-DIOX is a member of the European Network of National Reference Laboratories for Halogenated POPs in Feed and Food. Department of Metallomics is focused on determination of total contents and species (isotopic composition/valency/form) of chemical elements (including nanoparticles) in environmental components, food and human biological materials (tissues, body fluids) and in samples from in vivo and in vitro experiments; research activities follow the GLP criteria under internal quality control.

30.1 UK – PIC 999841566: Comenius University in Bratislava (UK) is a public university which participates in research in a number of scientific disciplines. The Faculty of Natural Sciences (FNS UK) is the most successful faculty in Slovakia in terms of co-financing projects from EU funds. In May 2015, financed from the Operational Programme Research and Development, a self-managed part of Comenius University in Bratislava - Science Park (SP UK) was established. It is a specialised research and development part of the UK with a priority on biomedicine, environmental medicine and biotechnology. SP UK provides space for interdisciplinary research - not only at the intra-university level, but also with domestic and foreign partners. The Comenius University Science Park is a unique centre with state-of-the-art technological equipment that connects research with practice. Division for Metabolomic Analyses SP UK has fully equipped laboratories for analyses of xenobiotics and their metabolites in environmental and biological matrices (e.g. HPLC in combination with tribrid HRMS Orbitrap Fusion and DAD; HPLC-MS/MS, DAD and FLD; HPLC in combination with ion trap MSn and DAD; GC in combination with HRMS-TOF...). Department of Analytical Chemistry FNS UK is equipped with: HPLC-DAD-qMS, HPLC-DAD-MS/MS, GC-MS/MS, ICP-MS, LC-ELSD, available for research and development of novel methods and/or applications.

The link between SZU-SK and UK is based on an Official Agreement on Cooperation.

31- INSTITUT JOZEF STEFAN, SLOVENIA (JSI) – PIC : 999971837

31.1 GeoZS – PIC: 999466370: The cooperation between the JSI and GeoZS is arranged by an Agreement on long-term cooperation (“Dogovor o dolgoročnem sodelovanju”). Fields of cooperation include all kinds of scientific and research activities that are in accordance with mutual benefits and needs of the individual laboratories within the JSI and GeoZS (art. 2 of JSI- GeoZS Agreement). The agreement entered into force in June 2021 and remains in force indefinitely (art. 4 of JSI-GeoZS Agreement).

Geological Survey of Slovenia (GeoZS) is a leading public geological institute with more than 110 employees, established by the Government of the Republic of Slovenia. Highly qualified staff contributes to the production of geological maps, assessment of natural and anthropogenic geological hazards to the living environment, expertise in groundwater, mineral resources, geothermal energy resources and natural geological heritage. The studies of the group of geochemists and hydrogeologists focus on natural and anthropogenic processes occurring in a media as a consequence of the rock-soil-water-pollutant-air interaction and on factors controlling these processes. The main focus of the research group is to determine the distribution of PHE as a result of natural conditions (mineralisation) or in combination with the influence of human activities, especially centuries of mining (Idrija, Mežica, Litija, etc.), metallurgy (Jesenice, Celje, etc.) and other anthropogenic activities (industry, waste, urbanisation, traffic). The objectives are to define geochemical associations in the studied environments, to identify solid carriers of geochemical information and their properties as markers of PHE sources, to assess the stability of PHEs and their solid forms and their changes in different environmental media, and to develop conceptual models of the flow of PHEs and their solid forms from sources through transport routes to sinks in the environment.

31.2 NIB – PIC: 999650476: The cooperation between the JSI and NIB is arranged by an Agreement on long-term cooperation (“Dogovor o dolgoročnem sodelovanju”). Fields of cooperation include all kinds of scientific and research activities that are in accordance with mutual benefits and needs of the

individual laboratories within the JSI and NIB (art. 2 of JSI-NIB Agreement). The agreement entered into force on June 2021 and remains in force indefinitely (art. 4 of JSI-NIB Agreement). Affiliated entity National Institute of Biology (NIB) is the largest independent Public Research Institution for Life Sciences in Slovenia, performing basic and applicative research in the fields of toxicology, biotechnology, biology, ecology, biophysics, biomedicine, systems biology, biostatistics and bioinformatics. The main expertise at the Department of Genetic Toxicology and Cancer Biology (GEN) is in the field of genetic toxicology (mutagenicity and genotoxicity) with the focus of studying the adverse effects of chemicals, including anthropogenic and natural compounds and their mechanisms of action as single compounds or in the form of complex mixtures. The GEN has specific knowledge in classical (sets of methods such as Ames assay, micronucleus and comet assay) and novel testing approaches including cutting-edge transcriptomic approach (targeted gene expression) supported by bioinformatics applied on in vitro bacterial models, various human, fish and rodent cell lines (2D and 3D) and in vivo model on zebrafish embryos. NIB owns state-of-the-art equipment, which will ensure the successful execution of the tasks in which NIB is involved. The GEN holds the accreditation for performing mutagenicity studies in compliance with the OECD Principles of Good Laboratory Practice (GLP).

31.3 NIC – PIC: 998756718: The cooperation between the JSI and NIC is arranged by an Agreement on long-term cooperation (“Dogovor o dolgoročnem sodelovanju”). Fields of cooperation include all kinds of scientific and research activities that are in accordance with mutual benefits and needs of the individual laboratories within the JSI and NIC (art. 2 of JSI-NIC Agreement). The agreement entered into force in July 2021 and remains in force indefinitely (art. 4 of JSI-NIC Agreement).

National Institute of Chemistry (NIC) is the scientifically excellent, established and breakthrough research institution based in Slovenia, Europe. With our cutting-edge research, we are enriching the global treasury of knowledge by solving the most pressing challenges facing society including health, sustainable energy, climate change, circular economy and safe food. Basic and applied research are focused towards fields that are of long-term importance to both Slovenia and the world: biotechnology, environmental protection, empirical and theoretical chemistry, analytical chemistry, materials research, and chemical engineering, through which the Institute performs a world class basic research and supports the needs for technology transfer of the domestic chemical, pharmaceutical, and food industries. NIC hosts Ažman Computing Centre (ARC). As part of the Institute’s research infrastructure, ARC includes computer clusters containing about 5000 cores, 6 TB RAM, 400 TB storage and featuring performance of about 32 teraflops. In the framework of the proposed research, ARC facilitates seamless and immediate computer power. NIC is the funding member of the organisation SLING (Slovenian Supercomputing Association), who will run European funded supercomputer centre HPC RIVR.

31.4 ULFFA – PIC: 999923240: The cooperation between the JSI and UL FFA is arranged by an Agreement on long-term cooperation (“Dogovor o dolgoročnem sodelovanju”). Fields of cooperation include all kinds of scientific and research activities that are in accordance with mutual benefits and needs of the individual laboratories within the JSI and UL (art. 2 of JSI-UL Agreement). The agreement entered into force on March 2006 and remains in force indefinitely (art. 6 and 8 of JSI-UL Agreement). ULFFA is a member of University of Ljubljana (Univerza v Ljubljani, UL), the oldest, largest, and internationally best-ranked university in Slovenia, being among the top 500 universities according to the Academic Ranking of World Universities Shanghai ranking (ARWU). The university was founded in 1919 and encompasses 23 faculties, 3 art academies, and 3 associated members. Faculty of Pharmacy (ULFFA) is the leading research and higher educational institution in the field of pharmacy, clinical biochemistry, toxicology and cosmetology in the region. The mission of the Faculty is to foster an environment supportive of education, research and service in order to promote the discovery, development and the appropriate use of medicines. We develop expertise in development of biomarkers, cell biology, molecular pharmacology and toxicology; in silico drug design, synthesis and evaluation of lead molecules/drug candidates in vitro; PK/PD modelling; development and validation of analytical

and bioanalytical methods; formulation design; solid-form prototype development, advanced drug delivery, nanotechnology and phytopharmacy. ULFFA has 1,400 students and approx. 150 teaching and research staff. ULFFA is strongly involved in basic and applicative research, financed by the government (68%), the pharmaceutical industry (21%), and EU projects (11%). ULFFA has excellent long-term research collaborations with the pharmaceutical industry, which has resulted in numerous international patent applications and patents. The ULFFA has valuable experience in managing large research EC projects: in the 6th FP (INTAFAR and CANCERDEGRADOME), in the 7th FP (NANOPHOTO and MAREX) and H2020 (MC-ITN) (<http://www.ffa.uni-lj.si/en/research>).

As an educational institution, it has a lot of experience in the implementation of education, organising symposia, summer schools, so its contribution to the implementation of the project will be visible in this area.

31.5 MFUM – PIC: 999903646: The cooperation between the JSI and MFUM is arranged by an Agreement on long-term cooperation (“Dogovor o dolgoročnem sodelovanju”). Fields of cooperation include all kinds of scientific and research activities that are in accordance with mutual benefits and needs of the individual laboratories within the JSI and MFUM (art. 2 of JSI- MFUM Agreement). The agreement entered into force in August 2021 and remains in force indefinitely (art. 4 of JSI-MFUM Agreement).

The Faculty of Medicine, University of Maribor (MFUM) is a medical institution which incorporates basic, translational and clinical research in topics pertaining human medicine and life sciences. The Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology focuses as part of their research focus on gynaecologic oncology in hormone dependent cancers, namely breast cancer and endometrial cancer. Previously our department has demonstrated a commitment to the understanding of the impact of phthalates on the reproductive outcomes in males. We own appropriate equipment to perform translational research (eg. Isolation of miRNA, genetic characterisation, chromatographs for determination of phthalate levels) on the impact endocrine disruptors have on cancer.

32- NACIONALNI INSTITUT ZA JAVNO ZDRAVJE, SLOVENIA (NIJZ) – PIC : 948891346

NIJZ (The National Institute of Public Health, Slovenia) is a tertiary national institution for health protection and disease prevention. It also functions as the principal national health statistics authority. According to the Health Service Act (9/92 and 14/13), NIJZ is responsible for comprehensive risk assessment (RA) for human health with over 20 years of experience in assessing risks from exposure to chemicals including RA based on HBM data. There is a substantial expertise in teaching on graduate and postgraduate level. In 2019, NIJZ set up an internal Committee for ethical issues concerning research activities in order to assist the National Medical Ethics Committee in areas specific to public health research. NIJZ pays much attention to developing effective risk communication (RC) methods. NIJZ will contribute to PARC by addressing priority knowledge gaps for evidence-based risk assessment, tracking sources of chemical exposure, assessing combined and aggregated exposures, identifying new and emerging exposures, establishing link between external and internal exposure, participating in development of limit values to be used in regulatory context and to facilitate the transition to the next generation risk assessment. Active participation in further advancement of systematic HBM will increase high quality human data and is seen as an important long-term contribution to the 3R strategies. A number of specific objectives of PARC project are in line with the current and future objectives of NIJZ, i.e. addressing key ethical challenges and facilitate implementation of procedures to review and ensure the proper application of ethical considerations, setting up of cross-disciplinary national network of risk assessors, responding to emerging challenges, strengthening of existing capacities and contribute to build new EU-wide transdisciplinary research and innovation platforms to support RA, health impact assessment and improve effective methods of risk communication.

32.1 OI – PIC: 986222475: The Institute of Oncology Ljubljana provides health services on the

secondary and tertiary levels as well as carries out teaching and research in oncology. The Epidemiology and Cancer Registry sector provides comprehensive management of oncological public health and oncological epidemiology in Slovenia. Slovenian Cancer Registry (SCR) provides information on incidence, prevalence and survival of cancer patients to professionals, decision-makers and lay public. Reporting cancer is obligatory in Slovenia and it is prescribed by law since the foundation of CRS in 1950. The quality and completeness of the collected data in CRS complies with all international standards. The researchers from OI-SCR are experts in the field of public health, epidemiology, and statistics with modelling and clinical oncology. Data is applied in geographical analyses, typically on the small-area level, where we are examining geographical patterns of cancer, possible clusters or correlations with risk factors, mostly linked to environmental pollution.

32.2 NLZOH – PIC: 949131227: The National Laboratory for Health, Environment and Food provides chemical analyses of environmental and food samples, evaluation of consumer products, microbiological tests, monitoring and surveys and research activities. According to the article 23c of the Health Care Act, NLZOH performs conformity assessment and risk assessment for samples taken within the national monitoring programmes of the official inspection and supervision. A specific focus is paid to the residues of pharmaceuticals for human and veterinarian use in the environment. A Mobile unit of the Ecological Laboratory acts in support of the Administration of the Republic of Slovenia for Civil Protection and Disaster Relief when chemical pollution occurs, such as in cases of environmental accidents. The NLZOH also participates in research projects and teaching.

32.3 ARSO – PIC: 920448812: The Slovenian Environmental Agency is a body of the Ministry of the Environment and Spatial Planning. It performs expert, analytical, regulatory and administrative tasks related to the environment at the national level. The Agency among others establishes, maintains and implements environmental monitoring and obtains environmental data. It participates in various international bodies (i.e. EEA, GSP) and is/was involved in international, cohesion projects. ARSO is responsible for air quality, water (rivers, lakes, marine water, groundwater and protected areas, i.e. bathing water) quality monitoring in Slovenia, and also classifies waters into chemical and ecological classes. Within the project “Soil Pollution Research in Slovenia” a lot of valuable data on soil quality in Slovenia was obtained. Various basic pedological parameters and inorganic and organic pollutants were determined in soil samples, which were sampled in various locations in Slovenia. ARSO prepares monitoring programmes, which are partially performed by the ARSO laboratory and partially subcontracted to other laboratories, such as NLZOH.

32.4 UKCMB – PIC: 999582188: The University Medical Centre Maribor is a teaching hospital providing secondary and tertiary healthcare service in north-eastern Slovenia. It is the second-largest medical institution in Slovenia. Annually, about 60,000 patients are treated as inpatients and almost 400,000 as outpatients in different sub-specialty units and 270 different outpatient clinics. The Clinic for Gynaecology and Perinatology is recognised, both locally and internationally, as one of the leading institutions in the region.

33- AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS (CSIC), SPAIN – PIC: 999991722

IDAEA is an environmental science institute in the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) devoted to the study of the human footprint on the biosphere. Much of our research is centred on two of the great environmental challenges of our time: the cleanliness and availability of water, the quality of air and the effects of environmental pollutants in human health.

Founded in 2008, IDAEA was envisaged as a new multidisciplinary research institute bringing together a wide range of expertise in environmental science and organised under two broad Departments (Environmental Chemistry and Geosciences).

The institute excels at the analysis of organic and inorganic pollutants and their impact on ecosystems and human health, the study and management of water resources, the development of algorithms in

chemometrics, and the study of gas-phase and inhalable particulate matter and toxic gases.

33.1 ULPGC – PIC: 999929739: This is a Spanish public university located in the Canary Islands that has a leading research group on endocrine disruption, population genetics, experimental oncology, toxicogenomics, and analytical toxicology. This AE is an associated Research Unit to CSIC since 1996.

33.2 UNAV – PIC: 999641746: This is a Spanish private non-profit university with an expert group on mycotoxins and genetic toxicology (> 20 year know-how). This AE is an Associated Research Unit to CSIC since 1995.

33.3 UGR – PIC: 999882015: This is a Spanish public university located in Granada that has a group with a strong tradition of participation in EU funded projects on environmental human health, including EU HBM, and has developed reference toxicology tests for endocrine disruption. This AE is an Associated Research Unit to CSIC since 2008.

33.4 UPO – PIC: 999846513: This is a Spanish public university located in Seville with a group expert on research toxicology in vitro. This AE is an Associated Research Unit to CSIC since 1999.

A Research Associate Unit between the AEs and CSIC was created. This Units allowed sharing of space, instruments, library resources and exchange of personnel. They also considered transfer of economic funds and joint purchase of equipment. Given that the AEs are Universities, these agreements also included participation of research staff from CSIC in academic courses from the Universities and inclusion of courses given in CSIC within the academic programs of the Universities. These agreements were signed at the highest level.

34- INSTITUTO DE SALUD CARLOS III, SPAIN (ISCIII) – PIC : 999507886

The Instituto de Salud Carlos III (ISCIII) is the main Public Research Entity funding, managing and carrying out biomedical research in Spain. The Institute has been conducting research and providing key services in the life and health sciences for over 20 years. It is also the body responsible for managing Spain's Health Research and Development Strategy within the framework of the National R+D+I Plan. It has as its main mission to support the development of scientific knowledge in the health sciences and to contribute to innovation in healthcare and the prevention of disease.

The ISCIII has up to date equipment for human, environmental and epidemiological analysis, with excellent facilities completely equipped for the analysis of biomarkers in human and environmental matrices. Completely equipped cell culture laboratory, toxicological bioassays with zebrafish embryos laboratory, and different ecotoxicity models assays working under OCDE methods and accredited according UNE-EN/ISO 17025. In addition, molecular biology equipment is also available and facility and methodology to carry out thyroid solute transport assays (iodine, thyroid hormones) with radioactive and non-radioactive methods. The institution has a core facility that provides DNA sequence analysis, electron microscopy, confocal microscopy, biosafety level 3 facility, animal experimentation facility, Proteomic facility and flow cytometry facility.

ISCIII and the following five affiliated entities described below (IISPV, EASP, FISABIO, UPV/EHU and UCLM), are legally linked, by the fact that all of them are associated to the Biomedical Research Networking Centres Public Consortium (CIBER-ISCIII-PIC 997154957), created by ISCIII around eight thematic scientific priorities and in which participate 90 different institution among the whole Spanish territory. The affiliated entities foreseen are present in the CIBER ISCIII as consortium members, in addition to ISCIII are:

34.1 EASP – PIC: 999859996: The Andalusian School of Public Health (Escuela Andaluza de Salud Pública, EASP), is a state-owned company operating under the Ministry of Health from the Regional Government of Andalusia. This institution was established to coordinate and develop training,

consultancy, and research at national and international level in the fields of public health and health services management. EASP develops environment and health research and provide scientific knowledge relevant for public health actions. Major research activities consist of epidemiologic and toxicological studies to evaluate the effect of persistent and non-persistent environmental pollutants on reproductive, respiratory, cardiovascular and cancer disease, as well as, early life origins of the neurobehavioral development and other diseases during childhood and adults periods. Moreover, EASP currently coordinates The Andalusian Health Survey and the Human Biomonitoring Study in Andalusia.

34.2 FISABIO –PIC: 951714046 : The Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of Valencia Region, FISABIO, is a nonprofit scientific and healthcare entity, whose primary purpose is to encourage, to promote and to develop scientific and technical health and biomedical research in Valencia Region.

Food Safety Area of FISABIO-Public Health focuses mainly on the development of analytical methods for the determination of pollutants and residues in foods and environmental matrices, and on the evaluation of the derived risk.

34.3 FINBA – PIC: 909900838: The Foundation for Biosanitary Research and Innovation of the Principality of Asturias (FINBA) is a non-profit organisation configured as the management structure for Research, Development and Innovation activities in the health centres of the Health Service of the Principality of Asturias (SESPA). The Board of Trustees of FINBA includes representatives from the Principado de Asturias (Asturian Regional Government), Universidad de Oviedo (University of Oviedo), Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), Ayuntamiento de Oviedo (Oviedo City Council) and private companies.

FINBA is the legal representative entity of the Biomedical Research Institute of Asturias (ISPA) created on April 5, 2016 by agreement signed between the Department for Health of the Asturian Regional Government, the regional Health Service of Asturias (SESPA) and the University of Oviedo (UO), with the aim of bringing together hospitals, universities and public and private research bodies of Asturias. Its core objective is to perform cutting-edge and interdisciplinary work in biomedical research as well as to provide scientific grounding for programmes and policies of the Spanish Health System. The legal link between FINBA and ISCIII is based the Spanish decentralised public administration.

34.4 FNS – PIC: 986357790 :Fundación Profesor Novoa Santos (FNS) holds the legal representation of the INIBIC since January 1, 2013. As such, FPNS enables the participation of the interdisciplinary research groups of INIBIC in research projects and handle the administrative and financial aspects of such participation.

ISCIII is the body responsible for managing Spain's Health Research and Development Strategy within the framework of the Spanish R+D+I Plan. Furthermore, in attention to the competences granted to ISCIII to fulfill its function of contributing to structuring research in the National Health System it became the scientific and technical accreditation body of the IIS. In this sense, the Biomedical Research Institute of A Coruña (INIBIC) was initially accredited as a health research institute on March 10, 2015 and subsequently renewed in March 10, 2020 for the next 5 years.

34.5 IISPV – PIC: 985772104: The Pere Virgili Health Research Institute (IISPV) was created within a scientific collaboration framework agreement between the following organisations: the Rovira i Virgili University (URV), the Institut Català de la Salut (Hospital Universitari de Tarragona Joan XXIII, Hospital de Tortosa Verge de la Cinta), the Hospital Universitari Sant Joan de Reus, and the Pere Mata Group. The URV provides in-kind contributions free of charge to the IISPV according to articles 6.1 and 9.2 of MGA. In particular, the URV biomedical research groups, develop their research activity through the IISPV with no charges from URV to IISPV for these resources. This research work is done at IISPV facilities. The URV and IISPV have signed an agreement to this end, implying collaboration that is not limited to PARC project.

34.6 INSST – PIC: 890173948: The INSST is the national reference organisation for health and safety at work in Spain and EU and provides information at the European Health and Safety Agency (EU-OSHA) and holds the general secretary of the Spanish Commission for Health and Safety at work. Its mission is the analysis and investigation of safety and health working conditions with the overall aim of improving workers health.

ISCIII and INSST are both national autonomous bodies depending upon the Spanish General State Administration. As such, there is a structural link (legal/capital) that exists independently of the project, exists beforehand and remains valid after the end of the action. Besides, to reinforce the existing structural link between both entities, they have renewed an agreement in February 2020 for the mutual collaboration and development of training, research and technical advice initiatives on the prevention of occupational risks and occupational health and that covers all those aspects that, within their respective competences, could be of mutual interest.

34.7 UCLM – PIC: 999840208: University of Castilla la Mancha (UCLM) integrates 36 academic departments offering 45 degree qualifications. UCLM has two peculiar features: a) it is multi-disciplinary, undertaking work in practically all branches of knowledge; and b) its activities are very wide-ranging, embracing the spectrum from basic research to technological development.

UCLM team participating in PARC has acquired extensive expertise in the field of evaluation of the effects of environmental pollution in wildlife. The team is currently coordinating a COST Action on pesticide risk assessment for amphibians and reptiles, and during the last 12 years, has conducted research, through several projects funded by national public and private institutions, on the characterisation of pesticide effects. These characterisation are conducted on an integrative manner, considering from the study of molecular and physiological biomarkers of exposure and effects that can be of application to the environmental biomonitoring of pollutants in wildlife.

34.8 UPV/EHU – PIC: 999865234: The Research group in Environmental Epidemiology and Children’s Neuropsychology (EANPsi), is a research group established in the University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU) since 2015. By supporting specialised research groups, the University creates a unique environment for innovation and development of top class scientific and technological research. The EANP research group has a wide experience in designing and directing human biomonitoring programmes in Spain.

35- NATURVARDsverket, SWEDEN (SEPA) – PIC: 998884079

The Swedish EPA (SEPA) is the public agency in Sweden that is responsible for environmental issues. The Agency carries out assignments on behalf of the Swedish Government relating to the environment in Sweden, the EU and internationally. The Agency’s remit is threefold; compiling knowledge and documentation, developing environmental policy by providing the Government with a sound basis for decisions and by giving an impetus to EU and international efforts, and implementing environmental policy by acting in such a way as to ensure compliance with the Swedish Environmental Code and achievement of the national environmental objectives.

35.1 UGOT – PIC: 999981925 : The University of Gothenburg -UGOT- is one of the major universities in northern Europe. The Department of Biological and Environmental Sciences, which will participate in PARC, hosts the Centre for Future Chemical Risk Assessment and Management (FRAM), a long-term collaboration between natural scientists (ecotoxicology, environmental chemistry, environmental modeling, mathematics) and legal scholars, policy experts & environmental economists. FRAM is especially active at the interface between science and policy, evaluating chemical risk assessment methods and, in particular, working towards developing new strategies, in order to better account for the complex and widespread chemical pollution that is so characteristic for the European environment these days.

Link of the participant to the affiliated entity: UGOT is a part of the national environmental monitoring programme, which is run and coordinated by SEPA. UGOT is also a participant in SEPA's environmental research programme

35.2 KI – PIC: 999978530 : Karolinska Institutet (KI), founded in 1810, is Sweden's only university especially focusing on biomedical sciences. KI ranks as one of the world's leading medical universities, thanks in part to the quality of its research activities, which today account for 40 per cent of all medical research in Sweden. KI has about 4 550 employees (full-time equivalents), nearly two-thirds of whom are female. Some 80 per cent of KI's income is devoted to research, distributed among some 600 research groups covering all medical fields. KI provides excellent postgraduate training with 2000 registered PhD students from around the world who are active in both basic and clinical research. Research at KI has a strong European dimension, with almost 200 project participations within the EU's Sixth Framework Programme (FP6). Of these, KI coordinated 28 projects. KI was also a major player in FP7, participating in 323 projects including 36 as coordinator as well as 31 European Research Council Grants. KI has to date been awarded 248 contracts within Horizon 2020, 14 as coordinator and 35 European Research Council Grants. KI is also a major European beneficiary of funds from the National Institutes of Health in the U.S. In addition, KI annually awards the Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine.

The Institute of Environmental Medicine (IMM) is a department at KI with research activities related to toxicology, epidemiology and health risk assessment, including various EU projects related to chemical risk assessment. IMM also has its own regulatory letter and instructions from the Swedish Government (as an authority within the authority) which state, among other things, the purpose of IMM and how it is to be governed. IMM operates within the framework of KI and conducts research and education as well as carries out investigations related to environmental medicine, including work environment, and health protection.

Link of the participant to the affiliated entity: According to the Swedish Government assignment, IMM at KI shall in particular support national and international authorities with expert knowledge. IMM is headed by a board where 10 out of 12 members are appointed from Swedish national authorities that are primarily affected by the Institute's activities. SEPA is one of these authorities. The Board's task is to decide about the direction of IMM's activities and prepare a basis for the budget and proposals for grant applications.

35.3 ULUND – PIC: 999901318 : Lund University (ULUND) is the largest university of Sweden. The Department of Laboratory Medicine conducts leading research, both broad and specialised, within the field of laboratory medicine, focusing on the onset of disease and how to improve diagnostics and treatment for patients. The Centre of Environmental and Climate Science is an interdisciplinary environment for research for solutions to environmental and societal challenges. The Department of Biology houses national biodiversity monitoring and capacity to conduct large scale field experiments to support environmental risk assessment (ERA). Researchers from ULUND participate in environment and food safety risk assessments, such as for the European Food Safety Authority EFSA and the Swedish Chemicals Agency (KEMI).

Link of the participant to the affiliated entity: ULUND is a part of the national environmental monitoring programme, which is run and coordinated by SEPA. ULUND manages several studies within the national health related environmental monitoring programme. ULUND is also one of the reference laboratories within HBM4EU and regularly performs analyses on behalf of SEPA.

35.4 ORU – PIC: 999650088: ORU is an advanced research centre at Örebro University, Sweden with around 50 researchers focusing on basic and applied, experimental and computational environmental toxicology and chemistry of new and emerging pollutants as well as legacy pollutants in collaboration with industry, authorities and NGOs. ORU holds personnel, equipment and facilities for mass spectrometric analysis of trace pollutants and metabolomics, effect-based monitoring and ecotoxicology research. ORU runs a bioanalytical laboratory for effect-based detection of endocrine disruptors and

genotoxicants and has facilities for high performance GC- and LC-based effect-directed analysis (EDA). ORU runs a laboratory directed at exposomics research using a metabolomics approach. ORU is a reference laboratory for UN Environment regarding PFAS analysis, responsible for air and water samples within the Global Monitoring Plan.

Link of the participant to the affiliated entity:

ORU is a part of the national environmental monitoring programme, which is run and coordinated by SEPA. ORU manages several studies within the toxic substances coordination programme.

35.5 RISE – PIC: 999613422: RISE Research Institutes of Sweden is an independent, 100% state-owned research institute that offers unique expertise and about 100 testbeds and demonstration facilities, instrumental in future-proofing technologies, products, and services. In 2016, the former institutes of Innventia, SP Technical Research Institute of Sweden and Swedish ICT merged to form RISE. During 2018, RISE expanded to include the former institutes Swerea IVF, Swerea SICOMP, Swerea SWECAST and part of Swerea KIMAB. Swetox became a part of RISE in 2019. The merged RISE drives advanced research in a broad spectrum of areas that are divided into five divisions. RISE has a long history of acknowledged high-quality research and conducting assignments in each of these divisions. RISE is a non-profit organisation.

Link of the participant to the affiliated entity: RISE and SEPA have a long-standing collaboration within environmental science. RISE provides specialist support to SEPA in several areas within environmental science, which is regulated in a framework agreement.

35.6 SU – PIC: 999885022 : Stockholm University (SU) provides higher education and research within science, the humanities and the social sciences. It was ranked as nr 73 in the 2019 Academic Ranking of World Universities (The Shanghai Ranking). The university participates in regional, national and international collaboration. Several world-leading researchers work here (4 Nobel Prizes over the years). In 2019 the revenue of Stockholm University was 53 million euro, of which 61% financed the research and postgraduate education. The 120 research projects funded by Horizon 2020 include 30 ERC projects and 37 MSCA projects.

At the Department of Environmental Science the aim is to contribute to a sustainable society through world-leading research and education in environmental science. The department has 170 faculty members, researchers, doctoral students and support staff from over 30 countries. It has consistently been ranked among the top 30 educational institutions in the world in environmental science and alumni have secured prestigious roles as policy makers, environmental consultants, and researchers. The research spans across four major areas: chemical contaminants, atmospheric science, biogeochemistry and (eco)toxicology. Unique is a research group focusing solely on regulatory (eco)toxicology.

Researchers at the department strongly engage in supporting Swedish and European environment agencies with their decision-making and policy drafting. Examples of engagements include: inquiry for the Swedish Government addressing combination effects and assessing chemicals in groups; member of the ECHA management board, observer of the CARACAL expert group; invited expert by UN Environment; and development of risk assessment methodology for implementation in the Water Framework Directive.

Link of the participant to the affiliated entity: SU is a part of the national environmental monitoring programme, which is run and coordinated by SEPA. SU manages several studies within the national health related environmental monitoring and toxic substances coordination programmes. SU is also the national reference laboratory for environmental monitoring in air on behalf of SEPA.

35.7 KEMI – PIC: 937974093: The Swedish Chemicals Agency (KEMI) is a supervisory authority under the Swedish Government and works to ensure that the companies' and society's chemicals control is managed in a good way. KEMI strives to reduce the risk of humans and the environment getting harmed by chemicals with the goal of preventing damage. KEMI has three departments, Development of Legislation and Other Instruments, involved in EU work, substance assessments, proposals for regulatory measures and development of rules at EU and international level; Authorisation and

Guidance, evaluating applications for pesticides and providing information and training on rules applying to chemicals; Enforcement and Registries, carrying out inspections of manufacturers and importers, providing national guidance on enforcement, and keeping Products and Pesticides Registers. Link of the participant to the affiliated entity: KEMI and SEPA are both governmental agencies governed by the Swedish state and by the same public body (Ministry of the Environment). In addition to this, KEMI and SEPA collaborate broadly and are ordained to do so in the regulations governing the two agencies.

35.8 IVL – PIC 999476361: IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute is a non-profit research organisation and Sweden's oldest environmental research institute, started in 1966. IVL is owned (governed) by a foundation formed jointly by the Swedish government and industry. The non-profit status ensures that IVL is approved for receiving research grants from government funding agencies and the EU with the same conditions as academia. IVL also receives direct annual government grants for research projects co-funded with industry. Research grants make up about 50% of IVL's annual turnover.

Link of the participant to the affiliated entity: IVL performs parts of the Swedish environmental monitoring programme and manages reference research stations for environmental monitoring in air, such as EMEP monitoring stations. IVL is thus a part of the national environmental monitoring programme, which is run and coordinated by SEPA.

35.9 SLV – PIC: 997318402: The Swedish Food Agency (SLV) is an autonomous government agency reporting to the Ministry of Enterprise and Innovation. We are tasked to promote healthy dietary habits and to enforce safe foods and fair practices in the food trade. Our tools are regulations, recommendations and communication. Our recommendations and communication support consumers in their everyday life, for example when shopping, feeding their children and cooking. The Swedish Food Agency takes an active part in the development of new legislation in co-operation with other EU member states and does take part in setting EU food safety standards. Food safety is the responsibility of the company that produces or sells food. Food control however, which includes drinking water, is carried out by the Swedish Food Agency at the national level, the County Administrations at the regional level and the municipal Environment and Health Protection Committees at the local level. The Swedish Food Agency is the competent authority when it comes to environmental issues in the food sector. We encourage people to learn more about eco-smart food choices and how to minimise food waste.

Link of the participant to the affiliated entity: SLV and SEPA are both governmental agencies governed by the Swedish state. In addition to this, SLV and SEPA collaborate broadly and are ordained to do so in the regulation governing SLV. In addition to this, SLV is a part of the national environmental monitoring programme, which is run and coordinated by SEPA. SLV manages several long-term studies within the health related environmental monitoring programme.

35.10 SLU – PIC: 999887350 : The Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU) is a world-class academic institution, and its mission is to develop the understanding and sustainable use and management of biological natural resources, which is achieved by research, education and environmental monitoring/assessment, in collaboration with the surrounding community. The Department of Aquatic Sciences and Assessment (IVM) and the Department of Biomedical Sciences and Veterinary Public Health (BVF) will participate in PARC. IVM is focused on improving our understanding of the environmental status of the aquatic environment as well as the underlying causes of any variation over time and space. The research includes environmental pollutants, biodiversity, and ecosystem services. BVF conducts research on animal health, food safety and environmental health.

Link of the participant to the affiliated entity: SLU is a part of the national environmental monitoring programme, which is run and coordinated by SEPA. SLU is the data host within nature data monitoring, which means that all data created within this programme is stored and managed by SLU on behalf of SEPA.

35.11 UMU – PIC: 999881821: The Department of Public Health and Clinical Medicine at Umeå University (UMU) was formed in 1999 and consists of the following divisions; Family Medicine, Sustainable Health and Medicine (here Dermatology and Venereology, Cardiology, Respiratory medicine and Rheumatology are included).

The research performed within the department covers a very wide range of areas. A large number of research groups are present, all with their specific interest areas. However, many collaborative projects exist both within and between the different divisions. In addition, a substantial number of clinicians from the University Hospital are affiliated with the respective divisions. The number of graduate students are around 130 and the number of permanently employed of all categories are around 180.

The Department of Chemistry is one of the largest departments at the faculty with more than 200 employees. Research at the department includes three major areas: Biological Chemistry, Environmental and Biogeochemistry and Technical Chemistry. The Chemistry Department is heavily equipped with infrastructure for characterisation of chemicals and chemical processes and chemical analysis. The Environmental Chemistry group has a strong research focus on developing new methodologies including chemical analysis and computational approaches for studying fate and effects of chemicals.

Link of the participant to the affiliated entity: UMU is a part of the national environmental monitoring programme, which is run and coordinated by SEPA. UMU manages several studies within the health related environmental monitoring programme for example regarding monitoring pollutants in human matrices.

35.12 UU – PIC: 999985029 : Uppsala University (UU) is the oldest university in the Nordic countries and was founded in 1477. Today UU is a comprehensive research university and research is pursued across nine faculties that include 41 000 students, 6 500 teachers and researchers, and more than 500 full professors. The programme for Environmental Toxicology at the department of Organismal Biology and the Department of Pharmaceutical Biosciences form the immediate research environments for the proposed activities.

Link of the participant to the affiliated entity: UU is a part of the national environmental monitoring programme, which is run and coordinated by SEPA. UU manages several studies within different programme areas.

36- ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS, GREECE (AUTH) – PIC: 999895692

Aristotle University of Thessaloniki is the largest university in Greece. It comprises 10 faculties which consist of 40 schools and 1 single-School Faculty. AUTH will participate with several research units from various Departments (Chemical Engineering, Chemistry, Medicine, Veterinary, Pharmacology) and will be led by EnvE Lab (Dept. of Chemical Engineering) Director, Prof D. Sarigiannis, who is also the Director of the research unit HERACLES Research Center; the HERACLES Research Center on the Exposome and Health within the Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation Center of Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) was established in 2015, bringing along novel approaches to environment and public health risk assessment and management developed over more than 20 years of international scientific work, including at the University of California at Berkeley and the European Commission's Joint Research Centre.

Significant infrastructure relevant to the proposed work includes a GC/MS-MS/QToF Agilent 7200A, a LC/MS-MS/QToF Agilent 1290-6540 UHD, a LC/MS-MS Thermo Orbitrap for targeted and untargeted metabolomics analysis, an NMR 600 MHz Agilent PremiumCOMPACT for untargeted metabolomics analysis, and a Microarray Scanner Agilent SureScan for transcriptomic analysis. Additional infrastructure includes Bioinformatics algorithms for molecular pathway analysis of multi-omics data (implemented in GeneSpring – mass profiler), as well as a deep freezer (-86 oC of 700 lt for storage of biological samples). Finally, there is also the respective IT infrastructure for modelling work

36.1 EFET – PIC:959188478: The Hellenic Food Authority is the Greek National Competent Authority for Food Safety and its main activities include: Risk-based control activities, (e.g. chemical

contaminants, in foods) and compliance of foodstuffs and food contact materials to quality and safety requirements. Risk assessment in various fields of food safety. Recent risk assessments include heavy metal contamination of vegetables, food additive-related risks, process-induced deterioration of frying oils, etc. Implementation of risk exposure assessment methodology for various chemical contaminants and additives. Information and awareness campaigns towards consumers and sector stakeholder on food safety, legislation and nutrition issues. Parallel to that, EFET cooperates with food business stakeholders for the compilation of Good Practice guides for the food industry.

EFET has considerable experience in implementing transnational cooperation projects (e.g. the “KnowInTarget MED, “Listeria Project” regarding microbial risk assessment and risk mitigation approaches).

36.2 GCSL – PIC:912807637: The General Chemical State Laboratory (GCSL) is a General Directorate within the Independent Authority for Public Revenue (I.A.P.R.). The mission of GCSL is to provide high quality technical and scientific services to public authorities regarding the protection of environment, public health, interests of consumers and supporting the proper function of the market and strengthen the competitiveness and innovation and support initiatives of I.A.P.R. to fight tax evasion. AUTH is linked to GCSL to work together on mutually beneficial projects focused on the development of assessment of risks related to chemical of indoor and outdoor air pollution and consumer products and to predict the trends and the associated health risks.

36.3 NKUA – PIC:999643007: The National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA), officially founded in 1837, is the first University in the Balkan peninsula and the Eastern Mediterranean region. It attracted more than 60 million Euro over the last three years for the research and development projects proposed by the Professors of the 43 Departments. The Department of Chemistry is one of the most active department in publishing scientific articles and is structured in seven laboratories. The Laboratory of Analytical Chemistry (LAC) has been established in 1968 and since then has achieved and demonstrated high experience in the development of analytical instrumentation, analytical techniques and methods for a vast variety of applications, including environment, pharmaceuticals, clinical chemistry, food and industrial products. LAC is an accredited laboratory (ISO 17025) that has strong links with water and wastewater treatment industry and regulatory bodies for environmental quality issues and emerging contaminants.

36.4 UOC - PIC:999588978: The Laboratory of Toxicology of University of Crete (UoC) is fully equipped with modern analytical instruments for certifications, preliminary examination instruments and preparation instruments for extraction and purification of samples. The research team of the laboratory consists of 2 academics, 3 biologists, 2 chemists, a biochemist, a food engineer, a physicist, an environmentalist (11 people), 6 PhD and management staff (secretary, technical, mechanographical support personnel). Professor Aristides Tsatsakis is the Director of the Department of Toxicology and Forensic Sciences of the Medical School at the University of Crete and the University Hospital of Heraklion Professor Tsatsakis has published well over 1000 works (articles in journals, books and abstracts proceedings), over 600 of them in ISI journals and PubMed. He is the holder of several patents and has an extensive array of citations (over 20,000 GS) and reads /downloads (over 170,000 RG) of his papers. His current IF index is 68 (GS) and 56 (Publons).

AUTH is linked with UoC is on mutually beneficial research programmes focused on the collection and analysis, of human specimen biosamples and toxicological analysis (including omics) for environmental health research.

37- BENAKI PHYTOPATHOLOGICAL INSTITUTE, GREECE (BPI) – PIC: 998193633

The scientific activities of BPI are directly related to the above-mentioned tasks. More specifically, BPI is the National Competent Authority for the evaluation and risk assessment of pesticides under the respective Regulations (EC) No.’s 1107/2009 and 396/2005 and Regulation No. (EU) 528/2012, as regards their efficacy, quality and specifications, safety for the environment and non-target species and

safety for human health (hazard identification, risk assessment related to both non-dietary and dietary exposures), proposals for Harmonised Classification and Labelling for registration purposes at EU and at National level. BPI's research activities are related to plant protection, and safety issues of agrochemicals, other pollutants and natural products for humans and the environment.

The main infrastructure and technical equipment relevant for the foreseen work is the following:

- Liquid/Gas chromatography tandem mass spectrometers (including an ion mobility Ionisation Tandem Mass Spectrometer, HPLC-ESI-SelexIon-QTrap), and Ultra-High Pressure Liquid Chromatography and Nano-Liquid Chromatography systems hyphenated with a High Resolution Mass Spectrometer (UHPLC-HRMS/MS & nano-LC-HRMS/MS, Q-Exactive Orbitrap). An Ion Chromatography - Inductively Couple Mass Spectrometry (IC-ICP-MS) is also available.
- Real time PCR
- Microtox® Analyser(Model 500)
- Fully equipped tissue culture facility (Laminar flow cabinet, CO2 cell culture incubator, Inverted microscope)
- Breeding units for *Danio rerio*, alga, aquatic invertebrates and soil organisms (*Eisenia foetida*)

38- Département Fédéral de l'Intérieur, SWITZERLAND (FOPH) – PIC : 957586329

FOPH is the Swiss national authority responsible for protecting public health and improving the country's healthcare system. More specifically, we are responsible for consumer protection, the supervision of health insurance and development of health policy. In these remits, we are also responsible for the healthy use of industrial chemicals, and work together with other national authorities regarding chemical risk assessment, and researchers in various institutions.

39- AGROSCOPE, SWITZERLAND – PIC: 998365711

Agroscope is the Swiss Confederation's centre of excellence for research and development in the fields of agriculture, food, and the environment. Agroscope researches for a resilient agriculture and food system, a healthy diet based on high-quality food, and an intact environment for the benefit of society, policy-makers and practitioners.

Among others, researchers at Agroscope are involved risk assessing plant protection measures in view of their impact on agricultural productivity and biodiversity and in investigating the potential of biodiversity measures to improve ecosystem services and agricultural productivity.

40- Policlinique Médicale Universitaire de Lausanne, SWITZERLAND (UNISANTE) – PIC : 903030134

The University Center for Primary Care and Public Health, designated by the name Unisanté, has close to 900 employees active in health-related research, academic training, prevention and primary care. Innovative and unique in Switzerland, this new academic center created in 2019 promotes interdisciplinarity as well as the union of skills involved in community health issues. Unisanté has five main missions: (1) to deliver health promotion and prevention interventions, including new programs for the public and their concerns including research on possible associations between the environment (physical, chemical, work and socio-economic) and health. (2) to deliver primary care services, including access to care and education of health professionals, (3) to respond to the health care needs, and improve access to care, of vulnerable populations, (4) to provide expertise and conduct research projects on the organisation and financing of health systems and services, (5) to conduct academic research and teaching activities in primary care, public health as well as environmental and work health.

**41- EIDGENOESSISCHE ANSTALT FUER WASSERVERSORGUNG
ABWASSERREINIGUNG UND GEWAESSERSCHUTZ, SWITZERLAND (EAWAG) – PIC:
998124569**

Eawag belongs to the domain of the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology (ETH) and houses 12 research departments among others in aquatic chemistry/toxicology/aquatic ecology/ water resource engineering/ system analysis. It employs 510 staff including more than 200 international scientists and currently about 150 PhD students from 32 nationalities. Half of the Eawag group leaders are also full/adjunct professors at ETH Zurich, EPF Lausanne or other Swiss Universities. Scientists from Eawag develop innovative approaches and technologies for the sustainable management of water and water bodies. Through close collaboration with experts from industry, government and professional associations, Eawag plays an important bridging role between theory and practice, allowing new scientific insights to be rapidly implemented. Eawag has extensive experience of managing EU projects & successfully administers 45 projects, including FP 7, Horizon 2020, COST, Scientific Exchange Programme Sciex-NMSch (Swiss Contribution to the New Member States of the EU).

**42- EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH, SWITZERLAND
(ETHZ) – PIC: 999979015**

ETH Zurich is one of the world's leading universities specialising in science and technology. We are renowned for our excellent education, cutting-edge fundamental research and direct transfer of new knowledge into society. Over 30,000 people from more than 120 countries find our university to be a place that promotes independent thinking and an environment that inspires excellence. Located in the heart of Europe, yet forging connections all over the world, we work together to develop solutions for the global challenges of today and tomorrow.

Profile/Infrastructure:

Our laboratory comprises a biosafety level 2 lab fully equipped for anaerobic fermentation techniques as well as bioanalytical facilities with state-of-the-art LC-MS/MS instrumentation. Further, we have access to PolyFerm™ bioreactors within the Institute of Food, Nutrition and Health. Extensive research experience and know-how concerning systems toxicology, toxin-microbiome interactions, natural toxins and pharmacokinetics is documented by various peer-reviewed articles for both, Prof. Shana J. Sturla and Dr. Georg Aichinger.

**43- EIDGENOSSISCHE MATERIALPRUFUNGS- UND FORSCHUNGSANSTALT,
SWITZERLAND (EMPA) – PIC: 999907138**

Empa, the Swiss Federal Laboratories for Material Science and Technology, is a research institution within the ETH domain and specializes in applications, focused research and development, and provides high-level services in the field of sustainable materials science and technology. Its core tasks are innovative collaboration with industry and public institutions, ensuring the safety of people and the environment, knowledge propagation and university-level teaching.

**44- FEDERAL DEPARTMENT FOR ENVIRONMENT, TRANSPORT, ENERGY AND
COMMUNICATIONS, SWITZERLAND (FOEN) – PIC: 999439210**

The mission of the Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN) is to ensure the sustainable use of natural resources including soil, water, air, quietness and forests. It is responsible for the protection against natural hazards, safeguarding the environment and human health against excessive impacts, and conserving biodiversity and landscape quality. It is also responsible for international environmental policy. Within its remit to protect biodiversity, FOEN is responsible for the environmental risk assessment of biocides and since the beginning of 2022 also for plant protection products.

45- UNIVERSITA DELLA SVIZZERA ITALIANA, SWITZERLAND (USI) – PIC: 999585874

Università della Svizzera italiana (USI), established in 1996, is one of the 12 certified public universities in Switzerland and member of swissuniversities. It is organised in six faculties and is active in several study and research areas, among which: architecture, communication sciences, computational science, data science, economics, health studies, humanities, informatics, law, medicine and biomedicine. 3'922 students and 1'008 professors and researchers are distributed over four campuses in Lugano, Mendrisio and Bellinzona. An interdisciplinary center “the house of sustainability” will open in Airolo in 2023.

46- UNIVERSITÄT BASEL, SWITZERLAND (UNIBAS) – PIC: 999907914

The Swiss Centre for Applied Human Toxicology (SCAHT) with its Regulatory Toxicology Group at the University of Basel (UNIBAS) comprises a network of scientific professionals with skills and experience in critical questions related to human safety of chemicals. It is funded by the Swiss Confederation and the participating universities of Basel, Geneva, Lausanne and the FHNW School of Life Sciences. The SCAHT provides expert advice and services in regulatory toxicology to the Swiss federal regulatory offices, the media, the general public and third parties. The Centre supports research in applied human toxicology and facilitates the exchange of multidisciplinary information and data. SCAHT contributes to education and training in human toxicology and encourages the recruitment of students and new members into the profession.

47- State Secretariat for Economic Affairs, SWITZERLAND (SECO) – PIC: 889610475

SECO is the federal government’s centre of expertise for core issues relating to economic policy. Its aim is to ensure sustainable economic growth, high employment and fair working conditions by providing a stable environment for regulatory, economic and foreign trade policy.

48- EUROPEAN CHEMICALS AGENCY, EU (ECHA) – PIC: 894182376

The European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) is a European Union (EU) body established on 1 June 2007 by Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH). ECHA’s mandate is to manage and carry out technical, scientific and administrative aspects of REACH. ECHA was also established to manage tasks related to the classification and labelling of chemical substances, which, since 2009, have been governed by Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on Classification, Labelling and Packaging of substances and mixtures (CLP). Since 2012, ECHA’s mandate covers Regulation (EU) No 528/2012 concerning the making available on the market and use of biocidal products (the Biocidal Products Regulation, BPR) and since 2014, also the recast prior informed consent (PIC) Regulation (EU) No 649/2012 concerning the export and import of hazardous chemicals.

49- EUROPEAN FOOD SAFETY AUTHORITY, EU (EFSA) – PIC: 893964320

EFSA is a European agency funded by the European Union and set up in 2002 following a series of food crises in the late 1990s to be a source of scientific advice and communication on risks associated with the food chain. The agency was legally established by the EU under the General Food Law - Regulation 178/2002. As the risk assessor, EFSA produces scientific opinions and advice that form the basis for European policies and legislation. Its remit covers: Food and feed safety; Nutrition; Animal health and welfare; Plant protection; Plant health. It also considers, through environmental risk assessments, the possible impact of the food chain on the biodiversity of plant and animal habitats. EFSA also plays an important role in collecting and analysing data to ensure that European risk assessment is supported by the most comprehensive scientific information available. It does this in

cooperation with EU Member States. Communicating on risks associated with the food chain is another key part of EFSA's mandate. This means providing appropriate, accurate and timely information on food safety issues to raise awareness and explain the implications of EFSA's scientific work.

50- Department of Health, UK (UKHSA) – PIC: 986454887

At the United Kingdom Health Security Agency (UKHSA) our mission is to provide health security for the nation by protecting from infectious disease and external hazards. The Radiation Chemical and Environment Division provides advice, research and services to protect the public from hazards resulting from exposure to chemicals and poisons, radiation (both ionising and non-ionising) and ultrasound and infrasound. We are a trusted source of advice to government and to the public.

The Toxicology Department undertakes research in chemicals and radiation that underpins advice and policy development. Research in environmental hazards includes from methods to analyse, model and calculate human exposure to environmental chemicals or pollutants, mechanisms of action of environmental hazards on health (adverse health effects) and the role of genetics and epigenetics in conferring differential risk to environmental hazards. All of the research underpins the UKHSA role in public health protection from environmental hazards.

UKHSA scientists engaged in PARC have experience and international reputations in toxicology, risk assessment and human biomonitoring. We work with UK Government Departments to develop strategies for safe management of chemicals. We have been part of many EU projects - COPHES/DEMOOPHES, HBM4EU, GOLIATH, NANO HARMONY and many more. We work with the OECD on the development of test guidelines, IATAs and Chair many expert subgroups. Furthermore, our scientists work with WHO, and other international bodies in the field of toxicology and human biomonitoring.

UKHSA has laboratory capability in chemical analysis as well as in vivo and in vitro assessment of hazards. Equipment for sample preparation includes accelerated solvent extraction, manual solid-phase extraction and automated solid-phase extraction (Extrahera, Biotage). For quantitation we have UHPLC-Orbitrap MS, ICPMS, IC-ICPMS, nanoLC-Orbitrap MS, GC/MS and GC-MS/MS. The latter two are fitted with SPME and we have desorption tube (Markes) capability.

51- BRUNEL UNIVERSITY LONDON, UK (BUL) – PIC: 999749610

The Centre for Pollution Research and Policy, formerly known as the Institute of Environment, Health and Societies, at Brunel University London, is one of the university's specialist research centres, devoted to exploring the effects of contaminants on human and wildlife health. It is recognised globally for its research in environmental sciences and has international collaborative links with pharmaceutical industries (e.g. AstraZeneca, Pfizer, Glaxo), water companies, and multilateral and national government authorities (e.g. SAICM, ECHA, European Commission, Joint Research Centre, EFSA, OECD, Defra, UK Environment Agency). It has a strong track record of coordinating and participating in EU-funded projects, including PHARMAS, EDEN, COMPRENDO, ACE, CONTAMED, ESNATS, SOLUTIONS, ATHENA, ENDPOINTS, GOLIATH. The Centre also focuses on translating research results into policy advice, and plays an active role in advising the European Commission, EFSA, the World Health Organisation (WHO) and the United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP). In recognition of these activities, the Institute won the Queen's Anniversary Prize as a leading example of excellence not just in research, but also in the global impact of its work. The Queen's Anniversary Prize is the highest accolade that can be conferred to an UK academic institution.

52- THE SECRETARY OF STATE FOR ENVIRONMENT, FOOD AND RURAL AFFAIRS, UK (Cefas-Defra) – PIC: 999904713

DEFRA:

Defra are the UK central government department responsible for improving and protecting the

environment. We aim to grow a green economy and sustain thriving rural communities. We also support our world-leading food, farming and fishing industries. Through development and delivery of policies, we are here to make our air purer, our water cleaner, our land greener. This includes effective management of chemicals to meet our objectives, as set out in the UK government's 25 Year Environment Plan to make sure that chemicals are safely used and managed, and that the levels of harmful chemicals entering the environment are significantly reduced. The Government's 25 Year Environment Plan commits to a new strategy to tackle chemicals of national concern. The development of a new Chemicals Strategy will provide an opportunity to set out future priorities, and to articulate a framework for our approach chemicals regulation.

Defra, along with UKHSA as governing body and grant signatory respectively, provide a coordination function for UK engagement and participation in PARC. Defra provides the secretariat function for PARC UK/UK ARCHE. This includes scheduling and leading the UK steering group meetings 2-3 times a year. The role of the UK PARC Steering Group is to provide strategic steer for UK input into the governance of PARC. Defra coordinates the UK National Hub which provides a forum for UK participants in PARC to exchange knowledge and discuss their respective involvements in PARC.

In addition to coordination role, Defra will support task 2.2 efforts to install a network of internal and external partners. Preparation for and participation in WP/task meetings and plan for future deliverables. Defra promotes efforts on building a science & policy interface, including through engagement with the OECD and national and international experts to support evidence-based policy making. This will in turn strengthen relationship within the UK, including with Hazardous Substances Committee (HSAC), as well as with international partners through engagement in OECD work areas relevant to chemicals risk assessment and NAMs and the new intergovernmental science policy panel on chemicals, waste and pollution.

Defra participates in task 8.1.2. which aims to translate safe and sustainable by design (SSbD) criteria and methodology into a toolbox. Defra is exploring options to promote innovation of safe(r) and sustainable chemicals and this includes engaging with stakeholders to understand how SSbD criteria could be used and applied internationally and in a UK setting. We will use the information generated from these engagements along with our policy expertise to feed into task 8.1.2.

CEFAS:

Cefas is an executive agency, sponsored by the Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs. They are world leaders in marine science and technology that collects, manages and interprets data on the aquatic environment, biodiversity and fisheries. Cefas involvement in PARC is relevant to WP5, task 5.1b which will focus on the environment. Our contributions will be guided by two important principles; a) the need to create a framework in which both chemical read-across and species sensitivities are addressed and b) the 'One Health' principle where environment and human health are considered together. We plan to work on two main areas within the objectives of WP5.

To further develop regulatory accepted methods under the OECD test guidelines and guidance (as we have a long-standing experience with international TG development and validation spanning more than two decades). This element of work will address both method and data gaps as they emerge from regulatory processes. Cefas would like to focus on marine invertebrates, as there are practically no TGs with marine species, whilst they tend to be more sensitive to chemicals than freshwater species. Other focus areas include degradation and metabolism products, PFAS/PFOS, endocrine disruptors, low-volume chemicals, and complex mixtures.

The second area of work is to engage with New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) that have a good potential of replacing classic in vivo methods that are based on protected vertebrates. These mechanistic data, especially when accompanied with empirical data or a robust Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOPs) are key requirements for building regulator confidence in the NAMs (along with WP5 task 5.2 and WP6). The programme of work we have planned is also connected with international initiatives via strong connections not only with Europe but also US and Japan colleagues.

53- UK CENTRE FOR ECOLOGY & HYDROLOGY, UK (UKCEH) – PIC: 897953251

UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology (UKCEH) is one of the world's leading bodies for research within the terrestrial and freshwater sciences. UKCEH leads research to support responsible environmental management, and is an independent, not-for-profit research institute with 350 scientists providing the data and insights that researchers, governments and businesses need to create a productive, resilient and healthy environment. UKCEH scientists that will engage with PARC have been central to a number of high profile national and international programs to assess the health and environmental risks of pollutants. These include the development of work around legacy and emerging pollutants, e.g. heavy metals, PBDEs, PFOS and rodenticides, as well as pharmaceuticals, nanomaterial and microplastics. This includes everything from developing and standardizing analysis and testing techniques for OECD and ISO; fate and exposure assessments for existing and emerging substances with ECHA and EFSA; modelling of nanomaterials transport in river catchment and soils; modelling engineered nanomaterial bioavailability and utilising transcriptomic, metabolomic and metal ion biology approaches to identify chemical mixture effects, right through to meeting UK obligations to UNECE Long-range transport modelling and reporting. The team involved in PARC have access to State of the art research facilities for ecotoxicological testing and measurements of toxic effects ranging from gene expression changes, sublethal endpoints, to impacts on populations and communities, including multi-generational and long-term mesocosm assessments. UKCEH has analytical laboratory accredited to ISO17025:2005 experience in environmental sample analysis from all environmental media and tissues, for: organics (PFOS, Pesticides, Polymers and plastics additives, PBDEs, PCBs etc), nutrients and metals (including stable isotope work, ion speciation and nanomaterial assessments), and micro plastics (FTIR and Pyrolysis GC).

54- ENVIRONMENT AGENCY, UK (EA) – PIC: 998712001

The Environment Agency is a non-departmental public body sponsored by the UK Government's Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (Defra). It is the primary public body for environmental regulation within England. The Environment Agency has over 10,000 staff and an annual budget of over £1 billion, which makes it the largest environmental protection agency in Europe. The principal aims of the EA are to protect and improve the environment, and to promote sustainable development. The EA is responsible for protecting and improving the ecological status of water bodies under the Water Framework Directive. It also plays a central role in delivering the environmental priorities of central government through its functions and roles.

EA staff also monitor river water quality by surveying, collecting and analysing thousands of water samples every year. The EA also collects information and data on ecology and hydrology across England and Wales. The Environment Agency has policy and research expertise as well as local environmental management and regulatory duties. The Environment Agency has a partnership agreement with the Health and Safety Executive to provide technical input on environmental matters under the UK REACH and CLP Regulations, and also provides similar support to the Department of the Environment, Food and Rural Affairs on Persistent Organic Pollutants.

The EA has specific ongoing work in relation to considerations for the future regulation of PFAS with a Risk Management Options Analysis currently being undertaken. As well as developing our own methods for PFAS analysis over recent years, we are also the lead organisation for the NORMAN network activity in 2021 on PFAS analytical exchange and in 2022 on TOP assay method comparisons. The Chemical Assessment Unit at the EA has also undertaken specific studies on groups of endocrine disrupting chemicals. Both of these areas link to initial projects in Task 4.2.

The Environment Agency has recently invested in the development of innovative tools such as non-target screening for environmental samples (water and complex matrices; biota and sediment) and has ongoing projects linked to effects-based analysis e.g. metabonomics linked to pesticide exposure in

freshwater invertebrates.

For Tasks 5.1 (Toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern), Task 5.2 (Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling), Task 5.3 (Quantitative systems toxicology and development of New AOPs), Task 6.3 (Review of risk assessment methodology) and Task 6.4 (Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies), the activities of all of these overlap closely with the activities undertaken by our Chemical Assessment Unit with involvement in UK REACH.

The EA in response to the horizon scanning commitment in the UK 25 Year Environment Plan has developed its own Prioritisation and Early warning System for England, as a result we are involved in Task 8.2.

55- HEALTH AND SAFETY EXECUTIVE, UK (HSE) – PIC: 999461811

The Health and Safety Executive (HSE) is Britain's national regulator for workplace health and safety; this includes being the competent authority for UK REACH and responsible for national Biocides and Plant Protection Products legislation. HSE's Science and Research Centre undertakes a wide range of scientific research as well as supporting HSE in incident investigation; specialisms include fire and explosions, engineering, human factors, biological, chemical and physical exposures and data analysis / modelling. The Biological Monitoring team is the leading UK laboratory for occupational biomonitoring and was actively involved in HBM4EU.

56- INSTITUTE OF OCCUPATIONAL MEDICINE, UK (IOM) – PIC: 999464818

The Institute of Occupational Medicine (IOM) is the UK's largest independent centre of expertise in occupational and environmental health, hygiene and risk. It was founded by the UK coalmining industry in conjunction with the University of Edinburgh in 1969 and is a charitable organisation dedicated to research into the working environment and its effect upon the health of workers. Our first major research programme on coalminers' lung diseases led to huge improvements in miner's working conditions and health and it became an internationally recognised bench-mark for studies in occupational hygiene and epidemiology. Over the next 20 years our applied research work spanned other industries (asbestos, chemicals, steel, textiles, construction) and other conditions (cancer, back pain, upper limb disorder, hearing loss). In 1990 the IOM became a fully independent charitable organisation with its own Board of Governors. Since independence, we have continued to develop our activities, focussing on the expanding UK and international needs for independent high-quality research in occupational and environmental health, hygiene and safety. We have a consultancy business (IOM Consulting Ltd) that provides a wide range of services in occupational health and hygiene, environmental consultancy, ergonomics, occupational psychology, and chemical analysis. We provide services, advice and research for Government, Government agencies, industry associations and individual companies. Our main research sponsors are the European Commission and EU-OSHA, UK government departments (e.g., DEFRA, HSE, Scottish Government) as well as other European government departments (e.g. BAuA in Germany, MOM in Singapore), professional or charitable organisations (e.g. IOSH) as well as industry (e.g. European chemical industry (CEFIC) and the European oil industry (CONCAWE)). The IOM was actively involved in HBM4EU, contributing to over 10 peer-reviewed publications arising from this project.

57- UNIVERSITY OF BATH, UK (UBAH) – PIC: 999842924

Ranked as the 8th best university in the UK by the Guardian University Guide 2022 and 8th by the Complete University Guide 2023, the University of Bath is one of the leading research intensive universities in the United Kingdom. This was augmented by an excellent performance in the 2014 Research Excellence Framework exercise, which assesses the quality of research in UK Higher Education Institution, with 92% of research deemed world-leading/internationally excellent. The University's current research funding portfolio is valued at over £150 million. Extremely successful for a university of its age, it ranked 179 out of approx. 1,500 in the QS World University Rankings 2023. The University boasts a robust infrastructure to support the development of research and maximise its value and impact. The central Post-Award and Project Management office is very experienced and fully compliant with the financial administration of European projects, and currently holds close to £27M in international funding. Bath has extensive experience of managing European projects, both as partner and coordinator. Current projects for which Bath is Coordinator include those in Healthcare, Transport, Space, Environment and Sustainability and span MSCA ITN, MSCA RISE, ERC Starting Grant and Horizon 2020 projects.

UBAH has been awarded 76 Horizon-funded grants as either Coordinating or Participant Institute. This includes 13 ERC grants, 27 CSA, RIA and IAs, and 31 MSCAs. The University has hosted 11 MSCA European/Postgraduate Fellows, with 4 of these projects ongoing.

UBAH has a well-established internationally leading research environment, which is supported by excellent facilities. The Department of Chemistry's research spans from fundamental chemistry to applications in catalysis, materials, healthcare and sustainable chemical technologies. 99% of the department's submitted research activity was ranked as 'world-leading' or 'internationally excellent' in the most recent Research Excellence Framework (REF2021). Dept of Chemistry hosts excellent advanced analytical infrastructure that will be utilised in PARC, including GC & LC-MS/MS: QqQ, QTOFs, TOF, NMR, sample prep laboratory for liquid and solid matrices.

58- UNIVERSITY OF ABERDEEN, UK (UNIABDN) – PIC: 999929448

Founded in 1495, the University of Aberdeen is the third oldest in Scotland and the 5th oldest in the English-speaking world. We are a community of over 700 researchers and around 15,000 students representing more than 130 nationalities. Our foundational purpose, reaffirmed in our Aberdeen 2040 strategy is to be open to all and dedicated to the pursuit of truth in the service of others. Aberdeen 2040 commits us to be inclusive, interdisciplinary, international and sustainable. Our research generates new insights in medicine, science and engineering, law, business, social sciences, arts and humanities. Announced in 2020, the Times Higher Education World University rankings 2021 confirmed our top 200 position and place us 15th in the UK for citations performance. We build capability and capacity through interdisciplinary collaboration and engagement with stakeholders across government, industry and community to ensure we build sustainable partnerships that tackle major societal challenges. The University of Aberdeen has been actively involved in European projects since Framework 3 and has, to date, been successful in participating in more than 700 grants funded through various European sources. Within Horizon 2020, the University of Aberdeen secured 73 awards including examples within the Marie Curie ITN, COFUND, RISE, NIGHT and Individual Fellowship schemes.

The Institute of Medical Sciences (IMS) is the flagship research institution of the University. Its mission is to lead and support biomedical research within the School of Medicine, Medical Sciences & Nutrition, coordinating with the other biomedical research institutes at the Foresterhill campus. In the last 12 months, staff at the IMS raised £30 million in research funding and published 415 peer-reviewed papers. The IMS is housed in dedicated buildings on the Foresterhill Health Campus, situated on the central site of the state-of-the-art Aberdeen hospitals, boasting one of the largest medical campuses in Europe. Partners in the research programmes REEF, PROTECTED and FREIA have been/are housed in the IMS.

59- THE UNIVERSITY OF BIRMINGHAM, UK (UOB) – PIC: 999907526

Founded in 1900, the University is one of the leading research-based universities in the United Kingdom; the breadth of research expertise is a distinctive characteristic of the University. The last UK Research Excellence Framework in 2014 confirmed that 87% of the University's research has global reach, meaning it is recognised internationally in terms of its originality, significance and rigour. Birmingham is 90th in the 2022 QS World University Rankings, cementing our position in the top 100 universities globally and placing us 14th out of the 24 Russell Group universities to feature in the ranking.

The University of Birmingham has extensive experience of EU collaboration and partnerships and in-depth expertise of Framework Programme matters including management, reporting and auditing. The University has been involved in 315 FP7 projects, 358 projects in H2020 and 33 projects in Horizon Europe, including projects in negotiation; it is ranked 18th for project participation amongst Universities in FP7, according to the Commission's final FP7 monitoring report (2015). Within this, UoB has been involved in:

	FP7	H2020 (as of Dec 2021)	Horizon Europe June 2022
Collaborative projects	112 (24 as lead)	126 (31 as lead)	13 (2 as Lead)
MSC ITN/DN	31 (19 as lead)	35 (14 as lead)	1 (1 as Lead)
MSC Fellowships	82	129	12
ERC	17 (14 as lead)	46 (38 as lead)	2 (2 as lead)
Other	73	22 (8 as lead)	5

The University is invested into strong interdisciplinary collaborations, across its five Colleges and beyond, to make real and measurable progress at solving critical problems of our times. A strategic mission of UOB is to build competencies in research and education across all relevant disciplines that together can address the public health implications of pollution, including exposure to harmful chemicals. For that reason, the key people involved in this PARC proposal participate in five work packages (WPs 1, 2, 5, 6 and 7) and as such the UoB team involves experts in both science and governance from Colleges of Life & Environmental Sciences, Medical & Dental Sciences, and Arts & Law. This same collaborative team contributes to global initiatives that include the Environment Care Consortium (www.environmentcareconsortium.org), the Solve Pollution Network (www.w.solvepollution.iu.edu), a significant (€20 million) H2020 Precision Toxicology project (www.precisiontox.org), the EU research infrastructure for FAIR (nano)safety data (www.nanocommons.eu), and numerous chemoinformatics projects (e.g., NanoSolveIT, CompSafeNano, SCENARIOS etc.), by applying state-of-the-art scientific advancements with governance expertise to identify and pursue effective interventions that transform human and environmental health protection.

60- UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON, UK (UCL) – PIC: 999975620

UCL has a global reputation for excellence in research and is committed to delivering impact and innovations that enhance the lives of people in the UK, across Europe and around the world. UCL was identified by the UK Research Excellence Framework as the top university in the UK for research strength and UCL is consistently placed in the global top 20 across a wide range of university rankings

(currently joint 8th in the QS World University Rankings).

UCL's total competitively awarded research income annually stands at an impressive € 530 million, of which 10% is European funded research & innovation. UCL is one of the leading recipients of European Framework Programme grants, with 74 Horizon Europe projects, over 600 Horizon 2020 projects and 700 projects funded during the Seventh Framework Programme (FP7). This includes over 160 ERC grants and over 240 MSCA projects in H2020 and Horizon Europe.

2.3 Resources to be committed

Table 2.3.d: Summary effort table

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	Total PMs per participant
1-ANSES	109.00	44.40	1.00	27.20	49.35	62.75	27.00	2.54	7.28	330.52
1.1-INSERM	-	4.50	-	1.50	204.00	17.00	3.00	9.50	3.00	242.50
1.2-INRAE	-	-	-	26.25	36.05	2.00	-	0.90	2.14	67.34
1.3-CEA	-	-	-	9.07	-	-	-	-	-	9.07
1.4-INERIS	-	-	-	16.00	17.30	16.00	-	1.50	2.10	52.90
1.5-CNRS	-	-	-	3.87	29.50	-	-	-	-	33.37
1.6-INRS	-	-	-	9.00	9.60	3.00	1.50	-	-	23.10
1.7-ONIRIS	-	-	-	7.60	-	11.00	-	-	1.00	19.60
1.8-IRSN	-	-	-	-	2.00	6.00	-	-	-	8.00
1.9-OFB	-	-	-	2.30	-	2.00	-	-	-	4.30
1.10-BRGM	-	-	-	9.50	-	-	8.00	-	3.80	21.30
1.11-LNE	-	-	-	1.00	-	-	-	-	5.10	6.10
1.12-CSTB	-	-	-	6.00	-	12.00	-	-	-	18.00
1.13-EHESP	6.00	-	-	13.50	-	0.50	-	-	-	20.00
2-SpF	4.00	2.00	0.50	61.90	-	-	-	-	3.00	71.40
3-EAA	4.90	3.50	5.50	9.50	-	2.00	-	-	-	25.40
3.1-AGES	-	-	3.00	-	-	15.00	-	-	-	18.00
3.2-AIT	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3.3-BNN	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.50	-	1.50
3.4-MUI	-	-	-	16.50	19.00	2.50	-	-	-	38.00
3.5-MUW	-	-	-	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	1.00
3.6-UG-AT	-	-	-	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	1.00
3.7-UIBK	-	-	-	-	21.20	-	-	-	-	21.20
3.8-UMIT	-	-	2.00	-	-	-	-	-	2.00	4.00
3.9-UNIVIE	-	-	-	14.20	40.00	-	3.00	-	7.00	64.20
4-VITO	5.20	-	1.00	37.00	-	28.00	30.25	-	-	101.45
4.1-KU Leuven	-	-	-	6.40	2.60	-	-	-	-	9.00
4.2-DOMG	4.00	1.50	2.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	7.50
4.3-UH	-	-	-	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	1.00
4.4-PIH	-	-	-	7.00	-	-	-	-	-	7.00

4.5-OVAM	-	-	-	5.50	-	-	-	-	-	5.50
4.6-ISSeP	-	-	-	14.20	-	11.00	12.00	2.50	4.00	43.70
4.7-UAntwerpen	-	-	-	18.89	42.00	18.00	-	-	-	78.89
5-SCIENSANO	0.40	-	-	10.50	24.00	51.00	-	-	5.88	91.78
5.1-UGent	-	-	-	-	15.75	11.00	-	-	-	26.75
5.2-EV-ILVO	-	1.00	-	2.00	-	-	2.10	-	-	5.10
5.3-VUB	-	-	-	-	25.00	18.00	-	-	-	43.00
6-CIPH	1.10	0.50	1.00	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	3.60
6.1-IMROH	-	-	-	2.50	-	-	2.00	-	1.00	5.50
7-MOH-CY/SGL	1.10	0.50	1.00	1.50	-	1.35	-	-	-	5.45
7.1-SHSO	-	-	-	0.50	-	-	-	-	-	0.50
8-MU	4.40	3.00	2.50	54.00	13.00	46.00	59.40	20.00	55.00	257.30
8.1-SZU-CZ	-	-	-	8.00	-	-	-	-	-	8.00
8.2-VSCHT	-	-	-	3.50	-	-	-	-	3.50	7.00
8.3-OU	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
8.4-JU	-	-	-	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	1.00
9-UZIS	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.90	-	-	0.90
10-DEPA	1.50	0.50	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.00
10.1-AU	-	-	-	25.40	15.00	22.90	-	2.30	4.64	70.24
10.2-DTU	-	-	-	-	29.00	22.00	-	1.50	-	52.50
10.3-REGIONH	-	-	-	9.00	-	7.00	-	-	2.00	18.00
10.4-UCPH	-	-	-	9.00	-	-	-	-	1.00	10.00
10.5-SDU	-	-	-	3.50	31.34	4.00	-	-	-	38.84
11-HB	1.20	0.50	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.70
11.1-SOM	-	3.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.00
11.2-UT	-	-	-	-	-	18.00	-	-	-	18.00
12-EEA	3.00	15.00	13.00	-	-	-	-	2.00	-	33.00
13-THL	0.10	-	-	3.25	-	-	-	-	-	3.35
13.1-SYKES	-	-	-	8.10	-	4.50	-	2.00	-	14.60
14-TTL	1.25	0.50	1.00	9.80	0.50	11.00	-	3.75	-	27.80
14.1-FFA	-	-	-	1.50	-	-	-	-	-	1.50
14.2-Tukes	-	-	-	-	-	3.00	-	-	-	3.00
14.3-UOULU	-	-	-	1.80	-	-	-	-	-	1.80
15-UBA	3.69	5.20	3.00	82.85	-	30.00	4.00	8.00	2.50	139.24
15.1-BfG	-	-	-	14.00	10.00	-	-	-	-	24.00
15.2-UFZ	-	-	-	30.00	53.25	22.00	8.00	-	-	113.25
15.3-IPA	-	-	-	18.50	-	-	-	-	5.35	23.85
15.4-UKOLD	-	-	-	-	-	15.00	-	-	-	15.00
15.5-UOS	-	-	-	-	-	2.00	-	-	-	2.00
15.6-KUM	-	-	-	3.32	-	-	-	-	-	3.32
16-BfR	4.50	16.25	1.50	-	71.50	-	-	-	-	93.75
16.1-Fraunhofer	-	-	-	14.20	6.80	5.00	-	-	-	26.00
16.2-KIT	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
16.3-IUF	-	-	-	-	18.00	-	-	-	-	18.00

16.4-IfADo	-	-	-	-	8.00	4.00	-	-	-	12.00
16.5-MLU	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
16.6-UKL	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
16.7-TUB	-	-	-	-	21.10	-	-	-	-	21.10
16.8-UKON	-	0.50	-	-	7.50	-	-	-	-	8.00
16.9-TiHo	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
16.10-UHC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
17-NPHC	1.00	5.50	15.10	7.00	32.20	-	-	-	3.00	63.80
18-UI	1.00	1.00	1.00	3.50	8.00	1.00	-	-	-	15.50
19-MOH	1.00	0.50	1.00	13.00	-	-	-	-	-	15.50
20-ISS	1.70	2.50	1.00	9.88	26.00	26.00	3.00	1.70	-	71.78
20.1-ICPS	-	-	-	-	-	3.85	-	-	-	3.85
20.2-CNR-IRSA	-	-	-	13.00	-	-	-	-	-	13.00
20.3-IRFM	-	-	-	6.00	12.00	7.00	-	14.00	1.50	40.50
20.4-IUSS	-	-	1.60	-	-	5.50	-	15.80	-	22.90
20.5-UMIL	-	-	-	0.75	7.36	-	-	-	-	8.11
20.6-UNINA	3.00	-	1.00	0.50	-	-	-	3.25	-	7.75
20.7-UNIPD	-	-	-	0.50	-	18.50	-	-	-	19.00
21-RSU	1.16	0.50	1.0	12.25	-	2.00	-	-	0.22	17.13
21.1-UL	-	-	-	3.86	-	-	-	-	-	3.86
22-NPHSL	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.25	-	-	-	-	15.00	18.25
23-LSMU	-	-	-	6.40	-	2.00	-	-	-	8.40
24-LNS	1.50	0.50	1.75	37.50	-	9.50	-	-	8.50	59.25
24.1-LIH	-	-	-	-	2.00	-	-	-	-	2.00
24.2-LIST	-	-	-	-	-	7.00	-	-	-	7.00
24.3-UniLU	-	-	-	7.00	-	-	6.00	2.70	-	15.70
25-RIVM	4.80	0.50	2.00	-	11.00	46.45	-	19.15	-	83.90
25.1-KWR	-	-	-	1.00	-	3.65	1.18	-	-	5.83
25.2-TNO	-	-	-	1.00	-	7.29	4.43	-	-	12.72
25.3-RUMC	-	-	-	7.25	-	1.00	-	-	-	8.25
25.4-UL-LACDR	-	-	-	-	45.00	41.20	10.10	1.35	-	97.65
25.5-UU-IRAS	-	-	-	35.50	6.00	38.40	12.50	11.45	5.00	108.85
25.6-VUA	-	-	-	15.50	4.50	1.00	-	0.50	-	21.50
25.7-WR	-	-	-	1.16	6.56	4.73	0.54	16.18	6.00	35.17
25.8-WU-TOX	-	-	-	-	6.57	18.47	-	0.86	-	25.90
26-NIPH	1.70	0.50	1.00	19.54	24.00	28.00	-	-	1.90	76.64
26.1-IMR	-	-	-	-	8.00	-	-	-	-	8.00
26.2-STAMI	-	1.50	3.00	5.40	9.00	25.50	-	-	5.38	49.78
26.3-NILU	-	2.00	-	6.00	2.00	2.00	-	4.50	-	16.50
26.4-NIVA	-	-	-	-	10.00	7.00	5.50	0.80	-	23.30
26.5-NMBU	-	1.40	-	1.10	2.70	-	-	0.50	10.30	16.00
26.6-NVI	-	-	-	-	9.00	-	-	-	-	9.00
26.7-UNN	-	-	-	0.25	-	-	-	-	0.74	0.99
27-NIOM	1.30	1.50	1.00	8.90	-	6.00	-	-	-	18.70

27.1-IEP-NRI	-	-	-	-	8.80	5.00	-	-	-	13.80
27.2-UG-PL	-	-	-	1.00	12.89	14.47	4.10	4.00	-	36.46
27.3-WULS-SGGW	-	-	-	5.50	-	-	-	-	-	5,50
28-FMUL	0.20	1.00	4.50	1.00	-	5.00	-	1.45	4.50	17.65
28.1-PL	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
28.2-UM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
29-INSA	6.00	13.00	34.50	19.40	26.00	13.00	-	-	34.43	146.33
29.1-APA	1.00	0.50	3.50	-	-	-	-	-	-	5.00
29.2-DGS	-	1.00	-	-	-	1.00	-	2.00	-	4.00
29.3-ENSP	-	2.00	1.50	2.00	-	9.00	-	-	4.00	18.50
29.4-UC	-	-	-	-	-	11.70	-	-	-	11.70
29.5-UAVR	-	-	2.50	-	11.22	3.15	-	-	2.40	19.27
30-SZU-SK	3.10	0.50	1.00	4.75	-	-	-	-	4.50	13.85
30.1-UK	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.00	1.00
31-JSI	0.50	0.72	1.50	34.25	-	20.50	17.00	-	3.16	77.63
31.1-GeoZS	-	-	-	1.00	-	10.70	-	-	-	11.70
31.2-NIB	-	-	3.50	1.00	41.00	-	-	-	-	45.50
31.3-NIC	-	-	1.50	-	8.00	-	-	2.75	-	12.25
31.4-ULFFA	-	-	-	5.25	12.00	-	-	-	1.00	18.25
31.5-MFUM	-	-	-	-	1.00	-	-	-	-	1.00
32-NIJZ	4.40	1.94	5.50	14.71	-	15.60	-	-	6.00	48.15
32.1-OI	-	-	-	-	-	6.00	-	-	-	6.00
32.2-NLZOH	-	-	-	0.20	-	0.30	-	-	0.10	0.60
32.3-ARSO	-	-	-	10.23	-	-	-	-	-	10.23
32.4-UKCMB	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
33- CSIC	0.40	-	-	28.27	21.60	60.00	-	-	13.49	123.76
33.4-ULPGC	-	-	-	0.25	-	-	-	-	-	0.25
33.2-UNAV	-	-	-	-	33.00	-	-	-	-	33.00
33.3-UGR	-	-	-	19.44	-	14.00	-	-	-	33.44
33.4-UPO	-	-	-	-	14.00	-	-	-	-	14.00
34-ISCIH	4.80	0.50	1.00	36.75	25.50	16.00	-	-	33.53	118.08
34.1-EASP	-	-	-	12.50	-	-	-	-	-	12.50
34.2-FISABIO	-	-	-	3.49	-	-	-	-	2.00	5.49
34.3-FINBA	-	-	-	-	-	9.00	-	-	-	9.00
34.4-FNS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5.40	5.40
34.5-IISPV	-	-	-	1.00	45.00	33.00	30.00	7.95	-	116.95
34.6-INSST	-	-	-	2.49	-	-	-	1.00	-	3.49
34.7-UCLM	-	-	-	3.00	-	8.00	-	-	-	11.00
34.8-UPV/EHU	-	-	-	8.00	-	-	-	-	-	8.00
35-SEPA	1.20	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.20
35.1-UGOT	-	-	-	-	-	10.00	-	-	-	10.00
35.2-KI	-	-	-	-	1.00	9.50	6.00	-	2.00	18.50
35.3-ULUND	-	-	-	12.50	-	5.00	-	-	-	17.50

35.4-ORU	-	-	-	12.30	-	-	-	9.20	-	21.50
35.5-RISE	-	-	-	-	-	12.00	-	-	-	12.00
35.6-SU	-	-	-	1.00	-	48.00	-	-	-	49.00
35.7-KEMI	3.00	-	1.00	-	-	15.00	-	-	-	19.00
35.8-IVL	-	-	-	13.00	-	6.00	-	6.75	-	25.75
35.9-SLV	1.00	0.50	1.00	-	-	-	-	0.25	-	2.75
35.10-SLU	-	-	-	23.50	27.00	20.00	-	16.05	-	86.55
35.11-UMU	-	-	-	1.00	-	-	-	10.25	-	11.25
35.12-UU	-	-	-	-	34.60	-	8.00	7.00	-	49.60
36-AUTH	3.30	25.50	10.00	3.50	22.00	50.00	8.00	63.50	3.00	188.80
36.1-EFET	-	-	5.50	4.50	-	-	-	3.40	-	13.40
36.2-GCSL	3.00	5.00	19.00	-	-	-	-	-	2.95	29.95
36.3-NKUA	-	-	13.00	14.00	-	-	-	7.25	-	34.25
36.4-UOC	-	-	3.50	3.00	17.00	-	-	12.70	-	36.20
37-BPI	-	-	2.50	28.50	41.30	40.00	-	-	6.20	118.50
38-FOPH	1.80	0.50	2.00	5.00	-	1.00	-	-	-	10.30
39-AGROSCOPE	-	-	-	-	-	1.00	-	-	-	1.00
40-UNISANTE	-	-	-	6.80	-	1.50	-	-	-	8.30
41-EAWAG	-	-	-	18.00	27.00	15.50	-	-	-	60.50
42-ETHZ	-	-	-	-	24.00	-	-	-	-	24.00
43-EMPA	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	12.50	-	12.50
44-FOEN	-	-	-	-	-	6.00	-	-	-	6.00
45-USI	-	-	-	0.40	-	2.00	-	-	-	2.40
46-UNIBAS	-	-	-	-	-	24.00	-	-	-	24.00
47-SECO	-	-	-	0.25	0.10	0.30	-	-	-	0.65
48-ECHA	-	24.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	24.00
49-EFSA	-	8.00	-	-	-	3.00	1.00	-	-	12.00
50-UKHSA	3.90	0.50	1.00	9.40	7.00	6.00	-	-	-	27.80
51-BUL	-	-	-	-	-	6.00	-	1.75	-	7.75
52-Cefas-Defra	-	1.00	-	-	1.09	-	-	0.75	-	2.84
53-UKCEH	-	-	-	2.40	0.80	2.60	-	-	-	5.80
54-EA	-	-	-	1.00	-	-	-	0.85	-	1.85
55-HSE	-	-	-	2.00	-	-	-	-	-	2.00
56-IOM	-	-	-	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	1.00
57-UBAH	-	-	-	1.00	-	-	-	-	-	1.00
58-UNIABDN	-	-	-	1.00	0.25	-	-	-	-	1.25
59-UOB	3.00	12.00	1.00	-	9.60	10.00	16.40	-	-	52.00
60-UCL						3.00				3.00
Total PMs	215.10	219.41	191.45	1 250.11	1 526.98	1 372.35	294.91	322.08	308.49	5 700.89

Table 2.3.e: Other major cost items (travel, equipment, infrastructure, goods and services)

1 - ANSES	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	73 779	26 190€ for travel and subsistence costs to attend consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 6 meetings in WP1 (5 070€) - 1 person to attend 5 meetings in WP2 (4 380€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP3 (830€) - 1 person to attend 3 meetings in WP4 (2 490€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP5 (2 120€) - 2 persons to attend 2 meetings in WP6 (4 800€) - 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP7 (3 550€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP8 (1 890€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP9 (1 060€) Provision for travel and subsistence of 30 GB members to the GB meeting (24 900€) Provision for travel and subsistence for National Hub coordinators, Chemical leaders and methodology leaders temporarily allocated to ANSES under T2.1 (16 600€) Travel and subsistence to attend conferences (3 000€) Provision for travel and subsistence of ethics advisors in T1.4 (1 660€) Travel and subsistence costs to attend conferences for WP5 (1429€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	236 071	Digital project management tool (130 000€) Organisation costs of consortium meetings (82 500€): launch event (80 000€) and WP5 annual meeting as WP co-leader (2 500€) Provision for fees for external experts in ethics under T1.4 (18 571€) Consumables under WP5 (5 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	11 428	
Total	319 135	
1.2 – INRAE	Cost (€)	Justification
Equipment	60 000	HCA confocal system (WP4)
Other Goods, Works & Services	65 036	Consumables costs for lab work in WP5: Antibodies, cell culture, molecular cell, T5.1.a (42 607€), T5.2.a (22 429€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	21 000	
Total	146 036	
1.4 – CEA	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	10 400	Consumables costs for lab work in WP4: Task 4.3.4
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 950	
Total	13 350	
1.7 – ONIRIS	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	7 700	Travel costs to attend consortium meetings:

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP4 (3550€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP6 (830€) - 1 person to attend 3 meetings in WP9 (2490€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	12 500	Consumables costs for lab work in WP4 and WP6: small laboratory devices (pipettes, cartridges, columns, filters, tubes, gloves), solvents, analytical standards in WP4: T4.3.3 (1 250), T4.3.4 (1250€) and WP6: T6.2.2 (10 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	20 200	
3.2 – AIT	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 950	Travel and subsistence costs for consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP5 (2 120€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	2 950	
3.3 – BNN	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 490	Travel and subsistence costs for consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP8 (1 660€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	2 490	
3.4 – MUI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	48 850	Consumables costs in WP4: liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry analysis will be performed to generate reference data for databases, to establish and validate workflows, and to verify the usefulness of developed workflows and identification tools. The claimed costs will cover expenses for reference standards, solvents, lab ware, chromatographic and extraction columns, as well as other spare parts and consumables (21 600€, T4.3.1 - 9 000€, T4.3.3 - 9 000€, T4.3.4 – 2 600€, T4.3.5 – 1 000€). Consumables costs in WP5: in vitro experiments to assess immunomodulatory properties will be performed using human cells/cell lines. The costs will cover expenses for media and supplements, antibodies, nucleic acid purification kits and qPCR reagents, reference standards, solvents, lab ware, chromatographic and extraction columns, as well as other spare parts and consumables. (27 250€, T5.1.a - 6 850€, T5.2.a - 20 400€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	5 920	
Total	54 770	
3.5 – MUW	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 490	Travel and subsistence costs for consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€)

		- 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP4 (1 660€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	2 490	
3.6 – UG-AT	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 660	Travel and subsistence costs for consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meetings in WP4 (830€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	1 000	Consumables costs for lab work in WP4: all day lab commodity materials, small la items (sealings, chromatographic columns, spare parts, glassware, tubes, vials, electrodes, etc.), solvents, gases, other chemicals
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	2 660	
3.9 – UNIVIE	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	11 130	Travel and subsistence costs for consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 3 persons to attend 2 meetings in WP4 (2 660€) - 5 persons to attend 3 meetings in WP5 (3 490€) - 2 persons to attend 2 meetings in WP7 (3 320€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP9 (830€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	54 500	Consumables costs for WP4 T4.3.1: sample preparation material, chromatographic columns, MS-grade solvents, gases for operating mass spectrometers (3000€) T4.3.3: chromatographic columns, MS-grade solvents, gases for operating mass spectrometers (2000€) T4.3.4: chromatographic columns, MS-grade solvents, gases for operating mass spectrometers (5000€) T4.3.5: reference standards (analytical grade), isotopically-labeled standards, MS-grade solvents, gases for operating mass spectrometers (2000€) Consumables costs for WP5 T5.1a: tissue culture and molecular biology reagents and kits, plastic and glassware, gases for operating incubators (20000€) T5.3.2: tissue culture and molecular biology reagents and kits, plastic and glassware, gases for operating incubators (7500€) T5.3.4: tissue culture and molecular biology reagents and kits, plastic and glassware, gases for operating incubators (15000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	65 630	
4.1 – KU Leuven	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	19 170	Bioinformatics costs (Genomics Core), occupational study in WP4 (5 170€) and in WP5 (14 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	7 660	

Costs)		
Total	26 830	
4.7 – Uantwerpen	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods & Services	102 625	<p>Consumables costs for WP4:</p> <p>Task 4.1.2: Chemicals, analytical reference standards, solvents, SPE and analytical columns, maintenance instrument (5000€)</p> <p>Task 4.1.3: Chemicals, analytical reference standards, solvents, SPE and analytical columns, maintenance instrument (2000€)</p> <p>Task 4.2.4: Exposure containers, vials, filters, pumps, reagentia, tubes, analytical reference standards, solvents, LC columns, maintenance instrument (25000€)</p> <p>Task 4.3.1: Purchase of SWBs, recipients for wastewater sample collection, chemicals, analytical reference standards, solvents, SPE and analytical columns, maintenance instrument (5000€)</p> <p>Task 4.3.3: Chemicals, analytical reference standards, solvents, SPE and analytical columns, maintenance instrument (5000€)</p> <p>Task 4.3.4: Chemicals, analytical reference standards, solvents, SPE and analytical columns, maintenance instrument (5000€)</p> <p>Task 4.3.5: Chemicals, analytical reference standards, solvents, SPE and analytical columns, maintenance instrument (5000€)</p> <p>Consumables costs for WP5:</p> <p>Task 5.2a: Chemicals, custom zebrafish feeds, plastic consumables for zebrafish embryo and juvenile exposures, kits and products for molecular and biochemical analyses, histopathology, consumables for zebrafish housing, maintenance of zebrafish housing systems, exposure and analysis equipment (26816€)</p> <p>Task 5.2b: Chemicals, purchase and maintenance of zebrafish transgenic lines, plastic consumables for zebrafish embryo exposures, kits and products for molecular and biochemical analyses, consumables for zebrafish housing, maintenance of zebrafish housing systems, exposure and analysis equipment (12682€)</p> <p>Task 5.3.2: Computer hardware, licenses for software packages, molecular and biochemical meta-analyses to support AOP development (5606€)</p> <p>Consumables costs for WP6:</p> <p>Task 6.1.1: Computer hardware, licenses for software packages, molecular and biochemical meta-analyses to support AOPN and IATA development, chemicals and consumables for the development of test methods for inclusion in IATAs (4721€)</p> <p>Task 6.1.2: Chemicals, plastic consumables for in vitro and zebrafish embryo exposures, kits and products for analyses, consumables for zebrafish housing, maintenance of zebrafish housing systems, exposure and analysis equipment (10000€)</p>
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	6 180	
Total	108 805	
5 – SCIENSANO	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	12 820	<p>Travel and subsistence costs for consortium meetings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP1 (1 060€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP4 (1 890€)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP5 (1 060€) - 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP6 (4 800€) - 1 person to attend 5 meetings in WP9 (4 010€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	86 667	<p>Consumables costs in WP4: Standards, reagents, glass and plastic ware related to sample preparation and analysis in T4.2.4 (14 400€)</p> <p>Consumables costs in WP5: Cells and cell culture media, additives and plastic ware, microscopic slides, chemicals and reagents, kits etc for genotoxicity research + Transcriptomic analyses in T5.1a (20 000€); cells and cell culture media, additives and plastic ware, chemicals and reagents + Transcriptomic analyses in T5.3.1 (15 000€)</p> <p>Consumables costs in WP6: Cells and cell culture medium, additives and plastic ware, microscopic slides, chemicals and reagents, kits etc for genotoxicity research in T6.1.3 (20 000€)</p> <p>Maintenance of equipment in relation to LC, GC or ICP-MS (as a function of the compounds to be analyzed) (16 667€)</p>
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	98 887	
5.2 – EV-ILVO	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	7 100	<p>Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP2 (2 120€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€) - 2 persons to attend 2 meetings in WP7 (3 320€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	7 100	
5.3 – VUB	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	75 000	Consumables costs in WP5 and WP6: purchase of cell culture media, growth factors, reagents, disposables, kits, arrays etc. for liver (T5.2a (37 500€) and genotoxicity (T6.1.1 (37 500€) research.
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	8 690	
Total	83 690	
6 – CIPH	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 890	Travel and subsistence costs for 1 person to attend 2 consortium meetings in WP1 (1 890€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	830	
Total	2 720	
6.1 – IMROH	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	6 870	<p>Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€) - 2 persons to attend 2 meetings in WP7 (3 320€)

		- 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP9 (1 890€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	6 870	
7 – MOH-CY/SGL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	8 250	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP1 (5 020€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP6 (2 400€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	5 000	
Total	13 250	
7.1 – SHSO	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 060	Travel and subsistence costs for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (1 060€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	3 500	Consumables for lab work in WP4: T4.1.1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	500	
Total	5 060	
8.2 – VSCHT	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	5 070	Travel and subsistence costs for travel consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€) - 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP9 (4 240€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	8 000	Consumables for lab work in WP4: Laboratory consumables (chemicals / solvents, material for sample preparation, standard reference materials), consumables for instrumentation used etc. T4.2.4 (5 000€), T4.3.3 (1 500€), T4.3.5 (1 500€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	13 070	
8.3 – UO	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	830	Travel and subsistence costs for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	830	
8.4 – JU	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 660	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	1 200	Consumables costs for lab work in WP4: chemicals and material for chemical analysis and in vitro tests: solvents and additives, standards for analysis, HPLC columns, SPE disks, media for in vitro tests, small laboratory utensils, plastics, liquid nitrogen. T4.3.1 (400€), T4.3.2 (400€), T4.3.5 (400€)

Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	–	
Total	2 860	
9 – UZIS	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 720	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (1 060€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP7 (1 660€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	2 720	
10.4 – UCPH	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	12 000	Costs consumables for carrying out various analyses in WP4: GCxGC-MS analyses T4.3.3 (2 000€); T4.3.4 (2 000€); T4.3.6 (2 000€) and SFC-MS analyses T4.3.3 (2 000€); T4.3.4 (2 000€); T4.3.6 (2 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	9 220	
Total	21 220	
11 – HB	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 890	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	1 890	
13 – THL	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	3 410	Fieldwork preparation: consumables related to sampling of human biospecimens necessary for the future analysis of contaminants for targeted studies and general survey (human biomonitoring studies and health examination surveys) in WP4 (T4.1.1)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 890	
Total	5 300	
14.1 – FFA	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	3 000	Human biomonitoring sampling consumables in WP4 (T4.1.1) for nutrition study including small children (urine samples and adults
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	830	
Total	3 830	
14.2 – Tukes	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	3 230	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP6 (2 400€)
Remaining purchase		

costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	3 230	
15.6 – KUM	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	8 320	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP4 (1 890€) - 1 person to attend 10 meetings in WP9 (5 600€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	6 000	Consumables in WP4 : lab chemicals, tips, tubes, microsampling devices (VAMS, DBS), Instrument consumables (argon, sample cups), etc. T4.1.2 (1 000€), T4.3.1 (5 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	14 320	
16.1 – Fraunhofer	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	5 810	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP4 (3 320€) - 1 person to attend 3 meetings in WP6 (2 490€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	25 000	Consumables costs in WP4 and WP5: Cell culture medium, growth factors, reagents for MNT, HPRT assay, mitotox assay, infrastructure and logistic for sampling, and consumables for sampling. T4.2.4 (5 000€), T5.1.a (15 000€), T6.1.2 (5 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	3 490	
Total	34 300	
16.3 – IUF	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	41 700	Consumables costs in WP5.2.a: Chemicals; stem cell culture medium; growth factors for stem cell maintenance, neural induction and neuronal differentiation; antibodies, multi-well plates suited for imaging; NHNP cells (Lonza) for the neurosphere assay; SynFire Kit (NeuCyte) for the hNNF assay; Microelectrode Array (MEA) plates; plasticware; consumables for cell banking.
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 890	
Total	43 590	
16.4 – IfADo	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	12 000	Consumables costs in WP5.1.a: The consumables are required for purchasing and cultivating human hepatocytes, test chemicals, antibodies, culture media and sera.
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 890	
Total	13 890	
16.6 – UKL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 060	Travel and subsistence costs for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP5 (1 060€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		

Costs)		
Total	1 060	
16.7 – TUB	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	27 293	Consumables costs in WP5.1.a: Reagents, chemicals, HPLC columns, solvents for chromatography, columns for combiflash, glass material, plastic material
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 890	
Total	29 183	
16.8 – UKON	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	25 700	Consumables costs in WP5.1.a: Reagents for cell culture (hPSC) (13 700€); Reagents for toxicological test (12 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 890	
Total	27 590	
16.10 – UHC	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 060	Travel and subsistence costs for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP5 (1 060€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	1 060	
17 – NPHC	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	82 554	Consumables costs in WP5: Reagents, consumables, kits, cell culture, T5.1.a. (52 320€), T5.3.2 (15 117€), T5.3.3 (15 117€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	7 190	
Total	89 744	
20.1 – ICPS	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	3 230	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 2 persons to attend 2 meetings in WP6 (2 400€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	1 000	Model developments, including kinetic, exposure and hazard models, will be done in WP 6.2 in close cooperation with the model implementation strategy of task 8.3. This combines approximately 30-50 different models. Model implementation ensure coherent model use in a European dimension via web-based interfaces and cloud computing (legacy from the EuroMix project). Additionally, the source codes of all separate models will be posted on repositories such as Zenodo to ensure FAIR model principles and flexibility for future refinements of the models by the scientific community.
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	4 230	
20.5 – UMIL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	3 230	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings:

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 2 persons to attend 2 meetings in WP6 (2 400€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	7 700	Consumables costs in WP5.1.a: culture media and supplements, disposable plastics for cell cultures, molecular biology reagents, antibodies
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 950	
Total	13 880	
20.6 – UNINA	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	4 610	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP1 (2 950€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP8 (830€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	5 357	Costs for publications for 1 to 2 papers which theme is in relation to T8.1.1 "Translate EC SSbD criteria & methodology towards operationalization"
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	9 967	
21 – RSU	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	7 840	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 3 meetings in WP1 (2 490€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€) - 2 persons to attend 2 meetings in WP6 (2 400€) <p>WP4: fieldwork: travel to hotspots (enterprises) in the country, sample collection. For occupational studies, samples should be collected during all working week, sometimes before and after shift. There is need collect not only biological samples, but work environment samples as well (2 120€)</p>
Other Goods, Works & Services	4 400	Consumable for T4.1.1 (4 000€) and T6.3 (400€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	286	
Total	12 526	
21.1 – UL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 859	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (1 029€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	714	Consumables (reagents, tubes, micropipette tips, microfilters) for T4.2.3
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	343	
Total	2 916	
22 – NPHSL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	8 390	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 3 meetings in WP1 (1 890€)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€); - 1 person to attend 7 meetings in WP9 (5 670€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	8 390	
23 – LSMU	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	6 690	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (1 060€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€); - 1 persons to attend 4 meetings in WP6 (4 800€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	600	
Total	7 290	
24.1 – LIH	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	9 000	Consumables costs in WP5: T5.1.a (4 500€), T5.2.a (4 500€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 660	
Total	10 660	
25 – RIVM	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	23 190	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings (13 190€): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 7 meeting in WP1 (4 840€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP3 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP5 (1 060€) - 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP6 (4 800€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP8 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP9 (830€) Travel and subsistence costs to attend conferences for WP6 (10 000€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	87 000	Costs for publications under WP6 (9 000€, 6000€ for T6.1.1 and 3000€ for T6.2.1) as WP co-leader Cloud computing for T6.2.1 (10 000€) Costs for organisation of workshops under T8.1.1 (3 000€) Consumables for T5.2a (30 000€) and for T6.1.1 (35 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	110 190	
25.3 – RUMC	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	4 430	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (1200€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP6 (2 400€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	11 200	Consumables costs in WP4 and WP6: standards, chemicals, disposables, T4.1.1 (7 000€), T6.2.1 (4 200€)
Remaining purchase	3 000	

costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	18 630	
25.4 – UL-LACDR	Cost (€)	Justification
Equipment	100 000	Equipment costs in WP5 and WP6: microscopy, culture facility, flow cytometry, sequencing, T5.2.a (37 500€), T5.3.1 (15 000€) T6.1.2 (47 500€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	117 000	Consumables costs in WP5 and WP6: Cell culture, molecular biology, microscopy, transcriptomics, chemicals, disposables, plastics, T5.2.a (47 000€), T5.3.1 (40 000€) T6.1.2 (30 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	9 500	
Total	226 500	
26.6 – NVI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	20 000	Consumables costs in WP5.1.a: MATTEK Inserts, SMI 100 FT; MIVO single flow Chips for organ on a chip; Consumables for cell culture (flasks, medium, plates, transwell inserts), Bio Plex 27-cytokine assaysn, Consumables for chemical analysis (column, solvents, SPE clean-ups etc.), Instrumentation
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 890	
Total	21 890	
26.7 – UNN	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 950	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meetings in WP4 (830€); - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP9 (2 120€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	2 950	
27 – NIOM	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	8 000	Insurance for medical experiment according to Polish law, cloud computing programmes for modelling of exposure WP1.1 (5 000€), WP6.2.1 (3 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	9 120	
Total	17 120	
27.1 – IEP-NRI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	14 000	Consumables costs in WP5.1.6: laboratory materials and reagents
Travel and subsistence	7 010	Travel and subsistence costs for travel for consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP5 (1 940€); - 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP6 (4 240€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	6 440	
Total	27 450	

27.2 – UG-PL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	13 240	Travel and subsistence costs for travel for consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP5 (1 060€) - 1 person to attend 6 meetings in WP6 (7 200€) - 2 persons to attend 2 meeting in WP7 (3 320€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP8 (830€)
Equipment	10 000	Equipment costs for 4 PC Workstations to perform analysis in WP6.1.1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	23 240	
27.3 – WULS-SGGW	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 660	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	–	
Total	1 660	
28 – FMUL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	9 080	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (1 060€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP2 (2 120€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP5 (830€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP6 (2 120€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP8 (830€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP9 (2 120€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	9 080	
28.2 – UM	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 660	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	–	
Total	1 660	
29 – INSA	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	53 210	Travel and subsistence costs to travel to consortium meetings (29 510€): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 7 meetings in WP1 (4 840€) - 2 persons to attend 2 meetings in WP2 (4 240€); - 1 person to attend 3 meetings in WP3 (2 490€), - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP4 (1 890€), - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP5 (2 120€); - 1 person to attend 6 meetings in WP6 (7 200€),

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 11 meetings in WP9 (6 730€) Travel and subsistence costs to attend Stakeholder Forum meetings, International Board meetings, SYNNet Forum meetings in WP3 (1 660€) Travel and subsistence costs to attend conferences under WP3.3 (1 290€) Budget for travel and subsistence to the Stakeholder Forum meetings and SYNNet Forum meetings, temporarily allocated to WP3 co-leaders (20 750€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	35 000	Consumables for activities in WP5 (20 000€): T51.a (10 000€) and T5.2a (10 000€) Budget for the organisation of WP3 annual meetings temporarily allocated to WP3 co-leader (15 000€)
Equipment	32 000	Depreciation costs for computers for WP3.3 (10 000€) Laboratory equipment for Task 5.1a (22 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	25 820	
Total	146 030	
29.2 – DGS	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	4 060	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP6 (2 400€), - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP8 (830€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	4 060	
29.3 – ENSP	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	24 200	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meetin in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP2 (1 660€), - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP3 (830€), - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€), - 2 persons to attend 5 meetings in WP6 (12 000€), - 1 person to attend 10 meetings in WP9 (8 050€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	24 200	
30 – SZU-SK	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	8 160	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 7 meetings in WP1 (4 380€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€), - 1 person to attend 3 meetings in WP9 (2 950€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 000	
Total	10 160	
30.1 – UK	Cost (€)	Justification

Travel and subsistence	2 720	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP9 (1 890€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	2 720	
31.2 – NIB	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	66 750	Consumables costs in WP5: Consumables such as plastic ware, chemicals, media for growth of bacteria and cell cultures, maintenance of fish, food for fish, S9 mix, specific antibodies, preamplification kits, assays for qPCR, etc., T5.1a (16 600€); T5.1b (16 150€), T5.2a (24 000€) T5.2b (10 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 720	
Total	69 470	
31.3 – NIC	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	3 550	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP3 (830€), - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP5 (1 060€), - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP8 (830€)
Equipment	7 400	Depreciation costs for computer cores for the Azman Computing centre for activities in WP5
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	10 950	
31.4 – ULFFA	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	24 000	Consumables costs in WP4 (4 000€) and WP5 (20 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 490	
Total	26 490	
31.5 – MFUM	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	830	Travel and subsistence costs for 1 person to travel to 1 consortium meeting in WP1 (830€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	830	
32.1 – OI	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	3 230	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 2 meeting in WP6 (2400€),
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	108	
Total	3 338	

32.2 – NLZOH	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	4 890	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€), - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP6 (2 400€), - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP9 (830€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	4 890	
32.4– UKCMB	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	830	Travel and subsistence costs for 1 person travel to 1 consortium meetings in WP1 (830€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	830	
33.1 – ULPGC	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 660	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	1 660	
33.4 – UPO	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	27 545	Consumables costs in WP5.2.b: Reagents, chemicals, media, plastic
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 890	
Total	29 435	
34 – ISCIH	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	79 660	Consumables costs in WP5 (30 000€): Consumables to carry out the projects in WP5 related to BPA (metabolic, thyroid, carcinogenicity), endocrine disruption-zebra fish embryos, and other projects with zebra fish and stem cells: T5.1a (10 000€): T5.2b (20 000€) Training sessions organisation costs under WP9 temporarily allocated to WP co-leader (47 160€) WP9 annual meetings organisation costs temporarily allocated to WP co-leaders (2 500€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	14 800	
Total	94 460	
34.2 – FISABIO	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	3 550	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€) - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP9 (1 890€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	2 000	Consumables and laboratory material for T4.2.4
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	5 550	
35.11 – UMU	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	3 755	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€) - 2 persons to attend 1 meeting in WP8 (2 095€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	6 337	Annual costs for the use of high performance computing and software for WP8 (8.2.2). This is in relation to the development of the early warning system.
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)		
Total	10 092	
35.12 – UU	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	91 667	Consumables costs for WP5 : Chemicals and reagents for experimental activities (cell culturing, staining, cell painting, imaging, epigenomics, microfluidics); T5.1b (3 000€); T5.2a (58 667€); T5.2b (30 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	8 440	
Total	100 107	
36.1 – EFET	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	3 320	Travel and subsistence costs for travel to consortium meetings (3 320€): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP3 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP8 (830€)
Other Goods, Works & Services	4 400	Cost to perform sampling for WP4 and WP8 (2 400€) Consumables for activities in WP4 and WP8 (1 000€) Cost to access scientific libraries in relation to T4.2.2 activities (1 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	500	
Total	8 220	
36.2 – GCSL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	29 450	Travel and subsistence costs for 1 person to attend 6 consortium meetings in WP1 (4010€); Costs for travel and subsistence for participants to attend Stakeholder Forum meetings, International Board meetings, and SYNNet Forum meetings allocated to WP3 Co-Leader (25 440€)

Other Goods, Works & Services	4 000	Costs for the organisation of Stakeholder Forum meetings, International Board meetings and of SYNnet Forum meetings allocated to WP3 Co-Leader
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	17 420	
Total	50 870	
36.4 – UOC	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	28 000	Consumables costs for WP5: T5.1.a (14 000€); T5;1.b (14 000)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	10 380	
Total	38 380	
37 – BPI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	100 880	Consumables costs for WP5: Consumables for in vitro testing, molecular biology, lab materials, chemicals, etc; T5.1a (41 400€); Consumables for bioassays, analytical measurements, T5.1b (13 200€); T5.2b (46 280€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	55 890	
Total	156 770	

Annex PARC SRIA

**STRATEGIC RESEARCH AND INNOVATION
ACTION PLAN**

September 2022 – V2

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T4.1 Human Biomonitoring – 9 PROJECTS

A4.1.1 Design, alignment and fieldwork of HBM studies – 5 PROJECTS

S4.1.1.1 Development of supporting materials for harmonized EU HBM conduct

No project submitted at present.

S4.1.1.2 General population survey – 1 PROJECT

P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO

Project Title	General population human biomonitoring survey		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	GenHBMSurvey		
Project Manager	Liese Gilles liese.gilles@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	Susana Pedraza Diaz ISCIIE PARC <PARC@isciii.es>	ISCIIE	Spain
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	81
PARC Workpackage number	WP 4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.1.2
Project Id	P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

An EU-wide human biomonitoring (HBM) survey targeting the general population will be organized. This General survey (PARC Aligned Studies) focusses on 3 age groups i.e. children (6-11 years), teenagers (12-17 years) and adults (18-39 years) and builds on existing HBM capacities in the member states by means of upfront harmonization to the maximum extent possible. The survey will collect samples between May 2023-April 2026. The results are expected by Y6-Y7 of PARC (2027-2028).

Objectives of the PARC General Survey are:

To obtain HBM data which are comparable between EU countries/regions.

To calculate European exposure values on a pooled EU dataset.

To identify exposure determinants on a pooled EU dataset.

To study exposure - effect associations.

Substances put forward per age group (based on the HBM4EU 3rd priority list and PARC stakeholder consultations):

Children	Teenagers	Adults
PFAS	PFAS	PFAS
Pesticides	Pesticides	Pesticides
Bisphenols	Bisphenols	Bisphenols
Metals	Arsenic species	Metals
OPFRs	Phthalates & substitutes	Mercury

Phthalates & substitutes Mercury

**substance groups in bold are common for all 3 age groups.*

The basic monitoring program will be complemented with “add-ons”. Participation/implementation in an add-on is optional. Add-ons are meant to incorporate research aspects or innovative aspects into the general survey as small-scale proof-of-concepts, e.g. NTS or SS on a subsample, application of innovative sampling methods (silicone wrist bands, VAMS, dried blood spot), collection of personal environmental samples to investigate exposure sources and analysis of effect biomarkers.

This project is of relevance for all regulatory frameworks restricting the production, use, environmental release, and environmental/dietary/consumer product exposure of chemicals, as well as frameworks targeted to environmental and human health protection.

Demonstrating the effectiveness of existing policies is essential for maintaining public trust and securing the ongoing collaboration of industry and stakeholders. Europe’s zero-pollution agenda should depart from an understanding of how the bodies of European citizens are polluted with synthetic chemicals and make reducing the chemical body burden and associated health impacts a key priority. Human biomonitoring conducted through harmonised approaches and quality assured analytical methods at European scale generates coherent data on the internal exposure of the European population to priority substances in different European regions. Human biomonitoring results from HBM4EU and PARC provide a baseline and time trends against which to track the efficacy of the European Green Deal's Zero Pollution Action Plan and the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (PARC HBM data will for instance feed into CSS indicators). Comparing human biomonitoring data from across Europe can highlight regional differences linked to variations in environmental quality, climate, diet, consumer behaviour and lifestyle. This project will also advance methodologies for assessing health effects due to exposure to chemical mixtures through real-life co-exposure assessment. Identifying exposure to chemicals of emerging concern, including substitutes for banned substances, in the population can serve as a warning of undetected risk. Measuring effect biomarkers and studying associations with health outcome data will provide insight into the extent to which chemicals and substitutes have an impact on health and support chemical grouping approaches and avoidance of regrettable substitution. An understanding of population exposure and the exposure of vulnerable groups against health-based human biomonitoring guidance values, provides the basis for effective cross-silo risk management aimed at reducing impacts on health.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will prepare and conduct a harmonized HBM surveillance programme for chemical exposure of European citizens through alignment of national (or regional) HBM initiatives. The project will deliver comparable HBM data for prioritized substances with EU wide coverage for children (6-11y), teenagers (12-19y) and adults (18-39 y) for period 2023-2026. The General survey aims for a minimum sample size per age group of N = 3300 collected across minimally 11 countries distributed over the 4 regions (North, East, South, West).

Data gaps filled by this project are expected to include:

- New internal aggregate and mixture exposure data and reference values for prioritized chemicals for all four geographical regions of Europe.
- Spatial and temporal trends in chemical exposure.
- Increased understanding of the sources and pathways of human exposure.
- Associations of exposures with (early) adverse effects and health impact.
- Identification of emerging chemicals of concern.

Innovations resulting from this project are expected to include new/improved analytical methods to cover the needs of the HBM survey, improvement of the analytical capacities for biomarker measurements of European laboratories, and proof-of-principle of self- and/or non-invasive sampling tools.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

HBM data from EU countries are scattered; within this project HBM surveys across Europe are harmonized and the data made FAIR. The project will support the discoverability, accessibility and availability of high

quality, reliable and coherent datasets on human exposure to chemicals at European level, supporting the sharing and reusing of human biomonitoring data across legislative silos. The HBM data can support time trend development and evaluation of policy efficacy (eg. effect of REACH restrictions on exposure levels). Baseline human exposure data also allow comparison with international chemical monitoring programs such as NHANES and CDC. In addition, data on internal exposure generated by human biomonitoring provide a complete picture of human exposure and can be used to enhance chemical risk assessment by providing information on actual human exposure via multiple exposure pathways likely to be regulated under separate policy silos. An understanding of the contribution that different exposure routes make to the overall exposure (taking into account differences in exposure modifiers, such as age and gender, as well as profession) provides the starting point for deciding on risk management measures under legislative silos. As such, this project contributes to the ‘one substance, one assessment’ approach included in the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. In addition, identifying upstream exposure routes in various material flows - including in consumer products, via diet and in the occupational setting - can inform targeted efforts to minimize exposure by eliminating chemicals from material flows. Over the long term, the availability of information on exposure to chemicals in specific material flows, including products, will stimulate the production of safer chemicals, products and materials.

The results of the general population survey can be used by different stakeholders:

- PARC project partners, Governing Board members (responsible for RA at EU/national/regional level), EU agencies, and the scientific community: input for exposure science, modelling, risk assessment, health impact assessment; monitor the impact of implementation of the EU’s chemicals strategy for sustainability
- Policy makers/regulators/OECD, WHO, UN: deriving policy recommendations for reduction of exposure, use of articles, chemicals production and release; evaluating the efficiency of regulation or the need for further action.
- Citizens: better understanding and awareness of exposure and risk; recommendations for lifestyle and prevention.
- Industrial hygienists, occupational physicians, workers, trade unions: release to the environment via production processes; worker exposure and protection.

Key words: Human biomonitoring (HBM), internal exposure levels, determinants of exposure, exposure-effect associations

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project contributes to the aim of T4.1 to perform an HBM survey targeting the general population which will form the basis of a well aligned HBM surveillance programme for chemical exposure of European citizens and will generate baseline internal exposure data. This project will deliver the statistically derived internal exposure reference values that will allow for evaluation of spatial and temporal trends in chemical exposure and monitoring of the impact of regulations and the EU’s chemicals strategy for sustainability.

By collecting and generating HBM data for PARC priority chemicals and exposure scenarios across Europe, the project will contribute to SO2 “European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint R&I program to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals risk assessment”. The project will support the understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases, to the reduction of environmental and human health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals, and as such to the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen’s health, and awareness of citizens and professionals about risks of chemical exposures.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Other T4.1 projects:
 - Further analysis of the data generated within HBM4EU
 - Derivation of health based HBM guidance values
 - Roadmap to explore the links between prioritized chemical substances exposures and health concerns
 - Link human biomonitoring studies to health examination and dietary surveys
 - Implementation of a sentinel surveillance system

- Targeted surveys
- Occupational surveys
- Feasibility study to evaluate occupational exposure in general surveys
- Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe
- T4.2: analyse associations between sources, external exposure data and internal exposure
- T4.3: development and proof of concept of innovative tools and methods
- WP1: indicators to monitor progress and impact
- WP2: priority setting and uptake into policy
- WP3: communication and dissemination of results
- WP5: identification of effect biomarkers relevant for specific chemicals, age groups and health outcomes
- T6.2 projects: internal exposure data can be used to feed into aggregate and internal-external exposure modelling, mixture risk assessment, and health impact assessment/burden of disease
 - Strategy for aggregate exposure from general life and occupational exposures
 - Developing, performing and validation of source to dose modelling including selected case studies
 - Refinement and development of PBPK models for risk assessment
 - Real-life mixtures assessment
 - Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies
 - Inventory of HIA data for PARC priority chemicals
 - Case studies on health impact assessment
 - Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators
- WP7: FAIR and sustainable storage of HBM data; innovative data analysis
- WP8: Early Warning System
- WP9:
 - inventory of HBM/HES studies (T9.2) that will support the identification of the opportunities in the HBM survey
 - laboratory networks (T9.1) as an essential key in the QA/QC programme organization (T9.3) and implementation as well as in the analysis of the samples
 - training activities (T9.4) that can cover issues related to all the study phases (sampling, chemical analysis, statistical analysis, etc.)

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU legacy: the project will build further on experiences, results, materials, and networks developed within HBM4EU
- European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) projects
- National/regional studies participating in the general survey

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- **D4.3; D4.8; D4.12:** Progress report on the general survey (M36; 48; 60)
- **D4.13:** Concluding report summarizing the outcome of all studies for a future monitoring approach (M81)

Expected Project Reports:

This project will deliver a statistical analysis plan (M48) and the results of the data analyses with interpretation and discussion will be summarized in a progress report and published in scientific peer-reviewed publications by different responsible partners (M70-M74).

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- Final selection of countries/studies included in the general survey + implementation plan (M8)
- List of mature innovative methods to implement in selection of HBM surveys (M10)
- Finalization of study design for the HBM surveys (M12)
- Finalization of sample collection for general survey (M48)
- Finalization of analysis of exposure biomarkers in the general survey (M53)
- Database general survey complete (M56)

Partners List:

Core partners: VITO (BE), ISCIII (ES), SPF (FR), UBA (DE), LNS (LU), RegionH (DK), INSA (PT).
 Partners involved in statistical analysis of the data: ANSES (FR), AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), EASP (ES), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), INSERM (FR), IPA (DE), ISCIII (ES), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), LNS (LU), LSMU, MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIPH (NO), PIH (BE), Sciensano (BE), SLU, SPF (FR), SZU-SK (SK), UBA (DE), UGR (ES), UH (BE), UNIVIE (AT), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 828.4 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 205.5 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 9 800 000 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 0 €

S4.1.1.3 Targeted surveys

No project submitted at present.

S4.1.1.4 Occupational surveys – 4 PROJECTS

P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL

Project Title	Feasibility study to evaluate occupational exposure in general surveys		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	OccupFeasability		
Project Manager	Tiina Santonen tiina.santonen@ttl.fi	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health	Finland
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	18M
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1
Project Id	P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The main idea of this project is to develop an approach to investigate if it is possible to analyse the data from HBM4EU general population studies to identify occupationally exposed groups, and to evaluate how general (adult) population studies can identify possible higher exposure of occupationally exposed groups. This will be done for selected HBM4EU priority chemicals, which are cadmium, PAHs and bisphenols that has been measured in HBM4EU aligned studies in adult population.

Thus, **the main scope of the project** is to analyse the existing (HBM4EU) biomonitoring data for its further use in the identification of occupational exposures.

The project is designed as a feasibility study with limited duration and resources. **The main output** will be a review and recommendations on the use of occupation-related information from general population

studies:

- Is it possible to identify some occupational groups and their exposure from the general population data? How much occupational exposure may contribute to explain the highest percentiles of exposure values in general population surveys?
- How should information on occupations be analysed in general population studies?
- Can analysis of population surveys be used to screen possible less well-known occupational exposures?

In addition, the project will provide recommendations for future general population studies for the collection of data relevant for the identification of occupational exposure from general population data.

Overall, **the project aims** to improve the use of HBM data to explore predictor variables that impact the exposure levels measured and thus contribute also to some of the variability observed. The results of the feasibility project can be used in general population HBM studies planned to be performed under WP4. Thus, one of the main user group of the project results will be researchers performing general population HBM studies.

The regulatory processes the project can support are mainly REACH and OSH processes. When general population HBM data is used for the exposure assessment it is important to understand the main sources of exposure. When performing general population risk assessment, potential confounding effect of occupational exposure needs to be identified and eliminated, if present. On the other hand, the data may contribute to the occupational exposure assessment under REACH or OSH processes. When setting reference values (or BGVs under ECHA OEL process) to distinguish occupational exposure from background (environmental, consumer) exposure, it is important to ensure that the background levels are not confounded with occupational exposure. As this is designed as a feasibility study to proof the concept there is currently no need for alignment the timeline with policy's agenda.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main output will be recommendations on the use of occupation-related information from general population studies:

- Is it possible to identify some occupational groups and their exposure from the general population data? How much occupational exposure may contribute to explain the highest percentiles of exposure values in general population surveys?
- How should information on occupations be analysed in general population studies?
- Can analysis of population surveys be used to screen possible less well-known occupational exposures?

In addition, the project will provide recommendations for future general population studies for the collection of data relevant for the identification of occupational exposure from general population data.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

If successful, the information generated in this project may contribute to the occupational exposure assessment under REACH or OSH processes. It is also expected to contribute to the design and analysis of future general population HBM studies.

Key words: occupational exposure, HBM, general population, aligned studies, Cd, BPA, PAH

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

T4.1 on human biomonitoring aims at measuring total exposure to priority compounds in humans considering the different sources, chemical fates & exposure pathways. The current project uses HBM data and tries to understand how much occupational exposure contributes to general, adult population total exposure to different compounds and whether it is possible to identify possibly new occupational exposure sources from general population survey datasets.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is highly linked to other activities within WP4, specifically aligned studies planned under WP4. It can provide recommendations to be considered in PARC aligned HBM studies. Thus, PARC WP4 projects it is closely linked include:

- Project: General population HBM survey
- Project: Assessment of exposure through a sentinel surveillance system

- Project: Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe

It also links to WP6 and especially to activities related to aggregated exposure assessment from different sources (task 6.2.1), WP7 on FAIR data and can also possibly feed in to WP8 toolboxes.

Links outside PARC

Outside PARC it is closely related to HBM4EU, since it will analyse the data collected/generated within HBM4EU.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

None identified at present

Expected Project Reports:

Report on the occupational exposure in general population surveys: analysis of existing data and recommendations for future general population studies (M18, October 2023). This deliverable describes the availability of occupational information in the existing general population datasets and gives an overview on the usefulness of this data in the identification of potential occupational exposed groups and final recommendations for the future studies.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- 1: Relevant general population studies with occupational information identified, studies for further analysis selected and agreements with data owners made (M7)
- 2: Data analysis completed, preliminary conclusions and recommendations made (M12)
- 3: Final results and recommendations for future studies (M18)

Partners List:

TTL (FI), SpF (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), LSMU (LT)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 31/10/2023

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 7.3 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 1.3 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 2 500 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 2 500 €

P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven

Project Title	Assessment of exposure through a sentinel surveillance system		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Sentinel System		
Project Manager	Liesbeth Gillisen Liesbeth.gilissen@kuleuven.be	KULeuven	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	81
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.1.4
Project Id	P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven		

Status: Planning phase

Summary of the project

A sentinel surveillance system has already been used successfully to collect information on occupational exposures to, for example, hazardous chemicals. In a sentinel surveillance system, a sentinel network is formed which consists of motivated occupational physicians in an occupational setting. Sentinel approaches are being increasingly used in occupational health and have been found a valid method to collect epidemiological health data.

This project aims to explore, design, and implement a European sentinel surveillance system to support human biomonitoring (HBM) surveys in the general adult population via occupational physicians (OPs)/nurses. It aims to assess the total exposure (environmental and occupational) of a representative sample of European working adults to a selection of chemicals.

14 EU countries have shown an interest to implement a sentinel surveillance system in their country: Belgium as lead, Portugal, Italy, Czech Republic, Latvia, France, Spain, Poland, The Netherlands, Denmark, Luxembourg, Switzerland, Sweden, and Greece (BPI, Benaki Phytopathological Institute).

We will follow a step-wise approach:

1. Mapping exercise: inventory of opportunities and barriers in each country in the 1st year (→Go/ No GO)
2. Setting up the sentinel system on a national level, network building
3. Collect data, health related measurement, and samples in a subgroup (countries participating in the general population survey for adults of PARC, with an adequately implemented system, infrastructure for analysis, and national co-funding)

Main expected outputs of the project

The evaluation of the sentinel system as a tool in an occupational setting to assess environmental exposure, next to occupational exposure.

By facilitating the recruitment of adult participants for the PARC General population HBM survey under PARC and the collection of data and samples, this project will contribute to all objectives and regulatory frameworks that are of relevance for the General population HBM survey.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project will support the Health & Safety at Work – EU Strategic Framework (2021-2027), which aims to maintain and improve the high health & safety standards for EU workers and will help to prepare for new crises and threats. By creating data on aggregated exposure from multiple sources the project supports EU zero pollution agenda, EU one-substance-one evaluation goals and exposome network/projects.

Key words: *Under development*

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

PARC DoA describes the link under task 4.1: *“An HBM survey targeting the general population will form the basis of a well aligned HBM surveillance programme for chemical exposure of European citizens and will generate baseline internal exposure data... In addition, targeted HBM surveys will address specific research and policy questions related to vulnerable groups (young children, pregnant women), highly exposed groups (workers, hotspot residents) or time trends.”*

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- T4.1.1b General population HBM survey
- T4.1.1d Occupational HBM surveys
- T4.1.1d Feasibility study to evaluate occupational exposure in general surveys
- T4.1.1a Development of supporting materials for the HBM surveys (SPOs, health related measurement, questionnaires)
- T 4.1.3 Roadmap to explore the links between prioritized chemical substances exposures and health concerns (questionnaire and protocol for health measurements/sample collection)
- T4.1.5 Design of a sustainable EU-wide HBM surveillance system

- WP 3.2 Communication, dissemination and synergies:
 - Awareness raising campaigns will be carried out by using targeted communication materials on the impact of environmental and occupational exposures on human health.
- WP 9.4 Training:
 - An online training module is needed for the recruited occupational physicians/nurses. This online training module will contain information about the sentinel system, recruitment of workers, sample collection, questionnaires, chemicals, etc.

Links outside PARC

Several participating countries have already used the sentinel system in an occupational setting. In Belgium, the PROBE (Hazardous chemical Products Register for Occupational use in Belgium) was set up to assess the occupational exposure of workers to a selection of hazardous chemicals. In the “Peilstation Intensief Melden” (PIM) study (The Netherlands), a group of motivated and trained occupational physicians (OPs) reported occupational diseases by using a sentinel surveillance system. The French Surveillance Medicale des Risques (SUMER) study, a national cross-sectional survey of occupational risks, collected good-quality exposure data through the sentinel system.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Not identified at present

Expected Project Reports:

Design of proof-of-concept (M12)

Implementation of proof-of-concept in general population HBM survey finalized (M60)

Partners List:

KU Leuven (Belgium), INSA (Portugal), ENSP-UNL (Portugal), UNINA (Italy), MU (Czech Republic), RSU (Latvia), SpF (France), UGR (Spain), NIOM (Poland), RUMC (The Netherlands), AU (Denmark), LNS (Luxembourg), STM (Luxembourg), STI (Luxembourg), UNISANTE (Switzerland), ULUND (Sweden), BPI (Greece).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: Estimation under development

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 24 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: Estimation under development

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: Estimation under development

P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthCareSurvey_TTL_RUMC

Project Title	Occupational survey in the healthcare sector		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	HealthcareSurvey		
Project Manager	Tiina Santonen tiina.santonen@ttl.fi	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health	Finland
Deputy Project manager	Paul Scheepers paul.scheepers@radboudumc.nl	Radboud University Medical Centre (RUMC)	Netherlands
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	48M

PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1
Project Id	P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthcareSurvey_TTL_RUMC		

Status: Planning phase

Summary of the project

In this project we will study how working in the healthcare sector may contribute to the uptake of chemicals. Biomarkers of exposure and effect will be used to study work practices in three areas in hospital settings: hazardous medicinal products, inhalation anaesthetics and disinfection and cleaning products (biocides). The main scope of the project is to perform a cross sectional study in the hospital-based healthcare to study priority chemicals of concern by use of exposure and effect biomonitoring and contribute to further improvement of healthy and safe working conditions. The project will target the following chemicals:

- Hazardous medicinal products (including cytotoxic drugs)
- Inhalation anaesthetics
- Disinfectant and cleaning products (including biocides)

The project is designed as a cross-sectional observational study. We aim for 20-24 hospitals in 10-12 EU member states. The main output will be an assessment of exposure to prioritized chemicals based on the use of biomonitoring and supported by occupational hygiene measurements and other contextual data. In addition, the project will provide recommendations for improved work practices to secure healthy and safe working conditions.

Overall, the project aims are to introduce human biomonitoring as an approach to study both exposure and effects related to the use of chemicals in hospital-based healthcare. This will lead to more awareness and better understanding of how work practices contribute to internal exposure to chemicals and how these practices can be further improved to reduce uptake of these chemicals.

More specifically the project aims to:

1. Identify chemical exposures of concern and relevant exposure scenarios in the hospital-based healthcare;
2. Study how human biological monitoring (HBM) can inform chemical risk assessment of hazardous medicinal products, inhalation anaesthetics, disinfection products and cleaning products (biocides);
3. Contribute to the further improvement of healthy and safe working conditions
4. Study contributions from different sources of exposure, also outside work, in assessment of aggregated exposure;
5. Develop HBM-based approaches for the assessment and management of chemical exposures in hospital-based healthcare.

The regulatory processes

In 2019 it was agreed that hazardous drugs, including cytotoxic drugs, should adhere to minimum requirements for the protection of health and safety of workers, in particular those provided for in the Council Directive 98/24/EC and in the Carcinogens and Mutagens Directive 2004/37/EC (CMD). Development of a new guidance to support the implementation of safe use of hazardous medicinal products at work is currently ongoing based on a previous evaluation (European Commission, 2021). In December 2021, the European Parliament proposed to bring reprotoxic chemicals under the remit of the CMD. This will require further development of protocols for measurement of chemical exposures on the workplace, especially for periods of higher susceptibility such as during pregnancy.

Main expected outputs of the project

1. A dataset describing the current exposure to selected chemicals in approximately 20-24 hospitals in approximately 10-12 EU member states
2. An improved understanding of how current work practices in the hospital-based healthcare translate to internal exposure to selected chemicals
3. Recommendations for policy changes in line with current and new health and safety procedures and sustainability programmes on national and EU level

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

- For workers, employers, occupational hygienists and occupational physicians: better understanding and increased awareness of the potential health risk of chemical exposures;
- Recommendations for risk management leading to improved work practices
- The scientific community and primarily other partners in PARC: potential added value of HBM approach as input for risk assessment and health impact assessment
- For policymakers, EU and national regulators, EU Agencies (EU OSHA): evaluating the efficiency of current regulations and further development of these existing regulations and implementation of the new harmonised guidance on safe use of HMPs including cytotoxic drugs.

Key words: occupational exposure, hospital, risk management measures, hazardous medicinal products, cytotoxic drugs, inhalation anaesthetics, disinfection, cleaning, biocides

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

T4.1 on human biomonitoring aims at measuring total exposure to priority compounds in humans considering different sources, chemical fates & exposure pathways. The current project uses HBM data and tries to understand how much occupational exposure contributes to general, adult population total exposure to different compounds and whether it is possible to identify possibly new occupational exposure sources from general population survey datasets.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is linked to other activities within WP4, specifically aligned studies planned under WP4. It can provide recommendations to be considered in PARC aligned HBM studies. Thus, PARC WP4 projects it is closely linked include:

- Project: General population HBM survey
- Project: Assessment of exposure through a sentinel surveillance system
- Project: Occupational survey in waste management

In addition, close collaboration is made with following activities/projects within T4.1:

- T4.1.1.1 activity related to development of supporting materials for fieldwork
- T4.1.2 on QA and analytics related to selection of laboratories
- Project 4.1.3bc on roadmap from exposure to health on the selection of AOP relevant effect biomarkers
- T4.1.4 related to statistical data analyses
- T4.3 related to the testing of new innovative methods in occupational surveys

This also links to WP6 and especially to activities related to aggregate exposure from multiple sources and routes of exposure for the general population and workers (task 6.2.1) and mixture risk assessment (task 6.2.3). Since the exposure of health care personnel typically consists of mixed exposure to several compounds, the data collected can be used as a case study in 6.2.3.

Links outside PARC

There are links the following projects outside PARC:

- Previous HBM4EU occupational studies on chromates, e-waste and diisocyanates
- EU-OSHA funded project aiming to provide a practical guidance on preventing and reducing occupational exposure to HMPs, including cytotoxic drugs
- Inhalation anaesthetics study funded by the social fund of the Netherlands Federation of Academic Hospitals (Project number F2491)
- Ethanol exposure assessment study funded by the social fund of the Netherlands Federation of Academic Hospitals (Project number F2492)
- Masarykova Univerzita (MU). National network of monitoring of drugs in the hospitals and pharmacies in Czech Republic and Slovakia (see: <https://www.cytostatika.cz/>)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D4.7 Progress report on occupational surveys (to be submitted by TTL in M48).

Expected Project Reports:

Not applicable.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- Identification of study populations in different countries (M4)
- List of selected chemicals and corresponding exposure biomarkers (M8)
- List of exposure and effect biomarkers in collaboration with 4.1.3b (M8)
- Questionnaires, SOPs and information materials (prepared in collaboration with 4.1.1.1 (M10)
- Study protocol and application for ethics approval (M12)
- Online training on the implementation of the study protocols and SOPs (M14)
- Submission of the study protocol and participant documents for ethics approval (M14)
- Data Management Plan in collaboration with WP7 (M16)
- Field work with (bio)monitoring and contextual data collection completed (M32)
- Analysis of the samples completed (performed under 4.2) (M36)
- Data analysis (performed by 4.1.4) completed (M42)
- Final results and recommendations (M48)
- Information materials for workers and other stakeholders (M48)

Partners List:

TTL (FI), RUMC (NL), MU (CZ), AU (DK), UGR (ES), INRS (FR), ISS (IT), UMIL (IT), UNINA (IT), UNIPD (IT), RSU (LV), LNS (LU), SGGW (PL), ENSP (PT), HSE (UK), IOM (UK)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 63 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 12.5 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 77 500 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 7752 €

P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL

Project Title	Occupational survey in the waste management sector		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Occup_Waste		
Project Manager	Tiina Santonen tiina.santonen@ttl.fi	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health	Finland
Deputy Project manager	Susana Viegas Susana.viegas@ensp.unl.pl	ENSP-UNL NOVA National School of Public Health	Portugal
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48 M
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1
Project Id	P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP-TTL		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The European Commission adopted a new Circular Economy Action Plan - one of the main building blocks of the European Green Deal, Europe's new agenda for sustainable growth. With measures along the entire

life cycle of products, the new Action Plan aims to make EU economy fit for a green future, strengthen competitiveness while protecting the environment and provide new rights to consumers (EC, 2020). As Europe moves towards a more circular economy, the product of today will become the raw material of tomorrow. The waste management sector is expected to play a pivotal role in this development.

Based on this, an increase is expected of the number of workers involved in processes and tasks related with waste streams where the potential for circularity is high. Some of these waste streams are for instance electronics, batteries and vehicles, plastics, textiles, general household, and construction and buildings materials. The reuse and recycling of these materials could result in an increase of exposure (e.g., metals, flame retardants, phthalates) of workers involved in different steps of the waste processing chain such as collection, sorting, dismantling, shredding and further pre-processing and purification of waste components to allow their use as raw materials in different processes and industries (e.g., textile, plastics - and also PVC, furniture, construction). Additionally, the increase in waste volumes and complexity may reduce the capability of the sector to process waste safely.

In the scope of HBM4EU project an exploratory study in occupational exposures in electrical and electronic waste (E-waste) processing was developed and a study protocol using a cross sectional survey design to study worker's exposures and compare these to the exposure of non-exposed individuals preferably was implemented (Scheepers et al., 2021). This study protocol can be adapted to future European-wide occupational studies developed in the scope of PARC such as the one described here.

Overall, **the project aims** to understand waste management workers exposure to chemicals since new materials in the waste stream may pose additional risks to waste sector workers. The waste streams that will be the focus of this study are the e-waste and plastics (household and industry).

The regulatory processes the project can support are mainly REACH and OSH processes. When general population HBM data is used for the exposure assessment it is important to understand the main sources of exposure. On the other hand, the data may contribute to the occupational exposure assessment under REACH or OSH processes.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main outputs and impacts expected from the project are:

- ✓ Provide EU relevant data on chemical exposures in the e-waste and plastics (household and industrial) waste streams to be used as scientific evidence to support several actions at different levels, namely: companies and workers level, country level and, also, EU policy level for adaptation and/or create new policies if considered needed.
- ✓ Evaluate the usefulness of BM as a tool to assess complex exposures such as the ones that can happen in these occupational settings.
- ✓ Identify the project outputs value as a contribute for identifying exposure scenarios at the general population level.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The results of the survey can be used by different stakeholders:

- ✓ PARC project partners and the scientific community: input for exposure science, modelling, risk assessment, health impact assessment; monitoring of the impact of implementation of the EU OSH directives
- ✓ Policy makers, EU and national regulators, EU Agencies (EU OSHA): deriving further regulation and guidance, evaluating the efficiency of current regulations.
- ✓ Workers and trade unions, industrial hygienists, occupational physicians: better understanding and awareness of exposure and risk; recommendations for risk management.

Key words: occupational exposure, HBM, waste management, circular economy

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

T4.1 on human biomonitoring aims at measuring total exposure to priority compounds in humans considering the different sources, chemical fates & exposure pathways. The current project intends to use

mainly HBM data to evaluate workers exposure to different compounds in the waste management sector, following the approaches already used in the occupational studies of the HBM4EU.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Considering the data that will be produced by the project it can be linked to **WP2** (Knowledge management and uptake into policy) and with **WP3** (Synergies and collaborations). Also, **WP5** (Hazard Assessment), particularly with the tasks developed in the scope of characterizing AOPs and relevant effect biomarkers since the project will also integrate the Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOPs) approach to allow a better understanding of the mechanism of action of the chemicals and mixtures and to select the most suitable biomarkers of effect to be used. Within **WP4**, the project is linked to all other WP4.1 activities and projects, especially to Occupational survey on health care workers (sharing e.g. some standard operating procedures (SOPs)), on the development of survey materials (4.1.1.1), QA and analytical activities (4.1.2), statistical data analysis activities (4.1.4). In addition, the project is linked to task 4.3: Innovative sampling methods and metabolomic studies since these new methods are planned to be tested within the project.

Additionally, this project will have several linkages with WP6 (innovation in regulatory risk assessment) where the exposure to several substances will trigger multiple collaborations such as development and use of integrative models to determine and quantify the internal exposure to chemicals from different routes and sources of exposure and to combine several routes and sources of exposure and/or exposures obtained from different methodologies. The data generated within this project can be used for the assessment of risks of mixed exposure to multiple hazardous substances within waste management sector. Along the same lines, links with WP9 (capacities) will probably emerge when planning the study and also in a later stage, when the data will start to become available and used for training and capacity building purposes.

Links outside PARC

The EU-OSHA's is developing a third foresight cycle that looks at changes in work that may result from the EU's transition to a circular economy (CE) and the potential impact on occupational safety and health (OSH) (<https://osha.europa.eu/en/emerging-risks/circular-economy>). Our project, developed in the scope of PARC, will provide useful information to streamline this objective. Additionally, our project will continue the work developed in the scope of HBM4EU Project, particularly in what concerns to the E-Waste study since it intends to use the samples (biomonitoring and industrial hygiene samples) already collected and look for other substances that were not targeted in the E-Waste study (Scheepers et al., 2021). These are for instance cobalt and antimony due to their possible presence in this type of waste and the need of exposure data already recognize in the IARC evaluation developed recently (Karagas et al., 2022). Additionally, for those results of E-waste study that were not possible to be analysed in detail during HBM4EU, an extensive statistical analysis will be performed for the further refinement of waste management study design to be developed in PARC.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Deliverable D4.7: First Progress report on occupational surveys (M48).

The project results are proposed to be reported in the form of D4.7 due to M48

Expected Project Reports:

N/A

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- 1: Field work collection completed (by M27)
- 2: Analyses of the samples collected (HBM4EU and more recent sampling campaigns) completed (by M32) with (bio)monitoring, environmental monitoring (industrial hygiene samples) and contextual data
- 3: Data analysis completed (by M36)
- 4: Final results and recommendations for future studies (M48)

In addition, following landmarks are planned, namely:

- List of selected chemicals for each waste stream and corresponding exposure biomarkers, list of effect biomarkers relevant for selected chemicals

- Study protocol including standard operating procedures
- Data Management Plan in collaboration with WP7
- Online training on the implementation of the study protocols and procedures (collaboration with WP9)
- First manuscript with the main messages
- Policy brief and guidance for companies on the management of risks present at waste management
- Additional scientific publications on specialist topics

Partners List:

ENSP-UNL (Portugal); AU(Denmark); ISS (Italy); UNIPD (Italy); UMIL (Italy); UNINA (Italy); WULS (Poland); ULUND (Sweden); STAMI (Norway); AUTH (Greece); INSA (Portugal); TTL (Finland); LNS (Luxembourg); MOH-CY (Cyprus); NIOM (Poland)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)
 Expected ending date: 30/09/2025 (M42)

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 85 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 16,50 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 84 000 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 8 750 €

S4.1.1.5 Implementation of innovative methods

No project submitted at present.

A4.1.2 Laboratory analysis and quality assurance

No project submitted at present.

A4.1.3 Link exposure and health related information – 2 PROJECTS

S4.1.3.1 Propose health-based HBM guidance values – 1 Project

P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA

Project Title	Propose health-based HBM guidance values (HBM-GVs)		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA		
Project Manager	Petra Apel Petra.apel@uba.de	UBA	Germany
Deputy Project manager	<Name> <Email>	<Institute>	<Country>
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	81
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.3.1
Project Id	P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Based on the policy needs identified by HBM4EU and to be subsequently established by PARC, and the exposure biomarkers defined and specified in T4.1.2, required health-based human biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GV) for the assessment of HBM data will be derived. This assumes that sufficient toxicological and epidemiological data are available from the scientific literature or generated as part of PARC. HBM-GVs for the general population and/or workers will be derived in general according to the agreed strategy for deriving HBM-GVs (Apel et al., 2020) 1, but continuous development of the strategy is foreseen and will be considered for the values derivation.

Basically, a graduated procedure will be followed, whereby as the highest priority option, epidemiological data or a point of departure (POD) determined from a relationship between internal concentrations of the biomarker(s) of a substance and a selected critical health effect observed in humans should be considered as starting point for the guidance value derivation. Where this is not possible because of missing or conflicting study results, the second option should be examined, estimating the concentration of the substance's biomarker(s) that correspond(s) to an external toxicity reference value (TRV) set by a recognised body, preferably European. If no TRV is available, the derivation by the third option should be chosen, extrapolating and adjusting a POD identified from a toxicological animal study. In individual cases, PBPK/TK modelling may be necessary and corresponding results would then have to be made available within PARC. Cooperation with T6.2.2 is sought in this regard.

The results of the methodology workshop under HBM4EU Task 5.2 could be a basis for further refinements, as could the development of a tiered approach starting from conservative standard methods and moving to more precise methods when guidance values are exceeded. In addition, with improved data, expanded use of epidemiologic data should be advanced. Also, development needs that may arise from the OECD work on deriving occupational biomonitoring level will be identified, and collaboration with relevant initiatives in Europe and abroad (e.g., Health Canada and WHO/ILO 4) will be pursued.

Each deliverable should refer to one substance and comprise relevant toxicological and epidemiological information in a summarized form with respective references. Only the point of departure, the further derivation of the HBM-GV(s) and its/their proper application as well as the level of confidence of the derived value(s) should be presented and justified in detail. Depending on the expertise of the PARC T4.1.3 team members, some teams may work together and the working draft should be discussed first within the task. After an exchange of information and content-related coordination within the task, the refined draft deliverable should be distributed to the NHCPs for comment within PARC. In this way, a broad scientific consensus should be reached. The consultation process has already proven useful and relevant within HBM4EU to ensure the quality of the reports and to promote the application of the values. The final deliverable should ideally be also valued via a peer-reviewed scientific publication (ideally deliverable = publication). HBM GVs can then be used in T4.1.1 to interpret HBM survey results and communicate results to participants.

Regulatory process/framework

REACH and the implementation of EU regulations on food safety, plant protection products, biocides, cosmetic products, toys and occupational exposure, among others, could benefit from human biomonitoring and data interpretation by HBM-GVs. At the national level, the values can also be used for case-based investigations.

Main expected outputs of the project

Under development

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Survey data from European countries can be compared directly with the consented values, so that a harmonised risk assessment can be carried out across Europe. The data evaluation allows statements on

whether citizens or subpopulations in some regions are at risk of health effects and whether measures for risk mitigation have to be recommended.

HBM-GVs can also be used to develop impact indicators that illustrate physical exposure and possible health risks in a simple and easily accessible way, helping to inform a wider audience. The impact indicators refer in this case to the 95th percentile of selected studies.

HBM-GVs can also be used as a basis for risk assessment of mixtures, e.g. by applying the hazard index approach or mixture assessment/ allocation factors.

Key words: Under development

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

To support EU chemicals policy through the use of HBM data, it is not only essential to generate comparable and harmonized HBM data at EU level for the general population, potentially at-risk subgroups, and workers in specific occupational settings, but guidance is also needed for the interpretation of these HBM data in the context of health risks.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Providing HBM-GVs requires a multidisciplinary approach, the main connexions with other WPs or tasks are:

- Exposure indicators in 6.2.4
- PBPK/TK modelling in 6.2 and/or 5.3
- Effects and AOPs in 6.1 and/or 6.2 and/or 5.3
- Risk assessment including mixture risk assessment in WP6

Links outside PARC

- *National activities on guidance values*
- *EFSA/ECHA activities*
- *OECD activities on guidance values*
- *i-HBM activities on guidance values*

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Not identified

Expected Project Reports:

Not identified

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Not identified

Partners List:

UBA (Germany), ANSES (France), FIOH (FI), MOH-IL (IL), NIPH (Norway), RUMC (NL), Uni Oulu (FI), Unisante (CH), AUTH (Greece), NIJZ (SI)

Schedule:

Starting date: M1 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: M81 31/01/2029

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 189 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 34.2 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: not defined yet

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: not defined yet

S4.1.3.2 Identify effect biomarkers for prioritized chemicals, populations and health outcomes

No project submitted at present.

S4.1.3.3 Link HBM studies to health examination and dietary studies – 1 Project

P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO

Project Title	Roadmap to explore the links between prioritized chemical substances exposure and health concerns		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth		
Project Manager	Hardiesse Bessonneau Hardiesse.BESSONNEAU@santepubliquefrance.fr	SpF	France
	Sylvie Remy Sylvie.remy@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	For effect biomarkers : Kirsten Baken (kirsten.baken@vito.be)	VITO	Belgium
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	52
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	T4.1.3.2 and T4.1.3.3
Project Id	P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Biomonitoring studies are key in studying the link between chemical exposure and adverse health effects. This project focuses on implementation of the assessment of adverse health effects in biomonitoring, through measurement of (molecular) biomarkers of (early) effects and through standardized health outcome assessment.

- Under HBM4EU, feasibility studies to combine HBM and health examination surveys (HES) were carried out and the possibility to link survey data to health registers was assessed. In addition, traditional and novel effect biomarkers were implemented in the EU-wide HBM4EU Aligned Studies to show the added value of complementing exposure biomarkers with effect biomarkers in HBM studies to increase the weight of evidence of causal exposure-effect relations and support evaluation of potential health impact. Building further on the HBM4EU recommendations, the aim of this project is to draw the roadmap that identifies concrete actions to undertake to foster investigations between chemical exposures and health outcomes, and explain this link through biomarkers of effect. The project will be conducted in a two-step approach; I. first, the integration of standardized effect biomarker and health measurements and questionnaires in HBM surveys conducted under T4.1.1 – HBM surveys design; II. Second, a feasibility study to explore the possibility to assess past exposures to prioritized chemicals and determine effect biomarker levels from biobanked samples collected earlier in cohorts and evaluate the prospective associations with health outcomes that will be collected under PARC. A case study will be applied to a specific PARC priority substance through retrospective analysis. This will enable us to define a core strategy for linking past exposures to current health effects and establish a baseline assessment.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Roadmap for exploration of the links between HBM data and existing health outcome

- Supporting materials for PARC surveys:
 - Standardized procedures and materials for collecting health, physical activity, dietary and occupational data to include in the general HBM survey and first occupational surveys
 - Effect biomarker implementation plan for PARC surveys
 - Investigation of the links between exposure and adverse health outcomes, from analyses of biobanked samples within Health examination cohorts

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The results and data of this project are of interest to:

- PARC project partners
- Governing Board members
- EU commission and agencies
- EU national bodies
- Broader scientific community
- Policy makers and regulators

The generated information materials will provide tools for a more comprehensive and integrative biomonitoring of chemical exposure in Europe and ascertain to study relationships among risk factors, health promotion and protection behaviors, and health status.

Key words: Human biomonitoring, biomarkers of effect, health outcome assessment, Molecular epidemiology

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

T4.1-: Effect biomarkers will complement exposure biomarkers, if input to regulatory needs can be derived, to evaluate associations between chemical exposure and adverse effects (LNS, SpF, UGR, VITO). Issues related to the linkage of HBM, health examination, occupational and dietary surveys will be identified and solved with support of WP7 (RSU, SpF).

Through the activities on exposure monitoring and toxicology, the Partnership will foster a better understanding the health impacts of exposures and, thereby, indirectly contribute with evidence for health cost estimations.

This project will contribute to SO2 “European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint R&I programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals risk assessment”. The project will support the understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases, to the reduction of environmental and human health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals, and as such to the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen’s health, and awareness of citizens and professionals about risks of chemical exposures.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

This project is mainly linked to T4.1 activities:

- General Survey
- Targeted surveys
- Occupational surveys
- Definition of standardised materials (questionnaires, protocols, etc.)
- Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe
- Data management and analysis

WP2: Prioritization of substances and uptake into policy

WP7: FAIR data management and technical issues related to the linkage of HBM and HES

WP9: Inventory of HBM/HES studies that will support the identification of the opportunities in the HBM survey

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU legacy: the project will build further on experiences, results and materials developed within HBM4EU
- European Human Exposome Network (EHEN)

- OECD interdisciplinary activity 'Addressing combined exposures and effects by using Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) knowledge in combination with relevant effect-biomarkers'
- OECD expert group related to Working Parties on Hazard and Exposure Assessments (WPHA/WPEA)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

There is no specific PARC deliverable for this project. The results will feed into T4.1 deliverables

- MS10 Finalisation of study design for the HBM surveys (M12)
- AD4.1 Periodic report on available supporting materials for HBM studies (M12)
- AD4.2 Periodic report on analytical methods and measurements for exposure and effect biomarkers (M12)
- D4.3 1st Progress report on the general survey (M36)
- D4.8 2nd Progress report on the general survey (M48)
- D4.12 3rd Progress report on the general survey (M60)
- D2.22 2nd PARC sustainability report (M81) contribution with the final strategy for a sustainable and centrally coordinated HBM programme for Europe

Expected Project Reports:

Report 1: Standardized procedures and materials for collecting health, physical activity, dietary and occupational data to include in the general HBM survey and first occupational surveys (SpF, M11)

Report 2: Effect biomarker implementation plan for PARC general and occupational surveys (VITO, M12)

Report 3: Progress report on investigation of the links between exposure and adverse health outcomes, from analyses of biobanked samples within Health examination cohorts (SpF, M22)

Report 4: Roadmap for exploration of the links between HBM data and existing health outcome (SpF-VITO, M52)

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Landmark 1: Identification of effect biomarkers associated with exposure to the chemicals and age groups studied in (add ons of) the general HBM survey and first occupational surveys + implementation plan (M12)

Landmark 2: Data management plan on implementation in the HBM4EU surveys (M12)

Landmark 3: Finalization of the case study, data analysis and data transfer (M40)

Partners List:

SpF (France), VITO (Belgium), AU (Denmark), AUTH (Greece), BPI (Greece), CEA (France), IDAEA-CSIC (Spain), EAA (Austria), EHESP (France), Fraunhofer (Germany), KI/IMM KI (Sweden), INRS (France), INSA (Portugal), INSERM (France), INSST (Spain), ISCIII (Spain), ISS (Italy), JSI (Slovenia), KULeuven (Belgium), LNS (Luxembourg), LSMU (Lithuania), MU (Czech Republic), NIJZ (Slovenia), NIOM (Poland), NLZOH (Slovenia), UKHSA (England), RUMC (Netherlands), RSU (Latvia), Sciensano (Belgium), SECO (Switzerland), STAMI (Norway), TTL (Finland), UBA (Germany), Ugent (Belgium), UGR (Spain), ULPGC (Spain), UNINA (Italy), UNIPD (Italy), UOC (Greece), UOULU (Finland), USI (Switzerland), UU-IRAS (Netherlands), WULS-SGGW (Poland)

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 310 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 45 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 1 891 000 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 0 €

A4.1.4 Data Management and analysis – 1 PROJECT

S4.1.4.1 Data management

No project submitted at present.

S4.1.4.2 Data analysis – 1 PROJECT

P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO

Project Title	Further analysis of the data generated within HBM4EU		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	DataAnalysisHBM4EU		
Project Manager	Eva Govarts Eva.govarts@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.4.2
Project Id	P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Within the context of the HBM4EU project, a large range of human biomonitoring data has been generated via the HBM4EU Aligned Studies in adults, teenagers and children, occupational studies (chromium VI, diisocyanates and e-waste), the MOM-study (mercury exposure during pregnancy) and the SPECIMEN study (pesticide hotspots). Much useful information has already been obtained during HBM4EU and more publications are expected to be out soon. It is nevertheless foreseen that research questions will remain or will emerge from the data analysis, and not all the generated data are analysed. In order to make optimal use of the available HBM4EU data and use the results to feed into the design of HBM studies planned under PARC, further statistical analyses will be performed on HBM4EU data. More information can be generated on exposure sources and routes, exposure-effect and pathway analyses.

The project is of relevance for all regulatory frameworks restricting the production, use, environmental release, and environmental/dietary/consumer product exposure of chemicals, as well as frameworks targeted to environmental, human and worker health protection. Europe's zero-pollution agenda should depart from an understanding of how the bodies of European citizens are polluted with synthetic chemicals, and make reducing the chemical body burden and associated health impacts a key priority. Measuring exposure and effect biomarkers in human biomonitoring studies will provide insight into the extent to which chemicals and substitutes have an impact on health, and support chemical grouping approaches and avoidance of regrettable substitution.

Main expected outputs of the project

Output will be generated with regard to exposure sources and routes and exposure-effect and pathway analyses. More information will be obtained on exposure sources and routes by linking HBM data with external exposure (e.g. products/articles, environmental monitoring, lifestyle, food consumption patterns) data (measured, estimated or modelled), both on individual level (as gathered by the HBM studies) as well as obtained on an aggregated level within the time frame of the HBM sampling. Results on exposure-effect associations of interest for further analysis based on literature studies (evaluating experimental and epidemiological studies and information collected in Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs)). Available effect biomarker and health outcome data will be collected and possibilities will be explored to analyse exposure-effect pathways to better understand causality and to identify adverse

effects in an early stage.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The results of the data analyses planned in this project can be used by different stakeholders:

- Policy makers/regulators/OECD, WHO, UN
Feed into policies for reduction of exposure, use of products/articles, chemicals production and release; support risk assessment and mitigation for known and emerging chemicals; support evaluation of the efficiency of regulation or the need for further action.
- EC, EU agencies, member states, and the scientific community
Input for exposure and hazard evaluation, modelling, risk assessment, health impact assessment; feed into monitoring of the impact of implementation of the EU's chemicals strategy for sustainability and zero pollution action plan.
- Industrial hygienists, occupational physicians, workers, trade unions
Release to the environment via production processes; worker exposure and protection.
- Citizens
Better understanding and awareness of exposure and risk; recommendations for lifestyle and prevention.

Key words: Human Biomonitoring, HBM4EU, exposure routes, exposure-effect analyses, health effects, effect biomarkers, pathways.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The results of the project will feed into the design of HBM studies planned under PARC. This is part of the objective of Task 4.1 on further developing the HBM platform, generating new HBM data. And to the overall goal of WP4 in observing different sources, chemical fates and exposure pathways.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Links to other Work package/Tasks/Activities:

- WP2: priority setting and uptake into policy
- WP3: communication on results data analyses with regard to specific research questions
- T4.1: design of general, targeted and occupational HBM surveys
- T4.2: external exposure data
- T6.2: exposure routes (modelling) and exposure-effect associations (risk and health impact assessment)
- WP7: linking of data sources and routes, data management plan, case study HBM data, innovative data analysis
- WP9: maybe training is needed on data analysis

Links to other projects:

- P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO
- P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL
- P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_Occuphealthcare_TTL_RUMC
- P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL
- P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMHES_SpF_VITO
- P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM
- P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU legacy: the project will perform further analyses on data generated and collected within HBM4EU
- European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) projects

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The project will contribute to:

- Deliverable D7.1 Data management plan (M6)
- Milestone MS7 Establishment of working groups (M12) by establishing a statistical working group with experts on HBM data analysis.

Expected Project Reports:

This project will deliver a statistical analysis plan (M12-M18 – VITO) and the results of the data analyses with interpretation and discussion will be summarised in a progress report and published in scientific peer-reviewed publications by different responsible partners (M24-M36 – multiple partners to be defined).

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Crucial for this project is availability and accessibility of the HBM4EU data.

Partners List:

Project manager: VITO (Belgium)

Project team: AU (Denmark), AUTH (Greece), BPI (Greece), EASP (Spain), INRAE (France), INRS (France), INSA (Portugal), INSERM (France), IPA (Germany), ISCIII (Spain), ISSeP (Belgium), JSI (Slovenia), LNS (Luxembourg), LSMU (Lithuania), MU (Czech Republic), NIJZ (Slovenia), NIPH (Norway), PIH (Belgium), Sciensano (Belgium), SPF (France), SZU-SK (Slovakia), TTL (Finland), UBA (Germany), UGR (Spain), UNIVIE (Austria), UU-IRAS (Netherlands), VITO (Belgium)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05:2022

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 187.9 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 65.5 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: not determined

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: not determined

A4.1.5 Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe – 1 PROJECT

P4.1.5.a_Y1_SustainHBMSsystem_VITO

Project Title	Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	P4.1.5.1_a_Y1_SustainHBMSsystem_VITO		
Project Manager	Liese Gilles liese.gilles@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	81
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.5
Project Id	P4.1.5_a_Y1_SustainHBMSsystem_VITO		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

A long-term sustainable and inclusive HBM surveillance system for exposure to chemicals within Europe to succeed the PARC general population survey will be prepared. This system will build further on

scenarios explored and recommendations developed under HBM4EU and take lessons learned from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies and PARC general survey and innovative approaches developed under various PARC Tasks into account. In addition, experts in charge of HBM surveys conducted in Europe, the USA, Canada, Japan, South Korea and Australia will be consulted. By 2028, a final concept should be ready for implementation to guide and support the HBM survey that succeeds the general survey under PARC. The sustainable HBM system should allow to obtain truly representative and maximally harmonized exposure data for Europe to provide useful results for policy makers and to answer the information needs of citizens. The relevance of HBM results will be increased by optimisation of the number of countries and subjects to be included and samples to be collected and analysed, for instance via reduction of costs and increased efficiency of fieldwork. Harmonization will be maximized via upfront alignment of studies and application of guidelines/protocols/SOPs/supporting materials.

The sustainable HBM system will comprise the following (non-exhaustive) set of components:

- EU-wide representative (covering the four geographical areas of Europe) and harmonized HBM surveillance system with regular frequency (t.b.d.).
- Transparent prioritisation process to select chemical classes/individual chemicals and age groups, including decision support for follow-up of time trends and of early warning signals, inclusion of emerging chemicals, and uptake of advancements in sampling and analytical methods.
- Terms for inclusion of studies/cohorts (criteria and flexibility t.b.d.):
 - Time frame for sample collection
 - Age group(s)
 - Minimal number of substances to be monitored per age group and required matrix types
 - Use of SOPs, questionnaires, appropriate ethical approval and informed consent (sharing of individual level data)
 - Sample size
 - Biobanking of sample material
 - Chemical analysis performed by qualified laboratories
 - Representativeness of study population: Sex, Degree of urbanisation, SES, Geographical representativeness
- Infrastructure:
 - Laboratory network & QA/QC system
 - Guidelines & QA for study design
 - Supporting materials (SOPs, questionnaires, ..)
 - Modelling and data analysis
 - Data management (FAIR data principles)
 - Ethics

Governing and coordination structure (incl. EU and national hubs, stakeholder forum, scientific advisory board, ..) .

Specific regulatory processes/frameworks that are being addressed:

The project is of relevance for all regulatory frameworks restricting the production, use, environmental release, and environmental/dietary/consumer product exposure of chemicals, as well as frameworks targeted to environmental and human health protection. The exact regulatory processes and frameworks for which future EU wide HBM campaigns will provide input will depend on the regulatory strategies and questions that are most prominent at that specific point of time.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will deliver a blueprint for a sustainable long-term Human biomonitoring program in Europe for implementation after PARC.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The results of a European HBM surveillance system with regular frequency can be used by different stakeholders:

- Policy makers/regulators/OECD, WHO, UN
Feed into policies for reduction of exposure, use of products/articles, chemicals production and release;

support risk assessment and mitigation for known and emerging chemicals; support evaluation of the efficiency of regulation or the need for further action.

- EC, EU agencies, member states, and the scientific community
Input for exposure and hazard evaluation, modelling, risk assessment, health impact assessment; feed into monitoring of the impact of implementation of the EU's chemicals strategy for sustainability.
- Citizens
Better understanding and awareness of exposure and risk; recommendations for lifestyle and prevention.

Baseline human exposure data will be suited for comparison with international chemical monitoring programs such as NHANES and CDC.

Key words: sustainable HBM programme, Europe, Harmonized, chemical RA toolbox.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will prepare the development of a sustainable HBM surveillance programme for chemical exposure of European citizens.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Links to other Work package/Tasks/Activities:

WP4:

T4.1: general population HBM survey

T4.2 & T6.2: associations between sources, external exposure to (mixtures of) chemicals and internal exposure

T4.3: development and proof of concept of innovative tools and methods

WP2: prioritization, sustainability and exit strategy

WP3: synergies

WP5: effect biomarkers

WP7: FAIR data

WP8: early warning system

WP9: capacities and infrastructure

National Hubs: implementation of the framework

Links to other projects:

P4.1.1.1_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO

P4.1.4.1_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO

P4.1.3.2_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMHES_SpF_VITO

P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU legacy: the project will build further on experiences, results, materials, and networks developed within HBM4EU
- National/regional studies participating in the general survey
- International key players in HBM research such as CDC (NHANES), Health Canada (CHMS), Japan, South Korea, Australia
- ISES HBM working groups

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Final strategy for a sustainable and centrally coordinated HBM program for Europe [M66] to be integrated in D2.22: 2nd PARC sustainability report [M81].

Expected Project Reports:

Not applicable

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Not applicable

Partners List: UBA (Germany), LNS (Luxembourg), ISCIII (Spain), VITO (Belgium), SPF (France), INSA (Portugal), LSMU (Latvia), FOPH (Switzerland), NIPH (Norway), SZU-CZ (Czech Republic),

MOH-CY (Cyprus)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 77.5 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 6.4 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 300 000 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 0 €

T4.2 Environmental and Multisource Monitoring – 1 PROJECT

P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU

Project Title	Establishment of the overall process of environmental and multisource monitoring with the help of a pilot study addressing PFAS and endocrine disruptors		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	EDC and PFAS pilot		
Project Manager	Katrin Vorkamp kvo@envs.au.dk Valeria Dulio Valeria.dulio@ineris.fr	Aarhus University INERIS	Denmark France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.2.1
Project Id	P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU		

Status: *Planning*

Summary of the project

Establishing a process for environmental and multisource monitoring is a key component in PARC. It has the purpose of supporting the EU chemical risk assessment in relation to i) environmental ecosystems and ii) human exposure, with a strong link to human biomonitoring. Together with the prerequisite of building on existing structures and knowledge, these objectives make environmental and multisource monitoring a complex task in PARC, which needs highly optimized processes to be fully beneficial.

A pilot project focussing on per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs) was started in Year 1, with the purpose to establish and validate environmental monitoring structures, including a review of state-of-the-art methods as well as design of monitoring study for the long-term work in T4.2. This project will continue in Year 2, with a focus on the actual monitoring study to be performed, and also proceed into Year 3.

Main expected outputs of the project

Based on the preliminary study design, a detailed monitoring plan will be developed targeting i) PFAS in the freshwater environment and ii) EDCs in a multicompartment approach. This plan will include the final selection of target compounds, based on the information collected in Year 1, ensuring comprehensive analytical approaches also involving suspect and non-target screening, sum parameters (for PFAS) and

effect-based methods (for EDCs), for example in tiered approaches or linked to specific monitoring purposes (e.g. hotspots vs. background monitoring). Eventually, this plan will specify the analysis of each sample.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Pilot data for two compound groups identified as particularly problematic, EDCs and PFAS, to test and verify the application of the developed prioritisation framework (T4.2.1) on monitoring studies.

Key words: Pilot study, EDCs, PFAS, environmental monitoring, knowledge gaps, freshwater, multicompartiment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project is tightly intertwined with the PARC overall aim to strengthen the EU's capacity for chemical risk assessment to protect human health and the environment, as well as closely linked to developing innovative models and concepts for chemical risk assessments.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Collaboration with WP9 on the surveys and inventories
- Links to T4.3 on innovative methods
- Links with T4.2.1: Characterisation of the compound groups

Links outside PARC

There is a need to develop a prioritisation framework for environmental pollutants, to characterise their sources and evaluate the effect of risk-reducing measures in support of the EU's Zero Pollution ambition including assisting governmental agencies as well as other stakeholders to focussing their monitoring campaigns on the most relevant compounds/matrices/end-points.

Other initiatives involving the prioritization of chemicals for monitoring will be addressed in the inventory such as the action categories approach developed by NORMAN is recognized as an efficient and pragmatic way to address regulatory questions. The NORMAN methodology will be central in the inventory to be conducted for the prioritisation scheme in PARC. An active collaboration of NORMAN with PARC is envisaged, facilitated by the fact that many PARC partners are also active in NORMAN.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D4.1 Description of a mechanism for selection of chemicals/matrices/endpoints for projects (M20)

Expected Project Reports:

Report 1: Procedures for agreement on transparent use of existing data, access to samples and involvement of external laboratories (M12)

Final project report (M36)

Expected Projects Landmarks:

The expected landmark is a successful finalisation of the technical specifications with detailed planning of the two monitoring campaigns (EDCs and PFAS) including agreed procedures for sample exchange the establishment of pilot data for two compound groups identified as particularly problematic, EDCs and PFAS, to test and verify the application of the developed prioritisation framework (T4.2.1) on monitoring studies.

Partners List:

INERIS (FR), AU (DK), INRAE (FR), MU (CZ), SYKE (FI), UBA (DE), CNR-IRSA (IT), IVL (SE), NKUA (GR), ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), CSTB (FR), SpF (FR), OVAM (BE), ISSeP (BE), Uantwerpen (BE), LNS (LU), VUA (NE), NILU (NO), JSI (SL), UL FFA (SL), ARSO (SL), ISCIII (ES), FISABIO (ES), UCLM (ES), EA (UK), UKCEH (UK), EFET (GR), BPI (GR), Sciensano (BE), BfG (DE), UFZ (DE), SLU (SE), Eawag (CH), CEH (UK), CNRS (FR), CSTB (FR), EV-ILVO (BE), Fraunhofer-IME (DE), ISS (IT), INSERM (FR), NIJZ (SI), NMBU (NO), ONIRIS (FR), OFB (FR), UniLu (LU), VITO (BE), VSCHT (CZ).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022
 Expected ending date: 30/04/2025

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 310.69 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 53.39 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: undetermined

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: undetermined

T4.3 Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys – 6 PROJECTS

A4.3.1 Transversal actions – 4 PROJECTS

P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01-Concept Paper_MU

Project Title	Global collective definition and prioritisation of main concepts, approaches and objectives associated to innovative methods undertaken in task 4.3 (inventories, selection/prioritisation, shared knowledge and visions among environmental-food-HBM communities)		
Project Acronym	P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01		
Project Manager	Elliott James Price elliott.price@recetox.muni.cz	MU	CZ
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	12
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.1
Project Id	P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01-Concept paper_MU		

Status: *Planning*

Summary of the project

Task 4.3 focuses upon assessing the potential of innovative methodological approaches to enhance characterization of chemical exposures. As a prerequisite, an alignment of main definitions and shared understanding of the objectives and strategical vision associated to those emerging approaches in the specific context of supporting policy for RA/RM is necessary. The purpose of the present project is then to stimulate this crossed discussion among representative of the environment, food safety and HBM communities, to finally elaborate a concept paper describing this conceptual and strategical positioning and projection. In particular, the landscape of innovative (self-)sampling methods will be surveyed with regards to implementation for chemical hazard /exposure risk identification, in link with 4.1.1 and 4.3.2 related activities. The concepts of non-target analysis (NTA) and suspect screening (SS) will be clarified and the current capabilities of NTA/SS and effect-directed analysis (EDA) data to support chemical agent prioritisation and early warning will be described. For instance, the distinction/overlap between NTA and SS with respect to whether division is limited to divergent data processing procedures or extends to differing analytical data acquisition is unclear, and the representativeness of measures from fractionated samples for composite toxicity profiles is a pressing question for EDA. Focus will be afforded to identifying areas of

shared interest across the environment-food-HBM domains and knowledge exchange to generate a common vision on capabilities and capacity of the approaches within and across different communities.

Main expected outputs of the project:

- Alignment of understanding and expectations from the environment-food safety-HBM communities with regard to innovative methodological approaches
- Enhancement of the availability and usefulness of new empirical evidence used for chemical hazard and exposure risk characterization through this conceptual alignment

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders:

Current landscape is that these innovative approaches and their potential application towards regulatory purposes are not well understood. As such, consolidation of a shared vision will enable improved communication and facilitate better understanding, which should enable expansion of a more diverse base of stakeholders and end-users with vested interests in the trajectory of development for these emerging methodologies, adding value.

Key words: innovative methods, critical review, dry blood spots, silicone wristbands, suspect screening, non-targeted screening, effect-directed analysis, bioactivity assays, chemical mixtures, exposure profiling

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA) :

The task directly contributes to facilitating the transition to next generation evidence-based risk assessment through the development of conceptual frameworks and strategies within the arena of innovative technologies (sampling, NTA/SS, EDA) to advance the identification and prioritisation of novel and emerging contaminants of concern with perceived, potential of real risk.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects) (between 2-8 lines):

WP4/A4.1.1 & A4.3.2: The task will contribute to the planned pro/con expert review and analysis, QAQC consolidation and implementation of DBS/SWB.

WP3: The task will attempt to clarify the discourse of innovative technologies, since currently available information is often unclear for stakeholders leading to misunderstanding. Communication of intended remit, pros and cons of the emerging strategies to broad range of stakeholders should be supported.

WP7: The task will advocate a need for open science policy and push FAIR principles as a primary need to advance the uptake of innovative technologies. The implementation strategy should be supported from WP7.

WP9: The task will outline and justify the development strategy for the field and thus will identify areas of need for capacity building and training that can then be mobilised via WP9.

WP2: The task includes development of concepts of how to progress innovative sampling, NTA/SS & EDA within a reporting for policy context; linking highly focussed needs to the broader agenda of Science-policy uptake and priority setting of WP2.

WPs 5,6,8: The task includes the conceptual development of frameworks related to chemical annotation that incorporate e.g., exposure, risk and hazard indices and uncertainty, with implications for early warning.

Links outside PARC:

1. HBM4EU – extension of many activities developed in WP15 (mixtures incl. prioritization e.g., CECscreen) WP16 (emerging chemicals incl. NTA/SS/EDA approaches),
2. H2020 European Human Exposome Network – includes generation of empirical data via novel technologies
3. ESFRI European Environmental Exposure Assessment Research Infrastructure – provision of service and consolidation of conceptual ambiguities within exposome research
4. H2020 European Cluster to Improve Identification of Endocrine Disruptors – includes generation of empirical data via novel technologies
5. The Periodic Table of Foods Initiative – food composition, use and health
6. BP4NTA – US-based working group focussing on NTA concepts and reporting, including for regulatory purposes (mostly via involvement of US EPA).

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD.4.6 Concept paper regarding common definitions and short to medium term support to policy objectives

of innovative (self-) sampling, suspect screening and NTA/EDA approaches - M12.

Expected Project Reports:

Report on common definitions and short to medium term support to policy objectives of innovative (self-) sampling, suspect screening and NTA/EDA approaches – MU, M12.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- Availability of a first draft of concept paper for partner’s edits and comments – M9.
- Final concept paper manuscript submitted to a peer review journal – M12.

Partners List: MU (CZ); Participants: INRAE (FR); VUA (NL); ANSES (FR); BRGM (FR); EAWAG (CH); EHESP (FR); INRS (FR); JSI (SI); LNS (LU); MUI (AT); UAntwerpen (BE); UBA (DE); UFZ (DE); VITO (BE); WR (NL); EV-ILVO (BE); NILU (NO); OFB (FR); UL-FFA (SI)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 30/04/2023

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 39.2 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 39.2 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 5000 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 5000 €

P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02-QAQC_WR

Project Title	QA/QC requirements for HRMS and EDA-based screening approaches in environmental, food and human matrices		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02		
Project Manager	Hans Mol Hans.mol@wur.nl	WR (WFSR)	NL
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	M36
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.1
Project Id	P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QAQC_WR		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

This project will consist to develop a transversal action aiming at defining minimal common quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) requirements to be used specifically for chemical suspect and non-targeted screening methods (SS/NTS) based on chromatography coupled to resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) and biological effect-directed assays (EDA). This project will inventory the existing QA/QC procedures, guidelines, proposals (and interpretations thereof) in the food, environmental and human biomonitoring (HBM) domains, identify inconsistencies and gaps, and aims to align and establish procedures and criteria across the application domains.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Protocol for QA/QC in suspect and non-target screening methods
- Guidance on identification (levels) of substances found by SS/NTS

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The proposed project appears as a necessary follow-up of the work achieved under HBM4EU, where a number of QA/QC provisions, guidance SOP, and supporting template for QA/QC data analysis were produced in the particular context of the Specimen Study (pesticide screening in 2000 human urine samples from 5 countries by 5 different laboratories). From that basis, the goal of the present project is to deliver to end-users interested to implement those innovative screening approaches an extended and consolidated QA/QC framework to be applied more globally for a wide range of different applications within the environmental-food-HBM communities. This medium term perspective should benefit a number of end-users and stakeholders through improvement of data quality / comparability.

Key words:

Quality Control, Quality Assurance, suspect screening, non-target screening, identification, effect-directed assays

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA) :

This project will deal with necessary QA/QC provisions specifically dedicated to the innovative approaches developed under task 4.3. Indeed, the analytical chemistry community has developed for many years appropriate QA/QC provisions for assessing the performance of conventional targeted methods applied to environmental, food or human matrices. The situation is less mature for emerging and innovative approaches where the objectives differ from the previous ones. A main need for qualitative (or semi-quantitative) suspect and non-targeted approaches relies on the precise and transparent documentation of the method application range, i.e. the contour of the accessible markers of exposure, in order to possibly compare and well interpret the results obtained by different methods. This workline was explicitly included in the task 4.3 DoA.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is very closely linked to WP9/task 9.3, and WP4, specifically to the QA/QC activities therein (T4.1.2, T4.2.4). Several experts/key contributors from these tasks are also involved in the present project 4.3_T02 that will permit to establish this necessary articulation. While in T9.3 overarching frameworks are set, this activity focusses specifically on HRMS and EDA based screening methods, and for that the generation of experimental- and experience-based QA/QC criteria and requirements, and establishing QA/QC programs of SS/NTS and EDA. Prioritised substance groups in activities in T4.1 and T4.2 are taken into account with respect to type of chemicals addressed (e.g. PFAS and endocrine disruptors, EDCs), and possible integration of QA/QC programs (e.g. proficiency testing using the same control materials in both target and screening methods).

Links outside PARC (between 2-8 lines):

Within the below mentioned projects and already existing regulations/guidance documents, QA/QC for screening methods has been (partially) addressed to various levels of detail. This project will link with and build forth on these projects:

HBM4EU (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/>)

NORMAN (<https://www.norman-network.com/?q=Home>)

MetroFood (<https://www.metrofood.eu/>)

JRC (<https://crm.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>)

EU-TOXRISK/RISKHUNT3R (<https://www.eu-toxrisk.eu/>)

Food screening regulations, e.g., dioxins Calux Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/644;...

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

None identified at present.

Expected Project Reports:

To be further defined.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

To be further defined.

Partners List:

Lead: WR (NL). Partners: INRAE (FR), ANSES (FR), AU (DK), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), EAWAG (CH), EHESP (FR), INRS (FR), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AU), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (UA), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), AUTH (GR), EV-ILVO (BE), IDAEA-CSIC (ES), LNE (FR) NILU (NO), WULS (PL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 72.5 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 7.2 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 360 250 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 36 025 €

P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_EWStools_SLU

Project Title	Illustrating the usefulness of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning system and harmonized framework from environment-food-human		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03		
Project Manager	Lutz Ahrens Lutz.ahrens@slu.se	SLU	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	M60
PARC Workpackage number	WP4.3	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.1.c
Project Id	P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_EWStools_SLU		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Establishment of an early warning system (EWS) for identification of new and existing potentially hazardous substances is a key component in PARC and current EU regulatory actions. For prioritization of new chemicals, several tools have been developed that can be used in combination or independently, among which suspect and non-targeted screening coupled to effect directed analyses approaches. This project will support the development of EWS under WP8 (task 8.2) by ensuring that data generated through those innovative methods can be used to identify and prioritize hazardous substances in human, food and environmental matrices that may be associated with a potential risk. The project will illustrate the usefulness of early warning monitoring tools both for environmental samples (e.g. soil, sediment, sludge, dust), human samples (e.g. blood), food (incl. drinking water) and products (incl. waste streams, recycled products). The project will identify in particular chemical properties, toxicological endpoints and HRMS features relevant

for the EWS, initially with the purpose to gather all necessary ones, and then identify criteria to assign relative weights to each parameter and endpoint.

Main expected outputs of the project

Review already existing information related to innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as early warning monitoring tools

Contribute/formulate criteria for categorizing annotated data to be integrated in the EWS format.

Elaborated a proof-of-concept illustrating (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to EWS

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project will generate proofs-of-concepts and tools of relevance to risk assessors and policy makers at national and EU level. Innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches are of utmost importance for identification of new and existing potentially hazardous substances at an early stage. Cutting edge tools will be conceptualized and illustrated for establishment of an EWS. End-users include ECHA, EFSA, EEA, national environmental and chemical agencies, national food safety authorities, NORMAN, researchers, industry, NGOs, national consumer protection organizations and the general public.

Key words:

Early warning system (EWS); early warning monitoring tools; Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA); suspect and non-targeted screening (NTS); high resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS); innovative sampling

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA) :

The project will establish a proof-of-concept illustration of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning systems and harmonized framework from environment-food-human. This will ensure that the generated data can be used to support the development of early warning systems under WP8 to communicate risks, facilitate awareness of risks and disseminate warnings to inform risk assessors and risk managers at an early stage of future challenges or emerging risks, linked to other activities and future projects in PARC.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP4:

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04_Data Processing Workflow_EHESP: Support annotation of generated data

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02_Occupational exposure_INRS: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03_Other complementary studies_JSI: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.3/P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-WBE_UFZ-UBATH: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.3/P4.3.3.b_Y2_E02-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.3/P4.3.3.c_Y3_E03-Other compl. studies_ORU-MTM: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.4/P4.3.4.b_Y3_F02_Other compl. studies_ANSES: Ensure useful output for EWS

WP5: Effect-directed tools based on bioassays using new approach methodologies (NAMs).

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...). FAIR Data libraries.

WP8: Conceptualization of an Early Warning System (EWS) from sampling/NTS/EDA methods in humans, environment, food and products combining exposure and hazard data. Computational methods for text mining, data curation and hazard scoring.

WP9: Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for SS/NTS/EDA approaches.

Links outside PARC:

- [HBM4EU](#) (data, models)
- [HEALS, CROME-Life](#)
- [UBA NTS Portal with BfG](#) (Water, suspended matter)
- [NORMAN Network](#) activities
- DG ENV Early Warning System project

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D.4.10 3rd Proof-of-concept illustrating the usefulness of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning system and harmonized framework from environment-food-human. M60, SLU.

Expected Project Reports:

Proofs-of-concept illustrating the usefulness of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning system and harmonized framework from environment-food-human. M60.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- Conceptual framework for innovative (self-)sampling for early warning monitoring tools has been established (M40)
- Conceptual framework for integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning systems has been established (M50)

Partners List:

SLU (SE), INRAE (FR), VUA (NL), ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), EAWAG (CH), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), ORU-MTM (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), UniLU (LU), AUTH (GR), ISS (IT), NILU (NO)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022
 Expected ending date: 30/04/2027

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 45.5 PM
 Expected PM for the first year of the project: 6 PM
Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):
 Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 58 000 €
 Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 0 €

P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04-Data Processing Workflow_EHESP

Project Title	Establishment of necessary advanced data processing methodologies and bioinformatic tools for NTS. Identify gaps / necessary methodological improvements for retrospective use of NTS HRMS data (digital sample freezing platform) and EU capacity in terms of centralized data repository		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04		
Project Manager	Arthur David Arthur.david@chesp.fr	EHESP	FR
Deputy Project	-	-	-

manager			
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	60
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub- activity:	4.3.1
Project Id	P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04-Data processing workflow_EHESP		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project:

Considering the vast amount of chemicals present on the market, there is currently a substantial lack of data on human and environmental exposure to these chemicals, preventing the implementation of efficient regulatory approaches by policy makers. Hence, suspect screening and non-targeted analyses based on high-resolution offer great promises to identify emerging and chemical mixtures without a priori. The lack of comprehensive and user-friendly automated pipeline for suspect (SS) and non-targeted screening (NTS) data processing however appears as a crucial issue and current major bottleneck for efficient implementation of these approaches. Indeed, a wide range of software tools are today available to perform one or several components of such data processing and extraction of the useful information from the raw data, including peak picking, peak alignment, and annotation. But still no consensual guidelines were proposed regarding both a preferable selection from this panel of existing tool or their fine appropriate parameterization in the context of NTS. Overall, an integrated, sustainable, and open access solution permitting to perform all these necessary steps with sufficient QA/QC consolidation for support to policy application and sufficient high throughput capacity for application to large scale cohorts, is still lacking and is urgently needed.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Built strong and dynamic consortium within the environment-food safety-HBM scientific communities to harmonize and mutualize the current and future resources
- Updated CECScreen database with the aim to improve the annotation quality
- Pursued development of an extended, unified, sustainable and open access European MS reference library through the collaborative generation of MS and MS/MS reference spectra
- Developed comprehensive and user-friendly automated pipeline for SS and NTS
- Defined appropriate quality strategies to ensure retrospective analyses/early warning system
- Developed / improved appropriate data processing workflow dedicated to bioassay data

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project appears as a pre-requisite methodological development related activity, expected to provide at medium term (4 years) new consolidated ground to implement SS/NTS approaches at larger scale and provide new data on human and environmental exposure for policy makers. This medium-term perspective should benefit a number of end-users including laboratories aiming to implement those new analytical approaches (capacity building within the EU), as well as actors aiming to build and use early warning systems for which the expected new exposure data generation capabilities will represent a significant input.

Key words:

Suspect screening; non-targeted screening; data processing, annotation, user-friendly workflow; CECScreen database; reference library; marker identification; automation

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA) :

The development of this comprehensive and user-friendly automated pipeline for SS and NTS is a necessary step for all the projects that will use these strategies in WP4 and other related WPs. Following the work done in HBM4EU, the development of an extended, unified, sustainable and open access European MS reference library as a key stone of the annotation workflow underlying to these HRMS-based suspect screening approaches applied across the environment-food-human continuum is clearly part of the defined DoA for task 4.3, as well as the establishment of necessary advanced data processing methodologies and bioinformatic tools for better efficiency and deployment of NTS (e.g. inspired from the Workflow for

Metabolomics W4M/Galaxy user friendly environment).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP4:

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02_Occupational exposure_INRS: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03_Other complementary studies_JSI: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.3/4.3.3/P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-WBE_UFZ-UBATH: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.3/4.3.3/P4.3.3.b_Y2_E02-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.3/4.3.3/P4.3.3.c_Y3_E03-Other compl. studies_ORU-MTM: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.3/4.3.4/P4.3.4.b_Y3_F02-Other compl. studies_ANSES: Mutualized resources / harmonization

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...)

WP9: Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for SS/NTS/EDA approaches

Links outside PARC

Continuity with regard to HBM4EU WP16 related activities that has developed bases of harmonisation and development for suspect and non-targeted screening but without considering the related innovative sampling approaches considered in the present project.

NORMAN (<https://www.norman-network.com/?q=Home>), JRC (<https://crm.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>)

France-Exposome, Institut Français de Bioinformatique (IFB, ELIXIR-FR, <https://www.france-bioinformatique.fr/elixir-fr/>), ELIXIR and EIRENE infrastructures

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D.4.9 Workflow for data processing and annotation of HRMS based chemical profiles generated from suspect/NTS approaches (e.g., inspired from W4M/Galaxy) - M54.

Expected Project Reports:

Report on the Establishment of necessary advanced data processing methodologies and bioinformatic tools for NTS – EHESP, M60.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- Conduct a strategical review of already existing initiatives and tools worldwide with all involved partners to select the best options for the envisaged workflow – M9
- Assignment of most of the tasks and development to all partners completed – M12
- Release of an operational prototype version of the user-friendly workflow – M42
- All planned outputs on track – M60

Partners List:

EHESP (FR), INRAE (FR), VUA (NL), ANSES (FR), INRS (FR), JSI (SI), KWR (DE), MU (CE), MUI (AT), Oniris (FR), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), UniLU (LU), WR (NL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 179.8 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 18 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 899 000 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 89 900 €

A4.3.2 Human samples based proof-of-concepts – 1 PROJECT

P4.3.2.a Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE

Project Title	Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based / EDA screening methods for exploring human perinatal exposure to chemicals of emerging concern		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01		
Project Manager	Jean-Philippe Antignac jean-philippe.antignac@inrae.fr	INRAE	FR
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.2
Project Id	P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Capturing the complex real human chemical exposure requires new conceptual frameworks and innovative methodological approaches. These ones, from sampling to exposure data generation and analysis, are however requiring a better consolidated development and a better documented performance assessment before large scale implementation in human cohorts. As formulated by several agencies (e.g. EFSA), early stage human exposure appears in particular as a high concern not yet well addressed, both in terms of risk assessment and link to health impact at latest stages (DoHAD concept). New sampling methods (e.g. silicone wristbands and/or dried blood spots (DBS)), compatible with the non-invasiveness and restricted sample requirements typically expected for those sub-populations represent potentially relevant options to be considered in that context. Suspect and non-targeted screening approaches (SS/NTS) based on high resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) coupled to effect directed analysis (EDA) are another new trend in analytical laboratories with high potential. The aim of this project is to develop and conduct a proof-of-concept permitting to assess the performances, and illustrate the usefulness, of those innovative methods, as complementary to conventional and targeted approaches, with a focus on human samples collected from mother-newborn/child individuals. By definition screening approaches should permit to capture simultaneously various substances from different classes, relying on the global prioritization strategy from WP2, including both non persistent and persistent organic chemicals of emerging concern.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Characterization of advantages/limitations of innovative approaches compared to conventional ones
- Scientifically supported prioritisation of some of them for short term implementation
- Paved way for further developments/improvements needed for long term implementation
- Identification of relevant markers/matrices combinations for perinatal exposure assessment
- Documenting real life mixtures associated to perinatal chemical exposure
- Prioritization of further targeted developments focused on particular exposure markers evidenced
- Contribution to feed early warning system through an established link between tasks 4.3 and 8.2

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The proposed project appears as a pre-required methodological development activity, expected to provide at medium term (4 years) consolidated bases for implementing a set of innovative sampling and exposure

measurement approaches for HBM. This medium-term perspective should benefit a number of end-users including laboratories aiming to implement those new analytical approaches (capacity building), as well as actors aiming to build and use early warning systems for which the expected new exposure data generation capabilities will represent a significant input.

Key words:

Biomonitoring, perinatal exposure, innovative methods, dry blood spots, silicone wristbands, suspect screening, non-targeted screening, effect-directed analysis, real-life mixtures, emerging chemicals

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

Conventional sampling and targeted quantitative analytical methods are already available to support environmental, food and human monitoring, risk assessment, and risk management decisions. However, these approaches sometimes suffer from a lack of sensitivity to characterize lowest exposed populations, face some limitations for large scale implementation, and only capture a limited number of a priori known and selected markers of exposure. From this global picture, a specific concern formulated by several agencies (e.g., EFSA) is related to a need for a better characterization of exposure for particularly vulnerable sub-populations, notably new-borns and young children. Human foetal exposure also appears as a not yet well addressed high concern in the context of linking this early exposure to human health impact at latest stages (DoHAD concept). This project is aiming to contribute addressing those issues related to the PARC objectives and DoA.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP4:

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_Early Warning System_SLU: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04_Data Processing Workflow_EHESP: Support annotation of generated data

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02_Occupational exposure_INRS: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03_Other complementary studies_JSI: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.1/4.1.1: Pro/con expert review and analysis, QAQC consolidation and implementation of DBS/SWB

WP6: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for mixture modelling

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...)

WP8: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for early warning system

WP9: Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for SS/NTS/EDA approaches

Links outside PARC

Continuity with regard to HBM4EU WP16 related activities that has developed bases of harmonisation and development for suspect and non-targeted screening but without considering the related innovative sampling approaches considered in the present project.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D.4.5: 2nd Proof-of-concept illustrating the usefulness of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning system and risk assessment for human monitoring - M48.

Expected Project Reports:

Report on the application of innovative (self-)sampling methods combined with suspect/NTS/EDA approaches for perinatal exposure assessment – INRAE, M48.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- Refined study design co-built and completed with all involved partners – M6
- Sample sourcing and sharing completed – M12
- At least 50% of planned analyses completed – M24

- All planned analyses completed and data processing on-track – M36

Partners List:

INRAE (FR), EHESP (FR), CEA (FR), VUA (NL), KUM (DE), UNIVIE (AT), UFZ (DE), WR (NL), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), UAntwerpen (BE), UGR (SP), AU (DK), UniLU (LU), LNS (LU), UNIADBN (UK), MU (CZ), ISPV (SP), VSCHT (CZ), BPI (GR), VITO (BE), IDAEA-CSIC (SP), ISCII (SP), ISS (SP), SU (SE)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 347.8 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 34.8 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 1 739 000 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 173 900 €

A4.3.3 Environment samples based proof-of-concepts – 1 PROJECT

P4.3.3.a Y1_EO1-Wastewater based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH

Project Title	Mining chemical information from wastewater treatment plants for I. human community (<i>wastewater fingerprinting for community wide human exposure assessment</i>) and II. environmental exposure assessment (<i>screening of wastewater treatment plant effluents to assess the release of Chemicals of Emerging Concern into the water cycle</i>).		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Wastewater based epidemiology		
Project Manager	Werner Brack werner.brack@ufz.de	UFZ	DE
Deputy Project manager	Barbara Kasprzyk-Hordern bkh20@bath.ac.uk	UBATH	UK
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.3
Project Id	P4.3.3.a_Y1_EO1-Wastewater-based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Wastewater can serve as a source of information with respect to human exposure, by measuring specific human metabolites in raw sewage (wastewater-based epidemiology – WBE). WWTPs are a main source for complex mixtures of chemicals in surface water, impacting the environment and human health (e.g., via drinking water). This project addresses both human and environmental exposure, focusing on (i) wastewater fingerprinting for community wide human exposure assessment and (ii) on screening of WWTP effluents to assess the release of Chemicals of Emerging Concern (CECs) into the water cycle. The development of wastewater-based epidemiology (WBE) as well as the screening of effluents using suspect and nontarget screening (SS/NTS) approaches and effect-directed analysis (EDA) will deliver innovative methods for

community wide human exposure assessment, environmental exposure assessment and the identification of CECs of (eco-)toxicological concern. The European-scale monitoring data generated by these methods as well as a re-evaluation of existing data will greatly improve our knowledge on CECs in wastewater and their primary sources as a basis for the revision of the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive with regard to reducing CEC emissions, providing candidate compounds and information on their sources for priority/river-basin-specific chemicals in the context of the Water Framework Directive, and providing information on chemical mixtures for the revision of REACH with regard to environmental mixture concerns.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Innovative screening / targeted methods for community-wide chemical exposure assessment by WBE
- Innovative screening methods and workflows for environmental exposure assessment of wastewater
- Europe-wide human community exposure patterns via targeted and non-targeted WBE
- Wastewater and source patterns representing typical emission scenarios in Europe
- Prioritisation of compounds of concern emitted with wastewater for further assessment

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

We will develop innovative analytical approaches that will define future approaches to exposure studies, both in the context of environmental and public health. This project is potentially transformative for several stakeholder groups including, regulatory sector and public health agencies.

Key words

wastewater, wastewater-based epidemiology, suspect and nontarget screening, compound prioritization, community exposure assessment, mixture risk drivers, effect-directed analysis

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project provides human exposure (via WBE), environmental and multisource monitoring data for regulatory purposes from the mining of existing HRMS-based datasets and Pan-European monitoring studies. The project enhances the collaboration between the partners conducting WBE and wastewater monitoring through consolidated and harmonised analytical and data processing workflows. Developing a proof-of-concept for illustrating the capacities of SS/NTS/EDA approaches in the particular case of environmental monitoring is then directly connected to task 4.3 DoA

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The proposed project will be closely linked to Tasks 4.1 (Human exposure assessment) and 4.2 (Environmental and multisource monitoring) providing innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys supporting these tasks. This project will inform on toxicity data gaps of concern based on realistic human and environmental exposure (Task 5.1) and will closely collaborate with Task 5.2 on innovative tools for toxicity testing, filtering Task 5.2 tools for methods useful for effect-directed analysis. The project will provide valuable measured human and environmental exposure information as input to Task 6.2. The project will also feed in directly into Task 8.2 aiming at the establishment of an early warning system.

Links outside PARC

Within the EU Horizon 2020 COST action SCORE (www.score-cost.eu), activities in the field of WBE are initiated and coordinated. While the main focus was on illicit drugs, the focus is shifting towards current, in-use compounds to investigate patterns of factors related to lifestyle, disease and environment. Hydra-EWS: Marie Curie initiative led by University of Bath (UBAH), in which connection with task 4.3 is already made, possibly providing synergy. E-PRTR programme (<https://industry.eea.europa.eu/#/home>) VANDALF: National Danish project aiming to develop and implement a risk assessment platform based on NTS and effect-based methods to identify CECs in wastewater, will be closely linked through the involvement of the coordinator UPCH. NORMAN network: Strong collaboration and exchange, use of and exchange with NORMAN database system.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D.4.2 Proof-of-concept illustrating the usefulness of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning system and risk assessment for environmental monitoring. **M35**

Expected Project Reports:

Not applicable.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Not applicable.

Partners List: UFZ (DE) & UBATH (UK), MUI (AT), UCPH (DK), EAWAG (CH), IRFM (IT), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), UniLU (LU), VUA (NL), ISS (SP), INERIS (FR), BfG (DE), UL-FFA (SI), BRGM (FR), WULS-SGGW (PL), JU (CZ), MU (CZ), INRAE (FR), OFB (FR), UL (PL), VITO (BE)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 298.6 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 59.72 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 1 493 000 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 298 600 €

A4.3.4 Food samples based proof-of-concepts

No project submitted at present.

WP5 Hazard Assessment - 12 PROJECTS

T5.1 Toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern 4 PROJECTS

A5.1.1 Closing data gaps of concern for human health – 2 PROJECTS

P5.1.1.a_Y1_Toxins_BfR_UNIVIE

Project Title	Hazard identification and hazard characterisation of the mycotoxins enniatins and <i>Alternaria</i> toxins in order to close data gaps and improve risk assessment for human health		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Toxins		
Project Manager	Doris Marko doris.marko@univie.ac.at	UNIVIE	Austria
Project manager	Jessica Dietrich jessica.dietrich@bfr.bund.de	BfR	Germany
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M<1>	Expected duration	<36>

PARC Workpackage number	WP<5>	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	<5.1.1>
Project Id	P5.1.1.a_Y1_Toxins_BfR_UNIVIE		

Status: *Planning*

Summary of the project

Natural toxins have no manufacturer or supplier that is responsible for providing hazard data. Due to climate changes, the human exposure to natural toxins will likely increase and regulatory agencies have asked for more hazard data to improve the risk assessment. This will ultimately result in recommendations on which natural toxins should be closely monitored in food feed and food products (Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006) in order to prevent adverse human health effects.

Different classes of natural toxins are in scope like phycotoxins, phytotoxins and mycotoxins. This proposal will initially focus on two classes of emerging mycotoxins, i.e. enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins where there is a pressing regulatory need for more specific hazard data. Preferably, the studies will be performed according to OECD test guidelines, but in some cases no guidelines are available to address the specific endpoints and NAMs will be employed.

EFSA's CONTAM Panel stated in a scientific opinion on the risks to human and animal health related to the presence of beauvericin and enniatins in food and feed that there might be a health concern regarding chronic exposure to enniatins however there is insufficient data to assess the risk on chronic exposure. Also in the case of *Alternaria* toxins, the scientific Panel was not able to conduct a systematic risk assessment due to the lack of data. Accordingly, the threshold of toxicological concern (TTC) approach for an initial evaluation was applied, indicating that the TTC values are frequently exceeded at least for AOH and AME. This underlines that further research, in terms of hazard identification and characterization, is required for both toxins.

Additionally, for both Enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins major data gaps were identified in toxicity data in a recent report from the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and the Environment (VKM et al., 2019).

Main expected outputs of the project

The study will provide urgently needed *in vitro* data and identify critical toxicological effects of enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins. The data is necessary for subsequent *in vivo* studies which are required to establish health-based guidance values and to perform an appropriate risk assessment and provide an efficient consumer protection.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project will generate toxicological data (mainly focusing on hazard identification and characterization), aiming at incorporating it in risk assessment performed in EU Agencies to set health-based guidance values that could therefore trigger the establishment of maximal levels in food in the context of Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006.

Key words: Natural toxins, *Alternaria* toxins, Enniatins, mycotoxins, genotoxicity, endocrine disruptive effects, immunotoxicology, *in vitro*, *in silico*

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project was designed in order to fill data gaps regarding the main representatives of emerging mycotoxins groups of enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins as defined by EFSA. The results are needed to identify critical toxicological effects for subsequent *in vivo* studies which are needed to establish health-based guidance values and to perform an appropriate risk assessment and provide an efficient consumer protection.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- **WP4:** Human exposure to the mycotoxins will be monitored in WP4. Analytical support in measuring the test items in test media is needed in order to support PBPK and IVIVE modelling.
- **WP5.2 and WP5.3:** The test items will also be studied in selected NAMs in WP 5.2 (Cf. project on immunotoxicology). Data that will be generated on kinetics and AOP will be used in task 5.3 in order to improve and expand existing models.
- **WP6:** Hazard data generated will be used in WP6 to build IATAs. Since most mycotoxins will be present in food and feed as mixtures, selected mixtures will also be tested. Relative Potency Factors could therefore be derived where possible and will provide important support for the assessments of risks of mixtures.

Links outside PARC

Not foreseen at the moment.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

In the 1st year:

AD5.2: M12 (April 2023) - Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted. Associated Task: T5.1 Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA

Expected Project reports

Submission of at least one review Papers on Enniatins and Alternaria toxins addressing the relevant endpoints of the project M9

Reports available with data generated – M35 (March 2025) – BfR, UNIVIE

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- First test items available in sufficient quantities and qualities M6 (October 2022)
- First experimental studies have started M9 (January 2022)
- Last experimental studies have been completed M30 (October 2024)
- Manuscripts submitted to peer reviewed journals M 36 (April 2025)

Partners List:

BfR (Germany), UNIVIE (Austria), BPI (Greece), IBMT (Germany), IMR (Norway), INRS (France), ANSES (France), INSA (Portugal), NIB (Slovenia), NIPH (Norway), Sciensano (Belgium), STAMI (Norway), UNAV (Spain), NVI (Norway), WU-TOX (Netherlands)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/ 2022

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 482,90 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 114,49 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 1 437 395 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 208 350 €

P5.1.1.b_Y1_BPA_HumTox_ISS

Project Title	Hazard assessment of bisphenol A alternatives to close data gaps of concern for human health and improve their risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	BPA_HumTox		
Project	Emanuela Testai	ISS	Italy

Manager	emanuela.testai@iss.it		
Deputy Project manager	Emanuela Corsini emanuela.corsini@uniroma1.it	UMIL	Italy
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.1/5.1.1/
Project Id	P5.1.1.b_Y1_HumanTox_ISS		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

This project is aimed at testing bisphenol A (BPA) analogues and alternatives, some of which being currently produced in low tonnages. However, they are already occurring in the environment and with the upcoming restrictions on BPA and some of its analogues, their tonnages and frequencies of use are expected to severely increase in the following years. BPA is the most widely used and studied of the bisphenols. BPA alternatives, such as BPS, which are already in use as BPA replacement, express some endocrine disrupting activities similar to those of BPA in particular in terms of estrogenic, anti-estrogenic, androgenic, and anti-androgenic activities while others although not characterized as endocrine disruptors might trigger other pathways such as, for example, TBBPA that is a PPAR α activator. Both in-vitro and in-vivo studies have also shown the immunotoxic potential of BPA (Nowak et al. 2019); the relevance of this end-point is witnessed by the identification of an immunotoxic parameter (increase of Th17 cells) as the critical end-point in the most recent EFSA opinion on BPA risk assessment (EFSA, 2022). Paradoxically, data on the potential toxicity of the bisphenol substitutes are scarce, with indications that some of them might be even more hazardous than BPA (Pelch et al. 2019a). For most bisphenol analogues, information on metabolism (biotransformation and toxicokinetics), ED potential, developmental neurotoxicity (DNT), and carcinogenicity is either absent or too limited for a full hazard assessment/characterization. In addition, there is also a growing need to determine the mechanism(s) through which the BPA alternatives act: identifying the key steps mode of action will be a key process underlying a tight synergism with WP 6 to improve/build AOPS. This is relevant for any end-points selected in the project, starting from the kinetics (that condition the possibility to assess internal doses) and including the effects on the immune system, which despite considered the critical effect for BPA, has been neglected for long time. Hence it is necessary to search for molecular biomarkers to develop a method to rapidly predict immunotoxicity, endocrine disruption, non genotox carcinogenesis and/or neurodevelopmental toxicity of novel bisphenols, before they come into widespread use.

This project, focused on human health in vitro models and end-points, aims to use different in vitro toxicity testing approaches as the first stage to address the substance-specific data or regulatory gaps, identified by key stakeholders. The substances to be tested include the major BPA alternatives among which BPS-MAE, BPS-IP, TCBPA and other halogenated analogues, PF-201, or others such as BPZ, BPE, BPP, BPAP, BPPH, BPS-MPE, as identified in a specific workshop with ECHA, EFSA as the major stakeholders. Not all the substances will be tested for the 5 different end-points: the selection will be based on the availability of literature data (and on information provided by ECHA) for some end-points. In the spirit of the WP, the missing data will be produced, following a tiered approach coordinating the different activities in order to have a complete data set for at least four of them.

Main expected outputs of the project

For the selected BPA alternatives, several data gaps concerning human health effects (as identified together with ECHA) are expected to be closed to the extent that in vitro data allows. The human health effects that will be studied include: endocrine disruption, developmental neurotoxic activity regarding potential adverse

cognitive effects, immune response modulation, non-genotoxic carcinogenesis. Metabolic invents and the occurrence of bioactivation pathways will be taken into consideration and specifically investigated using human hepatic in vitro models. The data obtained will feed mainly into the hazard assessment component of the risk assessment and will provide modellers input for PBPK and QIVIVE models contributing to definition of experimental strategies in an animal free environment. Obtained data will provide the assessors information to conduct a solid risk assessment on the basis of which the identification of the adequate risk management procedures to adopt to protect human health for the exposed population through the preparations and implementation of guidelines and directives at the national, regional (EU) and world level. This will contribute significantly to the enhanced protection of public health and requirements for safe food, consumer products and adequate drinking water.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Because of the restrictions on the use of BPA in consumer products a number of BPA substitutes have emerged. This includes alternatives such as BPS, but also other large-volume substances such as Pergafast 201 (used as an alternative in thermal printing) and other priority substances, as identified in an ad hoc Workshop together with ECHA and EFSA.

The Project will provide in vitro data on a set of toxicological endpoints for BPA alternatives that have not been assessed by the industry, to support the assessors in conduction an adequate risk assessment and regulation.

With this project we will address the concern of the general population regarding this kind of substances, contributing to a production of safe products, such as polypropylene plastic bottles, food cans and cash receipts, therefore minimizing the risk of toxicity for end users.

Key words:

Bisphenol A, BPA analogues, risk assessment, immunotoxicity, metabolism, kinetics, in vitro methods, ED properties, cell transformation, cognitive impairment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

A significant contribution to the PARC project will be made, providing useful data regarding BPA alternatives for both general awareness as well as for the needs of regulatory bodies. The data will provide also input for modellers working in PARC to build an experimental strategy relying only on NAMs.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP4: the availability of specific biomarkers of exposure could be used for biomonitoring studies
- WP5: Tasks 5.1b, 5.2; 5.3
- WP6: Task 6.1
- WP7: Task 7.3: data and text mining - data provision

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU
- EURION
- EU-NETVAL
- National Italian project: PRIN2017 'Endocrine disruptors: investigation of the effects on the immune and nervous systems (EDoNIS)' Ref N. 2017MLC3NF

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.1: M9 (January 2023) - Report on the workshop organised with national and EU agencies and stakeholders on the of-concern bisphenol A (BPA) alternatives.

AD5.2: M12 (April 2023) - Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted.

The project outputs will feed mainly into D5.4 - Report on closing data gaps due in M36. In addition, some results generated may also contribute to D5.3 1st new AOPs report (M24).

Expected Project Reports

A report on closing data gaps gathering the data obtained within this Project is planned for M36

Expected Projects Landmarks

None identified at present

Partners List:

INRAE (France), IBMT Fraunhofer (Germany), ISS (Italy), INRS (France), UMIL (Italy), ULFFA (Slovenia), ISCIH, CNRS (France), AUTH (Greece), TTL (Finland), MUI (Austria), LIH (Luxembourg), INSA (Portugal), MFUM (Slovenia)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05//2022

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 281,50 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 79,20 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 645 826 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 161 157 €

A5.1.2 Toxicity assessment addressing data gaps of concern (Environment) – 2 PROJECTS

P5.1.2.a_Y1_NaturalToxinsAqua_UGent

Project Title	Toxicity assessment of naturally occurring toxins on aquatic organisms		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	AquaToxins		
Project Manager	Jana Asselman Jana.asselman@ugent.be	Ghent University	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	Stefan Örn stefan.orn@slu.se	SLU	Sweden
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.1.2
Project Id	P5.1.2.a_Y1_NaturalToxinsAqua_UGent		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Natural toxins are regulated under EU regulations for human health and certain threshold values are set for safe human consumption. However, from an environmental health perspective, there are no '**predictive no effect concentrations**' (PNECs) available indicating safe exposure levels for aquatic species. In the frame of this activity, the toxicity of naturally occurring toxins will be investigated on aquatic organisms and more specifically on aquatic invertebrates and microalgae. Within aquatic ecosystems, invertebrates take up a crucial position in the food chain and the overall ecosystem as primary consumers and food sources for higher trophic levels. Microalgae are the food source for these invertebrates, being a lower level of the

trophic chain. By studying the effects of natural toxins on aquatic invertebrates and microalgae, the environmental impact of natural toxins on aquatic ecosystems can be properly assessed and the need for regulations and mitigation measures can be properly evaluated depending on the risks.

From a regulatory perspective, the results can also be integrated into the EU guidelines to achieve good environmental status for marine and freshwater environments (marine framework directive and water framework directive). It will also serve as a basis for the further regulation of nitrogen and phosphorus pollution within EU, as these contribute to eutrophication and are seen as a key driver in ‘harmful algae bloom’ (HAB) formation.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will contribute significantly to the effect assessment of natural toxins in aquatic ecosystems using standard OECD testing procedures that can be directly linked to risk assessment approaches. Particularly, the project will also provide comprehensive information on the ecotoxicity of natural toxins in mixtures using standard OECD tests and therefore contribute to a more realistic risk assessment of natural toxins and their impact on achieving good environmental status (*i.e.* water framework directive and marine framework directive).

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Although toxicological knowledge in invertebrate species may remain overlooked, they account for 95% of all species, and they are highly sensitive targets of hazardous chemicals. There is still some lack of knowledge regarding how toxins behave in mixtures of several toxins or with other chemical substances. The project will fill this data gap and the results can, together with public available data from the literature, serve as a basis to derive PNECs for aquatic species. The project will generate direct insights on the life history effects of natural toxins in single and mixture exposures in several keystone aquatic species across freshwater and marine habitats. As such, the project will be helpful to other scientists and regulators studying the impact of natural toxins on the environment.

Key words: natural toxins, aquatic ecosystems, invertebrates, algae, ecotoxicology

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will contribute to research knowledge for uptake of natural toxins, both in single as in mixture form, into regulatory assessment. The project results will provide a clear insight on the need to include natural toxins as key priority or emerging challenge.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects) (between 2-8 lines):

- **WP4:** Task 4.2 Environmental and multisource monitoring. WP4 can provide potential exposure assessments supplementing the effect assessment done here.
- **WP5:** All tasks T5.1, 2, 3. The data from our project may serve as input for Task 5.3, and also as potential alternative vertebrate testing methods relevant to T5.2
- **WP6:** Task 6.1, 6.2, 6.4 and others: Data input for regulatory/risk assessment

Links outside PARC

At this point, there are no ongoing interactions with national or international activities, which are also not taking place (as far as the partners are aware). However, the partners can build on extensive available published data which will be leveraged to ensure no duplicate work is done.

Expected Project Reports

Project Reports	Month	Partner
Ecotoxicity data for <i>Lymnaea</i> for single toxins	M24	SLU
Ecotoxicity data for <i>Daphnia</i> /marine copepods for single toxins	M24	UGent
Ecotoxicity data for <i>Lymnaea</i> for mixtures of toxins	M36	SLU

Ecotoxicity data for <i>Daphnia</i> /marine copepods for mixtures of toxins	M36	UGent
Ecotoxicity data for <i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> for single toxins	M24	UAVR
Ecotoxicity data for <i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> for mixture of toxins and toxins with other chemicals	M36	UAVR

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Landmarks	Month
Selection of individual toxins to be tested	M6
Selection of mixtures of toxins to be tested	M18

Partners List:

Ghent University, UGent (Belgium), Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, SLU (Sweden), University of Aveiro, UAVR (Portugal)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 51 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 25,50 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 64 450 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 32 225 €

P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU

Project Title	BPA alternatives and associated mixtures (data gaps and NAM development)		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Bisphenols_ENV		
Project Manager	Ludek Blaha (ludek.blaha@recetox.muni.cz) Ondřej Adamovský (ondrej.adamovsky@recetox.muni.cz)	Masarykova univerzita (MU)	Czech Republic
Deputy Project manager	Katerina Kyriakopoulou (k.kyriakopoulou@bpi.gr)	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	42
PARC Workpackage number	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	A5.1.2 A5.2.2
Project Id	P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The concerns regarding the potential adverse effects of bisphenol A (BPA) and tight restrictions of BPA in many countries has led to the development of alternative chemicals (e.g. BPZ, BPE, BPS-MAE, BPP,

BPAP, BPB, BPC, BPS, BPF, BPAF) resulting in emerging environmental contaminants found worldwide in various environmental components including water, sediment, sludge, soil, indoor dust and air. In addition, the use of BPA alternatives will be increased in the following years, since the use of BPA should be significantly reduced based on the upcoming EFSA scientific opinion in which EFSA has re-evaluated the risks from BPA in food and propose a lower tolerable daily intake (TDI) than the one previously set. Regarding their properties most bisphenols are characterized as toxic (or very toxic) to aquatic organisms, have been shown to exhibit adverse effects on the endocrine, reproduction, metabolism and immune system in different species and some of them are persistent, mobile or bioaccumulative and are characterized as PBT/vPvB or PMT/vPvM). In parallel, BPA alternatives are molecules regulated under REACH and their chemical safety assessment is carried out at different levels of comprehensiveness according to the specific data requirements based on the tonnage levels in which the substance is produced. These data are not always adequate to assess the potential adverse effects of BPA alternatives not only on human health but also on non-mammalian species, also considering the widespread use of many bisphenols and the possibility of exposure in the environment.

Finally, the current regulatory risk assessment focuses on single chemicals, widely disregarding potential adverse effects of mixtures of BPA alternatives on different organisms, especially after long-term exposure to environmentally realistic concentrations. Consequently, the assessment of combined effects of BPA alternatives and chemicals in general is recognized as one of the major needs in chemical risk assessment and this need has been highlighted in the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, in the European Green Deal and in PARC / HBM4EU prioritization survey.

Therefore, this project aims to fill the data gaps concerning the BPA alternatives (activities i and ii) and will serve as a platform for development of NAMs (activities iii-v).

Main expected outputs of the project

The specific aims and the relevant expected outputs of this project are the following:

- Investigation of the potential adverse effects (*e.g.*, apical endpoints such as mortality, effects related to the anticipated mode of action or MIE, effects on reproduction, effects on endocrine system) of certain individual substances and “real-life” mixtures of BPA alternatives on organisms belonging to different taxa (*activity i and ii*)
- Development of *in silico* and modelling tools for hazard assessment of BPA alternatives to ultimately support grouping of substances and read-across approaches based on NAMs (*activity iii*).
- Development / advancing invertebrates’ models as NAMs for the hazard assessment of BPA alternatives and/or other prioritized chemicals (*activity iv*)
- Development / advancing alternative 3R-compatible vertebrate aquatic models for environmental hazard assessment of BPA alternatives and other prioritized chemicals (*activity v*)

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The proposed activity will provide useful information for the risk assessment via the knowledge on **(i)** the toxicity of priority compounds and mixtures of BPA alternatives co-occurring in environmental components on different taxa of organisms, **(ii)** the mechanism of mixture toxicity, *i.e.*, possible additive, synergistic or antagonistic effects of these chemicals when co-occurring in the environment and **(iii)** contribute to the development of NAMs.

Furthermore, the results obtained by the abovementioned studies, including the assessment of the additional endpoints, will be exploited for the hazard assessment of BPA alternatives and other compounds providing input to delineate the mechanisms of toxicity for hazard characterization and subsequent development, enrichment with new KEs and exploitation of AOPs. This activity will provide some of the first case studies on the use of AI/Big data approaches for regulatory ecotoxicology.

Below are different regulatory fields that were identified to benefit from the outcomes of this activity:

- CLP regulation (Reg. (EC) No 1272/2008), the plant-protection-products (Reg. (EC) 1107/2009, Reg. (EC) 283/2013) and biocides regulations (Reg. (EU) No 528/2012) or the REACH regulation (Reg. (EC) No 1907/2006) (Weight of Evidence, read-across and grouping approaches).
- EFSA/ECHA Guidance for the identification of endocrine disruptors in the context of Regulations (EU) No 528/2012 and (EC) No 1107/2009.
- EU Green Deal: early identification of environmental hazardous properties with MoA-based ecotoxicity NAMs, data from NAMs could be used for prioritization for more detailed Environmental Risk Assessment
- EU Framework for Endocrine Disruptors (COM/2018/734 final): Tests covering other aspects of the endocrine system or other animal groups still needed to be developed and/or validated
- EU Strategy for Pharmaceuticals in the Environment (COM (2019) 128 final): Support research on monitoring individual substances and mixtures of substances in fresh and marine waters, soils, sediments, and wildlife, using conventional analytical and complementary techniques;
- EU Water Framework Directive - WFD (using NAMs for derivation of new-generation Environmental Quality Standard; EQS)
- EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (novel tools for field assessment of water quality; predicting pollutant effects in sediments);

Key words: data gaps, NAMs, BPA alternatives, *in silico*, *in vivo*, *in vitro*

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will contribute to the investigation and closing of data gaps regarding the hazard assessment of priority chemicals - bisphenols (single compounds and chemicals) with focus on the environment (Task 5.1b). In addition, this project will contribute to the development of innovative methodologies (NAMs) that will directly contribute to hazard identification and risk assessment not only for BPA alternatives but also for other chemicals (Task 5.2b).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP4: Task 4.2.1 and Task 4.2.2 - incorporation of environmental monitoring data into BPA selection process.

WP5: All tasks T5.1, 5.2, 5.3 - data derived in 5.1 and 5.2 will be valuable for AOP development / modeling in 5.3.

WP6: Task 6.1, 6.2 and others - discussion regarding building NAM confidence for regulatory purposes.

WP7: Data management – bilateral discussion regarding proper data storage and management.

WP3 and WP9: will be contacted for identification of synergies.

Links outside PARC

- **HBM4EU:** Information on exposure and real-life mixtures will be taken from information provided by HBM4EU.
- **POlySAFE :** French national program on assessment of plastic alternatives for food containers (Coordinated by CNRS)
- **Precision Tox:** A link to Precision Tox will be established to benefit from the 5-species 250 substances toxicogenomic approach, to create synergies and to avoid duplication of work.
- **PRORISK:** The activity will be synergized by sharing predicted and experimentally derived environmental hazard data to a novel integrative risk assessment platform developed in PRORISK (<https://prorisk-itn.eu/>) that links chemical-biological interactions, through AOPs, effects on organisms and populations up to predictions of risks for ecosystem services and the socio-economic costs of environmental damage.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.1: M9 (January 2023) - Report on the workshop organised with national and EU agencies and stakeholders on the of-concern bisphenol A (BPA) alternatives. Associated Task: 5.1. Leader of the deliverable: BPI, MU. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA

AD5.3: M12 (April 2023) - List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task: 5.2. Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU FOOD/VUB/MU

Expected Project Reports

Project Reports	Month	Partner
Progress report - advancing NAMs for the assessment of chemical mixtures including BPA alternatives (relevant for activities iii, iv and v).	12,42	INERIS, NIC, UG-PL, IISPV, EAWAG, UU, NIVA, SDU, BFG, BPI, SLU, UPO, NIB, UAnt, UFZ,
Reports on the results of toxicity assessment of BPA alternatives single compounds & mixtures (selected based on available existing data) on different organisms (relevant for activities i & ii).	28	BPI, SLU, IISPV, SDU, INERIS, NIB, IEP-NRI, UU, UG-PL, UAVP, EAWAG, CNRS
Reports on the results of toxicity assessment of BPA alternatives single compounds & mixtures (based on PARC environmental monitoring data) on different organisms (relevant for activities i & ii).	42	BPI, SLU, IISPV, SDU, INERIS, NIB, IEP-NRI, UU, UG-PL, UAVP, EAWAG, CNRS

Expected Projects Landmarks

Landmarks	Related to activity	Month
Selection of the compounds and mixtures to be tested based on available existing data and discussion among partners / stakeholders	i.-v.	M9
Selection of datasets (for <i>in silico</i> tools) and selection of endpoints for experimental tests assessing individual chemicals or their mixtures emphasizing BPA alternatives a priority chemical	iii, iv, v	M9
Selection of the compounds and mixtures to be tested based on PARC environmental monitoring data	i and ii	M30

Partners List:

Benaki Phytopathological Institute – BPI (Greece), Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences – SLU (Sweden), Institut d'Investigació Sanitària Pere Virgili – IISPV (Spain), University of Southern Denmark – SDU (Denmark), L'Institut national de l'environnement industriel et des risques – INERIS (France), National Institute of Biology – NIB (Slovenia), Institute of Environmental Protection, National Research Institute – IEP-NRI (Poland), Uppsala University – UU (Sweden), University of Gdańsk – UG-PL (Poland)*, University of Aveiro – UAVR (Portugal)*, Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology – EAWAG (Switzerland), Norwegian Institute for Water Research – NIVA (Norway), Masaryk University – MU (Czechia), Kemijski Institut – NIC (Slovenia), Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung GmbH – UFZ (Germany), Bundesanstalt fuer Gewaesserkunde – BFG (Germany), Universidad Pablo de Olavide – UPO (Spain), Universiteit Antwerpen – UAntwerpen (Belgium), Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique – CNRS (France), Medizinische Universitat Innsbruck – MUI (Austria).

* Partners to be involved from Y2 onwards

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 31/10/2025

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 808,40 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 65,65 PM *

(*only for activities i&ii, for activities iii to v date for Y1 were not collected)

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 1 027 274 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 376 446 €

T5.2 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling - 5 PROJECTS

A5.2.1 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling – 5 PROJECTS

P5.2.1.a_Y1_NGTX_INRAE

Project Title	T5.2.1_ Non-genotoxic carcinogens		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	NGTXCs		
Project Manager 1	Marc Audebert marc.audebert@inrae.fr	INRAE	France
Project Manager 2	Michael Oelgeschläger Michael.Oelgeschlaeger@bfr.bund.de	BfR	Germany
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	60
PARC Workpackage number	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	T5.2.1
Project Id	P 5.2.1.a_Y1_NGTXCs_INRAE		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project:

A range of organ and cellular model systems (including liver, breast, colon, adipocytes) will be investigated with innovative human-relevant NAMs, including state of the art transcriptomic approaches, high-content analysis, cell painting, epigenetics and high-throughput-compatible reporter systems addressing well established and relevant mechanisms of carcinogenesis, such as (oxidative) stress, epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT), inflammation, changes in metabolism, epigenetic marks or nuclear receptors signalling as well as proliferation. In addition, experimental approaches will be complemented by the optimization of *in silico* tools for the identification of NGTXCs to address the assay needs for the development of an NGTXCs IATA in cooperation with WP6.1 and ongoing activities at EU and OECD level. The project will improve our knowledge of the relationships between a range of different substances specific for distinct adverse outcome pathways that ultimately lead to cancer. In addition, methods with increasing complexity, from 2D cell culture up to 3D spheroids and zebrafish as a simple vertebrate model system, will facilitate the integration of the physiological and toxicological relevant information with respect to adversity in order to inform about potential carcinogens and to improve chemical assessment and regulation. The project will align with AOPs and IATA work under Task 5.3 as well as Task P6.1 and takes into account the ongoing work of the OECD expert group on NGTXCs as well as current EU initiatives.

Main expected outputs of the project

To develop internationally acceptable *in vitro* testing batteries (NAMs) and IATAs, the test methods (including *in silico* prediction tools) will be subject to testing of a sufficiently large set of reference compounds, including prioritized PARC compounds, to allow the evaluation of reliability and relevance taking into account sensitivity and specificity of the various systems as well as their complementarity detecting different MoAs involved on non-genotoxic carcinogenicity. The more complex systems will be further developed and optimized to allow a more physiological evaluation of activity for a subset of the reference compounds.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will be particularly helpful from a risk assessor's perspective because the innovative methods developed therein will allow for the first time a rapid mechanistic NGTXCs hazard analysis of a high number of substances thus contributing to detection of hazardous substances and to the zero pollution ambition of the green deal and the chemicals strategy for sustainability. Additionally, the methods will be capable of screening of mixtures thus also contributing to the aforementioned EU strategies. Furthermore, the utility and applicability of a shift towards a more quantitative approach for assessment of NGTxCs toxicity hazard will be explored.

In addition, the project will be helpful to other end-users like applicants from industry because as *in vitro* methods they will be rapid, reliable, cost efficient and will allow efficient product optimisation.

Stakeholders will acknowledge benefits in the reduction of animal testing, the identification and regulation of hazardous substances and ultimately, resulting from the regulatory implementation of the assays, the protection of public health and the environment.

Key words:

Carcinogenesis, 3D cell models, OMICs, MoA, risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

Some substances may induce cancer without being detectable in regulatory genotoxicity assays, namely non-genotoxic carcinogens (NGTXCs). These might act for instance as tumor promoters, modulators of nuclear receptors or as inducers of tissue-specific toxicity as well as immune and inflammatory responses. Here, the assessment of a potential hazard from chemical exposure that might lead to cancer relies on long-term rodent-based bioassays, in particular following OECD TG451 or TG453. However, these current "gold" standards are not only time-consuming, costly and require very high numbers of animals, but at the same time, are questioned due to limited human relevance. Therefore, there is an urgent need for a transition to *in vitro* and more human-relevant approaches that exploit our current understanding of cancer and employ the latest non-animal methods available in a modern safety assessment toolbox. The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), and other international regulatory authorities, have already recognized the urgent need for improvements in carcinogenicity testing and recognizes the lack of appropriate (*in vitro*) test methods or testing strategies. This NGTXCs project aims at filling this data gap by improving and implementing various test systems that address different aspects of carcinogenic mechanisms and generating sufficient data to develop an efficient and reliable testing battery or defined approach that ensures a sensitive and specific detection of non-genotoxic carcinogenic compounds.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The priorities regarding the various regulatory frameworks to be addressed will be confirmed in close collaboration with WP2 "A common science-policy agenda" and WP3 "Synergies, collaboration and awareness". Secondly, we will closely collaborate within WP5 "Hazard assessment" and with WP6 "Innovation in regulatory risk assessment" on topics related to NGTXCs and IATA development. These topics include: a) mapping of existing AOPs and associated NAMs for non-genotoxic carcinogenicity; b) interaction with the other T5.2a subjects related to endocrine disruption and immunotoxicity end-points; c) development of (quantitative) AOP networks using, among others, data generated in WP5; d) evaluation of NGTXCs IATA through case studies in WP6. The data generated in the project itself as well as the case

studies also provide a link to WP7 “FAIR data”, in which analysis of the uncertainties associated with the IATA will be one of the use cases. Lastly, this work relates to WP9 “Capacities”, since valuable learnings will be taken up in relevant training courses.

Links outside PARC

The project is closely linked to ongoing H2020 projects, in particular the ASPIS and the EURION clusters and OECD activities, including the work of the OECD Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST), the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment as well as and the OECD NGTxCs expert group.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Year 1

AD5.2: M12 (April 2023) - Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted. Associated Task: T5.1 Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA

AD5.3: M12 (April 2023) - List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU FOOD/VUB/MU

Expected Project Reports:

Project Report 1 – Provide sensitive, specific and accurate NAMs for the identification of NGTxCs.

Project Report 2 – Provide comprehensive information on the MoA of NGTxCs.

Project Report 3. – Provide additional data to allow the establishment of a reliable and efficient testing strategy.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- Selection of assays added to the NGTxCs.
- Test method set up with information provided for each method.
- Selection of the first set of test compounds for mechanistic (scientific) assay validation.
- Full NGTxCs test methods set-up.
- Selection of a large set of test compounds for mechanistic (scientific) assay validation.
- Incorporation of the test assays in AOPs/IATA

Partners List:

INRAE (FR); BfR (DE); ANSES (FR); INSERM (FR); NIB (SI); UL-LACDR (NL); UNAV (ES); IRFMN (IT); RIVM (NL); UKHSA (UK); UKL (DE); NILU (NO);

Schedule:

Starting date: May 2022

Expected ending date: April 2027

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 680 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 131 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 1 619 200 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 351 500 €

P5.2.1.b_Y1_MD-EDC_INRAE

Project Title	T5.2.1_ Metabolic Endocrine Disruption		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	MD-EDC		
Project	Daniel Zalko	INRAE	France

Manager	daniel.zalko@inrae.fr		
Deputy Project manager	Albert Braeuning Albert.braeuning@bfr.bund.de	German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment	Germany
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.2.1
Project Id	P5.2.1.b_Y1_MD-EDC_INRAE		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Over the past decade, progress in endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDC) research has demonstrated that one specific adverse effect of a number of EDC is their capability to induce a lasting disruption of endogenous metabolism. These substances, referred as "metabolism disrupting chemicals" (MDC) are largely suspected to contribute to the incidence of obesity and related metabolic disorders such as type II diabetes and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, in association with genetic factors, nutrition and lifestyle. Nowadays, more than 50 million people in Europe suffer from metabolic disorders with the role of environmental stressors (either man-made or natural chemicals) being increasingly recognized.

According to WHO/IPSC (2002), specific criteria should be fulfilled for a substance to be considered as an EDC/MDC. Despite MDC are suspected to play a major role in the worldwide epidemics of metabolic disorders, there are currently no specific regulatory *in vivo* or *in vitro* tests allowing to identify their adverse effects. From a regulatory perspective, it is thus of paramount importance to validate methodologies allowing to identify and assess MDC-associated risks. This section will focus on the development of new approach methodologies (NAM) allowing to answer key regulatory needs.

Specific compounds under investigation will come from the PARC priority list (BPA alternatives), other EU projects such as the EURION Cluster, and agencies like ECHA or EFSA. The EDC/MDC section of Task 5.2a will enhance synergies and avoid overlaps with ongoing projects such as EURION, by building on knowledge and experimental systems already established or in development, but with a focus on experimental systems not yet primarily addressed in these projects, as well as by extending the spectrum of MDC and focusing on priority-listed families of substances.

Main expected outputs of the project

A comprehensive exploration of NR-driven effects will be carried out using stably transfected cell lines, expanding the on-going pre-validation of transient cell lines in EURION. An extended spectrum of substances will be assessed for priority families, including major metabolites and breakdown molecules, allowing further MoA exploration, as well as adverse outcome pathway (AOP) and read-across development. We will develop NAMs encompassing hepatic and non-hepatic *in vitro* systems including multi-tissue cross-talk, opening the road for a refined assessment of the obesogenic effects of MDC. This will involve a deep mechanistic exploration of key cellular pathways using human *in vitro* models, as well as parallel additional 3R-compliant models and novel methods, including imagery. New developments enabling the proposal of accurate NAMs based on human as well as non-human models will enable to close major data gaps in the field of metabolic disruption, in close connection with other PARC topics, tasks and WPs.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Currently, there exists no regulatory test guidelines, approaches or testing strategies for MDCs. The sheer need for tests development in the field of metabolic disorders has been highlighted in recent work commissioned by DG Environment. In this project section, new methods will be developed for identifying MDC, with outcomes expected to be of great use for risk assessors. Work will be focused on projects aiming at a comprehensive exploration of NR-driven effects using stably transfected cell lines, expanding the on-

going pre-validation of transient cell lines. An extended spectrum of substances will be assessed for priority families, including major metabolites and breakdown molecules, allowing further MoA exploration, AOP and read-across development. We will develop NAMs encompassing hepatic and non-hepatic *in vitro* systems including multi-tissue cross-talk, to open the road for a refined assessment of the obesogenic effects of MDC. This will involve a deep mechanistic exploration of key cellular pathways using human *in vitro* models, but also additional 3R-compliant models and novel methods, including imagery. The goal is to produce new developments enabling the proposal of accurate NAMs based on human as well as non-human models, so to close major data gaps in the field of MDC, in close connection with other PARC topics, tasks and WPs.

Key words:

EDC, MDC, metabolic disruption, obesity, energy metabolism, fatty acid metabolism, metabolic disorders, metabolism, cellular signalling, NAM

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project is directly related to the PARC DoA, as it is directed towards the development of new approach methods to allow for animal-free testing of compounds. The tests to be developed to detect metabolic disruption will close a gap for which until now no specific test systems or guidelines are in place. Thereby the project will directly contribute to improved risk assessment and an elevated level of consumer protection in the EU.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- 1) Task 2.1: complementarity with guideline tests
- 2) Task 5.1a: link with the assessment of the fate of model EDs/MDCs and availability of major metabolites for testing.
- 3) Task 5.2b: link with environmental package whenever EDs are involved (e.g.data from fish can be used to inform on potential risks for human health; this is done in collaboration with WP5.2b, 5.3 and 6.1).
- 4) Task 5.3: use of NAMs for AOP development and effect marker validation
- 5) Task 6.1: use of NAMs for toxicity testing
- 6) Task 6.3: several case studies of which some are concerned with EDs

Links outside PARC

- H2020 projects HBM4EU & EDCmixrisk: compound selection.
- H2020 project cluster EURION (esp. projects GOLIATH, OBERON and EDCmet): compound selection, complementary test systems (duplication of work is avoided by focusing on other target organs and tissues), synergies in AOP and IATA development.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.2: M12 (April 2023) - Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted. Associated Task: T5.1 Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA

AD5.3: M12 (April 2023) - List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU FOOD/VUB/MU

Expected Project Reports:

- Project Report 1: Extended assessment of NR activities testing using transfected cell lines, and application of this testing strategy to major BPA alternatives, metabolites and other compounds (INSERM, M30).
- Project Report 2: *In vitro* assays for different cell types established and tools for MTOR signalling characterization established (BfR/UIBK, M34).

Expected Projects Landmarks:

No specific project landmarks to be mentioned here in addition to the deliverables and milestones mentioned above.

Partners List:

BfR (DE); NSERM (FR); IRAS (NL); (BE); UU (SE); UIBK (AT); UFZ (DE); IfADo (DE); INRAE (FR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 30/05/2025

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 347 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 95 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 329 875 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 84 188 €

P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU

Project Title	T5.2a_Endocrine disruptors – Thyroid hormone system disruption		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	ED-Thyro		
Project Manager	Terje Svingen tesv@food.dtu.dk	DTU	Denmark
Deputy Project manager	Tamara Vanhaecke Tamara.Vanhaecke@vub.be	VUB	Belgium
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.2.a ED-Thyro
Project Id	P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) has adopted the revised OECD Guidance Document 150 (OECD 2018) in its regulatory guidance for evaluating biocides and pesticides for ED activity. Despite these relative recent advances, current test strategies and regulations are inadequate with regard to specifically identifying thyroid hormone system disruptors (THSDs). Some *in vitro* assays (non-OECD TGs) for certain Molecular Initiation Events (MIEs) relevant for THSD are available and are currently in the process of regulatory validation (<https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/science-update/vitro-methods-detection-thyroid-disruptors>). However, there is still a pressing need to develop more extensive test batteries of NAMs that cover a broader range of Key Events (KEs) i.e. from MIE to Adverse Outcomes (AO). The goal of this project is to fill this gap by gaining more mechanistic knowledge on THSD for targeted NAM development. In addition, this project will also help to understand key species differences in THSD as well as *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation by relying on *in vivo* rodent studies, *in silico* assays, human relevant stem cell-derived *in vitro* systems and zebrafish as whole organism model.

Main expected outputs of the project

During the first 3-4 years of PARC, studies will be conducted that are aimed specifically at characterizing new mechanistic knowledge to enable the development of relevant NAMs, which is in line with the above-mentioned regulatory needs. Key aspects of THSD will be addressed: THS regulation and points of vulnerability to chemical perturbation, with a focus on characterizing molecular mechanisms that can be exploited for NAM testing; direct *versus* indirect perturbation of the TH axis by exogenous agents by employing sophisticated alternative test methods; building of a novel developmental stem cell-based NAM

with human relevance; characterizing further the evolutionary conservation of the THS axis in order to make better use of non-human NAMS (e.g. fish, invertebrates) to inform on human health risks.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will deliver valuable contributions to chemical safety assessors and regulators by providing evidence-based mechanistic knowledge for THSD that will enable better use of non-vertebrate animal test data for decision making. This will contribute greatly to the detection of hazardous chemical substances with focus on EDs and THSDs, thus adhering to the zero-pollution ambition of the Green Deal, as well as the Chemicals Strategy set out by the European Commission. Other end-users such as the chemical and cosmetic industry will benefit from gathered knowledge and developed test methods and strategies, as they may themselves adopt new and improved alternative test methods for a more rapid, reliable and cost-efficient internal testing regimen.

The long-term benefit for stakeholders will be a sizeable reduction in animals used for safety testing of chemical and cosmetic substances. Stakeholders will also benefit by minimizing exposure to unwanted THSDs, possibly leading to improved public health.

Key words:

Thyroid hormone system disruptors; T3; T4; endocrine; brain; liver; risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

In Europe, the chemical strategy for sustainability towards a toxic-free environment [COM (2020)667 final] places, among other priorities, a strong focus on ED and ED chemicals [COM(2018)734 final], to which THSDs belong. This project concerns THSD and directly address the PARC DoA by aiming at developing NAMs for THSD testing. The project will close much needed test-method and AOP-gaps within the thyroid hormone system. Thus, the project will contribute towards improved regulation and consumer protection for THSD chemicals.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- **WP2 Task 2.1:** complementarity with guideline tests
- **WP3:** Synergies, Communication and awareness
- **WP5: Task 5.2.2:** link with environmental package whenever EDs and THDs are involved (e.g. data from fish can be used to inform on potential risks for human health; this is done in collaboration with WP5.2.2, 5.3 and 6.1). **Task 5.3:** use of NAMs for AOP development and effect marker validation
- **WP6 Task 6.1:** use of NAMs for toxicity testing. **Task 6.3:** several case studies of which some concerned with EDs and THSDs (e.g. case study 10)
- **WP7:** Data management plan
- **WP9:** Training, laboratory network

Links outside PARC

- H2020 projects – EURION cluster: ATHENA project, SCREENED project and ERGO project
- Green Deal projects: PANORAMIX project

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Year 1

AD5.2: M12 (April 2023) - Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted. Associated Task: T5.1 Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA

AD5.3: M12 (April 2023) - List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU FOOD/VUB/MU

Expected Project Reports:

Report on the Deliverables will be provided at the end of the project (M36 and M48).

- Expand on available THS MIEs by delivering a test battery of MIEs related to thyroid hormone transporters across physiological barriers (M36).
- Establish plausibility links between TH system MIEs and downstream effects using transcriptomics of TH target tissues and of 2D-and 3D-liver (stem) cell-based cultures; validate MIEs of THSDs and provide a framework for interpretation of *in vitro* and molecular data (M48).
- Establishment and testing of *in vitro* assays, *in silico* and zebrafish/amphibian assays to identify MIEs (M36).
- Investigate the use of non-mammalian NAMs for extrapolation to human health for THSD: zebrafish embryo assays to be used in a case study for cross-species extrapolation (M36).
- Release of QSAR predictions for 650,000 substances including 80,000 REACH-preregistered / 11,000 registered substances and QMRF documentation in free Danish (Q)SAR Models website (M48)

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- Multi-organ transcriptomics (toxicogenomics) data from THSD rodents to identify pathways for incorporation in test assays or AOPs
- Toxicogenomics cross-species comparisons between rodent *in vivo* toxicity studies (liver) with human stem cell-based *in vitro* test assays
- Proteomics cross-species comparison between *in vivo* zebrafish toxicity studies with human cell-based *in vitro* assays

Partners List:

DTU (Denmark); VUB (Belgium), BfR (Germany); SDU (Denmark); UAntwerpen (Belgium); UFZ (Germany); VUA (Netherlands); ISCIII (Spain); INSERM (France)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 450,40 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 112,30 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 521 853 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 77 958 €

P5.2.1.d_Y1_Immunotox_Inserm

Project Title	Immunotoxicity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Immunotox		
Project Manager	Robert Barouki robert.barouki@u-paris.fr	Inserm	France
Deputy Project manager	Etienne Blanc etienne.blanc@u-paris.fr	Inserm	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	Task 5.2.1
Project Id	P5.2.1.d_Y1_Immunotox_Inserm		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Outline of the project. During the first three years of PARC and in line with regulatory needs we will develop research aiming at characterizing new NAMs addressing three major endpoints in immunotoxicity: organ-related immunotoxicity with a focus on respiratory toxicity and sensitization; immunosuppression, in particular through response to vaccination; characterizing new models for cellular immunotoxicity assessing key events. The major outcome will be the development of NAMs in these immunotoxicity areas. For this, reference chemicals will be used and once the NAMs are developed, PARC priority substances will be tested when relevant. These new NAMs will be used for the development of Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) (task 5.3) and the development of Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) (task 6.1).

Regulatory relevance.

- REACH: several immune related outcomes are relevant for REACH: skin sensitization, respiratory sensitization, immunosuppression. Currently under REACH, the immunotoxicity investigations are triggered based on repeated dose toxicity studies (28- or 90-day) in case there are some indications of immunotoxicity. If indications of immunosuppression are seen, one can include e.g. Cohort 3 into the study design of EOGRTS (developmental immunotoxicity) or request to have an immunotoxicity investigation included in a standard repeated dose toxicity study (adult immunotoxicity).
- CLP (Reg EC 1272/2008): While respiratory sensitization is mentioned as a hazard in the CLP regulation, it is acknowledged, that there is no respective method to detect respiratory sensitizers. Hence, a need to develop methods to detect respiratory sensitizers is recognized. On top of that the CLP regulation foresees that non-animal testing is conducted wherever possible, implying support for the development of NAMs.
- Plant protection products (Reg EC 1107/2009) and biocides (Reg EC 528/2012): Sensitization is analysed as part of the data requirements for PPP and biocides. The need to develop methods for respiratory sensitization as well as alternative testing strategies is recognized.
- Cosmetic products: skin sensitization
- Food contact materials (Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004): allergenicity
- Food contaminants (Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006) and enzymes (Regulation (EC) No 1332/2008): allergenicity
- Chemicals strategy: Immunotoxicity is listed as one of the top priority hazard classes in the chemicals strategy.

Main expected outputs of the project

This project will deliver a set of *in vitro* systems that allow the assay of key events in the immune system function or dysfunction. New parameters will be developed to better explore the immune system cellular content and activity, cytokine and antibody production and release, as well as the effect of signaling. Different primary cell systems and cell lines as well as epithelial and immune cell co-cultures will be characterized. Depending on the advancement of the work on the characterization of the NAMs, interlaboratory validation can be considered. The global aim is to provide task 5.3 and WP6 with assays and data that will support the build-up of AOPs and IATAs through a better characterization of key events in NAMs.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will be helpful from a risk assessor's perspective because the innovative methods developed therein will allow rapid mechanistic hazard analysis of a high number of substances thus contributing to detection of hazardous substances, to the Zero Pollution Ambition of the Green Deal and to The Chemicals Strategy. Additionally, the methods will be able to screen mixtures thus contributing to the aforementioned EU strategies. In addition, the project will be helpful to other end-users like applicants from industry as *in vitro* methods they will be rapid, reliable and cost efficient. Stakeholders will see benefits in the reduction of animal testing, the identification and regulation of hazardous substances and ultimately in the benefits for public health ultimately resulting from the regulatory implementation of the assays.

Key words: immunotoxicity, sensitization, immunosuppression, vaccination, inflammation, NAMs, tests,

AOPs

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The aim of PARC is to develop new toxicity tests in compliance with the 3R concept, particularly in outcomes that have been prioritized in the chemical strategy for sustainability. Immunotoxicity is one of these outcomes and this project directly addresses this objective.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- **WP2, Task 2.1:** complementarity with guidelines tests
- **WP4, Task 4.1:** immunotoxicity studies in human (the COVID-19 vaccination study)
- **WP5, Task 5.2b:** complementarity with environmental immunotoxicity, **Task 5.3:** use of NAMs for AOP development and effect marker validation
- **WP6, Task 6.1:** use of NAM for IATA/DA validation for regulatory purposes: NAM will be developed that feed into these IATAs.

Links outside PARC

- H2020 project on persistent and mobile chemicals (PFAS)
- EHEN projects on immune effects of the exposome: Hedimed and Eximious
- EURION projects, including Oberon, Goliath, EDCmet
- ASPIS projects including Ontox, RISKHUNT3R, PrecisionTox
- Polyrisk,
- Aurora
- VHP4Safety
- MOMENTUM
- EFSA (sensitization)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Year 1

AD5.2: M12 (April 2023) - Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted. Associated Task: T5.1 Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA

AD5.3: M12 (April 2023) - List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU FOOD/VUB/MU

Expected Project Reports:

- Characterization of *in vitro* systems relevant for respiratory immunotoxicity: usefulness, limitations, testing strategy: This project will explore different *in vitro* systems relevant for respiratory immunotoxicity and will characterize their usefulness and limitations. A testing strategy will be proposed based on the different systems. **(M36)**
- Immunosuppression and response to vaccination: *in vitro* or *ex vivo* systems relevant to human health. A chemical-induced decrease in response to vaccination reflects immunosuppression and this was investigated in several epidemiological and experimental studies. This project will combine studies in human, animal and in different primary cells and cell lines to determine common markers of immunosuppression and response to vaccination and identify the most relevant *in vitro* or *ex vivo* system relevant to human health. **(M36)**
- *In vitro* systems to assay key events in the immune system function or dysfunction. This project will deliver a set of *in vitro* systems that allow the assay of key events in the immune system function or dysfunction. New parameters will be developed to better explore the immune system cellular content and activity, cytokine and antibody production and release, as well as the effect of nuclear receptors. Different primary cell systems and cell lines as well as epithelial and immune cell co-cultures will be characterized. The global aim is to provide task 5.3 and WP6 with assays and data that will support the build-up of AOPs and IATAs through a better characterization of key events in NAMs. **(M36)**

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Landmarks are defined in each partner's project and cannot be defined globally.

Partners List:

INSERM (France), NIPH (Norway), MUI (Austria), NPHC (Hungary), RIVM (Netherlands), IRAS

(Netherlands), UL-FFA (Slovenia), INSA (Portugal), UFZ (Germany), WFSR (Netherlands), LIH (Luxemburg)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 432,10 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 132,20 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 769 717 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 243 271 €

P5.2.1.e_Y1_Neurotox_UFZ_IUF_UU

Project Title	Neurotoxicity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	DNT / NT		
Project Manager	Tamara Tal tamara.tal@ufz.de	UFZ	Germany
Deputy Project manager	Ellen Fristche ellen.fristche@iuf-duesseldorf.de	IUF	Germany
Deputy Project manager	Joëlle Rüegg joelle.ruegg@ebc.uu.se	UU	Sweden
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M 05	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.2.1
Project Id	P5.2.1.e_Y1_Neurotox_UFZ_IUF_UU		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Developmental (DNT) and acute (ANT) neurotoxicity are currently assessed via different OECD guideline studies. DNT/ANT guideline studies are extraordinarily resource-intensive and therefore not suited for studying adverse effects of large numbers of chemicals. In Reach regulation, DNT guideline studies are not mandatory and ANT testing is not performed for low tonnage compounds. There is international consensus, strongly supported by EFSA and the OECD that DNT testing has to be made faster and more human-relevant by implementing an alternative DNT testing battery for regulatory purposes.

The key strategy is to provide a comprehensive battery of NAMs that for DNT fills the gaps in the current DNT *in vitro* battery (IVB) and, for ANT, sets up such a battery, both according to DNT/ANT modes-of-action. The focus solely lies on (i) human cells that avoid the problem of species specificity and (ii) zebrafish, an alternative whole organism, low-cost screening tool with integrated nervous system functions. Novel methods include endocrine disruption-induced DNT, transcriptomic and epigenetic effects, synaptogenesis, neural network formation and function, blood-brain-barrier formation, myelin toxicity, startle response, anxiety-like behavior, and learning and memory tests. As there are currently not many neurotoxicity adverse outcome pathways (AOP) available, new AOPs will be generated (with T5.3). Methods newly established or optimized in this WP will undergo test method set-up and mechanistic

validation.

Main expected outputs of the project

- **New NAMs that fill the current DNT *in vitro* testing battery (IVB) gaps.** Here, test methods will be set up from existing test systems (human stem cell-based systems, zebrafish).
- **New NAMs for ANT.** Current test systems will be used for test method set-up (human stem cell-based systems, zebrafish).

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

- Additional IVB NAMs developed for DNT/ANT will provide **risk assessors** with rapid mechanistic hazard analysis supporting the green deal and the chemicals strategy.
- Mixture screening in these NAMs contributing to the aforementioned EU strategies.
- **Industry** will be strongly supported by developed NAMs as they will serve as valid tools for pre-screening and in-house prioritization based on rapid, reliable and cost-efficient methods.
- **NGOs** and **consumers** will see benefits in the reduction of animal testing, identification and regulation of hazardous substances and ultimately, in the benefits for public health upon regulatory implementation of the assays.

Keywords: Developmental neurotoxicity (DNT), Acute neurotoxicity (ANT), Alternative DNT testing battery, *in vitro* testing battery (IVB), New Approach methodologies (NAMs)

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

In the EU Green Deal strategy, the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability specifically mentions neurotoxicity (DNT/ANT) as well as endocrine disruption-related developmental neurotoxicity (ED-DNT) as critical outcomes. Moreover, mental and behavioral health are part of the children's health protection policy. Due to large data gaps, DNT has been recognized as a serious public health concern by many countries and regulatory agencies world-wide. The OECD provides the umbrella for current regulatory DNT efforts including the production of a guidance document for regulatory use of the DNT IVB. Within PARC, gaps within the DNT IVB will be closed and an ANT IVB will be established.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- **WP4:** Make use of results from human biomonitoring studies for prioritizing hazard assessment.
- **T5.1.** Toxicity testing to address chemicals of concern. **T5.3:** Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs that are relevant for DNT/ANT.
- **T6.1:** Delivering IATAs ready for regulatory application. WP 5.2 will provide data, tools and concepts to improve risk assessment in general. DNT (ANT is to be clarified) is a priority area for developing qAOP but not in the first round (ED, non-genotoxic carcinogenesis and liver are first).
- **WP7:** Data management plan. We will link with WP7 to make our data available, as soon as possible, for regulators, external researchers, and public. We need access to a database where we can store data, with immediate access for regulators and embargo dates for public use.

Links outside PARC

ENDpoiNTs and other projects within the EURION cluster. In ENDpoiNTs, a battery of assays (in silico, in vitro and in vivo) are developed that detect ED-induced DNT.

- ONTOX, Precisiontox and RiskHunter of the ASPIS cluster.
- H2020 Panoramix (panoramix-h2020.eu)
- US-EPA for common data analysis and DNT IVB assembly.
- ATHLETE project of the European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) cluster (athleteproject.eu).
- VHP4safety Virtual Human Platform for Safety Assessment – VHP4Safety
- Human Biomonitoring Plattform Austria

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes Year 1

AD5.2: M12 (April 2023) - Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted. Associated

Task: T5.1 Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA
 AD5.3: M12 (April 2023) - List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task
 T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU FOOD/VUB/MU

Expected Project Reports:

- Project Report 1: Development of NAMs relevant for detection of ANT
- Project Report 2: Fill existing gaps in the DNT IVB
- Project Report 3: Different zebrafish assays for complementing the DNT and ANT IVB with behavioral/cognitive function tests.

Partners List:

INSERM-UBX (FR); UU (SE); NIPH (NO); IUF (DE); UKON (DE); RIVM (NL); UFZ (DE); ISCIII (ES); TiHo (DE); AIT (AT); NMBU (NO);

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 456,80 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 122,55 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 1 118 135 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 171 151 €

A5.2.2 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling for Environmental Toxicology / Ecotoxicology

No project submitted at present.

T5.3 Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs - 3 PROJECTS

A5.3.1 Prioritized NAM-based mechanistic hazard characterization – 1 PROJECT

P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR

Project Title	Systems toxicology approaches for mechanism-based chemical safety assessment.		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SysTox		
Project Manager	Bob van de Water b.water@lacdr.leidenuniv.nl	UL-LACDR	NL
Deputy Project manager	Olivier Taboureau olivier.taboureau@u-paris.fr	INSERM	FR
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Work package	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-	T5.3.1 and

number		activity:	T5.3.3
Project Id	P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The SysTox project is part of WP5 and reflect the activities of T5.3.1 and T5.3.3. It involves the evaluation of mechanistic data for a quantitative hazard characterization. The AOP framework is becoming a driver for next generation risk assessment (NGRA) that is based on new approach methods (NAMs). These NAMs can be both *in silico* and *in vitro* approaches. The AOP framework is of importance for the diverse regulatory agencies, including ECHA, EFSA and SCCS. Mapping and quantifying MIE activity and KE activation is essential for the ultimate application of the AOP framework in chemical safety assessment. Systems toxicology involves the holistic quantitative assessment of perturbations of biological systems by chemicals and typically involves omics approaches, including transcriptomics and metabolomics. Omics approaches are used in human toxicology as well as ecotoxicology, hence systems toxicology can be applied to both areas. To derive confidence in the application of NAM-based omics data, there is a necessity to determine the relevance of *in vitro omics* data with the *in vivo* situation. Various bioinformatics approaches are available to uncover hazard. There is a need to understand the validity of each method with respect to the qualitative and quantitative characterization of hazards. In this project we will validate innovative *in silico* and bioinformatics approaches for quantitative chemical hazard assessment. We will also address the human *in vivo* relevance of *in vitro* findings. We aim to establish an initial framework for the application of omics data in a regulatory setting. The ultimate aim is that a quantitative assessment of hazard will contribute to classification of chemicals for specific health effects related to EDC, immunosuppression, DNT, NonGenotoxic carcinogenesis, areas that are of critical relevance for PARC. An omics-based hazard characterization will also contribute to prioritization of chemicals that might need further testing.

Main expected outputs of the project

We will have established innovative approaches for mechanism-based hazard assessment based on *in silico* prediction and omics approaches. This will involve both QSAR-based prediction of critical MIE activation as well as quantitative assessment of KE activation based on omics data. In addition, we will provide confidence in the relevance of *in vitro* transcriptomics responses with respect to responses occurring in the human *in vivo* situation.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will have important impact on the risk assessor's perspective because the innovative interactive online systems toxicology tools will allow rapid mechanistic understanding of novel omics data. Moreover, the data obtained from the public domain will provide information for AOP development and underpinning. The project will generate direct insight in the gene networks that may provide quantitative input for qAOPs. In addition, the project will increase the certainty for the application of omics data from *in vitro* NAMs as a reflection of the human pathophysiology. In addition, the project will be helpful to other end-users like applicants from industry since it will allow a cross-sector application of systems toxicology in a structured manner using similar bioinformatics tools. This will allow commonalities in the understanding of omics technologies in a quantitative manner for determination of point-of-departure for risk assessment. Since the project will be based on the application of omics using advanced human test systems, stakeholders will also see benefits in the reduction of animal testing. Finally, our systems toxicology-based project will allow for the regulatory implementation of omics strategies and, thereby, for the efficient mechanism-based identification and regulation of hazardous substances that will benefit public health.

Key words:

Omics, transcriptomics, systems toxicology, gene network, key events, human translation

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The SysTox project directly links to the DoA of WP5 T5.3: Quantitative systems toxicology and

development of new AOPs.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The SysTox project is linked to the following tasks:

- Task 4.1: human studies and effect markers à translate candidate biomarkers from SysTox studies to human biomonitoring effect markers.
- Task 5.1, 5.2: complementarity with gap filling studies (5.1) and experimental studies and NAM development (5.2) à data from T5.1 and T5.2 will be used in case study.
- Task 5.3.2: use of NAM data for AOP development and effect marker validation à findings from SysTox project can be used in Project 5.3.2.
- Task 6.1: development of qAOPs and IATA validation à information from SysTox can be used for data gap filling for qAOP development.
- Task 6.2: mixture effects à mixture effects can be quantitatively addressed through SysTox tools
- Task 7.3: data and text mining à data provision
- WP8: SysTox bioinformatics tools can be integrated in toolbox
- WP9: training of bioinformatics tools for regulators

Links outside PARC

The project will liaise with the below projects, clusters and initiatives to identify datasets that will be of importance for the SysTox project. Focus will be on omics datasets. This includes interactions with:

- EURION cluster
- EHEN projects on immune/neuro effects of the exposome: Hedimed and Eximious
- EU-ToxRisk project
- ASPIS cluster projects on application of NAM for chemical safety assessment: RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX, PrecisionTOX.
- H2020 green deal project on persistent and mobile chemicals (PFAS)
- OECD - Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST) and the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment (WPHA)
- US EPA and US NIEHS/NTP

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.4 Inventory of *in vitro*, *in vivo* and human omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected outcomes. M12

Expected Project Reports

- Report on the inventory of *in vitro*, *in vivo* and human omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts and bioinformatics approaches in public domain repositories at PARC partners for all selected adverse outcomes. (AD5.4, M12)
- Report on the applicability domain of systems toxicology bioinformatics approaches for regulatory implementation. M26
- Report on translation of systems toxicology data from *in vitro* NAM to human *in vivo*.

Expected Projects Landmarks

- Workshop on systems toxicology: data requirement and strategy; M9
- Datasets required for systems toxicology in data management systems; M16
- Novel human datasets for *in vitro* to *in vivo* translation established; M24

Partners List

Ugent (BE), MUI (AT), ISCII (ES), INSERM (FR), UHC (DE), ISS (IT), UL-LACDR (NL), BPI (GR), KIT (DE), NPHC (NO), WFSR (NL), Sciensano (BE), NIPH (HU), UNIABDN (UK), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), IRFMN (IT), UIBK (AT), UMIL (IT), AUTH (GR), IISPV (ES).

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 353,4 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 116,3 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 261 258 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 83 307 €

A5.3.2 AOP development based on integration – 1 PROJECT

P5.3.2.a Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm

Project Title	AOP Development		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	AOP		
Project Manager	Robert Barouki robert.barouki@u-paris.fr	Inserm	France
Deputy Project manager	Karine Audouze karine.audouze@u-paris.fr	Inserm	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.3
Project Id	P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The AOP is a framework for the causal relationships between molecular initiating events (MIE), subsequent key events (KE) at different biological levels and ultimately adverse outcomes. AOPs are developed by integrating and connecting data from various sources i.e. databases and the scientific literature, in a logical sequence of causally-linked events. New methodologies provide a large diversity and amount of data that are very challenging if not impossible to implement in regulatory application or mechanistic toxicology unless they are integrated and represented in a useful and widely accepted framework like AOP would become.

In PARC, AOP development will be focused on the selected priority outcomes related to immunotoxicology, neurotoxicology, non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, endocrine disruption and metabolic disruption. These are the priorities of WP5, in particular for NAM and AOP development. Different groups will first identify available AOPs (if any), gaps in knowledge, and will develop AOPs related to these outcomes. One group will focus on methodologies and tools for AOP development and another group will identify putative effect markers based on available AOPs. There will be a close interaction and exchange between the AOP projects and those activities related to NAMs (task 5.2) and systems biology (activities 5.3.1, 5.3.3) as well as those concerning IATA development and risk assessment (task 6.1).

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will be helpful from a risk assessor's perspective because the innovative methods developed therein will allow rapid mechanistic hazard analysis of a high number of substances thus contributing to detection of hazardous substances and to the zero pollution ambition of the green deal and the chemicals

strategy. Additionally, the methods will be capable of screening of mixtures (AOP network) thus also contributing to the aforementioned EU strategies. AOPs are currently used by different agencies to support for hazard identification. They are the basis for IATA development and for the identification of relevant effect markers

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will be helpful to end-users like applicants from industry because as a screening tool it will be rapid, reliable and cost efficient. Stakeholders will see benefits in the reduction of animal testing, the identification and regulation of hazardous substances and ultimately in the benefits for public health resulting from the regulatory implementation of the assays. Other possible outcomes:

- Develop protocols to optimize data collection, appraisal, synthesis and visualization based on artificial intelligence
- Acquire available and most recent information on toxicity pathways leading to immune and hormonal dysregulation, neurotoxicity and non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, including chemicals able to interfere with all the identified pathways
- Identify missing data, inconsistencies and scientific gaps that might affect extrapolation in a regulatory setting
- Link to the AOP-Wiki database contributing to the AOP- Knowledge Base project launched by OECD

Key words:

AOP, method, immunotoxicology, neurotoxicology, non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, endocrine disruption, metabolic disruption, development

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

In PARC, AOP development will be focused on the selected priority outcomes related to immunotoxicology, neurotoxicology, non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, endocrine disruption and metabolic disruption. These are the priorities of WP5, in particular for NAM and AOP development. There will be a close interaction and exchange between the AOP projects and those activities related to NAMs (task 5.2) and systems biology (activities 5.3.1, 5.3.3) as well as those concerning IATA development and risk assessment (task 6.1).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP2, Task 2.1: complementarity with guidelines tests

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness

WP4, Task 4.1: Human studies and effect markers

WP5, Task 5.2, 5.1: complementarity with experimental studies and NAM development. Task 5.3: use of NAMs for AOP development and effect marker validation

WP6, Task 6.1: development of qAOPs and IATA validation, Task 6.2: mixture effects, Task 6.3: text mining

WP7, Task 7.3: data and text mining. Data management plan

WP8, Task 8.2: emerging chemicals

WP9: Training

Links outside PARC

- H2020 green deal project on persistent and mobile chemicals (PFAS)
- EURION: European Cluster to improve identification of Endocrine Disruptors
- EHEN projects on immune/neuro effects of the exposome: Hedimed and Eximious
- EU-ToxRisk project
- ASPIS cluster projects on application of NAM for chemical safety assessment: RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX, PrecisionTOX.
- OECD - Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST) and OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment (WPHA)
- US EPA and US NIEHS/NTP
- EFSA, ECHA, EEA

- PEPPER

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Year 1

AD5.4: M12 (April 2023) - Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes. Associated Task T5.3. Leader of the deliverable: UL-LACDR/ SCIENSANO. Associated Task co-leaders: UL-LACDR/ SCIENSANO/INSERM/ Fraunhofer

AD5.5: M12 (April 2023) - Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC. Associated Task: T5.3 Leader of the deliverable: INSERM. Associated Task co-leaders: UL-LACDR/ SCIENSANO/INSERM/ Fraunhofer

AD5.6: M12 (April 2023) - Mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints. Associated Task T5.3. Leader of the deliverable: INSERM. Associated Task co-leaders: UL-LACDR/ SCIENSANO/INSERM/ Fraunhofer

Expected Project Reports:

- Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritization and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC.
- Progress report on AOP development in priority endpoints; M36. This report will summarize the PARC activities leading to the development or initiation of new AOPs as well as additions to previous AOPs. The focus is on the priority outcomes of the first 3 years.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Workshop on AOP methodologies and guidelines; M8

Partners List:

ACES or SU (SE); AU (DK); AUTH (GR); BfG (DE); BPI (GR); DTU (DK); IISPV (ES); Inserm (FR); IRSN (FR); ISS (IT); KI (SE); KIT (DE); KU-Leuven (BE); MUI (AT); NIPH (NO); NPHC (HU); UG-PL (PL); SDU (DK); Sciensano (BE); UAntwerpen (BE); UGent (BE); UHC (DE); UIBK (AT); UL-LACDR (NL); UMIL (IT); UNIVIE (AT); WFSR (NL); NILU (NO)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022, M1

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025, M36

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 415,45 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 120,88 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 206 744 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 56 690 €

A5.3.3 Translation to human pathophysiology

No project submitted at present.

A5.3.4 PBTK models and quantitative systems toxicology – 1 PROJECT

P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer

Project Title	PBK models and quantitative systems toxicology
Project	PBK_Kinetics

Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Manager	Sylvia Escher sylvia.escher@item.fraunhofer.de	ITEM	DE
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub- activity:	T5.3.4
Project Id	P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The aim of this project is to develop physiologically based kinetic (PBK) models and to integrate PBK models with AOPs as a basis for quantitative systems toxicology needed to predict adverse outcomes from realistic chemical exposure levels. This project is part of WP5 and reflects activities of T5.3.4. It involves the evaluation of kinetic data to establish physiological based kinetic (PBK) models suitable for *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation (IVIVE). IVIVE is one key aspect in hazard characterisation, as this process derives a human equivalent concentration in plasma or tissue, which can be used as point of departure for specific end-points in the risk assessment process. Moreover, PBK models will be needed for the systems toxicological framework (links to AOP-development in project SysTox), when progressing from AOPs to quantitative AOPs.

There is a need to integrate realistic biological factors that influence individual variability in bioavailable concentrations into existing PBK models in order to understand the validity of each model in terms of quantitative hazard characterisation.

There is for example a need to better understand the impact of the human microbiome into the already existing PBK models; to date a neglected component to the overall kinetics process.

Thus, we will establish generic models that describe the human organism on the basis of compartments defined by physiological parameters. Compound-specific input data will be derived by the validation and use of *in silico* and *in vitro* ADME approaches. PBK models for oral as well inhalation exposure will be created, and we will also integrate factors such as metabolic effects of the human microbiome.

The output of this project will be IVIVE-PBK-models for use with *in vitro* and *in silico* ADME data. To create these, we will compare PBK model predictions with ADME data measured *in vivo* from data-rich model compounds, and to some extent PARC priority compounds and classes (in WP4, WP5 and WP6). We will determine reliable scaling factors for corresponding *in vitro/in silico* ADME models.

We aim to establish an initial framework for the application the IVIVE-PBK models in a regulatory setting. The ultimate aim is that a quantitative assessment of hazard will be possible starting from the *in vitro* hazard identification in 5.3.1 and 5.3.3. This work will therefore contribute to characterise the hazard of chemicals for specific health effects related to endocrine disruptive compounds (EDC), immunosuppression, DNT and NonGenotoxic carcinogenesis, areas that are of critical relevance for PARC, possibly identifying a PoD for the risk assessment.

Main expected outputs of the project

We will have established innovative approaches to characterize the ADME processes of priority compounds by integrating *in silico* prediction and *in vitro* ADME data into PBK models for oral and inhalation exposures, accounting for uncertainty linked to relevant biological processes.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will have important impact on the integration of NAM based approaches into regulatory risk assessment because the innovative bottom up IVIVE-PBK model will allow the characterisation of the absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME) of chemicals in the human organism. *In vivo* ADME data are to date available only for few chemicals, as *in vivo* ADME studies are generally not within the standard regulatory test requirements. Moreover, the extrapolation from the *in vitro* bench mark concentration to a human equivalent concentration or dose, called qIVIVE, is a key element to NAM based hazard characterization. This will enable users to determine POD for RA based on standardized interpretation and quantitative analysis of NAM data such as omics data. Thereby the project links directly to the project 1 and 2 in WP5.3 in this reporting period.

In addition, the project will show the applicability and by this will promote use of *in vitro* and *in silico* ADME data in PBK models for predicting human *in vivo* data. In addition, the project will be helpful to other end-users like applicants from industry since it will allow a cross-sector application of kinetic modelling in a structured manner using similar PBK models.

Finally, this PBK project will enable regulatory implementation of NAM-based approaches and thus the efficient mechanism-based identification and regulation of hazardous substances, which will benefit public health.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The PBK_kinetic project directly links to the DoA of WP5 T5.3: Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The PBK_kinetic project is linked to the following tasks:

- Task 5.1, 5.2: complementarity with gap filling studies (5.1) and experimental *in vitro* ADME studies (5.2) à data from T5.1 and T5.2 will be used in case studies to develop and validate IVIVE-PBK approaches.
- Task 6.1: development of qAOPs and PBK models to be integrated into IATAs. à information from PBK_Kinetics can be used for qIVIVE and for qAOP development.
- Task 7.3: Data and text mining à data provision
- WP8: PBK_Kinetics bioinformatics tools can be integrated in toolbox
- WP9: training of PBK models for regulators

Links outside PARC

The project will liaise with the below projects, clusters and initiatives to identify datasets that will be of importance for the PBK_kinetic project. Focus will be on *in vitro*, *in silico* ADME model data, PBK modelling approaches as well as concepts for tiered testing strategies, starting from simple to more complex testing. This includes interactions with:

- EURION cluster
- EHEN projects on immune/neuro effects of the exposome: Hedimed and Eximious
- EU-ToxRisk project
- ASPIS cluster projects on application of NAM for chemical safety assessment: RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX, PrecisionTOX.
- H2020 green deal project on persistent and mobile chemicals (PFAS) like ZeroPM
- OECD – IATA case studies
- EFSA ADME4NGRA
- US EPA and US NIEHS/NTP

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.4: Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes. M12 (April 2023)

AD5.5: Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC. M12 (April 2023)

AD5.6: Mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints. M12 (April 2023)

Key Project Reports

- Report on *in vitro* and *in silico* ADME models available and needed for PBK case studies on model and priority compounds; M12
- Report on conceptual data gaps in IVIVE-PBK models and the thereof started case studies; M24
- Report on the first uncertainty analyses of case studies; M36

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- Workshop with WP5.1 and 5.2 on data requirement and strategy for their implementation for the proposed case studies; M10
- Case studies defined and data needs and deadlines communicated to all involved partners in 5.1 and 5.2; M14
- Workshop on the applicability of the IVIVE-PBK framework from this project to the needs in WP6.1 and 6.2; M26

Partners List:

ANSES (FR); ETHZ (CHE); IISPV (ES); INERIS (FR); Inserm (FR); ISCIII (ES); ISS (IT); ITEM (DE); NVI (NO); UHC (DE); UIBK (AT); UL-LACDR (NL); UNIVIE (AT); WFSR (NL); WU-Tox (NL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 346,40 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 112,70 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 2 488 276 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 810 548 €

WP6 Innovation in regulatory risk assessment – 40 PROJECTS

T6.1 Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment of Chemicals 4 PROJECTS

A6.1.1 Development of IATAs for regulatory purposes – 4 PROJECTS

P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM

Project Title	Workflow for Human Relevance Assessment of AOPs and Associated New Approach Methodologies		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Human Relevance		
Project Manager	Mirjam Luijten Mirjam.luijten@rivm.nl	RIVM	NL
Deputy Project manager	Elisavet Renieri elisavet_renieri@hotmail.com	AUTH	GR
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.1.1

Project Id	P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM
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Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The goal of Task 6.1 (T6.1) in PARC is to deliver Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA) for a selected set of health effects. The majority of the IATAs will focus on human health, which will be developed and evaluated in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders. Key elements of an IATA include Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) and new approach methodologies (NAMs). This project is focused on the assessment of human relevance of AOPs and the relevance of NAMs related to the key events (KEs) or key event relationships (KERs) of the pathway under study. Such assessment requires a harmonized and accepted workflow. A framework for analysis of mode of action (MOA)/human relevance has been developed in initiatives of WHO/IPCS. In spite of detailed methodological instructions, additionally provided templates and case studies, application of the framework in practice, including the analysis of species concordance, remains challenging. Therefore, this project aims to further optimize an existing draft workflow (v0.1) that was developed based on the WHO/IPCS framework. The refinements will be done in close collaboration with WHO, OECD and other international and regulatory organizations, to ensure its readiness for regulatory implementation. The goal is to establish a harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment and to demonstrate its applicability through dedicated case studies. The resulting assessments will directly feed into IATAs developed in PARC.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main output of the project is a pragmatic, harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of both AOPs and its associated NAMs, accompanied by a set of case studies demonstrating how the workflow can be applied.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

A pragmatic, harmonized workflow for the assessment of human relevance of AOPs will inform on which networks of AOPs should be covered by an IATA for human health risk assessment, while assessment of the relevance of NAMs related to the key events (KEs) or key event relationships (KERs) of the pathways under study will inform on which NAMs are well suited to be used for a regulatory assessment. Together, this information is highly valuable for end-users and other stakeholders.

Key words

human relevance, Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs), toxicological mechanisms, New Approach Methodologies (NAMs), weight of evidence, Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA)

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

PARC aims to deliver approaches to next-generation risk assessment. These approaches will, among others, involve IATAs and NAMs. Assessment of the human relevance of AOPs and the relevance of NAMs related to KEs and KERs is crucial for the development of IATAs that are fit-for-purpose.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is directly linked to the following PARC projects:

1. P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA-ED_UAntwerpen
2. P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA-GENTOX_Sciensano
3. P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA-STOT_UL-LACDR

To maximize synergy across the T6.1 projects, core teams addressing common elements will be established. These core teams include “AOP networks”, “Quantitative AOPs”, and “IATA development/evaluation”. The project team involved in the project on human relevance will closely collaborate with the other three projects, in particular with the core teams on AOP networks and quantitative AOPs.

WP2, A common science-policy agenda: Achievement of regulatory readiness of the workflow for human relevance assessment will require dedicated discussions with various international regulatory bodies, to ensure that regulatory needs are being addressed.

WP3, Synergies, Communication and awareness: The development of a workflow that is ready for regulatory implementation will strongly benefit from raising awareness, proper communication of the (draft) workflow and collecting feedback from stakeholders by WP3.

WP7, Data management plan: see below for the section Data Management.

WP9, Training, laboratory network: Implementation of the workflow in regulatory processes will be greatly facilitated by training courses, developed as a joint activity of WPs 9 and 6.

Links outside PARC

The project will build on, among others, the Mode of Action/Human Relevance framework developed by the WHO/IPCS. It is also closely linked to the OECD AOP programme and IATA case studies. In that context, regular interactions with the OECD Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST) and the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment (WPHA) are foreseen. Additionally, human relevance assessment is a topic of high interest to ILMERAC and the project will benefit from guidance documents on weight of evidence and uncertainty developed by e.g., EFSA.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The output from this project will substantially contribute to the following key deliverables/additional deliverables/milestones of WP6:

- D6.5; D6.12: Reports on IATAs and associated case studies (M42; M81)
- D6.11: Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs (M72)
- AD5.5: Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (M12; INSERM)
- AD6.2: Report on case studies for interim evaluation of IATAs (M12; UL-LACDR).

Expected Project Reports:

Reports are foreseen for year two and beyond. These will be explicitly mentioned in the respective AWPs.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Landmark 1: Inventory of relevant available approaches and frameworks, including available approaches for uncertainty analysis and weight of evidence, available (M10)

Landmark 2: Case studies for testing and evaluating workflow v0.1 defined (M13)

Landmark 3: Case studies for v0.1 discussed with relevant stakeholders (M24)

Partners List:

AUTH (GR); RIVM (NL); ENSP-UNL (PT); BPI (GR); WU-TOX (NL); NIPH (NO); STAMI (NO); ISS (IT); DTU (DK); IISPV (ES); LIST (LU); IRSN (FR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 104 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 34.7 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 110 729 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 29 413 €

P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA_ED_UAntwerpen

Project Title	Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for Endocrine Disruption
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	IATA-ED

Project Manager	Dries Knapen Dries.knapen@uantwerpen.be	UAntwerpen	BE
Deputy Project manager	Miriam Jacobs Miriam.Jacobs@ukhsa.gov.uk	UKHSA	UK
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.1.1
Project Id	P6.1_Y1_IATA-ED_UAntwerpen		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The goal of this project within Task 6.1 (T6.1) in PARC is to deliver Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA) for endocrine disruption (ED), one of the health effects that has been prioritized in the EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. Criteria for the identification of endocrine disrupting compounds have been stipulated for the Biocidal Products Regulation or the Plant Protection Products Regulation and a guidance document, i.e., “Guidance for the identification of endocrine disruptors in the context of Regulations (EU) No 825/2012 and (EC) No 1107/2009”, was written to guide identification of endocrine disrupting chemicals to comply with these obligations. In addition, other regulations such as REACH and the Cosmetic regulation also require information on the endocrine disruptive potential of chemicals. The OECD guidance document 150 provides guidance on the application and use of standardised TGs (Test Guidelines) for the evaluation of chemicals for endocrine disruption (2018), which include oestrogen, androgen and steroidogenesis endpoints but this does not provide details of assays. Therefore, there is an urgent need to develop IATAs for the identification of endocrine disrupting chemicals both in a human and environmental health context. This will structure, identify key gaps and facilitate direct regulatory application of PARC outcomes. Whilst at the moment there are no standardised *in vitro* assays for thyroid hormone system disruption (THSD) (OECD Revised GD150, 2018), standardisation and further review is in progress under the auspices of the OECD, based upon the assays documented (OECD Series on Testing and Assessment 207, 2014). Some of the ED toxicological pathways are considered low-hanging fruit for IATA development on the basis of test method developments and existing data. This is especially the case for THSD, for which the first IATA will be developed, and for anti-androgenic adverse effects, for which a second IATA will be developed. To ensure that the IATAs will address regulatory needs, they will be developed in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders and evaluated through dedicated case studies.

Main expected outputs of the project

The first main expected output is an IATA for THSD. Effects on the hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid axis are considered low-hanging fruit because of the relatively large number of AOPs available (e.g. Noyes et al 2022) or under development for this system and the ongoing project to assess the pre-validated *in vitro* assays for the detection of THSD, conducted at the JRC, the USEPA, and within the EURION cluster. Anti-AR signaling, and metabolic disruption work, following the completion of the EURION projects at the end 2023 will be considered as next priorities.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Regulatory strategies for identifying endocrine disrupting chemicals in line with the advancing legislation in this context are mostly lacking. This project will ultimately enable better regulatory decision making and significantly improve the hazard identification of endocrine disrupting chemicals with the long-term aim to limit exposure and improve human as well as environmental health. The use of predictive methods and NAMs will significantly reduce the need for long-term, low-throughput and costly toxicity tests requiring large numbers of animals, thus contributing to the replacement of animal tests.

Key words

Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA), Endocrine disruption (ED), Thyroid hormone system disruption (THSD), Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP), Risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project responds to Specific objective 3 (SO3) “European risk assessors, their scientific network and the wider stakeholder community have access to the R&I capacities required to implement innovative chemical RA”, and more specifically to Operational Objective 9 “Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA”.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

To maximize synergy across the T6.1 projects, core teams addressing common elements will be established. These core teams include “AOP networks”, “Quantitative AOPs”, and “IATA development/evaluation”. The work described in this project is further connected to other WPs in PARC. Firstly, the proposed priorities regarding regulatory frameworks to be addressed will be confirmed with stakeholders in close collaboration with WP2 “A common science-policy agenda” and WP3 “Synergies, collaboration and awareness”. Secondly, we will closely collaborate with WP5 “Hazard assessment”, especially with T5.3.2 on AOPs and with T5.2 on NAMs to be used in IATAs. For the evaluation of IATAs through case studies, we will also closely collaborate with T6.2 – T6.4 and WP7 “FAIR data”, in which analysis of the uncertainties associated with the IATA will be one of the used cases. Lastly, this work relates to WP9 “Capacities”, since valuable learnings will be taken up in relevant training courses.

Links outside PARC

The project is closely linked to the OECD Task Force on Endocrine Disruptors Testing and Assessment (EDTA), the EURION cluster and the PEPPER platform. It is also linked to work ongoing at OECD in relation to thyroid hormone system assay assessment, AOP development (OECD’s AOP programme) and IATA case studies. As such, regular interactions with the OECD Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST) and the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment (WPHA) are foreseen.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The output from this project will substantially contribute to the following key deliverables of WP6:

- D6.5; D6.12: Reports on IATAs and associated case studies (M42; M81; Sciensano)
- D6.11: Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs (M72, RIVM)
- AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (M12; INSERM);
- AD6.2 Report on case studies for interim evaluation of IATAs (M12; UL-LACDR).

Expected Project Reports:

Reports are foreseen for year two and beyond. These will be explicitly mentioned in the respective AWPs.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Landmark 1: AOP network for ED and associated assays defined (M8)

Landmark 2: First data for ED collected (M18)

Landmark 3: Framework for qAOP for ED defined (M24)

Partners List:

UAntwerpen (Belgium); UKHSA (United Kingdom); MU (Czechia); AUTH (Greece); UGent (Belgium); INSERM (France); UL-LACDR (Netherlands); RIVM (Netherlands); ISS (Italy); DTU (Denmark); SDU (Denmark); LIST (Luxembourg); BPI (Greece); UG-PL (Poland); IISPV (Spain); STAMI (Norway); KI (Sweden); IRFMN (Italy); ENSP-UNL (Portugal); Sciensano (Belgium); CEFAS (UK)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01-05-2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30-04-2025 (M36)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 313.4 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 82.10 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 284 123 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 68 131 €

P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano

Project Title	Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for Genotoxicity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	IATA-GENTOX		
Project Manager 1	Birgit Mertens birgit.mertens@sciensano.be	Sciensano	BE
Project manager 2	Marc Audebert marc.audebert@inrae.fr	INRAE	FR
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.1.1
Project Id	P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The goal of Task 6.1 (T6.1) in PARC is to deliver Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA) for a selected set of health effects. The majority of the IATAs will focus on human health; however, environmental health will also be addressed in some projects. To ensure that the IATA will address regulatory needs, they will be developed in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders and evaluated through dedicated case studies. This project is focused on IATA development for genotoxicity, one of the health effects that has been prioritized in the EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. Moreover, genotoxicity is considered a low-hanging fruit for IATA development based on existing data and available test systems. The test strategies for genotoxicity that are in place under the current regulations for the different regulatory frameworks are somewhat similar but often rely on animal testing, and do not integrate NAMs such as Pig-a, Multiflow, ToxTracker or transcriptomic-based gene expression biomarkers. By delivering an IATA, the project aims to move towards the assessment of genotoxicity without the use of animals.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main expected output of the project is an IATA for genotoxicity that is based on an AOP framework. This will include an overview of the test methods and assays that can be applied and a quantification AOP framework for this endpoint. Information on absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME) will be integrated as well through collaboration with T5.3. The applicability of the IATA will be demonstrated by means of case studies. Overall, this project will provide a conceptual framework for the application of an AOP-based IATA for the assessment of genotoxicity that can be included for future assessment.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project impact on stakeholders and end-users will involve a defined IATA for genotoxicity that can be

applied for safety testing. It will allow insight in a defined testing approach including the test methods to assess this endpoint without the use of animals. Furthermore, assessment of genotoxic potential is closely linked to assessment of carcinogenic potential due to the strong association between the accumulation of genetic damage and cancer. Hence, this project also directly relates to the ongoing review of the REACH testing requirements to see how they could be amended (if appropriate) to allow identification of carcinogens irrespective of the registration volume band. Where feasible, case studies to test and evaluate the IATA will also address the revised requirements for REACH. Furthermore, the utility and applicability of a shift towards a more quantitative approach for assessment of genetic toxicity hazard will be explored.

Key words

Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA), genotoxicity, DNA damage, gene mutations, chromosome damage, (quantitative) Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP), key events

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will deliver an IATA for genotoxicity. Such a testing strategy could be integrated in future alternative testing strategies without the use of animals. This is an important objective of PARC.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

For T6.1 the project is linked to the three other T6.1 projects in PARC:

1. P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM
2. P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA_ED_UAntwerpen
3. P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR

To maximize synergy across the T6.1 projects, core teams addressing common elements will be established. These core teams include “AOP networks”, “Quantitative AOPs”, and “IATA development/evaluation”. The project team involved in the project on human relevance will closely collaborate with the other three projects, in particular with the core teams on AOP networks and quantitative AOPs.

The work described in this project is connected to other WPs in PARC, in multiple ways.

Firstly, the proposed priorities regarding regulatory frameworks to be addressed will be confirmed with stakeholders in close collaboration with WP2 “A common science-policy agenda” and WP3 “Synergies, collaboration and awareness”. Secondly, we will closely collaborate with WP5 “Hazard assessment” on various topics related to IATA development. These topics include: a) mapping of existing AOPs and associated NAMs for genotoxicity; b) development of (quantitative) AOP networks using, among others, data generated in WP5 (e.g. data generated with toxins); c) linkage to QIVIVE and PBK modeling (T5.3) and evaluation of IATA through case studies. Within WP6, the case study *T6.3_CS11: Analysis and evaluation of genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment across legislations, with a special focus on (Q)SAR based approaches* will be particularly relevant for the mapping of existing AOPs but also for the evaluation of IATA through case studies, we will closely collaborate with T6.2, T6.3 and T6.4. The case studies also provide a link to WP7 “FAIR data”, in which analysis of the uncertainties associated with the IATA will be one of the use cases. Integrative models developed in T8.3 of WP8 will be considered as well. Lastly, this work relates to WP9 “Capacities”, since valuable learnings will be taken up in relevant training courses.

Links outside PARC

The project is closely linked to work done by the HESI Genetic Toxicology Technical Committee (GTTC), on AOP development and Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA). It is also linked to work ongoing at OECD, in relation to NAMs for genotoxicity (e.g., ToxTracker and miniaturized versions of the bacterial reverse gene mutation test), AOP development (OECD AOP programme) and IATA case studies. As such, regular interactions with the OECD Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST) and the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment are foreseen. The link with the work on AOP development for radiation effects done within the context of the MELODI project will also be investigated.

Finally, wherever applicable and relevant, a link to ongoing activities on IATAs for non-genotoxic carcinogenicity will be made as well.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The output from this project will substantially contribute to the following key deliverables of WP6:

- D6.5; D6.12: Reports on IATAs and associated case studies (M42; M81; Sciensano)
- D6.11: Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs (M72, RIVM)
- AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (M12; INSERM);
- AD6.2 Report on case studies for interim evaluation of IATAs (M12; UL-LACDR).

Expected Project Reports

Reports are foreseen for year two and beyond. These will be explicitly mentioned in the respective AWP.

Expected Projects Landmarks

Landmark 1: AOP network for genotoxicity and associated assays defined (M8)

Landmark 2: First data for genotoxicity available (M18)

Landmark 3: Framework for qAOP for genotoxicity defined (M24)

Partners List

Sciensano (BE), INRAE (FR), VUB (BE), UL-LACDR (NL), WU-TOX (NL), ISS (IT), IBMT (DE), UG-PL (PL), STAMI (NO), LIST (LU), BPI (GR), IRSN (FR), RIVM (NL), KWR (NL), NILU (NO), IRFMN (IT), MUI (AT), NIPH (NO), WFSR (NL).

Schedule

Starting date: 01-05-2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30-04-2025 (M36)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 253.84 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 81.71 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 442 792 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 151 397 €

P6.1.1.d Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR

Project Title	Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for Systemic Target Organ Toxicity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	IATA-STOT		
Project Manager	Bob van de Water b.water@lacdr.leidenuniv.nl	UL-LACDR	NL
Deputy Project manager	Joost Beltman j.b.beltman@lacdr.leidenuniv.nl	UL-LACDR	NL
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.1.1

Project Id	P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR
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Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The goal of Task 6.1 (T6.1) in PARC is to deliver Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA) for a selected set of health effects. The majority of the IATAs will focus on human health; however, environmental health will also be addressed in some projects. To ensure that the IATA will address regulatory needs, they will be developed in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders and evaluated through dedicated case studies. This project is focused on IATA development for specific target organ toxicity (STOT). The project will initially focus on liver toxicity, and at a later stage, but in parallel, other types of target organ toxicity will be started such as respiratory toxicity. Liver toxicity is the most often observed toxic effect in 90-day studies and also considered low-hanging fruit for IATA development based on existing data and liver test systems. Yet, liver toxicity is complex and involves different end-points that typically have different mechanisms as well as time course for development. An initial focus will be on liver fibrosis as a critical endpoint. In contrast, for respiratory toxicity there is a need for IATA development and implementation/application of scientifically developed in vitro methods. Lung fibrosis is an important human health end-point and we will consider how an IATA for liver fibrosis could be generalized to other target organs, including lung fibrosis.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main expected output of the project is an IATA for liver toxicity with an initial focus on liver fibrosis that is based on an AOP framework. This will include an overview of the test methods and assays that can be applied and a quantification AOP framework for this endpoint. This project will provide a conceptual framework for the application of an AOP-based IATA for the assessment of STOT that can be included for future assessment of systemic toxicity. The case study of the project will demonstrate the applicability of the established IATA.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

There is currently no IATA for liver toxicity. The project impact on stakeholders and end-users will involve a defined IATA for liver fibrosis that can be applied for safety testing. It will allow insight in a defined testing approach including the test methods to assess this end-point without the use of animals. Moreover, it will move beyond a qualification and also give a quantitative assessment of the involved assays in relation to the adverse outcome.

Key words

Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA), systemic toxicity, liver, fibrosis, (quantitative) Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP), key events

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will deliver an IATA for liver fibrosis. Such a testing strategy could be integrated in future alternative testing strategies without the use of animals. This is an important objective of PARC.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is linked within the following PARC activities:

For T6.1 the project is linked to three other projects in T6.1:

1. P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM
2. P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA_ED_UAntwerpen
3. P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano

To maximize synergy across the T6.1 projects, core teams addressing common elements will be established. These core teams include “AOP networks”, “Quantitative AOPs”, and “IATA development/evaluation”. The project team involved in the project on human relevance will closely collaborate with the other three projects, in particular with the core teams on AOP networks and quantitative AOPs.

The work described in this project is connected to other WPs in PARC, in multiple ways.

Firstly, the proposed priorities regarding regulatory frameworks to be addressed will be confirmed with

stakeholders in close collaboration with WP2 “A common science-policy agenda” and WP3 “Synergies, collaboration and awareness”. Secondly, we will closely collaborate with WP5 “Hazard assessment” on various topics related to IATA development. These topics include: a) mapping of existing AOPs and associated NAMs for endocrine disruption; b) development of (quantitative) AOP networks using, among others, data generated in WP5; c) linkage to QIVIVE and PBK modeling (T5.3); and c) evaluation of IATA through case studies. For the latter, we will also closely collaborate with T6.2 – T6.4. The case studies also provide a link to WP7 “FAIR data”, in which analysis of the uncertainties associated with the IATA will be one of the use cases. Lastly, this work relates to WP9 “Capacities”, since valuable learnings will be taken up in relevant training courses.

Links outside PARC

Furthermore, the project is closely linked to the Horizon2020 projects EU-ToxRisk, RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX and PrecisionTox, and to work ongoing at OECD in relation to AOP development (OECD AOP programme) and IATA case studies. As such, regular interactions with the OECD Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST) and the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment (WPHA) are foreseen.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The output from this project will substantially contribute to the following key deliverables of WP6:

- D6.5; D6.12: Reports on IATAs and associated case studies (M42; M81; Sciensano)
- D6.11: Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs (M72, RIVM)
- AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (M12; INSERM);
- AD6.2 Report on case studies for interim evaluation of IATAs (M12; UL-LACDR).

Expected Project Reports

Reports are foreseen for year two and beyond. These will be explicitly mentioned in the respective AWP and include a report on liver fibrosis case study for interim evaluation of IATAs (M24).

Expected Projects Landmarks

Landmark 1: AOP network for liver fibrosis and associated assays defined (M8)

Landmark 2: First data for liver fibrosis available (M18)

Landmark 3: Framework for qAOP for liver fibrosis defined (M24)

Partners List

UL-LACDR (NL), WU-TOX (L), INSERM (FR), Ugent (BE), AUTH (GR), MU (CZ), IISPV (ES), STAMI (NO), ISS (IT), IRFMN (IT), WFSR (NL).

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 139 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 41.2 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 211 952 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 64 637 €

A6.1.2 Evaluation of IATAs through case studies

No project submitted at present.

A6.1.3 Stakeholder engagement

No project submitted at present.

T6.2 Integrative exposure and risk assessment - 8 PROJECTS

A6.2.1 Aggregate exposure from multiple sources and routes for general population and workers – 2 PROJECTS

P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO

Project Title	Developing, performing and validation of source to dose modelling including selected case studies		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SourcetoDose		
Project Manager	Katleen De Brouwere katleen.debrouwere@vito.be	VITO	BE
Deputy Project manager	Radu Duca radu.duca@lms.etat.lu	LNS	LU
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	M36
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.1
Project Id	P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

This project aims to model from sources to doses, the human exposure of general population to chemicals, potentially arising from a variety of sources and routes. Sources include different types: environmental sources including 1) emissions from industrial facilities, traffic and households, etc. 2) diffuse environmental sources (e.g. historical soil contamination, water etc), and 3) consumer sources present in our everyday life, (e.g. construction products, household products, etc.) potentially releasing chemicals that may enter our bodies.

It is anticipated that for some source and route of exposure, models do exist, but are (overly) conservative in nature because of their intended uses for screening purposes. However, when it comes to combination of exposures from different sources into an aggregated exposure (and comparison with HBM values) and health impact assessment, realistic external exposure models are crucial, and needed for policy makers (e.g. in view of comparing impact of different policy or risk management options).

This project is connected to the project on aggregate exposure modelling. The scope of this project will be routes and sources for which realistic exposure models are currently lacking. Where models are lacking, they will be developed. Where possible, we will rely on existing models and improve them in order to shift from screening models to higher tier models generating realistic exposure estimates.

This project focus is on modelling as a complementary tool to human biomonitoring, for the general population (occupational exposure is out of scope). Case studies will be tailored toward chemical classes in line with PARC projects (e.g. case studies on PFAS, flame retardants, metals, pesticides).

The ultimate goal is to come up with robust, mechanistic model(s) and tools which are, at the same time relatively simple in use for risk assessors.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Improvement of existing models for generating realistic exposure assessment for selected consumer articles or products, and environmental sources

- Development of new model(s) for routes and sources for which there is currently a lack of models (for selected sources)
- Transcription of the conceptual model(s) to T8.3

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The output of the project (a demonstrated, validated set of modelling tools generating realistic exposure estimates) will be useful as input for the aggregation of exposures from different sources and routes in the 6.2.1 project ‘strategy for aggregate exposure’.

For the purpose of aggregation of exposures from different sources and routes, it is very important that the inputs for different sources and routes are based on modelling are realistic. Otherwise, aggregation of several overly conservative exposure estimates will not lead to realistic aggregated exposure estimates, hypothesizing an appropriate selection of adequate risk management options. The role of modelling in aggregate exposure assessment is that modelling offers a complementary tool to human biomonitoring to perform chemical risk assessment.

This project will make it possible to end-users to perform risk assessment for chemicals (environment and consumer exposure) covered in this project. It will offer end-users the opportunity 1) to expand the assessment to other groups not included in HBM studies (e.g. specific age groups, vulnerable groups), 2) to assess the relative contribution of different sources and exposure routes, and 3) to calculate the impact of risk management options (e.g. predicting impact of restrictions, mitigations). The latter can inform policy makers about the most efficient risk management strategies thus allowing for better informed decision making

The development/improving, performing and validation of source to dose modelling includes two main aspects: 1) direct and indirect exposure to chemicals present in consumer products and articles, and 2) direct and indirect exposure to chemicals present in the environment. Throughout the project, application of scientifically sound models in selected case studies will be central (case studies covering hotspots and diffuse contamination). This will help policy makers and other stakeholders to understand the models and the obtained results.

In a next project in the subsequent years of PARC, the applicability of the models towards other sources (consumer and articles) and chemical groups will be considered.

Key words: human exposure, modelling, consumer exposure, exposure *via* the environment, realistic exposure modelling, migration, articles

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will contribute to the aim of T6.2 to develop innovative and practical approaches for human health risk and impact assessment of single, aggregated and combined exposure to chemicals via multiple sources across regulatory silos and routes during lifetime, and to foster their regulatory uptake. Relative contributions of sources and routes will be determined from aggregate exposure to support effective RM measures. Living and working environment as well as chemical transfer from soil to water, food, and air and migration from consumer products, articles and materials will be integrated to advance knowledge on the exposure sources.

This project will the model exposures covered under different regulatory process (REACH, CLP, Plant protection products, Biocides, Cosmetic products, Food contact materials, Construction Products, Waters, Consumer products etc.) and will provide tools to assess and compare impacts of relevant management options. By combining exposures from multiple sources and scenarios of exposure through different routes (oral, dermal, inhalation), the project will support PARC’s contribution to the “one substance, one assessment” approach.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Connection with T4.1 (HBM data from T.4.1 will be used to validate the model outcome)
- Connection with A6.2.1 Interoperability of models for aggregate exposures:
 - gaps identified will steer the priorities in 6.2.1

- model outcomes generated in this project can be included in aggregate exposure modelling in 6.2.1.
- Connection with T8.3: outcome (model) will be taken up in T8.3
- Project “Strategy for aggregate exposure from general life and occupational exposures” (project P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES)
- Projects from T8.3

Links outside PARC

This project will start from the work of previous initiatives such as the ones from ISES Europe and the REACH Exposure Expert Group (REEG), HBM4EU (WP 12), and 7th FP projects (e.g., 4-FUN)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- AD6.3. Roadmap on aggregated exposure strategy through different living environments sources and routes (M12)
- D6.1. 1st Report on aggregate exposure for general population and workers, and source to dose models applied to case studies (M36)

Expected Project Reports:

- Report 1: Conceptual model for human exposure to chemicals from the environment, including inventory of available data and models for selected cases studies and recommendations for data and model generation (M12)
- Report 2: Conceptual model for consumer exposure to chemicals in articles, including inventory of available data and models for selected cases studies and recommendations for data and model generation (M18)
- Scientific article on case studies for the migration from articles and transfer from environment (M36)
- Scientific article on case studies for transfer from environment to human exposure (M36)

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- Selection of exposure routes and sources for which there is a lack of realistic source to dose exposure models (M12)
- Availability of data (e.g., exposure factors, transfer parameters, physico-chemical properties) to feed the exposure models, or to (M24)

Partners List:

VITO (BE); RIVM (NL); ANSES (FR); SPAQUE (BE); LNS (LU); IVV (DE); CSTB (FR); KWR (NL); IVL (SW); NIJZ (SI); FOPH (CH); GeoZS (SI); FMUL (PT)

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/25 (M36)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 76 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 38.6 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

None identified at present.

P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_Anse

Project Title	Strategy for aggregate exposure from general life and occupational exposures		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Aggregate		
Project Manager	Crépet Amélie amelie.crepet@anses.fr David Vernez david.vernez@unisante.ch	ANSES UNISANTE	France Switzerland

Deputy Project manager	NA	NA	NA
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	May 2022	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.1
Project Id	P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

In the context of a compartmentalized view of risk assessment, this project aims to advance knowledge on the combination of various exposure environments including occupational and general life exposures. It will help to propose a more integrative risk assessment and management crossing regulatory silos. This project will draw up the strategy to aggregate exposures from multiple sources and routes in considering both general life and occupational exposures. It is divided into three parts. The first one aims to review available models, tools and data and draw a functional design for model connection. The second part is to work on methods and criteria to perform aggregate exposure and the last part is to organize and start the relevant case studies selected from the defined criteria and PARC priorities. Building from current knowledge, this project is an important step to propose advanced aggregate exposures assessment from multiple sources and routes. It will provide a better understanding of the main sources and routes of exposure during occupational and general life to support effective risk management measures.

Main expected outputs of the project

Model interoperability and data inventory

- Model and tools description and structural analysis
- Functional design for model connection for T8.3
- Data inventory for T7.1 and data gaps to be feed by T4.1, T4.2.

Methods for aggregate exposure

- Strategy and roadmap for aggregate risk assessment
- Innovative methods to perform aggregate risk assessment
- Criteria for prioritisation of case studies
- Advance knowledge on the combination of various exposure environments including occupational and general life exposures

Case studies for aggregate exposure

- Selected relevant case studies of aggregate exposure including general life and occupational exposures
- Prioritization of main sources and routes of exposure from general life and occupational exposures

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Provide tools to facilitate comparisons between entry routes and exposure situations and, ultimately, prioritize areas for action and prevention. This project will also make it possible to end-users to perform risk assessment from several sources and routes of exposure. It will make possible to account for both general life and work activities in risk assessment. Concrete case studies will be conducted for prioritized chemicals.

Key words: Aggregate exposure, multiple sources, multiple routes, risk mitigations, occupational exposures, general life exposures,

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project will aggregate the exposures from different regulatory process (REACH, CLP, Plant protection products, Biocides, Cosmetic products, Food contact materials, Construction Products, Waters, Consumer products etc.) and will identify main sources and routes to propose relevant management options.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

This project is also strongly connected to other projects from T6.2. As example aggregate exposures can be used as input in mixture (P6.2.3) and health impact projects (P6.2.4). The output of the sources to dose (P6.2.1.a) and PBPK projects (P6.2.2.a) can be used as input of this project.

This project will be strongly connected to the T8.3 on integrative models in involving the task leader WR-BIOM. The objective is to deliver the functional design to task T8.3 for its implementation.

The data inventory will be conducted in connection with the T4.1 and T4.2 and the results of the data gap analysis will be discussed with the leaders to see how they can be handled.

A connection with T7.3 on methods to combine data to account for uncertainty will be also done as aggregate exposure can be a good case study.

It can also propose input for training in WP9.

Links outside PARC

This project will start from the work of previous initiatives such as the ones from ISES Europe and the REACH Exposure Expert Group (REEG). It is also linked to the Scientific Committee Consumer Safety.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.3. Roadmap on aggregated exposure strategy through different living environments sources and routes (including inventory of databases, models and tools (M12)

D6.1. 1st Report on aggregate exposure for general population and workers, and source to dose models applied to case studies (M36)

Expected Project Reports:

Proposal of reports that can be changed and aggregated during the project

- Inventory of existing models and tools for general population and occupational exposure assessment, data and model gaps analysis (M12, INSA/ ISCII)
- Functional design for model connection including structural analysis and model selection (M24, WR-BIOM)
- Roadmap on aggregated exposure strategy through different living environments, sources and routes (M12, UNISANTE/ANSES)
- Access to relevant databases and models organized for selected case studies and needs for data collection and kinetic models addressed to WP4, WP5 and 6.2.2 (M12, UU/NIJZ)
- Minimal corpus of information for exposure determinants to deal with a large set of occupational situations (M12, Unisante/FIOH)
- Scientific articles on first case studies and identification of main exposure sources and routes (M48)

Expected Projects Landmarks:

None identified at present.

Partners List: ANSES, UNISANTE, RIVM, VITO, UU, NIOM, INSA, TNO, SPAQUE, NIJZ, AU, FIOH, RUMC, GeoZS, LNS, ISSeP, CSTB, EFSA, MU, WR-BIOM, CSIC, INRS, NIPH, KWR, IVL, ISCII, OVAM, FOPH, STAMI, FMUL, ENSP-UNL, IVV, etc.

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 596 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 153 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 812 000 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 116 000 €

A6.2.2 Modelling exposure through life – 1 PROJECT

P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPk_INERIS_AUTH

Project Title	Refinement and development of PBPk models for human risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PBPk		
Project Manager	Céline BROCHOT celine.brochot@ineris.fr	INERIS	France
Deputy Project manager	Spyros KARAKITSIOS spyros.karakitsios@gmail.com M1	AUTH	Greece
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.2
Project Id	P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPk_INERIS_AUTH		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Although we are in the phase of transition in risk assessment, we lack comprehensive methodological workflows for evaluating multiple lines of evidence associated with both exposure related (environmental, route, personal activity and exposure, HBM) and hazard related data using NAMs (*in vitro* testing). In this sense, the assessment of internal-external exposure provides unique opportunities in advancing risk assessment, by employing refined (internal) exposure metrics that account for ADME differences related to developmental stage, gender, route of exposure or genetics. PBPk models were identified as essential tools in risk assessment since they connect external exposure with internal exposure metrics and might help in the interpretation of NAMs data in the risk assessment.

PBPk (Physiological Based Pharmacokinetic) models are continuously gaining ground in regulatory toxicology, describing in quantitative terms the absorption, metabolism, distribution and elimination processes in the human body, with a focus on the effective dose at the expected target site. Considering the continuously growing interest of using PBPk models in risk assessment process, guidelines for proper species, doses, and exposure scenarios extrapolations have been proposed. The mechanistic basis of PBPk models is well adapted to toxicological risk assessment (US EPA, 2006; IPCS, 2010; OECD, 2021), in particular for dealing with extrapolations inherent to these domains (*in vitro* to *in vivo*, laboratory animals to humans, various exposure or dosing schemes, etc.). In addition, PBPk models can also be used to compare subgroups (sex, age, and sensitive population), characterise inter-individual variations, support read-across between substances by comparing kinetic profiles of structurally similar substances, and assist in predicting levels at the organs of interest as identified in the hazard assessment to predict the margin of safety. They can also address increased vulnerability during critical developmental windows of susceptibility, such as foetal stages and childhood. It could also be due to developmental physiology and exploratory behaviours of children, but also to the immaturity of their xenobiotic detoxifying processes or different adiposity during early stages of development. Moreover, such strategies are in line with the OECD AOP concept, which is considered as an important guideline to compile tests.

The ever-increasing computing capabilities and the advent of statistical approaches applicable to uncertainty and population variability modelling have turned PBPk models into well-developed tools for risk assessment of chemical substances. The need for the widespread use of PBPk model is amplified by the continuously increasing scientific and regulatory interest about aggregate and cumulative exposure; PBPk models translate external exposures from multiple routes into internal exposure metrics, addressing the effects of exposure route in the overall bioavailability. Also, they can be employed to translate a target

HBM GV using PBPK modelling to the corresponding external exposure.

The scope of the project is the refinement and the development of PBPK models for compounds in PARC prioritization process and with a large scientific and regulatory interest. In particular, this project will fill gaps in the assessment of the internal exposure (i.e., in the human body) of single compounds or mixtures.

The HBM4EU project has already identified and reviewed the available PBPK models for about 30 compounds, but the review emphasized the lack or paucity of toxicokinetic data for a high number of these prioritized compounds specially for the inhalation (very important for occupational settings) and dermal (very important for assessing exposure to cosmetics) exposure routes for which absorption and metabolism data are lacking for most substances. The HBM4EU review of the PBPK models also highlighted that models and data are lacking for sensitive populations as the pregnant women and their fetuses, newborns, young children, or elderly.

In this project, PBPK models will be refined or developed to address the different sensitivities resulting from the interindividual variability of population sub-groups by integrating the evolution of physiological and biochemical processes through life, the aggregation of multiple exposure routes and sources, the interpretation of biomonitoring data (e.g., concentrations of parent compounds or metabolites in blood, urine, hair or nails), and the mixtures of chemicals. Different sources of data will be used (either from literature, or from synergies with WP5), for refining or developing PBPK models necessary for the use of internal dose metrics for risk assessment. This project will be done in close collaboration with WP5 (generation of toxicokinetic data), WP4 (HBM data), WP8 (implementation in platforms), and WP2 (prioritization of chemicals and exposure scenarios) and other activities of WP6 (e.g. activity 6.2.1 on the aggregate exposures or activity 6.2.3 on mixtures).

Compounds of increased regulatory interest will be investigated, including bisphenols (BPA, BPS, BPF and other bisphenols), per- and polyfluoroalkyl compounds (PFAS), pesticides, metals, and natural toxins. Therefore, the project will address several compounds regulated under different frameworks:

- bisphenols, as a case study that includes both data rich (BPA) and data poor analogue compounds (BPS, BPF), related to food, consumer products and food contact materials,
- PFASs are related to air, water, food, food contact materials and consumer products and articles, and soil contamination (diffuse and hotspots) and the related transfer from soil and water to the food chain.
- Pesticides, that belong to plant protection products and biocides.
- Metals, that are regulated in environmental and food contaminants frameworks
- Natural toxins like mycotoxins, that are regulated in the food contaminant domain.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main outputs of the project will be to:

- Review available and relevant PBPK models for risk assessment and identify the experimental needs with WP5.
- Develop generic PBPK models for sub-groups of the human populations: pregnant women, fetuses, newborns, young children, teenagers and the elderly. The existing models and tools (e.g., the EFSA platform TKPlate) will be reviewed and complemented.
- Adapt the generic PBPK models for the aggregation of the exposures through the three routes (oral ingestion, inhalation, and dermal contact) and three sources of exposure (occupational, consumer, and environmental).
- Investigate the kinetic interactions for mixture exposures with PBPK modelling. The exposures will be determined from HBM data to select relevant doses and mixtures of chemicals.
- Develop QSARs for PBPK models that pertain to parameters related to kinetics and partitioning, so as to expand the applicability domain of the generic PBPK models (e.g., including analogue hazards).
- Integrate in PBPK models new biomarkers of exposure predictive of specific exposure, such as the concentration of chemicals in hair or meconium for newborns.
- Make the models developed in this task interoperable (in collaboration with WP7 and WP8) with open platform used for risk assessment, e.g. TKPlate, MCRA and INTEGRA.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

As PBPK models are tools used to support risk assessors and managers, it is essential to provide models that are adapted to their requirements and that follow the most up-to-date guidance, e.g., the OECD document on the characterisation, validation and reporting of PBK models for regulatory purposes (Series on Testing and Assessment No. 331, ENV/CBC/MONO(2021)1). This project within PARC will focus on the refinement or development of PBPK models for prioritized compounds and mixtures, e.g., with limited information, sensitive populations, and the aggregation of the various exposures. The models that will be proposed will be made interoperable (in collaboration with WP7 and WP8) with other modules in integrative open platforms used for risk assessment.

Key words: PBK models; multi-route exposures; lifelong exposure; sensitive human sub-groups; metabolic interactions; barrier models.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The PBPK project directly links to the DoA of WP6 T6.2: Integrative exposure and risk assessment. The PBK models developed in this project will address the different sensitivity of humans within a population. They will also be adapted for estimating and reconstructing chemical exposure through life, accounting for varying exposure scenarios and physiological and biochemical characteristics over time. These PBK models will simulate the concentrations in target tissues will be linked to AOPs and IATAs (WP5, WP6 task 6.1).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Activities undertaken in WP5 (Tasks 5.1, 5.2, 5.3) for the generation of toxicokinetic data and the development of AOP, WP8 (Task 8.3) for the model integration in an open platform, WP4 for the availability of HBM data.

Other T6.2 projects that aim to link internal and external exposures from multiple sources and for mixtures:

- Strategy for aggregate exposure in order to confirm external exposure assessment with HBM data.
- New risk assessment and exposome methodologies to reduce exposure and risk of real-life mixtures

Links outside PARC

Bisphenols, PFAS, pesticides, metals and mycotoxins have been priority compounds among the HBM4EU project and modelling efforts, as well as review of existing models and identification of gaps has been carried out.

Some compounds are also endocrine disruptor compounds that are studied in the EURION cluster, specifically in the OBERON project.

Links to the exposome projects, such as ATHLETE.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.4: Inventory of PBK models for assessing the internal exposure through life (M12)

D6.2: Innovative methods based on PBK models (M36)

Expected Project Reports:

Report 1: Refinement of existing/development of PBPK models towards multi-route and lifelong exposure (M36)

Report 2: Case studies of the application of refined/developed PBPK models in the risk assessment process (M48)

Expected Projects Landmarks: None identified at present.

Partners List: INERIS (France), AUTH (Greece), IISPV (Spain), ANSES (France), RIVM (Netherlands), SLU (Sweden), NIPH (Norway), VITO (Belgium), WR-BIOM (Netherlands), WR-WFSR (Netherlands), IRFMN (Italy), IVL (Sweden)

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 233 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 78 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 50 400 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 16 800 €

A6.2.3 Mixture exposure and risk assessment – 1 PROJECT

P6.2.3.a Y1 RealLifeMixtures_RIVM

Project Title	New risk assessment and exposome methodologies to reduce exposure and risk of real-life mixtures		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	RealLifeMixtures		
Project Manager	Amélie Crépet Amelie.crepet@anses.fr Jacob Van Klaveren jacob.van.klaveren@rivm.nl	Anses RIVM	France Netherlands
Deputy Project manager	NA	NA	NA
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	M48
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.3
Project Id	P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

In many European Member States there is concern about existing mixtures of chemicals present in our daily food and/or our living environment. There are different views among stakeholders on the size of the mixture problem. At the Member State level, national institutes responsible for risk assessment are frequently asked to perform assessments to respond to these societal concerns (e.g. mixtures of PFAS or pesticides). There is a need for better understanding the magnitude of the mixture problem by interpretation of real-life mixture exposure observations and better identification of the sources of exposure to reduce the exposure whenever necessary. The mixture concerns are reflected in the prioritisation process and were ranked as a high priority for many stakeholders and Member States. Furthermore, there is a need to regulate chemicals in such a manner that potential mixture effects are already considered in the registration or authorisation process (prospective risk assessment of mixtures).

The project will build on scientific progress made on mixture risk assessment, by international organisations (such as EFSA, EEA and ECHA, EC-JRC), regarding hazard based grouping of chemical and statistical approaches developed in previous project such as Euromix, HBM4EU and exposome projects (EHEN and Athlete). The project combines risk assessment and epidemiological approaches to support scientific needs from Member States, DG SANTE and DG Environment. It will integrate the needs identified in the Chemical Strategy and the linked EC Policy Document SWD 250 final STAFF WORKING DOCUMENT Progress report on the assessment and management of combined exposures to multiple chemicals (chemical mixtures) and associated risks. According to this working document there are relatively few cases where regulatory assessment of unintentional mixtures is actually performed. Apart from retrospective mixture

risk assessment observation, there are discussion ongoing how to prevent the risk of mixtures by prospective mixture risk assessment or by setting stricter criteria as suggested in regulatory frameworks and the Farm-to-Fork Strategy. WP6 and the European Commission are in dialogue on how scientific innovation will support European policy on reducing the risk of exposure to mixtures.

The main objectives of the projects are to:

- Build a common strategy to perform human risk assessment to chemical mixtures
- Integrate exposome and risk assessment approaches
- Prioritize real-life mixtures from HBM data
- Develop hazard and kinetic information on prioritized mixtures
- Study the link between mixture biomarkers of exposures and effects
- Perform mixture risk assessment for prioritized mixtures

In that way, this project will combine:

1. real-life co-exposure observations of unintentional mixtures from HBM data across Europe covering the mixtures of concern currently identified in EFSA/ECHA opinions (PFAS, pesticides, heavy metal, mycotoxins, EDCs (priority mixtures));
2. toxicological and epidemiological interpretation of co-occurrence observations;
3. kinetic conversion to bridge internal, as observed in HBM, and external exposure estimates as typically addressed in regulations;
4. the use of *in silico* tools and modelling, effect monitoring and statistical approaches to identify unintentional mixtures across regulations and not identified yet;
5. identification of sources of exposure and chemicals of concern (major contributors to mixtures) by performing dedicated regulatory risk assessment of combined exposure as under development in different regulations;
6. coherent implementation of the data and models for evaluating the risk of mixtures for end-users being EFSA panels/ECHA working groups, national experts responsible for risk assessment of mixtures and stakeholders.

Main expected outputs of the project

- The proposed project will bring together advances made for mixtures in regulatory risk assessment and in the field of exposome and epidemiology. Epidemiologists and toxicologists will jointly interpret the risk of co-exposure events following the recent EFSA and OECD guidance on harmonised methodologies for the risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals and the EFSA guidance on the scientific criteria for grouping chemicals into assessment groups for human risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals. Prioritisation methods and/or grouping approaches to select the components to be considered;
- Options to use (eco)toxicity and exposure data on the single components to predict mixture hazard and/or risks, through component-based approaches based on dose additivity;
- Tiered approaches to refine the assessment depending on the availability and quality of data and information on the mode of action.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

- EFSA, ECHA and EEA in future scientific opinions on risk assessment of mixtures
- EU Member States in communication towards stakeholders and the general public
- Industry addressing the risk of mixtures when assessing the risk of new chemicals before entering the market

The project includes training activities for end-users that will be organised by WP3 and WP9.

Key words: Mixture, HBM, co-exposure, health effects, AOP, RPF, PBPK, risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project will propose data, methods and practical tools as well as a general strategy to perform mixture risk assessment to answer associated policy questions.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

This project has strong connection with:

- WP1: management and indicators

- WP2: priority setting and uptake into policy
- WP3: communication and dissemination of results
- WP4:
 - Derivation of health-based HBM guidance values
 - Link human biomonitoring studies to health examination and dietary surveys
- WP5: further hazard characterisation for mycotoxins, PFAS and heavy metals
- WP7: link with external data sources (e.g. IPCHEM, Tox data or EFSA data)
- WP8: task 8.3 integrative models

This project is strongly connected to other projects from T6.2. For, example aggregate exposures (T6.2.1) can be used as input in this project and development from PBPK projects (T6.2.2) will be directly applied in the context of mixture.

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU legacy: the project will build further on experiences, results, materials, and networks developed within HBM4EU
- EuroMix legacy and EuroMix follow-up: make use of the MCRA software developed in the EuroMix project
- Green Deal projects addressing PFAS and mixtures (e.g. awarded projects as PANORAMIX for mixtures) and SPRINT (pesticides).
- EFSA RACEMIC Roadmap for the
- OECD activity effect biomarkers/AOPs

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.5. Report describing co-occurrence probabilities of chemicals forming real life mixtures of the selected HBM studies across Europe and overview of the kinetic and grouping aspects of prioritised mixtures (M12)

D6.3. 1st Report on innovative approaches for real-life mixture RA (M36)

Expected Project Reports:

Proposal of intermediate reports that can be changed and aggregated during the project:

- Report 1: Training material for stakeholders and end-users in close cooperation with WP3 and WP9 (M12, M24, M36, M48)
- Report 2: Reports and/or scientific papers overviewing real-life exposure from the selected HBM cohorts, including a pragmatic grouping approach and lower tier (simple) kinetic conversion (M12) and more advanced kinetic models (M42)
- Report 3: Report on the results of in silico approaches (e.g. QSAR) to identify chemicals with the same effect of the prioritised mixtures but regulated under other regulatory silos (unintentional mixtures) and recommendations on how this can be used in a test strategy. (M12, M42).
- Report 4: Scientific papers describing how regulatory risk assessment and exposome approach based on biomarkers of effect can be linked to assess real life mixtures (M48)
- Report 5: Case studies addressing the risk of combined exposure to the real-life mixtures based on co-exposure patterns including aggregate exposure (M48).
- Report 6: Report on the agreement between real-life mixtures from HBM data and real-life mixtures from external exposures using PBPK modelling (M36)
- Report 7: Statistical techniques to link biomarkers of exposure with biomarkers of effects (M24).
- Report 8: Final list of prioritized chemicals mixtures in the PARC prioritisation process, EFSA opinions and ECHA evaluations and Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (e.g. metals, mycotoxins, PFAS, pesticides, EDCs) agreed between WP4, 5, 6 and 8. (M6)
- Report 9: An overview of available RPFs for the prioritized mixtures in the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (e.g. metals, mycotoxins, PFAS, pesticides, EDCs) (M12)

Expected Projects Landmarks: None identified at present.

Partners List:

ANSES (FR), RIVM (NL), UNISANTE (CH), AU-PH (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), CEH (UK), CSIC (ES), DTU (DK), EA (UK), EASP (ES), EFSA (EU), EHESP (FR), FINBA (ES), ICPS (IT), JSI (SI), INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR), IPA (DE), IRFMN (IT), ISCIII (ES), IVL (SE), KI (SE), LNS (LU), MOHCY/SGL (CY), MU Recetox (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIPH (NO), NMBU (NO), ONIRIS (FR), RUMC (NL), SLU (SE), STAMI (NO), Swiss SECO (CH), TNO (NL), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), UGPL (PL), UGR (ES), UNIPD (IT), University of Vienna (AT), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE), WR-BIOM (NL), WR-WFSR (NL), WUR (NL)

Schedule

Starting date: 01-05-2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30-04-2026 (M48)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 1025 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 256 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 532 000 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 76 000 €

A6.2.4 Health impact assessment and risk indicators – 4 PROJECTS

P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO

Project Title	Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	HIADDataAvailability		
Project Manager	Kirsten Baken Kirsten.baken@vito.be	VITO	BE
Deputy Project manager	Jelle Vlaanderen J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl	UU-IRAS	NL
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	M81
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.4
Project Id	P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Availability of data on external or internal exposure (including variation per geographical location and socioeconomic status), health outcomes (based on mode of action and dose-response data from toxicological as well as epidemiological studies), relative risk, disease incidence or prevalence, and demographic data are a prerequisite to perform Health impact assessment (HIA) for chemical exposures prioritized in PARC. However, data required to perform HIA are often incomplete. This project will evaluate and increase the availability of data for HIA for PARC priority substances for specific or aggregated exposure routes, windows of exposure, vulnerable populations, occupational settings, geographical locations, age groups, health outcomes etc. Increased availability of suitable data for HIA calculations for specific exposure scenarios will facilitate health impact assessments to be used by

regulators for evaluation and prioritization exercises.

This project is part of four interrelated projects on health impact assessment. Together with results of the project on ‘Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies’, the results will serve as input for the projects ‘Case studies on health impact assessment’ and ‘Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators’.

Main expected outputs of the project

The inventory and collection or generation of data required for health impact assessment of chemicals and exposure scenarios (specific or aggregated exposure routes, windows of exposure, vulnerable populations, occupational settings, geographical locations, age groups etc.) prioritized in PARC will be a recurring activity, to be initiated for a selected set of chemicals and populations every two years starting from PARC year 1.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Risk assessment (RA), Burden of Disease (BoD) calculations, health impact assessment (HIA), and (social) cost benefit analyses ((S)CBA) inform stakeholders and policymakers to help protect and eventually improve human health. The EU Green Deal, in particular the Zero Pollution Ambition policy, in which the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability is a cornerstone, aims at reducing the planetary health impact from chemical exposures. HIA and SCBA allow to objectify the impact of current chemical exposure on health in EU populations, prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken, and estimate the environmental burden of disease and costs avoided as a result of EU policies and regulations.

Key words: Health impact assessment (HIA), data gaps

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project contributes to the aim of T6.2 to develop innovative and practical approaches for human health risk and impact assessment of single, aggregated and combined exposure to chemicals. Data availability to perform health impact and cost-benefit assessment for prioritised chemicals, exposure routes, windows of exposure, subpopulations, geographical locations, and health outcomes will be improved.

By collecting and generating data for HIA for PARC priority chemicals and exposure scenarios across Europe, the project will contribute to SO2 “European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint R&I programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals risk assessment”. The project will support the understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases, to the reduction of environmental and human health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals, and as such to the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen’s health, and awareness of citizens and professionals about risks of chemical exposures.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Measured or modelled internal and external exposure data will be collected in cooperation with WP3, WP4, WP8 and other T6.2 activities and with support from WP7
- Exposure-effect data may be generated by WP4 (epidemiological studies) and in WP5 (toxicity studies)
- T4.1.3 and WP9 will be consulted for information on health data registers
- Projects inside PARC:
 - T6.2.4 Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies
 - T6.2.4 Case studies on health impact assessment
 - T6.2.4 Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU and NHANES for internal exposure data (*link via VITO, UU-IRAS, ANSES*)
- ATHLETE, EXPANSE, HEALS for exposure data (*link via ANSES*)
- EHEN for exposome data (*link via UU-IRAS*)
- COST Action CA18218 European Burden of Disease Network (*link via Sciansano*)
- EU health information projects (e.g., PHIRI, TEHDAS)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- AD6.6. Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC (M12)
- D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications (M36)

Expected Project Reports: None identified at present.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Selection of exposure estimates for (sub)populations and geographical regions, exposure-effect functions, health outcome data and socio-economic status information for case studies and for development of indicators (M18-30-42-54-66)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR); AUTH (EL); DTU (DK); ENSP (PT); FMUL (PT); IISPV (ES); INSA (PT); ISSeP (BE); IVL (SE); KI (SE); MU (CZ); NIJZ (SI); NIPH (NO); NLZOH (SI); OI (SI); RIVM (NL); RUMC (NL); Sciensano (BE); STAMI (NO); USI (CH); UU-IRAS (NL); VITO (BE)

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/01/2029 (M81)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 294.7 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 39 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

None identified at present.

P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS

Project Title	Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	HIAMethod		
Project Manager	Jelle Vlaanderen J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl	UU-IRAS	NL
Deputy Project manager	Kirsten Baken Kirsten.baken@vito.be	VITO	BE
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	M81
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.4
Project Id	P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Data on exposure, exposure-effect relations, health outcomes, relative risk, and demographics can be used for burden of disease (BoD) calculations, analytical Health Impact Assessment (HIA), cost analysis (direct, indirect and intangible) and cost-benefit analysis for chemical exposures. Several aspects of HIA methodologies can be improved to reduce uncertainties in HIA calculations. The methodological improvements of HIA calculations to be realized via this project will reduce the uncertainties in health impact assessment and allow the use of a broader range of data as input for HIA calculations. This will improve the usability of HIA calculations by policy makers for evaluation and prioritization exercises. This project is part of four interrelated projects on health impact assessment. Together with results of the

project on ‘Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals’, the results will serve as input for the projects ‘Case studies on health impact assessment’ and ‘Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators’.

Main expected outputs of the project

Facilitation of burden of disease (BoD) calculations, analytical HIA, cost analysis (direct, indirect and intangible) and cost-benefit analysis and improved confidence in results due to further development and improvement of methods to assess e.g., exposure-effect associations, dynamics in exposure and mixture risks.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Risk assessment (RA), Burden of Disease (BoD) calculations, health impact assessment (HIA), and (social) cost benefit analyses ((S)CBA) inform stakeholders and policymakers to help protect and eventually improve human health. The EU Green Deal, in particular the Zero Pollution Ambition policy, in which the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability is a cornerstone, aims at reducing the planetary health impact from chemical exposures. HIA and SCBA allow to objectify the impact of current chemical exposure on health in EU populations, prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken, and estimate the environmental burden of disease and costs avoided as a result of EU policies and regulations.

Key words: Health impact assessment (HIA), methodologies, uncertainty

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project contributes to the aim of T6.2 to develop innovative and practical approaches for human health risk and impact assessment of single, aggregated and combined exposure to chemicals. Methodologies to perform health impact and cost-benefit assessment for prioritised chemicals, exposure routes, windows of exposure, subpopulations, geographical locations, and health outcomes will be improved.

Further development and improvement of methodologies for HIA will contribute to SO2 “European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint R&I programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals risk assessment”. The project will support the understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases, to the reduction of environmental and human health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals, and as such to the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen’s health, and awareness of citizens and professionals about risks of chemical exposures.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- T6.2.4: Case studies on health impact assessment
- T6.2.4: Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators
- T6.2.4: Exposure through life
- T6.4.4 Risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity
- T4.1: General population survey, Targeted surveys, Occupational surveys
- T5.3: projects identifying effect biomarkers

Links outside PARC

- HERA project: Guidelines for health impact assessment (HIA) of environmental factors
- COST Action CA18218 European Burden of Disease Network
- EPHOR: methodology for exposure dynamics (falling risk curves) and for appropriately adding effects estimates of correlated exposures
- HEALS, ICARUS, EXPANSE: ABM models for estimating the expected effect of environmental interventions

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- AD6.6. Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC (M12)
- D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications (M36)

Expected Project Reports: None identified at present.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- Overview of current frameworks and methodologies of HIA for chemical exposure and associated uncertainties (M12)
- Overview of current methodologies, indicators and frameworks (WHO, ECHA, etc.) used for cost analysis (direct, indirect and intangible) related to health impact of chemical exposures (M30)
- Selection of methodological improvements ready for implementation in case studies and indicator development (M18-30-42-54-66)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR); AUTH (EL); DTU (DK); ENSP (PT); FMUL (PT); IISPV (ES); INSA (PT); IVL (SE); KI (SE); MU (CZ); NIPH (NO); OI (SI); RIVM (NL); Sciensano (BE); UBA (DE); USI (CH); UU-IRAS (NL); VITO (BE); WR-BIOM (NL)

Schedule

Starting date: 01-05-2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30-01-2029 (M81)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 353.45 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 48.4 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

None identified at present.

P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS

Project Title	Case studies on health impact assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	HIACaseStudies		
Project Manager	Jelle Vlaanderen J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl	UU-IRAS	NL
Deputy Project manager	Kirsten Baken Kirsten.baken@vito.be	VITO	BE
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	81
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.4
Project Id	P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Health impact assessment (HIA) and external costs or social cost benefit analysis (SCBA) of chemical exposures allow to objectify the impacts of current chemical exposure on health in EU populations, prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken, and estimate the environmental burden of disease (BoD) and costs avoided as a result of policies and regulations. Case studies will be performed for PARC priority substances.

Based on results of the projects 6.2.4.a and 6.2.4.b on data availability and methodological improvements, a selection of case studies will be performed to calculate the health impact and risk/benefit or cost/benefit scenarios for chemical substances, classes or mixtures, adverse health effects and exposed populations prioritized in PARC, using existing data and/or data generated in PARC. The results of the case studies will also feed into the P6.2.4.d project 'Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators'.

Main expected outputs of the project

In year 1, criteria for selection of case studies to be implemented will be defined (e.g., availability of required data, part of the population exposed above health based guidance values, possibility for EU-wide assessment, ..) and the case studies to be initiated in year 2 will be selected and designed. In order to define the chemicals and exposure scenarios addressed in the case studies, a risk ranking exercise may be conducted based on evidence-based semi-quantitative methodologies. Prioritization of case studies will take the preferences of key stakeholders into account, across priority societal domains, quantified through multi-criteria decision analysis, and will be done in consultation with WP2 and PARC boards. The selection, design, and performance of case studies will be recurring activities during the course of PARC.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Risk assessment (RA), Burden of Disease (BoD) calculations, health impact assessment (HIA), and (social) cost benefit analyses ((S)CBA) inform stakeholders and policymakers to help protect and eventually improve human health. The EU Green Deal, in particular the Zero Pollution Ambition policy, in which the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability is a cornerstone, aims at reducing the planetary health impact from chemical exposures. HIA and SCBA allow to objectify the impact of current chemical exposure on health in EU populations, prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken, and estimate the environmental burden of disease and costs avoided as a result of EU policies and regulations.

Key words: health impact assessment (HIA), case studies

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project contributes to the aim of T6.2 to develop innovative and practical approaches for human health risk and impact assessment of single, aggregated and combined exposure to chemicals.

By calculating health impact and risk/benefit or cost/benefit for chemical substances or mixtures, adverse health effects and exposed (sub)populations prioritized in PARC, the project will contribute to SO2 “European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint R&I programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals risk assessment”. The project will support the understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases, to the reduction of environmental and human health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals, and as such to the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen’s health, and awareness of citizens and professionals about risks of chemical exposures.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP2 for prioritization
- WP3 for stakeholder consultation and communication
- Use of existing data in cooperation with WP3 and data generated in WP4, WP5 and other T6.2 activities
- Data sharing options and integrative model tools provided by WP7 and WP8
- Projects inside PARC:
 - P6.2.4.a: Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals
 - P6.2.4.b: Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies
 - P6.2.4.d: Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators
 - *Projects from other WPs/Tasks to be identified*

Links outside PARC

Projects generating quantitative chemical exposures and effects data e.g. ATHLETE, EXPANSE, NHANES, HEALS, NEUROSOME

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications (M36)

Expected Project Reports: None identified at present.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Criteria for selection of case studies and prioritization of case studies for human health impact assessment

to be started in 2023 (M13)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR); AUTH (EL); BPI (EL); ENSP (PT); FMUL (PT); IISPV (ES); INSA (PT); KI (SE); OI (SI); RUMC (NL); Sciensano (BE); STAMI (NO); UU-IRAS (NL); VITO (BE)

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/01/2029 (M81)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 166.5 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 19 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

None identified at present.

P6.2.4.d Y1 HIAIndicators_VITO

Project Title	Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	HIAIndicators		
Project Manager	Kirsten Baken Kirsten.baken@vito.be	VITO	BE
Deputy Project manager	Jelle Vlaanderen J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl	UU-IRAS	NL
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	M81
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.4
Project Id	P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Indicators related to health impact of chemical exposure support national and European policy makers and can complement and support monitoring frameworks for eg. the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability, the Zero Pollution Strategy, and the 8th Environment Action Programme (EAP).

The suitability of one health impact indicator over another depends on the policy questions that need to be answered, the availability and quality of data, the uncertainties of each indicator, and on the availability of resources and expertise. Indicators applying generally to detrimental effects of chemicals range from attributable cases to DALYs/QALYs and external costs. When insufficient data for health impact analysis are available, exceedance of health-based guidance values (RCR, MOE, ..) can be used to indicate which part of the population is exposed to levels above such guidance values as a measure of potential health impact.

This project is part of four interrelated projects on health impact assessment and will interact with the three other projects: ‘Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals’, ‘Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies’, and ‘Case studies on health impact assessment’.

Main expected outputs of the project

An inventory of different types of existing risk and health impact indicators for exposure to chemical (single, combined, aggregated, ..) will be made in year 1, followed by a proposal for development of

(complementary) indicators based on PARC data and results (including outcomes of the T6.2 projects on data availability and methodological improvements). A selection of indicators integrating dynamic exposure and hazard data and accounting for variability in the population and for uncertainties will be developed in subsequent years, to assess the health impact of specific exposure scenarios (including between- and within-person variance estimates, and dynamics of population exposure and health risk via combining monitoring data with exposure trends as a function of specific socio-economic parameters that condition the level of population exposure per route and pathway).

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Risk assessment (RA), Burden of Disease (BoD) calculations, health impact assessment (HIA), and (social) cost benefit analyses ((S)CBA) inform stakeholders and policymakers to help protect and eventually improve human health. The EU Green Deal, in particular the Zero Pollution Ambition policy, in which the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability is a cornerstone, aims at reducing the planetary health impact from chemical exposures. HIA and SCBA allow to objectify the impact of current chemical exposure on health in EU populations, prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken, and estimate the environmental burden of disease and costs avoided as a result of EU policies and regulations. Indicators related to health impact of PARC priority substances can be developed to support policymakers.

Key words: health impact assessment (HIA), indicators

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project contributes to the aim of T6.2 to develop innovative and practical approaches for human health risk and impact assessment of single, aggregated and combined exposure to chemicals. A selection of indicators integrating dynamic exposure and hazard data and accounting for variability and uncertainties will be developed to estimate the health risk and impact of specific exposure scenarios.

By developing indicators related to health impact and risk/benefit or cost/benefit for chemical substances or mixtures, adverse health effects and exposed (sub)populations prioritized in PARC, the project will contribute to SO2 “European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint R&I programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals risk assessment”. The project will support the understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases, to the reduction of environmental and human health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals, and as such to the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen’s health, and awareness of citizens and professionals about risks of chemical exposures.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Cooperation with T1.3 for the Partnership monitoring framework, WP2 for prioritization and policy uptake, and WP3 for communication
- Exchange of data and computation and visualization tools in collaboration with WP7 and Task 8.3.
- Projects inside PARC:
 - T6.2.4 Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals
 - T6.2.4 Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies
 - T6.2.4 Case studies on health impact assessment

Links outside PARC: None identified at present.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications (M36)

Expected Project Reports: None identified at present.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Inventory of existing HIA indicators and proposal for set of indicators for health impact (assessment) to be developed in PARC (M13)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR); AUTH (EL); ENSP (PT); FMUL (PT); INSA (PT); IVL (SE); MU (CZ); NIJZ (SI); OI (SI); Sciensano (BE); UU-IRAS (NL); VITO (BE); WR-BIOM (NL)

Schedule

Starting date: 01-05-2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30-01-2029 (M81)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 129 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 19.5 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

None identified at present.

T6.3 Review of risk assessment methodologies - 17 PROJECTS

A6.3.1 Substance and effect specific reviewers – 9 PROJECTS

P6.3.1.a_Y1_CS7_REGPREP_EAWAG

Project Title	CS7: Protecting the same ecosystem under different regulations: Differences and similarities of prospective and retrospective risk assessment for pesticides		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	REGPREP		
Project Manager	Marion Junghans Marion.junghans@eawag.ch	Eawag	Switzerland
Deputy Project manager	Annette Aldrich Annette.aldrich@bafu.admin.ch	FOEN	Switzerland
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	84
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.1
Project Id	P6.3.1.a_Y1_CS7_REGPREP_EAWAG		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The project aims at reviewing the risk assessments for pesticides under the different prospective regulations 1107/2009 (PPP), 528/2012 (BPR), 2019/6 (veterinary pharmaceuticals) as well as the retrospective directive 2000/60/EC (WFD). Currently, one substance may have up to four different regulatory threshold values for the protection of surface water ecosystems. This has led to confusion among scientists and in the public domain, where the expectation prevails that there could only be one threshold concentration that can be labelled “safe”. For a final assessment of the apparent inconsistencies, it is important to also consider the differences in the exposure assessments, which differ between the different regulations. This review will produce results important for the one substance one assessment goal of the EU commission. During the first 3 years we will focus on water and sediment risk assessment, during the remaining years it will be extended to soil and air.

The project will try to link the regulatory approaches to assess the risk of pesticides through mutual

exchange of information. This will lead to a more realistic and dynamic risk assessment without increasing complexity and can contribute to the transformation of ERA to a holistic systems-based approach. The outcome will be a recommendation of areas of collaboration for regulators working on different frameworks as well as potential for aligning the approaches.

Revisions of the different regulations and directives addressed in this review may benefit from the knowledge produced in this project.

The timelines of the revisions of the different regulations and directives will be monitored. Input will be given by project partners involved in working groups under the different regulations.

Main expected outputs of the project

This case study will provide a review on the current PPP risk assessments under different regulations. It will address the problems and frictions arising from the current pesticide RA, the similarities across all regulations that can immediately be harmonised with regard to the One Substance One Assessment goal, specific parts in the risk assessment methodologies with a high potential for harmonisation, identification of differences not easily to overcome. For the latter it will be identified whether there is a need for harmonisation or whether the differences can be embraced to further a holistic EU pesticide risk assessment and management.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The results of the case study will support the Commission regarding one substance one assessment of pesticides and will lay a groundwork for better communication of pro- and retrospective risk assessment for pesticides to the public. The project will try to link the regulatory approaches to assess the risk of pesticides through mutual exchange of information, allowing to balance the precautionary principle with the principle of proportionality of regulatory actions. This will lead to a more realistic and dynamic risk assessment without increasing complexity and can contribute to the transformation of ERA to a holistic systems-based approach. The outcome will be a recommendation of areas of collaboration for regulators working on the frameworks and potential for aligning the approaches.

Key words

pesticides, environmental risk assessment, 1107/2009, BPR, WFD, veterinary pharmaceuticals, one substance one assessment, harmonisation, risk communication

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will contribute to PARC objective OO4 ‘Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge. Based on the priorities, PARC will deliver results relevant to support use of new approaches and methods, fill data gaps and reduce uncertainty in risk assessment.’

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness

We would like to use WP3 as a sounding board with regard to the risk communication part in our case study

WP7: Data management plan

Storage of data collected

WP9: Training, laboratory network: none

Other WPs:

4.2: “Case study on Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals (EDCs)”.

One of the aim of this case study is to promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity by ensuring that the environmental and multisource monitoring is designed based on complete and up-to-date information, answering the identified regulatory needs. EDCs will include a variety of different classes of chemicals, among which pesticides. Besides, it will allow for the comparison of chemical approaches, such as in prospective assessment, with effects actually found in the field using effect-based tools. Exchange will be ensured through a common research partner (INERIS, EAWAG).

WP 6.3: Potential exchange to achieve synergies with the following case studies:

CS1: Comparative analysis of risk-based decision benchmarks in the EU regulatory frameworks

CS4: Assessment of the approaches used to address secondary poisoning under current chemical regulations and identification of possible improvements needed to achieve an adequate protection of wildlife

CS14: Identification of loopholes for substances with biocidal properties

CS16: Practical challenges in using quantitative expressions of uncertainty in assessment

WP 6.4.4: many project partners of this case study are also working in 6.4.4 on improving PPP risk assessment

Links outside PARC

All project members are risk assessors with a broad network regarding EU environmental risk assessment. The following list of collaborations should give a non-exhaustive example of the collaborations: Marion Junghans is member of the WG chemicals under the WFD. Annette Aldrich is member of the PPR panel under 1107/2009 as well as project member of the EFSA project PERA. Alexandra Kroll has contact to Premier project on improving pharmaceutical risk assessment. Marion Junghans and Peter von der Ohe are members of the Norman Network and are collaborating on the ecotoxicology database. Sandrine Andres and Sabine Duquesne are collaborating in a project for EEA on soil risk assessment.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Findings of the project will feed into the following PARC deliverables and milestones:

- Deliverable 6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42
- Deliverable 6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81
- Milestone 13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42

Expected Project Reports:

Report/publication/policy brief 1 (including PPT set of slides) on the differences and similarities between regulatory threshold values for surface waters, including sediment, under different EU legal frameworks (namely PPP, BPR and WFD) – M18

Report/publication/policy brief 2 suggesting approaches to align the different frameworks and proposing feedback-loops between the different regulatory frameworks to bridge the identified differences in risk assessment outcomes to further the goal of OS-OA - M24

Report/publication 3/policy brief focussing on soil and air as a result of the second project phase - Month to be specified after finalisation of first project phase

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- Expert workshop to define problem formulation - M6
- Expert workshop to discuss report 1 and proposals for report 2 - M20

Partners List: Eawag (CH), FOEN (CH), INERIS (FR), UBA (DE), ISSeP (BE)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2029 (M84)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 79 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 11 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

None identified at present.

P6.3.1.b_Y1_CS8_OccupReproDev_KI

Project Title	A review of guidance values targeting occupational exposures to
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reproductive and developmental toxicants			
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	OccupReproDev		
Project Manager	Linda Schenk	Karolinska institutet (KI)	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.1
Project Id	P6.3.1.b_Y1_CS8_OccupReproDev_KI		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

With the changes in workforce demographics and work life organization new challenges arise to work environment and chemical regulations as well as health risk assessments under these. Current work environment legislation implicitly holds the healthy male worker as the norm. An implication of this implicit norm is that women, including pregnant women, tend to be less protected than men. A reflection of this is that while many regulatory areas identify carcinogenic, mutagenic and reprotoxic substances as of special concern, in the work environment arena the focus lies on carcinogens and mutagens, through the Carcinogens and Mutagens Directive (CMD). While there also are regulations specifically developed for female workers, e.g., the provisions applying to pregnant and breast-feeding workers, this represents a differentiated regulatory strategy not efficient for the purpose of protecting the offspring and may aggravate discrimination of women on the labour market (Hansson and Schenk, 2016, doi: 10.1017/S1867299X00005808). The option to regulate also reprotoxic substances under CMD is currently under discussion. A recognised challenge is that CMD is tailored for non-threshold substances, whereas a majority of reproductive toxicants are considered to have an effect threshold. One option would be to include only substances with assumed non-threshold reproductive effects under CMD. For this, the relevant non-threshold reproductive toxicants need to be identified. Since a part of these substances may already be regulated by REACH restrictions/authorizations, there is a need to ensure the coherence of the legislative requirements and also a need to clarify what benefits the inclusion of these substances under CMD would have on occupational health. The focus of this case study is the guidance values for occupational exposure and their scientific basis and it will not specifically target the perspectives of commissioners or end-users (regulatory agencies and workplaces).

Research questions: What protection does the work environment legislation offer towards reproductive and developmental toxicity though occupational exposure limits? Would inclusion of (non-threshold) reproductive toxicants under CMD improve the level of protection?

Main expected outputs of the project

Report/publication containing: Comparison of coverage of known reproductive toxicants by OELs and DNELs, Analysis of the weight given to reproductive toxicity in OEL-setting, Quantitative estimates of OELs' margin of safety to reproductive toxicity, Recommendations for regulatory actions, such as re-evaluation of specific OELs.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This is a research project that analyses the weight given to reproductive and developmental toxicity by expert groups recommending occupational exposure limit and a quantitative estimation of the margin of safety to reproductive and developmental toxicity offered by occupational exposure limits and DNELs for workers. The findings will aid evaluation of the efficiency of regulatory tools for occupational risk management of reproductive toxicants. The findings may also contribute to an analysis of the implications of a potential expansion of the CMD to also include reproductive and developmental toxicity endpoints (which would affect the protection for both women and men).

Key words

Occupational exposure, occupational exposure limit, DNEL, reproductive toxicity, developmental toxicity

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will contribute to PARC objective OO4 ‘Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge. Based on the priorities, PARC will deliver results relevant to support use of new approaches and methods, fill data gaps and reduce uncertainty in risk assessment.’

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: Interaction with WP3 foreseen to clarify how to best communicate on recommendations for regulatory action.

The project is related to the T6.3 project (case study) CS3 *Use of regulatory information in workplace chemical risk assessment*.

Links outside PARC

Several of the partners are closely connected to various OSH-stakeholders, are expert group members, besides being active as researchers.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Findings of the project will feed into the following PARC deliverables and milestones:

- Deliverable 6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42
- Deliverable 6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81
- Milestone 13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42

Expected Project Reports

Report/publication containing: Comparison of coverage of known reproductive toxicants by OELs and DNELs, Analysis of the weight given to reproductive toxicity in OEL-setting, Quantitative estimates of OELs’ margin of safety to reproductive toxicity, Recommendations for regulatory actions, such as re-evaluation of specific OELs. (M36; KI)

Expected Projects Landmarks: None identified at present.

Partners List: KI (SE), TTL (FI), LSMU (LT), STAMI (NO), RSU (LV)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 18 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 6 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

None identified at present.

P6.3.1.c Y1_CS9_SKINSENSIRISK_REGIONH

Project Title	Skin sensitisation and risk assessment methodologies
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Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SKINSENSIRISK		
Project Manager	Jeanne Duus Johansen Jeanne.duus.johansen@regionh.dk	REGIONH	Denmark
Deputy Project manager	Jose Hernán Alfonso jose.alfonso@stami.no	STAMI	Norway
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M6	Expected duration	54
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.1
Project Id	P6.3.1.c_Y1_CS9_SKINSENSIRISK_REGIONH		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Skin sensitization is a systemic repeat dose toxicity caused by chemicals leading to permanent changes in the immune system and potentially chronic skin disease in case exposure continues. At least 25% of the European adult population are sensitized to one or more chemicals from consumer products and/or exposures in the work environment. Skin sensitization may lead to permanent skin disease, affect quality of life, and impair work ability. The economic expenses on a European level in considerable, alone skin sensitization due to fragrance ingredients are estimated to cost 11-16 billion Euro/year. This is a result of lack of effective risk assessment and regulation of skin sensitizers across regulations in EU, despite a large, scientific, and practical knowledge base from humans and previous animal experiments in this area. In this project the regulatory practices for skin sensitizers will be mapped across regulatory areas in EU further a systematic review of the scientific aspects of risk assessment methodologies for skin sensitization. The goal is to suggest of a common, science-based risk assessment model for skin sensitisation, which can be considered for regulations of cosmetics, biocides, and in CLP. It will be a major step forward in prevention of skin sensitization among European citizens, consumers at all ages and workers, leading to substantial gain in health, well-being, and economics.

Main expected outputs of the project

This project will contribute to the evaluation of the performance and efficacy of current regulations by using skin sensitisation as case story. It will identify gaps of knowledge and provide suggestions for improvements in risk assessment. This is a major issue in human health and will concern all types of substances (eg. biocides; fragrances; dyes; industry chemicals) intended for skin contact or where this may accidentally happen. The different parts of the project will be published in scientific peer-reviewed papers and as a PhD thesis.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

At least 25% of the European adult population are sensitized to one or more chemicals from consumer products and/or exposures in the work environment. Skin sensitization may lead to permanent skin disease, affect quality of life, and impair work ability. The economic expenses on a European level in considerable, alone skin sensitization due to fragrance ingredients are estimated to cost 11 -16 billion Euro/year. In contrast to this situation no generally accepted risk assessment model exist in EU to be used in regulations. This means that the health of the citizens incl. children is not sufficiently protected by current practices. Likewise, it is difficult for companies producing/using chemicals/products to do this safely. The project outcome is expected to change this situation and will increase safety concerning skin sensitization, reduce disease and improve economics.

Key words

skin sensitization; allergy; chemicals, risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project will contribute to the evaluation of the performance and efficacy of current regulations by using skin sensitisation as case story. It will identify gaps of knowledge and provide suggestions for improvements in risk assessment and management.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Other WPs: 6.4.1: Mixtures. Most exposures to skin sensitizers are in mixtures. The effects of mixtures on outcome (skin sensitization) have been shown in some studies to be synergistic and in others additive. This constitutes an important knowledge gap, which will be closed by data generation in 6.4.1.

Need of coordination of questionnaires to EU and national regulatory bodies as well as other stakeholders performed in WP6.

Links outside PARC

The investigations are closely linked to projects being performed by our group and in collaboration with University of Copenhagen already on immune reactions to skin sensitizers. Prevention of skin sensitization is a priority of several national authorities. At the moment France, Germany and Ireland assess whether there is a need for regulatory actions on skin sensitizers in consumer mixtures in order to prevent skin sensitisation in the general population. A workshop is planned in Brussels concerning Application of the EU Cosmetics Regulation (1223/2009) and relevant OSH Directives for the safe use of cosmetic products by hairdressers at 25/10/2022, where skin sensitization is one of the health effects in focus. Internationally focus is also on inadequate safety concerning skin sensitization from pesticides and a workshop was held in Basel addressing the need for developing as model of quantitative risk assessment for skin sensitising pesticides (August 2022) by the State Secretariat for Economic Affairs (SECO) - Chemicals and Occupational Health, and the Swiss Centre for Applied Human Toxicology together with an international scientific organising committee.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Findings of the project will feed into the following PARC deliverables and milestones:

- Deliverable 6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42
- Deliverable 6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81
- Milestone 13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42

Expected Project Reports/scientific papers

- Mapping of regulatory practices for skin sensitizers; M18 (REGIONH-GE)
- Systematic review on risk assessment methodologies; M 30 (REGIONH-GE)
- Mapping of strategic regulatory needs and strategies to fill them. Case story: success and failures; M36 (REGIONH-GE)
- Conclusions and recommendations; M54 (REGIONH-GE)

Expected Projects Landmarks:

End-of systematic review on risk assessment methodologies for skin sensitization (expected M30). The contents will be decisive of the project can end with a recommendation for a common risk assessment model or if there are too many gaps of knowledge, which will have to be closed first.

Partners List:

National Allergy Research Centre, Denmark (REGIONH-GE); STAMI, Norway; Stockholm University: SU; Institute Mario Negri, IT; Swiss Centre for Applied Human Toxicology, CH

Schedule:

Starting date: 15/10/2022 (M6)

Expected ending date: 15/04/2027 (M54)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 72 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 15 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 6 440 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: NA

P6.3.1.d Y1_CS10_ED-Cosmetics_VUB

Project Title	Evaluation of risk assessment approaches used for cosmetic ingredients with endocrine-disrupting (ED) concern		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	ED-cosmetics		
Project Manager	Vera Rogiers Vera.Rogiers@vub.be	Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB)	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	Tamara Vanhaecke Tamara.Vanhaecke@vub.be	Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB)	Belgium
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M8	Expected duration	24 months
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.1
Project Id	P6.3.1.d_Y1_CS10_ED-cosmetics_VUB		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

This case study is of particular importance for cosmetics. Scientific concerns about ED properties of cosmetic ingredients are addressed in the risk assessment of the Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety (SCCS) within the framework of the Cosmetics Regulation (EC) N°1223/2009. The latter is a vertical legislation and unique in the sense that it is in the EU the only legislation in which the use of experimental animals for safety assessment is fully prohibited since March 2013. In contrast, when the same compound is used for another purpose than cosmetics, the REACH Regulation (EC) N° 1907/2006 applies where animal use for toxicity testing is restricted, but still possible. Such regulatory differences clearly impede the movement to ‘One substance - One assessment’ in support of the European Green Deal. This case study therefore aims to propose possible solutions on bridging these legislative inconsistencies by moving towards a Weight of Evidence (WoE) approach which combines both existing and newly emerging New Approach Methodologies (NAMs). This will be done by bringing in the experience and expertise gained over the years in the use of NAMs and a WOE approach in the cosmetic field for substances that belong to the so-called Annex substances of Regulation N°1223/2009. In particular attention will be given to the risk assessment of the 28 cosmetic substances with ED concerns present in the Group A & B priority lists, composed by the Commission together with the different stakeholders.

The policy and regulatory landscape.

According to OECD 150 (revised) there are 5 levels which need to be fulfilled before a compound can get the label of being an ED. Due to the animal testing ban laid down in the EU Cosmetics Regulation N°1223/2009, compliance for cosmetic ingredients is currently only possible for exposure (biological relevance) and the first two levels as these are concerned with data obtained through *in silico* (e.g. read-across, QSAR), *in chemico* (e.g. physico-chemical data), *in vitro* and *ex vivo* (e.g. 2D-, 3D-cultures, organ-on-chip) methodology and new emerging technologies (e.g. ‘-omics’, artificial intelligence). These data can, however, be combined with historical ‘Point of Departure’ values acquired *via* traditional *in vivo* repeated dose systemic toxicity and reproductive toxicity tests, provided that they were executed before the

implementation of the animal testing bans. Yet, since March 2013, no testing on experimental animals is allowed anymore (for the purpose of cosmetics), which creates major differences in the safety evaluation of existing *versus* new cosmetic ingredients. For chemicals under the REACH regulatory framework, these testing restrictions do not apply and *in vivo* testing to meet the next 3 to 5 levels to assess ED activity involving experiments in mammals and amphibians, is still possible. Furthermore, according to WHO/IPCS (2002), 3 criteria must be fulfilled when assessing EDs: (i) adverse effects need to be observed in an intact organism; (ii) endocrine activity should be measurable; (iii) correlation/causality between the mode of action (MOA) and adversity should be demonstrated. The fact that an intact organism is included in this procedure creates an extra challenge for cosmetic ingredients to show non-ED activity. On the contrary, animal data can be generated for environmental reasons or for safety on the work floor (factsheet Interface between REACH and Cosmetics regulations, ECHA-14-FS-04-EN).

A comparison between the Cosmetic and REACH Regulations has recently been done by JRC (Pistollato *et al.*, Arch Toxicol 95, 2021) and the research team involved in this case study (Arnesdotter *et al.*, Crit Rev Toxicol 51:5, 395-417, 2021). These reviews form a good basis to pinpoint current similarities and constraints. However, follow-up and adjustments will be needed due to (i) ongoing scientific developments in the field of NAMs and (ii) legislative changes announced within the coming 2 years related to revisions of the Cosmetic Regulation, the CLP Regulation where different categories in which “essential use” will play a role (CASG-ED/2021/02), the Scientific Committees moving to ECHA, etc. Within the context of these upcoming legislative changes and in support of the “One compound - One assessment” goal, a key scientific question that will have to be addressed is how to use newly developed NAMs for those endpoints where *in vivo* methods are still used e.g. acute systemic toxicity, genotoxicity, repeated dose toxicity, carcinogenicity, reproductive & developmental toxicity, including ED activity. This is also a question recently posed by JRC to the SCCS (<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/surveyNAM>). As proposed by ECHA, one of the main challenges for EDs will be to design methods that are complex enough to cover the entire signaling network and the relevant MoAs (ECHA 2019, <https://echa.europa.eu/it/ed-assessment>). A test battery of several methods or a tiered screening strategy, including WoE evaluation, may be most useful. Yet, the outcome of the recently finished HBM4EU project and ongoing projects like the EURION cluster need to be taken into consideration as well. Batteries of tests that act at various levels of complexity, such as *in silico*, (Q)SAR, read across, *in chemico*, *in vitro*, *ex vivo*, *in vivo* (non-mammalian), omics technologies, and Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) may mimic better than animal studies key aspects of biological complexity to enable the prediction of human health effects. Hence, more complex systems such as induced pluripotent stem cells to produce target cells, 3D-culture models, spheroids, mini-organs, organ-on-chip developments, artificial intelligence, ... might provide information on MoAs. The possibility to include human cells and tissues further opens new insights in the relevance of species differences of compounds with potential ED activity (e.g. effects on thyroid function).

Main expected outputs of the project

- Report on methodological differences between the legislative frameworks of cosmetics and chemicals, with emphasis on substances with ED activity (M20).
- Report providing possible solutions, shifting away from animal use to a WoE approach which combines both existing and newly emerging NAMs making use of new technology, preferentially based on human material (M32).

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project will contribute to a more harmonized way of using existing and emerging NAMs for risk assessment of compounds with potential endocrine disrupting concerns.

Key words

cosmetics, endocrine, risk assessment, NAMs, WoE

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project will contribute to the WoE assessment of endocrine disruptors using NAMs, facilitating the transition to next generation risk assessment (NGRA).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

This case study is linked to the following WPs and Tasks:

- WP2: This work could add to the objective of 6.3 to contribute to priorities as defined in WP2 to meet the European Commission’s Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic-Free Environment.
- WP6/Task 6.3: Case studies on “*Use of independent non-guideline or non-validated in vitro studies for ED assessments (CS17)*” and “*New hazard classes and test requirements for endocrine disruption (CS18)*”.
- WP6/Task 6.4: Regulatory uptake.

Links outside PARC

Links with the EURION cluster, the work performed by the OECD Performance Based Test Guidelines (OECD PBTG) and the activities of the CARACAL Subgroup on Endocrine Disruptors (CASG ED).

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Findings of the project will feed into the following PARC deliverables and milestones:

- Deliverable 6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42
- Deliverable 6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81
- Milestone 13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42

Expected Project Reports:

- Report on methodological differences between the legislative frameworks of cosmetics and chemicals, with emphasis on substances with ED activity (M20).
- Report providing possible solutions, shifting away from animal use to a WoE approach which combines both existing and newly emerging NAMs making use of new technology, preferentially based on human material (M32).

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Proposal for a WoE based risk assessment approach for cosmetic ingredients with endocrine-disrupting (ED) concern.

Partners List:

Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) (Belgium)

Stakeholders to be involved: Cosmetics Europe, SCCS (U. Bernauer, BfR), EPAA (European Partnership for Alternative Approaches to Animal Testing) and its mirror group, ECHA

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/12/2022 (M8)

Expected ending date: 30/11/2024 (M32)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 10 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 5 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 9 400 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 4 700 €

P6.3.1.e_Y1_CS11_GenotoxCarc_ISS

Project Title	Analysis and evaluation of genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment across legislations, with a special focus on (Q)SAR based approaches.		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	GenotoxCarc		
Project Manager	Cecilia Bossa cecilia.bossa@iss.it	Istituto Superiore di Sanità - ISS	Italy

Deputy Project manager	Chiara Laura Battistelli chiara_battistelli@iss.it	Istituto Superiore di Sanità - ISS	Italy
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	MI	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.1
Project Id	P6.3.1.e_Y1_CS11_GenotoxCarc_ISS		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Genotoxicity and carcinogenicity are essential components of human health safety assessment, still, the current paradigm suffers from limitations which prevent an efficient reduction of exposure to hazardous chemicals. Although various EU and international regulations are open to the use of approaches such as *in vitro* short-term tests and structure-activity based methodologies, current alternative strategies generally rely on paradigms that fail to detect the full spectrum of genotoxic and carcinogenic chemicals. This case study will review the methodologies employed under different regulatory frameworks related to genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment. All identified gaps and inconsistencies will be further discussed with the most relevant stakeholders (*e.g.*, in ECHA, EFSA, OECD, and other relevant frameworks) to possibly propose improvements to the legislations.

Particular attention will be paid to reviewing the current state of the art of the regulatory use of (Q)SAR approaches, to promote their acceptability by reducing uncertainties and to support the incorporation of the most recent innovations.

Main expected outputs of the project

Protocols and recommendations summarising the main directions for increasing the regulatory acceptance of QSAR-related methodologies will be developed, in close collaboration with the main stakeholders. This should also help in integration of the information from different sources (*e.g.*, *in vitro*, *in silico*), detailing and possibly addressing the underlying uncertainties. Achievements will be illustrated through selected case studies.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Main outcomes will include:

- Identification of the most relevant gaps/inconsistencies in current legislations for genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment, highlighting potential of improvement and harmonization, towards OSOA.
- Support for the integration of the information from different sources (*e.g.*, NAMs and AOP based information) identifying their best placement into risk assessment procedures, detailing and addressing the underlying uncertainties.

Key words

Genotoxicity, carcinogenicity, QSAR, NAMs

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The present project will contribute to the overall goal of driving innovation in regulatory risk assessment by mapping and evaluating current methodologies employed in genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment, to identify gaps and needs in methodological knowledge.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Interactions can be foreseen with:

- WP2: to ensure the adequate links between the research and the regulatory EU-added value
- WP3: to foster synergies and collaborations with other projects/programmes at national, EU and international levels
- Task 5.3: development of new AOP for non-genotoxic carcinogenesis

- Task 6.1: development of quantitative networks of AOPs and IATA for genotoxicity
- Task 6.3: Case study 10 on cosmetic ingredients and CS12 towards one substance-one assessment
- Task 6.4.2: developing and fostering the uptake of innovative, effective and protective regulatory approaches
- WP7: FAIR data
- WP8: Safe and Sustainable by Design and Early warning system

Links outside PARC

Interactions with the most relevant stakeholders (*e.g.*, in ECHA, EFSA, OECD, and other relevant frameworks) will be established, to align with ongoing relevant international activities.

In particular with:

- OECD: Chemicals and Biotechnology Committee (OECD / EHS Prog.); QSAR Assessment Framework project ; IATA case studies project; QSAR Toolbox Management Group ; Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics EAGMST (AOP Programme); WG on revision of Genotoxicity Test Guidelines;
- ECHA: Member State Committee (MSC), Committee for Risk Assessment (RAC), Risk Management and Evaluation (RiME+) platform, Competent Authorities for REACH and CLP (CARACAL).
- EFSA: Expert Panel on Food Additives and Flavouring (FAF); Working Group on Genotoxicity of the Scientific Committee; Working Group on Technological Additives of the Expert Panel on Feed Additives and Products (FEEDAP), and working groups on genotoxicity and toxicology.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The output from this project will contribute to the following deliverables of WP6:

- D6.6. First report on conclusions from case studies reviewing risk assessment methodologies (M42).
- D6.17. Final synthesis report on conclusions from case studies reviewing risk assessment methodologies (M81).

Expected Project Reports

Final report on the main outcomes of the CS will be released at the end of the project (M45-M48), (ISS)

Expected Projects Landmarks

The following internal landmarks could be envisaged:

- Refined work plan and methodology (M12)
- Internal report on the review of the methodologies employed under different regulatory frameworks related to genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment, with a focus on QSAR based approaches (M30)

Partners List:

ISS (Italy); IFRMN (Italy); NILU (Norway); INSA (Portugal)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 27

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 6.75

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

None identified at present.

P6.3.1.f_Y1_CS12_MethodOSOA_SU

Project Title	Methods to identify coordination needs towards a 'one substance one assessment' approach.
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	MethodOSOA

Project Manager	Christina Rudén	Stockholm University	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	Marlene Ågerstrand	Stockholm University	Sweden
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP6.3	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.1
Project Id	P6.3.1.f_Y1_CS12_MethodOSOA_SU		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

There is a significant number of EU legislations in force that deal with chemicals directly or indirectly. These rules have been developed at different points in time and for different purposes. Attempts have been made to harmonize and stream-line different parts of the system. The REACH regulation combined for instance more than 30 different pieces of legislations. Nevertheless, the regulatory system for risk assessment is still scattered across different laws and agencies, and between EU and national levels. This has led to a situation where there are inconsistencies between the different regulatory frameworks and only little exchange of information between them (Evans et al. 2016, Sci Total Environ 543, Part A, 757–764.). Meeting the concerns about inconsistencies and inefficiency requires a move towards a more holistic approach. This is in line with the foreseen development towards a ‘one substance – one assessment’ ambition. A key question is whether coordination of assessments and sharing of data can achieve this novel ambition, or whether scientific assessment frameworks (data requirements, guidance) need to be harmonized or consolidated.

Main expected outputs of the project

The overall aim of this project is to develop and apply methods that can help analyse how to achieve a ‘one substance – one assessment’ approach. One area of interest is risk assessment of chemicals that are regulated by different legislations implemented by different EU agencies, see e.g. ECHA and EFSA position paper (https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/21877836/efsa-echa-position-paper-osa_en.pdf/74b1ae31-290b-a608-85e9-05b340840b34).

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The method developed will contribute to a process where the rules and practices according to the different risk assessment processes and legislations can inform each other. In the long term, this can contribute to better coordination, or distribution of risk/hazard assessment tasks between agencies, development of procedures that can take cumulative exposures into account, i.e. exposures from all uses of the same chemical, recommendations on how to facilitate sharing of data between authorities, researchers, industry and the public, and the need for stream-lining, harmonization or consolidation of requirements or guidance.

Key words

one substance one assessment, harmonisation

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

See previous sections

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project will interact with WP2 for prioritizations, and WP3 for stakeholder input.

Links outside PARC

The project is not linked with other projects outside of PARC, but we will have a dialogue with

stakeholders.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Findings of the project will feed into the following PARC deliverables and milestones:

- Deliverable 6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42
- Deliverable 6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81
- Milestone 13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42

Expected Project Reports:

The results will be published in articles submitted for publication in international peer-reviewed journals.

Expected Projects Landmarks: None identified at present.

Partners List: Stockholm University (SU); Karolinska Insitutet (KI)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 36

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 12

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

None identified at present.

P6.3.1.g_Y1_CS13_PlasticizersRA_UCL

Project Title	Identification of differences and loopholes in the regulation of plastic additives		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PlasticizersRA		
Project Manager	Olwenn Martin olwenn.martin@ucl.ac.uk	Department of Arts and Science, University College London	United Kingdom
Deputy Project manager	NA	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	24
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.1
Project Id	6.3.1.g_Y1_CS13_PlasticizersRA_UCL		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Exposure to some substances, due to their use patterns and/or ubiquity, are regulated under multiple sectoral legislations. Plastic additives are chemical substances used for various technical purposes in plastic, rubber materials and other polymers including inks and coatings. This case study will map intended use in specific polymers to regulatory requirements in order to identify and analyse commonalities and differences between regulatory process for specific intended uses of plastic additives. This aligns with task 6.3 objectives by considering process-related differences and similarities across regulations for a category of substances whose risks have to be managed across regulatory silos and will inform strategic regulatory

needs highlighted both in the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability such as One Substance One Assessment or the Essential Use concept and in the Farm to Fork Strategy (revision of FCM regulation), or the Circular Economy Action Plan.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main expected outputs include a map of relevant legislation linking to functions of additives in specific polymers for various intended use, a technical report describing current regulatory processes in relevant legislation, analysing commonalities and differences and justification thereof, as well as barriers and opportunities for harmonisation, and recommendations for policy makers.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The identification of dissimilarities in testing requirements and hazard assessments of substances depending on specific uses will offer valuable information for the implementation and potential impacts of the One Substance One Assessment approach on regulations targeting specific uses of chemicals. Further, the potential barriers and opportunities, and available methods, for harmonisation, including e.g. an integrated exposure assessment framework accounting for contributions from different exposure sources in a systematic way will be presented. The analysis of justification for risk management measures will reveal implicit or explicit value judgment that may inform the development and refinement of essential uses criteria.

Key words

plastic, polymer, additives, essential use, circularity, one substance one assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This case study will leverage existing data to generate knowledge that can inform and support the development of new risk assessment methods, regulatory processes and/or policy developments related to the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability such as One Substance One Assessment, Essential Use.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: Various initiatives related to the issue of additives in polymers may be underway in European institutions such as the Commission, EFSA or JRC. Being alerted to such developments, particularly if they are not widely advertised by responsible institutions could avoid the duplication of efforts or identification of synergies.

WP6: Potential interactions identified within WP6 that need to be explored further; Project 6.2.1.b Source-to-dose models, Activity 6.4.3 Comprehensive review and application of databases in materials

WP8: Can inform case use studies for SSbD criteria (task 8.1)

Links outside PARC

Work currently undertaken under the auspices of the Food Packaging Forum may potentially be of interest, specifically the FCCMigex database (<https://www.foodpackagingforum.org/fccmigex>) or other tools available from <https://www.plastiverse.org/tools>

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.6 1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies due M42

D6.17 2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies due M81

M13 Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget due M42

Expected Project Reports:

Final report delivered on month 24 by UCL.

Peer-reviewed publications to be drafted during the second year of the project.

Expected Projects Landmarks: None identified at present.

Partners List: University College London (United Kingdom), Sciensano (BE), IRFM (IT)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2024 (M24)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 11.5

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 7.5

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 3320 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 1660 €

P6.3.1.h Y1_CS14_Biocides RA_SU

Project Title	Identification of loopholes for substances with biocidal properties.		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	BiocidesRA		
Project Manager	Marlene Ågerstrand	Stockholm University	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	Diana Kättström	Stockholm University	Sweden
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	24
PARC Workpackage number	WP6.3	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.1
Project Id	P6.3.1.h_Y1_CS14_BiocidesRA_SU		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Biocides is a group of chemicals that are used to destroy or control the occurrence of unwanted organisms. Due to their intrinsic ability to affect living organisms, it is recognized that these substances require tight regulation to avoid unintentional release into the environment. The Biocidal Product regulation ((EU) No 528/2012) (BPR) regulates the use of substances with biocidal properties in biocidal products and requires both risk assessment and authorization, ensuring a high level of protection of human health and the environment before such products can be put on the market. The same substances might however be allowed for other uses, not regulated by BPR, such as in personal care products, without the requirement of extensive risk assessment or authorization. This gap in the current regulatory system may result in unrestricted release, and subsequent effects, of these substances to the environment.

The aim of this project is to identify differences in regulation and risk assessment of substances with biocidal properties, describe the implications of these differences and propose solutions to how to close the regulatory gap. As such it contributes towards the aim of WP 6.3 of “evaluating and mapping the performance and efficiency of current processes”, as well as the goal of “one substance-one assessment” described by the European Chemicals Agency.

Main expected outputs of the project

This project will provide new insights concerning the regulation and assessment of substances with biocidal properties for uses other than in biocidal products, and account for most important differences as well as suggest possible ways to improve the assessment for these chemicals.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The outcomes of this project may serve as ground for adjustments of the relevant regulations, specifically important for substances that may contribute to the development of antimicrobial resistance.

Key words

biocides, one substance one assessment, harmonisation

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The aim of this project is to identify differences in regulation and risk assessment of substances with biocidal properties, describe the implications of these differences and propose solutions to how to close the regulatory gap. As such it contributes towards the aim of WP 6.3 of “evaluating and mapping the performance and efficiency of current processes”, as well as the goal of “one substance-one assessment” described by the European Chemicals Agency.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is not linked with other projects inside or outside of PARC.

Links outside PARC

The project is not linked with other projects inside or outside of PARC.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Findings of the project will feed into the following PARC deliverables and milestones:

Deliverable 6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42

Deliverable 6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81

Milestone 13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42

Expected Project Reports:

The results will be published in two peer-reviewed papers, and as part of a PhD-thesis. The first paper will be published during year 1, and the second paper during year 2.

Expected Projects Landmarks: None identified at present.

Partners List: Stockholm University (SU); Karolinska Insitutet (KI)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2024 (M24)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 24

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 12

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

None identified at present.

P6.3.1.i_Y1_CS15_DNT_SU

Project Title	Evaluation of conclusions drawn in guideline-compliant developmental neurotoxicity studies		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	CS15_DNT		
Project Manager	Axel Mie axel.mie@aces.su.se	Stockholm University, Department of Environmental Science (Aces)	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date	M1	Expected duration	36

PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.1
Project Id	P6.3.1.i_Y1_CS15_DNT_SU		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The following research questions will be addressed:

1. Are the conclusions drawn by the test laboratory from observed effects in guideline DNT studies reliable and balanced, as indicated by a novel typology?
2. Does a uniform statistical analysis of behavioural outcome data, developed for high statistical power, identify previously unreported effects?
3. Thus, do test laboratories use the flexibility in the test guideline to maximise the sensitivity of the test design?

This project responds to a need to evaluate the overall compliance of chemicals testing in the food chain with applicable standards, as identified in recent transparency regulation 2019/1381. Ultimately, the project therefore contributes to achieving and maintaining a high level of protection for human health.

In particular, the project is relevant for the following regulatory processes:

Assessment of developmental neurotoxicity (DNT) in

- Plant protection products (active substances, EU level)
- biocides, food contact materials, REACH (EU level) (potentially. Mainly depending on data availability and supporting toxicological and epidemiological evidence)

Thereby, the project will evaluate existing and provide innovative tools to those responsible for assessing and managing the risks of chemical exposure, which is a PA priority.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will advance the understanding of overall compliance in guideline DNT studies, including how flexibility in design, analysis and conclusions is used by the test laboratory. Any consistent deviations from expected practices will be identified.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will identify areas where further development of legislation or regulatory practice regarding the performance of DNT studies may be warranted, in order to ensure a high level of protection for human health.

Key words

developmental neurotoxicity, DNT, guideline compliance, OECD TG 426, conclusions, behavioural outcomes, motor activity, habituation

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project contributes to the PARC objective “Provide new data, methods and innovative tools to those responsible for assessing and managing the risks of chemical exposure”.

The project will help support the European Union's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, by providing new methods for the evaluation of guideline DNT studies to those responsible for assessing and managing the risks of chemical exposure.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

There is a potential link to WP5 that addresses other aspects of DNT. This potential link will be evaluated during the project.

Links outside PARC

In related projects, we have had direct contacts with EFSA, ECHA, EU Commission. These contacts will be used for the present project as needed.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Findings of the project will feed into the following PARC deliverables and milestones:

Deliverable 6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42

Deliverable 6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81

Milestone 13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42

Expected Project Reports

The findings from this project are expected to lead to two peer-reviewed scientific publications. A session on this case study will be included in at least one of the annual stakeholder workshops in WP 6.3.

Expected Projects Landmarks

Availability of a sufficiently high number of original DNT study reports for this project is a necessary prerequisite for the successful performance of this project. This landmark has been reached during summer 2022. (See also “description of risks” below).

Scientific publication 1: 2024

Scientific publication 2: 2025

Partners List

Aces, Stockholm University, Sweden

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 18

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 6

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

None identified at present.

A6.3.2 Use tools, criteria, and methods – 8 PROJECTS

P6.3.2.a_Y1_CS1_CARB_SYKE

Project Title	Comparative analysis of risk-based decision benchmarks in the EU regulatory frameworks		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	CARB		
Project Manager	Jussi Reinikainen jussi.reinikainen@syke.fi	SYKE	Finland
Deputy Project manager	Elodie Bouhoulle e.bouhoulle@issep.be	ISSeP	Belgium
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.2
Project Id	P6.3.2.a_Y1_CS1_CARB_SYKE		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

This project will review and analyse the current regulatory risk assessment methodologies in different EU chemical frameworks, focusing on a selection of decision benchmarks that govern the retrospective assessment of exposure to non-intentionally added substances (NIAS) in various matrices (e.g., soil, water, waste and food), including both human and ecological receptors. The study aims at identifying deficiencies, inconsistencies and gaps in the selected regulatory frameworks and benchmarks and providing outlooks and means for their development and justified application, as well as promoting their transparency. The interconnection between the selected risk assessment frameworks (i.e., the regulation of NIAS in specific matrices in the context of retrospective risk assessments) and the generic registration frameworks (e.g., the REACH) will also be addressed. The project will also benefit national/regional policies on risk assessment in the Member states, especially when they build on regulatory thresholds issued at the EU level. Given that several European regulatory frameworks and thresholds in our focus are currently under preparation or revision (e.g., the Soil Health Law and the environmental quality standards of specific priority substances), we also aim at aligning our project timeline with these policy developments.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will identify inconsistencies, loopholes and gaps in the current chemical risk assessment frameworks by a comparative analysis of relevant case examples (literature review) on specific decision benchmarks (thresholds). In addition to this analysis, a policy brief on the topic will be provided with proposals for potential regulatory improvements or harmonization.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will give the regulators, legislators and other stakeholders an in-depth outlook on the commonly used decision benchmarks and help them to understand the significance of their appropriate foundation and application. This contributes to equal treatment of operators and problem owners and creates a basis for justified regulation and sustainable management of chemical risks.

Key words

risk, assessment, comparative analysis, regulations, threshold, benchmark, quality standard, reference value

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will review existing tools/criteria/methods used in chemical risk assessment across EU regulations and promote more transparent and harmonised risk analysis as well as application of scientific information and chemical data.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project has potential synergies with several other WPs, tasks, activities or projects that address holistic approaches for risk assessment, especially when the risks they encompass are caused by exposure to different environmental matrices and evaluated by using generic threshold values or quality standards. Plans for concrete cooperation will be specified during the study regarding other projects in WP6 as well as potential interactions at the task level e.g., with WP2, WP7 and WP3.

Links outside PARC

The project may contribute to other EU regulations and policy frameworks (i.e., those not currently or directly embedded in our project plan), such as the EU's Soil Strategy, Circular Economy and Zero Pollution Action Plans, and the EFSA funded projects RACEMiC (RA of Combined Exposure to Multiple Chemicals) and PERA (Building a European Partnership for next generation, systems-based Environmental Risk Assessment).

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Findings of the project will feed into the following PARC deliverables and milestones:

Deliverable 6.6 '1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies' due M42

Deliverable 6.17 '2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies' due M81

Milestone 13 'Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget' due M42

Expected Project Reports:

Final report of the comparative analysis (32 M), manuscript of a scientific, peer-reviewed article on the

results of the project (36 M), and policy paper (36 M).

Expected Projects Landmarks: None identified at present.

Partners List:

Finnish Environment Institute, SYKE (Finland)
 Scientific Institute of Public Service, ISSeP (Belgium/Wallonia)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01-05-2022 (M1)
 Expected ending date: 30-04-2025 (M36)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 51
 Expected PM for the first year of the project: 6

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 47 900 €
 Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 7 700 €

P6.3.2.b_Y1_CS2_RiskReduction_SU

Project Title	Identification and review of methods for evaluating the effectiveness of risk assessment for reducing risk.		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	RiskReduction		
Project Manager	Marlene Ågerstrand	Stockholm University	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	Davor Kontic	Jožef Stefan Institute	Slovenia
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	24
PARC Workpackage number	WP6.3	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.2
Project Id	P6.3.2.b_Y1_CS2_RiskReduction_SU		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

In all parts of chemical regulation, we are dependent on assessment methodologies that make use of available data and guide risk assessors towards a conclusion. Every assessment methodology has its advantages and its limitations, and knowledge about this is crucial for the overall trust of and certainty in the assessment. Currently, there are some methods available for how to evaluate the effectiveness of risk assessment for risk reduction, but still, data from these evaluations are scarce, and even when data is available, causal relationship between a measure and an effect can be difficult to establish.

The aim of this project is to identify, characterize, assess, compare, and possibly further develop methods for evaluating the effectiveness of risk assessment for risk reduction. The identified methods will be assessed in terms of their usefulness, e.g. data requirements, resource effectiveness, and accuracy in results, for understanding how to best reduce risks from exposure to harmful chemicals.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will contribute with increased understanding of how to measure the effectiveness of risk assessment aimed at reducing risk. The results could be used to guide future design of regulation and risk

assessment of chemicals towards adequate and feasible evaluation methods.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The results could be used to guide future design of regulation and risk assessment of chemicals towards adequate and feasible evaluation methods.

Key words: effectiveness; risk assessment; risk reduction

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This study will contribute towards the WP6.3 objective to “map and evaluate current methodologies employed in regulatory risk assessment to identify gaps and needs in methodological knowledge” by increasing the understanding of how to measure the effectiveness of risk assessment aimed at reducing risk.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

We will establish contacts with WP3 for coordination of stakeholder interactions. We will collaborate with WP4 regarding biomonitoring data.

Links outside PARC

We will perform interviews with key stakeholders when appropriate. The interviews will be semi-structured and designed to supplement the written information with knowledge from experts with first-hand experience from the relevant regulatory processes.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Findings of the project will feed into the following PARC deliverables and milestones:

Deliverable 6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42

Deliverable 6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81

Milestone 13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42

Expected Project Reports:

The results will be published in 3-4 peer-reviewed papers. The papers will be submitted for publication during the second year of the project. During the yearly workshop organised by WP6.3, we will discuss the design and outcome of the project with relevant stakeholders on European and national level.

Expected Projects Landmarks: None identified at present.

Partners List: Stockholm University (SU); German Environment Agency (UBA); National Institute of Occupational Health in Norway (STAMI); University College of London (UCL); Jožef Stefan Institute (JSI).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2024 (M24)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 61

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 30.5

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

None identified at present.

P6.3.2.c_Y1_CS3_WorkplaceRA_TTL

Project Title	Use of regulatory information in workplace chemical risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	WorkplaceRA		
Project Manager	Tiina Santonen tiina.santonen@ttl.fi	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health	Finland

Deputy Project manager	Piia Taxell piia.taxell@ttl.fi	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health	Finland
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36 M
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.2
Project Id	P6.3.2.c_Y1_CS3_WorkplaceRA_TTL		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The OSH legislation obligates employers to carry out a risk assessment on chemical agents present at the workplace. In the risk assessment, the employer often relies on to limit values and related regulatory information produced under the OSH legislation (CAD 98/24/EC; CMRD 2004/37/EC), and more recently, under the REACH regulation (1907/2006/EC). The limit values and other information provided under the different regulatory processes may be interpreted and implemented differently at the workplace level, which may impact the workplace chemical risk assessment and risk management. The present case study aims to evaluate how the limit values and related regulatory information are interpreted and utilised in the workplace chemical risk assessment and risk mitigation in practice. The project is implemented as a questionnaire study, complemented with interviews, addressing both workplaces and other stakeholders (authorities, employee and industry organisations), and also includes a review on regulatory literature to identify case examples on the different options to regulate occupational chemical exposure. The information obtained in the project is expected to support both regulatory decisions making and providing guidance for workplaces.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project clarifies how regulatory information provided under different regulatory processes (OSH and/or REACH) is utilized in workplace chemical risk assessment and risk mitigation in practise, supporting both regulatory decisions making and providing guidance for workplaces.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project provides background information for developing guidelines for selecting the most efficient regulatory option to a specific substance/case (under OSH and/or REACH), and also provides guidance for workplaces on the use of the regulatory information in workplace chemical risk assessment.

Key words: occupational chemical exposure; risk assessment; OSH legislation; REACH

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

T6.3 aims to review current regulatory risk assessment methodologies and their effectiveness e.g., in relation to reducing risks, within and across relevant sectors through a series of case studies. The present case study will provide information on the implementation of legislation related to occupational chemical exposure at the workplace level, and map the potential differences in the outcome depending on the regulatory process.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is related to other case studies under T6.3, most importantly C8 (*A review of guidance values targeting occupational exposures to reproductive and developmental toxicants*) and C2 (*Identify and review methods for evaluating the effectiveness of risk assessment in reducing risk*). Linkages/synergies with other WPs are still to be clarified.

Links outside PARC

None identified at present.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Findings of the project will feed into the following PARC deliverables and milestones:

Deliverable 6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42
 Deliverable 6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81
 Milestone 13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42

Expected Project Reports:

The outcomes of the project will be collected into a project report finalised by 5/2025, including the regulatory review, results of the case study/interviews, analysis of the results, and recommendations/guidance.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Literature study completed; questionnaire study ready for launching (content finished, respondents decided), M12

Questionnaire study and interviews completed; analysis of their results well underway, M24

Analysis of study results completed; case study report, recommendations and guidance written (M36)

Partners List:

Finnish Institute of Occupational Health (FIOH/TTL), Finland (FI) (project manager); Karolinska Institutet (KI), Sweden (SE); Jozef Stefan Institute (JSI), Slovenia (SI); Statens Arbeidsmiljøinstitutt (STAMI), Norway (NO); Riga Stradins University (RSU), Latvia (LV)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 21

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 6

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

None identified at present.

P6.3.2.d_Y1_CS4_SecPoisoning_INERIS

Project Title	Assessment of the approaches used to address secondary poisoning under current chemical regulations and identification of possible improvements needed to achieve an adequate protection of wildlife		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SecPoisoning		
Project Manager	Sandrine Andres Sandrine.andres@ineris.fr	Institut national de l'environnement industriel et des risques - Ineris	France
Deputy Project manager	NA	NA	NA
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M2	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3
Project Id	P6.3.2.d_Y1_CS4_SecPoisoning_INERIS		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The study will define the main gaps and discrepancies in current approaches for the assessment of secondary poisoning, with the aim of facilitating the One substance One assessment implementation. Secondary

poisoning relates to toxic effects to organisms in higher trophic levels of the food chain, resulting from ingestion of lower trophic level organisms having accumulated substances. If a substance has potential to bioaccumulate and to cause secondary toxic effects, a detailed assessment should be conducted. Most regulations focus on direct exposure and methods to assess secondary poisoning are generally less developed and differ widely across regulatory frameworks.

The risk of secondary poisoning only becomes preponderant (over direct exposure) for the most bioaccumulative substances; as a consequence, a lower number of assessments has been conducted overall. This leads to a situation where less experience has been gained to allow for the development of guidance. Under REACH for instance, simplified food chains are proposed for aquatic and terrestrial environment (bird eating fish or earthworm). Both refers to an unspecified species of predator, with a single source of diet. For plant protection products, secondary poisoning *per se* is assessed as in REACH based on simple bird eating fish or earthworm scenario. However, at the same time the guidance for the assessment of ecotoxicity to birds and mammals (EFSA Journal 2009; 7(12):1438, currently under review) contains detailed scenarios including different species, with various diets.

While looking on retrospective risk assessment, mainly under the Water Framework Directive, secondary poisoning is clearly identified as one of the 5 protection goals. The methodology followed relies on both REACH and EFSA Guidance which may introduce discrepancies among assessments. The Guidance on EQS was revised in 2018, including the section on secondary poisoning which now takes into account assimilation efficiency. For 11 priority substances, significant in terms of environmental contamination (e.g. mercury, ...), threshold values are defined in biota. The assessment of compliance of these EQS leading to monitoring in biota has been complex because the prospective risk assessment does not specify the species, sex, or size or age of the fish eaten by birds or mammals. These parameters are necessary for the interpretation of monitoring data and question the uncertainties related to prospective risk assessment. One of the key elements about bioaccumulation (and persistence) is that internal burden of substances continues to build over time, eventually reaching toxic concentration and adverse effect. This temporal appreciation of bioaccumulation is insufficiently studied, especially for top predators, and needs to be further explored.

Finally, the interpretation of field data remains difficult, especially for the determination of metrics such as the trophic magnification factor (TMF) which is relevant for PBT assessment but also for the EU POP regulation and the UN Stockholm Convention. Although recommendations have been recently proposed in the literature, data availability and guidance are still lacking.

The CS is a review which will also include the analyse of research projects outcome which may be relevant for the study. This will allow for the identification of regulatory contexts where improvement would be beneficial.

PBT/vPvB assessment is considered as critical in most of the chemical regulation. For the most problematic substances (e.g. (very) Persistent, (very)Bioaccumulable and Toxic or PBT/vPvB) the risk is managed using hazard-based principle, leading eventually to the ban of the placing on the market / use of those chemicals due to their P/B/T properties.

For borderline chemicals, which do not strictly fulfil all PBT criteria (as in Reach Annex XIII) there is still a need to properly assess the risk of secondary poisoning. These chemicals may affect durably the environment, by long terms contamination of ecosystems including biota, leading to unwanted effects.

The CS aims to review the practices under different regulatory schemes and the robust and mature approaches available in the literature for secondary poisoning assessment. The CS will provide recommendations on most effective approach to address secondary poisoning assessment in an effective way.

The CS will consider the review of tools and methods already available and fulfilling the requirements such as validation to be applied in a regulatory context. The legislations in place have already included this protection goal and it is not expected that it requires a strong policy change. However, guidance and methods may need to be improved and aligned in a timely manner.

Main expected outputs of the project

The review of differences and best practice will facilitate secondary poisoning across regulatory frameworks thereby contributing to the one-substance-one assessment approach.

The outcome of the CS will be to propose improvements for the assessment of chemicals which tends to accumulate within trophic networks and have, as an impact, a better protection of ecosystems. It aims to give more guidance to risk assessors and ensure consistency when assessing secondary poisoning.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

- The first output will be the identification of gaps, uncertainties and discrepancies in the existing regulatory framework for secondary poisoning assessment
- The second output will be a targeted review of approaches and tools that are available for potential innovation in risk assessment of secondary poisoning.
- The main output will be the development of recommendations to improve the assessment of bioaccumulated compounds in a sound and consistent way within EU regulatory framework with clear identification for end-user of acceptable approaches.

Key words: secondary poisoning, accumulation, long term effect, harmonisation

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The CS will contribute to PARC objective **004** “*Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge. Based on the priorities, PARC will deliver results relevant to support use of new approaches and methods, fill data gaps and reduce uncertainty in risk assessment.*”

The project also contribute to PARC objective **009** “*Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA’ by proposing recommendations that are harmonized across EU policies*”

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

This case study is linked to the following PARC WPs and Tasks:

- WP2: This work will support the objective of 6.3 to contribute to priorities as defined in WP2 to meet the European Commission’s Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic-Free Environment.
- WP4: This work will be linked to WP4 for the collection of monitoring data in wildlife and their possible use in secondary poisoning assessment.
- WP5: This CS could provide feedback on the need of input data for ecotox studies and models to be used for SP assessment.
- WP6/Task 6.2: The CS will provide feedback for the need of models for a better understanding of exposure kinetics.
- WP6 / Case study 7 “Protecting the same ecosystem under different regulations: Differences and similarities of prospective and retrospective risk assessment for pesticides” for mutualization of the work regarding the inclusion of secondary poisoning within the study of prospective/retrospective Risk assessment.
- WP6/Task 6.4: uptake of the outcome of the CS in Regulatory frameworks

Links outside PARC

This project will be complementary to EU and national activities regarding monitoring in biota, as a regular task under WFD, but also for the interpretation of biota level in wildlife.

The project will also be linked to the Horizon project PROMISCES, in the interpretation of the risks due to the promotion of the circularity of natural resources (water, soil) during life cycle of chemicals. The project will also grounds on the EU LIFE VERMEER ([Life Vermeer – Integrating VEGA, toxRead, MERLIN-Expo and ERICA in A Platform for Risk Assessment and Substitution of Risky Substance \(life-vermeer.eu\)](https://life-vermeer.eu)) for the use of the SPHERA Tools and models.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Findings of the project will feed into the following PARC deliverables and milestones:

Deliverable 6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42

Deliverable 6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81

Milestone 13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42

Expected Project Reports:

- Report 1: review and analysis of the existing approaches in regulatory framework and relevant research projects for the assessment of secondary poisoning, M10
- Report 2: case studies comparing the outcome of existing approaches for a selection of chemicals leading to the identification of gaps, inconsistencies, and uncertainties, M18
- Report 3: Recommendations for the uptake of the results of the CS into regulations, M30

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Interviews of Risk assessors / regulators: M3-6

Expert workshop: M22

Supporting material for workshop on the identification of priorities for improvement of guidance for secondary poisoning

Review of existing methods in the main regulations on chemicals (Year 1)

Partners List: Ineris (France)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/06/2022 (M2)

Expected ending date: 30/06-2025 (M38)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 16

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 6

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 2500 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 675 €

P6.3.2.e_Y1_CS6_SusChemControl_MUI

Project Title	Holistic overview and agreements on strategic regulatory needs for a sustainable chemical control		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SusChemControl		
Project Manager	Martin Paparella martin.paparella@i-med.ac.at	Medical university Insbruck, MUI	AT
Deputy Project manager	NA	NA	NA
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	24
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.2
Project Id	P6.3.2.e_Y1_CS6_SusChemControl_MUI		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Policy expectations for a sustainable chemical control are high. This requires considering actions at multiple levels, ideally actions towards first order changes, like the use of NAMs, AOPs and IATAs, but also towards second order changes, i.e. alternative ways of managing chemical risks. The latter may reflect experience from other sectors, such as the cosmetics regulation and extend on this, by integrating NAM based NGRA, with metrics for carbon footprint, renewable feedstock/circular design and sustainable chemical use. A deep uncertainty characterization of all metrics may be used to weight the various evidence streams in the sustainability assessment and management of chemicals. Third order changes influencing the values of the human society may be equally important to maintain or accelerate the pace of change and eventually give birth to new second or first order ideas.

Importantly second and third order changes may also be relevant in overcoming potential obstacles for the necessary investments into research and development and in seeking multi-stakeholder consensus on the limitations and acceptable levels of uncertainties of current and new approaches. The development of a holistic view and a structure for the discussion of facts, uncertainties and perspectives may be important for the evolution of a safe and sustainable chemical control.

Research question: Which type of longer- and shorter- term societal and regulatory changes may be useful and agreeable for a future safe and sustainable chemical control?

Main expected outputs of the project

- Hierarchical mindmap and summary paper as an overview on options beyond AOP, NAM and IATA development for a sustainable regulation of chemicals, “for the near perspective and what would require more time for knowledge and policy development”
- Including possible “new support decision tools and holistic risk assessment frameworks”, e.g. a summary for possible approaches for the assessment of non-chemical alternatives to chemical biocides and pesticides. The latter may support all three spheres of sustainability, i.e. environmental and health safety, reducing societal/ethical conflicts with animal testing and reducing socio-economic burden from chemical production, use and assessment.

Dissemination through publication, webinars.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Options for a sustainable chemical control beyond AOP, NAM and IATA development, including possible approaches for the assessment of non-chemical alternatives to chemical biocides and pesticides.

Key words: holistic overview, strategic regulatory options, sustainable chemical control

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will contribute to PARC objective OO4 ‘Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge. Based on the priorities, PARC will deliver results relevant to support use of new

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: Interaction with WP3 foreseen to coordinate stakeholder interactions and clarify how to best communicate on recommendations for regulatory action.

The project is related to the activity A6.4.2 *Facilitate the regulatory acceptance and use of new methods.*

The project will connect to and explore synergies with tasks 2.2 *Knowledge management and uptake into policy* and 8.1 *Safe and sustainable by design (SSbD).*

Links outside PARC

The Austrian Green Chemicals Plattform (<https://www.grünechemieösterreich.at/>) is led by the Austrian Ministry of Environment and aims to develop concepts and multi-stakeholder agreements to develop green chemistry in Austria beyond (eco)toxicological assessments.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Findings of the project will feed into the following PARC deliverables and milestones:

Deliverable 6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42

Deliverable 6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81

Milestone 13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42

Expected Project Reports:

Hierarchical mindmap and summary paper as an overview on options for sustainable regulation of chemicals, beyond AOP, NAM and IATA development, “for the near perspective and what would require more time for knowledge and policy development” including possible “new support decision tools and holistic risk assessment frameworks”, e.g. Including possible approaches for the assessment of non-chemical alternatives to chemical biocides and pesticides.

Expected Projects Landmarks: None identified at present.

Partners List: MUI (AT), (KEMI (SE) and UNIBAS (CH) TBD)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2024 (M24)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 5 (project manager)

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 2.5 (project manager)

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):
 None identified at present.

P6.3.2.f_Y1_CS16_UncertaintyRA_ULUND

Project Title	Practical challenges in using quantitative expressions of uncertainty in assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	UncertaintyRA		
Project Manager	Ullrika Sahlin Ullrika.sahlin@cec.lu.se	Lund university, ULUND	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	Linda Schenk Linda.schenk@ki.se	Karolinska institutet, KI	Sweden
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	24
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.2
Project Id	P6.3.2.f_Y1_CS16_UncertaintyRA_ULUND		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Decision makers, both regulators and general public, are sensitive to uncertainty. Several agencies and organisations responsible for scientific assessment are leaning towards honest communication of uncertainty in assessments (EFSA et al., 2019, 2018; Joint FAO/WHO Codex Alimentarius Commission, 2015; NRC, 2009; SAPEA, 2019).

Quantitative expressions of uncertainty in a conclusion of a risk assessment, as a mean of communication, have several advantages (transparent, possible to combine, unambiguous) (Benford et al., 2018), and “expressions of uncertainty or variability in risk estimates may be qualitative or quantitative, but should be quantified to the extent that is scientifically achievable” (§ 23 Section IV: Risk Analysis Joint FAO/WHO Codex Alimentarius Commission, 2015). Statements about (un)certainty about a conclusion can be expressed using probabilities.

Uncertainty analysis is strongly related to the context, resource, and knowledge bases for each assessment.

There are several sources to uncertainty that may influence a conclusion of an assessment, and often several methods are required to treat uncertainty at every step in the assessment. Assessment can be complex ranging from those integrating multiple lines of evidence to inform the quantity of interest or parameters in models, to assessment integrating models describing variability and functional relationships between variables to derive the quantity of interest (Benford et al., 2018; Institute of Medicine, 2013).

Uncertainty analysis should be framed in a way that it e.g. can bridge across evidence-based decision making and assessment using quantitative scientific models (van der Bles et al., 2019).

To express uncertainty requires judgement by scientific experts. Therefore, structured expert knowledge elicitation is an important method for uncertainty analysis and in particular for the characterisation of overall uncertainty (EFSA, 2014). In addition to expert judgement, Bayesian statistical inference quantify uncertainty by probability, combining data with expert judgement, allowing for quantification and propagation of uncertainty through assessment models.

Quantitative expressions of uncertainty are preceded by clearly defined assessment questions, which may require some careful consideration. Assessment models must also be specified to express key sources to variability, to allow for a distinction between uncertainty and variability.

The implementation of uncertainty analysis resulting in quantitative expressions of uncertainty requires experience and training, and an understanding of the benefits of considering uncertainty. Although uncertainties are discussed

by EU regulatory bodies, there is a need for more cases studies demonstrating the benefit of quantifying overall uncertainty.

This case-study will focus on the practical aspects of uncertainty analysis including the practical challenges in producing quantitative expressions of uncertainty from experts and data and benefits from quantitative compared to qualitative expressions when communicating uncertainty to decision makers.

Research questions

- What are the practical challenges in using quantitative expressions of uncertainty and how can these be handled?
- What are the benefits of considering uncertainty in a quantitative way in assessment and communication?

Main expected outputs of the project

A general introduction to uncertainty analysis for risk assessment in a PARC context.

Descriptions with pedagogical examples on a set of generic uncertainty analyses which can serve as inspiration for future assessment.

A list of methodological challenges in implementing uncertainty analysis resulting in a quantitative expression of uncertainty, to be addressed in further case studies.

A new or better understanding of barriers, both methodological and personal, to implement quantitative uncertainty analysis.

A set of examples demonstrating the benefit of uncertainty analysis where uncertainty is expressed by probability.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will:

- Provide new knowledge about the practical challenges in using quantitative expression of uncertainty in assessment.
- Provide pedagogical examples of the how to implement quantitative expressions of uncertainty and the benefit of these in assessment and communication.

Key words: uncertainty, quantitative expression of uncertainty, practical challenges

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will contribute to PARC objective OO4 ‘Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge. Based on the priorities, PARC will deliver results relevant to support use of new approaches and methods, fill data gaps and reduce uncertainty in risk assessment.’

The project will contribute to the PARC main objective ‘Drive innovation in regulatory RA by strengthening its scientific basis, with implementation of NGRA as ultimate goal’ by strengthening implementation of uncertainty analysis in NGRA.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project will feed into the work of WP7, specifically task 7.3 which targets the development and implementation of innovative data analytical approaches from the computational, statistical and mathematical field, including quantification of the uncertainties and propagation of these uncertainties when combining different sets of data. This case-study is a retrospective analysis of practitioners’ experience, which make the findings valuable for the work under task 7.3 which approaches the issue of uncertainty analysis from a more normative and methodological perspective.

Links outside PARC: None identified at present.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Findings of the project will feed into the following PARC deliverables and milestones:

Deliverable 6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42

Deliverable 6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81

Milestone 13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42

Expected Project Reports:

- A general introduction to uncertainty analysis for risk assessment in a PARC context.

- Descriptions with pedagogical examples on a set of generic uncertainty analyses which can serve as inspiration for future assessment.
- A list of methodological challenges in implementing uncertainty analysis resulting in a quantitative expression of uncertainty, to be addressed in further case studies.
- A new or better understanding of barriers, both methodological and personal, to implement quantitative uncertainty analysis.
- A set of examples demonstrating the benefit of uncertainty analysis where uncertainty is expressed by probability.

Expected Projects Landmarks: None identified at present.

Partners List: ULUND (SE), KI (SE), BPI (EL), UBA (DE)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2024 (M24)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 5 (Year 1), to be identified for Year 2

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 5

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

None identified at present.

P6.3.2.g_Y1_CS17_ED-in vitro_BPI

Project Title	Use of non-guideline in vitro studies for ED assessments		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	ED-in vitro		
Project Manager	Eliana Spilioti e.spilioti@bpi.gr	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Deputy Project manager	Dimitra Nikolopoulou d.nikolopoulou@bpi.gr	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36 months
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.2
Project Id	P6.3.2.g_Y1_CS17_ED-in vitro_BPI		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The purpose of this case study (CS) is to develop scientific criteria for harmonised evaluation of reliability and relevance of data on endocrine parameters from non-guideline *in vitro* studies or data derived by studies conducted with non-validated protocols for use in weight of evidence assessments. Furthermore, the sources of uncertainty for these types of studies used in regulatory assessments across legislations will be assessed. For this purpose, a review of data from available existing validated and non-validated *in vitro* methods for ED assessment, related to both human health and the environment, will be performed. An adequate number of studies will be selected from the open literature that will be considered as the basis for the development of evaluation criteria.

The European Guidance for the identification of endocrine disruptors in the context of Regulations (EU) No 528/2012 and (EC) No 1107/2009 (ECHA-EFSA, 2018) describes how to perform hazard identification for endocrine-disrupting properties by following the scientific criteria which are outlined in the respective EU Regulations for biocidal and plant protection products. The guidance document describes “*how to*

gather, evaluate and consider all relevant information for the assessment, conduct a mode of action (MoA) analysis, and apply a weight of evidence (WoE) approach, in order to establish whether the ED criteria are fulfilled". However, scientific criteria on how to evaluate data from non-guideline *in vitro* studies are not described and such data, that might be reliable and relevant, are often dismissed. Based on this, the proposed CS aims to be used as a complementary document to assist risk assessors to evaluate these data and be able to implement the ED guidance in a systematic and harmonised way.

During the authorisation procedure for different substances (e.g. pesticides, chemicals under REACH), risk assessors often evaluate *in vitro* studies which are either non-guideline compliant or performed according to non-validated testing methods. Structured and harmonized evaluation of *in vitro* data is especially critical during assessment of endocrine disrupting (ED) properties, as it requires to elucidate endocrine mechanisms and mode of action. The main challenge is that as there is no harmonised procedure for the evaluation of these types of studies, risk assessors often dismiss them or data derived from these studies are not treated in a consistent manner.

The main output will be the development of a complementary document including illustrative examples on the scientific criteria for consideration of data from non-validated *in vitro* methods for ED assessment across legislations with the purpose to filling the gap for the evaluation of non-validated studies in a harmonized way.

The project is considered in line with the policy agenda and its timelines are not expected to change as it will build on already available tools and guidelines such as the [SciRAP tool](#), OECD Performance Based Test Guidelines ([OECD PBTG](#)), OECD GDs (e.g. [Revised Guidance Document 150 on Standardised Test Guidelines for Evaluating Chemicals for Endocrine Disruption](#)), [ABU project](#) etc.

Main expected outputs of the project

The development of specific criteria for the evaluation of non-validated *in vitro* methods will facilitate ED assessments across regulatory frameworks thereby contributing to the one-substance-one assessment approach. The project is relevant for both human health and environmental risk assessments.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The outcomes of the CS will be to provide confidence in risk assessors and consistency in the assessment of data from non-validated ED test methods for use in weight of evidence assessment, as well as to remove current bottlenecks regarding acceptance of non-validated *in vitro* ED test methods.

Key words: endocrine, risk assessment, reliability, relevance, *in vitro*

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project will contribute to the identification of endocrine disruptors using all available data and methods in a structured and transparent way and facilitate the transition to next generation risk assessment.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

This case study is linked to the following WPs and Tasks:

WP2: This work could add to the objective of 6.3 to contribute to priorities as defined in WP2 to meet the European Commission's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic-Free Environment.

WP5: This CS could provide feedback on which *in vitro* studies available in the open literature are considered OECD compliant and therefore could be used to assist in the identification of regulatory gaps for the compounds that are going to be selected.

WP6/Task 6.1: The CS will provide feedback for the evaluation of studies that will be proposed for IATAs relevant to endocrine disruption.

WP6/Task 6.4: Regulatory uptake.

WP6/Task 6.3/ CS5 (Use of scientific studies in the REACH restriction process): This CS will provide feedback on the use of non-guideline studies for the risk assessment of chemicals under REACH.

Links outside PARC

Links with the EURION cluster, the work performed by the OECD Performance Based Test Guidelines

(OECD PBTG), the [OECD IATA Case Study Project](#), the ABU Project, Better use of academic data (CSS), one-substance one-assessment.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Findings of the project will feed into the following PARC deliverables and milestones:

Deliverable 6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42

Deliverable 6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81

Milestone 13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42

Expected Project Reports:

Year 1: Comprehensive list and report on *in vitro* test methods assessing prioritised ED endpoints (lead: BPI).

Year 3: Report on harmonised scientific criteria for consideration of data from non-validated *in vitro* methods for ED assessment across legislations (lead: BPI).

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Year 1: Compilation of the comprehensive list of non-validated existing ED test methods that will be used as a basis for the development of scientific relevance and reliability criteria.

Partners List:

Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI) (Greece); Karolinska Institutet (KI) (Sweden); French National Institute of Health and Medical Research (Inserm) (France); French National Institute for Industrial Environment and Risks (Ineris) (France)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 33

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 11

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 15 000 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 4 000 €

P6.3.2.h_Y1_CS18_ED-classes_BPI

Project Title	New hazard classes and test requirements for endocrine disruption		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	ED-classes		
Project Manager	Dimitra Nikolopoulou d.nikolopoulou@bpi.gr	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Deputy Project manager	Eliana Spilioti e.spilioti@bpi.gr	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36 months
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.2
Project Id	P6.3.2.h_Y1_CS18_ED-classes_BPI		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

New hazard classes for endocrine disruption will be included in Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 (CLP). In this direction, relevant actions are taken by the CARACAL sub-group on endocrine disruptors (CASG ED). Since the CLP Regulation is applicable to all chemicals and their mixtures in the European Market, these new hazard classes on ED properties are expected to substantially contribute to harmonization in the identification of ED chemicals. Nevertheless, specific scientific guidance will be necessary on how NAMs (*in vitro* assays, *in silico* tools, read-across approaches) could contribute to the assignment of a chemical in a specific hazard class (e.g. Category 1 or 2 for human health and environmental effects) or not after comparison with the CLP criteria. This task might be more or less critical for data-rich (e.g. under PPPR, BPR) or data poor (e.g. under REACH) chemicals or for chemicals where animals experimentation is minimized in the context of the 3R principles or restricted (e.g. under CPR). Although data availability depends highly on data requirements which is a legal issue (outside the scope of this project) there is a need to highlight the implications in scientific assessments due to consideration of different datasets or approaches (e.g. hazard-based vs risk-based). Moreover, certain NAMs such as read-across are used more often in e.g., BPR and REACH rather than PPPR. This case study will focus on the added value of NAMs (*in vitro*, *in silico*, read-across) to delineate human/ population relevance aspects that are critical in deciding on classification of chemicals either as Category 1 or 2 for ED properties under the upcoming new CLP criteria.

Over the past few years, chemicals with endocrine disrupting (ED) properties have been identified under different regulatory frameworks, including Regulation (EC) 1107/2009 (Plant protection Products Regulation, PPPR), Regulation (EU) 528/2012 (Biocides Products Regulation, BPR), Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 (REACH) and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 (Cosmetic Products Regulation, CPR). Whilst all of these pieces of legislation endorse the WHO/IPCS (2002) definition for an endocrine disruptor, different methodology and approaches are followed for ED assessments of chemicals. For REACH, PPPR and BPR, ED assessment is hazard-based, whereas under the CPR a risk assessment might be needed before a conclusion is reached. The EFSA/ECHA Guidance for the identification of endocrine disruptors in the context of Regulations (EU) No 528/2012 and (EC) No 1107/2009 has been endorsed to provide harmonised scientific criteria for the identification of pesticides with ED properties but not for chemicals regulated under REACH or the CPR. European Commission has also communicated an intention for the development of a horizontal approach for identification of EDs across EU legislation building on the criteria established for PPPs and BPs (*European Commission Communication COM (2018)734/final. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Towards a comprehensive European Union framework on endocrine disruptors*). This project contributes towards the one-substance one assessment approach.

This case study will focus on substances falling under specific regulatory frameworks, including PPPR, BPR, REACH and CPR. NAMs specifically designed to assess Estrogen, Androgen, Thyroid, Steroidogenesis (EATS)-mediated toxicity (including liver-mediated thyroid toxicity) will be considered:

- In data-poor situations, as in REACH, “read-across” may have been the most frequently implemented NAM. Read-across approaches currently available will be mapped.
- Identification of (Q)SAR tools that could be of relevance in predicting potential interaction of chemicals with any of the EATS pathways will be investigated.
- Available *in vitro* assays that could be considered for the assessment of endocrine activity with regard to EATS modalities will be identified.

The scientific principles, methods and approaches described in existing relevant guidance documents e.g. the EFSA/ECHA GD (2018), the OECD GD 150 (2018) will be considered.

This project runs in parallel to the activities of the CASG ED and the expected new hazard classes on endocrine disruption will be considered within the project timelines.

Main expected outputs of the project

This project will highlight the added value of NAMs (*in vitro*, *in silico*, read-across) in classification of

chemicals either as Category 1 or 2 for ED properties under the upcoming new CLP criteria. It contributes to the one-substance-one assessment approach and it is relevant for both human health and environmental risk assessments.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project will contribute to the harmonized implementation of the new CLP criteria on hazard classes for endocrine disruption taking into consideration all available methods and tools.

Key words: endocrine, classification, risk assessment, NAMs, *in vitro*, *in silico*, read-across

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project will contribute to the classification of endocrine disruptors using all available data and methods in a structured and transparent way and facilitate the transition to next generation risk assessment.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

This case study is linked to the following WPs and Tasks:

- WP2: This work could add to the objective of 6.3 to contribute to priorities as defined in WP2 to meet the European Commission's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic-Free Environment.
- WP6/Task 6.1: The CS will provide feedback for the evaluation of studies that will be proposed for IATAs relevant to endocrine disruption.
- WP6/Task 6.3: Case studies on “Use of independent non-guideline or non-validated *in vitro* studies for ED assessments” and “Evaluation of risk assessment approaches used for cosmetic ingredients with endocrine-disrupting (ED) concern”.
- WP6/Task 6.4: Regulatory uptake.

Links outside PARC

Links with the EURION cluster, the work performed by the OECD Performance Based Test Guidelines (OECD PBTG) and the activities of the CARACAL Subgroup on Endocrine Disruptors (CASG ED).

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Findings of the project will feed into the following PARC deliverables and milestones:

Deliverable 6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42

Deliverable 6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81

Milestone 13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42

Expected Project Reports:

Year 1: Report and database on existing *in vitro* assays, *in silico* tools and read-across approaches for ED assessment of EATS modalities under PPPR, BPR, REACH and CPR (lead: BPI).

Year 3: Report on the added value of NAMs (*in vitro*, *in silico*, read-across) to delineate human/ population relevance aspects that are critical in deciding on classification of chemicals either as Category 1 or 2 for ED properties under the new CLP criteria (lead: BPI).

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Compilation of the database on existing *in vitro* assays, *in silico* tools and read-across approaches for ED assessment of EATS modalities.

Partners List:

Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI) (Greece); French National Institute of Health and Medical Research (Inserm) (France); Environment Agency Austria (EAA) (Austria); Mario Negri Institute for Pharmacological Research (IRFMN) (Italy); Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) (Belgium)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 26

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 7.5

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 14 200 € to be confirmed

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 3 400 € to be confirmed

T6.4 Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies **11 PROJECTS**

A6.4.1 **Develop regulatory and legally accepted risk assessment and management approaches and methods for chemical mixtures – 2 PROJECTS**

P6.4.1.a Y1_OPREMIXCS1_BRUNEL_UGot

Project Title	Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	OPREMIX		
Project Manager	Thomas Backhaus thomas.backhaus@gu.se	University of Gothenburg	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	Andreas Kortenkamp andreas.kortenkamp@brunel.ac.uk	Brunel University London	UK
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.1.
Project Id	P6.4.1.a_Y1_OPREMIXCS1_BRUNEL_UGot		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

This project has its focus on the current approaches related to the management of mixtures across regulatory areas as e.g. REACH, CLP, Pesticides and Biocides, cosmetics, food contact material, pharmaceuticals. Further regulation on food and drinking water as well as on environmental media and emission will be considered. It will also explore the use of the MAF approach for the assessment and management of mixtures across regulatory areas and uses (beyond REACH) and compare it to other mixture approaches. This project will address the question if and under which circumstances a MAF is applicable or not and how different are the conclusion drawn by different mixture approaches when challenged with real word data sets and if there are differences to what extend would the MAF approach might provide biased results.

This project is highly relevant for supporting the improvement of the regulatory management of mixtures across chemicals legislation and areas of use, regarding human health and the environment. It will address the overall objectives of activity 6.4.1 “*Develop regulatory and legally accepted risk assessment and management approaches and methods for chemical mixtures*”, while specifically focusing on and comparing the methods and tools currently used for the regulatory assessment and management and providing guidance for further development.

Main expected outputs of the project

A systematic comparative evaluation of current mixture tools (and those that are currently under development or might be developed within PARC). The mixture tools will be compared regarding their

practicability, effectiveness and efficiency, level of protection, feasibility, applications domain and data demands.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project will provide the input to develop a “European cookbook” of mixture tools that describes the application domain for each tool, its data demands, protectiveness, feasibility and reliability, in the view of the different demands from regulators, industries and civil society.

Key words: *mixtures, MAF, Mixture tools, European cookbook of mixtures.*

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The management of mixtures was one of the highest scoring topics in the “PARC survey”. Further mixtures are an integral part in the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (CSS). However, the work under PARC will (a) expand the scope to encompass all relevant chemical classes, exposure scenarios and protection goals, and will (b) focus on supporting European regulation.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: a cooperation for the foreseen survey would be of value, especially in distributing it to risk assessor

WP7: Data management plan: see the section *Data Management*

WP9: Training, laboratory network

Other WPs: The project will primarily link to and exchange findings and input with project P6.4.1.b_Y1_CS2_UFZ (Dealing with unknown mixtures in regulatory risk assessment through the use of monitoring data and NAMs). Findings from WP 4 and WP5 regarding monitoring data and toxicity data will be considered in this Project. Further, there will probably be links to and exchange with 6.2.3 on issues related to human real life exposure and modelling of exposure. In WP6.2 mixtures will be approached from a research science perspective with the focus on modelling, human health and dietary exposure. Relevant findings of Task 6.2 will be considered in this project for sizing one or more MAFs.

Links outside PARC

There are several currently ongoing research and policy development activities on mixtures in the EU. Under Horizon 2020, the so-called Green Deal Call includes a call dedicated to mixture toxicity, with a certain focus on aquatic environment and the occurrence of pharmaceutical residues in unintentional mixtures. There are also ongoing and planned mixture related activities related to the remit of EFSA (e.g. food safety and pesticides), e.g. regarding the further development of the Cumulative Assessment Groups (CAGs), primarily for the assessment of mixtures of pesticide residues in food. Further, the European Commission will conduct an impact assessment of the introduction of a MAF or MAFs under REACH, which will be supported by a consultant study.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.18: Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations (M81)

Expected Project Reports:

Project Report 1: Evaluation of the stakeholder feedback collected from a survey and expert interviews on the usefulness of current mixture assessment tools (Technical report, public, M18)

Project Report 2: Comparative assessment of mixture tools with respect to application domain, feasibility, data demands, protectiveness, reliability, bias. (Technical report, computer code, data repository, all public, M24)

Project Report 3: Draft for a European mixture framework, accompanied by a validated toolbox of instruments for mixture risk assessment and management (Technical report, public, M48)

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Landmark 1: Updated inventory of current mixture assessment tools and compilation of current regulatory requirements (M12)

Landmark 2: Documented interviews with experts in chemical risk assessment (human health as well as the

environment). (M12)

Landmark 3: Selection of case studies for the comparative assessment of current or newly developed mixture tools (M12)

Partners List: AGES (AT), UBA (DE), BPI (EL), UI (IS), ISS (IT), NIVA (NO), ENSP (PT), EAWAG (CH), KEMI (SE), UK Env. Agency (UK), STAMI (NO), IEP-NRI (PL), UAVR (PT), NIJZ (SZ), UK-CEH (UK)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/4/2025 (M36)

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: minimum 158 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: minimum 45,75 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: *

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: *

*In the current status of the project it is not possible to estimate the number of publications, therefore we cannot estimate these costs yet.

P6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIXCS2_UFZ

Project Title	Dealing with unknown mixtures in regulatory risk assessments through the use of monitoring data and NAMs		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	MONAMMIX		
Project Manager	Wibke Busch wibke.busch@ufz.de	Helmholtz Environmental Research center (UFZ)	Germany
Deputy Project manager	tbd	tbd	<Country>
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.1
Project Id	P6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIX CS2_UFZ		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The project is highly relevant for supporting the improvement of the regulatory management of mixtures across chemicals legislation and areas of use, regarding human health and the environment by bridging data gaps. It will address the overall objectives of activity 6.4.1 “Develop regulatory and legally accepted risk assessment and management approaches and methods for chemical mixtures” and strives to link prospective mixture assessment methods with monitoring and AOP knowledge. In particular, it is focusing on case studies on environmental monitoring under EU directives such as WFD, (Directive 2000/60/EC), Sustainable Use of PPPs Directive 2009/128/EC) and human biomonitoring initiatives such as HBM4EU or the cohort studies within the European Exposome Network. In this project the use of new approach methods (NAMs) i.e. bioanalytical methods for untargeted exposure detection and hazard identification in conjunction with chemical screening data, to deal with unknown mixtures will be compared with mixture risk assessment methods relying on component-based standard toxicity information.

In this project we will address the following research question:

- How can data from NAMs be used to provide more comprehensive pictures of the chemical exposure that needs to be addressed in chemical risk assessment?
- How could available bioanalytical methodology and information from environmental monitoring contribute to mixture risk assessment?
- Are AOP networks a way to overcome data gaps and account for compounds mixture contributions?
- Can priority mixtures be defined with the application of non-target methods?
- Can NAMs complement component-based mixture risk assessment?

Main expected outputs of the project

The availability of empirically based support data from established monitoring efforts on human health and environmental quality, as well as adverse outcome pathway knowledge compiled under OECD efforts, will be important for developing the assessment and management of mixtures in several ways. It will for example be crucial to argue the size of a mixture assessment factor (MAF), to define common assessment groups, or to aggregate exposures across regulatory silos. Accepted use of pollutant monitoring and NAM generated data will be essential to provide support in these respects, while providing additional options for tiered mixture assessment strategies.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

To advance the regulatory assessment of unintentional mixtures additional approaches are needed which are practicable in a regulatory context and capable of dealing with data constraints. It can be foreseen that monitoring information based on non-target chemical and bioanalytical methods will be utilised to define - unknown mixture exposures. Furthermore, mechanistic information from *in vitro* bioanalytical NAMs can be employed for establishing AOP networks to bridge data gaps in mixture assessment. End-users might e.g. be interested to using NAMS to consider the expectable additional effect of product formulation compounds to the toxicity of an individually assessed active ingredient.

Key words: *chemical mixtures, new approach methods, environment, human health, regulatory acceptance*

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The management of mixtures was one of the highest scoring topics in the “PARC survey”. Further mixtures are an integral part in the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (CSS). However, the work under PARC will (a) expand the scope to encompass all relevant chemical classes, exposure scenarios and protection goals, and will (b) focus on supporting European regulation.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: we will do a survey in cooperation with Task 6.4.2, for that we will need some support in distributing the survey to risk assessor.

WP7: Data management plan: see the section *Data Management*

WP9: Training, laboratory network: for now, we see no need for support from WP9, but if we identify needs, we will contact WP9

Other WPs: The project will primarily link to and exchange findings and input with project P6.4.1.a_Y1_CS1_BRUNEL_UGot (Optimising regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe) and with Task 6.4.2. Further, there will be links to and exchange with 6.2.3 on issues related to human real-life exposure and modelling of exposure. In a later stage, if available, the newly generated monitoring data from WP 4 and the outcome of WP 5 regarding toxicity testing and AOPs will be considered in our case studies.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.18: Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations (M81)

Expected Project Reports:

Project Report 1: Literature review on use of NAM for describing mixture exposure relevant for regulation (M18)

Project Report 2: Guidance document for use of NAM data for specific regulatory options (M36)

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Landmark 1: Selection of case studies for the use of NAMs in specific regulatory areas (M12)
 The above-mentioned research questions can also be considered as landmarks.

Partners List: UBA (DE), NIVA (NO), BPI (EL), UI (IS), ISS (IT), AGES (AT)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/4/2025 (M36)

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: minimum 60.25 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: minimum 19,55 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: *

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: *

*In the current status of the project it is not possible to estimate the number of publications, therefore we cannot estimate these costs yet.

A6.4.2 Facilitate the regulatory acceptance and use of new methods – 3 PROJECTS

P6.4.2.a Y1 LandscapingSurv_UNIBAS

Project Title	Status of integration and use of New Approach Methodologies in the EU regulatory risk assessment landscape		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurv_UNIBAS		
Project Manager	Martin F. Wilks martin.wilks@unibas.ch	University of Basel (UNIBAS)	Switzerland
Deputy Project manager	Nicolas Roth nicolas.roth@unibas.ch	University of Basel (UNIBAS)	Switzerland
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36 months
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.2
Project Id	P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurv_UNIBAS		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Current regulatory health and environmental risk assessment practice for chemicals faces substantial challenges to meet present and future scientific, societal, and policy needs to support more efficient, transparent and sustainable chemical safety governance. Innovative approaches to regulatory science and chemical risk assessment are needed to meet the goals and vision laid down by the EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability and the EU Green Deal. The overall aim of the project is to promote and facilitate the regulatory acceptance and practical use of New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) for use in chemical risk assessment for human health and the environment. Emphasis is put on real-life situations and application contexts encountered by risk assessors and regulators at desk level, e.g., situations with complex modes of action and/or often severe knowledge gaps. We will (i) review the status of development (incl. harmonization), integration, and use of NAMs in the different EU chemical sectors/regulatory

frameworks/application contexts, through literature review and expert consultation activities (expert elicitation, survey); (ii) identify gaps, needs, barriers, opportunities, and drivers for success towards the regulatory acceptance and implementation of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory landscape. The ultimate goal is to promote NGRA and use of NAMs across human health and environmental risk assessment domains and sectorial chemical legislation.

The demand for novel toxicity testing strategies and risk assessment will continue to increase for a vast number of chemical substances and mixtures, processes and technologies as well as new toxicological endpoints. The paradigm shift in toxicity testing towards the use of alternative non-animal methods (3R) as well as the development of systems toxicology and evidence-based toxicology approaches (3S)², has led to a substantial increase in available *in vitro* and mechanistic data derived from NAMs for use in next generation risk assessment (NGRA). One particular challenge for risk assessment is to integrate these scientific developments into existing regulatory frameworks and best practice at desk level. While policies have long had the vision to protect human health and ecosystems with new and innovative methods, solid downstream implementation has been lagging behind, often because novel scientific methods have failed to consider regulatory needs as a driver for successful use and integration into chemical risk assessment and management practice. This has been confirmed by the outcome of the open survey to identify priorities for PARC, as well as the recent fitness checks of chemicals legislation, that called for (i) better addressing the regulatory needs of risk assessment and risk management, and (ii) further ensuring that decisions are based on robust and relevant, up-to-date knowledge to increase the level of protection of human health and the environment. The project intends to follow-up on these needs, consolidating knowledge and fostering scientific cross-fertilization and harmonization in the field to develop criteria for the acceptance of NAMs and guidelines to support their integration in the daily risk assessment workflow.

Emphasis is put on real-life situations and application contexts encountered by human and environmental risk assessors and regulators at desk level, e.g., situations with complex modes of action and/or often severe knowledge gaps. We will review the status of development (incl. harmonization), integration, and use of NAMs in the regulatory context, and identify opportunities, barriers, and drivers for success towards the development, validation, and implementation of NAMs. The species agnostic nature of the AOP approaches, means that any insights gained from the use of NAMs that provide mechanistic understanding of the chain of key events leading to effects will inform both on the potential human health risks and also on the likelihood that environmental species may be affected by a similar mechanism leading to ecological impacts.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Summary of the landscaping exercise assessing the status of integration and use of NAMs at across sectorial frameworks
- Summary of the gaps & needs analysis, barriers, opportunities, drivers for integration and use of NAMs and roadmap for use at desk level across sectorial frameworks
- Action plan for prioritization of regulatory-relevant scenario-based case studies, as an output from an international workshop
- Summary of the scenario-based case-studies

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The outcome of the landscaping exercise and gaps & needs analysis will further support the priority setting in PARC Activity 6.4.2. In particular, activities in years 1 and 2 will inform the development of regulatory-relevant case studies focused on regulator/risk assessor needs and risk assessment context specificity, looking across regulatory silos and product categories. We will develop narratives with a focus on the development and application of criteria for risk assessment methodologies using evidence-based approaches that are fit-for-purpose and ultimately useful to regulators. The selected scenario-based case studies will cover a variety of complex situations that regulators are facing when conducting hazard, exposure, and risk assessment, e.g., data-rich vs. data-poor chemicals, grouping decisions, different exposures, (occupational, environmental, consumer), identification and selection of species for testing and

monitoring studies and model systems for hazard testing and assessment, classification and labelling, setting health-based guidance and environmental protection values, cumulative exposures etc. Focus will be on previously identified priority areas of regulatory and public concern, e.g., endocrine-mediated effects, transgenerational effects, neurodevelopment, immunotoxicity, biologically active environmental releases and others. The output of this project will be used to orientate future coordination and harmonization efforts, foster cross-fertilization of scientific knowledge, order research needs and sharing of best research-to-policy practice in relation to the development, use and regulatory uptake of NAMs.

Key words: New Approach Methodologies; landscaping; expert elicitation; survey; regulatory acceptance; gaps & needs analysis; research road-mapping, confidence, human health risk assessment, environmental risk assessment.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will address PARC operational objectives OO9 by promoting and facilitating the integration and use of NAMs in chemical risk assessment practice, as well as their regulatory acceptance and uptake. The project is directly relevant and useful for chemical risk managers and to the broad scientific, regulatory toxicology and environmental management communities.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Important coordination efforts will be invested over the entire project duration within PARC to avoid overlaps and create synergies with:

- WP2, Task 2.1, Task 2.2
- WP5, Task 5.2, Task 5.3
- WP6, Task 6.1, Task 6.3

Links outside PARC

- ASPIS cluster: a number of activities in PrecisionTox and RISK-HUNT3R are directly relevant to or even overlap with A6.4.2. ASPIS collaborators are partners in PARC 6.4.2 and/or WP6. Active collaboration is pursued ;
- PARERE at EURL ECVAM Network for Preliminary Assessment of Regulatory Relevance, which includes validation of NAMs for regulatory purposes ;
- EFSA and JRC, regarding ongoing projects in the field of computer-based approaches/automation of the systematic review approach ; advisors for PARC A6.4.2;
- OECD, regarding ongoing projects in the field of harmonization and regulatory acceptance of NAMs.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.19: Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs). (M81)

Expected Project Reports:

Project Report 1 – Landscaping Exercise

Project Report 2 – Gaps & needs analysis

Project Report 3 - Prioritization and development of regulatory-relevant case studies

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- Landmark 1: Technical report mapping of activities and processes related to the status of development, integration and use of NAMs in selected regulatory environments (M12).
- Landmark 2: Technical report summarizing the outcome of the gaps and needs analysis (M24).
- Landmark 3: Workshop to design regulatory scenario-based case studies resulting in an action plan prioritizing the case studies (M26).
- Landmark 4: Technical report summarizing the key learnings from the case studies (M36).

Partners List:

UNIBAS (Switzerland); NIPH, represented by VKM (Norway); UT (Estonia); ISS (Italy); UOB (United Kingdom); INERIS (France); UBA (Germany); BPI (Greece); EAA (Austria); UNL (Portugal); UKCHE (United Kingdom); UAVR (Portugal); NIVA (Norway)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022
 Expected ending date: 30/04/2025

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 84 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 28 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: Estimation under development

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: Estimation under development

P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRApractice_VKM_NIPH

Project Title	Next generation risk assessment applied in practice		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	NGRApractice		
Project Manager	Gro Haarklou Mathisen Gro.haarklou.mathisen@vkm.no	National Institute of Public Health (NIPH), represented by the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment (VKM)	Norway
Deputy Project manager	Camilla Svendsen Camilla.svendsen@fhi.no	National Institute of Public Health (NIPH), represented by the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment (VKM)	Norway
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity	6.4.2
Project Id	P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRApractice_VKM_NIPH		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The VKM project “NGRA applied in practice” focus on the development of evidence-based tools and guidance’s for risk assessment based on NAMs, which will be included in an overall evidence-based NGRA framework usable for the evaluation of human health risk/safety across sectors (e.g. food and cometic). The framework will enable risk assessors to use NAMs, and to give better risk assessments to risk managers and decision-makers. The tools and guidance’s will be based on already established systematic review principles and guidance’s, evidence-based toxicology thinking, and established tools for chemical risk assessment. The draft tools/guidance’s will be tested in case studies. The deliverables will be tools (a tool for evaluation of internal validity of NAMs; a tool for evaluation of external validity of NAMs; a tool for evaluation of certainty in evidence), guidance’s (for the identification of a point of departure from NAMs; for the evaluation of uncertainty in NAMs), and checklists (reporting standards for reporting of different NAMs to ensure that published studies can be used as evidence in NGRAs). The VKM project “NGRA applied in practice” consists of several sub-projects for the 7-year PARC period. The first (ongoing, month 1-12) is limited to the use of *in vitro* studies in evidence-based hazard assessment. In the second (month 13-36), the use of *in silico* studies in evidence-based hazard assessment will also be included.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Generic, sector-independent tools for evidence-based hazard assessment of chemicals using NAMs addressing potential adverse human health effects.
- Generic, sector-independent guidance documents on identification of a PoD from NAMs and on the evaluation of uncertainty in NAMs
- Generic, sector-independent checklists (reporting standards) for different NAMs, to ensure adequate design and reporting for the research outcome of NAMs to be usable as evidence in risk assessment.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

No complete evidence-based framework for the use of NAMs in NGRAs of chemicals are available. Thus, today it is not possible to perform NGRAs based systematic review principles aiming to ensure that only evidence of sufficient quality is included based on the weight of evidence principle, that the effects addressed are relevant for human adverse health effects, and that the hazard assessment process and product is objective, robust, transparent, and reproducible.

The tools developed in this project will be part of an evidence-based framework for NGRA, and thus enabling risk assessors to use NAMs in evidence-based risk assessment.

The checklists (reporting standards) will be developed, and these should be used by researchers to ensure adequate study design and reporting.

The tools and guidance's will feed into e.g.

- Derivation of HBM-GVs (one dossier per substance; 3-4 substances)
- List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints
- Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes
- Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC
- Mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints
- Draft strategy for the development of bioinformatics tools that are needed to link omics data and other mechanistic information to human relevant disease mechanisms
- 1st New approach methodologies report

The checklists for in vitro studies and in silico methods will be relevant for all PARC projects developing such methods, and projects using such studies to develop AOPs.

Key words:

Chemical risk assessment, evidence-based, guidance, NAMs, NGRA, systematic review, tool.

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project will contribute to the development of innovative tools that enable transition from traditional risk assessments largely depending on animal studies as evidence to evidence-based NGRAs using NAMs as evidence. This way, NGRAs will be useful for risk managers in policy and regulations.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

A scientific advisory group has been established for this project. Vera Ritz (WP2) has the role as observer and will have the possibility to participate in all meetings with the scientific advisory group.

This project is related to the two other Activity 6.4.2-projects:

- Status of integration & use of NAMs in the EU regulatory risk assessment landscape
- Landscape and readiness of advanced ML & AI approaches for Next Generation Risk Assessment

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.19: Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs). (M81)

Expected Project Reports:

An overview of the planned project reports and the provisional month of delivery is given below. NIPH, represented by VKM, is in charge of all deliveries.

Protocols for the development of:

- A tool for evaluation of internal validity of *in vitro* studies (December, 2022).
- A tool for evaluation of external validity of *in vitro* studies (March, 2023).
- A tool for evaluation of internal validity of *in silico* studies (February, 2024).
- A tool for evaluation of external validity of *in silico* studies (November, 2024).
- A tool for evaluation of certainty in evidence (December 2025)
- A guidance document for the identification of PoD from NAMs (July, 2026).
- A guidance document for the identification and evaluation of uncertainty in NAMs (May, 2027).

Tools for

- Evaluation of internal validity of *in vitro* studies, including a practical guidance with examples (September, 2023).
- Evaluation of external validity of *in vitro* studies, including a practical guidance with examples (February, 2024).
- Evaluation of internal validity of *in silico* studies, including a practical guidance with examples (October, 2024).
- Evaluation of external validity of *in silico* studies, including a practical guidance with examples (August, 2025).
- Evaluation of certainty in evidence from different NAMs, including a practical guidance with examples (the development will start February 2025 and are planned to end November 2026).

Guidance's for

- Identification of a PoD from different NAMs (the development will start April 2026 and are planned to end July 2027).
- Identification and evaluation of uncertainty in different NAMs (the development will start February 2027 and are planned to end February 2028).

Checklists (reporting standards) for:

- *In vitro* studies (April, 2024)
- *In silico* studies (October, 2025)

Expected Projects Landmarks:

The protocol development for each tool and guidance are “go” achievements. The dates are given above. The tool development for evaluation of external and internal validity are “go” achievements for the development of the checklists. The dates are given above.

Partners List:

NIPH, represented by VKM (Norway); UNIBAS (Switzerland); UT (Estonia); BPI (Greece); ISS (Italy); NIVA (Norway); UAVR (Portugal)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 30/04/2029

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 48,50 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 19,45 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: Estimation under development

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: Estimation under development

P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT

Project Title	Landscape and readiness of computational New Approach Methods based on advanced AI and ML approaches for chemicals' next generation risk assessment
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	NAMAM

Project Manager	Uko Maran uko.maran@ut.ee	University of Tartu	Estonia
Deputy Project manager	Sulev Sild sulev.sild@ut.ee	University of Tartu	Estonia
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	T6.4.2
Project Id	P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

This project will address the existing landscape and the potential acceptance of AI & ML driven QSAR models to important properties in chemical risk assessment with an emphasis on the regulatory use. The aim is to conduct a review and analysis of the AI and ML QSAR models and to identify best practices and further actions to ensure a transparent regulatory use, uncertainty estimation and its communication towards end-users, independent verification and understanding of the outcome of such models. To develop reporting standards and decision-making criteria for ML and AI predictive models in the context of NAMs and NGRA. The best examples will be identified and made available as FAIR data through the [QsarDB.org](https://qsardb.org) repository.

The EU is exploring ways to exploit New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) for chemical risk assessment (RA) in a regulatory context. Among them are computer based approaches that allow to estimate effects and doses (QSAR and Read-across) and to integrate multiple *in silico* and *in vitro* data (Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA)). Today more and more advanced machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) mathematical approaches are used to estimate effects and doses (QSAR) and to learn patterns of chemical behaviour from multiple data (in silico and in vitro). The aim of using these data-driven approaches is to make better informed decisions for the protection of human health and environment while reducing animal testing. Advanced ML methods often outperform classical statistical methods, specifically in the case of chemically diverse and big data. Several recent applications of AI approaches (e.g. protein folding, playing chess and the board game “go”) have demonstrated that they can rival or outperform traditional computational methods or human experts. ML and AI approaches in chemical next generation risk assessment (NGRA) have good potential to support and improve complex processes and activities. For example, to fill data gaps, improve models for important properties (also referred as endpoints), and gather evidence for helping decision making.

However, the application of these novel approaches is not a trivial task for various reasons. Since NAMs are still under active research, there is a lack of knowledge outside the research community. Therefore, more knowledge together with detailed guidelines are required for their application and acceptance in the regulatory context of chemical RA. This can be mitigated through teaching and education to advance the uptake across all stakeholders groups. Also there is a lack of transparency due to limited documentation or accessibility to underlying data and algorithms. This makes advanced computational methods (ACM) in content of NAMs difficult to understand and characterise uncertainty associated with using them. Thus, there is a clear need for better standardisation, transparent reporting, validation and illustration of AI & ML driven *in silico* models.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will provide a framework for more transparent reporting of predictions obtained using AI and ML models for regulatory purposes. This will help stakeholders (for better predictions’ reporting) and regulators (for predictions’ evaluation).

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The main outcomes and impacts of the project include:

- Identification of ML and AI QSAR models of PARC focused properties that could be used for filling data gaps.
- Knowledge of the transparency and potential reproducibility of ML and AI models for chemical risk assessment and decision-making workflows.
- Identification of main roadblocks related to the applications of QSAR models, including applicability domain evaluation and uncertainty estimation related to ML and AI models.
- Case studies that attempt to reuse published ML and/or AI models to identify issues that need addressing to improve acceptance for regulatory use.

Key words:

AI model, ML model, in silico models, QSAR, QSPR, NAMs, reporting framework, applicability domain, uncertainty

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will address PARC operational objectives OO9 by facilitating the uptake of new approach methods in regulatory RA processes and is mainly focused on advanced ML and AI models.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Interactions with other WPs in PARC are summarised as follows:

- € Cooperation is foreseen with WP2 task 2.1 to define priorities for the research.
- € Potential cooperation with WP5 task 5.1 on the topic of computational NAMs for closing data gaps in human health and environmental endpoints
- € Potential collaboration with WP5 task 5.3 on the evaluation of in silico methods for ADME/Tox parameters in PBK models and quantitative systems toxicology.
- € Potential collaboration with WP7 task 7.1 on the PARC's FAIR Data Policy (PFDP).
- € Cooperation with WP8 task 8.2 on the evaluation of computational NAMs for the early warning system (EWS) on chemical risks.
- € Cooperation with WP8 task 8.3 on the integrating of computational NAMs.

Links outside PARC

OECD-QAF: (OECD QSAR Assessment Framework, duration 2021-2024) develops criteria on how to assess (i) QSAR and any other computational model validity used as NAMs and (ii) how to assess validity of QSAR and any other computational prediction. Three partners (ISS, INERIS, UT) of the project are involved in OECD-QAF.

ASPIS-cluster (<https://www.aspis-cluster.com/>): cluster acts as roof organisation for the RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX & PrecisionTOX projects. IRFM (E. Benfenati) is co-leading the WG on computational methods with other people from the lab being part of the WG; i.e. acting as liaison.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.19: Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs). (M81)

Expected Project Reports:

- Project Report 1: Overview of exploratory analysis and identification of research priorities and requirements (M12)
- Framework to facilitate an adequate reporting for the AI/ML NAMs to be used for regulatory purposes (M24)
- Final report on the main outcomes of the project (M34)

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- LM1: Refined work plan and methodology for years 2 and 3 (M12)
- LM2: Selection of case studies (M16)
- LM3: Framework tested on case studies (M30)

Partners List:

UT (Estonia); UG-PL (Poland); IRFM (Italy); UNIBASEL (Switzerland); NIPH(VKM) (Norway); ISS (Italy); INERIS (France); UKCHE (United Kingdom); NIVA (Norway)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 77,16 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 25,72 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: Non identified at present

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: Non identified at present

A6.4.3 A comprehensive framework to assess exposure and facilitate enforcement of chemicals in articles and materials on the EU-market – 1 PROJECT

P6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProM_MU

Project Title	6.4.3.1 A comprehensive review and application of databases and testing methods for SUBstances in PProducts and Materials		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SuProM		
Project Manager	Lisa Melymuk lisa.melymuk@recetox.muni.cz	MU (RECETOX)	Czechia
Deputy Project manager	Robin Vestergren robin.vestergren@kemi.se	KemI	Sweden
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36 Months
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.3
Project Id	P_6.4.3. a_Y1_SuProM_MU		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The European Commission’s Green Deal and the Chemical strategy for sustainability provides the direction for a toxic free and sustainable future where chemicals are produced and used in a way that maximises their contribution to society while minimizing risks for the environment and human health. In these strategic documents it is envisaged that products and material used in society should be designed without the use of the most harmful chemicals and that the use of other harmful chemicals should be minimized.

Enforcement of EU chemicals safety and environmental legislation has a central role in implementing the European Green Deal agenda and the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. No matter how ambitious the legislation is on paper, it will never fulfil the level of protection of consumers and workers if not properly enforced. The methods developed in this activity will facilitate a systematic risk-based identification of priority substances, products, and materials, as well as support and direct the development of efficient analytical methods for enforcement actions. This will support national enforcement authorities of chemicals legislation, including product specific legislations (for example, the RoHS Directive, EC Toys directive,

regulations on food contact materials, etc.) and restrictions of chemicals in various products. Enforcement is essential, and without enforcement any law will be ineffective.

The newly proposed Sustainable Products Initiative (SPI) aims to reduce the environmental footprint of products throughout their lifecycle. The legislative proposal will extend the scope of the Ecodesign framework beyond energy-related products, while also considering additional sustainability principles to regulate the environmental impact of goods, including chemicals in products. A consistent and complete methodology for assessing the environmental, climate and health impacts of products (and services) over their life cycle are needed. The Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) has been suggested as a basis for such a consistent and complete methodology. However, there is still a need to further develop the PEF methodology to more adequately address toxicity impacts of chemicals. The proposed project will evaluate how such sustainability assessments of products and materials are implemented with respect to chemicals, and provide a basis for future work providing recommendations on the application of this framework.

Main expected outputs of the project

This project will evaluate the currently available information on substances in products and materials, and how this information is integrated in enforcement activities and life cycle assessments, based on a comprehensive review of chemical databases and gap and needs analysis of analytical testing methodologies. Based on this analysis, future projects on the development of new databases tools, and analytical testing methods will be designed. This will support the aim of Activity 6.4.3, in applying tools and databases that enable a systematic identification of priority substances in products and materials to support the transition to the circular economy.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The primary stakeholders for this project are national and EU agencies responsible for enforcement of chemical and product legislations. It is envisaged that the results from this project and follow-up projects will contribute to a more systematic and effective enforcement of chemicals.

Key words

substances in products; chemical databases; materials; consumer products; enforcement; product composition;

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

Identifying harmful chemicals and prioritizing risk assessment efforts from the rapidly growing number and large diversity of chemical substances on the market constitutes one of the core challenges identified in PARC. Furthermore, the identification of priority substances from regulatory databases and information transfer structures will also facilitate the work to establish early warning systems, integrative exposure models and implementation of the concept of “safe and sustainable by design”.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: Support in administering questionnaires to national chemical agencies as an information gathering exercises on the topics of chemical databases and enforcement of chemical regulations in products and materials.
- WP7: Data management plan
- WP9: Training, laboratory network: Evaluation of chemical laboratories/methods involved in enforcement activities related to substances in products and materials; capacity-building related to enforcement activities
- Other WPs: WP4 (Task 4.2 Prioritization of substances for screening/monitoring; Task 4.3 Analytical method development), WP6 (Task 6.2 Exposure via consumer articles); WP8 (Task 8.1 Safe and sustainable by design; Task 8.2 Early warning systems)

Links outside PARC

The research on developing databases and improving chemical information transfer is linked to several initiatives such as the SCiP database (ECHA), development of product passports and the use of product environmental footprints.

The research on new testing methods for products and materials will be carried out in close collaboration

with national agencies responsible for enforcing chemical and product legislations.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

None identified at present.

Expected Project Reports:

Report on existing database structures with recommended structures – M36 – MU

Report on current screening and enforcement structures – M24 – TUKES

Report on LCA incorporation of chemical hazards – M24 – MU

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Stakeholder advisory board meeting to share information and recommendations on current data structures relevant to products and materials – M6

Completion of information gathering from national chemical agencies – M8

Mapping of database structures and gaps – M12

Annual communication through online meetings with Stakeholder advisory board: (M12, M24)

Identification of case study topics – M14

Partners List:

MU (Czechia); KemI (Sweden); Rise (Sweden); TUKES (Finland); VUA (Netherlands), Vito (Belgium) (WP7); TNO (Netherlands) (WP7)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 99,75PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 33,22 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 423 093 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 141 031 €

A6.4.4 Risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity – 5 PROJECTS

P6.4.4.a_Y1_CRNCS1_KEMI

Project Title	Clarify regulatory needs – Transform EU strategies into regulatory useable research projects		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	CRNCS1		
Project Manager	Johan Axelman Johan_axelman@kemi.se	Swedish Chemicals Agency	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	Sabine Duquesne Sabine_Duquesne@uba.de	Umweltsbundesamt (UBA)	Germany
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	81
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	A.6.4.4
Project Id	P6.4.4.a_Y1_CRNCS1_KEMI		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The activity is tailored toward supporting strategic transition initiatives such as the roadmap to systems-based ERA (by EFSA - European partnership for next generation, system-based ERA [PERA]) and European co-funded partnership on biodiversity (Biodiversa+).

The activity aims at better assessing effects on overall biodiversity and the possibility to simplify (i.e. less resource demanding) the methods used for the environmental risk assessment (ERA) of plant protection products (PPP) without compromising the level of protection to be ensured by the assessment. Furthermore, we will explore new holistic approaches to environmental risk assessment to overcome the shortcomings of the current substance-by-substance paradigm and consider the environmental context more realistically. Both existing and new models for prospective risk assessment will be reviewed and amended using monitoring data. The activity will also help to explore new frameworks for risk characterisation that support system-based approaches to risk assessment by expanding the current approach.

The project is directly applicable to the environmental risk assessment for the authorisation of PPP and aims to better link the goal of the EU environmental and agricultural strategies to the EU regulation 1107/2009. According to EU policy's PPP are regarded as an important tool for plant protection, their use and risk should be reduced and biodiversity loss stopped. Therefore, an integrated ERA approach is needed.

Revisions of the EU regulation 1107/2009, EU environmental or agricultural strategies may benefit from the knowledge produced in this project as the goal is to develop a next generation ERA, with a better assessment of impact on biodiversity. The close collaboration of scientists, risk assessors and EFSA in this project will aid the anticipation and integration.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will ensure that the outcome of the other projects within 6.4.4 address the common goal of an improved ERA-scheme better aligning with EU strategies and assessing biodiversity. Considering regulatory needs and ensuring regulatory acceptance are key components of this project. It will be identified how the input from other stakeholders (risk managers, farmers, etc) can be integrated in the ERA development.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The current ERA scheme is well established, but has fallen out of step with environmental reality and technological possibilities. The project will provide a more realistic and resource-efficient ERA-scheme. However, the development needs to be supported by EFSA to be taken up by the risk assessors in the MS. The close collaboration with EFSA in this project, ensures a targeted and operational development of a new ERA-scheme and facilitates the application by end-users and stakeholders, e.g. risk assessors and applicants.

Key words:

Environmental risk assessment, Systems-based approach, Regulatory needs, Stakeholder engagement

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

PARC WPs interlinking within Activity 6.4.4.

- WP 2 and 3 to ensure a coordinated dialogue with regulators and policy makers.
- T 6.3 Project within *Review of risk assessment methodologies*: Specificities and similarities of prospective and retrospective risk assessment for pesticides.
- Activity 6.4.1 Environmental risk assessment of chemical mixtures to ensure alignment and avoid overlaps in system approaches.
- Activity 6.4.2 Project on NAMs in environmental risk assessments
- T 4.2 Environmental monitoring.
- WP 7 Data policy (management, harmonisation, interoperability, exchange). A standardised and comparable methodology would facilitate sharing and downstream use of the ERA-data.

Links outside PARC

Strategic partnerships at the EU-level, such as EFSA initiative Partnership and Roadmap to systems-based environmental risk assessment (PERA) and Biodiversa+, as well as projects such as SPRINT.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.21 Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M81)

Expected Project Reports:

- Discussion document on Drivers of change, Problem description, Future state of ERA, Gap analysis, Short term-remedies and potential long-term solutions, Prioritised Areas of work. End of year 1.
- Updated document on Drivers of change, Problem description, Future state of ERA, Gap analysis, Short term-remedies and potential long-term solutions, Prioritised Areas of work. Annually updated.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Non identified at present

Partners List:

KEMI (SE); UBA(DE); FOEN (CH); ANSES (FR); EFSA; ULUND (SE); NIVA (NO); UOS (DE)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 32 PM (for the first 3 years)

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 11,65 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: Non identified at present

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: Non identified at present

P6.4.4.b_Y1_PPPEXPCS2_SLU

SProject Title	Reduce complexity of models for predicted environmental concentrations of plant protection products while ensuring their predictive capacity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PPPEXPCS2		
Project Manager	Mikaela Gönzei Mikaela.Gonzei@slu.se §	SLU	Se
Deputy Project manager	Gusatf Boström Gusatf.bostrom@slu.se §	SLU	SE
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	81
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.4.2
Project Id	P6.4.4.b_Y1_PPPEXPCS2_SLU		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

In 2019 the SLU Centre for Pesticides in the Environment (CKB) at the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences developed a new method for calculating predicted concentrations in surface water (called PEC CKB) (Boström et al., 2019). This approach successfully extends the type of methods which predict

environmental concentrations of PPPs in water bodies with fewer input parameters, but on the basis of established knowledge of environmental processes (e.g. Kattwinkel et al. 2011). The proposed calculation method is very simple and requires minimal input data. However, there is obviously some spread in the underlying data, and further work would aim at achieving even closer conformity between predicted (PEC) and measured (MEC) concentrations by focusing improvements on the most important factors of the calculations.

The PEC CKB concept serves as an example for possible simplification of the exposure component in the ERA. This proposed project aims at exploring further ways of simplifying the PEC calculations within the ERA. This can be pursued through testing and further development of the PEC CKB or similar concepts like the German models Exposit and GERDA, and through comparing the predictability of these simpler models to MEC from different EU member states (MS).

The new models will be validated against currently existing models and monitoring data additional to those used to derive the models.

To start with, the work will focus on the aquatic environment where there are different PEC models in use and where there are numerous monitoring data. What we learn from that work, however, will be used to develop the PEC models for the terrestrial environment in a similar way.

Main expected outputs of the project

The comparison of several models for exposure, including different parameters, with the same dataset will give us information on differences and similarities of the models' predictive capacity and protection level. By various analyses we will be able to evaluate which factors are most important to explain the concentrations in the environment and how the predictive capacity can be improved. We will also assess the transferability of the models between data from different MS and identify factors that play an important role such as geography, climate or soil properties.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The end-users of the research are mainly risk assessors in the context of authorization of plant protection products at MS and EU level. In addition, the project aims to contribute to a transition to a systems-based ERA by facilitating reusability of data generated within the ERA. In order to efficiently allocate resources, we need to examine if the ERA used for plant protection products can be simplified.

Key words:

Environmental risk assessment, exposure assessment, systems-based approach, plant protection products, monitoring

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project will contribute to fulfil the need to develop the ecological RA approaches to overcome the shortcomings of the current substance-by-substance paradigm and consider the environmental context more realistically as identified in the DoA.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

PARC WPs interlinking within Activity 6.4.4:

- WP 2 and 3 to ensure a coordinated dialogue with regulators and policy makers.
- WP 6.3 Project within *Review of risk assessment methodologies*: Specificities and similarities of prospective and retrospective risk assessment for pesticides.
- Activity 6.4.1 Environmental risk assessment of chemical mixtures to ensure alignment and avoid overlaps in system approaches.
- Activity 6.4.2 Project on NAMs in environmental risk assessments
- Task 4.2 Environmental monitoring.
- WP 7 Data policy (management, harmonisation, interoperability, exchange). A standardised and comparable methodology would facilitate sharing and downstream use of the ERA-data.

Links outside PARC

A member of the former FOCUS (FORum for the Co-ordination of pesticide fate models and their USE) surface water workgroup is participating in the project. Since their work is the basis of the exposure component of the existing ERA this will improve the possibility that the results of the project will be implemented in a regulatory context. Other groups working with exposure models, such as GERDA will also be contacted.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.21 Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M81)

Expected Project Reports:

- Technical report describing comparison of different existing methods for predicting PPP concentrations in surface waters within agricultural catchments validated against monitoring data from various European geographical regions.
- Technical report describing the most relevant factors for predicting PPP concentrations in surface waters within agricultural catchments.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Non identified at present

Partners List:

SLU (CKB), UFZ (SE), Fraunhofer IME (DE), University of Osnabrück (DE), EAWAG (CH), NIVA (NO), ULUND (SE), IEP-NRI (PL). Regulatory core group: KEMI, UBA, FOEN, ANSES, EFSA.

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 51 PM (for the first 3 years)

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 19 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: Non identified at present

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: Non identified at present

P6.4.4.c_Y1_PPPEFFCS3_UFZ

Project Title	Reduce complexity of models for predictions of environmental effects of plant protection products while ensuring their predictive capacity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PPPEFF CS3		
Project Manager	Matthias Liess matthias.liess@ufz.de	UFZ	DE
Deputy Project manager	Paulo Sousa ips@zoo.uc.pt	CFE	PT
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	01	Expected duration	81
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.4.2
Project Id	P6.4.4.c_Y1_PPPEFF CS3_UFZ		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The aim of this project is moving towards a protective ERA with reduced complexity and resources required while keeping it as information-rich as necessary. This will be achieved by including only the information and processes that have been proven by ecosystem monitoring and effect modelling to be relevant. This improves the extrapolation of effect information from lower tier laboratory investigations to field effects. This approach, realized by an extrapolation cycle – as known from the design of dynamic models – will reduce complexity of ERA and enable a field-based validation of effect assessment. The framework will be made accessible by a software package to enable a practicable and reproducible ERA.

The ongoing biodiversity crisis is caused by a variety of anthropogenic stressors including PPPs (European Environment Agency, 2015). This contradicts the requirements of the Regulation (EU) 1107/2009 that PPPs must not exert “unacceptable effects on the environment” considering “particularly contamination of surface waters “with regards to “non-target species” and “impact on biodiversity and the ecosystem“ (EU Parliament, 2009). Accordingly, risk assessment of PPPs needs to be improved in order to better protect the environment.

The risk assessment process of PPPs has developed into a highly sophisticated, time consuming and complex process. Despite this elaborated procedure, the occurrence of PPP has been linked to adverse ecological effects on non-target organisms in several field investigations. This does not comply with the Regulation (EU) 546/2011 that “Member States shall ensure that use of plant protection products does not have any long-term repercussions for the abundance and diversity of non-target species” (EU Commission, 2011). Even the responsible authorities are questioning the extent to which these environmental protection requirements are being implemented in practice. For example, the European Court of Auditors noted “limited progress in measuring and reducing risks” of PPPs (European Court of Auditors, 2020). Accordingly, the effect assessment within the ERA needs also to be improved and furthermore simplified (Liess et al. 2021). Reasons for the mismatch of regulation and ecosystem level protection are numerous. Concerning the effects assessment, they include effects of multiple PPPs (applied in combination/ tank mixture and successively), unexpected high field sensitivity of vulnerable species due to the interaction of additional environmental stressors along with PPPs, and observed indirect effects; these may produce more severe effects than predicted from the single compound based prospective risk assessment. On the other hand, effects propagation, genetic adaptation and migration from recovery areas may mitigate adverse effects. However, to avoid higher complexity in the ERA due to the integration of highly relevant ecological factors, we have to identify appropriate strategies to reduce the complexity of effect assessment while achieving the desired level of protection. This will help to develop a more efficient process, which uses the resources available for risk assessment wisely and allows to rapidly identify the pesticide use harming ecosystems.

Main expected outputs of the project

Field monitoring data related to exposure and effects of PPP in a great variety of member states will be collated. Currently high-quality data have been identified for Germany, Sweden, Switzerland. Data from a variety of member states in different regions of the EU need to be included to reflect the European diversity. A feedback loop between existing risk assessment thresholds and retrospective ecosystem monitoring results will be formalized to constantly improve the level of realism and validation of ERA. By this the project will enable regulators to identify ecological process to be included into the risk assessment.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The end-users will be provided with the identification of the relevant factors needed to link laboratory lower-tier tests and effects at the ecosystem level to make better use of lower-tier test information. Additionally, effect information obtained from the ecosystem level will enable to better use higher-tier test information within the risk assessment framework

The implementation of the most relevant environmental factors into the risk assessment process so that the sensitive field populations can be identified and protected and that ERA at the same time strives an improved balance between reduced complexity and increased ecological realism.

Increase regulatory usability by documenting a transparent and easy to follow framework on how effect models can be replicated and adapted to ensure transferability between member states.

Key words:

Environmental risk assessment, effect assessment, systems-based approach, plant protection products, monitoring

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

This project will contribute to fulfil the need to develop the ecological RA approaches to overcome the shortcomings of the current substance-by-substance paradigm and consider the environmental context more realistically as identified in the DoA.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

PARC WPs interlinking within Activity 6.4.4:

- WP 2 and 3 to ensure a coordinated dialogue with regulators and policy makers.
- Task 6.3 Project within *Review of risk assessment methodologies*: Specificities and similarities of prospective and retrospective risk assessment for pesticides.
- Activity 6.4.1 Environmental risk assessment of chemical mixtures to ensure alignment and avoid overlaps in system approaches.
- Activity 6.4.2 Project on NAMs in environmental risk assessments
- Task 4.2 Environmental monitoring.
- WP 7 Data policy (management, harmonisation, interoperability, exchange). A standardised and comparable methodology would facilitate sharing and downstream use of the ERA-data

Links outside PARC

Strategic partnerships at the EU-level, such as EFSA initiative Partnership and Roadmap to systems-based environmental risk assessment (PERA) and Biodiversa+, as well as projects such as SPRINT.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.21 Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M81)

Expected Project Reports:

- Technical report on the most relevant factors describing the transfer function that enables a link between laboratory lower-tier tests and effects at ecosystem level. Ranking the relevance of the factors describing the lab to field transfer function. Identification to which extent interactions between PPPs and additional environmental factors increase the sensitivity of field populations.
- Technical report informing on factors and processes needed to be included in the ERA to obtain an improved balance between reduced complexity and increased ecological realism.
- Software package software to make the framework for an improved ERA accessible to the regulators. The usability and integration of software tools needs to be developed within a structured feedback process involving the regulators within an extended timeframe. Starting

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Non identified at present

Partners List:

UFZ (DE), CFE (PT), EAWAG (CH), SLU (SE); UKOLD, (DE); ULUND (SE), NIVA (NO), UCLM (ES), UOS (DE), ISCI (ES)

Regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), EFSA, ANSES (FR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 69 PM (for the first 3 years)

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 29 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: Non identified at present

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: Non identified at present

P6.4.4.d_Y1_PPPBENCHCS4_UKOLD

Project Title	Benchmark ERA to support the transition towards a holistic paradigm		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PPPBENCH		
Project Manager	Ralf Schäfer schaefer-ralf@uni-landau.de	UKOLD	DE
Deputy Project manager	NA		
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	81
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.4.3
Project Id	P6.4.4.d_Y1_PPPBENCHCS4_UKOLD		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

This project aims to ensure that results of any independently performed ERA of a PPP can be used as a benchmark for ERAs of other PPPs, i.e. comparing and ranking risk profiles of PPPs among substances and in different areas (e.g. for selected organism groups) of the ERA when assessed on the basis of similar level of refinement. The development of an ERA methodology yielding comparable results is the specific topic of this project. This helps in delivering consistent ERA results and once compared to monitoring results, it will eventually improve its reliability regarding the estimation of environmental risks. The overall aim of the project is to contribute to a more holistic ERA that manages the overall risk in an efficient manner. This topic is dependent on results of other projects within 6.4.4 and can also serve as a building block for a systems-based risk assessment. Moreover, it is dependent on clarifications from the regulatory and policy level. The project will therefore be coordinated with other work packages, activities and projects within PARC as well as initiatives outside PARC.

Main expected outputs of the project

Expected output is an ERA concept and defined methodology to be used as a basis to develop a new guidance for ERA within the authorisation process. The resulting ERA should have an improved performance in terms of capturing the relative risk of different PPPs in a relevant spatial and temporal scale when assessed on the basis of similar data/ level of refinement. The improved ERA should also support systems-based risk assessments and facilitate use down the line, such as improved advisory services and systems-based risk management

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

One fundamental property of the ERA to improve would be the comparability of the methodology used to assess the environmental risks (not to be confused with comparative assessment performed as part of substitution process in the current assessment). If used in connection with specific decision rules, this methodology in turn could ensure that newly authorised PPPs have a lower, or if other reasons apply (e.g. resistance management) similar, risk level than those previously authorised.

Key words:

Environmental risk assessment, effect assessment, systems-based approach, plant protection products,

monitoring, benchmarking, comparative risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

PARC WPs interlinking within Activity 6.4.4:

- WP 2 and 3 to ensure a coordinated dialogue with regulators and policy makers.
- Task 6.3 Project within *Review of risk assessment methodologies*: Specificities and similarities of prospective and retrospective risk assessment for pesticides.
- Activity 6.4.1 Environmental risk assessment of chemical mixtures to ensure alignment and avoid overlaps in system approaches.
- Activity 6.4.2 Project on NAMs in environmental risk assessments
- Task 4.2 Environmental monitoring.
- WP 7 Data policy (management, harmonisation, interoperability, exchange). A standardised and comparable methodology would facilitate sharing and downstream use of the ERA-data.

Links outside PARC

Strategic partnerships at the EU-level, such as EFSA initiative Partnership and Roadmap to systems-based environmental risk assessment (PERA) and Biodiversa+, as well as projects such as SPRINT.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.21 Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M81)

Expected Project Reports:

Project Report 1 – Compiled data for internal risk benchmarking (month 12)

Project Report 2 – Analyses for internal risk benchmarking accomplished (month 18)

Project Report 3 – Database of ERA results and complementary data (month 18)

Project Report 4 – Data compiled for external risk benchmarking (month 21)

Project Report 5 – Analyses for external risk benchmarking accomplished (month 27)

Project Report 6 – Methodology for comparability analyses developed (month 33)

Project Report 7 – Technical report on results of benchmarking analyses with suggestions for methodology and most important factors having an impact on the result of the ERA (month 36)

Project Report 8 – Report on the implementation of the comparability methodology into the risk assessment paradigm (month 81)

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Non identified at present

Partners List:

UKOLD (DE), UFZ (DE), ISCIII (ES); EAWAG (CH), NIVA (NO), ULUND (SE). Regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), ANSES (FR), EFSA

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 45,80 PM (for the first 3 years)

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 17,50 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: Non identified at present

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: Non identified at present

P6.4.4.e_Y1_PPPOSCS5_ISCIII

Project Title	Quantify effects of PPP and other stressors through landscape risk assessment informing on environmental impacts
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Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PPPOS		
Project Manager	José Tarazona Jose.TARAZONA@efsa.europa.eu	ISCI3	ES
Deputy Project manager	Matthias Liess matthias.liess@ufz.de	UFZ	DE
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	81
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.4.3
Project Id	P6.4.4.e_Y1_PPPOSCS5_ISCI3		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The aim is moving the ERA paradigm from single chemical-crop combination to landscape-based ERA integrating landscape structures and aggregated (several crops) and combined (several pesticides) exposures into the current risk assessment methods. Due to the complexity of environmental landscape-scale assessments, the identification of the key “drivers” for exposure and effects and the benchmarking proposed in the other three projects constitute a prerequisite. This project will build landscape models considering the results from the three previous projects, which will be used for the identification of the key modelling blocks under different landscape conditions. In addition, the EFSA proposals for setting protection goals based on ecosystem services and biodiversity in ERA will be implemented to develop risk characterisation tools that could be used as information source for environmental impact assessments; this will help to overcome the currently too fragmented ERA approaches.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project has direct connections and will benefit from the outcomes of the projects aiming to compare predictions with monitoring data, using the agricultural landscape characteristics for strengthening the feedback loop from environmental monitoring and vigilance and ensure focus on factors that trigger the risk and overall impact on biodiversity in terrestrial agro-biosystems and aquatic ecosystems. In addition to supporting regulatory decisions, including the design and implementation of National Plans under the Sustainable Use Directive (SUD), a complementary long-term goal is to deliver management tools to advise and support practitioners to make informed decision (e.g. considering in selection of a PPP versus another PPP the local and regional levels/ ecotype) in the design and implementation of Integrated Pest Management and optimizing use and effects of ecosystem restorations with multiple purposes (i.e. improving biodiversity, reducing PPP pollution etc. through e.g. Nature Based Solutions).

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project aims to deliver methodologies and tools to promote a transition to a system- based ERA. End-users will be actors responsible for a systems-based risk assessment, such as authorisation, enforcement and agricultural advisors. Comprehensible data on environmental impact and tools will enable these actors to take informed decisions.

The project will provide direct support to the implementation of measures under the SUD and reduction of pesticide impacts under the EU Green Deal and specifically the Farm to Fork Strategy.

The integration of farm management with agricultural landscape characteristics will provide support to decisions on sustainability at local, regional and national level, supporting the integration of sustainability concepts in food production and the CAP.

These new approach for ERA would support other policies, including WFD and the Habitats Directive. Optimizing the overlap of concepts and terminologies between central compartments in environmental management is essential for a (cost)efficient collaboration between different public management bodies. The outcomes will successfully pinpointing key stressors at regional level that impair biodiversity, ecological quality, and ecosystem services.

Key words:

Environmental risk assessment, systems-based approach, plant protection products, landscape assessment, multiple stressors, holistic risk assessment

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

PARC WPs interlinking within Activity 6.4.4:

- WP 2 and 3 to ensure a coordinated dialogue with regulators and policy makers.
- Task 6.2 and 6.3. The landscape approach for ERA will be used as the basis for case studies on aggregated human pesticide exposure from the environment, including the integrative prospective assessments (case study under 6.2) and a retrospective assessment (case study under 6.3) using human biomonitoring data
- Task 6.3 Project within *Review of risk assessment methodologies*: Specificities and similarities of prospective and retrospective risk assessment for pesticides.
- Activity 6.4.1 Environmental risk assessment of chemical mixtures to ensure alignment and avoid overlaps in system approaches.
- Activity 6.4.2 Project on NAMs in environmental risk assessments
- Task 4.2 Environmental monitoring.
- WP 7 Data policy (management, harmonisation, interoperability, exchange). A standardised and comparable methodology would facilitate sharing and downstream use of the ERA-data.

Links outside PARC

Strategic partnerships at the EU-level, such as EFSA initiative Partnership and Roadmap to systems-based environmental risk assessment (PERA) and BiodivERsA.

The proposed work will be interlinked with several national and international projects including the Norwegian Agriculture monitoring program for pesticides and supporting cumulative risk assessments (<https://www.nibio.no/en/subjects/environment/the-norwegian-agricultural-environmental-monitoring-programme-jova>), the project « Cumulative hazard and risk assessment of complex mixtures and multiple stressors (MixRisk) » (www.niva.no/mixrisk), and several activities of NIVAs Computational Toxicology Program, NCTP (www.niva.no/nctp).

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.21 Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M81)

Expected Project Reports:

Conceptual models for aggregate and combined exposure to pesticides at landscape level covering the local and regional needs as well as national and EU needs. The tools will support the selection of the best IPM approach allowing an ERA-based scientifically sound assessment of sustainability regarding pesticide use as well as a comparative impact with other stressors.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- Identification on protection needs covering also for SUD, CAP and biodiversity strategy,
- Prioritisation of case studies,
- Verification of key elements for landscape ERA from the case studies,
- Extrapolation of the case study outcomes into quantitative landscape ERA tools,
- Adaptation of the tools to different regulatory/policy and voluntary initiatives through networking activities.

Partners List:

ISCIH (ES), UFZ (DE), UKOLD (DE), CFE (PT), NIVA (NO), IEP-NRI (PL), OFB (FR), UCLM (ES), ULUND (SE), Uni Osnabrück (DE)

Regulatory core team: KEMI, UBA, FOEN, EFSA, ANSES

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 124,30 PM (for the first 3 years)

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 39 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: Non identified at present

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: Non identified at present

WP7 FAIR data – 3 PROJECTS

T7.1 PARC FAIR Data Policy (PFDP) and DMP

No project submitted at present.

T7.2 Data libraries – 2 PROJECTS

A7.2.1 PARC FAIR Data Policy (PFDP) and DMP

No project submitted at present.

A7.2.2 Implement a PARC FAIR data hub – 2 PROJECTS

P7.2.2.a Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO

Project Title	Chemicals in the Environment data reuse		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	ENV DATA (RE)USE		
Project Manager	Richard Hůlek richard.hulek@recetox.muni.cz CZ	Masaryk University (MU, RECETOX)	CZ
Deputy Project manager	Jana Klánová jana.klanova@recetox.muni.cz CZ	Masaryk University (MU, RECETOX)	CZ
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP7	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	7.2.2
Project Id	P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Over the years various tools and database platforms were created to provide for storage, analysis, and visualization of occurrence data and trends in chemical exposure in the environment at global, EU, and national levels (for example, GMOS, EMEP, EBAS, GENASIS, GMP data warehouse, NORMAN, IpCHEM, etc.). Nevertheless, each of the tools or knowledge hubs was developed for different communities and comprise different services and scopes. Available datasets are often organized by environmental matrix,

contain different scopes and contents, and are at various stages of development (harmonization principles, ontology, tools).

The environmental monitoring and exposure component of PARC explores the presence of (priority) chemicals in a multicompartment environment and the resulting exposure of humans when chemical substances come from multiple sources and move along different pathways, fostering a “one health” chemical risk assessment strategy. Aggregated, combined, and cumulative exposures will be assessed through surveys of the co-occurrence of chemical substances, their metabolites, and degradation products in different matrices.

Members in R&I work packages in PARC ask for solutions to access/connect to existing data resources* in monitoring programs, databases, and libraries to help them with mapping and accessing the information available in the various data resources. This comprises a need to extract and combine information on (priority) chemicals in the environment that will then guide their further work on improvements of human and environmental/ecological risk assessment.

* *Data resources in this project and in WP7 represent “the major existing and planned databases, repositories, platforms, registries, portals and libraries relevant for chemical risk assessment”.*

Main expected outputs of the project

The project’s main goal is to support the reuse of existing data in relation to environmental exposure and the production and management of newly generated data in accordance with FAIR principles and in view of the concepts of Open Data and One substance, one assessment.

Therefore, the project is structured around three main activities: i) map the existing data resources relevant for environmental exposure to chemicals and assess the current landscape; ii) when having sufficient knowledge about the existing landscape, develop solutions for accessing and re(using) exposure data available in the existing/newly developed data resources, iii) cooperate and support other WPs in producing and managing data in line with FAIR principles and in accordance with the Open Data approach, which should ultimately support the concept of “One substance, once assessment”.

This will be achieved via a series of steps:

a) mapping the existing data resources relevant for exposure to chemicals in the environment (*landscaping*), **M1-12**

b) comparison of existing platforms and systems and assessment of their FAIRness (*architecture & assessment*), **M1-M12**

Output (a+b): selection of best-fit components (cornerstones) for “Initial architecture for PARC FAIR data platform for chemicals risk assessment”.

c) creating access to existing data resources that successfully passed through the FAIRness assessment and updating other data resources so that they become FAIR (*solutions for data reuse*), **M10**

d) developing FAIR data libraries if the appropriate solutions are missing (*solutions for FAIR data libraries*), **M12**

Output (c+d): online platform(s) connecting existing data resources on (priority) chemicals for reuse in risk assessment in PARC (and in particular in WPs 4, 6, 8), but also for national users, regulatory agencies, and the research community.

The ultimate goals of the project are that:

- data on (priority) chemicals in across environmental matrices are available for re-use between different risk assessment actors,
- existing and new relevant data resources are connected across silos and geographical areas (national, EU, and international)
- data to be re-used are harmonized, validated, FAIR, and cover the most complete available datasets with relevant metadata and are easily accessible.
- PARC generated data are stored in a FAIR online platform

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project contributes to REACH - supports human and environmental/ecological risk assessment, and allows for reuse of data and knowledge - regulatory agencies to have direct access to environmental data, and indirectly that data will be available for reuse in models and toolboxes or for addressing research questions.

Key words: (meta)data, data resources, libraries, FAIR, harmonization, (open) access, open data, environmental exposure

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project supports the achievement and is closely aligned with operational objective 0010 “Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for risk assessment”. It aims for an effective exchange of reliable, relevant, curated, and FAIR data on chemicals (specifically environmental exposure data) between different stakeholders and policy domains (in line with the European Strategy for Data). Via mapping the existing data landscape and developing tailored solutions for data re(use) and the implementation of FAIR principles, the chemical RA community in PARC and beyond will increasingly reuse both scientific and regulatory data for application and innovation in risk assessment, thus empowering the European Green Deal Data Space.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: The project in 7.2 would need to establish synergies with existing projects such as ERA Planet (H2020), e-shape (H2020 project EuroGEOSS Showcases: Showcasing and promoting users’ uptake of GEOSS), Solutions, IPCHEM, NORMAN, European - EMEP, global - Stockholm Convention and Minamata Convention monitoring plans and also shared infrastructures (i.e., Elixir, CESNET, EOSC, EnvriFAIR-ESFRI).

WP7: Data management plan: The project is planned and will be implemented in task 7.2. Therefore, it is expected that partners in 7.2 will assist in the development of DMPs in other projects, mainly of WP 4, 6, and 8.

WP9: Training, laboratory network: Currently, the capacities and expertise of partners involved in WP7, and in particular task 7.2, are not considered sufficient to respond to the various needs that may arise from PARC WPs in relation to the data reuse and data FAIRfication. This issue will be circumvented by employing Go Fair Foundation experts who will assist in building a network of experts within PARC (i.e., of the FAIR implementation task group comprising a subset of data champions and data liaisons). Training will consist of several “train the trainer” sessions which will be organized and performed in close collaboration with task 9.4 on Training. Apart from task 9.4, the project will cooperate with tasks 9.1 and 9.2 in the development of the best-fit architecture for WP9 catalogues on laboratory and exposure monitoring networks. This cooperation between WP9 and WP7 is already ongoing and described in more detail in WP9 projects (i.e., 9.1_Y1_HBM catalogues and 9.2_Y1_ENV catalogues) led by ISCHIII and MU.

Other WPs:

For this particular project, close collaboration is expected with task 4.2 Environmental exposure and monitoring. Projects developed and implemented under 4.2 will focus on environmental exposure data and multisource monitoring. It is therefore expected that data from various data resources would need to be brought together, assessed against the FAIR principles, and combined to allow for multiple source exposure assessment. This project will cooperate and support 4.2 project partners in finding and applying the best solutions for accessing all the relevant data, their connection, re(use) and management in accordance with FAIR principles and if needed, making them available and accessible via a FAIR platform/repository. Similarly, close cooperation is foreseen in regard to WP6 and WP8, whenever data generated outside or within PARC are to be used in models.

The specific needs arising from the R&I WPs and solutions to be developed in 7.2 will be defined as individual project cases, so-called “use cases”. For each relevant R&I WP project, a data champion (from within WP7) and a data liaison (from within the respective WP and project) will be appointed to support the establishment of a horizontal link between WP7 (task 7.2) and the project of WPx. These will then further cooperate in the preparation of the data management plan and its implementation, and the definition

of a use case, if relevant.

Links outside PARC

This project serves experts/data holders and data users in tasks 4.2, 4.3, 6.2., 6.4., and WP8 but would need to establish synergies with existing projects and infrastructures, such as ERA Planet (H2020), e-shape (H2020 project EuroGEOSS Showcases: Showcasing and promoting users' uptake of GEOSS), Solutions, IPCHEM, NORMAN, European - EMEP, global - Stockholm Convention and Minamata Convention monitoring plans, and shared infrastructures (i.e., Elixir, CESNET, EOSC, EnvriFAIR-ESFRI).

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The project will partly contribute to the following deliverables of WP7 (task 7.1):

D7.1. Data Management Plan (DMP) (M6)

D7.2. PARC FAIR data policy (PFDP) (M18)

D7.3. 1st report on Data infrastructure, tools and services for FAIRification and reuse of chemical RA data (M36)

MS11. Network of trained FAIR data stewards (M12)

MS12. Architecture of PARC FAIR data hub & its integration with the COPCSD (M24)

Expected Project Reports: None identified at present.

Expected Projects Landmarks: None identified at present.

Partners List: MU (CZ), VITO (BE), UFZ (DE), BRGM (FR), UNILU (LU), ISSEP (BE), JSI (SI), ANSES (FR),

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 620 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 68 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 45 000 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 15 000 €

P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO

Project Title	FAIR and sustainable storage of human biomonitoring (HBM) datasets		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	HBMdatasets		
Project Manager	Jan Theunis Jan.theunis@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	Dirk Devriendt Dirk.devriendt.ext@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	42
PARC Workpackage number	WP7	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	7.2
Project Id	P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

This project deals with availability and (re)use of existing Human Biomonitoring (HBM) datasets (including datasets from HBM4EU, but also datasets produced in other projects), as well as with new datasets generated in PARC (i.e., in Task 4.1). HBM dataset will be made available as FAIR datasets for potential reuse by the broad risk assessment community. HBM datasets are challenging for reuse as they contain personal, sensitive data, which poses specific challenges for storage and reuse, related to ethical and legal issues. The full strength of the data for scientific and regulatory purposes will only be attained if analyses can be carried out on the individual data, if the coherence of the dataset is maintained, and if the data can be linked to different domains (e.g., health, biomolecular, spatial-environmental data, food, consumption, occupational). Finally, HBM datasets contain analyses of chemical metabolites for which no standardized identifications exist.

HBM datasets will be made available to allow reuse by different user groups: scientific users who may want to reuse the entire datasets (for research questions on exposure determinants, geographical comparisons, time trends, exposure-effect analyses, link with environmental sources, ..., comparing modelled exposure with observed exposure, ...), regulatory users who may be interested in the core occurrence data (for assessment and follow-up, integration of HBM data in models and toolboxes), and the general public. As such this project indirectly supports multiple regulatory processes and frameworks through support for improved human risk assessment, and for reuse of data and knowledge.

The broader relevance of the project lies in the development and implementation of scalable solutions for reuse of personal sensitive data while safeguarding legal and ethical constraints, including cross-domain linking of data, semantic and technical interoperability, and development and implementation of cross-domain ontologies, vocabularies and metadata schemes.

The project will be strongly aligned with Task 4.1, and more specifically with Task 4.1.5 as part of a sustainable HBM system.

Methodologically the project will investigate the feasibility to make use new developments in federated data infrastructures and federated data analysis. These methods are still in an early phase.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Hybrid federated data infrastructure allowing
 - o Reuse of HBM datasets by *new parties* while respecting privacy and consent
 - New data collected in PARC
 - New PARC partners working with the data
 - o Integration with *external HBM datasets* from other projects (e.g. EHEN projects)
 - o Federated data analysis
- Metadata, schema mappings and search engines to increase *findability and interoperability* across disciplines (health, biomolecular, lifestyle, ...) for cross-domain linking
- Identification scheme for metabolites linking metabolites and parent chemicals

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Facilitated access and reuse of both (individual) HBM datasets and core HBM (occurrence) data by researchers and risks assessors

Regulatory agencies improve human risk assessment

Decision makers evaluate effectiveness of adopted regulatory measures (Chemicals policy)

Researchers make new generation risk assessment tools and models available

Key words: human biomonitoring, FAIR data, personal sensitive data, federated data analysis, metadata schemas, ontologies

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project supports the achievement and is closely aligned with operational objective 0010 “Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for risk assessment”. It aims for an effective exchange of reliable, relevant, curated, and FAIR data on chemicals (specifically human biomonitoring data) between different stakeholders and policy domains (in line with the European Strategy

for Data). Via mapping the existing data landscape and developing tailored solutions for data re(use) and the implementation of FAIR principles, the chemical RA community in PARC and beyond will increasingly reuse both scientific and regulatory data for application and innovation in risk assessment, thus empowering the European Green Deal Data Space.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is obviously strongly related with Task 4.1 and more specifically 4.1.4 and 4.1.5, with Task 6.2 for linking predicted exposure to observed exposure, with Task 8.3 for integrating HBM data in the modelling toolbox, and with Task 2.2 (data layer of PARCopedia).

WP3: a strategy will be developed on communication and awareness on FAIR data, both in general and in specific communities. This project will benefit from organisation of synergy networks and networking events. Collaboration on these aspects will be discussed with WP3.

Internally in WP7 the project will exchange with Task 7.1 on data policies, and on training and awareness on FAIR data, and with Task 7.3 for exploration of novel approaches towards enhanced privacy preservation for personal sensitive data (e.g., federated data analysis).

WP9 will be involved for the inventory of HBM projects and datasets, and for collaboration on training and awareness on FAIR data.

Links outside PARC

The project will start from the achievements of HBM4EU. It will link with other initiatives that are working on similar data, such as the European Human Exposome Network, EOSC-Life, EIRENE RI, and on generic metadata schemas and ontologies, such as HL7, Bioschemas, RDA, OHDSI. It will align with the EC's roadmap and activities towards a Common Open Platform on Chemicals data, and i.e., with IPCHEM's activities on HBM data.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D7.2. PARC FAIR data policy (PFDP) (M18)

D7.3. 1st report on Data infrastructure, tools and services for FAIRification and reuse of chemical RA data (M36)

D7.5. 1st review of the Data Management Plan (DMP) (M42)

MS11. Network of trained FAIR data stewards (M12)

MS12. Architecture of PARC FAIR data hub & its integration with the COPCSD (M24)

Indirectly, the project will contribute to deliverables in the related Tasks mentioned above.

ADs will be defined when drafting AWP2.

Expected Project Reports: None identified at present.

Expected Projects Landmarks: None identified at present.

Partners List:

VITO (BE); MU (CZ); UU (SW); UBA (DE); ISSEP (BE); JSI (Slovenia)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01-05-2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31-10-2025 (M42)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 140 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 22 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

None identified at present.

T7.3 Innovative analyses – 1 PROJECT

A7.3.1 Identify and evaluate innovative methods for combined analyses of FAIR (heterogeneous) data

No project submitted at present.

A7.3.2 Methods for uncertainty characterisation, propagation and quantification as a basis for harmonisation in RA

No project submitted at present.

A7.3.3 Novel computational methods for integrating and extracting knowledge from non-structured data – 1 PROJECT

P7.3.3a_Y1_ALT-IST_IISPV

Project Title	Alternative Predictive Testing Strategy for the Safety of Chemicals based on Integrative Systems Toxicology		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	ALT-IST		
Project Manager	Vikas Kumar Vikas.kumar@iispv.ca	IISPV	ES
Deputy Project manager	NA	NA	NA
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M6	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP7	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	7.3.3
Project Id	P7.3.3.a_Y1_ALT-IST_IISPV		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The ALT-IST project is a part of T7.3. It involves the development of an ontology-based text-mining and data integration scheme for the classification and storage of information about chemical hazards and risk assessment. Followed up by the development of tools using the database of risk assessment. Several regulatory agencies such as OECD, EFSA and ECHA have adopted evidence-based methodologies for risk assessment i.e. AOP (Adverse outcome pathway). The utmost requirement for developing this mechanistic pathway is data. The well-curated, connected, structured and unambiguous database will ease the accessibility of information and also compliments AOP development by filling experimental data gaps. Ontology-based data integration will further help toward the broader application of Advance data science including network biology and machine learning to predict the chemical adverse effect on the human system. The developed tools and methodologies will be validated by real case studies selected in collaboration with other WPs (WP4, WP5, WP6). Project will explore different text mining tools (e.g. INDRA, TRIPS or other tools) during scoping study to understand its usability and set the agenda for future research needs. Aside the application in developing (quantitative) adverse outcome pathways and supporting network biology approaches to identify and describe hazards in relation to disease development (i.e. AOP), other applications of AI, network approaches, text mining and ontology assisted hazard identification are foreseen as well. These, to accommodate the need for the faster detection of potential emerging risks from imported goods/chemicals into the EU, as well as the identification of data gaps within heterogeneous hazard data sources to help the further prioritization of testing.

Main expected outputs of the project

This project will establish NAM for risk assessment using the available data and the data developed in different work packages. This will involve ontology-based data curation and its automated maintenance using NLP (Natural language processing). In addition, developed ontology will assist the further development of QAOP in collaboration with different partners.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project is designed according to the perspective of a computational toxicologist, epidemiologists and risk assessor because it introduces a novel *in-silico* approach toward defining associations between human health outcomes and exposure to chemicals through the integrated use of advanced analytical and predictive tools for hazard and risk assessment and chemical screening for regulatory purposes. It will employ natural language processing, cheminformatics and bioinformatics techniques directly to the data mining of the integrated data set which will lead to the advancement of *in-silico* methodologies for OECD's integrated approaches to testing and assessment (IATA) and support the 3R strategy of chemical testing.

Key words:

Ontology, Text mining, Artificial intelligence, Natural Language Processing, System toxicology

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will assist in delivering FAIRified data and help in the development of AOPs or IATAs. Automated ontological text mining can be further integrated into future evidence-finding strategies with the ontology-based structured knowledge base. This is an important objective of PARC.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Task 5.3.2: AOP developed in 5.3.2 can be used as case study and data generated in this project can help in developing AOPs

Task 6.1: data generated in this project can help in the development of qAOPs and IATA.

Task 6.2: mixture effects can be quantitatively addressed through targeted data mining and network modelling

WP8: SysTox bioinformatics tools can be integrated in the toolbox

WP9: training of informatics tools for regulators

Links outside PARC

Relevant text mining AI data initiatives (ELIXIR, Bio.Tools). Furthermore, the project is closely linked to other EU project in similar domain like EU-ToxRisk, RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX and PrecisionTox, and to work ongoing at OECD in relation to AOP development (OECD AOP programme) and IATA case studies. As such, regular interactions with the OECD Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST) and the OECD Working Party for Hazard Assessment (WPHA) are foreseen.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

D7.4: 1st Evaluation of innovative analytical approaches and uncertainty approaches for introduction in chemical RA (M36)

Expected Project Reports:

Scoping study of AI, text mining and ontology-assisted hazard identification and risk assessment (M12)

Report on the available tool and framework, and different methodologies (like NLP and text mining) used for human health risk assessment, including ontology development.

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Landmark 1: Workshop on Ontology-assisted text mining for human health risk assessment strategy; M10

Landmark 2: Case Study 1 and 2 presentation of results with respective stakeholders; M24

Landmark 3: Integrated knowledge base /datasets for selected case studies (like AOPs development) established; M30

Partners List:

IISPV (ES); ANSES (FR); JSI (SI); UoB (UK); IRFM (IT)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025 (M36)

Cost:

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 21 PM (Project manager), under development for the other partners

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 24.4 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 30393 € (Project manager), under development for the other partners

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 12 830 € (Project manager), under development for the other partners

A7.3.4 Identify additional needs in PARC for innovative analyses and promising evolutions in the data science landscape, and translate them in use cases for evaluation

No project submitted at present.

WP8 Concepts and Toolboxes – 3 PROJECTS

T8.1 Safe and sustainable by design (SSbD) – 1 PROJECT

A8.1.1 Translate EC SSbD criteria & methodology towards operationalisation

No project submitted at present.

A8.1.2 Toolbox development – 1 PROJECT

P8.1.2.a Y1_SSbD_toolbox_AUTH

Project Title	Development of a toolbox for supporting SSbD		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SSbD_toolbox		
Project Manager	Denis Sarigiannis sarigiannis@auth.gr	AUTH	Greece
Deputy Project manager	Bernd Nowack Bernd.Nowack@empa.ch	EMPA	Switzerland
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP8	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	8.1.2
Project Id	8.1.2.a_Y1_SSbD_toolbox_AUTH		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The SSbD toolbox will support the European Green Deal towards its vision and objectives to put European economy and society on a sustainable pathway, to move towards climate neutrality, a circular economy and

to fulfil the zero pollution/creating a toxic-free environment ambition. It has been widely recognised that prevention is always preferable over mitigation, thus, the adoption (and more importantly the implementation) of the SSbD concept is *a sine qua non* towards ensuring that chemicals and materials are designed, produced, used and disposed (or reused and recycled) in a way that minimises the adverse impacts for human health and the environment. At the same time, the SSbD concept is among the cornerstones of the Circular Economy Action Plan towards an environmental and financially sustainable Europe, where products are fully in line with the SSbD concept, improving their durability, reusability, upgradability and reparability, and addressing the presence of hazardous chemicals. The SSbD toolbox, will also support in practice the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability; the latter aims at a transition to a toxic free environment through chemicals, materials and products that fulfil safety and sustainability requirements during their complete life cycle.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main output of the project will be the development of a toolbox for supporting the operationalization of the SSbD concept. This toolbox will be available to all interested stakeholders and users for evaluating whether a chemical, material or product fulfils the criteria for SSbD, as well as to evaluate alternative(s) of newly developed processes, chemicals, materials and products. This will facilitate the uptake of the SSbD concept and methodological framework by all related stakeholders. It is furthermore geared towards allowing the uptake of scientific progress along the chemical life cycle in order to ensure that all new chemicals and materials gradually shift towards the SSbD concept.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The delivered toolbox will be of use to both regulatory and industrial stakeholders, as follows:

- Regulatory agencies will be able to assess whether a chemical, material or product fulfils the criteria for SSbD
- Industry will have a toolbox available, that will support the development of chemicals, materials or products that fulfil the criteria for SSbD from the initial phase of design, as well as during its materialisation.
- In the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, SSbD is foreseen to effectively support the transition to a circular economy, nontoxic environments and zero pollution. The toolbox will help regulators and stakeholders alike to operationalize the EC's SSbD criteria and methodology.

Key words: SSbD, NAMs, LCIA, chemicals, materials, safety, sustainability, circular economy, toolbox

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The scope of the project is to provide the necessary tools to support the implementation of the SSbD concept on the basis of the criteria that will be developed by the EC. In this sense, the project will deliver innovative methods that will further support the elimination or the minimisation of risks for humans and the environment. The toolbox will allow the quantification of “sustainability” requirements, thus, accounting for life cycle assessment (LCA) coupled operationally with risk assessment methodologies. The SSbD approach will take into account the whole life cycle and will encompasses materials and products from their development, synthesis/ production up to application, disposal or recycling phases. This seems important also in the view of an implementation of a sustainable, circular economic system aimed to provide users and consumers high-quality, functional and safe products, which are efficient and affordable, last longer and are designed for reuse, repair, and high-quality recycling. To assess sustainability at market level the toolbox will also include Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA) and socio-economic assessment functionalities. When coupled with LCA, material/chemical flow analysis (M/CFA) and CBA as well as other methods commonly used for socio-economic assessment (contingent valuation, hedonic pricing, etc.) can inform on the overall environmental and economic sustainability of new chemicals and their applications in materials and products at an early stage. This toolbox will be used to describe methods with which critical properties (such as toxicity, exposure, [durability, reparability, upgradability, reusability, recyclability]) of chemicals, products, materials, packaging and application processes can be identified from early stage of innovation or development onwards. Guidelines for implementing the toolbox will be formulated. Parallel developments at the international level (in particular within OECD) will be followed and considered along

the project implementation process.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: Consultation with the Stakeholder Forum and the International Board on the SSbD toolbox expectations and user requirements

WP7: Data management plan: Need to ensure the available data pipelines from other WPs, necessary for SSbD assessment

WP9: Training, laboratory network: Training needs of stakeholders, user groups and within the PARC consortium, related to the SSbD toolbox use.

Other WPs:

- Activities undertaken in WP4 (Task 4.1, Task 4.2) related to exposure models and available HBM data
- Activities undertaken in WP5 (Tasks 5.2, 5.3) in hazard assessment, use of NAMs and predictive toxicology
- Activities undertaken in WP6 (Tasks 6.1, 6.2, 6.4), related to models in exposure, kinetics and risk assessment

Links outside PARC

The applicability of toolboxes and decision support systems for transregulatory application, addressing Safe by Design for Nanomaterials and products, as developed in a series of EU-projects like NANoREG, NanoReg2, CALIBRATE, GRACIOUS, the presently running collaborating risk governance projects Gov4Nano, NanoRigo, and RISKGONE and the CEFIC-LRI project DOREMI. Collaboration with the EU NanoSafetyCluster will be established to derive the state of the art in the toolbox development on nanosafety.

The SSbD toolbox will take stock of the integrated modelling platform that has been developed in HBM4EU (WP12), coordinated by the Task 8.1 Co-leader (AUTH, Prof. D. Sarigiannis)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- D8.1 M12 Report on the conceptual design of the SSbD toolbox
- D8.4 M24 1st Report on the testing and uptake of the SSbD toolbox through use cases

Expected Project Reports:

- Report 1: M18, report on feedback from potential customers and end users (EMPA)
- Report 2: M24 Report on the user requirements and conceptual design of the integrative tools (AUTH)
- Report 3: M36 Alpha version of the SSbD toolbox (AUTH)

Expected Projects Landmarks:

Not applicable

Partners List:

AUTH (EL), EMPA (CH), RIVM (NL), INERIS (FR), BNN (AT), MU (CZ), DTU (DK), EEA (EU), SYKE (FI), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), IUSS (IT), UNINA (IT), NILU (NO), NMBU (NO), UG-PL (PL), FMUL (PT), NIC (SI), INSST (ES), IVL (SE), BUL (UK), Cefas-Defra (UK)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 171.0 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 57.0 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 66 000 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 22 000 €

A8.1.3 SSbD toolbox operationalisation: Use cases & indicators

No project submitted at present.

A8.1.4 Knowledge sharing & Education as key factors for efficient SSbD operationalisation

No project submitted at present.

T8.2 Scientific and technical basis for an Early warning system (EWS) on chemical risks – 1 PROJECT

A8.2.1 Conceptualisation of early warning monitoring tools for identification of prioritised substances – 1 PROJECT

P8.2.1.a_Y1_EWS_SLU

Project Title	Conceptualization of early warning monitoring tools		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	EWS_tools		
Project Manager	Lutz Ahrens Lutz.ahrens@slu.se	SLU	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	M18
PARC Workpackage number	WP8.2	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	8.2.1
Project Id	P8.2.1.a_Y1_EWS_SLU		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

Establishment of an early warning system (EWS) for identification of new and existing potentially hazardous substances is a key component in PARC. It has been highlighted by the Chemical Strategy for sustainability and is on the agenda of several EU DGs and agencies. An EWS includes early warning monitoring toolboxes to identify chemical hazards in humans, food (including drinking water), and environmental matrices that may be associated with an unacceptable health risk. For prioritization of new chemicals, several tools have been developed that can be used in combination or independently: Trend analysis in combination with AI and big data technology tools in humans and wildlife, exposure assessment by linking human exposure to food, drinking water, indoor environment and their sources, and combinations of chemical and toxicity or effect tools in humans and in environmental samples to prioritize new toxic drivers. However, the exact set of tools for an efficient EWS still needs to be determined. The development of QA/QC validation of early warning monitoring tools is also of crucial importance to achieve an effective EWS. An efficient EWS is the key to identify risk signals, facilitate awareness of risks and disseminate/send warnings. The output should inform risk assessors and managers in industry and authorities at an early stage of future challenges or emerging risks and identify needs for measures.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Review of early warning monitoring tools and exploration of current knowledge and tools
- Innovative EWS tools will be conceptualized and designed for the identification of substances of concern for further activities including hazard assessment, exposure assessment, risk assessment
- Have a proof-of-concept EWS which can be used as a prototype
- Generated EWS tools will be selected for application in human and environmental matrices

- Identification of data gaps of early warning systems and monitoring tools

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project will generate proofs-of-concepts and tools of relevance to risk assessors and policy makers at national and EU level. Cutting edge tools will be conceptualized and illustrated for establishment of an EWS. End-users include ECHA, EFSA, EEA, national environmental and chemical agencies, national food safety authorities, NORMAN, researchers, industry, NGOs, national consumer protection organizations and the general public.

Key words:

Early warning system (EWS); early warning monitoring tools; Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA), suspect and non-targeted screening (NTS); high resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS); AI; computational methods; QSAR

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will establish an early warning system proof-of-concept for material, environment, food, and human. This will ensure that the generated data can be used to support the development of early warning systems to communicate risks, facilitate awareness of risks and disseminate warnings to inform risk assessors and risk managers at an early stage of future challenges or emerging risks, which will be linked to other activities and future projects in PARC.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP4:

- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA
- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data
- 4.3/4.3.1/4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_EWS_SLU: EWS concept
- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04_Data Processing Workflow_EHESP: Support annotation of generated data
- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02_Occupational exposure_INRS: Mutualized resources / harmonization
- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.2.c_Y3_F02_Other complementary studies_JSI: Mutualized resources / harmonization
- 4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE: Support/harmonization HRMS/EDA methods

WP5: Effect-directed tools based on bioassays using new approach methodologies (NAMs).

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...). FAIR Data libraries.

WP8: Conceptualization of an Early Warning System (EWS) from sampling/NTS/EDA methods in humans, environment, food and products combining exposure and hazard data. Computational methods for text mining, data curation and hazard scoring.

WP9: Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for SS/NTS/EDA approaches.

Links outside PARC

- [HBM4EU](#) (data, models)
- [HEALS](#), [CROME-Life](#)
- UBA [NTS Portal with BfG](#) (Water, suspended matter)
- [NORMAN Network](#) activities
- DG ENV Early Warning System project

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

None identified at present.

Expected Project Reports:

- Report 1: Conceptualization of early warning monitoring tools M18.
- Report 2: Conceptualization of effect directed analysis (EDA) for EWS (M18)
- Report 3: Conceptualization of a computational system using AI and systems modeling for environmental and human samples and products for the EWS (M18)

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- Review of early warning monitoring tools and exploration of current knowledge and tools
- Innovative EWS tools will be conceptualized and designed for the identification of substances of concern for further activities including hazard assessment, exposure assessment, risk assessment
- Have a proof-of-concept EWS which can be used as a prototype
- Generated EWS tools will be selected for application in human and environmental matrices
- Identification of data gaps of early warning systems and monitoring tools
- Concepts of novel effect-based methods have been established for humans, food and environmental matrices (M18)
- First phase computational framework for text mining, data curation and hazard scoring has been designed (M18)
- A conceptual framework for early warning monitoring tools has been established (M18)

Partners List:

SLU (SE), AUTH (EL), UMU (SE), NKUA (EL), INSERM (FR), ORU-MTM (SE), VU (NL), ISS (IT), NILU (NO), UniLu (LU), EFET (EL), WR-WFSR (NL), UG (PL), AU (DK), EA (UK), UBA (DE), INRAE (FR), VITO (BE), IRFMN (IT), NMBU (NO), IRAS (NL), IVL (SE), DGS (PT), KI (SI), IISPV (ES)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 31/10/2023

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 170.5 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 114 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 156 000 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 75 000 €

A8.2.2 Identification framework

No project submitted at present.

A8.2.3 Applicability and performance testing of EW toolbox

No project submitted at present.

A8.2.4 Computational framework to support the EWS

No project submitted at present.

T8.3 Integrative models – 1 PROJECT

A8.3.1 Modelling network, model governance and user requirements

No project submitted at present.

A8.3.2 Designing and implementing the PARC model network – 1 PROJECT

P8.3.2.a Y1_DIMN_AUTH

Project Title	Preparing design and implementation of the PARC model network with a conceptual model based on existing and new collaborations
Project Acronym (15)	DIMN

letters max)			
Project Manager	Denis Sarigiannis sarigiannis@auth.gr	AUTH	Greece
Deputy Project manager	Hilko van der Voet hilko.vandervoet@wur.nl	WR-BIOM	The Netherlands
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP8	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	8.3.2
Project Id	P8.3.2.a_Y1_DIMN_AUTH		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The scope of the project is to facilitate the successful design of the model network, rendering it able to address regulatory needs through transparent use of rigorous computational tools and FAIR data. This will actually increase the capacity of the interoperable tool network to be developed in Task 8.3 to continuously assimilate the different type of data that will be generated from WPs 4-8. The PARC model network will offer a number of generally applicable models ranging from multimedia environmental models to indoor air quality models and from exposure models capturing the different exposure routes (inhalation, oral and dermal) as well as exposures from mixtures to a suite of Physiology Based Toxicokinetic (PBTK) models allowing the estimation of internal doses. Additional models will include QSARs for predicting toxicity, but also physicochemical properties of compounds, as well as parameters necessary for toxicokinetic models parameterisation. Finally, the model network will provide tools for advanced bioinformatics analysis and identification of molecular and metabolic pathways, as well as articulation and quantification of AOPs.

As a starting point, this project will set up a comprehensive workflow for multiple compounds making use of existing tools like modules of INTEGRA, MCRA, USEtox, VEGAHUB, ConsExpo, and PACEM in an interoperable network, while identifying new functionalities that have to be implemented and integrated in the model network. Overall, this project will contribute to the development, testing and integration of interoperable tools for innovative models. These models will be developed and validated for further activities, by implementing AOP-based modeling and benchmark dose (BMD) models applied to NAM data in hazard assessment, integrated external and internal exposure assessment towards refined risk assessment. This will be carried out by integrating models related to near and far field exposure modelling, reconstruction of HBM data, internal exposure assessment accounting for co-exposure interaction and QIVIVE for introducing NAMs in the risk assessment process. Assessment of variability and uncertainty will be key elements. Although the project aims at acting as a case study for the model network design optimization, it will also deliver risk assessment with the conventional ways as well (using the respecting animal delivered TDIs) so as to identify the differences and the levels of refinement of the NAMs based methods, as well as their limitations and the needs for further elaboration. The main output of the project will be the functional design of the PARC model network, based on available and new modules such as are partly already available in tools like MCRA, INTEGRA, USEtox, VEGAHUB, ConsExpo, PACEM or other. Within the project, platforms like MCRA and INTEGRA will be adapted to the needs of the functional design and the requirements of the case studies. As a secondary outcome, the foreseen case studies will be implemented in a web-based platform or in a network of linked web services. The PARC model network will be a multi-modular software especially designed to meet the end-user real needs and requirements for executing risk assessment accounting for both aggregate and cumulative exposure assessment, enabling the integration and assimilation of models and data needed to execute a source to effect assessment.

Important part of the model network design, will be appropriate user interfaces. Each user interface will be optimised for a specific user group, for example as a standard regulatory action (SRA) to be developed per

case study together with other tasks/projects in PARC. Links will be created with the SSbD toolbox under development in T8.1 and the envisaged PARCopedia in WP 3. The user interface might in some cases be a client-side application, executed inside the web browser's window that will guide the user through the model network.

Another consideration is the e-infrastructure needed to train, integrate, and serve models and tools both within PARC and to the wider community. Within WP8 according to the current thinking we will aim at vendor-agnostic and modern e-infrastructures (e.g. cloud computing and Kubernetes), and implement solutions as portable components that can be deployed in multiple settings (e.g. software containers) and with APIs and user interfaces that are primarily web-based. For authentication and authorization, Life Science Login will be used, and for all PARC systems we will aim for single-sign-on. The STACKn framework will be evaluated as a platform for collaborative AI/ML modelling and serving, while AUTH will contribute with several USARs and exposure models that rely in AI.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will address the WP 8 objective to develop an overarching integrative model network that encompasses all modelling tools developed and used in the Partnership in a harmonised approach. Whereas this is a long-term objective, the project will foster the conceptual design of the PARC model network to address regulatory and scientific requirements, guided by the needs of specific areas which are urgent in view of the need to reduce animal testing and refine chemical risk assessment. This will facilitate the design of the IT architecture of the integrative model network according to the open architecture paradigm to allow future models to be readily used within the same framework on the basis of a standardized input / output protocol and ensure model transparency and FAIR data management. In this way, the toolset will easily adapt to scientific / technical progress in the future, assimilating the tools expected to be developed in WPs 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8 of PARC and in other relevant HE and H2020 projects.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Currently, innovation of risk assessment by using NAMs and IVIVE is mainly considered a research activity which is not yet fit for regulatory use. In fact, most stakeholders have difficulty to overview all possibilities and uncertainties, and come to decisions about further implementation. The proposed project will identify the necessary tools that have to be implemented in the model network, to support to make such considerations.

Case studies will identify the models and data that have to be implemented in the model network that will allow different areas of exposure science and toxicology (and in particularly NAMs) to be connected mechanistically to address questions of regulatory context such as identifying risk drivers in real-life mixtures. The model network will allow the use of heterogeneous data, supporting the integration of multiple lines of evidence including environmental and HBM data, together with data from tox and epi studies. Of particular importance will be the incorporation of in vitro outcomes in the regulatory process ensured by QIVIVE and reverse QIVIVE extrapolation, setting also the scene for the development of qAOPs.

Key words: Integrative modelling, model network, meta-model, computational models, computational platform

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will focus on human health risk assessment, and in particular on the use of dietary and non-dietary exposure models, new approach methodologies (NAMs) for toxicological testing, in-vitro in-vivo extrapolation (IVIVE) and validation with human biomonitoring (HBM) data. We will use the inventory of requirements to design conceptually elements in the PARC model network that are needed to address the modelling needs. The aim is to create a first draft of an overarching conceptual model to map models and tools to user requirements and RA questions, guided by initially one case study and later by additional case studies. We will implement a first prototype of the conceptual PARC model as an open-source dynamical system under version control, to allow continuous development and adaptation to regulatory needs to create web service connections between models and platforms.

To better respond to contemporary risk assessment needs and foster the transition towards next generation risk assessment, this project will try to fill the gaps of comprehensive methodological workflows for evaluating multiple lines of evidence associated with both exposure related (dietary, environmental, personal activity and exposure, HBM) and hazard (NAMs, in vitro testing) related data. The integrative modelling tool network that task 8.3 will develop will allow the quantitative association among the heterogeneous data that are available and will be generated in the field of risk assessment. Aiming at a successful design of the model network, we will track the needs of data processing and modelled data generation, following the exemplified case study on risk assessment of bisphenols (BPA, BPS, BPF). For this group of compounds, the project needs several types of data, and if these data are not available through the work implemented in other PARC WPs, it will rely on available data from previous EU projects (HBM4EU, HEALS, CROME) to retrieve and/or generate these data. In this project an ontology will be defined using the example data as inspiration. An overview of models that are available or needed will be defined, and available tools will be matched to this overview. Daily intake and exposure estimates will be accounted for several population groups, including the most susceptible ones (fetus, neonates, children), as well as occupationally exposed and high-end consumer population groups. Exposure will be estimated by combining bottom up (by aggregating multisource, multipathway, multiroute exposure), and top down (reconstruction of available HBM data), accounting for the best data available. The aim is to identify the needs for aggregate (multi-source, multi-pathway and multi-route exposure) modelling, including multimedia environmental emission and fate modelling, food contact materials migration, as well as percutaneous and inhalation exposure for consumer and occupational settings. Toxicokinetics of bisphenols and especially during the prenatal and perinatal period play a particular role. A framework for assimilating HBM data, and translating them into external, intake-level and internal exposure estimates (exposure reconstruction) will be defined. Quantitative AOPs (qAOPs) will be constructed to describe the toxicodynamics after triggering of MIEs and downstream key events. Relevant key events will be assessed combining relevant cell-based system and holistic approaches, including toxicogenomics and co-expression analysis. NAM toxicity assessment metrics and approaches will be used for delivering risk characterisation estimates. Internal dosimetry models will hold a key role, serving the need for translating external exposure estimates into internal dosimetry metrics, for quantitative in-vitro in-vivo extrapolation (QIVIVE), while it is also a key component of the models for exposure reconstruction starting from HBM data. Moreover, the impact of co-exposure to the three bisphenols in the biologically effective dose and the way this impacts the QIVIVE extrapolation will also be examined. Aiming at addressing these questions, precise needs for the various models and modules, will be mapped and translated to model network needs.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: Consultation from the Stakeholder Forum and the International Board on the model network expectations and user requirements

WP7: Data management plan: Ensure data flows from the rest of the technical work packages

WP9: Training, laboratory network: Training needs of stakeholders, user groups and within the PARC consortium, related to the model network use.

Other WPs:

This project will collaborate with other PARC projects, and have joint deliverables or contribute to deliverables in those projects.

Links outside PARC

- Bisphenols have been priority compounds in the HBM4EU partnership and new harmonised data for all three compounds has been generated across EU. Additional data will come from other EU projects (HEALS, CROME, OBERON, the EURION cluster on EDs) to which we already have access. This data will be of particular importance for the successful implementation of the case study foreseen in this project.
- Integration of models is a subject for the EuroMix follow-up consortium, including application for bisphenols.
- EFSA has selected the MCRA platform for mixture risk assessment and is cooperating with RIVM and WR-Biometris in a Framework Partnership Agreement 2022-2025 to develop an Open MCRA model collection and opportunities for co-creation.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- Deliverable year 1: D8.3 - Report on the conceptual design of the integrative tools (AUTH)
- Deliverable year 3: D8.6 - Report on the development and validation of the integrative model network (WR-BIOM)

Expected Project Reports:

Implementation of ontologies and data formats (M36, WR-BIOM)

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- Development of the PARC models/tools inventory (M12)
- Report on PARC model network user requirements
- Draft definition of the use cases

Partners List:

AUTH (EL), WR-BIOM (NL), ANSES (FR), INERIS (FR), VITO (BE), ISSeP (BE), MU (CZ), DTU (DK), SYKE (FI), TTL (FI), IRFMN (IT), IUSS (IT), UL-LACDR (NL), WU-TOX (NL), NIVA (NO), IISPV (ES), INSST (ES), NIC (SI), UU (SE), UOC (EL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 30/04/2025

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 345.5 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 111.1 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 93 000 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 38 000 €

A8.3.3 Application of the integrative model network in use cases

No project submitted at present.

WP9 Building infrastructural and human capacities – 3 PROJECTS

T9.1 Laboratory networking – 1 PROJECT

A9.1.1 Identify existing laboratory networks, draw up and maintain up-to-date and active a database of the laboratory networks – 1 PROJECT

P9.1.1.a_Y1_ENV_CATALOGUES_MU_ISCIII

Project Title	Building capacities (laboratory networks and information catalogues) in environmental monitoring		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	ENV CATALOGUES		
Project Manager	Jana Klánová jana.klanova@recetox.muni.cz	RECETOX, Masaryk University (MU)	CZ
Deputy Project	Ana Isabel Cañas Portilla acanas@isciii.es	Instituto de Salud Carlos III (ISCIII)	ES

manager			
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	81
PARC Workpackage number	WP9	PARC Task/Activity/Sub- activity:	9.2/9.1
Project Id	P9.1.1.a_Y1_ENV CATALOGUES_MU_ISCIII		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

In the present project, a cross-cutting activity consisting in the mapping and building of the infrastructural elements and capacities related to environmental exposure and monitoring (including air, water, sediment, soil, biota, food and feed, indoor environments, and articles) is described.

The project arises from the need to bring together the individual infrastructural elements, i.e., laboratories, networks, information sources, samples, projects, studies related to environmental exposure monitoring, consolidate the existing information and networks into catalogs, analyze them, identify the gaps and stabilize, expand and consolidate the networks by filling the identified gaps. This is necessary for the development of national and Europe-wide infrastructures in the various environmental and risk assessment domains and for the achievement of the PARC project goals that relate to multiple source exposure (WP4), chemical hazard characterization (WP5), data FAIRification/data harmonization (WP7), development of new models (WP8) and of new risk assessment strategies (WP6).

The project will continue with and eventually further expand the work done in the different environmental domains previously, will consider both the scientific and regulatory arena and encompass both the national and European level. The developed catalogues on laboratories, environmental exposure monitoring networks and other information (sample collections, biobanks, repositories, projects etc.) will be brought together under one umbrella using a suitable system architecture allowing for harmonized solutions that will be available to PARC members, policy makers, risk assessors, and scientific communities and will support achievement of the PARC project goals.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will develop and consolidate the different elements of infrastructure into one overall system (laboratories, information catalogues, monitoring programs, etc.) and under one umbrella and analyze the existing gaps in the current monitoring activities that can be issues of regulatory concern (implementation of new laboratory networks, support the development of the less-mature laboratory networks, monitoring programs, analytical methods, training needs, QA/QC schemes, if necessary). Finally, the project will set up actions to close these gaps.

Key words: catalogue, inventory, environmental monitoring network, laboratory network, capacities, infrastructure, sustainability, resources

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project will contribute to the operation objective of PARC 0011 Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centers.

The activities of this project support the activities specified under the R&I WP4 (Task 4.2) on Environmental monitoring and exposure, are closely aligned and feed into the activities of WP7 on data management and (re)use in line with the FAIR principles, as well as significantly contribute to the sustainability and impact of the PARC project (WP2 and WP3). The infrastructural element on laboratories is closely related to joint activities (harmonization) and QA/QC schemes that will be targeted in Task 9.3 while the strengthening of human capacities will be achieved in cooperation with Task 9.4 among others.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: In order to collect relevant information for building the laboratory and exposure monitoring catalogues in the environmental domains, the existing capacities at both the national and the European level would need to be surveyed. Therefore, WP9 would require

assistance from WP3 and most likely also WP2 with the administration of the surveys in order to cover both the national and European level and all the partners in PARC and beyond, if relevant. The administration of the surveys would need to follow an established protocol and functional mechanisms allowing for transparent, documented, and effective distribution of the surveys and their collection, for example via the network of national hub contacts points and the PARC-European hub. We expect (and are ready to further discuss our needs in this regard) that WP3 in collaboration with WP2 will provide a proposal with respect to survey formatting, distribution, and collection as well as will provide sufficient awareness of this action among the partners and relevant stakeholders. The catalogues would also need to be promoted via PARCopedia (task 2.2).

WP7: *Data management plan:* Various metadata will be collected. WP9 foresees a collaboration with task 7.2 on the terminology, ontology and FAIRification of the metadata to be collected within the surveys to allow that they compile with the FAIR principles. Collected data (in the form of catalogues) will be made publicly available.

WP9: *Training, laboratory network:* The infrastructural element on laboratories is closely related to joint activities (harmonization) and QA/QC schemes that will be targeted in Task 9.3 while the strengthening of human capacities will be achieved in cooperation with Task 9.4 among others. There are currently no specific needs foreseen with respect to training.

Other WPs: 4 (task 4.2)

The activities of this project support the activities specified under the R&I WP4 (Task 4.2) on Environmental monitoring and exposure.

Links outside PARC

The project is expected to significantly contribute to the sustainability of the PARC project, and it is foreseen that its outputs will be incorporated into existing/newly developing infrastructure to assure sustainability beyond PARC. In this respect, the EIRENE (Environmental Exposure Assessment Research) infrastructure, which has been recently placed on the ESFRI roadmap and, thus, gained recognition at the European level, is considered highly relevant. The EIRENE infrastructure project synergizes with the activities of WP9 and will be coordinated by RECETOX (MU) who also is a WP9 co-leader. Via this link, the synergy between these two projects will be assured.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

None identified at present.

Expected Project Reports:

- Report on partners' needs (M12) – MU, ISCIII
- Report on WP7 and WP9 meetings dedicated to the catalogue architecture/structure (M6) - MU, ISCIII
- The overall architecture and best-fit solution(s) for building the information catalogues (M12) MU, ISCIII
- Report on the catalogue construction on laboratory networks (M12(+)) ISCIII
- Report on the catalogue construction on environmental studies, projects, networks and other relevant information (M12(+)) MU
- Establishment of the Standard Operating Procedure to include laboratories in the networks defined in PARC. (M12+)
- List of harmonized criteria for designation of Reference Laboratories within PARC. (M12+)
- Report on identified gaps and a list of possible actions aiming at closing these gaps (M12+)

Expected Projects Landmarks:

LM1. Mapping the needs of other PARC partners in collaboration with WP2 and 3, and through the cooperative mechanisms and the structure of horizontal contacts points established in WP9 and bridging towards the other WPs (a recurrent activity that need to be periodically reported).

LM2. Organization of the workshop in relation to developing and building the best-fit system for information catalogues

LM3. Compilation of the catalogue on environmental laboratory networks and their information.

LM4. Compilation of the information catalogues on environmental monitoring networks_
 LM5. Initial analysis of the laboratory networks and other networks on environmental monitoring and compilation of suggestions for further actions towards closing the existing gaps

Partners List:

ANSES (FR), INERIS (FR), Oniris (FR), BRGM (FR), LNE (FR), Sciensano (BE), ISSeP (BE), MU (CZ), VSCHT (CZ), AU (DK), RSU (LV), NPHSL (LT), LNS (LU), STAMI (NO), NMBU (NO), INSA (PT), SZU-SK (SK), UK (SK), CSIC (ES), ISCIII (ES), FISABIO (ES), BPI (GR), GCLS (GR), INSERM (FR), SpF (FR), NPHC (HU), JSI (SI), AUTH (GR)

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 498 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 71 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 24 900 €

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 155 000 €

A9.1.2 Promote the development of new laboratory networks and support their consolidation

No project submitted at present.

A9.1.3 Facilitate the coordination and linkage of existing and new laboratory networks

No project submitted at present.

A9.1.4 Develop an interactive tool (dashboard) to show the capacities of the laboratory networks

No project submitted at present.

T9.2 Building exposure monitoring capacities– 1 PROJECT

A9.2.1 Mapping of exposure monitoring capacities – 1 PROJECT

P9.2.1.a_Y1_HBM CATALOGUES_ISCIII_MU

Project Title	Building capacities (laboratory networks and information catalogues) in human biomonitoring and population cohorts		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	HBM CATALOGUES		
Project Manager	Ana Isabel Cañas Portilla acanas@isciii.es	Instituto de Salud Carlos III (ISCIII)	ES
Deputy Project manager	Jana Klánová jana.klanova@recetox.muni.cz	RECETOX, Masaryk University (MU)	CZ
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	81
PARC Workpackage	WP9	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-	9.1/9.2

number		activity:	
Project Id	P9.2.1.a_Y1_HBM_CATALOGUES_ISCIII_MU		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

The project describes a cross-cutting activity that is related to the infrastructural elements of human biomonitoring (HBM) and population cohort studies. The project defines the necessary steps for i) building the national and European capacities in human biomonitoring and population cohort studies, which will be achieved via mapping, cataloguing, and expanding and consolidating the existing networks of HBM laboratories and of the relevant information sources into catalogues, and for ii) strengthening the HBM networks by promoting their collaboration and networking, analyzing and identifying gaps and supporting actions towards closing these gaps.

The project arises from the need to continue with and eventually further expand the work done in HBM4EU with regard to the mapping and inventorying of capacities related to HBM and longitudinal population cohort studies. The PARC project builds to a significant extent on the legacy of HBM4EU, intends to capitalize on the efforts and experience gained there, and aims to further develop and streamline the work done previously in line with the goals of PARC.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will develop and consolidate the different elements of infrastructure into one overall system (laboratories, information catalogues, monitoring programs, and other related information like samples collections, biobanks etc.) and under one umbrella promoting their collaboration, and analyze the existing gaps in the current monitoring activities that can be issues of regulatory concern (implementation of new laboratory networks, monitoring programs, analytical methods, training needs, QA/QC schemes, if necessary). Finally, the project will set up actions to close these gaps.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The developed catalogues on laboratories and HBM exposure monitoring networks will be brought together using a suitable system architecture allowing for harmonized solutions and will be made available to PARC members, policy makers, risk assessors, and scientific communities and will support the achievement of the PARC project goals. The project will inventory existing national and European infrastructural capacities in human biomonitoring, will increase their visibility to the stakeholders and their collaboration/networking, and, thus, it will contribute to the development of new and better use of existing HBM capacities and resources across Europe.

The present project accounts for the need to build a harmonized HBM platform and the European-wide infrastructure to serve as pillars for the next generation risk assessment and in support for data (re)use, harmonized solutions, and integrated risk assessments in HBM. The project will develop and apply an overall system architecture to gather the different elements of infrastructure (laboratories, information catalogues and human capacities), analyse the existing gaps, and set up actions to close these gaps.

Key words: catalogue, inventory, human monitoring network, HBM laboratory network, collaboration, capacities, infrastructure, sustainability, resources

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

In order to collect relevant information to build the laboratory and exposure monitoring catalogues in HBM, the existing capacities at both the national and the European level would need to be surveyed. Therefore, WP9 would require assistance from **WP3** (*Synergies, Communication and awareness*) and most likely also **WP2** (*A common science-policy-agenda*) with the administration of the surveys in order to cover both the national and European level and all the partners in PARC and beyond, if relevant. The administration of the surveys would need to follow an established protocol and functional mechanisms allowing for transparent, documented, and effective distribution of the surveys and their collection, for example via the network of national hub contacts points and the PARC-European hub. We expect (and are ready to further discuss our needs in this regard) that WP3 in collaboration with WP2 will provide a proposal with respect

to survey formatting, distribution, and collection as well as will provide sufficient awareness of this action among the partners and relevant stakeholders. The catalogues would also need to be promoted *via* PARCopedia (task 2.2).

In relation to data management (**WP7**), various metadata will be collected. WP9 foresees a collaboration with task 7.2 on the terminology, ontology and FAIRification of the metadata to be collected within the surveys to allow that they compile with the FAIR principles. Collected data (in the form of catalogues) will be made publicly available.

Within **WP9**, the infrastructural element on laboratories is closely related to joint activities (harmonization) and QA/QC schemes that will be targeted in Task 9.3 while the strengthening of human capacities in HBM and population cohorts will be achieved in cooperation with Task 9.4 among others. In this planning phase, there are currently no specific needs foreseen with respect to training.

The project is horizontally linked with other WPs of the PARC project. It is complementary to the needs and activities specified under the R&I **WP4** (Task 4.1) on Human biomonitoring.

Links outside PARC

The project is expected to significantly contribute to the sustainability of the PARC project, and it is foreseen that its outputs will be incorporated into existing/newly developing infrastructure to assure sustainability beyond PARC. In this respect, the EIRENE (Environmental Exposure Assessment Research) infrastructure, which has been recently placed on the ESFRI roadmap and, thus, gained recognition at the European level, is considered highly relevant. The EIRENE infrastructure project synergizes with the activities of WP9 and will be coordinated by RECETOX (MU) who also is a WP9 co-leader. Via this link, the synergy between these two projects will be assured.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

None identified at present.

Expected Project Reports:

- *Report on partners' needs (M12) – MU, ISCIII*
- *Report on WP7 and WP9 meetings dedicated to the catalogue architecture/structure (M6) - MU, ISCIII*
- *The overall architecture and best-fit solution(s) for building the information catalogues (M12) MU, ISCIII*
- *Report on the catalogue construction on HBM laboratory networks (M12(+)) ISCIII*
- *Report on the catalogue construction on HBM studies and cohorts, projects, networks and other relevant information (M12(+)) MU*
- *Standard Operating Procedure for inclusion/qualification of laboratories on the HBM network (M12+)*

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- LM1. Mapping the needs of other PARC partners in collaboration with WP2 and 3, and through the cooperative mechanisms and the structure of horizontal contacts points established in WP9 and bridging towards the other WPs (a recurrent activity that need to be periodically reported)_
- LM2. Organization of the workshop in relation to developing and building the best-fit system for information catalogues
- LM3. Compilation of the catalogue on HBM laboratories_
- LM4. Compilation of the information catalogues on HBM networks and population cohort networks_
- LM5. Initial analysis of the laboratory and monitoring networks on HBM and population cohorts and suggestion for further actions towards closing the existing gaps

Partners List:

ANSES (FR), LNE (FR), Sciensano (BE), ISSeP (BE), MU (CZ), VSCHT (CZ), AU (DK), IPA (DE), NPHSL (LT), LNS (LU), NIPH (NO), STAMI (NO), NMBU (NO), FMUL (PT), INSA (PT), SZU-SK (SK), UK (SK), CSIC (ES), ISCIII (ES), FISABIO (ES), FNS (ES), BPI (GR), GCLS (GR), INSERM (FR), SpF (FR), IMROH (HR), NPHC (HU), ENSP (PT), JSI (SI), AUTH (GR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022
 Expected ending date: 31/01/2029

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 399 PM
 Expected PM for the first year of the project: 80,80 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: 26 600 €
 Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 186 000 €

A9.2.2 Strengthening of exposure monitoring capacities

No project submitted at present.

T9.3 Joint activities – harmonisation – 1 PROJECT

A9.3.1 Overarching guidance on (new) sampling methods

P9.3.1.a_Y1_QAQC_WR

Project Title	Towards harmonised QA/QC in laboratory testing		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	QAQC		
Project Manager	Hans Mol hans.mol@wur.nl	WR	NL
Deputy Project manager	Jochem Louisse jochem.louisse@wur.nl	WR	NL
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M1	Expected duration	M81
PARC Workpackage number	WP9	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	9.3
Project Id	P9.3.1.a_Y1_QAQC_WR		

Status: Planning

Summary of the project

This project comprises the cross-cutting activity dealing with harmonisation of quality assurance (QA) and quality control (QC) of laboratory analysis (chemical methods, bioassay-based methods, toxicity testing, and toxicokinetic studies), and related QA/QC on sampling, within PARC. The project arises from the need to ensure use and generation of data that are consistent, of high quality, and comparable across the different chemical, sample type and technique domains. While general principles are established by metrology and standardisation organisations (ISO, CEN, OECD), differences in interpretation and degree of implementation in research and monitoring activities are observed in the various technical and application domains as used in WP4 and WP5. The project will establish a core-QA/QC group, inventory and prioritise QA/QC topics to work on, and establish sub-groups on each of the sub-topics. Each sub group will first inventory existing interpretations and guidances, then identify inconsistencies and gaps. Next, more detailed guidances will be drafted with the aim to harmonise procedures and criteria where meaningful and as much as possible within PARC, without conflicting with existing principles outside PARC.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Establishment of a QA/QC core group with representatives from WP4 and WP5
- Prioritised list of QA/QC topics to work on
- Establishment of sub-groups for prioritised QA/QC topics
- For each sub-topic: a) overview of existing situation: inventory of QA/QC definitions, criteria, guidances, inconsistencies, gaps, needs for harmonisation; b) guidance documents and/or reports to harmonise interpretation, criteria, establishment of performance parameters.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project is expected to merge existing fragmented QA/QC into more harmonised procedures and performance criteria by (re)assessing existing protocols/criteria, filling identified gaps, taking practicality for the end-users (laboratories) into account. For the stakeholders (users of data generated by the laboratories) this will result in more consistent and reliable data across the different matrix/chemical/technique domains where possible and applicable.

Key words: Quality Control, Quality Assurance, Harmonisation, Laboratory testing, Chemical Analysis, Toxicity testing, Sampling

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The project addresses the need to ensure use and generation of data in chemical risk assessment that are consistent and of high quality, following the same principles across the different chemical, sample type and technique domains.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is very closely linked to WP4, specifically to the QA/QC activities therein (T4.1.2, T4.2.3/4 and T4.3.5), and WP5 and WP6. Many experts/key contributors from these tasks are also involved in T9.3. Division of activities between T9.3 and QA/QC from WP4/5/6 is that T9.3 deals with overarching frameworks, guidance documents, and performance criteria aiming at harmonisation and alignment. Experimental work on QA/QC (e.g., organisation of proficiency tests, method comparison studies, experimental verification and comparisons of QC protocols and practical feasibility of criteria and requirements) is done in the research WPs 4/5/6.

The project is also linked to WP7 in relation to data acceptability and the contribution of uncertainty of laboratory analysis results to the overall uncertainty in risk analysis.

The project also links to T9.1 on laboratory networks, and to T9.4 on training requirements. Training needs on laboratory QA/QC to the laboratories involved in PARC will be addressed by T9.4.

Links outside PARC

Laboratory related QA/QC is addressed in various levels of detail in the following organisations and infrastructures, which will be taken into account and involved where relevant:

- EURL infrastructure food; EURL-ECVAM
- EFSA
- ECHA
- ISO/CEN
- EURAMET
- OECD
- HBM4EU (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/>)
- NORMAN (<https://www.norman-network.com/?q=Home>)
- MetroFood (<https://www.metrofood.eu/>)
- JRC (<https://crm.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>)
- EU-TOXRISK/RISKHUNT3R (<https://www.eu-toxrisk.eu/>)
- Food screening regulations, e.g. dioxins Calux Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/644; ...

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D9.4 1st Generic guidance documents for QA/QC on sampling; chemical analysis; toxicity, EDA, &

toxicokinetics studies (M24)

Expected Project Reports:

- Report on the establishment of the QA/QC core- and sub-groups, the prioritised QA/QC topics, and the sub-activities and/or sub-projects to further work on after Y1 (M12, WR).
- Reports on prioritised QA/QC topics related to sampling, chemical analysis, toxicity testing (\geq M24, additions/updates in subsequent years; partners in charge to be identified)

Expected Projects Landmarks:

- Establishment of a QA/QC core group with representatives from WP4 and WP5
- Prioritised list of QA/QC topics
- Establishment of sub-groups for prioritised QA/QC topics

Partners List:

WR (NL), UNIVIE (AT), SCIENSANO (BE), MU (CZ), VSCHT (CZ), IPA (DE), UBA (DE) UCPH (DK), RegionH (DK), AU (DK), CSIC (ES), ISCIII (ES), FNS (ES), INRAE (FR), ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), INERIS (FR), LNE (FR), BPI (GR), GCSL (GR), LNS (LU), UU (NL), NIPH (NO), UNN (NO), STAMI (NO), NMBU (NO), INSA (PT), JSI (SI), NLZOH (SI)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029

Costs

PM:

Total PM for the whole duration of the project: 425,78 PM

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 67,22 PM

Other direct costs (ODC) (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):

Total ODC for the whole duration of the project: None identified at present

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: None identified at present

A9.3.2 Generic QA/QC in chemical analysis

No project submitted at present.

A9.3.3 Generic QA/QC in toxicity testing and toxicokinetics studies

No project submitted at present.

T9.4 Training

No project submitted at present.